

3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values

Deliverable Report

D5.9

WP5 - Translation of results into policy

Deadline: September 2020

Upload by Coordinator: 15 October 2021

Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Received]
Coordinator	Marike Kolossa-Gehring	UBA	06/08/2021
Grant Signatory	Marike Kolossa-Gehring	UBA	06/08/2021

Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Approved]
Pillar Leader	Greet Schoeters	VITO	12/08/2021
Work Package Leader	Greet Schoeters	VITO	12/08/2021
Task leader	Petra Apel	UBA	06/08/2021

Responsible authors (short name of institution)	Petra Apel (UBA), Claire Beausoleil (ANSES), Farida Lamkarkach (ANSES), Matthieu Meslin (ANSES), Jens Uwe Voss (on behalf of UBA), Marcel Mengelers (RIVM)
Co-authors and Contributors	Rosa Lange (UBA), Madlen David (UBA), Christophe Rousselle (ANSES), Florence Zeman (ANSES), Jean-Philippe Antignac (ANSES), Sylvie Babajko (ANSES), Marie-Chantal Canivenc (ANSES), Nicolas Chevalier (ANSES), Claude Emond (ANSES), Nicole Hagen-Picard (ANSES), Brigitte LeMagueresse-Batistoni (ANSES), Sakina Mhaouty-Kodja (ANSES), Catherine Viguié (ANSES), Robert Garnier (ANSES), Claude Viau (ANSES), Annick van den Brand (RIVM), Eva Ougier (Anses), Rudolf Hoogenveen (RIVM)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 2

General introduction

Under HBM4EU Task 5.2, Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) are derived for HBM4EU priority substances. These HBM-GVs can be directly compared with HBM data and, as jointly agreed values under HBM4EU, are a valuable tool for the harmonised assessment of health risks. The HBM-GVs relate to both the general population and occupationally exposed adults.

Deliverable D5.9 comprises substance specific information as well as the presentation of derivation paths and numerical values of HBM-GVs for 6 substances (NMP, NEP, Bisphenol S, DMF, DMAC and DON). Additionally, substance dossiers for BPF and PFHxS are submitted. For the latter 2 substances the database was not sufficient to derive HBM-GVs.

All parts of the deliverable except Part VII for PFHxS went through a consultation process within HBM4EU. For PFHxS, not only is the database insufficient for HBM-GV derivation, but the substance is also found mainly as part of mixtures of different PFAS. For this reason, the submitted dossier should only be considered as a compilation of information that can be used for future work.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 3

Table of Contents

Part I and II

Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for the pyrrolidones NMP (1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone, CAS no. 872-50-4) and NEP (1-ethylpyrrolidin-2-one, CAS no. 2687-91-4): HBM-GV _{GenPop} for the general population.....	4
--	---

Part III

Derivation of Bisphenol S: HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs): BPS HBM-GV _{GenPop} for the general population & BPS HBM-GV _{Worker} for occupationally exposed adults.....	70
---	----

Part IV

Substance dossier on Bisphenol F	218
--	-----

Part V

Derivation of N-dimethylformamide (DMF) HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs): DMF HBM-GV _{Worker} for occupationally exposed adults	267
---	-----

Part VI

Derivation of N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAC) HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs): HBM-GV _{Worker} for occupationally exposed adults	339
--	-----

Part VII

Substance dossier on perfluorohexane sulfonic acid (PFHxS) - CAS no.: 355-46-4.....	388
---	-----

Part VIII

Derivation of an HBM Guidance Value (HBM-GV) for Deoxynivalenol (DON): HBM-GV _{GenPop} for the general population	418
--	-----

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 4

Part I and II

Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for the pyrrolidones NMP (1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone, CAS no. 872-50-4) and NEP (1-ethylpyrrolidin-2-one, CAS no. 2687-91-4): HBM-GV_{GenPop} for the general population

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 5

Table of contents (Part I and II)

Authors and acknowledgements	7
Glossary.....	8
1 Introduction	9
2 General information and physico-chemical properties of NMP and NEP	10
3 Potential uses of NMP and NEP	13
4 EU legislation and regulation	14
4.1 Classification	14
5 Exposure of the general population to NMP and NEP	15
6 Toxicological profile of NMP	16
6.1 Toxicokinetics of NMP	16
6.1.1 Absorption.....	16
6.1.2 Distribution and metabolism	16
6.1.3 Excretion.....	17
6.2 Toxicity of NMP	17
6.2.1 Human health effects of NMP	18
6.2.2 Animal studies and in vitro tests with NMP	18
7 Evaluation of NMP by various bodies and conclusion.....	34
8 Selected biomarkers and analytical method for NMP	37
8.1 Choice of biomarkers of exposure for NMP	37
8.2 Analytical method.....	37
9 Derivation of HBM-GVs for NMP with regard to the general population	38
9.2 Calculation of HBM-GVs for the general population for NMP	39
10 Toxicological profile of NEP.....	40
10.1 Toxicokinetics of NEP	40
10.1.1 Absorption.....	40
10.1.2 Distribution and metabolism	40
10.1.3 Excretion.....	40
10.2 Toxicity.....	40
10.2.1 Human health effects of NEP	40
10.2.2 Animal studies and in vitro tests with NEP	41
11 Evaluation of NEP by various bodies and conclusion	47
12 Selected biomarkers and analytical method for NEP	49
12.1 Choice of biomarkers of exposure for NEP.....	49

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 6

12.2 Analytical methods for NEP	49
13 Derivation of HBM-GVs for NEP with regard to the general population	50
14 Level of confidence attributed to the derived HBM-GVs	52
15 Discussion.....	53
16 Factsheets HBM-GVs for NMP and NEP for the general population.....	54
17 References.....	62

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 7

Authors and acknowledgements

Authors

Madlen David, UBA, Germany

Petra Apel, UBA, Germany

Rosa Lange, UBA, Germany

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the experts who provided us feedback on this work during the consultation period. Comments were taken as far as possible into consideration for the finalisation of this report.

The responses to the comments formulated by the Task 5.2 partners will be sent to the contributing experts.

Entity	Contributing expert
NH France	Christophe Rousselle (ANSES), Matthieu Meslin (ANSES)
NH Austria	Maria Uhl (EAA)
NH Spain	Piedad Martín Olmedo (EASP)
NH Portuguese	Susana Viegas (ENSP), Sónia Namorado (INSA), Teresa Borges (DGS)
NH Netherlands	Floris Groothuis (RIVM) Marjolijn Woutersen (RIVM)
NH Switzerland	Reginald Edward (Rex) FitzGerald

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 8

Glossary

AF	Assessment factor - Assessment factors are used to address the differences between the experimental data and the human situation, taking into account the uncertainties in the extrapolation procedure and in the available data set.
2-HESI	2-hydroxy-N-ethylsuccinimide
2-HMSI	2-hydroxy-N-methylsuccinimide
5-HNMP	5-hydroxy-N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone
5-HNEP	5-hydroxy-N-ethyl-2-pyrrolidone
ALP	Alkaline phosphatase
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging of substances
DNEL	Derived no-effect level
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
GD	Gestational day
HBM4EU	European Human Biomonitoring Initiative
HBM-GV	Human Biomonitoring Guidance Value
LC50	Lethal concentration 50 %
LD50	Lethal dosis 50 %
LOAEL	Lowest observed adverse effect level
NEP	N-Ethyl-2-pyrrolidone
NMP	N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone
NOAEC	No observed adverse effect concentration
NOAEL	No observed adverse effect level
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PBPK/PBTK	Physiologically based pharmacokinetic (toxicokinetic) modeling
POD	Point of departure
RAC	Risk Assessment Committee
REACH	Registration, Evaluation and Authorisation of Chemicals
RIVM	National Institute for Public Health and the Environment of Netherlands
SCCS	Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety
SCOEL	Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limits
SVHC	Substances of very high concern
TRV	Toxicity Reference Value – health-based, external exposure guidance value proposed by a European or relevant non-European institution (e.g. TDI, RfD, OEL)
TRV-like value	Value for external exposure guidance, calculated according to generally accepted rules, e.g. ECHA 2012 Chapter R.8
WHO	World Health Organisation

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 9

1 Introduction

Within the framework of Task 5.2 of HBM4EU, HBM guidance values (HBM-GVs) are derived for HBM4EU priority substances for the general population (HBM-GV_{GenPop}) and for workers (HBM-GV_{worker}) after their derivation approach underwent a consultation process by national experts nominated by HBM4EU partners.

The methodological approach has been summarised in a concept document previously released in the HBM4EU Task 5.2 workframe (HBM4EU concept paper) and recently published in a peer-reviewed journal (Apel et al., 2020). HBM-GVs are epidemiologically and/or toxicologically derived values referring to the internal exposure biomarker concentration and can thereby directly be compared with internal exposure levels measured in HBM studies in the general population or at the workplace. They serve as a useful screening tool for a health-related interpretation of population's exposure levels to identify potential health risks from the exposure to environmental chemicals. Thus, they can be used by policy makers to identify possible regulatory needs or to evaluate measures already implemented.

In the current report, the derivations of HBM-GVs for the general population (HBM-GV_{GenPop}) are presented and discussed for the pyrrolidones NMP (1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone, CAS no. 872-50-4) and NEP (1-ethylpyrrolidin-2-one, CAS no. 2687-91-4). NMP is an aprotic solvent for which comprehensive toxicological data are available. Several reports and review articles describe relevant exposure routes and risk to human health from NMP exposure (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG), 1994 and seq.; Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety (SCCS), 2011; German Committee on Indoor Guide Values (Ad-hoc AG des Umweltbundesamtes), 2014; German HBM Commission, 2015a; RAC and SCOEL, 2016). NEP is used as substitute for NMP. Less toxicological data is available for NEP than for NMP, but due to a chemical structure similar to NMP, NEP is expected to have a comparable toxicological profile (German HBM Commission, 2015b). Specific uses of NMP are restricted under Annex XVII to Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 whereas NEP is still in the evaluation process of ECHA.

The state of epidemiological knowledge based on human exposure to NMP and NEP, on whether and how they might cause human health effects is not sufficient to derive HBM-GVs directly based on human data. Neither are there any toxicity reference values (TRVs) that are considered suitable for the derivation of HBM-GVs. Thus, the derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population relies on findings from animal studies, mainly rodents. Developmental toxic effects of NMP and NEP have been selected as critical effects.

The initial proposal for the derivation of HBM-GVs was based on the derivation of the HBM-values for NMP and NEP by the German HBM Commission (2015a, b), updated by current literature. But the comments received during the consultation led to a change in the selection of the key study for the NEP HBM-GV derivation and thus to a change in the endpoint and POD used. However, after necessary extrapolations, a similar TRV-like value for NEP resulted, so the final values for the HBM-GVs remained the same.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 10

2 General information and physico-chemical properties of NMP and NEP

Table I.1: General information on NMP

Name	1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP)
Synonyms	N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone, 1-methylpyrrolidin-2-one, N-Methylpyrrolidone
Trade names	Pyrol-M, POLYFLON PTFE SM-3900, N-methyl pyrrolidone
CAS Number	872-50-4
EC Number	212-828-1
IUPAC Name	1-methylpyrrolidin-2-one
Molecular weight	99.13 g/mol
Molecular formula	C ₅ H ₉ NO
Structural formula	<p>Figure I.1: Structural formula of NMP Source: https://echa.europa.eu/de/substance-information/-/substanceinfo/100.011.662</p>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 11

Table I.2: General information on NEP

Name	1-ethyl-2-pyrrolidone (NEP)
Synonyms	N-ethyl-2-pyrrolidone, 1-ethylpyrrolidin-2-one
Trade names	2-Pyrrolidinone, 1-ethyl- (6CI, 7CI, 8CI, 9CI), N-Ethylpyrrolidinone
CAS Number	2687-91-4
EC Number	220-250-6
IUPAC Name	1-ethylpyrrolidin-2-one
Molecular weight	113.16 g/mol
Molecular formula	C6H11NO
Structural formula	<p>Figure I.2: Structural formula of NEP Source: https://echa.europa.eu/de/substance-information/-/substanceinfo/100.018.409</p>

At 20°C, NMP is a colourless up to slightly yellowish liquid. The vapour pressure is estimated to be 0.32 hPa at 20° C and therefore NMP is not highly volatile. 20 ml/m³ (ppm) \cong 82 mg/m³; 1 mg/m³ \cong 0.243 ml/m³ (ppm) (Hartwig and MAK Commission, 2019). 1-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone has a measured log Kow of -0.46 (at 25°C), indicating a low adsorption potential. Table I.3 lists the key physico-chemical properties of NMP.

Table I.3: Physico-chemical properties of NMP (ECHA brief profile, access 22.10.2020)

State at room temperature	Fluid, colourless (slightly yellowish)
Melting point	-24.2°C (101.3 kPa)
Boiling point	204.1°C (101.3 kPa)
Density	1.03 g/cm ³ at 25°C
Vapour pressure	32 Pa (20°C)
Partition coefficient log Kow	-0.46 (25°C)
Water solubility	1000 g/L (20°C)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 12

At 20° C, NEP is a colourless up to slightly yellowish liquid. The vapour pressure is estimated to be 18 Pa at 20° C and therefore NEP is not highly volatile. 5 ml/m³ (ppm) \triangleq 23,5 mg/m³; 1 mg/m³ \triangleq 0,213 ml/m³ (ppm). As also NEP has a low log Kow of -0.2 (at 20° C), a low adsorption and low bioaccumulation potential is expected. Table I.4 lists the key physico-chemical properties of NEP.

Table I.4: Physico-chemical properties of NEP (ECHA brief profile, access 22.10.2020)

State at room temperature	Fluid, colourless (slightly yellowish)
Melting point	-120 ° C (101.325 kPa)
Boiling point	212.5°C (101.325 kPa)
Relative density	0.997 g/cm ³ at 20° C
Vapour pressure	18-165 Pa (20°C-50° C)
Partition coefficient log Kow	-0.2 (20° C)
Water solubility	1000 g/L (23°C, pH 9-12)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 13

3 Potential uses of NMP and NEP

NMP is an aprotic and medium polar organic solvent which is completely miscible with water. For this reason, the applications in industry and professional settings are manifold. NMP is used as a solvent, e.g. for the extraction of aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons in the petrochemical industry, in the production of polymers (membranes), in coating products and waterborne paints. In addition, it is used in cleaning agents for the removal of coatings and paints, also in stripping and cleaning applications in the microelectronics fabrication industry. It is further used both in lithium ion batteries and in other hybrid batteries, in functional fluids like coolants, insulators, refrigerants, hydraulic fluids in industrial equipment, and in construction chemicals. Applications are also described for the pharmaceutical industry (ECHA, 2011c; RIVM, 2013a (Annex XV Restriction Report); Danish Ministry of the Environment, 2015).

Different consumer products may include NMP, such as (printer) inks, toners, coatings, cleaners (RIVM, 2013a (Annex XV Restriction Report)).

According to the ECHA brief profile, NMP is manufactured and/or imported in the European Economic Area in a high (aggregated) tonnage of 10 000 - 100 000 tonnes per year.

N-Ethyl-2-pyrrolidone (NEP), also a polar aprotic solvent, is used in many applications as substitute for the structural analogue N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP), e. g. for surface coatings, in cleaning agents and paint strippers (German HBM Commission, 2015b). In industry NEP is used as a solvent, catalyst and cationic surfactant. Release to the environment of this substance is likely to occur from use of machine wash liquids/detergents, automotive care products, paints and coatings or adhesives, fragrances and air fresheners (ECHA, 2011b). The industrial sectors in which NEP is used have been reported to be very similar to those of NMP (ECHA, 2011a). Consumers are expected to be exposed to NEP by using anti-freezing products, coating products, lubricants and greases, adhesives and sealants, air care products, non-metal-surface treatment products, inks and toners, leather treatment products, polishes, waxes and cleaning products (ECHA, 2011b).

According to ECHA, NEP is manufactured and/or imported in the European Economic Area in 100 - 1 000 tonnes per year.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 14

4 EU legislation and regulation

According to ECHA's SVHC supporting document (ECHA, 2011c), NMP is on **the candidate list of substances of very high concern for authorisation**. Regulation (EC) No 790/2009 shows that the substance meets the criteria for classification as toxic to reproduction, in accordance with Article 57(c) of REACH. Manufacture, placing on the market and use of NMP are **restricted under** restriction entry 71 of Annex XVII to Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006: NMP shall not be placed on the market, manufactured or used as a substance on its own or in mixtures in a concentration equal to or greater than 0.3 % after 9th of May 2020. If the substance is imported, produced, or used in concentrations of 0.3 % or more, manufacturers, importers and downstream users must have included in the relevant chemical safety reports and safety data sheets the mandatory Derived No-Effect Levels (DNELs) and manufacturers and downstream users must put appropriate risk management measures and operational conditions in place to comply with the mandatory DNELs for worker's exposure. The DNELs were derived by the authorities as part of the REACH restriction process and are 14.4 mg/m³ if NMP is inhaled and 4.8 mg/kg/d if skin is exposed to NMP (COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) 2018/588, amending Annex XVII to Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council. The DNELs refer to a level of exposure below which no negative health effects are expected.

Using CMR 1A or 1B substances in cosmetics is prohibited under Article 15(2) of the Cosmetics Regulation 1223/2009. Therefore, NMP and NEP as reproductive toxicants are forbidden in cosmetic products, irrespective of the concentration limit (Annex II, Regulation 1223/2009/EC on Cosmetic Products, as amended by Regulation 2019/1966/EU, 28 November 2019).

NEP is not listed in Annex XVII ("Restrictions") to Regulation EU No. 1907/2006 (REACH). It is still in the first phase of the ECHA's dossier evaluation process that covers compliance checks and the examination of testing proposals for the substance.

4.1 Classification

According to the **harmonised classification and labelling** (CLH report, 2013) approved by the European Union, NMP may damage the unborn child, causes serious eye irritation, causes skin irritation and may cause respiratory irritation. Specific target organ toxicity for NMP is described: may cause respiratory irritation after single exposure.

NEP may damage the unborn child and is officially classified in the EU as toxic to reproduction. The classification provided by companies to ECHA in REACH registrations identifies that this substance may cause serious eye damage. There is no overall agreement among data submitters, but a minority indicates that they consider this substance as persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic (14.29 % of REACH registrations).

Table I.5: Harmonised CLP classification of NMP and NEP

NMP	NEP
Repr. 1B (H360D) Skin Irrit. 2 (H315) Eye Irrit. 2 (H319) STOT SE 3 (H335)	Repr. 1B (H360D)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 15

5 Exposure of the general population to NMP and NEP

Dermal and inhalation exposure of the general population might occur outdoors from the use of NMP as ingredient in paints (sprays) and in graffiti remover, indoors from use in paints, inks and carpeting (HBM-Commission, 2015a). The potential for exposure via the oral route is expected to be negligible (NICNAS, 2018). At 100 % air humidity NMP is present as aerosol (Ausschuss für Gefahrstoffe (AGS), 2011). Due to the structural chemical similarities of NEP, a similar tendency to aerosol formation is likely for NEP, and human exposure may also be mainly dermal and inhalation through products containing NEP.

Exposure data for the two pyrrolidones in the general population is scarce, however in an HBM study from the German Environmental Specimen Bank, time trends of NMP and NEP metabolites in urine samples have been investigated (Ulrich et al., 2018). Metabolites of NMP (5-HNMP and 2-HMSI) were quantified in almost every sample analysed (98.0 respectively 99.6% of the samples), whereas metabolites from NEP (5-HNEP and 2-HESI) were only quantifiable in 34.8 and 75.7 % of the samples, respectively. The LOQ for 2-HMSI and 2-HESI was 2 µg/L and for 5-HNMP and 5-HNEP it was 2.5 µg/L. Interestingly, metabolite concentrations were rather constant over time and the market introduction of NEP as NMP substitute did not alter concentration levels dramatically. The hazard index calculated for the combination of both substances in relation to the HBM-I values was less than 0.1. Thus, based on the investigated subpopulation of the German population, combined NMP and NEP exposures were within acceptable ranges in the investigated timeframe. The authors noted that the exposure sources for the general population in the 1990s and 2000s are unclear.

HBM data of children and adolescents (3-17 years old, more than 2100 urine samples) from the German Environmental Survey (GerES) V show similar frequencies of quantification for NMP and NEP metabolites. Geometric mean concentrations were 103.1 µg/l (88.21 µg/g_{creatinine}) for the sum of NMP metabolites and 11.86 µg/l (10.15 µg/g_{creatinine}) for the sum of NEP metabolites (Schmied-Tobies et al., 2021).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 16

6 Toxicological profile of NMP

6.1 Toxicokinetics of NMP

6.1.1 Absorption

Inhalation

A high absorption rate of NMP by inhalation has been described for experimental animals and humans (RIVM, 2013a (Annex XV Restriction Report)). Measurements of exhaled air showed for humans a pulmonary retention rate of 90 % (Anundi et al., 2000; Åkesson & Jönsson, 2000a; Carnerup et al., 2006; Bader et al., 2007). The evaluation of the toxicokinetic differences between rats and humans to inhalation exposure revealed that a deviation from the default assessment factor for toxicokinetics (remaining differences factor of 2.5 for inhalation route of exposure) is not supported by experimental rat and human data (RIVM, 2013a (Annex XV Restriction Report)).

Dermal absorption

Rapid dermal absorption of liquid NMP is documented from several experimental studies in vitro with animal and human excised skin and in vivo in the rat and in human volunteer studies, but also dermal absorption from the vapour phase is described to contribute significantly to the total uptake of NMP. Also, the proportion of uptake of NMP depends on the composition of mixtures (Ursin et al., 1995; Akrill et al., 2002; Åkesson et al., 2004; Bader et al., 2008). Ligocka et al., 2003 (as cited in OECD SIDS 2007) observed a mean 67.9 % absorption of NMP through the skin in 12 human volunteers exposed to 300 mg NMP via a skin patch (unknown duration). By using human skin (OECD Draft Guideline 428) the highest absorption was 80 %. RIVM (2013a, Annex XV Restriction Report) decided to use a conservative dermal absorption percentage of 100 % throughout the restriction dossier and pointed out that aside from the vehicle (matrix) also other factors like occlusion, and the duration of contact may affect the dermal absorption.

Oral absorption

Experimental animal studies showed that also via the oral route NMP is well absorbed (~100 %) (Becci et al., 1983; Carnerup et al., 2005, RIVM, 2013a (Annex XV Restriction Report)).

6.1.2 Distribution and metabolism

NMP absorption is followed by a rapid distribution in the body. Experimental studies on rats showed that regardless of the route of exposure, NMP enters all organs, but the highest concentrations of NMP can be found in liver, gall bladder, small intestine as well as in kidneys, stomach and testes (Wells & Digenis, 1988). In a study on rats by Sitarek & Kilanowicz (2006) the highest concentrations of NMP were measured 4 hours after intraperitoneal administration in muscle and fat tissue as well as in liver and testes. No sex differences in distribution rates were observed. Studies on reproduction in rats showed that maternally inhaled NMP passes the placental barrier and reaches concentrations in foetal blood as high as maternal blood levels (Bolt et al., 2016). RAC/SCOEL (2016) argue beyond this that the intense bad smell of NMP and its irritation effects are plausibly explaining stress observations on animals and reduced food uptake or reduced uptake of mother milk.

Transfer of solvents to human breast milk has been reported (Anderson and Wolff, 2000), but for NMP further studies are missing. Physico-chemical properties such as molecular weight, lipophilicity and protein binding efficiency are relevant to estimate the possibility for entering in

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 17

human breast milk. Due to the low log Pow of NMP and its relatively short half-life, the accumulation in fat is not very likely and the possibility of a transfer into human milk fat is reduced (Breitzka et al., 1997). But as NMP as well as its metabolites have a very small molecular weight and through their solvent properties, it cannot be excluded that they may pass the human membranes into human breast milk via aqueous pores according to their concentration gradient (Kustrin et al., 2002), but at the moment no studies exist to confirm this hypothesis.

NMP is rapidly metabolised in the liver by gradual oxidation of the pyrrolidone ring. In the first step 5-hydroxy-N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (5-HNMP) is produced and further oxidised via N-methylsuccinimide (NMSI) to 2-hydroxy-N-methylsuccinimide (2-HMSI). Independent of the exposure route, 5-HNMP is identified as the main metabolite of NMP both in rats and humans (Åkesson & Jönsson, 1997; RIVM, 2013a (Annex XV Restriction Report)). In both species, a further putative metabolite 2-pyrrolidone was detected in low concentrations in blood and urine, which is assumed to be the result of demethylation of NMP (Carnerup et al., 2006).

6.1.3 Excretion

Excretion occurs in experimental animals as well as in humans mainly via the kidneys, primarily in form of the abovementioned metabolites. A study in rats with intraperitoneal administration of ¹⁴C-NMP showed that about 80 % of the NMP dose was eliminated as metabolites in the urine over 24 hours and only a low proportion (5 %) of the NMP dose was eliminated via faeces (Sitarek & Kilanowicz, 2006). Regarding the ratios of metabolites in urine, NMP is metabolised in rats mainly (70 %) to 5-HNMP, and only by 30% to 2-HMSI; 1 % consists of NMSI and the parent compound (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG), 2008).

Results of human volunteer studies on the metabolism of NMP are also available. Three healthy male volunteers received one single dose of 100 mg NMP orally. The complete urine was collected over nine days; within these 9 days, 65 % of the administered dose was recovered, either as parent compound or as its metabolites. NMP and the three metabolites 5-HNMP, MSI and 2-HMSI were detected analytically in urine using GC/MS, their proportions were 1.2 % for NMP, 67 % for 5-HNMP, and 31 % for 2-HMSI. The observed half-lives were 4 hours for 5-HNMP, 8 hours for NMSI, and 17 hours for 2-HMSI in urine (Åkesson & Jönsson, 1997). Mean urinary excretion fractions were 0.44 for 5-HNMP and 0.2 for 2-HMSI. No glucuronide or sulfate conjugates of the metabolites were identified.

Inhalation exposure of 16 male volunteers (average age 26.5 +/-2.4 years) to concentrations of 40 mg/m³ NMP also led to a similar ratio of the urinary metabolites 5-HNMP, 2-HMSI and free NMP (68:31:1). Half-lives were at the exposure level of 40 mg/m³ NMP under resting conditions 3.9, 7.5 and 28 hours for NMP, 5-HNMP and 2-HMSI, respectively (Bader et al., 2007).

At 6-h topical exposure of male and female volunteers to a single dose of 300 mg NMP, peak plasma concentrations of NMP were found three hours after application. 22 - 24 % of the total dose was recovered in the urine (Åkesson & Jönsson, 2000b).

6.2 Toxicity of NMP

NMP is classified as a skin and eye irritant and has effects on body weight, liver, kidney, spleen, and thymus. However, developmental toxicity is considered as the most sensitive effect for human health risk assessment regarding NMP exposure (NICNAS, 2018). In the following sections, the toxicity for NMP is presented in brief.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 18

6.2.1 Human health effects of NMP

There are no epidemiological studies available investigating the health effects of NMP in humans.

A patch test on 50 test persons (concentrations of NMP unknown) showed no irritations of the skin after 24 hours of exposure to NMP (only available as a secondary citation under Lee et al., 1987). According to a further report, swellings and wrinkling of the skin were seen after 3 days of several skin contacts with NMP, but without any irritant effects (Jungbauer et al., 2001). In contrast to this, a contact over several days with liquid NMP showed dermal irritations among workers (Leira et al., 1992). In a patch test on 50 human volunteers (with unknown concentrations of NMP) slight up to moderate reversible skin irritation was observed after 15 days of dermal contact. But no contact sensitisation was reported (only available as a secondary citation under Lee et al., 1987).

Inhalation exposure up to 50 mg/m³ NMP of six male test persons (4 x 2 hours with 5 minutes break after every 2 hours) showed no subjective irritation on eyes, nose and the upper respiratory tract and also no changes in lung function (spirometric data) and in nasal volume (Åkesson & Paulsson, 1997).

In another acute study on 16 human volunteers no eye irritation was seen after exposure to 80 mg/m³ NMP (2 x 4 hours with 30 minutes break) or after a peak test with 25mg/m³ baseline and 160 mg/m³ peaks (4 x 15 min, time-weighted average: 72 mg/m³) (Kleinbeck et al., 2006). A further study with the same study protocol revealed an odour nuisance of the test persons but no irritations (van Thriel et al., 2007).

Evidence on reproductive effects in humans is based on only one case report (RIVM, 2013a (Annex XV Restriction Report)). In week 16 of her pregnancy, a woman had an accidental contamination of her clothes and skin from spilling of NMP. No information exists on the extent of exposure. After the accident, the woman complained of having headaches, nausea and general feeling of sickness. In week 25 delayed development of the foetus was noted. In week 31 a stillbirth occurred.

6.2.2 Animal studies and in vitro tests with NMP

The following toxicity data on NMP are from the registration dossier and the OECD-SIDS that are summarised within the Annex XV report by RIVM (2013a).

6.2.2.1 Acute toxicity

Acute toxicity is low regardless of the route of exposure. After **oral** administration in mice and rats a LD50 between 3605 and 7725 mg/kg bw was reported. After **dermal** application in rats, LD50 values were in a similar range between 5000 and 7000 mg/kg bw. In an acute **inhalation** toxicity study with an aerosol/vapour mixture (87 % considered respirable), the 4h LC50 was >5100 mg/m³.

6.2.2.2 Skin, eye irritation and irritation of the mucous membranes

Single application of 0.5 ml NMP solution to the intact skin and the shaved skin of rabbits led under occlusive conditions only to temporary redness. Minimal irritation was also described in a modified Draize test on rabbits with 20 % NMP containing oily solution performed under occlusive conditions for **24 hours**. Experimental tests at the eyes showed that in rabbits 0.1 ml liquid NMP led to strong but reversible irritations in form of red eyes, corneal clouding and iritis.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 19

In a 3-months **subchronic inhalation** study in rats (6h/day and 5 times/week) 1000 mg/m³ led to irritations of the respiratory tract, the NOAEC was 500 mg/m³.

6.2.2.3 Sensitisation

Only two studies regarding sensitisation of NMP are available, the focus is on the skin. In the two animal studies on guinea pigs, which were not conducted according to OECD guidelines, no skin sensitisation was observed.

6.2.2.4 Repeated-dose toxicity

Oral exposure

Results relating to repeated-dose toxicity are available from studies in rats, mice and dogs (see Table I.6).

A 28-days **subacute feeding** study with 5 Sprague-Dawley rats per sex and dose (feeding doses: 0; 2000, 6000, 18000 and 30000 ppm corresponding to male/female 0, 149/161, 429/493, 1234/1548, 2019/2269 mg/kg bw per day) (Malek et al., 1997). 18000 ppm in male rats (1234 mg/kg bw/d) and 30000 ppm in female rats (2268 mg/kg bw/d) led to compound-related effects such as reduced body weight and feed intake, and reduced serum albumin and glucose concentrations. Slight lymphopenia, reduced cell density in bone marrow and thymus atrophy were judged to be treatment-related. In this study a NOAEC of 6000 ppm NMP in food was derived, which corresponds to a NOAEL of 429 mg/kg bw/d and a LOAEL of 1234 mg/kg bw/d.

In a **subacute study** from BASF, 10 Sprague-Dawley rats per sex and dose received for 28 days doses of 0, 258, 517, 1033 and 2066 mg/kg bw/d NMP **by gavage** (BASF AG, 1987). Male rats showed reduced body weights at a dose of 517 mg/kg bw/d. At higher doses, changes in kidney and liver weights occurred, but without histopathological findings. In the highest dose damage of the testis with degeneration of the germinal epithelium was observed (NOAEL 258 mg/kg bw per day, LOAEL 517 mg/kg bw/d).

In B6C3F1 mice (5 male and female per dose) a **subacute exposure** over 28 days with **feed** at dose levels of 0, 500, 2500, 7500 or 10000 ppm NMP (= 0, 160, 820, 2500, 3379 mg/kg bw per day) had no effects on food consumption or body weight (NMP Producers Group, 1994). Changes were detected in renal tubular epithelia (cloudy swelling of the distal portions) at doses \geq 7500 ppm for males and 10000 ppm for females. Significantly reduced ALP levels were observed at 10000 ppm in female mice. One male mouse died at the highest dose due to renal toxicity. At doses \geq 2500 ppm, yellowish discolouration of the urine was observed and described as an indicator of systemic availability of NMP. Based on the renal effects in males, a NOAEC of 2500 ppm was derived (NOAEL 820 mg/kg bw/d, LOAEL 2500 mg/kg bw/d).

A **combined subchronic and neurotoxicity study** was performed on 20-26 Sprague-Dawley rats per dose (Malley et al., 1999). Male and female rats were fed for 3 months with dose levels in the **feed** of 0, 3000, 7500 or 18000 ppm NMP, which corresponds to doses for males/females of 0, 169/217, 433/565, 1057/1344 mg/kg bw/d. 10 animals of each sex of the control group and the highest dose group were surveyed over one month after treatment (recovery period). A change in urine colouration was observed at 3000 ppm and above in both males and females. This was considered to be evidence of systemic availability since it was not associated with any functional or pathological changes. Doses at and above 7500 ppm led to reduced body weight (gain) and food consumption, at 18000 ppm increased absolute and relative liver (females) and kidney (males/females) weights were observed without pathological or functional changes. At 7500 and 18000 ppm, effects in the foot-splay test in male rats were observed indicating

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 20

neurotoxic effects, but these were no longer observable after the recovery period. Furthermore, at 18000 ppm sedative effects were observed in male rats (NOAEC 3000 ppm NMP corresponding to a NOAEL of 169/217 mg/kg bw/d, and a LOAEL of 433/565 mg/kg bw/d).

In a 3 months **subchronic feeding** study in B6C3F1 mice (10 per sex and dose), dose levels of 0, 1000, 2500 or 7500 ppm NMP were given in food, which corresponds to about 0, 277, 619, 1931 mg/kg bw/d, a satellite group which was only exposed for 4 weeks was included.

At 2500 ppm and above increased liver weights were observed in male mice, at 7500 ppm a centrilobular hypertrophy of the liver was observed in both sexes. In the satellite group at 2500 ppm, clinical chemistry showed changes in triglyceride and cholesterol concentrations as well as ALP activity. A NOAEC of 1000 ppm NMP corresponding to a NOAEL of 277 mg/kg bw/d and a LOAEL of 619 mg/kg bw/d were derived (Malley et al., 1999).

In a 90 days **subchronic study**, Beagle dogs (6 dogs per sex and dose group) received 0, 25, 79 or 250 mg/kg bw/d with the **diet**. As no substance-related or permanent effects were observed at any dose level a NOAEL of 250 mg/kg bw/d was derived (Becci et al., 1983).

Table I.6: Repeated-dose effects after oral exposure to NMP

Species, strain, sex and number/dose	Duration	Dose	NOAEL mg/kg bw/d	LOAEL mg/kg bw/d	Effects at LOAEL/remarks	Reference
Rat, Sprague-Dawley, 5 m/5 f	Subacute, 28 d	0; 2000, 6000, 18000 and 30000 ppm in the diet (male/female 0, 149/161, 429/493, 1234/1548, 2019/2269 mg/kg bw/d)	429	1234	bw ↓, changes in clinical chemistry, male the more susceptible sex	Malek et al., 1997
Rat, Sprague-Dawley: 10 m/10 f	Subacute, 28 d	0, 258, 517, 1033 and 2066 by gavage	258	517	bw ↓, male the more susceptible sex	BASF AG, 1987
Mouse, B6C3F1, 5 m/5 f	Subacute, 28 d	0, 500, 2500, 7500 or 10000 ppm NMP in diet (= 0, 160, 820, 2500, 3379 mg/kg bw/d)	820	2500	Renal toxicity	NMP Producers Group, 1994
Rat, Sprague-Dawley, 20-26 m/f	Subchronic, 90 d	0, 3000, 7500 or 18000 ppm in the diet (male/female 0, 169/217, 433/565, 1057/1344 mg/kg bw/d)	169/217 m/f	433/565 m/f	Bw (gain) ↓	Malley et al., 1999

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 21

Species, strain, sex and number/dose	Duration	Dose	NOAEL mg/kg bw/d	LOAEL mg/kg bw/d	Effects at LOAEL/remarks	Reference
Mouse, B6C3F1, 10 m/10 f	Subchronic, 90 d	0, 277, 619, 1931 mg/kg bw/d	277	619	Liver weight↑, changes in clinical chemistry	Malley et al., 1999
Beagle dog, 6 m/6 f	Subchronic, 90 d	0, 25, 79 or 250 mg/kg bw/d	250	-	NOAEL= highest tested dose	Becci et al., 1983

m: male, f: female, bw: body weight, d: days

Inhalation exposure

Several **inhalation** studies from BASF on NMP exposure are summarised in the RIVM reports (RIVM, 2013a, 2013b). Focus of research was the impact of the mode of exposure (head-nose versus whole-body), the influence of humidity and physicochemical status (aerosol vs. vapour). For this purpose, female Sprague-Dawley rats or Wistar rats were exposed over 6 hours per day, on 5 days per week over 2 or 4 weeks to 0 or 1000 mg/m³. With a “**nose-only**” exposure there were only local effects observed independent of aerosol fraction and humidity. A discolouration of the urine was observed resulting from resorption and metabolism of NMP.

Whole-body exposure (that means inhalation but also dermal and oral exposure) with coarse aerosol droplets accompanied by high relative humidity led to heavy systemic toxic effects culminating in high mortality rate. In contrast to this, **whole-body exposure** to fine droplets at low or high relative humidity led to less severe effects and no increased mortality rate. The differences were attributed to increased dermal and oral exposure to the coarse aerosol droplets.

In a *subacute* study over 28 days with 5 male and 5 female Wistar rats (6 hours per day on 5 days per week with 0, 10, 30, 100 mg/m³ of **aerosol, nose only**) no treatment-related adverse effects were noted. At the highest concentration a discolouration of the urine was observed, indicating the systemic availability of NMP (BASF AG, 1993).

In another *subacute inhalation* study, Sprague-Dawley rats (15 per sex and dose) were **whole body** exposed to NMP (0, 100, 500, 1000 mg/m³) for 6 hours per day and 5 days per week (Lee et al., 1987). Lethargy and respiratory problems were observed after 3-4 hours NMP exposure in all animals and at all concentrations. No treatment-related pathologic changes were observed in the lower doses. A slight testicular atrophy was reported without quantitative data. In the highest dose 13 animals died during the first nine days. The surviving rats after those nine days showed loss of body weight, focal pneumonia, hypoplasia of the bone marrow, atrophy of the lymphoid tissue in thymus, spleen and lymph nodes. Three of the surviving male rats of the highest dose group showed a severe testicular atrophy. From this study a NOAEC for systemic effects of 500 mg/m³ (LOAEC 1000 mg/m³) was derived. A derivation of a NOAEC for local effects was not possible because of slight irritation symptoms at all dose levels.

In a **subchronic study** on Wistar rats (10 per sex and dose) a **head-nose** only exposure with 0, 125, 250, 750 ppm (0, 500, 1000, 3000 mg/m³) on 6 hours per day for 5 days per week for about 13 weeks was carried out (BASF AG, 1994). A recovery period of 4 weeks without treatment

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 22

was additionally tested in a satellite group after exposure to 0 and 3000 mg/m³ NMP. All concentrations led to a discolouration of the urine. At ≥1000 mg/m³ nasal irritation was observed. Furthermore, male rats showed a reduced body weight gain at this concentration (at 1000 mg/m³ not significant, at 3000 mg/m³ significant). At 3000 mg/m³ hematological and clinical chemistry parameters were significantly different from controls, and effects on testes in form of cellular depletion were identified. In the satellite group, male rats showed reduced body weight gain and cellular depletion in the testes after the recovery period. A NOAEC for systemic and local effects of 500 mg/m³, and a LOAEC for systemic and local effects of 1000 mg/m³ were derived.

Table I.7: NOAEC and LOAEC after subacute and subchronic inhalation exposure to NMP

Species, strain, sex and number/dose	Type and duration	Dose	NOAEC mg/m ³	LOAEC mg/m ³	Effects at LOAEC	Reference
Rat, Wistar, 5 m/5 f	Subacute, 6h/d, 5d/week, head-nose exposure of aerolised NMP (10 % aqueous solution)	0, 10, 30, 100 mg/m ³	100	-	NOAEC= highest tested concentration	BASF AG, 1993
Rat, Sprague-Dawley (CD strain): 15 m/15 f	Subacute, 6h/d, 5d/week, whole body exposure	0, 100, 500, 1000 mg/m ³	500 (systemic)	1000 (systemic), 100 (local)	Severe general toxicity, testicular atrophy, mortality, local: respiratory symptoms	Lee et al., 1987
Rat, Wistar, 10m/10f	Subchronic, 90 d, head-nose only, 6 h/d 5 d/w	0, 125, 250, 750 ppm (0, 500, 1000, 3000 mg/m³)	500 (systemic and local)	1000 (systemic and local)	Reduced body weight gain, effects on the testes, changes in hematological and clinical chemistry parameters	BASF AG, 1994

m: male, f: female, bw: body weight, d: days, h: hours

Dermal exposure

In a **subacute study** on rabbits (not conducted according to OECD guidelines), 2 male rabbits per dose were treated once a day on 5 days per week with 0, 413, 826 and 1653 mg/kg bw/d NMP on the intact or slightly scratched **skin** over 4 weeks (IBRTL, 1963). All concentrations led to slight local irritations of the skin. Clinical, haematological and histopathological investigations showed no systemic toxic effects. Also, the body weight was not affected. It cannot be excluded that one death of a rabbit with scratched skin of the highest dose group was due to NMP exposure. A NOAEL for systemic effects of 826 mg/kg bw/d and LOAEL of 1653 mg/kg bw/d were set.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 23

Table I.8: NOAEL and LOAEL for subacute dermal exposure of rabbits

Species, strain, sex and number/dose	Duration	Dose	NOAEL [mg/kg bw/d]	LOAEL [mg/kg bw/d]	Effects at LOAEC	Reference
Rabbit, 2 males	Subacute, 28 d, 5d per week, once per day	0, 413, 826, 1653 mg/kg bw/d	826	1653	lethality	IBRTL, 1963

Conclusion for repeated-dose toxicity studies

In the repeated-dose toxicity studies mainly the decrease in body weight (gain) and food consumption as well as generic toxic effects on liver, kidney and thymus and histopathological changes were seen as the most critical effects. At higher doses these effects were accompanied by effects on the testes and spleen.

6.2.2.5 Genotoxicity and mutagenicity

In vivo

In vivo, orally to NMRI mice administered NMP showed no aneuploidies or clastogenic effects in the micronucleus test after 72 hours (up to acute toxic concentrations of 3800 mg/kg bw/d). No chromosome aberrations in bone marrow of male or female hamsters were observed after acute toxic doses of 3800 mg/kg bw/d after 24 hours. In another study with inhalation exposure of male and female hamsters (3300 mg/m³, 6 h/d, 5d/week, duration 6 weeks) a slight increase of chromosome aberrations in bone marrow was seen, the effects were not significant. In a dominant lethal assay with i.p. injection of 391 mg/kg bw/d once per week over 8 weeks, increase of post-implantation losses was observed (SCCS, 2011). This effect may be attributable to the developmental toxicity of NMP.

In vitro

Several studies on different bacterial strains of *Salmonella typhimurium* with presence or absence of an exogen metabolic activation system from rat or hamster liver showed no mutagenic effects up to cytotoxic concentrations. A minimal, not dose-dependent increase of revertant colonies of the bacterial strains TA102 and TA104 in absence of an exogenous metabolic activation system was shown in one study but couldn't be confirmed with other studies on these strains (SCCS, 2011).

In cells of the yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* NMP induced dose-dependent aneuploidies in the range of 7.6 - 23 g/L, concentrations ≥18 g/L had a strong cytotoxic effect (> 50 % decreased survival rate). In L5178Y lymphoma cells of mice no mutagenic effects occurred and in primary cell cultures of rat liver cells no increased DNA synthesis was observed (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG), 2012). In a HGPRT (hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyl transferase gene mutation) test on ovary cells of hamsters no mutagenic effects were observed.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 24

6.2.2.6 Carcinogenicity

Oral exposure

In a **chronic 2-year** study with **oral** administration of NMP in feed, Sprague-Dawley rats received 0, 1600, 5000 or 15000 ppm with their diet (corresponding to 0, 66.4, 207, 678 mg/kg bw/d in males and 0, 87.8, 283, 939 mg/kg bw/d in females). At the end of treatment, the body weight of the animals in the highest dose group was significantly decreased when compared to the control group. Decrease of the survival rate of male rats in the high dose group was observed related to chronic-progressive nephropathy (Malley et al., 2001). In the highest dose group of male rats, effects in mesenteric lymph nodes, effects in spleen (accumulation of macrophages), centrilobular fatty liver degeneration, degeneration of the cortex of the kidneys, degeneration and atrophy of the testes and oligospermia of the epididymis were described. In female rats, effects on spleen were reported. A treatment-induced increased incidence of tumors was not noted for both sexes. Therefore, a NOAEL of 207/283 mg/kg bw/d and a LOAEL of 678/939 mg/kg bw/d were derived.

The same working group published a **chronic study** on B6C3F1 mice (18-month, 50 males and females per dose) with 0, 600, 1200 or 7200 ppm NMP via **diet** (corresponding to 0, 89, 173, 1089 mg/kg bw/d in male and 0, 115, 221, 1399 mg/kg bw/d in female mice). At the end of the treatment the body weight of male mice of the highest dose group was decreased in contrast to the control group. The absolute and relative liver weight in male mice was increased ≥ 1200 ppm, in female mice ≥ 7200 ppm. Changes in other organ weights showed no dose-dependency or no histological correlate and were therefore described as not substance-induced. In the liver an increase of eosinophilic and basophilic foci as well as centrilobular hypertrophy were observed. Additionally, in male mice the number of adenomas and carcinomas and in female mice of adenomas in the highest dose group each were significantly increased (NOAEL/LOAEL in males 89/173 mg/kg bw/d, in females for non-carcinogenic effects 221/1399 mg/kg bw/d). The at all doses slightly increased incidence of lung adenomas and lung adenocarcinomas in male mice is not considered to be substance-related as the incidence in the control group was very low, the incidence in the other groups was of the same order of magnitude as the historical controls and the tumors, also occurring spontaneously in this strain of mice, show a considerable variability in their incidence (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG), 2006).

Additional studies in B6C3F1 mice given 7200 ppm NMP in their **diet** over **4 weeks** showed an increase in cell proliferation in liver. It was concluded that at the highest dose the increased incidence of liver tumors is due to not-genotoxic, stimulating effects on cell proliferation of NMP (Parod et al., 2001).

Inhalation exposure

Chronic toxicity and carcinogenicity was examined in a two-year **inhalation** study on Sprague-Dawley rats (CD rats) (Lee et al., 1987). For this purpose, 120 males and females per dose group were exposed (**whole-body**) to 0, 40 or 400 mg/m³ NMP over two years at 6 hours per day on 5 days per week. Vapour of NMP was the main exposure medium with only traces of aerosols. In the highest dose group, the body weight gain of male rats was significantly reduced (by 6%) and the urine volume increased. In both sexes a dark yellow discolouration of the urine was observed at the highest dose and also effects in the lungs in contrast to the control group (males: acute focal alveolitis in 10/85 rats vs. 2/84 rats of the control group, furthermore hyperplasia of the alveolar cells in 4/84 rats vs. 0/84 of the control group; females: hyperplasia of the alveolar cells in 9/84 vs. 4/84 of the control group). Female rats of all dose groups and male

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 25

rats of the highest dose group showed more frequently discoloured, humid perineal regions as the control group. In a male subgroup the haematocrit and the activity of the alkaline phosphatase in serum was increased. These effects could not be detected after 2 years. Male rats of the highest dose group that died or were euthanised before month 18 of the study due to poor general health status, showed more often than the control animals a chronic nephropathy with glomerulosclerosis. The differences between the two groups were neither after 18 months nor after 24 months significant. Likewise, the mortality as well as the incidence of neoplastic and other changes in organs were not increased in contrast to the control group. Therefore, a NOAEC of 40 mg/m³ and a LOAEC of 400 mg/m³ were derived.

Dermal exposure

No carcinogenicity studies on dermal exposure are available.

Table I.9: NOAEL/NOAEC and LOAEL/LOAEC for non-cancerogenic effects after chronic exposure to NMP by oral and inhalation routes

Species, strain, sex and number/dose	Duration/ exposure route	Dose	NOAEL/ NOAEC	LOAEL/ LOAEC	Effects at LOAEL/LOAEC, carcinogenicity	Reference
Rat, Sprague-Dawley, CrI:CD (SD)BR rats, 62 m/62 f	2 years, oral, via diet	0, 1600, 5000 or 15000 ppm in diet (0, 66.4, 207, 678 mg/kg bw/d in males and 0, 87.8, 283, 939 mg/kg bw/d in females)	207 mg/kg bw/d for males; 283 mg/kg bw/d for females	678 mg/kg bw/d for males; 939 mg/kg bw/d for females	bwg↓, nephropathy (male), not carcinogenic	Malley et al., 2001
Mice, B6C3F1, 50 m/50 f	18 months, oral, via diet	0, 600, 1200 or 7200 ppm via diet (0, 89, 173, 1089 mg/kg bw/d in males and 0, 115, 221, 1399 mg/kg bw/d in females)	89 mg/kg bw/d for males; 221 mg/kg bw/d for females	173 mg/kg bw/d for males; 1399 mg/kg bw/d for females	bwg↓, adenomas and carcinomas in liver (males), adenomas in liver (females)	Malley et al., 2001
Rat, Sprague-Dawley, CD rats, 120m/120 f	2 years, inhalation, 6h/d on 5d/week, whole-body	0, 40 or 400 mg/m³	40 mg/m³	400 mg/m³	bwg↓ (males), temporary changes in clinical chemistry parameters (males after 18 month)	Lee et al., 1987
m: male, f: female, bwg: body weight gain, d: days, h: hours						

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 26

Conclusions for genotoxicity and carcinogenicity

The available studies do not suggest a genotoxic potential of NMP. Two lifetime rodent carcinogenicity studies with inhalation and oral exposure give no indication of a carcinogenic potential of NMP. Complementary investigations in B6C3F1 mice showed an increase in liver adenomas and adenocarcinomas after oral administration of high doses of NMP (7200 ppm) over 4 weeks. Referring to additional test results, it was concluded that the increased incidence of liver tumors at the highest dose is due to non-genotoxic, cell proliferation stimulating effects of NMP. The peroxisome proliferation pathway related effects observed in B6C3F1 mice are not considered relevant for humans.

6.2.2.7 Effects of NMP on reproduction

Experimental studies on animals with effects on fertility and embryonic development are described in the following chapters.

Reproductive toxicity studies

Oral exposure

The reproductive toxicity in rats was assessed in a **2-generation study** on Sprague-Dawley rats (30 per sex and dose group). NMP was administered *via* the **diet** at doses of 0, 50, 160 or 500 mg/kg bw/d (Exxon, 1991). According to the authors of the study, the test substance affected the fertility, reproductive performance and survival rate of the offspring only at the highest dose tested, which also induced parental toxicity. In contrast to this assessment, the U.S. EPA (2015) stated that the reduced male and female fertility in the lower dose groups should be regarded as relevant effects, even though the changes were not statistically significant, and that a NOAEL was not achieved.

Because of these equivocal results, another **2-generation study** was performed. Wistar rats (25 per sex and dose) were exposed starting 10 weeks before mating, during pregnancy and lactation to 0, 50, 160 or 500 mg/kg bw/d *via* **diet** (NMP Producers Group, 1999a). Two successive matings were performed in each generation (F1a, F1b, and F2a and F2b). There was high mortality in F1a pups on postnatal days 1-4. The highest dose level was therefore reduced to 350 mg/kg bw/d for the subsequent course of the study. NMP showed no treatment-related effects on fertility of the F0 and F1 parental animals. But the reduced highest dose (350 mg/kg bw/d) led to systemic toxicity with reduced body weight gain, reduced food consumption and kidney effects in parental animals as well as developmental toxicity (increased mortality, reduced body weight gain) in the offspring (no detailed information provided in RIVM 2013a). From this study a NOAEL for parental systemic and developmental toxicity of 160 mg/kg bw/d and a LOAEL of 350 mg/kg bw/d were derived.

In a similar **2-generation study** in Sprague-Dawley rats, the mortality rate of the F1a offspring was also increased at the initially high dose of 500 mg/kg bw/d (NMP Producers Group, 1999b). NMP had no effects on fertility. The reduced high dose of 350 mg/kg bw/d showed in contrast to the study on Wistar rats no treatment-related systemic toxic effects, but led in the F2b offspring to reduced body weight and reduced number of the offspring (due to a reduced survival rate after the lactational phase). In this study the NOAEL for fertility and parental systemic toxicity was 350 mg/kg bw/d, for developmental toxicity the NOAEL was stated to be 160 mg/kg bw/d and the LOAEL 350 mg/kg bw/d.

Effects of NMP on **male fertility** were investigated in Wistar rats. Seven weeks old male rats (22-24 per dose) received NMP *via* **gavage** (0, 100, 300 or 1000 mg/kg bw/d) on **5 days per**

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 27

week for 10 weeks and for 1 further week during mating (Sitarek & Stetkiewicz, 2008).

Mating with untreated female rats was allowed and the survival rate and developmental effects on the offspring were monitored up to postnatal day 28. At the highest dose, NMP induced extensive damage to seminiferous epithelium in the seminal tubules of the testis and reduced fertility. Only two of the 44 female rats that were paired with treated males gave birth to six rats (in total). Exposure of the males to 300 mg/kg bw/d led to a reduction in postnatal survival until day 4. The dose of 100 mg/kg bw/d had no effects on fertility and spermatogenesis of the male rats and no developmental effects on the offspring. A NOAEL/LOAEL for fertility of 300/1000 mg/kg bw/d and for developmental toxicity of 100/300 mg/kg bw/d were derived.

Effects of NMP on **female fertility** were investigated by the same group in female Wistar rats (22-28 animals per dose group) dosed for **two weeks before mating** with untreated males, continuing **during mating and pregnancy up to the end of the lactation** phase with 0, 150, 450 or 1000 mg/kg bw/d NMP **via gavage** on 5 days per week (Sitarek et al., 2012). At 1000 mg/kg bw/d, two non-pregnant females died on day 30 and 32 of treatment, the number of surviving offspring was significantly reduced and the number of stillbirths per litter increased. At 450 mg/kg bw/d the fertility index was reduced. In all dose groups, postnatal survival of the offspring was reduced (viability and lactation indexes). The body weight of the dams was significantly reduced from gestational day 6 on. From this study no NOAEL could be derived, as the lowest dose already led to adverse effects. Therefore, a LOAEL of 150 mg/kg bw/d was derived. Selected study results are summarised in Table I.10.

Table I.10: Selected statistically significant effects on the fertility of parent and development of offspring female/male Wistar rats from the study of Sitarek et al., 2012

Parameter/effect	Oral dose (mg/kg bw/d)			
	0	150	450	1000
Body weight [g] of females, gestational day 20 ^a	321.3 ± 29.0 (22)	299.6 ± 11.1 (24)*	284.3 ± 40.4 (20)*	259.7 ± 17.9 (15)*
Number of mated females	24	26	28	22
Number of surviving/dead offspring per litter	11.5 ± 3.5 / 0.18 ± 0.85	10.4 ± 2.6 / 0	10.5 ± 3.4 / 0.13 ± 0.34	0.33 ± 0.82 / 0.80 ± 1.1
Fertility index	91.7	92.3	71.4*	68.2*
Viability index	94.0	86.4*	71.6*	0
Lactational index	96.1	78.2*	43.4*	0
Body weight [g] of offspring, postnatal day 4, female/male	9.79 ± 1.42 / 11.05 ± 1.13	7.35 ± 1.2* / 7.70 ± 1.29*	6.07 ± 0.83* / 6.34 ± 1.02*	–

^a mean value and standard deviation, in brackets: number of pregnant animals

* Statistically significant at p<0.05

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 28

Table I.11: Summary of NOAEL and LOAEL from reproductive toxicity studies with orally administered NMP

Species, strain, sex and number/dose	Duration	Dose (mg/kg bw/d)	NOAEL (mg/kg bw/d)	LOAEL (mg/kg bw/d)	Effects at LOAEL	Reference
Rat, Wistar, 25 m/25 f	2 generation study	0, 50, 160 or 500 (350)	160 (parental systemic, developmental), 350 (fertility)	350 (parental systemic and developmental)	bwg↓, kidney effects, offspring: mortality, bwg↓	NMP producer group, 1999a
Rat, Sprague-Dawley, 25 m/25 f	2 generation study	0, 50, 160 or 500 (350)	350 (parental systemic, fertility), 160 (developmental)	- (parental systemic, fertility), 350 (developmental)	Offspring: mortality, bwg↓	NMP producer group, 1999b
Rat, Wistar, 22-24 males	10 + 1 w, 5 d/week before and during mating	0, 100, 300 or 1000	300 (fertility), 100 (developmental)	1000 (fertility), 300 (developmental)	Effects in testis, fertility↓, offspring: postnatal mortality	Sitarek & Stetkiewicz, 2008
Rat, Wistar, 22-28 females	2 weeks before mating until end of lactation phase, 5d/w	0, 150, 450 or 1000	-	150 (lowest dose)	Females: bw↓ from gd 6, offspring: survival rate↓	Sitarek et al., 2012

m: male, f: female, bwg: body weight gain, gd: gestational day, d: days, h: hours

Inhalation exposure

In a 90 day inhalation study on male rats with whole-body exposure for 6 hours per day with 618 mg/m³ NMP vapour, changes of the testis weight and testis tissue or the morphology and number of the sperms were reported (Fries et al., 1992). In other experimental studies with higher concentrations of aerosol-vapour-mixtures (4 days with 7000 mg/m³, 2 weeks with 4000 mg/m³, or 13 weeks with 3000 mg/m³) reduced testicular weight, also histopathological changes and cell loss of the germinal epithelium of the testis were observed.

In a **2-generation study** 10 male and 20 female Sprague-Dawley rats per dose group were **whole body exposed** to 0, 41, 206, or 478 mg/m³ NMP vapour for at least 14 weeks on 6 hours per day and 5 days per week (Solomon et al., 1995). After 12 weeks exposure, mating between males and females of the same dose group was allowed. One part of the offspring (F1 generation) was exposed to 0 or 478 mg/m³ at the beginning of day 4 after birth. The NMP exposed group of one sex was mated with the F1 control group of the other sex. No effects on

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 29

body weight and weight of reproductive organs or fertility were observed. The offspring of the F1 generation showed reduced body weights by 4 - 11% up to day 21, but not after day 28. No dose-dependency could be verified. For the assessment of developmental toxicity pregnant rats were exposed to 0 or 478 mg/m³ and had a c-section at day 21. In the group of exposed female rats the body weight of the foetuses was reduced by 7% in comparison to the control group. No indications of embryo- and fetotoxicity were detected. Finally, a NOAEC of 206 mg/m³ and a LOAEC of 478 mg/m³ were derived.

Dermal exposure

There are no studies on reproduction for **dermal** exposure.

Conclusions for reproductive toxicity

In conclusion, NMP has effects on development and fertility, mainly effects on the survival rate and on testes.

Developmental toxicity studies

Oral exposure

Female Sprague-Dawley rats (21-25 pregnant rats per dose group) were **orally (by gavage)** exposed to 0, 125, 250, 500 or 750 mg/kg bw/d NMP on gestational days 6 - 20 (Saillenfait et al., 2002). Maternal body weight gain was reduced by 9 % at doses of 250 mg/kg bw/d. The body weight of foetuses decreased dose-dependently by 2.5 - 48 % with a significant effect of 10 % reduced body weight at a dose level of 250 mg/kg bw/d. At ≥500 mg/kg bw/d other effects on foetuses were observed, such as incomplete ossification of the skull and sternum, increased appearance of skeletal variations, and different types of malformations (external, visceral and skeletal malformations), further observed were increased post-implantation losses and resorption. In conclusion, a NOAEL for maternal and developmental effects of 125 mg/kg bw/d and a LOAEL of 250 mg/kg bw/d were derived.

Supplementary studies by the same working group showed no developmental effects for 5-HNMP and 2-HMSI when the three main metabolites of NMP (5 HNMP, NMSI and 2-HMSI) were administered **by gavage** (Saillenfait, et al., 2007). NMSI showed at doses of 750 mg/kg bw/d maternal toxicity, at 1000 mg/kg bw/d and 1250 mg/kg bw/d foetus weight was significantly reduced. Thus, effects were only seen at concentrations higher than those at which NMP already showed developmental toxicity.

In another developmental toxicity study on Sprague-Dawley rats (CrI:CD rats), doses of 0, 40, 125, or 400 mg/kg bw/d NMP were **orally, via gavage**, administered to pregnant rats (25 per dose group) at gestational days 6-15 (Exxon, 1992). The maternal body weight gain was reduced at 400 mg/kg bw/d between gestational days 6-9, 9-12 and 6-15, but not over the total gestational phase (GD 0-21) and after correction for gravid uterine weight. The body weight of the female foetuses was at 125 mg/kg bw/d significantly but only slightly reduced (3%). But the female foetal body weight was within the range of historical controls. At doses of 400 mg/kg bw/d these effects were more pronounced (10 %). At 400 mg/kg bw/d the number of stunted foetuses was increased. Finally, a NOAEL/LOAEL for maternal and developmental toxicity of 125/400 mg/kg bw/d was derived.

In an unpublished study on rabbits (20 pregnant New Zealand White/dose), liquid NMP was **orally** given at doses of 0, 55, 175, 540 mg/kg bw/d at gestational days 6-18 (IRCD, 1991). At 175 mg/kg bw/d maternal toxic effects were detected (transiently reduced body weight gain, but

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 30

the effect was also observed at higher concentrations and followed a dose response relationship). In the highest dose group post-implantational losses due to early and late resorptions and reduced litter size were observed. Additionally, malformations of the cardiovascular system and skeleton were noted. Detailed results of the study are missing. The NOAEL/LOAEL for maternal toxicity is 55/175 mg/kg bw/d, for developmental toxicity is 175/540 mg/kg bw/d.

Inhalation exposure

Pregnant Sprague-Dawley rats (25-26 per dose) were **whole-body exposed** to dose levels of 0, 124, 247 or 494 mg/m³ aerosol-free NMP on 6 hours per day from day 6 - 20 of pregnancy (Saillenfait et al. 2003). A transient decrease in body weight gain and food consumption was observed at 247 and 494 mg/m³ NMP. The highest dose showed maternal toxicity accompanied by reduced foetal body weight. Incidence and types of malformations were comparable among all groups. Therefore, a NOAEC for maternal toxicity of 124 mg/m³ and for developmental toxicity of 247 mg/m³ was derived.

In another study on developmental toxicity after **whole-body exposure** of pregnant Sprague-Dawley rats (25 per dose) with 0, 100 or 360 mg/m³ of vapour-aerosol-mixture NMP over 6 hours per day on days 6 - 15 of pregnancy, several exposed rats showed sporadic lethargy and irregular respiration during the first three days (Lee et al., 1987). Additional maternal toxic effects and impairment of the embryonic development did not occur.

According to the summary of an unpublished study, pregnant rabbits (Himalaya, 15 per dose) were exposed to 0, 200 mg/m³ (**only vapour**), 500 or 1000 mg/m³ (**vapour-aerosol-mixture**) on 6 hours per day at days 7 - 19 of pregnancy (BASF, 1993a). C-section was done on day 29. At 1000 mg/m³ increased skeletal variations (additional 13. rib), but no teratogenic effects were observed. No maternal toxicity was detected. However, in a range-finding study maternal toxicity was found at 1000 and 2000 mg/m³ with increased liver weights and impaired clinical chemistry parameters (BASF, 1991). The highest concentration of this pilot study led to an increase of resorptions and reduced number of surviving foetuses. An experimental design was chosen that makes an additional oral uptake of NMP via cleaning of the skin unlikely, but this could not be excluded. Thus, the study was considered as whole-body study. A NOAEL/LOAEL for maternal and developmental toxicity of 500/1000 mg/m³ was derived.

Dermal exposure

25 Sprague-Dawley rats of each dose group (0, 75, 237 or 750 mg/kg bw/d) received NMP on gestational days 6-15 (Becci et al., 1982). The test substance was applied as aqueous solution on the **skin** (25 cm²), rubbed in (no occlusion) and washed off after 8 hours. Oral uptake was prevented with a collar. Significant maternal toxicity (28 % reduced body weight gain, skin irritations) as well as developmental toxicity (reduced number of surviving foetuses, increased incidence of resorptions, reduced body weight of foetuses, delayed ossification, malformations of skeleton) were observed at the highest dose. A NOAEL/LOAEL for maternal and developmental toxic effects of 237/750 mg/kg bw/d was derived.

In another study on pregnant rabbits (white Himalaya, 15 per dose group) with semioclusive coverage of the **skin** and doses of NMP (40 % in water) of 0, 100, 300 or 1000 mg/kg bw/d on gestational days 7 - 19 over 6 hours per day, a yellow discolouration of maternal urine showed systemic availability (BASF, 1993b). In the offspring no malformations were induced, but a slight increase of variations like additional 13th rib was discussed as evidence for a reached minimal

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 31

toxic dose in the highest dose group. Therefore, a NOAEL for maternal toxicity of 1000 mg/kg bw/d and a NOAEL/LOAEL for developmental toxicity of 300/1000 mg/kg bw/d were derived.

Table I.12: Summary of NOAEL/NOAEC and LOAEL/NOAEC derived from developmental toxicity studies with NMP (including oral, inhalation and dermal exposure)

Species, strain, sex and number/dose	Exposure	Dose	NOAEL/NOAEC	LOAEL/LOAEC	Effects at LOAEL/LOAEC	Reference
Rat, Sprague-Dawley, 21-25 f	Oral (gavage) GD 6-20	0, 125, 250, 500 or 750 mg/kg bw/d	125 (maternal and developmental)	250 (maternal and developmental)	bwg↓ and bw↓ (maternal and offspring), external soft-tissue and skeletal malformations of the offspring	Saillenfait et al. 2002
Rat, Sprague-Dawley, 25 f	Oral (gavage) GD 6-15	0, 40, 125, or 400 mg/kg bw/d	125 (maternal and developmental)	400 (maternal and developmental)	bwg↓ and bw↓ (maternal and offspring)	Exxon, 1992
Rabbit, New Zealand, 20 f	Oral GD 6-18	0, 55, 175, 540 mg/kg bw/d	55 (maternal) 175 (developmental)	175 (maternal) 540 (developmental)	bwg↓, development: post-implantational losses, malformations	IRCD, 1991
Rat, Sprague-Dawley, 10 m/10 f	Inhalation 2gen.-study, 6 h/d, 5 d/week, at least over 14 weeks, whole-body	0, 41, 206 or 478 mg/m3	206 (developmental) 478 (fertility)	478 (developmental) - (fertility)	offspring: body weight↓ up to postnatal day 21	Solomon et al., 1995
Rat, Sprague-Dawley, 25-26 f	Inhalation GD 6-20, 6 h/d, whole-body	0, 124, 247 or 494 mg/m3	124 (maternal) 247 (developmental)	247 (maternal) 494 (developmental)	bwg↓, development: bw of fetuses↓	Saillenfait et al., 2003
Rat, Sprague-Dawley, 25 f	Inhalation GD 6-15, 6 h/d, whole-body	0, 100 or 360 mg/m3	- (maternal) 360 (developmental)	100 (maternal) - (developmental)	GD 6-8 infrequent lethargy, irregular respiration, no other effects	Lee et al. 1987

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 32

Species, strain, sex and number/dose	Exposure	Dose	NOAEL/NOAEC	LOAEL/LOAEC	Effects at LOAEL/LOAEC	Reference
Rabbit, Himalaya, 15 f	Inhalation GD 7-19, 6 h/d, whole-body	0, 200 mg/m ³ (only vapour), 500 or 1000 mg/m ³ (vapour-aerosol-mixture)	500 (maternal and developmental)	1000 (maternal and developmental)	Hepatotoxicity, development: variations of skeleton↑ and resorptions↑	BASF, 1991 and 1993a
Rat, Sprague-Dawley, 25 f	Dermal GD 6-15, 8 h/d	0, 75, 237 or 750 mg/kg bw/d	237 (maternal and developmental)	750 (maternal and developmental)	bwg↓, development: fetotoxicity, variations and malformations of the skeleton	Becci et al., 1982
Rabbit, Himalaya, 15 f	Dermal GD 7-19	0, 100, 300 or 1000 mg/kg bw/d	1000 (maternal) 300 (developmental)	- (maternal) 1000 (developmental)	Variations of the skeleton	BASF, 1993b

m: male, f: female, bwg: body weight gain, gd: gestational day, d: days, h: hours

6.2.2.8 Immunotoxicity

In a study on mice that were sensitised to ovalbumin, the effects of **inhaled** NMP exposure on allergic reactions to ovalbumin were investigated (Bönisch et al., 2012; Ulrike et al., 2012). To induce an *acute* allergic inflammation of the respiratory system, pregnant BALB/cByJ mice received 20 µg ovalbumin i.p. on aluminium/magnesium-hydroxide at days 1 and 14 of the study and 20 µg ovalbumin in 40 µl salt solution intranasal on days 14 and 17-19. At least 9 mice were **whole-body exposed** with ambient air or ambient air with added NMP (0.019 or 0.051 mg/m³) on 5 hours per day on days 0-19 or only on days 17-19. When applied during antigen sensitisation, 0.019 mg/m³ NMP increased the allergic immune response of treated mice in contrast to the control group showing an increased number of eosinophilic granulocytes in bronchial lavage (BAL), an elevated Th2-cytokine level, an increased antigen-specific IgE level and reduced formation of gamma interferon, whereas the lung resistance was slightly but not significantly increased when provoked with methacholine. In already sensitised mice, no increase in allergic immune response was noted with 0.019 mg/m³, but higher, still indoor-relevant NMP levels (0.051 mg/m³) during the antigen challenge enhanced the allergic immune response compared to unexposed OVA-immunised control animals, accompanied by – at least in part – significantly increased lung resistance compared to non-exposed OVA-immunised control mice. Similar effects were observed when animals were exposed to gaseous evaporations of carpets which contained besides a high proportion of NMP also 2,2,4-trimethyl-1,3-pentane-diol-diisobutyrate (TXIB), glycol ethers, 2-ethyl-1-hexanol, aliphates and phenol.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 33

The inflammatory effects were prevented with the additional administration of N-acetylcystein in drinking water. This study showed that inhalation exposure to NMP may cause respiratory irritations and chemosensory effects.

There are no animal studies or finding on humans available indicating a sensitising effect when only NMP is administered. Also, it is unclear, if persons with already existing sensitisation of the respiratory system towards other substances may suffer adverse effects of NMP exposure (Nielsen et al., 2007). For this no indications exist. Therefore, the mentioned findings cannot be considered for the assessment of NMP.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 34

7 Evaluation of NMP by various bodies and conclusion

In the REACH restriction (Annex XVII to Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals) the mandatory DNELs for workers are 14.4 mg/m³ for inhalation exposure and 4.8 mg/kg/d for dermal exposure, with no further differentiation according to subgroups like pregnant women. The document on “How to comply with REACH Restriction 71, guideline for users of NMP” (ECHA, 2019) suggests the following urinary metabolite concentrations corresponding to the inhalation DNEL:

5-HNMP: 25 mg/g creatinine (post-shift sample)

2-HMSI: 8 mg/g creatinine (next morning sample)

However, to give an overview of different evaluation approaches: RIVM proposed a maximum concentration at workplace (DNEL) of 5 mg/m³ for inhalation exposure and a maximum dose of 2.4 mg/kg bw/d for dermal exposure in order to ensure the safety of workers including pregnant women (RIVM, 2013a). The assessment regarding the inhalation route was based on the developmental toxicity study of Saillenfait et al. in rats (2003) that showed a reduction in foetal body weight as the most sensitive, adverse developmental effect for exposure via inhalation. This effect was consistently observed across studies and routes of administration. Consequently, the NOAEC for this endpoint of 247 mg/m³ served as the POD. Corrections for differences in exposure conditions resulted in 124 mg/m³ and further extrapolation (AF 25: 1 for allometric scaling, 2.5 for remaining differences and 10 for intraspecies differences) led to an inhalation developmental toxicity DNEL of 5.0 mg/m³ for pregnant workers. For the workers excluding pregnant workers an inhalation chronic systemic toxicity DNEL of 10 mg/m³ was derived based on reduced body weight (gain) in males at the LOAEC in a 90-day inhalation study (BASF, 1994).

For dermal exposure of workers including pregnant women a DNEL based on a NOAEL of 237 mg/kg bw/d from the study of Becci et al. (1982) on rats was established (effects: reduced number of surviving foetuses, reduced body weight of foetuses, malformations of skeleton). Extrapolation factors for inter- and intraspecies differences were applied based on ECHA guidance (10 x 10) resulting in a DNEL of 2.4 mg/kg bw/d. A dermal chronic systemic toxicity DNEL of 4.6 mg/kg bw/d was derived for the workers excluding pregnant workers based on a NOAEL of 826 mg/kg bw/d and increased mortality at the LOAEL in a dermal 28-day repeated dose toxicity study on rabbits (IBRTL, 1963). The assessment factors used were 6 for exposure duration, 2.4 for allometric scaling, 2.5 for remaining differences, and 5 for intraspecies differences.

In the restriction proposal for NMP, RIVM did not derive an oral DNEL for the general population, as they presumed a reduced usage of NMP in consumer products based on its classification as SVHC. According to Regulation (EU) 2018/588, NMP “shall not be placed on the market as a substance on its own or in mixtures in a concentration equal or greater than 0.3 % after 9 May 2020”.

The World Health Organisation has listed in the “Concise International Chemical Assessment Document” (CICAD) a tolerable inhaled concentration of 0.3 mg/m³. This value is based on a NOAEC of 500 mg/m³ in a subchronic inhalation study on rats with “head only” exposure to aerosol-vapour mixture. Extrapolation was performed to continuous (x (6/24) x (5/7)) and chronic

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 35

exposure (factor 3) and intraspecies as well as interspecies differences (factors of 10 both) were considered (WHO, 2001).

In Germany, the German Ad-hoc Group on Indoor Guidelines of the Indoor Air Hygiene Commission and the States' Supreme Health Authorities (today named German Committee on Indoor Guide Values) (2014) has also issued indoor air guidance values for NMP. Based on its assessment, the Guide value II (RW II – Health hazard value) was set at 1 mg/m³ and the Guide value I (RW I – precautionary value) at 0.1 mg/m³. This calculation was based on a chronic inhalation toxicity study in rats that showed significant impairment of weight gain (NOAEC = 40 mg/m³, LOAEC = 400 mg/m³) (Lee et al., 1987).

The Scientific Committee of Consumer Safety (SCCS) did not derive a TDI, but considered the NOAEL of 125 mg/kg bw/d from the study on developmental toxicity of Saillenfait et al. (2002) as well as of Exxon (1992) to estimate the margin of safety (MOS).

Table I.13: Overview of toxicity reference values (TRVs) derived for NMP

Panel/Author	Critical effects	Key study	Point of departure	Assessment factors	TRV
General population					
WHO (2001), CICAD	Retardation of body weight gain, effects in testis, changes in haematologic parameters	Subchronic inhalation toxicity study (BASF, 1994)	NOAEC (inhalation): 500 mg/m ³	Exposure conditions (x 6/24 x 5/7 :3) Intraspecies 10 and inter-species 10	TC (inhalation): 0.3 mg/m ³
SCCS (2011)	Reduced foetal body weight, foetal malformations and embryo-lethality	Developmental toxicity study on rats (Saillenfait et al., 2002)	NOAEL: 125 mg/kg bw/d	-	-
German Committee on Indoor Guide Values (2014)	bwg↓ (males), temporary changes in clinical chemistry parameters (males after 18 month)	Chronic inhalation toxicity study in rats (Lee et al., 1987)	NOAEC (inhalation): 40 mg/m ³ LOAEC (inhalation): 400 mg/m ³	Exposure conditions (x 6/24 x 5/7) AF interspe-cies: 2.5, AF intraspecies: 10, AF 2 to protect particularly sensitive groups of people	RW-I: ca. 0.1 mg/m ³ RW-II: ca. 1 mg/m ³

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 36

Panel/Author	Critical effects	Key study	Point of departure	Assessment factors	TRV
Workers					
RIVM (2013a)	<p>Reduced body weight of fetuses</p> <p>Reduced number of surviving fetuses, reduced body weight of fetuses, malformations of skeleton</p>	<p>Developmental toxicity study on rats, GD 6-20, 6 h/d, inhalation, whole body (Saillenfait et al., 2003)</p> <p>Developmental toxicity study on rats, GD 6-15, 8 h/d, dermal (Becci et al., 1982)</p>	<p>NOAEC (inhalation): 247 mg/m³ bw/d</p> <p>NOAEL (dermal): 237 mg/ kg bw/d</p>	<p>Exposure conditions, remaining differences (2.5), intra-species differences (10)</p> <p>AF for inter- and intraspecies differences (10 x 10)</p>	<p>DNEL (workers including pregnant women, inhalation): 5 mg/m³</p> <p>DNEL (workers including pregnant women, dermal): 2.4 mg/kg bw/d</p>

There is a common agreement that the developmental toxic effects are the relevant adverse effects of NMP. Also, the U.S. EPA (2015) selected the developmental toxicity endpoints of decreased fetal body weight and increased fetal resorptions/fetal mortality for quantifying dose-response and calculating the PODs, because they were consistent, relevant and sensitive across studies. EPA has high confidence in these endpoints, as they were identified in multiple studies, with different exposure routes. In the study of Poet et al. (2016), a physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) model was used together with benchmark dose modeling to derive short-term and chronic occupational exposure limit (OEL) values for NMP. Two developmental endpoints were evaluated for human health risk assessment: (a) increased incidence of skeletal malformations for acute exposure, (b) effects on foetal body weight for chronic exposure. Finally, a short-term occupational exposure limit value of 86 ppm (for inhalation and dermal vapor exposures combined) and a chronic occupational exposure limit (OEL) value of 24 ppm (for inhalation and dermal vapor exposures combined) were derived.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 37

8 Selected biomarkers and analytical method for NMP

8.1 Choice of biomarkers of exposure for NMP

It is recommended to analyse the two metabolites 5-HNMP and 2-HMSI in urine as substance-specific biomarkers of exposure for NMP (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG), 2008; Käfferlein et al., 2013; Meier et al., 2013).

8.2 Analytical method

A specific method is available for the identification and quantification of NMP metabolites in urine. This is according to Deliverable 9.5 which is published under www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/ a stable isotope dilution analysis using solid phase extraction followed by derivatisation (silylation) and GC–EI–MS/MS. The limit of quantification (LOQ) is for 5-HNMP 2.5 µg/L and for 2-HMSI 2 µg/L. The sensitivity of the method is sufficient for the purpose of assessing internal exposure burden in the general population (Schindler et al., 2012; Ulrich et al., 2018).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 38

9 Derivation of HBM-GVs for NMP with regard to the general population

A lack of data on human exposure to NMP exists. The database for NMP is not sufficient to derive an HBM-GV based on the relationship between human internal concentration of the biomarker(s) and related health effects. Furthermore, no toxicity reference value for the general population suitable for the derivation of HBM-GVs was found. Therefore, the derivation of HBM guidance values is based on findings from toxicity studies on animals and additionally on human toxicokinetic studies. Critical effects that are considered relevant for the derivation of HBM-GVs are in particular effects on body weight (gain), and the embryo/foetotoxic and teratogenic effects observed in studies on reproductive and developmental toxicity (RIVM, 2013a; RIVM, 2013b, RAC/SCOEL, 2016).

9.1 Choice of the key study, POD and assessment factors

According to the strategy paper to derive HBM-GVs (Apel et al., 2020) the selection of a key study shall include the exposure pathway that is also considered as the relevant exposure pathway for humans. NMP may enter the human body via the skin, via inhalation or orally and is rapidly distributed in the whole body. Due to the good skin permeability for NMP on the one hand and the low vapour pressure of NMP under standard conditions on the other hand, it can be assumed that the dermal route of exposure is more relevant for the general population than the inhalation route (SCCS, 2011). Whether inhalation exposure occurs as vapour, an aerosol or a mixture of both may also depend on temperature and relative humidity in air (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG), 1998). Due to the areas of application of NMP, the oral pathway is secondary. However, a conceivable derivation of HBM-GVs on the basis of animal studies with dermal administration is considered too uncertain because of the difficulties in extrapolation, especially with regard to the differences in dermal absorption in rodents and humans. Furthermore, even in the available studies with whole-body inhalation exposure, uncertainties exist regarding the amount of additional dermal and oral intake, so that results from studies with oral exposure were considered more appropriate to derive HBM-GVs.

The oral developmental toxicity study from Saillenfait et al. (2002) on rats was chosen as key study and in addition the study from Sitarek et al. (2012) as supporting study. The study of Saillenfait et al. (2002) resulted in a NOAEL of 125 mg/kg bw/d for maternal and developmental toxic effects, that was only slightly below the 150 mg/kg bw/d that showed already maternal and developmental toxic effects in the study of Sitarek et al. (2012). As no NOAEL could be determined by Sitarek et al., 2012 and the LOAEL is in the same order of magnitude of the identified NOAEL by Saillenfait et al. (2002) an assessment factor (AF) of 3 was applied to the NOAEL of 125 mg/kg bw/d from the Saillenfait et al. (2002) study to consider the uncertainties in the underlying database. In order to account for inter- and intraspecies differences further AFs of 10 each were applied resulting in a TRV-like value of 0.42 mg/kg bw/d.

To answer the question of whether the route to route extrapolation is at least suitable for the inhalation pathway, it was examined whether the NOAEC of the key inhalation study by Saillenfait et al. (2003), which was used by the RIVM (2013a) to derive the DNEL_{inhalation} for workers (including pregnant women), would lead to a body burden of a similar magnitude. According to the toxicokinetic data described above, nearly 100 % absorption can be assumed for both, the oral and inhalation route.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 39

Developmental toxicity study on rats, GD 6-20, 6 h/d, inhalation, whole body (Saillenfait et al., 2003).

- a) NOAEC referring to developmental toxicity = 247 mg/m³
- Extrapolation regarding exposure conditions: 247 mg/m³ x 6/24 = 61.75 mg/m³
 - Extrapolation to body dose per 24 h according to the default conversion factor for rats of 1.15 m³/kg bw for 24h exposure (ECHA, 2012): 61.75 mg/m³ x 1.15 = 71 mg/kg bw/d
- b) NOAEC referring to maternal toxicity = 124 mg/m³
- Extrapolation regarding exposure conditions: 124 mg/m³ x 6/24 = 31 mg/m³
 - Extrapolation to body dose per 24 h: 31 mg/m³ x 1.15 = 35.65 mg/kg bw/d

The rough calculation presented here supports the above shown selection of the oral NOAEL of 125 mg/kg bw/d from the Saillenfait et al. (2002) study as POD and the application of an AF of 3 to consider uncertainties in the underlying database (→ 42 mg/kg bw/d). It has to be noted that the chronic inhalation toxicity study was performed with whole body exposure of the rats, but the resulting additional dermal and oral absorption has not been considered for calculation.

9.2 Calculation of HBM-GVs for the general population for NMP

By using the mass balance equation, assuming steady-state conditions, an HBM-GV_{GenPop} of 15 mg/l for adults (rounded value) and 10 mg/l for children (rounded value) was calculated for the sum of the selected urinary exposure biomarkers 5-HNMP und 2-HMSI. Main urinary excretion fractions were 44 % for 5-HNMP (F_{ue}: 0.44) and 20 % for 2-HMSI (F_{ue}: 0.20) (Åkesson and Jönsson, 1997). As shown by the authors, a nearly complete excretion within 24 hours can be assumed as parent compound or its metabolites (80 % of the dose administered within 24h). In addition, as the TRV-like value is given in relation to body weight, the daily urine excreted is adjusted to body weight. As estimated by the German HBM Commission (2014) and included in the HBM4EU strategy to derive HBM-GVs (Apel et al., 2020), the daily urine volume adjusted to the body weight is assumed to be 0.02 l/kg bw/d for adults and 0.03 l/kg bw/d for children. However, data on daily urine volume adjusted to the body weight are currently reassessed and dependent on the outcome, might need to be adapted later.

Mass balance equation for the derivation of an HBM-GV_{GenPop} for the two exposure biomarkers of NMP based on a TRV-like value calculated from an animal POD:

$$\text{General formula: } \frac{\text{TRV-like value} \cdot \left[\frac{\text{MW}(\text{Metabolite1}) \cdot \text{Fue}(\text{Metabolite1}) + \text{MW}(\text{Metabolite2}) \cdot \text{Fue}(\text{Metabolite2})}{\text{MW}(\text{Substance})} \right]}{\text{Daily urinary flow rate adjusted to the BW}}$$

TRV = Toxicity Reference Value; MW = Molecular Weight; Fue = proportional urinary excretion factor; BW = Body Weight

$$\text{HBM - GV}(\text{GenPop, adults}) = \frac{0.42 \frac{\text{mg}}{\text{kg}}}{\text{d}} \cdot \frac{115.1 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}} \cdot 0.44 + 129.1 \text{ g/mol} \cdot 0.20}{99.1 \text{ g/mol}}}{0.02 \text{ l/kg}}$$

= 16.2 mg/l, **rounded 15 mg/l**

$$\text{HBM - GV}(\text{GenPop, children}) = \frac{0.42 \frac{\text{mg}}{\text{kg}}}{\text{d}} \cdot \frac{115.1 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}} \cdot 0.44 + 129.1 \text{ g/mol} \cdot 0.20}{99.1 \text{ g/mol}}}{0.03 \text{ l/kg}}$$

= 10.8 mg/l, **rounded 10 mg/l**

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 40

10 Toxicological profile of NEP

10.1 Toxicokinetics of NEP

10.1.1 Absorption

Rapid oral, inhalation and dermal absorption of NEP is expected due to structural similarity to NMP (German HBM Commission, 2015b).

10.1.2 Distribution and metabolism

Like NMP, NEP is metabolised in the liver with gradual oxidation of the pyrrolidone ring (Koch et al., 2014).

A toxicokinetic study on NEP was performed on pregnant rats, non-pregnant rats and fetuses (Bury et al., 2019). Maximum plasma concentrations for NEP, 5-HNEP, and 2-HESI were reached after 1, 4, and 8 hours respectively, thus comparable to the toxicokinetics of NMP. Plasma elimination of NEP, the transformation in metabolites and their elimination rate in pregnant rats were much slower compared to non-pregnant rats and efficient placental transfer of NEP was noted. It was pointed out that differences in toxicokinetics between pregnant and non-pregnant rats with respect to developmental toxicants, such as NEP, need to be addressed in risk assessment (Bury et al., 2019). No information was found on the transfer of NEP via breast milk. Transfer of solvents to human breast milk has been reported (Anderson and Wolff, 2000), but for NEP further studies are missing. Physico-chemical properties such as molecular weight, lipophilicity and protein binding efficiency are relevant to estimate the possibility for entering in human breast milk. Due to the low log Pow of NEP and its relatively short half-life, the accumulation in fat is not very likely and the possibility of a transfer into human milk fat is reduced (Breitzka et al., 1997). But as NEP as well as its metabolites have a very small molecular weight and through their solvent properties, it cannot be excluded that they may pass the human membranes into human breast milk via aqueous pores according to their concentration gradient (Kustrin et al., 2002), but at the moment no studies exist to confirm this hypothesis.

10.1.3 Excretion

A human oral study with NEP was conducted on three male volunteers (1 x 220–250 µg/kg bw). Elimination half-life for 5-HNEP in urine was 7 hours and for 2-HESI 22–27 hours. Elimination of 5-HNEP ended 72 hours after oral administration, but 2-HESI was still eliminated after 96 hours (2 % of the administered dose) (Koch et al., 2014). After 96 h the metabolites 5-HNEP and 2-HESI were detected in all urine samples at about 50.5 % (45.9–55.4 %) of the administered dose. 5-HNEP accounted for 28.9 % and 2-HESI for 21.6 %. Most of the excretion of 5-HNEP was achieved on the first day (26.4 %).

10.2 Toxicity

10.2.1 Human health effects of NEP

The current knowledge based on human exposure to NEP on whether and how it might cause human health effects is not sufficient to derive HBM-GVs directly based on human data. Thus, HBM-GVs are based on a point of departure (POD) identified in a key animal study.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 41

10.2.2 Animal studies and in vitro tests with NEP

The following study information on acute toxicity and skin irritation is based on the substance dataset of ECHA.

10.2.2.1 Acute toxicity

Acute toxicity is described as being low after oral, inhalation or dermal administration. A study with **oral** administration of NEP in rats derived a LD50 of 3200 mg/kg bw. Impaired respiration, apathy, balance disorders, atony and paralysis were observed. Post-mortem examinations showed dilatations of the heart, pale kidneys, blood congestion and oedemas in the lung and an atonic intestinal tract. **Inhalation** exposure of rats to NEP (**head only**, aerosol-vapour-mixture) over 4 hours (according to OECD guideline 403) led to accelerated respiration, bristling of the fur and other signs of physical discomfort (OECD, 2009a). In the week after exposure temporary delayed body weight gains were observed. Finally, an LC50 of > 5100 mg/m³ was noted. After **dermal** exposure to 2000 mg/kg bw/d on the rased skin of rats no systemic effects were observed (according to OECD guideline 402). An LD50 >2000 mg/kg bw/d was derived (OECD, 1987).

10.2.2.2 Skin and eye irritation

According to OECD guideline 405 a study in rabbits was performed (OECD, 2012). Undiluted NEP on the eye of the rabbits led to serious eye damages. In another study on rabbits undiluted NEP showed temporary redness of the eyes, but NEP was not assessed as being a skin-irritant.

10.2.2.3 Sensitisation

No sensitising effects of NEP could be verified with a local lymph node assay (LLNA) in mice according to OECD guideline 429 (OECD, 2010).

10.2.2.4 Repeated-dose toxicity

Inhalation exposure

In a **subacute inhalation** study (according to OECD guideline 412), rats were exposed to an aerosol/vapour mixture (OECD,2009b). At concentrations of 200 mg/m³ irritant effects on eyes and mucous membranes were noted immediately after exposure (Ma-Hock et al., 2011). At 200 mg/m³ and 400 mg/m³ histologic findings, namely focal degeneration of the olfactory epithelium, were raised in both sexes. Female rats also showed effects on the larynx at doses of 400 mg/m³, and temporary reduced body weight gain in male rats was noted. No substance-induced systemic changes of organs or clinical chemistry parameters were observed. A NOAEC for local effects of 80 mg/m³ was derived.

In a **subchronic inhalation** study with rats exposed according to OECD guideline 413 (OECD, 2009c) **head-nose only** to NEP (90% vapour), no substance-induced effects were recorded in the lowest and middle concentration of 30 and 60 mg/m³. The highest concentration of 200 mg/m³ led to local degenerations of the olfactory system. Substance-related systemic effects didn't occur (Ma-Hock et al., 2013). Thus, the NOAEC for local effects is 60 mg/m³ and for systemic effects 200 mg/m³.

Oral exposure

In a **subchronic feeding** study in rats (according to OECD guideline 408 (OECD, 1998)) with NEP administered at doses 0, 100, 300 or 1000 mg/kg bw/d, a dark yellowish up to orange discolouration of the urine was observed for all male exposed rats and for the middle and

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 42

highest dose group of female rats (Kaspers et al., 2006). This discolouration has been described as substance-related and a result of the excretion of NEP or its metabolites. This indicates the systemic availability of NEP but is not a sign of adverse toxic effects.

Already the lowest dose of 100 mg/kg bw/d caused in male rats a centrilobular hypertrophy of the hepatocytes and an increased liver weight. In male rats, also the kidney weight was increased and basophilic tubules and an accumulation of hyaline droplets were observed in the kidneys. No treatment-related effects were noted at the lowest dose in the females. At the middle dose of 300 mg/kg bw/d the body weight gain and final weight as well as food consumption were reduced in both sexes. In male rats also the grasping intensity was reduced. In blood, the content on total bilirubin was reduced in male rats and the total protein and albumin was reduced in female rats. In both sexes the liver weight was increased. At the highest dose of 1000 mg/kg bw/d a centrilobular hypertrophy of the female liver cells was noted. In blood and serum several changes of hematological and clinical chemical parameters were observed (both sexes: increase of blood platelet counts, of phosphate, of calcium, cholesterol and triglycerides, shortened prothrombin time, reduced creatinine; male rats: reduced chloride, glucose and total bilirubin; female rats: reduced total protein and albumin). In female rats reduced motoric activity was observed and was attributed to systemic toxicity. An increase of abnormal sperms was detected in male rats without changes in sperm counts or motility or histological changes of the testes.

Finally, a NOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/d for female rats and <100 mg/kg bw/d for male rats were derived by the authors of the study. The centrilobular hypertrophy of the liver cells was regarded as a sign for the induction of the cytochrome P450 which was considered as an adaptive process without signs of cytotoxicity. Changes in the kidneys were seen at doses of 100 mg/kg bw/d and were assigned to first signs of species and sex-dependent α 2-nephropathy which is not relevant for humans. The increase of the relative kidney weight of the female rats was estimated as a result of reduced final body weight due to systemic toxicity.

In a **4-week** repeated dose study with Sprague-Dawley rats, NEP was administered **orally** via gavage in doses of 0, 5, 50 and 250 mg/kg bw/d (Saillenfait et al., 2016). At 50 and 250 mg/kg bw/d a transient decrease in the body weight and in the body weight gain of the males was observed. No significant changes in hematological and clinical parameters were seen in both sexes after necropsy. At a dose of 250 mg/kg bw/d histological changes were observed in male rats, as an increase in hyaline droplets in the renal tubules of the kidneys and hepatocellular centrilobular hypertrophy in the liver. Also, a slight increase of cytochrome P450 concentration in liver microsomes was observed at this dose in male rats. The authors concluded that NEP has mild to no effects at doses up to 250 mg/kg bw/d and male rats seem to be the more susceptible sex.

Dermal exposure

There are no repeated-dose toxicity studies with dermal exposure.

10.2.2.5 Genotoxicity

The following studies on genotoxic effects were included in the registration dossiers submitted in the context of REACH.

In vitro

No mutagenic effects were seen in the Ames test in different strains of *Salmonella Typhimurium* and *Escherichia coli* with and without an exogenous metabolic activation system (tests according

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 43

to OECD guideline 471) (OECD, 1997a). Also, no mutagenic effects of NEP were noted in an HPRT-test on mammal cells (ovary cells of Chinese hamster) with and without the presence of an exogenous metabolising system according to OECD guideline 476 (OECD, 1997b).

In vivo

Orally administered NEP of concentrations up to acute toxic doses induced no increase in the number of polychromate erythrocytes with micronucleus according to OECD guideline 474 (OECD, 2014a). In an additional test according to OECD guideline 475 on mice, the test substance induced no increase of chromosome aberrations in bone marrow cells (OECD, 2014b).

10.2.2.6 Carcinogenicity

There are no data available on carcinogenicity of NEP.

10.2.2.7 Effects of NEP on reproduction

In a **subchronic** toxicity study in rats, an increase in abnormal sperms was detected in male rats without changes in sperm counts or motility or histological changes of the testes after **oral** administration of 1000 mg/kg bw/d NEP (Kaspers et al., 2006).

Several studies on **prenatal developmental toxicity**, carried out in accordance with OECD guideline 414 (OECD, 2001), were submitted with the registration dossier for NEP in the context of REACH and are described in the following:

Dermal exposure

A developmental toxicity study was performed in 25 pregnant Himalaya rabbits per dose group with **dermal** administration of NEP in doses of 0, 100, 300 and 1000 mg/kg bw/d (GD 6-28). 33.3 % aqueous NEP solution was given every day on the intact shawed dorsal skin. The area was covered under semiocclusive conditions. Remaining material was removed after 6 hours and the skin was dried. On day 29, animals were euthanised and examined. No effects on skin were seen. All animals treated with the highest dose showed an orange up to red discolouration of the urine. This effect was classified as the systemic bioavailability of the substance and not as an adverse toxic effect. At the highest dose a reduced food intake (-17 % over the entire treatment period) was observed in comparison to the control group.

At the beginning of the treatment (GD 6-9) significantly reduced body weight gain and significant body weight loss were noted. Towards the end of the treatment and considered over the whole treatment period the effects were not significant. The body weight gain corrected for uterus weight was not significantly influenced and was similar in all dose groups. Effects of treatment on parameters of reproduction, especially postimplantational losses and body weight of the fetuses were not observed. In one foetus of the highest dose group the occurrence of a cleft palate was noted, but the incidence was according to RAC (ECHA, 2011a) comparable to historical controls. No significant increase of visceral malformations was observed. Single malformations of the cardiovascular system were noted, especially the lack of the arteria subclavia in one foetus of the middle and highest dose group. This effect was not observed in historical controls.

Furthermore, in three fetuses (same litter) of the highest dose group ventricular septum defects and dextrocardia were observed that were not observed in historical controls. In the highest dose group, also a statistically significant increase of skeletal variations (additional 13. rib) but

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 44

no malformation was described. A LOAEL of 1000 mg/kg bw/d and a NOAEL of 300 mg/kg bw/d were derived.

In another related study, 25 pregnant Wistar rats were **dermally** exposed to NEP doses of 0, 200, 400 and 800 mg/kg bw/d on gestational days 6 - 19 (ECHA, 2011a). For this, the test substance was applied over 6 hours per day to the skin under semiocclusive conditions and the remaining substance was washed off from the skin after the 6 hours. Animals were euthanised and examined. No changes of the skin of the animals were described. In the middle and highest dose group a reddish and orange discolouration of the urine was detected that indicates the systemic bioavailability of NEP.

In the highest dose group, the food consumption of the animals was reduced over the whole treatment period. In the middle dose group, the food consumption was reduced on gestational days 6 - 8. Over the whole treatment period a reduced body weight gain (about 22 %) was observed in the highest dose group. That effect was also confirmed after the correction for uterus weight. The foetus body weight was slightly reduced (-11 %) in the highest dose group in comparison to the other dose groups and controls. Whether this effect is due to direct foetotoxic effects or maternal effects remains unclear. In three foetuses of one litter of the control group external malformations in form of an umbilical cord hernia were observed. Other external or visceral malformations or variations were not seen. Malformations of the skeleton were observed in one foetus of each dose group. The incidence of skeletal variations showed no dose-dependancy and was in the range of historical controls. Only redundant 14. rib occurred significantly more frequent than in historical controls. A LOAEL of 800 mg/kg bw/d and a NOAEL of 400 mg/kg bw/d were derived (unpublished study submitted under REACH).

Oral Exposure

In another study pregnant Himalaya rabbits received daily doses of 0, 20, 60 and 200 mg/kg bw/d NEP on gestational days 6 - 28 **via gavage**. Animals were euthanised on day 29 and examined. As in other studies an orange up to reddish discolouration of the urine is described after treatment. At the highest dosage, body weight gain was significantly reduced from GD 6 - 29 compared to the control. Correction for uterus weight showed no differences of body weight for gestational day 29. The relative but not absolute weight of liver and kidneys was significantly increased at the highest dose. The activity of alanine aminotransferase (ALT) was slightly increased in the middle dose group, and the activity of the gamma-glutamyl transferase (γ -GT) was slightly increased at the highest dose.

These effects were evaluated as minor. Additionally, the effects in the middle dose group with slight increase of levels of calcium and inorganic phosphate were estimated as substance-related effects with unclear pathogenesis. A histological examination of the organs was not carried out. Parameters for reproduction, in particular the number of postimplantational losses and the body weight of the foetuses were not significantly changed. External malformations like spina bifida were described in the middle dose group and a meningocele (mild form of *spina bifida aperta*) was noted in the highest dose group. Both malformations are very rare and were not recorded in historical controls. Litters with foetuses that showed skeletal malformations were significantly more frequent in the highest dose. Affected were mainly sternum, spine, ribs and cranial bones. The frequency with which certain skeletal malformations occurred in the individual doses did not indicate a clear dose dependence. Visceral malformation like a ventricular septal defect was detected in two foetuses of the highest dose group and one foetus of the control group, but the incidence was still in the range of historical controls.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 45

An additional study was performed to collect more details on toxic effects. Therefore, rabbits received doses of 0 and 200 mg/kg bw/d under the same conditions as in the first study. As confirmed also from other studies, the urine of NEP treated animals showed a discolouration between orange and red. The food intake of the exposed animals was reduced in the beginning and in interim periods of the treatment. Compared to the control group, a reduced body weight gain of animals treated with NEP was noted over the whole treatment period and also over the whole pregnancy time. At the end of the study, the effect of reduced body weight was not significant after correction for uterus weight. An increase of the absolute and relative liver weight was noted. Changes in clinical chemistry parameters showed changes in liver metabolism with an induction of microsomal enzymes and a slight increase of alanine aminotransferase points to a slight liver damage. The foetus weight of the NEP treated group was significantly reduced.

As in the preliminary study, at doses of 200 mg/kg bw/d the number of litters with animals showing malformations were significantly increased. A significant increase of external and visceral malformations as well as visceral variations were described. In addition, an increased number of litters with malformations of the skeleton were registered. Most of the observed malformations like cleft palate, lacking arteria subclavia or damage of the vertebral bodies were of a serious nature and occurred more frequently than in the historical controls. Finally, a NOAEL of 60 mg/kg bw/d and a LOAEL of 200 mg/kg bw/d were derived.

In a study on Sprague-Dawley rats, 19-24 pregnant rats per dose group received on days 6 - 20 of pregnancy doses of 0, 50, 250, 500 or 750 mg/kg bw/d NEP as liquid solution **via gavage** (Saillenfait et al., 2007). Animals were euthanised on day 21 and examined. No clinical changes were observed except a light-yellow discolouration of the urine. The maternal body weight gain was reduced in all dose groups on gestational days 6 - 9. From doses of 250 mg/kg bw/d the body weight gain was additionally reduced on gestational days 15 - 18 and from 500 mg/kg bw/d on gestational days 18 - 21. The dose group with 750 mg/kg bw/d of NEP showed reduced body weight gain also at gestational days 12 - 15.

However, the body weight on day 21 corrected by the weight of the gravid uterus was not significantly reduced. The food intake was significantly reduced at the beginning of the treatment (GD 6-9) in the two lowest dose groups, at 500 mg/kg bw/d at GD 6-12 and in the highest dose group also in the later stage of the treatment period. The number of implantations was similar in all dose groups. In the highest dose groups significantly increased postimplantational losses were detected due to late resorption. The foetus weight significantly and dose-dependently decreased from concentrations of 250 mg/kg bw/d (-7 % (250 mg/kg bw/d), -28 % (500 mg/kg bw/d), -42 % (750 mg/kg bw/d)). The incidence of foetuses/number of litters with all types of malformations was at the two highest doses significantly and dose-dependently increased.

A significant increase of external as well as skeletal malformations was seen from doses of 500 mg/kg bw/d and an increase of visceral malformations at 750 mg/kg bw/d. Variations of the skeleton occurred already more frequently from doses of 250 mg/kg bw/d. The malformations were mostly severe malformations such as oedema, anal atresia with missing tail, cardiovascular malformations and skeletal deformations such as fused cervical vertebral arches. All malformations that occurred are in principle rare malformations whose incidence exceeded that of historical controls. Consequently, a NOAEL of 50 mg/kg bw/d and a LOAEL of 250 mg/kg bw/d were derived.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 46

Conclusions regarding toxicity to reproduction

Finally, based on the before mentioned studies, the RAC evaluated NEP as having adverse effects on the foetus weight of rabbits after oral exposure and on rats after dermal and oral exposure (ECHA, 2011a). Also, NEP showed effects on postimplantational losses, in particular led to late resorptions in rats after oral exposure. Moreover, teratogenic effects were highlighted in rabbits after dermal and oral administration of NEP and in rats after oral administration of NEP. In both species, malformations of the skeleton after oral administration as well as rare cardiovascular malformations in rats after oral administration and in rabbits after dermal and oral administration were noted.

It can be concluded that the developmental toxic effects of NEP, especially the incidence of malformations in rats after oral administration are comparable to those of NMP. RAC (ECHA, 2011a) emphasised that the described developmental effects were specific and not a consequence of maternal toxicity.

10.2.2.8 Neurotoxicity

A **subchronic** study on rats with **oral** exposure of 300 mg/kg bw/d NEP showed a reduction in grip strength and a reduced motor activity. Whether this is based on specific neurotoxic effects of NEP or general systemic toxic effects of NEP is not proven. Further studies are not available.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 47

11 Evaluation of NEP by various bodies and conclusion

No TDI value or any guidance value for workplace exposure has been derived for NEP, but NEP is banned from use in cosmetic products for sale in the European Union and NEP is listed also in the Directive 92/85/EEC for improvements in the safety and health at work of pregnant workers and breastfeeding workers. For the registration under REACH, DNEL values have been derived for NEP and published in the registration dossiers (ECHA, 2013), see Table I.14. NEP is also classified as toxic for reproduction Cat 1B – H360D (CLP regulation) based on the developmental toxicity studies on NEP showing an increase of postimplantational losses, the reduction of body weight of fetuses and the induction of malformations.

Table I.14: ECHA DNEL values for NEP

DNEL	Workers	General population
<i>Acute exposure – systemic effects</i>		
Inhalation (mg/m ³)	No hazard identified	No hazard identified
<i>Acute exposure – local effects</i>		
Inhalation (mg/m ³)	20.1 (DNEL extrapolated from long term DNEL)	1.2 (DNEL extrapolated from long term DNEL)
<i>Chronic exposure – systemic effects</i>		
Dermal (mg/kg bw/d)	4 (NOAEL: 100)	0.5 (NOAEL: 100)
Inhalation (mg/m ³)	16.75 (NOAEC: 200)	1 (NOAEC: 200)
Oral (mg/kg bw/d)		0.5 (NOAEL: 100)
<i>Chronic exposure – local effects (respiratory tract)</i>		
Inhalation (mg/m ³)	10.05 (NOAEC: 60)	1.2 (NOAEC: 60)

NOAELs and NOAECs from animal studies

HBM values by the German HBM Commission were derived on the basis of oral exposure studies. Two developmental toxicity studies were regarded as relevant: one in rabbits with a LOAEL of 200 mg/kg bw/d and a NOAEL of 60 mg/kg bw/d (RAC, 2011), the second in rats with a LOAEL of 250 mg/kg bw/d and a NOAEL of 50 mg/kg bw/d (Saillenfait et al., 2007). Application of inter- and intraspecies assessment factors of 10 each, resulted in a TRV-like value of ca. 0.5 mg/kg bw/d. Also regarded as relevant and primarily considered was the **subchronic feeding** study in rats (Kaspers et al., 2006) with a NOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/d. The next higher dose (LOAEL) of 300 mg/kg bw/d led in combination with unspecific toxic effects (feed intake, reduced weight gain and final weight) to haematological and clinical-chemical changes and in the functional observational battery (FOB) to motor deficits (reduced grip strength). The authors presented for this subchronic feeding study results of a benchmark modelling, considering the reduction in grip strength in FOB and the reduction in final body weight or terminal weight gain in males and females. The BMDL₀₅ was within the range of the experimentally determined NOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/d and could support this value. However, experts participating in the HBM4EU consultation on the document at issue here, questioned

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 48

whether the endpoint grip strength in combination with the effect size was suitable for the determination of a TRV-like value. Therefore, this approach will not be pursued further.

A 4-weeks repeated-dose study with oral administration of NEP showed that NEP has mild to no effects at doses up to 250 mg/kg bw/d with males being the more susceptible sex (Saillenfait et al., 2016), thereby confirming the order of magnitude of the findings of Kaspers et al. (2006) and Saillenfait et al. (2007) considered for the derivation of the German HBM values. As effects were described the increase in hyaline droplets in the renal tubules of the kidneys and hepatocellular centrilobular hypertrophy in the liver of males. Also, the cytochrome P450 concentration in liver microsomes was slightly increased in males.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 49

12 Selected biomarkers and analytical method for NEP

12.1 Choice of biomarkers of exposure for NEP

As substance-specific biomarkers for NEP exposure the two metabolites 5-HNEP and 2-HESI are recommended to be analysed in urine (Koch et al., 2014).

12.2 Analytical methods for NEP

A specific method is available for the identification and quantification of metabolites of NEP in urine of the general population. NEP metabolites 5-hydroxy-N-ethyl-2-pyrrolidone (5-HNEP) and 2-hydroxy-N-ethylsuccinimide (2-HESI) can be determined by stable isotope dilution analysis using solid phase extraction followed by derivatisation (silylation) and GC–EI–MS/MS. The LOQ for 5-HNEP is 2.5 µg/L and for 2-HESI 2 µg/L (Schindler et al., 2012; Ulrich et al., 2018). This analytical method is also identified as best suitable in the Deliverable 9.5 under HBM4EU (see www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 50

13 Derivation of HBM-GVs for NEP with regard to the general population

13.1 Choice of the key study, POD and assessment factors

A lack of data on human exposure to NEP exists. The database for NEP is not sufficient to derive an HBM-GV based on the relationship between human internal concentration of the biomarker(s) and related health effects. Furthermore, apart from DNEL values derived under REACH, no toxicity reference values for the general population are available. Therefore, the derivation of HBM guidance values is based on findings from toxicity studies on animals, thereby also taking note of the DNELs mentioned above. Regarding the toxicokinetics, information from humans is available.

According to the strategy paper to derive HBM-GVs (Apel et al., 2020), the selection of the key study shall include the exposure pathway that is considered relevant for humans. For NEP, as well as for NMP, it can be assumed that dermal exposure is the most relevant exposure route followed by the inhalation exposure. However, a conceivable derivation of HBM-GVs on the basis of animal studies with dermal administration is considered too uncertain because of the difficulties in extrapolation, especially with regard to the differences in dermal absorption in rodents and humans. For this reason, the derivation of HBM-GVs dealt with here considers animal studies with oral exposure, but additionally findings from “head-nose only” inhalation studies documented in the registrant summaries in the registration dossier from ECHA.

The selected key study is the oral developmental toxicity study by Saillenfait et al. (2007) in rats with a LOAEL of 250 mg/kg bw/d and a NOAEL of 50 mg/kg bw/d, supported by a further oral developmental toxicity study in rabbits with a LOAEL of 200 mg/kg bw/d and a NOAEL of 60 mg/kg bw/d (RAC, 2011). Application of inter- and intraspecies assessment factors of 10 each, resulted in a TRV-like value of 0.5 mg/kg bw/d. This value is the same as the oral DNEL for systemic chronic effects although the derivation is different.

Regarding a comparison with the inhalation route of exposure, the database is not very broad and allows only a rough estimation of the body dose having no effects. A study with subacute exposure of rats has been conducted as well as one with subchronic exposure of rats (head-nose only) (Ma-Hock et al., 2011 and 2013). In the latter study, local effects on the mucous membranes of the nose were observed at the highest applied vapour concentration of 200 mg/m³ as before in the subacute study at the same concentration, but no systemic toxic effects were observed. Thus, the highest dose tested in this study, 200 mg/m³, is regarded as the NOAEC for systemic effects. Extrapolation of this value regarding study duration and exposure conditions ($200 \text{ mg/m}^3 : 2 \times 6/24 \times 5/7 = 17.86 \text{ mg/m}^3$) and extrapolation to body dose per 24 h ($17.86 \text{ mg/m}^3 \times 1.15 \text{ (ECHA, 2012)} = 20.5 \text{ mg/kg bw/d}$) lead to a lower body burden compared with the NOAEL of the oral developmental toxicity study, but it should be kept in mind that higher concentrations haven't been tested so far and we also have no information on a LOAEC for systemic effects via the inhalation path.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 51

13.2 Calculation of HBM-GVs for the general population for NEP

By using the mass balance equation, assuming steady-state conditions, an HBM-GV_{GenPop} of 15 mg/l for adults and 10 mg/l for children was calculated for the sum of the selected urinary exposure biomarkers 5-HNEP and 2-HESI. Main urinary excretion fractions were 28,9% for 5-HNEP (F_{ue}(96h): 0.289) and 21,6 % for 2-HESI (F_{ue}(96h): 0.216) (Koch et al., 2014). In addition, as the TRV-like value is given in relation to body weight, the daily urinary flow rate was adjusted to body weight as proposed by the German HBM Commission (2014) and taken over in the strategy to derive HBM-GV in the context of HBM4EU (Apel et al., 2020). The daily urinary flow rate adjusted to the body weight is assumed to be 0.03 l/kg bw/d for children and 0.02 l/kg bw/d for adults. However, data on daily urine volume adjusted to the body weight are currently reviewed and dependent on the outcome, values might need to be adapted later.

Mass balance equation for the derivation of an HBM-GV_{GenPop} for the two exposure biomarkers of NEP based on a TRV-like value calculated from an animal POD

$$\text{General formula: } \frac{\text{TRV-like value} \cdot \left[\frac{\text{MW}(\text{Metabolite1}) \cdot \text{Fue}(\text{Metabolite1}) + \text{MW}(\text{Metabolite2}) \cdot \text{Fue}(\text{Metabolite2})}{\text{MW}(\text{Substance})} \right]}{\text{Daily urinary flow rate adjusted to the BW}}$$

TRV = Toxicity Reference Value; MW = Molecular Weight; Fue = proportional urinary excretion factor; BW = Body Weight

$$\text{HBM - GV}(\text{GenPop, adults}) = \frac{0.5 \frac{\text{mg}}{\text{kg}}}{\text{d}} \cdot \left[\frac{129.2 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}} \cdot 0.289 + 143.2 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}} \cdot 0.216}{113.2 \text{ g/mol}} \right] \\ \frac{0.5 \frac{\text{mg}}{\text{kg}}}{\text{d}} \cdot \left[\frac{129.2 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}} \cdot 0.289 + 143.2 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}} \cdot 0.216}{113.2 \text{ g/mol}} \right]$$

= 15.08 mg/l, **rounded 15 mg/l**

$$\text{HBM - GV}(\text{GenPop, children}) = \frac{0.5 \frac{\text{mg}}{\text{kg}}}{\text{d}} \cdot \left[\frac{129.2 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}} \cdot 0.289 + 143.2 \text{ g/mol} \cdot 0.216}{113.2 \text{ g/mol}} \right] \\ \frac{0.5 \frac{\text{mg}}{\text{kg}}}{\text{d}} \cdot \left[\frac{129.2 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}} \cdot 0.289 + 143.2 \text{ g/mol} \cdot 0.216}{113.2 \text{ g/mol}} \right]$$

= 10.05 mg/l, **rounded 10 mg/l**

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 52

14 Level of confidence attributed to the derived HBM-GVs

As mentioned in the HBM4EU strategy paper to derive HBM-GVs (Apel et al., 2020), it is suggested to attribute a level of confidence (low, medium or high) to each calculated HBM-GV. The level of confidence (LoC) should reflect the uncertainties identified during the elaboration of the value and could constitute a good incentive to revise later on values with estimated 'lower' LoC.

Attributing low levels of confidence for the criteria described below may help to highlight the data gaps and to address them to the scientific research community. However, a low level of confidence does not necessarily mean a low level of protection, because the HBM-GV derivation is based on very conservative scenarios and default assumptions (Apel et al., 2020).

It should be noted that the LoC proposed in this document are not determined according to an established recognised methodology, but rather rely on expert judgment regarding the reliability of the data and the calculation method used to derive the HBM-GV values.

The overall LoC attributed to the HBM-GV_{GenPop} are set to '**medium**' for NMP and to "**medium/low**" for NEP. Please, refer to the n 2 note of the factsheet presented in section 16 for explanation on this LoC appreciation and to review the LoC for the single criteria that taken together define the overall LoC.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 53

15 Discussion

The German HBM Commission already derived HBM values for NMP and NEP and as no further studies with new findings were identified, those values were proposed as HBM-GVs for the use within HBM4EU. As outcome of the consultation procedure, a slight deviation was made referring to the selected key study for NEP, the relevant endpoint, and POD, but this did not change the numerical values.

Developmental toxic effects formed the basis for the derivation of the HBM-GVs. Therefore, pregnant women are likely to be the most sensitive population. However, any decisions protective for women of childbearing age and pregnant women are also expected to protect other populations including men and children (U.S. EPA, 2015). Internal exposure burden of NMP in the general population can be determined with the metabolites 5-HNMP and 2-HMSI in urine and the measured concentrations can be compared with the derived HBM-GVs: 10 mg/l for children and 15 mg/l for adults.

For comparison, the document on “How to comply with REACH Restriction 71, guideline for users of NMP” (ECHA, 2019) suggests the following urinary metabolite concentrations corresponding to the worker’s inhalation DNEL of 14.4 mg/m³: a) 5-HNMP: 25 mg/g creatinine (post-shift sample) and b) 2 HMSI: 8 mg/g creatinine (next morning sample). These values are higher compared to the values for the general population but refer to workplace conditions and not to a continuous exposure.

For evaluating exposure to NEP in the general population it is recommended to determine the sum of the concentrations of the NEP metabolites 5-HNEP and 2-HESI in urine and to compare the analytical results with the HBM-GVs for the general population derived here above: 10 mg/l for children and 15 mg/l for adults.

HBM data from the German Environmental Specimen Bank show that NMP metabolites 5-HNMP and 2-HMSI could be quantified in 98 % and 99.6 % of the urine samples of young adults and NEP metabolites 5-HNEP and 2-HESI could be quantified in 34.8 % and 75.7 % of the urine samples of young adults. These results clearly indicate that the investigated population is exposed to both NMP and NEP. Median NMP metabolite levels were 30.3 µg/l 5-HNMP as well as 38.8 µg/l 2-HMSI and median NEP metabolite levels were < LOQ for 5-HNEP as well as 6.1 µg/l 2-HESI. 95th percentiles were higher for NEP (5-HNEP: 212 µg/l, 2-HESI: 230 µg/l) than for NMP (5-HNMP: 98.1 µg/l, 2-HMSI: 100 µg/L) (Ulrich et al., 2018).

HBM data of children and adolescents (3 - 17 years old, more than 2100 urine samples) from the German Environmental Survey (GerES) V show similar frequencies of quantification for NMP and NEP metabolites. Geometric mean concentrations were 103.1 µg/l (5-HNMP: 56.01 µg/l, 2-HMSI: 45.08 µg/l) for the sum of NMP metabolites and 11.86 µg/l (5-HNEP: 3.06 µg/l, 2-HESI: 7.57 µg/l) for the sum of NEP metabolites (Schmied-Tobies et al., 2021).

In the case of combined exposure, it must be taken into account that both substances are toxic for development. How this is dealt with needs to be decided in the framework of the discussions on mixture risk assessment.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 54

16 Factsheets HBM-GVs for NMP and NEP for the general population

FACTSHEET for N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) for the general population			
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
HBM-GV_{GenPop} and Status			
HBM-GV _{GenPop}	1	Children: 10 mg/l Adults: 15 mg/l	Sum of 5-HNMP and 2-HMSI
Level of confidence	2	Medium	See note for explanation
HBM-GV _{GenPop} status	3	Agreed on within HBM4EU	See note for explanation
HBM-GV _{GenPop} year of issue	4	2020	
General Information			
CLP-INDEX-No.	5	Index No 606-021-00-7	
EC-No.	6	212-828-1	
CAS-No.	7	872-50-4	
Harmonised CLP classification	8	Repr. 1B (H360D) Skin Irrit. 2 (H315) Eye Irrit. 2 (H319) STOT SE 3 (H335)	
Molar mass	9	99.13 g/mol	
Biomarker(s)			
Identification	10	5-HNMP 2-HMSI	
Molar mass of biomarker(s)	11	5-HNMP: 115.1 g/mol 2-HMSI: 129.1 g/mol	
Toxicokinetic data			
Key studies for TK data, authors, year	12	Åkesson and Jönsson, 1997	
Type of study	13	Human male volunteer study (n=3)	
Route of exposure	14	Oral administration	
Half-life of biomarker(s)	15	Urinary metabolite T1/2 (h) 5-HNMP: 4 2-HMSI: 17	
Factor for metabolic conversion (F _{ue(9d)})	16	5-HNMP: 0.44 (44%) 2-HMSI: 0.20 (20%)	

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 55

FACTSHEET for N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) for the general population			
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
Derivation method and calculation			
Derivation method	17	Based on an animal POD	
Key study, Author(s), Year	18	Saillenfait et al., 2002	Supplemented by Sitarek et al. 2012
Species	18	Female Sprague Dawley rats	Female Wistar rats
Route, type of study	18	Oral, developmental toxicity	Reproductive toxicity
Exposure duration	18	GD 6-20	2 weeks before mating until end of lactation
Critical endpoint	18	External soft tissue and skeletal malformations in foetuses and reduced survival rates of offspring	
POD value	18	NOAEL of 125 mg/kg bw/d	
Assessment factors	19	: 3 : (10 x10)	The study of Saillenfait et al. (2002) resulted in a NOAEL of 125 mg/kg bw/d for maternal and developmental toxic effects, that was only slightly below the 150 mg/kg bw/d that showed already maternal and developmental toxic effects in the study of Sitarek et al. (2012). As no NOAEL could be determined by Sitarek et al., 2012, an AF of 3 was applied to the NOAEL of 125 mg/kg bw/d to consider the uncertainties in the underlying database. Intra- and interspecies differences
TRV-like value	20	0.42 mg/kg bw/d	
Calculated HBM-GV_{GenPop}	21	Children: 10 mg/l Adults: 15 mg/l	mass balance approach

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 56

Explanation of notes:

- 1) HBM-GV_{GenPop}: numerical value of the HBM-GV_{GenPop} value in mg/l
- 2) Level of confidence of the HBM-GV_{GenPop}: reflects the reliability of the proposed HBM-GV. The level of confidence takes into account the various uncertainties underlying the derivation of the HBM-GV (e.g. reliability of the key study used to derive the TRV/TRV-like value, uncertainties related to the extrapolations leading to the TRV/TRV-like value, to toxicokinetic data on the substance of interest, and to the calculation of the final HBM-GV). Attribution of a global level of confidence for the proposed NMP HBM-GV_{GenPop} is suggested, considering:
 - the nature and quality of the NMP toxicological data: information on toxicity to humans is very limited, the assessment of toxicity is based mainly on animal studies. Several reproductive and developmental toxicity studies on at least two different species via different routes of exposure have been conducted. The toxicokinetic data used for the HBM-GV calculation is based on one human volunteer study on only 3 males, thus data on children and females are lacking. → **medium confidence**
 - the critical endpoint and mode of action: the evidence of the NMP effects on reproduction is based on several animal studies via different routes of exposure. There is no data giving the indication for a rodent-specific mechanism, thus it can be assumed that these effects are also relevant for humans. However, no evidence for these effects is available from epidemiological studies. → **medium confidence**
 - the selected key study: developmental toxicity study in rats after oral administration of NMP (Saillenfait et al. 2002), according to ECHA reliable without restriction, comparable to guideline study (OECD Guideline 414 - prenatal developmental toxicity study). Study results are available that allow the assessment that the route to route extrapolation is appropriate. → **medium/high confidence**
 - the selected POD: NOAEL-LOAEL pair is given for Saillenfait et al. (2002). Additionally, the oral study of Sitarek et al. (2012) on reproductive toxicity was used. In the study by Sitarek et al. (2012) no NOAEL could be determined as effects already occurred at the lowest dose tested (reduced body weight of maternal animals, and reduced survival rates of offspring). There is only a small margin between the NOAEL of Saillenfait et al. (2002) and the LOAEL of Sitarek et al. (2012). A BMD approach regarding the Saillenfait data could improve the LoC. → **medium confidence**
 - the extrapolations leading to the TRV-like value: AFs for inter-species and intra-species variability as well as an AF considering the uncertainty in the database according to default values → **low confidence**

Altogether the global level of confidence for the NMP HBM-GVs in the general population is set to '**medium confidence**'.

- 3) HBM-GV_{GenPop} status: Agreed on within HBM4EU, the values were derived according to the feedback received in a consultation process.
- 4) HBM-GV_{GenPop} year of issue: year of setting the HBM-GV_{GenPop} in the HBM4EU workframe
- 5) CLP Number: according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures, implementing the globally harmonised system of chemical classification or GHS
http://guidance.echa.europa.eu/docs/guidance_document/clp_introduutory_en.pdf
- 6) EC Number: under European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS), ELINCS (European List of Notified Chemical Substances) in support of

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 57

Directive 92/32/EEC, the 7th amendment to Directive 67/548/EEC, NLP (No-Longer Polymers), see: ESIS: European chemical Substances Information System:
[https://web.archive.org/web/20131106181548if /http://esis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/](https://web.archive.org/web/20131106181548if/http://esis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/)

- 7) CAS Number: collection of disclosed chemical compound information by Chemical Abstracts Service. Almost all molecule databases can be searched by CAS Registry Number.
- 8) Harmonised CLP classification: CLP classification including CMR and other health relevant effects. In the case that classification is not harmonised, this should be stated. For selfclassifications by industry the ECHA-CLP inventory can be searched at:
<http://echa.europa.eu/web/guest/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database>
- 9) Molar mass: mass of NMP per amount of this substance expressed in g/mol
- 10) Biomarker(s) identification: the biomarkers identified as relevant for assessing the exposure to NMP are 5-HNMP and 2-HMSI. Consequently, these 2 metabolites are selected for the HBM-GV derivation.
- 11) Molar mass of the biomarker(s): mass of the selected biomarkers (expressed in g/mol)
- 12) Study for TK data, Authors, Year: Åkesson & Jönsson, 1997, three healthy male volunteers received one single dose of 100 mg NMP orally. The complete urine was collected over nine days; within these 9 days, 65% of the administered dose was recovered, either as parent compound or as it's metabolites, GC/MS was used.
- 13) Type of study: Human male volunteer study (n=3)
- 14) Route of exposure: oral
- 15) Half-life of biomarker: estimated elimination half-lives for the NMP biomarkers of exposure
- 16) Factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}): fractional urinary excretion of NMP
- 17) Derivation method: the existing database on NMP does not allow for the derivation of health-based guidance values from human data, based on internal concentration and health effects relationship. Therefore, a derivation method based on a TRV-like value established from an animal study is used.
- 18) POD: NOAEL of the Saillenfait et al. (2002) pivotal study; the critical effects considered assessment-relevant are the developmental effects.
- 19) Assessment factors used consider uncertainties in the database and inter- as well as intraspecies differences
- 20) TRV-like value: application of a total assessment factor of 300 leads to a TRV-like value of 0.42 mg/kg bw/d
- 21) HBM-GVs:

$$\text{HBM - GV(GenPop, adults)} = \frac{0.42 \frac{\text{mg}}{\text{kg}}}{d} \cdot \left[\frac{115.1 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}} \cdot 0.44 + 129.1 \text{ g/mol} \cdot 0.20}{99.1 \text{ g/mol}} \right] \\ 0.02 \text{ l/kg}$$

For children calculation is performed with 0.03 l/kg.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 58

FACTSHEET for N-ethyl-2-pyrrolidone (NEP) for the general population

Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
HBM-GV_{GenPop} and Status			
HBM-GV _{GenPop}	1	Children: 10 mg/l Adults: 15 mg/l	
Level of confidence	2	Medium/low	See note for explanation
HBM-GV _{GenPop} status	3	Agreed on within HBM4EU	See note for explanation
HBM-GV _{GenPop} year of issue	4	2020	
General Information			
CLP-INDEX-No.	5	None	
EC-No.	6	220-250-6	
CAS-No.	7	2687-91-4	
Harmonised CLP classification	8	Repr. 1B (H360D)	
Molar mass	9	113.16 g/mol	
Biomarker(s)			
Identification	10	5-HNEP 2-HESI	
Molar mass of biomarker(s)	11	5-HNEP: 129.2 g/mol 2-HESI: 143.2 g/mol	
Toxicokinetic data			
Key studies for TK data, authors, year	12	Koch et al. (2014)	
Type of study	13	Human male volunteer study (n=3)	
Route of exposure	14	oral	
Half-life of biomarker(s)	15	Urinary metabolite T1/2 (h) 5-HNEP: 7 2-HESI: 27	
Factor for metabolic conversion (F _{ue(96 h)})	16	5-HNEP: 0.289 (28.9%) 2-HESI: 0.216 (21.6%)	
Derivation method and calculation			
Derivation method	17	Based on an animal POD	
Key study, Author(s), Year	18	Saillenfait et al. (2007)	
Species	18	Rat, Sprague-Dawley	
Route/type of study	18	Oral developmental toxicity study	
Exposure duration	18	GD 6 - 20	

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 59

FACTSHEET for N-ethyl-2-pyrrolidone (NEP) for the general population			
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
Critical endpoints	18	Foetus weight, variations of the skeleton	
POD value	18	NOAEL: 50 mg/kg bw/d	
Assessment factors	19	: 100	Inter- and intraspecies assessment factors of 10 each
TRV-like value	20	0.5 mg/kg bw/d	
Calculated HBM-GV _{GenPop}	21	Children: 10 mg/l Adults: 15 mg/l	

Explanation of notes:

- 1) HBM-GV_{GenPop}: numerical value of the HBM-GV_{GenPop} value in mg/l
- 2) Level of confidence of the HBM-GV_{GenPop}: reflects the reliability of the proposed HBM-GV. The level of confidence takes into account the various uncertainties underlying the derivation of the HBM-GV (e.g. reliability of the key study used to derivate the TRV/TRV-like value, uncertainties related to the extrapolations leading to the TRV/TRV-like value, to toxicokinetic data on the substance of interest, and to the calculation of the final HBM-GV). Attribution of a global level of confidence for the proposed NMP HBM-GV_{GenPop} is suggested, considering:
 - the nature and quality of the NEP toxicological data: information on toxicity to humans is very limited, the assessment of toxicity is based mainly on animal studies. Developmental toxicity studies on at least two different species via different routes of exposure have been conducted, repeated-dose toxicity studies concern rats only, which were exposed by oral or inhalation route (no studies on dermal exposure exist). Chronic or carcinogenicity studies are lacking. The toxicokinetic data used for the HBM-GV calculation is based on one human volunteer study on only 3 males, but data on females and children are lacking. → **low confidence**
 - the critical endpoint and mode of action: the evidence of the developmental effects of NEP is based on some animal studies via two different routes of exposure (oral and dermal). There is no data giving the indication for a rodent-specific mechanism, thus it can be assumed that these effects are also relevant for humans. However, no evidence for these effects is available from epidemiological studies. → **medium confidence**
 - the selected key study: the oral developmental toxicity study by Saillenfait et al. (2007) in rats was assessed by ECHA as reliable with restrictions because the guideline is not reported and it is not reported whether the study was conducted according to GLP. The supporting oral developmental toxicity study in rabbits (RAC, 2011) was assed by ECHA as reliable without restriction. Available study results allow only a rough estimate as to whether the route to route extrapolation is appropriate → **medium/low confidence**

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 60

- the selected POD: Robust NOAEL - LOAEL (50 - 250 mg/kg bw/d) pair. → **medium confidence**
- Level of confidence with regard to extrapolations across and within species: default values for inter- and intra- species variability → **low confidence**

Altogether the global level of confidence for the NEP HBM-GVs in the general population is set to '**medium/low confidence**'.

- 3) HBM-GV_{GenPop} status: Agreed on within HBM4EU, the values were derived according to the feedback received in a consultation process.
- 4) HBM-GV_{GenPop} year of issue: year of setting the HBM-GV_{GenPop} in the HBM4EU workframe
- 5) CLP Number: according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures, implementing the globally harmonised system of chemical classification or GHS
http://guidance.echa.europa.eu/docs/guidance_document/clp_introduutory_en.pdf
- 6) EC Number: under European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS), ELINCS (European List of Notified Chemical Substances) in support of Directive 92/32/EEC, the 7th amendment to Directive 67/548/EEC, NLP (No-Longer Polymers), see: ESIS: European chemical Substances Information System:
https://web.archive.org/web/20131106181548if_/http://esis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/
- 7) CAS Number: collection of disclosed chemical compound information by Chemical Abstracts Service. Almost all molecule databases can be searched by CAS Registry Number.
- 8) Harmonised CLP classification: CLP classification including CMR and other health relevant effects. In the case that classification is not harmonised, this should be stated. For selfclassifications by industry the ECHA-CLP inventory can be searched at:
<http://echa.europa.eu/web/guest/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database>
- 9) Molar mass: mass of NEP per amount of this substance expressed in g/mol
- 10) Biomarker(s) identification: the biomarkers identified as relevant for assessing the exposure to NEP are 5-HNEP and 2-HESI. Consequently, these 2 metabolites are selected for the HBM-GV derivation.
- 11) Molar mass of the biomarker(s): mass of the selected biomarkers (expressed in g/mol)
- 12) Study for TK data, Authors, Year: Koch et al. (2014) examined the metabolism of NEP in humans. Three male volunteers at the age of 40-43 received one single oral dose at breakfast of 20.9 mg NEP. Urine was collected over 4 days and metabolites were measured with isotope-dilution GC-MS.
- 13) Type of study: human male volunteer study
- 14) Route of exposure: oral administration
- 15) Half-life of biomarker: estimated elimination half-lives for the NEP biomarkers of exposure
- 16) Factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}): fractional urinary excretion
- 17) Derivation method: the existing database on NEP does not allow for the derivation of health-based guidance values from human data, based on internal concentration and health effects relationship. Therefore, a derivation method based on a TRV-like value established from an animal study is used.
- 18) POD: NOAEL of 50 mg/kg bw/d of the oral developmental toxicity study by Saillenfait et al. (2007) in rats. The critical effects considered assessment-relevant are foetus weight and variations of the skeleton.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 61

- 19) Assessment factors used consider inter- and intra-species differences
- 20) TRV-like value: application of a total assessment factor of 100 leads to a TRV-like value of 0.5 mg/kg bw/d
- 21)

$$\text{HBM - GV(GenPop, adults)} = \frac{0.5 \frac{\text{mg}}{\text{kg}}}{\text{d}} \cdot \left[\frac{129.2 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}} \cdot 0.289 + 143.2 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}} \cdot 0.216}{113.2 \text{ g/mol}} \right] \\ 0.02 \text{ l/kg}$$

For children calculation is performed with 0.03 l/kg.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 62

17 References

- Åkesson, B., Carnerup, M.A., & Jönsson, B.A. (2004). Evaluation of exposure biomarkers from percutaneous absorption of N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone. *Scand J Work Environ Health*, 30(4), 306-312. doi:10.5271/sjweh.799
- Åkesson, B. & Jönsson, B.A. (2000a) Biological monitoring of N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone using 5-hydroxy-N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone in plasma and urine as the biomarker. *Scand J Work Environ Health*, 26(3): 213-218. doi:10.5271/sjweh.534
- Åkesson, B. & Jönsson, B.A. (2000b). Dermal absorption study on N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone in male and female volunteers. In: 26th International Congress on Occupational Health, Singapore (Abstract OT1390)
- Åkesson, B. & Jönsson, B.A. (1997). Major metabolic pathway for N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone in humans. *Drug Metabolism and Disposition*, 25(2), 267-269. Retrieved from <http://dmd.aspetjournals.org/content/dmd/25/2/267.full.pdf>
- Åkesson, B., & Paulsson, K. (1997). Experimental exposure of male volunteers to N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP): acute effects and pharmacokinetics of NMP in plasma and urine. *Occupational and environmental medicine*, 54(4), 236-240.
- Akrill, P., Cocker, J., & Dixon, S. (2002). Dermal exposure to aqueous solutions of N-methyl pyrrolidone. *Toxicol Lett*, 134(1-3), 265-269. doi:10.1016/s0378-4274(02)00175-3
- Anderson, H.A., Wolff, M.S., 2000. Environmental contaminants in human milk. *J Expo Anal Environ Epidemiol* 10, 755-760.
- Anundi, H., Langworth, S., Johanson, G., Lind, M.-L., Åkesson, B., Friis, L., Itkes, N., Soderman, E., Jönsson, B.A.G., Edling, C. (2000). Air and biological monitoring of solvent exposure during graffiti removal. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health*, 73(8), 561-569. doi:10.1007/s004200000157
- Apel, P., Rousselle, C., Lange, R., Sissoko, F., Kolossa-Gehring, M., Ougier, E. (2020). Human biomonitoring initiative (HBM4EU) - Strategy to derive Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for health risk assessment. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*, 230. doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2020.113622
- Ausschuss für Gefahrstoffe (AGS) (2011). *Begründung für die Festlegung der Schwangerschaftskategorie für N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidon (CAS 872-50-4)*. Retrieved from http://www.baua.de/de/Themen-von-A-Z/Gefahrstoffe/TRGS/pdf/900/900-n-methyl-2-pyrrolidon.pdf?_blob=publicationFile&v=1:
- Bader, M., Brodbeck, T., Weiß, T., & Koch, H. (2014). Human-Biomonitoring von N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidon (NMP) und N-Ethyl-2-pyrrolidon (NEP) im Urin mittels Gaschromatographie-Tandem-Massenspektrometrie. 54. *Wissenschaftliche Jahrestagung der Deutschen Gesellschaft für Arbeitsmedizin und Umweltmedizin eV*.
- Bader, M., Wrbitzky, R., Blaszkewicz, M., Schäper, M., & van Thriel, C. (2008). Human volunteer study on the inhalational and dermal absorption of N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) from the vapour phase. *Archives of Toxicology*, 82(1), 13-20. doi:10.1007/s00204-007-0230-5
- Bader, M., Wrbitzky, R., Blaszkewicz, M., & van Thriel, C. (2007). Human experimental exposure study on the uptake and urinary elimination of N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) during simulated workplace conditions. *Arch Toxicol*, 81(5), 335-346. doi:10.1007/s00204-006-0161-6
- BASF AG (1994). Study on the inhalation toxicity of N-methylpyrrolidone as a liquid aerosol in rats. 90-days test including an about 4-week post-exposure observation period. http://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/13641/nmp_annex_xv_report_en.pdf.
- BASF AG (1993). Department of Toxicology, unpublished results, project No. 40I0544/90067, 26 Oct 1993. In: ECHA (2013) Annex XV Restriction Report Proposal for a restriction substance name(s): N-METHYLPYRROLIDONE (NMP)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 63

BASF AG (1993a). Study of the prenatal toxicity of N-methylpyrrolidone in rabbits after inhalation of vapour-aerosol mixtures. Dept. of Toxicology. In: ECHA (2013) Annex XV Restriction Report Proposal for a restriction substance name(s): N-METHYLPYRROLIDONE (NMP)

BASF AG (1991). *Range finding study for the maternal inhalation toxicity of N-methylpyrrolidone in pregnant rabbits*. Dept. of Toxicology. In: ECHA (2013) Annex XV Restriction Report Proposal for a restriction substance name(s): N-METHYLPYRROLIDONE (NMP)

BASF AG (1987). *Unpublished results. Study XXV/436*. Dept. of Toxicology. In: ECHA (2013) Annex XV Restriction report proposal for a restriction substance name(s): n-Methyl-pyrrolidone (NMP). Retrieved from

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/13641/nmp_annex_xv_report_en.pdf

Becci, P.J., Gephart, L.A., Koschier, F.J., Johnson, W.D., & Burnette, L.W. (1983). Subchronic feeding study in beagle dogs of N-methylpyrrolidone. *J Appl Toxicol*, 3(2), 83-86 doi:10.1002/jat.2550030206

Becci, P.J., Knickerbocker, M.J., Reagan, E.L., Parent, R.A., & Burnette, L.W. (1982). Teratogenicity study of N-methylpyrrolidone after dermal application to Sprague-Dawley rats. *Toxicological sciences*, 2(2), 73-76

Bolt, H., Greim, H., Cocker, J., Hartwig, A., Hoffmann, S., Johanson, G., . . . Klein, C. (2016). *SCOEL/REC/119 N-Methyl-2-Pyrrolidone Recommendation from the Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limits*.

Bönisch, U., Böhme, A., Kohajda, T., Mögel, I., Schütze, N., von Bergen, M., . . . Polte, T. (2012). Volatile Organic Compounds Enhance Allergic Airway Inflammation in an Experimental Mouse Model. *PLOS ONE*, 7(7), e39817. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0039817

Breitzka, R.L., Sandritter, T.L., Hatzopoulos, F.K., 1997. Principles of drug transfer into breast milk and drug disposition in the nursing infant. *J Hum Lact* 13, 155-158.

Bury, D., Käfferlein, H.U., Brüning, T., Koch, H.M., Saillenfait, A.M., & Marquet, F. (2019). Toxicokinetics of N-ethyl-2-pyrrolidone and its metabolites in blood, urine and amniotic fluid of rats after oral administration. *Archives of Toxicology*, 93(4), 921-929. doi:10.1007/s00204-019-02404-x

Carnerup, M., Spanne, M., & Jönsson, B.A. (2006). Levels of N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) and its metabolites in plasma and urine from volunteers after experimental exposure to NMP in dry and humid air. *Toxicol Lett*, 162(2-3), 139-145. doi:10.1016/j.toxlet.2005.09.035

Carnerup, M., Saillenfait, A.M., & Jönsson, B.A. (2005). Concentrations of N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) and its metabolites in plasma and urine following oral administration of NMP to rats. *Food Chem Toxicol*, 43(9), 1441-1447. doi:10.1016/j.fct.2005.04.007

CLH report (2013). Proposal for Harmonised Classification and Labelling based on Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 (CLP Regulation), Annex VI, Part 2, substance name: 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone Retrieved from <https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/9a6bb3e4-6265-41d2-b963-00e37f95a20e>

COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) 2019/1966 of 27 November 2019 amending and correcting Annexes II, III and V to Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council on cosmetic products.

COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) 2018/588 of 18 April 2018 amending Annex XVII to Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) as regards 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone.

COMMISSION REGULATION (EC) No 790/2009 of 10 August 2009 amending, for the purposes of its adaptation to technical and scientific progress, Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 64

Danish Ministry of the Environment (2015). Survey of 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone, part of the LOUS review. Retrieved from

<https://mst.dk/service/publikationer/publikationsarkiv/2015/jul/survey-of-1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone-nmp/>

Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) (2012). N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidon (Dampf). Gesundheitsschädliche Arbeitsstoffe. Toxikologisch-arbeitsmedizinische Begründungen von MAK-Werten, 52. Lieferung. Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, S 1–6

Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) (2008). N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidon. In: Greim, H. (ed.): Grenzwerte in biologischem Material, 15. Lieferung. Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, S 1–13

Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) (2006). N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidon (Dampf). Gesundheitsschädliche Arbeitsstoffe. Toxikologisch-arbeitsmedizinische Begründungen von MAK-Werten, 41. Lieferung. Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, S 1–25

Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) (2002). N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidon (Dampf). Gesundheitsschädliche Arbeitsstoffe. Toxikologisch-arbeitsmedizinische Begründungen von MAK-Werten, 34. Lieferung. Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, S 1–2

Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) (1994). N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidon (Dampf). Gesundheitsschädliche Arbeitsstoffe. Toxikologisch-arbeitsmedizinische Begründungen von MAK-Werten, 20. Lieferung. Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, S 1–2

ECHA brief profile NMP (accessed 22.10.2020): <https://www.echa.europa.eu/web/guest/brief-profile/-/briefprofile/100.011.662>

ECHA brief profile NEP (accessed 22.10.2020): <https://echa.europa.eu/brief-profile/-/briefprofile/100.018.409>

ECHA (2019).

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/13641/entry_71_how_to_comply_en.pdf/c6e09198-c0b1-44e3-abae-6b3d0bc909a8

ECHA (2011a). Annex 1 Background document to the Opinion proposing harmonised classification and labelling at Community level of N-ethyl-2-pyrrolidone (NEP). ECHA/RAC/CLH-O-0000002192-83-01/A1

ECHA (2011b). PROPOSAL FOR HARMONISED CLASSIFICATION AND LABELLING OF A CHEMICAL SUBSTANCE: N-ethyl pyrrolidone (NEP). *CLH report*.

ECHA (2011c). SVHC support document for identification of 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone because of its CMR properties. Retrieved from <https://echa.europa.eu/de/candidate-list-table/-/dislist/details/0b0236e1807da281>

ECHA (2012). Guidance on information requirements and chemical safety assessment

Chapter R.8: Characterisation of dose [concentration]-response for human health

Reference: ECHA-2010-G-19-EN

Exxon (1992). Developmental toxicity study in rats with N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone. In: ECHA (2013) Annex XV restriction report proposal for a restriction substance name(s): N-Methylpyrrolidone (NMP). Retrieved from

http://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/13641/nmp_annex_xv_report_en.pdf

Exxon (1991). Multigeneration rat reproduction study with N-methylpyrrolidone. In: World Health Organization (WHO) (2001) Concise International Chemical Assessment Document 35, N-METHYL-2-PYRROLIDONE <http://www.who.int/ipcs/publications/cicad/en/cicad35.pdf>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 65

Exxon (1991). Multigeneration rat reproduction study with N-methylpyrrolidone. Biomedical Science, Inc.; Study for GAF Corp. (USA) (Project No. 236535, 26 November 1991).

Fries, A.S., Hass, U., Jakobsen, B.M., Jelnes, J.E., Lund, S.P., & Simonsen, L. (1992). Toxic effects of N-methylpyrrolidone on foetal development, the central nervous system, testes and semen in rats. In: Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG): <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/3527600418.mb87250dame0010/pdf>

German Committee on Indoor Guide Values (Ad-hoc AG des Umweltbundesamtes) (2014). Richtwerte für 1-Methyl-2-pyrrolidon in der Innenraumluft. *Bundesgesundheitsblatt Gesundheitsforschung Gesundheitsschutz*, 57, 1232-1241. doi: 10.1007/s00103-014-2041-1

German HBM Commission (2015a). Stoffmonographie für N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidon (NMP) und Human-Biomonitoring-Werte für die Metaboliten 5-Hydroxy-NMP und 2-Hydroxy-N-methylsuccinimid im Urin von Erwachsenen und Kindern. Stellungnahme der Kommission Human-Biomonitoring des Umweltbundesamtes. *Bundesgesundheitsblatt Gesundheitsforschung Gesundheitsschutz*, 58(10), 1175-1191. doi:10.1007/s00103-015-2217-3

German HBM Commission (2015b). Stoffmonographie für N-Ethyl-2-pyrrolidon (NEP) und Human-Biomonitoring (HBM)-Werte für die Metaboliten 5-Hydroxy-NEP (5-HNEP) und 2-Hydroxy-N-ethylsuccinimid (2-HESI) im Urin: Stellungnahme der Kommission Human-Biomonitoring des Umweltbundesamtes. *Bundesgesundheitsblatt Gesundheitsforschung Gesundheitsschutz*, 58(9), 1041-1052. doi:10.1007/s00103-015-2210-x

German HBM Commission. (2014). Grundsatzpapier zur Ableitung von HBM-Werten. *Bundesgesundheitsblatt - Gesundheitsforschung - Gesundheitsschutz*, 57(1), 138-147. doi:10.1007/s00103-013-1867-2

IBRTL (1963). Twenty day subacute dermal toxicity study in rabbits with GAF - Methyl-Pyrrolodone. ECHA (2013).

http://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/13641/nmp_annex_xv_report_en.pdf.

IRCD (1991). Developmental toxicity study in New Zealand White rabbits. Testing laboratory: IRCD. Retrieved from In: ECHA (2014) Committee for Risk Assessment RAC Annex 1 Background document to the Opinion proposing harmonised classification and labelling at Community level of N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP):

<http://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/f0fd41ff-e1c1-4cc4-bc8b-7a4912cffdb2>

Jungbauer, F.H.W., Coenraads, P.J., & Kardaun, S.H. (2001). Toxic hygroscopic contact reaction to N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone. *Contact Dermatitis* 45, 303-304.

Käfferlein, H.U., Meier, S., Koslitz, S., Weiß, T., Koch, H.M., Ronge, T., & Brüning, T. (2013). Exposition gegenüber entwicklungstoxischen N-Alkyl-2-pyrrolidonen. *IPA-Journal* 01/2013

Kaspers, U., Strauss, V., Kaufmann, W. & Fabian, E. (2006). N-Ethyl-2-pyrrolidone: Repeated Dose 90-day oral toxicity study in Wistar rats; Administration in the Diet. BASF SE, Ludwigshafen.

Kleinbeck, S., Juran, S., Schaper, M., Kiesswetter, E., Blaszkewicz, M., Bader, M. & van Thriel, C. (2006). Chemosensorische Empfindungen bei akuten Expositionen gegenüber N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidon (NMP) - Effekte von Expositionsspitzen und körperlichen Belastungen. *Arbeitsmed Sozialmed Umweltmed* 41(3):106–106

Koch, H.M., Bader, M., Weiss, T., Koslitz, S., Schütze, A., Käfferlein, H.U. & Brüning, T. (2014). Metabolism and elimination of N-ethyl-2-pyrrolidone (NEP) in human males after oral dosage. *Archives of Toxicology*, 88(4), 893-899. doi:10.1007/s00204-013-1150-1

Kustrin, S., Ling, L., Tham, S.Y., Alany, R., 2002. Molecular descriptors that influence the amount of drugs transfer into human breast milk. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis* 29, 103-119.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 66

Lee, K.P., Chromey, N.C., Culik, R., Barnes, J.R., & Schneider, P.W. (1987). Toxicity of N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP): Teratogenic, Subchronic, and Two-Year Inhalation Studies. doi:10.1093/toxsci/9.2.222

Leira, H.L., Tiltnes, A., Svenden, K., & Vetlesen, L. (1992). Irritant cutaneous reactions to N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP). *Contact Dermatitis* 27, 148-150

Ligocka, D., Lison, D., Haufroid, V. (2003) Contribution of CYP2E1 to N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone metabolism. *Arch Toxicol* 77, 261– 266

Ma-Hock, L., Strauss, V., Küttler, K., Becker, M. & van Ravenzwaay B. (2013). N-Ethyl-2-pyrrolidone: 90-day inhalation study in Wistar rats, vapour exposure. 5010033/041036. *BASF SE, Ludwigshafen*.

Ma-Hock, L., Strauss, V., Becker, M., Küttler, K. & van Ravenzwaay B. (2011). N-Ethyl-2-pyrrolidone: subacute 28-day inhalation lung toxicity in Wistar rats, liquid aerosol with vapour fraction. 4010033/041021. *BASF SE, Ludwigshafen*.

Hartwig, A. & MAK Commission (2019). N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidon (Dampf) [MAK Value Documentation in German language]. doi: 10.1002/3527600418.mb87250damd0066

Malek, D., Malley, L., Slone, T., Elliott, G., Kennedy, G., Mellert, W., . . . Murphy, S. (1997). Repeated dose toxicity study (28 days) in rats and mice with N-methylpyrrolidone (NMP). *Drug and Chemical Toxicology*, 20(1-2), 63-77

Malley, L., Kennedy, G., Elliott, G., Slone, T., Mellert, W., Deckardt, K., . . . Parod, R. (2001). Chronic toxicity and oncogenicity of N-methylpyrrolidone (NMP) in rats and mice by dietary administration. *Drug and Chemical Toxicology*, 24(4), 315-338

Malley, L., Kennedy, G., Elliott, G., Slone, T., Mellert, W., Deckardt, K., . . . McCarthy, T. (1999). 90-day subchronic toxicity study in rats and mice fed N-methylpyrrolidone (NMP) including neurotoxicity evaluation in rats. *Drug and Chemical Toxicology*, 22(3), 455-480

Meier, S., Schindler, B.K., Koslitz, S., Koch, H.M., Weiss, T., Käfferlein, H.U., & Brüning, T. (2013). Biomonitoring of exposure to N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone in workers of the automobile industry. *Ann Occup Hyg*, 57(6), 766-773. doi:10.1093/annhyg/mes111

NICNAS (2018). IMAP assessment: 2-Pyrrolidinone, 1-methyl-: Human health tier III assessment.

Nielsen, G.D., Larsen, S.T., Olsen, O., Løvik, M., Poulsen, L.K., Glue, C., & Wolhoff, P. (2007). Do indoor chemicals promote development of airway allergy? *Indoor Air*, 17(3), 236-255. doi:10.1111/j.1600-0668.2006.00468.x

NMP Producers Group. (1999a). *N-Methylpyrrolidone (NMP): Two generation reproduction toxicity study on Wistar rats - Administration in the diet*. In: ECHA (2013) Annex XV Restriction report proposal for a restriction substance name(s): N-Methylpyrrolidone (NMP) Retrieved from

http://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/13641/nmp_annex_xv_report_en.pdf

NMP Producers Group. (1999b). *Two-generation toxicity study with N-Methylpyrrolidone (NMP) in Sprague-Dawley rats - Administration in the diet*. In: ECHA (2013) Annex XV Restriction report proposal for a restriction substance name(s): N-Methylpyrrolidone (NMP) Retrieved from

http://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/13641/nmp_annex_xv_report_en.pdf

NMP Producers Group. (1994). *Repeated dose toxicity study with N-methylpyrrolidone in B6C3F1 mice - Administration in the diet for 4 weeks (range-finding study)*. Department of Toxicology of BASF AG. In: ECHA (2013) Annex XV Restriction report proposal for restriction substance name(s): n-Methylpyrrolidone (NMP). Retrieved from http://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/13641/nmp_annex_xv_report_en.pdf

OECD (1987). OECD Guidelines for the Testing of Chemicals, Section 4 Health Effects Test. No. 402: Acute Dermal Toxicity. Retrieved from <https://www.oecd.org/environment/test-no-402-acute-dermal-toxicity-9789264070585-en.htm>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 67

OECD (1997a). Test No. 471: Bacterial Reverse Mutation Test.

OECD (1997b), Test No. 476: In Vitro Mammalian Cell Gene Mutation Tests using the Hprt and xprt genes, OECD Guidelines for the Testing of Chemicals, Section 4, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264264809-en>.

OECD (1998). Test No. 408: Repeated Dose 90-Day Oral Toxicity Study in Rodents.

OECD (2001), Test No. 414: Prenatal Developmental Toxicity Study, OECD Guidelines for the Testing of Chemicals, Section 4, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264070820-en>.

OECD SIDS (2007). SIDS Initial Assessment Report on 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone.

OECD (2009a). OECD Guidelines for the Testing of Chemicals, Section 4 Health Effects Test No. 403: Acute Inhalation Toxicity. Retrieved from https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/environment/test-no-403-acute-inhalation-toxicity_9789264070608-en

OECD (2009b). Test No. 412: Subacute Inhalation Toxicity: 28-Day Study.

OECD (2009c). Test No. 413: Subchronic Inhalation Toxicity: 90-day Study: Éditions OCDE / OECD Publishing.

OECD (2010). OECD Guidelines for the Testing of Chemicals, Section 4 Health Effects Test No. 429. Skin Sensitisation Local Lymph Node Assay. Retrieved from https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/environment/test-no-429-skin-sensitisation_9789264071100-en

OECD (2012). Test No. 405: Acute Eye Irritation/Corrosion.

OECD (2014a), Test No. 474: Mammalian Erythrocyte Micronucleus Test, OECD Guidelines for the Testing of Chemicals, Section 4, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264264762-en>.

OECD (2014b), Test No. 475: Mammalian Bone Marrow Chromosomal Aberration Test, OECD Guidelines for the Testing of Chemicals, Section 4, OECD Publishing, Paris,

Parod, R.J., Kaufmann, W., Deckardt, K., & et al. (2001). Liver tumors in mice - N-Methylpyrrolidone (NMP) acts via enhanced cell proliferation. *The Toxicologist*, 60, 286.

Poet, T.S., Schlosser, P., Rodriguez, C.E., Parod, R.J., Rodwell, D.E., Kirman, C. (2016). Using Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic Modeling and Benchmark Dose Methods to Derive an Occupational Exposure Limit for N-Methylpyrrolidone. *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 76

RAC and SCOEL (2016). Joint Opinion to resolve differences in scientific opinion as regards exposure levels for N-Methyl-2-Pyrrolidone (NMP). *Committee for Risk Assessment (RAC) and Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limits (SCOEL), European Chemicals Agency (ECHA)*.

REGULATION (EC) No 1223/2009 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 30 November 2009 on cosmetic products

REGULATION (EC) No 1907/2006 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH), establishing a European Chemicals Agency, amending Directive 1999/45/EC and repealing Council Regulation (EEC) No 793/93 and Commission Regulation (EC) No 1488/94 as well as Council Directive 76/769/EEC and Commission Directives 91/155/EEC, 93/67/EEC, 93/105/EC and 2000/21/EC

RIVM (2013a). Annex XV Restriction Report. Proposal for a Restriction. Substance Name: N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP). Retrieved from

<http://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/ee4c88a9-d26f-4872-98fd-fb41646cc9e1>

RIVM (2013b). CLH report. Proposal for Harmonized Classification and Labelling Based on Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008, Annex VI, Part 2. *Bureau REACH (Ed.), Version number 2*. Retrieved from <http://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/9a6bb3e4-6265-41d2-b963-00e37f95a20e>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 68

Saillenfait, A.M., Marquet, F., Sabaté, J.P., Ndiaye, D., & Lambert-Xolin, A.M. (2016). 4-Week repeated dose oral toxicity study of N-ethyl-2-pyrrolidone in Sprague Dawley rats. *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology*, *81*, 275-283.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yrtph.2016.09.011>

Saillenfait, A.M., Gallissot, F. & Sabate, J.P. (2007). Developmental toxic effects of N-ethyl-2-pyrrolidone administered orally to rats. *J Appl Toxicol*, *27*(5), 491-497. doi:10.1002/jat.1237

Saillenfait, A.M., Gallissot, F., & Morel, G. (2003). Developmental toxicity of N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone in rats following inhalation exposure. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, *41*(4), 583-588

Saillenfait, A.M., Gallissot, F., Langonné, I., & Sabaté, J.P. (2002). Developmental toxicity of N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone administered orally to rats. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, *40*(11), 1705-1712. doi:10.1016/S0278-6915(02)00115-1

Schmied-Tobies, M.I.H., Murawski, A., Rucic, E., Schwedler, G., Bury, D., Kasper-Sonnenberg, M., Koslitz, S., Koch, H.M., Brüning, T., Kolossa-Gehring, M. (2021). Alkyl pyrrolidone solvents N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) and N-ethyl-2-pyrrolidone (NEP) in urine of children and adolescents in Germany – human biomonitoring results of the German Environmental Survey 2014–2017 (GerES V). *Environment International* *146*, doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.106221. Epub 2020 Oct.

Schindler, B.K., Koslitz, S., Meier, S., Belov, V.N., Koch, H.M., Weiss, T., . . . Käfferlein, H.U. (2012). Quantification of Four Major Metabolites of Embryotoxic N-Methyl- and N-Ethyl-2-pyrrolidone in Human Urine by Cooled-Injection Gas Chromatography and Isotope Dilution Mass Spectrometry. *Analytical Chemistry*, *84*(8), 3787-3794. doi:10.1021/ac300439w

Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety (SCCS) (2011). Opinion on N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP). *SCCS/1413/11*

Sitarek, K., Stetkiewicz J., Wąsowicz, W. (2012). Evaluation of reproductive disorders in female rats exposed to N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone. *Birth Defects Res B Dev Reprod Toxicol*, *95*(3),195-201. doi: 10.1002/bdrb.21001. Epub 2012 Feb 6. PMID: 22311695.

Sitarek, K. & Stetkiewicz, J. (2008). Assessment of reproductive toxicity and gonadotoxic potential of N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone in male rats. *International Journal of Occupational Medicine & Environmental Health*, *21*(1), 73-80. doi:10.2478/v10001-008-0006-z

Sitarek, K. & Kilanowicz, A. (2006). Tissue distribution and excretion of N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone in male and female rats. *Int J Occup Med Environ Health*, *19*(2), 142-148. doi:10.2478/v10001-006-0018-5

Ulrich, N., Bury, D., Koch, H.M., Rütter, M., Weber, T., Käfferlein, H.-U., Weiss, T., Brüning, T., Kolossa-Gehring, M. (2018). Metabolites of the alkyl pyrrolidone solvents NMP and NEP in 24-h urine samples of the German Environmental Specimen Bank from 1991 to 2014. *International archives of occupational and environmental health*, *91*(8), 1073-1082. doi:10.1007/s00420-018-1347-y

Solomon, H.M., Burgess, B.A., Kennedy, G.L. Jr, Staples, R.E. (1995). 1-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP): reproductive and developmental toxicity study by inhalation in the rat. *Drug Chem Toxicol*, *18*(4), 271-93. doi: 10.3109/01480549509014324. PMID: 8586021.

Ulrike, B., Alexander, B., Tibor, K., Iljana, M., Nicole, S., Martin von, B., . . . Tobias, P. (2012). Volatile organic compounds enhance allergic airway inflammation in an experimental mouse model. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0039817

United States Environmental Protection Agency (U.S. EPA) (2015). TSCA Work Plan Chemical Risk Assessment N-Methylpyrrolidone (NMP). <https://www.epa.gov/assessing-and-managing-chemicals-under-tsc/tscawork-plan-chemical-risk-assessment-n-0>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 69

Ursin, C., Hansen, C.M., Van Dyk, J.W., Jensen, P.O., Christensen, I.J., & Ebbehøj, J. (1995). Permeability of commercial solvents through living human skin. *Am Ind Hyg Assoc J*, 56(7), 651-660. doi:10.1080/15428119591016665

van Thriel, C., Blaszkewicz, M., Schäper, M., Juran, S.A., Kleinbeck, S., Kiesswetter, E., . . . Bader, M. (2007). Chemosensory effects during acute exposure to N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP). *Toxicology Letters*, 175(1), 44-56. doi:10.1016/j.toxlet.2007.09.007

Wells, D.A. & Digenis G.A. (1988). Disposition and metabolism of double-labeled [3H and 14C] N-methyl-2-pyrrolidinone in the rat. *Drug Metab Dispos* 16(2), 243–249. (<http://dmd.aspetjournals.org/content/16/2/243.abstract>)

WHO (2001). N-METHYL-2-PYRROLIDONE. *Concise International Chemical Assessment Document 35*. Retrieved from: <https://www.who.int/ipcs/publications/cicad/en/cicad35.pdf>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 70

Part III

Derivation of Bisphenol S

HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs):
BPS HBM-GV_{GenPop} for the general population &
BPS HBM-GV_{Worker} for occupationally exposed
adults

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 71

Table of contents (Part III)

Authors and acknowledgements	73
Abbreviations	74
1 Introduction	81
2 General information on BPS.....	82
2.1 Identification of the substance.....	82
2.2 Physico-chemical properties of BPS	83
2.3 Use of BPS	83
2.4 Existing EU classification and regulation on BPS	84
2.4.1 Harmonised classification and labelling.....	84
2.4.2 EU directives and regulations of BPS.....	84
2.5 Human exposure to BPS.....	85
2.5.1 Environmental and consumers exposure	85
2.5.2 Occupational exposure	87
3 Toxicological profile of BPS.....	88
3.1 Toxicokinetics	88
3.1.1 BPS toxicokinetic data after an intravenous administration	90
3.1.2 Absorption and bioavailability of BPS administered by oral route	91
3.1.3 Absorption of BPS through the skin	94
3.1.4 Binding of BPS to plasma proteins.....	95
3.1.5 Distribution of BPS in the materno-fetal unit.....	95
3.2 Health effects of BPS.....	98
3.2.1 Acute toxicity.....	98
3.2.2 Irritation and sensitisation	98
3.2.3 Repeated dose toxicity.....	98
3.2.4 Genotoxicity	102
3.2.5 Carcinogenicity	103
3.2.6 Toxicity to reproduction.....	103
3.2.7 Studies on other endocrine effects.....	142
4 Existing toxicity reference values for BPS	159
5 HBM parameters.....	162
5.1 Choice of biomarkers	162
5.2 Analytical methods.....	162

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 72

6	Derivation of HBM-GVs for BPS.....	163
6.1	Derivation method.....	163
6.2	Derivation of the HBM-GV for the general population.....	163
6.2.1	Choice of a Point of Departure (POD).....	163
6.2.2	Prediction of the total BPS urinary concentration with 100 % oral exposure.....	170
6.3	Derivation of the HBM-GV for workers.....	172
7	Level of confidence attributed to the HBM-GVs.....	175
8	Discussion	176
9	Factsheets	178
9.1	Factsheet reporting the HBM-GV _{GenPop} derivation.....	178
10	References	186
11	Annexes.....	197
11.1	Annex 1.....	197
11.2	Annex 2 : Derivation of HBM-GVs for BPS under scenario 1.....	214

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 73

Authors and acknowledgements

Lead authors

Claire Beausoleil (ANSES)

Contributors

ANSES Working Group on Biomarkers, especially Florence Zeman, Jean-Philippe Antignac, ANSES Working Group on Endocrine Disruptors, Sylvie Babajko, Marie-Chantal Canivenc, Nicolas Chevalier, Claude Emond, Nicole Hagen-Picard, Brigitte LeMagueresse-Batistoni, Sakina Mhaouty-Kodja and Catherine Viguié, Christophe Rouselle (ANSES), Matthieu Meslin (ANSES), Petra Apel (UBA), Rosa Lange (UBA)

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank the following experts for reviewing this report:

Andreas Kortenkamp (Brunel University, London), Dirven Hubert (NIPH), María Angeles Martínez Rodríguez (IISPV), Maria Uhl (EEA), Rex FitzGerald (SCAHT), Shalenie den Braver-Sewradj (RIVM), Wieneke Bil (RIVM), Sophie Ndaw (INRS), Susana Viegas (ENSP), Teresa Borges (DGS)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 74

Abbreviations

8-OHDG	8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine
ADI	Acceptable Daily Intake
ADME	Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion
AF	Assessment Factor
AFA	Assessment Factor for interspecies differences
AFH	Assessment Factor accounting for intraspecies differences
AGÖF	Arbeitsgemeinschaft ökologischer Forschungsinstitute e.V (Association of Ecological Research Institutes)
AGP	Alpha1-acid glycoprotein
ALP	Alkaline Phosphatase
ALT	Alanine aminotransferase
ANSES	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety
ANSES ED-EG	ANSES Expert Group for endocrine disruptors
AR	Androgen Receptor
AST	Aspartate aminotransferase
AUC	Area Under the Curve
BADGE	Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether
BAT	Brown Adipose Tissue
BE	Biomonitoring Equivalent
BfR	Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung (Federal Institute for Risk Assessment)
BGV	Biological Guidance Value
BLV	Biological Limit Value
BLV	Bundesamt für Lebensmittelsicherheit und Veterinärwesen, Schweiz (Federal Food Safety and Veterinary Office, Switzerland)
BMD	Benchmark Dose
BMDL	Benchmark Dose Lower confidence Limit
BMI	Body Mass Index
BPA	Bisphenol A
BPA-DG	Bisphenol A diglucuronide
BPA-DS	Bisphenol A disulfate
BPAF	Bisphenol AF
BPA-G	Bisphenol A glucuronide

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 75

BPA-MG	Bisphenol A monoglucuronide
BPA-MS	Bisphenol A monosulfate
BPAP	Bisphenol AP
BPA-S	Bisphenol A sulfate
BPB	Bisphenol B
BPE	Bisphenol E
BPF	Bisphenol F
BPM	Bisphenol M
BPP	Bisphenol P
BPS	Bisphenol S
BPS-G	BPS glucuronoconjugated
BPS-MAE	Bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)sulfonylphenyl
BPS-S	Bisphenol S sulfate
BPZ	Bisphenol Z
Bw	Body weight
CAT	Catalase
CEF Panel	Panel on Food Contact Materials, Enzymes, Flavourings and Processing Aids
CHL	Chinese Hamster Lung (cells)
CHO	Chinese hamster ovary (cells)
CL	Clearance
Cl_F	Apparent clearance
CLH	Harmonised Classification and Labelling
CLP	Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures
Cmax	Maximum plasma concentration
CMC	carboxy-methylcellulose
CMR	Carcinogenic, Mutagenic, and Reprotoxic
CoRAP	Community Rolling Action Plan
DFG	German Research Foundation
DHEA	Dehydroepiandrosterone
DMSO	Diméthylsulfoxyde
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DNEL	Derived No-Effect Level

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 76

DPC	Day post coitum
DPHP	Di-2-propylheptyl phthalate
E2	Estradiol
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EDC	Endocrine disrupting chemical
EE2	Ethinylestradiol
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
ER/ESR	Estrogen Receptor
ERE	Estrogen Response Element
ERR γ	Estrogen-related receptor gamma
EU	European Union
F	Female
FABP4	Fatty acid binding protein
FCM	Food contact materials
FSH	Follicle-stimulating hormone
GA	Gestational age
GC-MS	Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry
GD	Gestation day
GI	Gastrointestinal
GM	Geometric Mean
GPER	G protein-coupled estrogen receptor
GPMT	Guinea pig maximisation test
GR	Glucocorticoid receptor
GSH	Glutathione
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU	European Human Biomonitoring Initiative
HBM-GV	HBM Guidance Value
HBM-GV _{GenPop}	HBM-GV for the general population
HBM-GV _{Worker}	HBM-GV for occupationally exposed adults
HDL	High density lipoprotein
HED	Human Equivalent Dose
HEDF	Human Equivalent Dose Factor

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 77

HGPRT	Hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyltransferase
HPLC	High-Performance Liquid Chromatography
HPRT	Hypoxanthin Phosphoribosyltransferase
HR	Hazard Rate
HSA	Human serum albumin
IARC	International Agency for Research on Cancer
IOELV	Indicative Occupational Exposure Limit Value
ip	Intraperitoneal
iv	Intravenous
Km	Michaelis constant
LC	Liquid Chromatography
LD	Lactation day
LD50	Median lethal dose
LDL	Low density lipoprotein
LH	Luteinising hormone
LLE	Liquid-Liquid Extraction
LLNA	Local Lymph Node Assay
LLOQ	Lower Limit of Quantification
LO(A)EC	Lowest observed (adverse) effect concentration
LO(A)EL	Lowest observed (adverse) effect level
LOD	Limit of Detection
LOQ	Limit of Quantification
LPO	Lipid peroxidation
M	Male
MAK	Maximale Arbeitsplatz-Konzentration (Threshold Limit Value)
MCH	Mean corpuscular hemoglobin
MCHC	Mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration
MCV	Mean corpuscular volume
MEOGRT	Medaka Extended One Generation Reproductive Toxicity
MoA	Mode of Action
MR	Mineralocorticoid receptor
mRNA	Messenger ribonucleic acid
MRT	Mean Residence Time

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 78

MTT	[4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl]-2,5-diphenyl tetrazolium
nd	No data
NHANES	National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey
NICNAS	National Industrial Chemicals Notification and Assessment Scheme
NIOSH	National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (United States of America)
NO(A)EC	No Observed (Adverse) Effect Concentration
NO(A)EL	No Observed (Adverse) Effect Level
NTP	National Toxicology Program
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OECSEH	Office of Environmental Chemicals Safety Environmental Health Bureau
OEL	Occupational Exposure Limit
PACT	Public Activities Coordination Tool
PBPK modelling	Physiologically-based pharmacokinetic modelling
PBPK/PBTK	Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic/Toxicokinetic
PC	Polycarbonate
PCE	Polychromatic erythrocytes
PCNA	Proliferating cell nuclear antigen
PCPs	Personal care products
PFOA	Perfluorooctanoic acid
PG	Progesterone
P-gp	P-glycoprotein
PR/PGR	Progesterone Receptor
PND	Postnatal day
PNW	Postnatal week
POD	Point of Departure
PPARG	Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma (PPAR- γ)
ppm	Parts per million
PRL(R)	Prolactin (receptor)
p-TDI	Provisional Tolerable Daily Intake
PVB	Polyvinyl butyral
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride plastic polymer
PXR	Pregnane X receptor
RBC	Red blood cell

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 79

REACH	Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
RfD	Reference dose
RIVM	Netherlands National Institute for Public Health and the Environment
RMOA	Risk Management Options Analysis
SAR	Seasonal allergic rhinitis
SCE	Sister chromatid exchange
SCF	Scientific Committee on Food
SCOEL	Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limit Values (European Commission)
SD	Standard deviation
SDN-POA	Sexual dimorphic nucleus of the preoptic area
SIDS	Screening Information Dataset
SLRL	Sex-linked recessive lethal (assay)
SML	Specific Migration Limit
SOD	Superoxide dismutase
SPE	Solid-Phase Extraction
SPE-HPLC-MS/MS	Solid-Phase Extraction (SPE)–High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) with Mass Spectrometry (MS)/MS
SRBC	Sheep red blood cells, T-cell dependent antibody response
sRV	Standard respiratory volume
STAR	Steroidogenic acute regulatory protein
SULT	Sulfotransferase
SVHC	Substance of Very High Concern
T	Thyroid hormone
T3	Triiodothyronine
T4	Thyroxine
TDI	Tolerable Daily Intake
TEB	Terminal end bud
TG	Triglycerides
TGSA	Bis-(3-allyl-4-hydroxyphenyl) sulfone
TK	Toxicokinetic
Tmax	Time to maximum concentration
TRV	Toxicity Reference Value

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 80

TSD	Toy Safety Directive (Directive 2009/48/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 June 2009 on the safety of toys)
TSH	Thyroid stimulating hormone
t-TDI	Temporary Tolerable Daily Intake
TTP	Time to pregnancy
TWA	Time Weighted Average
UBA	German Federal Environment Agency
UDP	Uridine 5'-diphospho-glucuronosyl
UGT	Uridine 5'-diphospho-glucuronosyl transferase
UPLC-MS/MS	Ultraperformance liquid chromatography and tandem mass spectrometry
US EPA	United States Environment Protection Agency
USA	United States of America
VITO	Flemmish Institute for Technological Research
VLDL	Very low density lipoprotein
Vmax	Maximum volume
Vss	steady state volume of distribution
WBC	White blood cell
WG	Working group
WoE	Weight of Evidence
ZEOGRT	Zebrafish Extended One Generation Reproductive Toxicity
γGT	γ-Glutamyl transferase

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 81

1 Introduction

Within the framework of the task 5.2 of the European Joint Programme, HBM4EU, Human Biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) are derived for HBM4EU priority substances. The methodology applied to derive these values is described in the strategy paper previously released in the HBM4EU task 5.2 workframe (Apel et al., 2020).

For the time being, HBM-GVs are derived in HBM4EU under inclusion of experts from the 30 partner countries. Future use and implementation will be discussed among partners and the EU Commission.

In the current report, general population HBM-GVs (HBM-GV_{GenPop}) and HBM-GV for workers (HBM-GV_{worker}) are derived and discussed for Bisphenol S (BPS).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 82

2 General information on BPS

2.1 Identification of the substance

Bisphenol S (see Figure 1) is a structural analogue of and a substitute for bisphenol A (BPA).

Figure III.1: Structural formula of bisphenol S (left) and bisphenol A (right) for comparison

Some chemical identification data are reported in Table III.1.

Table III.1: BPS Chemical identification

Name*	4,4'-sulphonyldiphenol
Synonyms	BPS, 1,1'-Sulfonylbis[4-hydroxybenzene], 4,4'-Bisphenol S, 4,4'-Dihydroxydiphenylsulfone, 4,4' Sulfonylbisphenol, 4,4'-Sulfonyldiphenol, Bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)sulfone)
IUPAC Names*	4-(4-hydroxybenzenesulfonyl)phenol
CAS Number	80-09-1
EC /List no.*	201-250-5
InChI Key*	InChI=1S/C12H10O4S/c13-9-1-5-11(6-2-9)17(15,16)12-7-3-10(14)4-8-12/h1-8,13-14H
SMILES*	OC1=CC=C(C=C1)S(=O)(=O)C1=CC=C(O)C=C1

*: Data from (ECHA Dissemination 2020)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 83

2.2 Physico-chemical properties of BPS

The physico-chemical properties of BPS are shown in table III.2. At room temperature, BPS is an odourless whitish powder. BPS is sparingly soluble in water but well soluble in a number of organic solvents.

Table III.2: Physico-chemical properties of BPS

Sum formula*	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₄ S
Physical state	Solid (20 C, 1013 hPa) / particulate/powder
Colour	Whitish
Density (g/cm ³)	1.37-1.4 at 15 C
Molar mass (g/mol)	250.28
Vapour pressure (hPa)	6.29 x 10 ⁻¹⁰ at 25 C (calculated)
Melting point	242-248 C at 101.3 kPa*
Boiling point (°C)	(decomposition at ≥ 315 C)
Partition coefficient n-octanol/water (log Kow)	1.2 at 23 C and pH 6.2*
Water solubility (mg/L)	714 at 20 C and pH 5.7
pKa	8.0 (at 20 C)*

*: Data from (ECHA Dissemination 2020)

2.3 Uses of BPS

Technical BPS can be prepared by reacting phenol with concentrated sulfuric acid or oleum. As the structurally related BPA, which is produced and used in higher amounts, BPS is used for epoxy resins, in coatings for cans, in the production of plastics, especially in polycarbonate plastics (or number 7 plastics) and as additive in dyes and tanning agents (Chen, Kannan et al. 2016). BPS is especially used in thermal paper as a substitute for BPA (ECHA 2014; Goldinger, Demierre et al. 2015; US EPA 2015; Björnsdotter, Jonker et al. 2017; Eckardt and Simat 2017). A market analysis conducted in Germany in 2015-2017 revealed that BPA still is the most often used dye coupling developer in thermal paper which could be found in about 50 % of all thermal papers examined. Within this three-year period BPS could be detected in 11.4 %, 9.2 % or 6.1 % of all thermal papers examined, respectively (Eckardt and Simat 2017). An EU-wide market survey in 2014-2017 revealed that BPS was present in 4 %, 3.5 % or 9 % of developers used overall in thermal papers and that the absolute amount of BPS put on the market for this purpose more than doubled from 15 to 34 kt. This is seen as indication that European paper producers increased their efforts in replacing BPA by BPS in 2017. It is expected that the importance of BPS will further increase within the next years (ECHA 2014).

ECHA's fourth and final market survey on the use of BPA and other developers in thermal paper confirms that paper manufacturers have continued to replace BPA with BPS. In 2019, 187 kilotonnes of BPS-based thermal paper were placed on the EU market. By 2022, it is expected that 61 % (or 307 kilotonnes) of all thermal paper in the EU will be BPS-based. According to the survey,

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 84

BPA-based thermal paper still had a 29 % market share in 2019 in the EU. From 2020 onwards, BPA is expected to be replaced mainly by BPS (ECHA, 2020a).

2.4 Existing EU classification and regulation on BPS

2.4.1 Harmonised classification and labelling

There is currently no harmonised classification and labelling for BPS under the EU classification and labelling (CLP) Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 (ECHA, 2020b). However, a proposal of EU classification and labelling has been recently made by the Belgium Member States with a classification as Repr. 1B H360FD.

BPS is self-classified by its Registrants and CLP Notifiers as Repr. 2 H361F, Eye Irrit. 2 H319, and Aquatic Chronic 3 H412.

Table III.3: BPS classification according to Annex VI of the EU Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008

International Chemical Identification	CAS No	Classification		Labelling	
		Hazard Class & Category code(s)	Hazard statement code(s)	Pictogram, Signal Word code(s)	Hazard statement code(s)
4,4'-sulphonyldiphenol	80-09-1	<i>Warning!</i> According to the classification provided by companies to ECHA in REACH registrations this substance is suspected of damaging fertility or the unborn child.			

Table III.4: BPS self classification proposal

International Chemical Identification	CAS No	Self-classification and labelling proposal		
		Hazard Class & Category code(s)	Hazard statement code(s)	Pictogram, Signal Word code(s)
4,4'-sulphonyldiphenol	80-09-1	Repr. 2 Eye Irrit. 2 Aquatic Chronic 3	H361 (H361F: Suspected of damaging fertility or the unborn child..) H319 H315 H335 H412	GHS08 GHS07

2.4.2 EU directives and regulations of BPS

BPS is not addressed at the present time in the following EU Directives and regulations: cosmetic products safety, toy safety directive or occupational safety and health. BPS is currently authorised to be used as a monomer in the manufacture of plastic food contact materials (FCM) and is listed

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 85

in Annex I of Commission Regulation (EU) No 10/2011¹, with a Specific Migration Limit (SML) of 0.05 mg/kg. The current authorisation is based on an evaluation by the Scientific Committee on Food (SCF) concerning the 10th additional list of monomers and additives for FCM, which was adopted by the SCF in 22 June 2002. At that time, BPS was classified in list SCF list 3 meaning that a TDI could not be established although the use could be accepted. Switzerland banned BPS and BPA from being used in thermal paper at a concentration equal to or greater than 0.02 % by weight. Companies will need to comply by 1st June 2020³.

2.5 Human exposure to BPS

2.5.1 Environmental and consumers exposure

2.5.1.1 Environmental, food, and other product related external exposure

Compared to the much more studied analogue BPA, limited data are available regarding the occurrence of BPS in environmental matrices. Based on few samples determinations in surface water showed an average of 26.5 µg/l in India (N=5) and of 0.5 µg/l in China (N=5) with 0.07 ng/g in sediments sampled in China. Samples of sewage sludge from Korea, China and the USA (N=40, 52, 76) contained average concentrations of 3.8-5.8 ng/g (Chen, Kannan et al. 2016). Surface waters collected in Japan, Korea, China, and India and in seawater from Tokyo Bay contained average concentrations of 1.6 to 8.7 ng/L (Yamazaki et al., 2015).

BPS was also detected in waste water from textile cleaning companies in Denmark and from two food production/processing plants located in Denmark and Slovenia. Among the investigated Bisphenols only BPS and BPF were detected exclusively in effluents, whereas other Bisphenols were present in both, influents and effluents (Česen et al. (2018)).

BPS could also be detected in samples of house dust. Indoor samples obtained in the USA and three Asian countries (N=156) contained 0.13-0.82 µg/g on average. Another study conducted in the USA and 11 other countries revealed mean values of < 2 to 860 µg/g in indoor house dust (Chen, Kannan et al. 2016).

Studies in food revealed that BPS and some other bisphenols can be detected in a large number of foodstuffs at relatively low concentrations. A study in Spain could detect BPS in canned food at concentrations ranging from around ten to almost 200 ng/g (Vinas, Campillo et al. 2010). A further study measured the concentration of eight bisphenols in 289 food samples in Chinese urban areas in 2012. Altogether, 77.5 % of all food samples were above the limit of detection for the total bisphenols. The mean value of BPS reached 0.287 ng/g wet weight (median: 0.005 µg/g, 95th percentile 0.241 µg/g). The lowest median was noted in the category “fish and seafood” (0.145 ng/g), and the highest value was observed in a sample of meat (42.3 µg/g) (Liao and Kannan 2014).

In a US study performed in 2008-2012, food samples (N = 267) from nine categories (drinks, dairy products, fats and oils, fish and seafood, cereals, fruits, meat and meat products, vegetables, “other”) showed an average cumulative value for eight bisphenols of 4.38 ng/g wet weight (95th percentile 21 ng/g). Bisphenols could be detected in 74.5 % of samples studied. As expected, the main part of bisphenols was represented by BPA (68 % in total), whereas BPS made up 3 %. The

¹ Commission Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 of 14 January 2011 on plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food. Available online: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32011R0010&from=EN>

² https://ec.europa.eu/food/sites/food/files/safety/docs/sci-com_scf_out62_en.pdf

³ <https://chemicalwatch.com/77769/switzerland-bans-the-use-of-bpa-and-bps-in-thermal-paper>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 86

highest average of BPS was found in meat and meat products (0.609 ng/g fresh weight), the lowest in drinks and “other” foodstuff (0.007 ng/g). The concentration of BPS in meat and meat products was nearly as high as that of BPA (0.852 ng/g), and both concentrations were exceeded by that of BPF (1.34 ng/g) (Liao and Kannan 2013). Based on this study, the average daily intake of BPS with food was estimated to be 1.31 µg/kg bw/day) for adults, and the 95th percentile to be 1.66 µg/kg bw/day. Children aged 1-6 years old had the highest estimated intake (mean 4.34 µg/kg bw/day, 95th percentile 4.74 µg/kg bw/day). Overall, the estimated dietary intake of BPS, between 2008-2012, reached only about 3 % of that for BPA. Given that the samplings were done more than 10 years ago, we can assume that the level of bisphenols in food items is nowadays different.

Another study examined the presence of 24 endocrine-disrupting chemicals (EDCs), including eight bisphenols, in seven categories of feminine hygiene products (i.e., pads, panty liners, tampons, wipes, bactericidal creams and solutions, and deodorant sprays and powders; n = 77) collected in the Albany area of New York State, USA (Gao and Kannan, 2020). BPF, BPA, and BPS were the major bisphenols found in feminine hygiene products. BPF was widely found in tampons (92 %) and panty liners (69 %) at median concentrations of 8.44 and 4.82 ng/g, respectively. BPA was widely found in pads (72 %), panty liners (69 %), tampons (92 %), and wipes (75 %). Panty liners (5.12 ng/g) contained the highest concentration of BPA, followed by pads (2.77 ng/g), tampons (0.70 ng/g), and wipes (0.57 ng/g).

BPS was found in bactericidal creams and solutions (62 %), but was rarely (<20 %) found in other categories of samples. Bisphenol P (BPP), Bisphenol Z (BPZ), Bisphenol AP (BPAP), Bisphenol AF (BPAF), and Bisphenol B (BPB) were seldom found in feminine hygiene products (<20 %). BPA and BPF were reported to be present in <50 % of non-feminine hygiene related personal care products (PCPs) from the United States (Liao and Kannan 2014a). Toilet soaps in the United States contained BPA at a mean concentration of 4.05 ng/g, which was lower than that found in panty liners (8.44 ng/g) and tampons (4.82 ng/g). The source of bisphenols in tampons and panty liners could be the plastic polymers that may contain these chemicals as additives or impurities.

A study examined the presence of thirteen bisphenol related compounds in paper products (120 thermal papers and 81 non-thermal papers) collected in Beijing, China (Yang et al., 2019). The results indicated that the replacement of BPA by alternatives such as Bisphenol S (BPS), Bis(2-chloroethyl)ether-4,4"-dihydroxydiphenyl sulfone copolymer (D-90), 4-hydroxyphenyl 4-isopropoxyphenylsulfone (D-8), Bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)sulfonylphenyl (BPS-MAE) and Bis-(3-allyl-4-hydroxyphenyl) sulfone (TGSA) has been significantly advanced in several types of thermal paper (i.e., market weight stickers, train tickets, express labels, air boarding passes and lottery tickets), while BPF was not detected in any sample.

The mean value for the total analyte concentrations in thermal paper was 6.06 mg/g, and the highest level found was 26.0 mg/g. The frequent detection of these chemicals in non-thermal paper (>80 %, n = 81) demonstrated that the contamination in thermal paper can be spread into other recycled paper, such as corrugated boxes, newspapers, food contact papers, etc. The estimated daily intake of BPA and its alternatives through the handling of thermal paper was 0.025 µg/kg bw/day for the general population.

2.5.1.2 Urinary internal exposure levels

Similar to BPA, the excretion in urine appears as the more commonly used parameter to estimating the internal exposure to BPS. In the vast majority of available studies, the urinary exposure level is estimated after enzymatic hydrolysis of the conjugates, so that the total of both free plus conjugated forms is determined. The determination of total urinary BPS also is the prioritised

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 87

marker within the HBM4EU project. Although the unconjugated form of BPS is known to be more biologically active, the measurement of total BPS allows simpler comparison with current methodological detection limits, and is a protective exposure assessment approach considering possible endogenous deconjugation. Conversely, very few data are available on the levels of excretion of unconjugated BPS in the urine, confirming a very low proportion (<1 %) of free urinary BPS (Santé Publique France, 2019). Most existing studies have determined exposure levels in spot urine samples. The results of these studies will be described in the deliverable D5.8: “3rd set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals”.

2.5.1.3 Blood, plasma and serum internal exposure levels

Existing data extracted from the examined studies with regard to reported human blood (including whole blood, plasma or serum) levels of BPS will be detailed in the deliverable D5.8. Conversely to what is observed for urinary analyses where a systematic hydrolysis of conjugated metabolites is done prior to detection, analytical protocols for blood analysis appear more heterogeneous as some of them are reporting the levels of the free form while others may apply a double analysis to separately determine the free and the total of free plus conjugated form. Generally, it must be mentioned that the analysis of bisphenols in human blood is less common than in urine.

2.5.1.4 Exposure levels in other human matrices

Other matrices such as breast milk (Dualde et al. 2019a and b) and Jin et al. 2020) or hair (Katsikantami et al. 2020) have been used to measure bisphenols' levels but data are up to now too limited to recommend the use of such matrices in the context of the HBM4EU project.

2.5.2 Occupational exposure

Occupational exposure to bisphenol compounds other than BPA (i.e. BPS and BPF) is limited. In fact, among the 65 articles identified by our literature search only two describe the exposure assessment of workers to BPS and these were related to thermal receipts. These studies will be detailed in the deliverable D5.8.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 88

3 Toxicological profile of BPS

A registration dossier in accordance with REACH is available on Annex X (full dossier, 10,000-100,000 t/a) (ECHA Dissemination 2020). BPS is listed in the Public Activities Coordination Tool (PACT) list, according to which a regulatory management options analysis (RMOA) has been prepared by the Belgian Federal Public Service Health because BPS is suspected to have endocrine disrupting and CMR properties (ECHA, 2016c)⁴.

BPS is also listed in CoRAP (Community Rolling Action Plan) (ECHA 2016a) and accordingly, several studies were requested under Substance Evaluation (a toxicokinetics study according to OECD TG 417, in vivo alkaline comet assay according to OECD TG 489, an Extended One Generation Reproductive Toxicity (EOGRT) study according to OECD TG 443, and a Medaka or Zebrafish Extended One Generation Reproductive Toxicity study (MEOGRT or ZEOGRT) (ECHA 2016b). The toxicokinetics study and the EOGRT study that were submitted to ECHA in 2019 following from this Substance Evaluation were reviewed by the Belgian Member State Competent Authority as well as EFSA and ECHA (see EFSA Technical Report doi:10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1844).

A proposal of Harmonised Classification and Labelling (CLH) of BPS as Repr. 1B – H360FD based on Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 (CLP Regulation) has been submitted by the Belgian Competent Authority (EC Number: 201-250-5). This CLH proposal gives an overview of the reproductive toxicity studies carried out on BPS according to OECD technical guidelines, including a description of the rat EOGRT study conducted according to OECD TG 443.

In addition to the REACH registration dossier, an OECD SIDS (OECD SIDS 2013) and a “Human Health Tier II Assessment“ of the Australian NICNAS are available (NICNAS 2016). Within the scope of the US National Toxicology Program (NTP) only in vitro studies have been performed; in vivo studies, e.g. a 90-d study with rodents are planned but no data have been published yet (NTP 2018). An overview of studies regarding endocrine effects is presented by Rochester and Bolden 2015 and also in reports of both the US EPA 2015 and NTP 2017.

Lastly, an update on the scientific literature available on BPS was conducted up to January 2020 in using a single concept literature search strategy in searching “Bisphenol S” in Pubmed data base via EndNotes.

3.1 Toxicokinetics

Animal studies revealing systemic effects after oral exposure (see chapter 3.2.1 and 3.2.3.2) indicate resorption of BPS *via* this route of exposure. The detection of BPS in urine of humans (see chapter 2.5) shows that this substance is absorbed, systemically available and eliminated, as parent molecule or its metabolites, via the kidneys.

Bisphenols are largely detoxified by phase II conjugating enzymes, including UDP-glucuronyl transferases (UGT) and sulfotransferases (SULT) (Zalko et al., 2003; Gramec Skledar et al., 2016). Glucuronidation by UGT results in the monoglucuronide conjugate, which is a major metabolite of BPS (Gramec Skledar et al., 2016) and BPA (Hanioka et al., 2008; Kurebayashi et al., 2010). Other BPA metabolites, presumably also BPS metabolites given structural similarities between the two substances, include the monosulphate conjugate produced by SULT (Yalcin et al., 2016), and

⁴ <https://echa.europa.eu/pact>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 89

various sulphate/glucuronide diconjugates (Inoue et al., 2016; Yalcin et al., 2016). Studies with recombinant human UGT enzymes indicated that the hepatic UGT1A9 showed a higher activity against BPS compared to the intestinal UGT1A10. UGT2A1, an enzyme mainly expressed in the respiratory tract, showed a high activity towards BPS (and also BPA and BPF) (Gramec Skledar, Troberg et al. 2015).

A toxicokinetic study according to OECD test TG 417 has been requested as part of the evaluation within REACH (ECHA 2016b). This study is detailed below.

No toxicokinetic (TK) studies are available via the inhalation route nor dedicated study to the transfer to maternal milk or transfer from maternal milk to the newborn. Only very few data are available on the measures of bisphenols' levels in breast milk (Dualde et al. 2019a and b and Jin et al. 2020) see chapter 2.5.1.4.

TK studies are essential to evaluate and integrate the exposure potential of BPS in the human risk analysis process related to the substitution of substances of concern. These TK data can help to predict and understand the internal exposure to the bioactive form of BPS, in humans (Figure III.2).

Figure III.2: Relationship between external and internal exposure and plasma concentrations of non-conjugated (active) and conjugated forms of Bisphenols (BPs).

The internal dose (as parent BPS or its metabolites) is the absorbed fraction of the external dose reaching the systemic circulation from the site of administration. Bioavailability refers to the amount of BPS which reaches the systemic circulation as bioactive, parent substance, i.e. quantifies the proportion of Bisphenol which is absorbed and available to produce systemic effects.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 90

3.1.1 BPS toxicokinetic data after an intravenous administration

Table III. 5 summarises several toxicokinetic parameters like clearance (CL), half-life ($t_{1/2}$), volume of distribution and Mean Residence Time (MRT), evaluated after a single intravenous (iv) administration of BPS in several species (rat, pig, sheep).

Table III.5: Toxicokinetic parameters (Mean \pm SD) calculated with a non-compartmental model for different species following a single intravenous administration.

Species	Dose (iv) (mg/kg bw)	Plasma clearance CL (L/kg.h)	Elimination half-life ($t_{1/2}$) (hour)	Steady state volume of distribution (Vss) (L/kg)	Mean Residence Time(MRT) (h)	References
Female rats	5	0.92	4.77	3.64	3.96	Gayrard et al., 2020
Female piglets	5	0.95 \pm 0.24		0.75 \pm 0.38	0.75 \pm 0.53	Gayrard et al., 2019
Sheep (non pregnant)	5	0.57 \pm 0.13		0.17 \pm 0.44	0.30 \pm 0.04	Grandin et al., 2017
Sheep (pregnant)	5	0.99		0.38	0.38	Grandin et al., 2018

In these species, the plasma concentration profile of BPS was characterised by a phase of rapid decrease in blood concentrations followed by a slow elimination phase from the blood. Plasma concentrations of glucuronoconjugated BPS (BPS-G) increased rapidly after iv administration of BPS indicating that BPS (like BPA) was rapidly and mainly metabolised into its glucuronide form (in adult sheep, glucuronoconjugation of 75 \pm 4% over 72 h, Grandin et al., 2017), In rat, a rebound in BPS-G plasma concentrations was observed and may reflect the BPS enterohepatic recirculation. This enterohepatic cycling was also suggested by the rather high fecal excretion of BPS and its metabolites following iv administration corresponding to 32.5 % of the dose (Waidyanatha et al., 2018).

The BPS clearance, a scaling parameter between administered dose and plasma concentration (for a linear distribution), was similar between different species. In sheep and piglets, the BPS clearance was between 2-3.5 times lower than BPA clearance (Grandin et al., 2017; Gayrard et al., 2019), indicating that BPS is eliminated less efficiently than BPA. In addition, BPS is more persistent in rats than in sheep and piglets, as reflected by the parameter MRT which is between 5-13 times higher, and apparent volume of distribution (Vss), 5-21 times higher.

Following iv BPS exposure, the mean fraction of BPS dose recovered in urine, mainly as BPS-G, through 24 h was 29.5% and 37.5% in rat (respectively, Waidyanatha et al., 2018 and Gayrard et al., 2020), compared to 76.8 \pm 20.1 % in piglets, and 90 \pm 34 % in pregnant sheep (Grandin et al., 2018). In rat, the fraction of sulfoconjugated BPS recovered in urine was very low (Waidyanatha et al., 2018). In the piglets, unconjugated BPA and BPS in urine represented, respectively, 0.044 and 0.027 % of the iv BPA and BPS doses, indicating that the renal clearance of the parent substances is negligible, and that BPS and BPA clearances are mainly driven by conjugation.

An allometric methodology using TK data in animals was used to estimate parameters in humans (Gayrard et al., 2020; Grandin et al., 2017; Grandin et al., 2018). Following this approach, the human clearance for BPS was estimated as 0.79 L/kg*h, a value 2-fold lower than that estimated for BPA in humans. The Vss and MRT were estimated to be 2.26 l/kg and 2.86 h respectively.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 91

3.1.2 Absorption and bioavailability of BPS administered by oral route

Four TK studies evaluate the distribution of BPS after an oral administration, two in humans, one in rats and one in pigs.

Pig model (Gayrard et al., 2019):

TK studies of BPS and BPS-G were performed in a pig model, a species which is generally considered relevant to humans in terms of gastrointestinal physiology. In one experiment, 6 female piglets at the age of 28 days (10.9 ± 0.39 kg bw) received two successive iv administrations of BPS and BPS-G at respective doses of $20 \mu\text{mol/kg}$ (5 mg/kg bw) and $2.23 \mu\text{mol/kg}$ (1 mg/kg bw), 72 h apart. In the second experiment, 6 female piglets at the age of 28 days (10.6 ± 0.83 kg bw) received BPS in two periods separated by 72h, respectively at the dose of $20 \mu\text{mol/kg}$ (5 mg/kg) by iv route and at a dose of $40 \mu\text{mol/kg}$ (10 mg/kg) by orogastric gavage. The resulting ratio of the maximum plasma concentration to oral dose ($C_{\text{max}}/\text{dose}$) was 0.51 ± 0.29 and $2.94 \pm 4.78 \mu\text{mol/L}$ per $\mu\text{mol/kg bw}$ for BPS and BPS-G respectively. The time to maximum concentration (T_{max}) was 0.53 ± 0.28 and 0.73 ± 0.30 hours for BPS and BPS-G respectively. The apparent clearance (Cl_{F}) was 1.86 ± 0.73 and $0.38 \pm 0.11 \text{ L/kg}\cdot\text{h}$ for BPS and BPS-G respectively. The mean fractional urinary excretion of BPS, as BPS-G, collected for 72 hours following oral BPS exposure was $86.5 \pm 23.9\%$, indicating that the glucuronidation was the major metabolic pathway.

In addition, a semiphysiologic based TK model for BPS and BPA (including previously published data) was built to estimate the relative contributions of the different pathways controlling BPA and BPS plasma concentrations, using a non-linear mixed effects model. After gavage administration, the authors estimated that the near totality (99%) of BPS was absorbed after gavage administration, whereas the absorption fraction represented only about 77% for BPA. According to the model, BPS metabolism did not occur in the enterocytes, whereas using the same model, the gut was shown to contribute to the first-pass glucuronidation by 44 % of the BPA absorbed fraction. Although only 41 % of the BPS absorbed fraction was glucuronidated in the liver, the near totality (99 %) of BPA unmetabolised in the enterocytes underwent an extensive hepatic first-pass glucuronidation. The moderate efficiency of hepatic first-pass BPS glucuronidation led to a bioavailability of BPS (fraction of BPS reaching the systemic circulation unchanged) 100 fold higher than that for BPA (57.4 versus 0.50 %) respectively (Gayrard et al., 2019).

This difference due to the extent of BPS and BPA glucuronidation both in the liver and the intestine was also observed in vitro in human cell lines, with liver and intestinal intrinsic clearances of BPS (computed from V_{max} , K_m) respectively 11 and 6 times lower than those of BPA (Karrer et al., 2018).

A toxicokinetic study according to OECD test TG 417 has been requested as part of the evaluation within REACH (ECHA 2016b). A TK and metabolism study was then conducted in which male and female Wistar rats were dosed orally with ^{14}C -BPS at 30 or 300 mg/kg bw. The study results were evaluated by EFSA (see EFSA report: doi: [10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1844](https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1844)). The indications given below were mentioned by EFSA as the view of the study authors.

^{14}C -BPS was rapidly absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract. Based on the bile excretion experiments, oral absorption was calculated to be about 93 and 96 % of the administered dose at a dose level of 300 mg/kg bw for male and female rats, respectively. At a dose level of 30 mg/kg bw about 95% of the administered dose were absorbed by males and 87% of the administered dose were absorbed by females. The excretion of radioactivity occurred mainly within two days after dosing, mainly via urine and bile in bile excretion experiments and with a generally, slightly higher excretion in urine than in feces in balance experiments. Plasma kinetics confirmed high oral absorption and demonstrated potential enterohepatic recirculation, fast excretion and a slight

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 92

supralinear correlation of the internal exposure to the oral dose. In tissue distribution experiments, residues of ¹⁴C-4,4'-sulphonyldiphenol and/or its metabolites in organs and tissues showed generally sublinear correlation to administered oral doses. However, supralinear correlation between radioactive residues in carcass and the external dose was observed in these experiments that is in relation to the findings of plasma kinetics. (Study report, unnamed, 2019).

As regards the metabolism of BPS in rats, the study authors stated that the parent molecule was found to be almost completely unmetabolised in faeces, mostly metabolised in urine and almost completely metabolised in bile.

The study author's proposed metabolic pathway in Figure III.3 shows that glucuronidation of BPS resulted in the main metabolite SES24606 (BPS-G). Metabolite SES24604 (BPS-S) resulted from the sulphation of the parent compound. Metabolite SES24628 (BPS-GS) may result both from the sulphation of SES24606 (BPS-G) and from the glucuronidation of SES24604 (BPS-S).

The results show that in urine BPS-G was the main component (30-35% for the single and repeated low-dose groups and 6-20% for the high-dose groups) in almost all the dose groups, followed by the parent compound. In faeces, the main component was the parent compound with higher proportions in females than in males (high-dose group). BPS-G was found as the main metabolite in bile samples.

Figure III.3: Proposed metabolic pathway for BPS (as quoted in EFSA report: doi:10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1844).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 93

Conclusion from the EFSA Report published in April, 2020 (doi:10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1844) on the TK and metabolism study:

- BPS is rapidly and efficiently (>90%) absorbed after oral administration (with possible enterohepatic recirculation) and excreted within two days.
- It displays gender-specific differences in tissue distribution.
- There is evidence of bone marrow exposure at all BPS doses.
- BPS is mostly excreted in urine as BPS-glucuronide (BPS-G)
- Eliminated as such in faeces
- Excreted in bile as almost completely metabolized to glucuronidated and sulphated derivatives (BPS-S, BPS-G and BPS-GS).

The fact that biliary excretion consists almost completely of conjugates, but that fecal excretion is almost completely unmetabolised, implies extensive deconjugation, consistent with enterohepatic recirculation in the rat (ANSES WG appraisal, 2020).

Human studies

Oh et al. 2018a/b documented the time courses of deuterated BPS (free d4-BPS and total d4-BPS) in plasma and urine of 7 male and female Korean volunteers after a single oral administration of 8.75 µg d4-BPS/kg bw. Total d4-BPS was quickly absorbed within 1 hour after the administration. The concentration profile of BPS observed was different from that of BPA (Thayer et al., 2015). Indeed, after oral exposure, the unconjugated fraction of serum BPS (28%) was much higher than the corresponding value for BPA (0.5%), suggesting a lower glucuronidation rate for BPS. The percentage of the oral dose recovered in urine during 48h as BPS-G (total BPS minus unconjugated BPS) was 92 ± 17 % (67-104%) for men and 70 ± 36 % (59-77%) for women. The percentage of the administered molar dose recovered in urine as unconjugated d4-BPS varied between 0.9 to 3.3%, indicating that the renal clearance of unconjugated d4-BPS is low.

A recent study (Khmiri et al., 2020) evaluated plasma profile and urinary rate time course of BPS and BPS-G in six female volunteers orally exposed to a d8-BPS deuterated dose of 0.1 mg/kg bw. Following oral exposure, the plasma concentration-time courses of d8-BPS and d8-BPS-G over 48 h evolved in parallel, and showed a rapid appearance of BPS in plasma and elimination, mainly as the conjugated form. For plasma d8-BPS and d8-BPS-G, T_{max} (mean ± SD) was 0.7 ± 0.1 and 1.1 ± 0.4 h postdosing and the apparent terminal elimination half-life t_{1/2} was 7.9 ± 1.1 and 9.3 ± 7.0 h, respectively. Similar initial rates in plasma of d8-BPS and d8-BPS-G after oral exposure suggest that both forms reach the systemic circulation around the same time period, indicative of a rapid conjugation of d8-BPS by the enterocytes or hepatocytes prior reaching the systemic circulation (first-pass effect). Furthermore, the observed time profiles of d8-BPS and d8-BPS-G in plasma show a significant enterohepatic recirculation as reported in rats (Gayrard et al., 2019) and from the modelling of BPA in humans (Karrer et al., 2018). The fraction of unchanged d8-BPS reaching the systemic circulation (i.e. bioavailability) was estimated to be 62 ± 5% (mean ± SD), a value similar to that obtained in the pig model. In addition, assuming that first pass metabolism only occurs in the liver, the systemic plasma clearance was estimated to be at 0.57 ± 0.07 L/kg bw/h, a value similar to that estimated by an allometric approach (Gayrard et al., 2020).

In this study, the percentage of the administered molar dose recovered in urine as unconjugated d8-BPS following oral exposure was low, with a range of 0.6 to 4.4%, similar to that observed in

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 94

female volunteers of the study of Oh et al., 2018a/b (0.9 to 3.3%), demonstrating a low renal clearance of unconjugated d8-BPS. 37 to 72% of the administered oral dose were recovered in urine as d8-BPS-G over the 0-72 h collection period postdosing, suggesting that clearance of d8-BPS is mainly driven by its glucuronidation. Furthermore, in an *in vitro* study in human HepaRG hepatic cell line, Le Fol et al., 2015 found that 85.8 % of BPS was conjugated to glucuronides and 10.5 % to sulfates.

In summary, these and the above-mentioned TK studies performed in humans, rats and pigs showed BPS absorption to a considerable extent by the oral route and a large part of the dose recovered in urine as a conjugated form, suggesting that clearance of BPS is mainly driven by its glucuronidation. These data indicate that the internal exposure to BPS in populations can be approximately estimated by determining total BPS amount excreted in urine during 24 h.

There are apparently major differences between BPA and BPS kinetics in humans, with much higher systemic levels of active BPS than BPA, and much higher availability of BPS associated with a lower plasma clearance. In pigs, a species which is generally considered relevant towards humans in terms of gastrointestinal physiology circulating BPS was 100-fold higher in comparison with BPA after oral dosing, and plasma clearance was 3.5 times lower resulting in a 250-fold higher systemic exposure to BPS than to BPA after oral dosing. These TK analyses indicate that the replacement of BPA by BPS may lead to increased exposure to a potentially hormonally active substance.

3.1.3 Absorption of BPS through the skin

One *in vivo* TK study (Khmiri et al., 2020) evaluated the distribution of BPS after transcutaneous administration, and two *in vitro* studies explored the incorporation of BPS across a human skin model derived from keratinocytes (Liu and Martin, 2019; Champmartin et al., 2020).

Plasma and urinary time course of BPS and BPS-G were assessed in six female volunteers exposed by the dermal route to a d8-BPS dose of 1 mg/kg bw, applied on 40 cm² of the forearm and then washed 6 h after application (Khmiri et al., 2020). Following dermal application, plasma levels were below the lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) at most time points. Peak values were reached between 5 and 8 h after the beginning of the exposure suggesting a slower absorption rate compared to oral exposure. Similarly, limited amounts of d8-BPS and d8-BPS-G were recovered in urine and peak excretion rates were reached between 5 and 11 h postdosing. The average percent (\pm SD) of the administered dose recovered over 72 h postdosing in urine as d8-BPS and d8-BPS-G was about 0.004 ± 0.003 and $0.09 \pm 0.07\%$, respectively, indicating that dermal absorption of BPS was limited.

Liu and Martin, 2019 compared the dermal absorption and biotransformation of BPS and BPA *in vitro* using human epidermal cells (EpiDerm™ EPI-212 tissue constructs, a three-dimensional tissue model consisting of normal human epidermal keratinocytes on tissue culture inserts). They found a permeability coefficient for BPS lower than for BPA. At both doses (1.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ and 7.7 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$), <10% of total BPS had migrated into the receiver solutions, whereas 43–46% of total BPA were recovered in receiver solutions (permeability coefficient: 0.009 and 0.003 for BPS *versus* 0.036 and 0.033 cm/h for BPA respectively, after 25 h application). They also reported only limited metabolism in the skin, since more than 70% of total BPS and total BPA were found in the unconjugated form in skin tissue and in receiver solutions.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 95

These authors further compared the dermal penetration of BPS (not isotope-labeled) with published data (Liu and Martin, 2017) for isotope-labeled d6-BPA for the same five volunteers simulating handling of thermal receipts. Urinary excreted total BPS was lower than total d6-BPA. However, it should be noted that BPS was already detected in urine before handling of thermal receipts. BPS was not detected (<0.10 ng/ml) in serum collected over 7.5 h following the dermal exposure, consistent with the results for d6-BPA.

Additionally, Champmartin et al., 2020 compared the dermal absorption of BPS and BPA *in vitro* using fresh human skin samples in static Franz diffusion cells. BPA absorption was vehicle-dependent ranging from 3% with sebum to 41% with water. BPS absorption was much lower than BPA absorption whatever the vehicle tested (less than 1% of applied dose). A high proportion of BPS (20% to 47% of the applied BPS dose) remained in the skin depending on the vehicle used (sebum versus water). Since tape stripping analysis was not conducted, the HBM4EU WP 5-2 team considered it rather difficult to estimate the proportion of BPS present in the stratum corneum and presumably not absorbable.

TK studies performed in humans showed that percutaneous absorption of BPS is very limited (<2 % *in vivo*) and lower than BPA *in vitro* and *in vivo*.

3.1.4 Binding of BPS to plasma proteins

Once the bisphenols are absorbed, they reach the systemic circulation and are distributed in different tissues including the target organs. Bindings to plasma proteins of bisphenols modulate the biodistribution process and the fraction unbound to plasma proteins.

Grumetto et al., 2019 investigated the interactions between eight bisphenols (BPA, BPS, BPF, Bisphenol E (BPE), BPB, BPAF, Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (BADGE) and Bisphenol M (BPM)) and two plasma proteins, human serum albumin (HSA) and alpha1-acid glycoprotein (AGP) by using three approaches: biomimetic liquid chromatography, molecular docking simulations and *in silico* predictions. They showed that the interactions of bisphenols with HSA and AGP were found non-specific and lipophilicity driven. BPA analogues with higher lipophilicity (BPM and BPAF) exhibited a higher affinity for both plasma proteins. For BPB, both *in vitro* and *in silico* approaches demonstrated consistent results and the interaction of BPB with plasma proteins (HSA and AGP) is very similar to BPA

For BPS (as lower lipophilic compound compared to BPA and the only sulfone of the dataset), both, the *in vitro* biomimetic Liquid Chromatography (LC) approach and *in silico* ADME predictions indicated that the percent of unbound BPS in the presence of HSA is higher than that of BPA.

The interactions of bisphenols with plasma proteins (HSA and AGP) were found to be non-specific and lipophilicity-driven. BPS exhibited a higher binding to HSA compared to BPA whereas BPF exhibited a lower binding to HSA and AGP compared to BPA.

3.1.5 Distribution of BPS in the materno-fetal unit

The fetal exposure to bisphenols results from a complex interplay between bidirectional placental clearances and fetal metabolism. To take into account all these determinants simultaneously, two studies (Grandin et al., 2018 and Gingrich et al., 2019) were performed on the late-stage fetal ovine model, a relevant and well-known model for human pregnancy and fetal exposure to xenobiotics, to evaluate the mechanism determining fetal exposure to BPS.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 96

Grandin et al., 2018 evaluated in the materno-feto-placental unit of pregnant ewe the toxicokinetic parameters determining the distribution of BPS and its main metabolite, BPS-G, and compared them to those of BPA and BPA-G previously published (Gauderat et al., 2016). Pregnant ewes received an intravenous bolus of 2.7 mg/kg bw BPS-G and then at the same time the fetus received an iv dose of BPS deuterated (5 mg in total). During the second period of gestation three days apart, the mother received 5 mg/kg bw of BPS and the fetus 17.5 mg total of BPS-G deuterated. In the maternal compartment, BPS was mainly metabolised into BPS-G and totally eliminated in urine.

BPS clearance was 993 mL/h*kg, the Vss 380 mL/kg, MRT 0.38 hours and the $t_{1/2}$ 2.37h (See also Table 5). For BPS-G, the clearance was 48.6 mL/h*kg, the Vss 121 mL/kg, MRT 2.49 hours and the $t_{1/2}$ 5.22h. Only 0.40% of the maternal BPS dose was transferred to the fetus, which means that the fetus was exposed to a dose related to its body weight, that was ten times lower than the maternal BPS dose. However, once in the fetal compartment, only 26% of the BPS dose entering the fetal blood against 74% for BPA was rapidly eliminated through its transfer into maternal blood. This result is in agreement with the higher efficiency of fetal to maternal transfer observed with BPA as compared to its maternal to fetal counterpart evidenced in the perfused human placenta (Grandin et al., 2019). About half of the remaining BPS (46%) was glucurono-conjugated by the fetus. The fetal BPS clearance was 423 mL/h*kg, the Vss 597 mL/kg, MRT 1.41 hours and the $t_{1/2}$ 1.92h. In the fetal compartment, the BPS-G clearance was 1.87 mL/h*kg, the Vss 251 mL/kg, MRT 134 hours and the $t_{1/2}$ 93.6h. The very slow elimination of BPS-G from the fetal compartment due to deconjugation-reconjugation recycling and to the restricted placental passage of BPS, leads to an accumulation of BPS in the fetal circulation. Indeed, BPS accumulated as BPS-G in the fetal compartment must be deconjugated into its active form before it can be ultimately eliminated by the placenta. Thus, despite a low materno-fetal placental transfer of BPS, this BPA analogue can accumulate in the fetal compartment after repeated maternal exposure, leading to chronic fetal exposure to BPS in a range of concentrations similar to those of BPA.

Gingrich et al. (2019) determined the time courses of total BPA, BPS and BPF (conjugated and non-conjugated) in the plasma of pregnant sheep following subcutaneous exposure to 0.5 mg/kg bw. Only total BPA, BPS and BPF were measured after incubation of samples with beta-glucuronidase, a major limitation in this TK comparison between the three bisphenols. The computation of TK parameters is erroneous because the TK parameters were calculated using the plasma concentrations of total BPA, BPS or BPF (i.e. unconjugated and conjugated forms of bisphenols). The maternal C_{max} for total BPS (643 ± 29.9 ng/ml) is an order of magnitude higher than for BPA and BPF (66.7 ± 1.7 ng/ml). The area under the curve of the total maternal BPS concentrations (AUC_m) was significantly higher than that of BPA and BPF. Nine hours after bisphenol administration, maternal urine concentrations for BPA, BPS and BPF were 1300±210 ng/ml, 3870±888 ng/ml and 3.9±3.4 ng/ml respectively. These differences in urine excretion are difficult to interpret because the spot urine sampling at 9 h post-dosing was too late. The fetal /maternal ratio was 1.31, 0.03 and 0.42 for total BPA, BPS and BPF, respectively. In the fetal compartment, the total BPS concentrations decreased much slower compared to those of BPA and BPF. Yet again, it is not possible to understand the mechanism determining BPS and BPF fetal exposure because only total plasma bisphenol concentration profiles were described.

The transfer of BPS and BPS-G from fetomaternal and materno-fetal directions was also evaluated in the human perfused cotyledon ex-vivo model, using 10 placentas (Grandin et al. 2019). The placental materno-fetal transfer rate of BPS was 3.18 ± 2.64% and 0.339±0.263% for BPS and BPS-G respectively. The materno-fetal clearance index of BPS (0.0852) was about 10-fold lower than that of BPA. The materno-fetal transfer of BPS-G is almost non-existent, suggesting

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 97

that fetal exposure to the BPS conjugate could result from fetal metabolism, at least during late gestation. The fetomaternal transfer rates were $5.85 \pm 1.22\%$ and $3.97 \pm 0.919\%$ for BPS and BPS-G respectively. Overall, this study showed that BPS and BPS-G fetomaternal clearance indices were much higher than the corresponding materno-fetal clearance indices. The authors assessed the role of the P-glycoprotein (P-gp) as a transporter of BPS and BPS-G, using an inhibitor of P-gp. They concluded that P-glycoprotein does not seem to be involved in limiting materno-fetal transfer.

The materno-fetal placental transfer of BPS is limited, ten times lower than for BPA, both in the pregnant sheep model and in an ex-vivo model of the perfused human placental cotyledon. But in the sheep model, BPS is able to accumulate in the fetal compartment. This means that under steady state conditions, following repeated gestational exposure to the same bioavailable dose of BPA/BPS, BPS in the fetal compartment can attain similar persistent levels to those of BPA.

Conclusion

Toxicokinetic studies in several species, including humans, showed that BPS is well absorbed by oral route, whereas dermal absorption of BPS is very limited (<2 % *in vivo*).

As previously shown for BPA, BPS clearance is mainly driven by renal excretion following glucuronidation.

Major differences between BPA and BPS toxicokinetics were observed both in animals and in humans:

- the plasma clearance of BPS was lower than that of BPA, indicating that the capacity to eliminate BPS is less than for BPA.
- In rat and human, an enterohepatic recirculation of BPS was evident.
- The oral bioavailability of active, non-conjugated BPS is suggested to be higher in animals as well as in humans compared to that of non-conjugated BPA.

Dealing with the critical period of gestation, TK studies showed that the blood-placental barrier is much more efficient in limiting fetal exposure to BPS than to BPA. But the higher persistence of BPS in the sheep fetal compartment leads with these animals to expected BPS concentrations in fetal plasma of the same order as BPA for the same maternal exposure.

These TK considerations indicate that the daily intake of BPS in populations can be approximately estimated by determining total BPS amount excreted in urine during 24 h. In addition, the replacement of BPA by BPS leads to increased exposure to a hormonally active substance.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 98

3.2 Health effects of BPS

Unless the ANSES ED-EG or the HBM4EU–Task 5.2 Team expressed different view or conclusions, the conclusion of the authors (eg. registrants on the ECHA dissemination website, OECD SIDS authors, Dossier Submitter in the CLH dossier, EFSA evaluation panel, ECHA or scientific author) are reported in the following section.

3.2.1 Acute toxicity

No case reports or studies are available regarding acute toxic effects of BPS in humans. BPS is of very low acute oral toxicity in rats (LD50: 2,830 mg/kg bw in a test similar to the OECD 401 guideline, LD50 > 1600 to > 5000 mg/kg bw in other tests). Dermal toxicity in rabbits is also low (LD50 > 1000 mg/kg bw). No data are available on inhalation toxicity. However, we consider that inhalation exposure to BPS as a vapour is not relevant because of the very low vapour pressure of BPS (OECD SIDS 2013; ECHA Dissemination 2020).

3.2.2 Irritation and sensitisation

Human dermal patch testing with BPS did not elicit an effect (Jelen et al., 1989).

In vitro tests with a reconstructed three-dimensional human epidermis model according to OECD TG 431 did not reveal skin irritation potential. Animal experiments following OECD TG 404 revealed no or at most (after 24 h occlusive exposure) slight transient skin effects and, in summary, no evidence of a skin irritation potential. Slight transient irritation was also observed in eye irritation studies (mostly following OECD TG 405). Effects were too slight to lead to a classification as “eye irritant” (ECHA Dissemination 2020).

BPS did not reveal any dermal sensitisation potential in a mouse local lymph node assay (LLNA) according to OECD TG 429 and in a guinea pig maximisation test (GPMT) according to OECD TG 406 (ECHA Dissemination 2020).

3.2.3 Repeated dose toxicity

3.2.3.1 Data in humans

In a cross-sectional study based on data from the U.S. National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES), 2013 to 2014, relationships between the excretion of BPF, BPA, and BPS and obesity (Body Mass Index (BMI) \geq 30) were studied in adults (minimum age 20 y, non-pregnant, no diagnosed neoplasia). Overall, data from 1521 participants could be evaluated. It was observed that obese participants had higher median values of all three bisphenols in urine than non-obese. After adjusting for demographic, socioeconomic and lifestyle factors the association was still statistically significant for BPA but not for BPS and BPF (Liu, Lehmler et al., 2017).

3.2.3.2 Animal data

Only studies with oral exposure are available.

The registration dossier summarises the results of three oral repeated dose toxicity studies, a 90 day (BASF SE, 2014 also named Anonymous 17, 2014 in the ECHA CLP, 2019), a 28 day (Office of Environmental Chemicals Safety Environmental Health Bureau, 1999 also named Anonymous 16, 1999 in the ECHA CLP, 2019) and a 13-day study (Eastman-Kodak, 1973 also named Anonymous 18, 1973 in the ECHA CLP, 2019). Additionally, the results of another repeated dose study according to OECD TG 421 (Reproduction/Developmental Toxicity Screening Test) with up to 53 day of exposure of rats was described (ECHA Dissemination 2020, ECHA CLP 2019 (quoted as Anonymous 12, 2000), OECD SIDS 2013).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 99

A subchronic study according to OECD TG 408 (ECHA Dissemination, 2020 (quoted as BASF SE, 2014), ECHA CLP, 2019 (quoted as Anonymous 17, 2014)) was performed with oral administration of BPS to Wistar rats (10 males + 10 females/dose). The animals received 0, 100, 300 or 1000 mg BPS/kg bw/day) in carboxymethyl cellulose via gavage for 90 day. Because of the marked reduction in weight gain (-20 % on day 63) in males, the highest dose was reduced to 600 mg/kg bw/day from day 70 on. Salivation was noted directly after the administration of BPS. Soft, light brown discoloured faeces were observed at the middle and high dose. Both observations are regarded in the REACH registration dossier as treatment-related local effects in the gastrointestinal tract. In males, the caecum showed a macroscopically visible dilatation which was confirmed by histopathology in both sexes at the highest and in females also at the mid dose. At the highest dose, regenerative anaemia with extramedullary haematopoiesis in the spleen, reduced haemoglobin concentration and erythrocyte and increased reticulocyte counts and lowered total bilirubin in blood were observed. The increase of the adrenal gland weight in the high dose male animals, which correlated with hypertrophy/hyperplasia in the cortex was regarded as adverse and treatment related by the registrant. The kidney of males showed multifocal tubular mineralisation at all doses but no degenerative changes; therefore, this observation was regarded as not adverse by the registrant. The relative liver weight in females increased with dose (significant with +20 % from the mid dose on), this was accompanied by a dose-dependent hepatocellular hypertrophy (2/10, 5/10, 10/10 animals). Additionally, predominantly eosinophilic foci were noted at the highest dose. The hypertrophy in the liver in combination with the increased liver weight of high dose females was assessed as adverse due to the presence of these foci. The hypertrophy alone in low and mid dose groups was assessed as non-adverse as no concurrent findings in clinical pathology were noted. While the increased relative liver weight in high dose males was assessed as adverse by the registrant together with clinical pathology findings (lower cholesterol and higher triglyceride levels).

In the mammary gland of male animals of the mid and high dose, a change from the physiological lobulo-alveolar morphology to a tubulo-alveolar appearance with smaller more basophilic epithelial lining cells (atrophy) was seen. According to the registrant, the occurrence of atrophy has been correlated in the literature to altered hormone levels (increased prolactin or decreased androgen) but also with emaciation. The findings were regarded as adverse.

In the uterus, focal squamous cell metaplasia of glandular epithelium was observed (in 0, 2, 2 and 5 of 10 animals at 0, 100, 300 and 1000 mg BPS/kg bw/day, respectively). In the high dose group this finding was assessed as treatment-related and adverse due to the higher incidence while the increased uterus weight without correlating histopathological findings was assessed as treatment-related. Lastly, the increased weights of the ovaries in the high dose female animals were assessed as treatment related by the registrant although there were no correlating histopathological findings.

Overall, the lowest dose of 100 mg/kg bw/day was regarded as the NOAEL in male and 300 mg/kg bw/day in female Wistar rats (ECHA Dissemination 2020). This oral sub-chronic study was considered by the registrant as the key study.

In a subacute oral toxicity study (comparable to OECD TG 407) Sprague-Dawley rats (6 or 12 males + 10 females/dose) received 0, 40, 200 or 1000 mg BPS/kg bw/day in aqueous carboxymethyl cellulose *via* gavage for 28 day. Additional 200 and 1000 mg/kg bw/day recovery groups were examined after a 14-day post exposure period. Two males in the highest dose group died, both showed signs of intestinal bleedings in the caecum area which were regarded as the probable cause of death. At necropsy, females showed a dilatation of the caecum at the highest dose. Histopathology revealed a hyperplasia of the mucosa with single cell necrosis in the mucosa

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 100

epithelium, with the incidence and severity increasing at ≥ 200 mg/kg bw/day. Additionally, food consumption and weight gain were reduced at these doses. At the highest dose, both sexes showed haematological changes (erythrocyte count, haemoglobin concentration and haematocrit reduced). Cholesterol in serum was lowered in males and females. Females had increased total protein, albumin and calcium levels in serum; males showed increased phosphatase and reduced lactate dehydrogenase activity in serum. The relative kidney weight was increased in both sexes at ≥ 200 mg/kg bw/day; this effect persisted at the highest dose up to the end of the post exposure period. No histopathological changes were observed in the kidneys. Urine analysis revealed proteinuria at doses ≥ 200 mg/kg bw/day and also an increased excretion of urobilinogen and a lowered pH of the urine at 200 mg/kg bw/day in males only. The relative liver weight was increased at the highest dose, histologically, a hepatocellular centrilobular hypertrophy was observed. Thymus atrophy occurred at the highest dose. The weight of the adrenals was increased and the zona fascicularis was hypertrophic at the highest dose. Furthermore, a spongy structure of the femoral bone was apparent at the highest dose. Based on the described effects on body weight, kidneys, and caecum a NOAEL of 40 mg/kg bw/day and a LOAEL of 200 mg/kg bw/day were derived from this study (OECD SIDS 2013, ECHA Dissemination 2020 (quoted as Office of Environmental Chemicals Safety Environmental Health Bureau, 1999) and ECHA CLP, 2019 (quoted as Anonymous 16, 1999)).

An unpublished subacute oral toxicity study with rats (5 males/dose, strain not reported) is also briefly described. The animals were exposed to food containing 0, 0.1, or 1 % BPS (corresponding to applied doses of 0, 97 or 810 mg/kg bw/day) for 13 days. At the highest dose, effects were mainly observed as tubular epithelial alterations in the kidney (cytoplasmic basophilia). Other slight changes of haematological and clinical chemical parameters, atrophy of the adipose tissue and reduced weight of liver and kidneys were attributed to the observed anorexia. Based on the observed nephrotoxicity, a NOAEL of 97 mg/kg bw/day was determined by the registrant (ECHA Dissemination, 2020 (quoted as Eastman-Kodak, 1973), ECHA CLP, 2019 (also named Anonymous 18, 1973)).

In an OECD guideline 421 study (Reproduction/Developmental Toxicity Screening Test), rats were gavaged with daily dose levels of 10, 60 and 300 mg/kg bw/day. The total exposure period was 45 days for males and 53 days in females (from 14 days before mating to day 3 of lactation). Parental toxicity was characterised by suppressed body weight gain and decreased food consumption in both genders of the high dose group. Relative liver and pituitary weights were increased in high dose males only, though histological hypertrophy of hepatocytes was indicated in both sexes of the 300 mg/kg bw group. Absolute weight of seminal vesicles was decreased in high dose males. Caecum distension was observed in both sexes from the 60 mg/kg bw group, accompanied by diffuse hyperplasia of the caecum mucosal epithelium. The NOAEL for parental toxicity in this study was determined at 10 mg/kg bw/day by the registrant. No kidney effects were reported in the study report (ECHA Dissemination 2020, ECHA CLP 2019 (quoted as Anonymous 12, 2000), OECD SIDS 2013).

In the ECHA CLP report, 2019 the results of a 28-day repeated dose toxicity study, quoted as Anonymous 15, 2017, is described. This study was performed as a range finding study preceding the EOGRT. Sprague-Dawley rats (5 males + 5 females/dose) received 0, 100, 300 or 600 BPS mg/kg bw/day in aqueous carboxymethyl cellulose via gavage for 28 days. Males exhibited a significantly decreased final body weight (-9 and -12 % respectively at 300 and 600 mg/kg bw/day, compared to control). Enlarged kidneys were observed in males from 300 mg/kg bw/day. The relative kidney weight was increased at 300 and 600 mg/kg bw/day in both sexes. Minimal to moderate tubular degeneration/regeneration were observed in kidneys at 100, 300 and 600 mg/kg

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 101

bw/day (in 2, 5 and 5 males respectively) with a minimal tubular hypertrophy at 100 and 300 mg/kg bw/day (in 1 and 5 males respectively) and a moderate tubular hypertrophy at 600 mg/kg bw/day (in 5 males). The relative weight of adrenals was increased in males from 300 mg/kg bw/day compared to the control group with a minimal hypertrophy/hyperplasia of the adrenal cortex at 600 mg/kg bw/day in males. The liver exhibited also changes. The relative weight of the liver was increased in females from 300 mg/kg bw/day compared to the control group. Centrilobular hypertrophy of the liver was noted from 100 mg/kg bw/day in males (minimal hypertrophy in 1 male at 100, slight hypertrophy in 4 males at 300 and moderate hypertrophy in all males at 600) and slight hypertrophy in females at 600 mg/kg bw/day. No further information is reported. The relative weight of prostate and seminal vesicles were decreased at 600 mg/kg bw/day (-15 % for prostate and -16 % for seminal vesicles). Lastly, diffuse atrophy of the mammary gland was observed in 3 males at 300 and in 4 males at 600 mg/kg bw/day. No further information is available, no N(L)OAEL derivation exercise was conducted for any of the reported effects in ECHA CLP report, 2019 (study quoted as Anonymous 15, 2017). Based on the observed kidney effects, the HBM4EU –Task 5.2 Team tentatively estimated the LOAEL at 100 mg/kg bw/day.

A number of repeated dose toxicity studies are published in literature. A study in male ICR mice points to a hepatotoxic potential of BPS in this species/strain (Zhang, Lin et al. 2018). In this study, the animals were given food containing 0, 0.05, 0.5, 5 or 50 ppm BPS. Each subgroup of 6 male mice received treatment with BPS for 4 or 8 weeks. Considering a diet consumption of 10 % of the body weight per animal and day (Marmugi et al., 2012), the authors estimated applied doses of 0, 5, 50, 500 or 5000 µg/kg bw/day. Body weight, weight gain, absolute and relative liver weight were not affected by treatment. An increase by a factor of about two was observed for alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and total bilirubin in serum at the highest dose after 8 weeks. In the liver, the concentration of malondialdehyde was increased, the activity of the enzymes SOD, catalase and GSH peroxidase decreased. Histologically, focal necrosis and sporadic infiltrates of lymphoid cells were observed. The expression of m-RNA for haemoxygenase 1 (HO-1) and for GADD45b (growth arrest and DNA-damage-inducible 45 beta) were increased; this is regarded as linked to the induction of hepatic oxidative stress. In this study, no effects were detected in the liver at all doses after 4 weeks and at doses up to 500 µg BPS/kg bw/day after 8 weeks. Other organs besides the liver were not examined in this study. The authors estimated that 5000 µg/kg bw/day BPS for 8 weeks was not a NOAEL due to the induced liver injury and hepatic oxidative stress in mice observed at this dose level. The HBM4EU –Task 5.2 Team estimates that a LOAEL can be estimated at 5,000 µg/kg bw/day.

Potential toxic effects of BPS on the functions of haemopoietic and cardiovascular systems were investigated by Pal et al. (2017). Adult male albino rats of the Sprague-Dawley strain received BPS by oral gavage at a dose of 30, 60 and 120 mg/kg bw/day in DMSO (20 %) for 30 days. Red blood cell (RBC) count, white blood cell (WBC) count, Hb concentration, and clotting time were significantly reduced dose dependently in all exposed groups of rats compared to the control. Treatment also increased total serum glucose and protein concentration, serum total cholesterol, triglyceride, glycerol free triglyceride, low density lipoprotein (LDL), and very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) concentrations, whereas high density lipoprotein (HDL) concentration was reduced in the exposed groups. BPS significantly increased serum AST, ALT, and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activities dose dependently. Serum calcium, bilirubin, and urea concentrations were increased in all exposed groups. The authors concluded that BPS probably impairs the functions of blood and promotes cardiovascular risks in rats.

BPS also disrupted glucose metabolism and was associated with increased food consumption and body weight gain in mice exposed to 25, 50, and 100 µg/kg in water for 10 weeks (Rezg et al.,

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 102

2018 and 2019). Exposure to BPS (10 and 100 µg/kg bw/day) was also associated with significant nephrotoxicity in mice (Zhao et al., 2018a).

No data are available from chronic studies.

3.2.4 Genotoxicity

3.2.4.1 *In vitro*

BPS was not mutagenic in Ames assays in the absence or presence of an exogenous metabolising system (S9) when tested up to cytotoxic concentrations. Examined test strains were *Salmonella typhimurium* TA98, TA100, TA1535, TA1537, TA1538 and *Escherichia coli* WP2 *uvrA*. Available assays include both tests according to OECD TG 471 and non-guideline tests (Fic, Zegura et al., 2013; OECD SIDS 2013; ECHA Dissemination 2020).

No evidence for mutagenic activity was found in mammalian cells (L5178Y mouse lymphoma cells and CHO/HGPRT mutation assay) when BPS was tested without or with an exogenous metabolising system at up to cytotoxic concentrations (OECD SIDS 2013; ECHA Dissemination 2020).

A chromosomal aberration assay performed according to OECD TG 473 with Chinese hamster cells showed after 24 h an increase in structural chromosomal aberrations and gaps but not of cells with polyploidy at the highest test concentration without cytotoxicity of 0.4 mg BPS/ml in the absence of metabolic activation. A slight increase in the number of cells with polyploidy was noted after 6 h incubation with up to 1.4 mg/ml in the absence or presence of metabolic activation. In view of the low frequency of the observed changes, the result was rated as negative by the study authors. Cytotoxicity was observed without and with an exogenous metabolic activation system at ≥ 0.7 mg/ml (OECD SIDS 2013; ECHA Dissemination 2020).

In a further chromosomal aberration assay performed according to OECD TG 473 with CHO cells, an increase of aberrations was described at 500 and 600 µg/ml (cytotoxic levels, 25 - 35 %) in the absence of S9 mix (two sets of experiments). Cytotoxicity precluded an analysis at concentrations > 700 µg/ml. No increase was observed in the presence of S9 (OECD SIDS 2013; ECHA Dissemination 2020).

BPS did not induce the formation of DNA double strand breaks in human hepatocellular carcinoma (HepG2) cells (Hercog et al., 2019).

3.2.4.2 *In vivo*

A micronucleus test (according to OECD TG 474) was conducted with male CD-1 mice. The animals (6/group) received 0, 500, 1000, or 2000 mg BPS/kg bw/day (limit dose) by gavage (two doses with a 24 h interval). Neither toxic effects nor an induction of micronuclei in polychromatic erythrocytes (PCE) was observed. The relative amount of PCE on the total amount of erythrocytes did not change. It is not clear whether the substance actually had reached the bone marrow. In a further assay (according to OECD TG 474), male NMRI mice (5/group) received by gavage in DMSO 0, 500, 1000 or 2000 mg BPS/kg bw/day once. Slight toxic effects were mentioned, but again no induction of micronuclei could be observed (ECHA Dissemination 2020).

Within the scope of the evaluation of the REACH registration dossier a comet assay (according to OECD TG 489) with oral administration of BPS in rats has been requested, because of the positive result of the *in vitro* assay on chromosomal aberrations. Taking into account the available (negative) findings regarding the induction of micronuclei in the bone marrow of mice, it was stated that the comet assay may be omitted in case the requested toxicokinetic study in rats shows without doubt that the parent compound will reach the bone marrow in mice (ECHA 2016). Since

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 103

the requested TK study showed evidence of bone marrow exposure at all BPS doses, we may assume that the comet assay will not be requested within REACH regulation.

3.2.5 Carcinogenicity

No data are available regarding the carcinogenicity of BPS in humans or animals. For BPA, carcinogenic potential was assessed by EFSA.

According to the EFSA CEF Panel (EFSA 2015) the very few epidemiological studies do not allow to draw conclusions regarding carcinogenic effects of BPA in humans. BPA was not carcinogenic in two NTP guideline carcinogenicity oral studies in rats and mice nor in animals exposed during their perinatal phase or as adults in more recent studies. Previous observations of BPA effects on cell proliferation and differentiation in the mammary gland and other tissues are supported by more recent studies. However, the proliferative changes observed in, among others, non-human primates are not sufficient to suggest a link to the development of neoplasia in later phases of life. The Panel concluded on a likelihood level of “unlikely to – as likely as not” for carcinogenic effects of BPA. With regard to the proliferative responses and the possible role of BPA in enhanced sensitivity to mammary gland carcinogens, the CEF panel concluded that these might be relevant for humans.

3.2.6 Toxicity to reproduction

3.2.6.1 Data in humans

Three studies evaluated the impact of BPS on fetal growth (Ferguson et al., 2018⁵; Mustieles et al., 2018⁶; Wan et al., 2018⁷). In one study, maternal prenatal urinary BPS concentrations were consistently, but not significantly, associated with various markers of fetal growth such as reduced abdominal circumferences, femur length and the combined determination of estimated fetal weight and birth weight in repeated measures models, with the latter reaching statistical significance (Ferguson et al., 2018). The other two studies did not report associations between maternal urinary BPS concentrations and birth weight, birth length, or head circumference (Mustieles et al., 2018; Wan et al., 2018).

Also, the impact of BPA analogues on other pregnancy related health outcomes has been examined. Wan et al., 2018 for example reported that urinary BPS levels were correlated with increased gestational age and increased risk of late term birth for girls (Wan et al., 2018), whereas Aung et al. (2019)⁸ reported urinary BPS concentrations around 35 weeks of pregnancy to be associated with preterm birth. Philips et al., 2018 evaluated the impact of BPA analogues on fecundability in 877 participants of the population-based Generation R pregnancy cohort (EU cohort; Philips et al., 2018 a/b)⁹. They reported no association of urinary bisphenol analogues including BPS with fecundability, but that total bisphenols (including 4,4-BPF, BPS, BPB, BPP,

⁵ The LIFECODES birth cohort is an ongoing prospective study begun in 2006 at Brigham and Women's Hospital (BWH) in Boston, Massachusetts.

⁶ The Environment and Reproductive Health (EARTH) Study is an ongoing prospective preconception cohort of couples recruited from the Massachusetts General Hospital (MGH) Fertility Center.

⁷ The population in the present study was selected from pregnant women participating in the Healthy Baby Cohort (HBC), China, focusing on environmental exposures and mother-infant health.

⁸ The LIFECODES birth cohort is an ongoing prospective birth cohort conducted at Brigham and Women's Hospital in Boston, Massachusetts, USA. Between October 2006 and September 2008, 1648 women ages 18–50 delivered as part of the cohort. Pregnant women who planned to deliver at Brigham and Women's Hospital were recruited to participate in their first trimester.

⁹ The current study was embedded in the Generation R Study, a population-based prospective cohort study from early pregnancy onward that was approved by the Medical Ethical Committee of the Erasmus Medical Centre in Rotterdam

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 104

BPAF, BPAP, or BPZ) were associated with a longer time to pregnancy in women with lack of folic acid supplement preconceptionally (Philips et al., 2018 a/b).

Further studies are needed to replicate these findings and investigate potential mechanisms before using human data to derive HBM-GV for BPS.

3.2.6.2 Animal data

3.2.6.2.1 OECD guidelines studies:

A developmental toxicity study according to OECD TG 414 in pregnant Wistar rats (25/group) gavaged with 0, 30, 100 or 300 mg BPS/kg bw/day on GD 6-19 did not reveal any significant reproductive, developmental or teratogenic effects (ECHA, CLP 2019 quoted as Anonymous 19, 2014). Salivation after gavaging and maternal systemic toxicity during the course of the study (reduced food uptake and weight gain) were observed at the highest dose (ECHA Dissemination 2020). For dams, no test substance-related changes were observed for the gravid uterus weight (59.1, 59.6, 58.7 and 55.8 g respectively at 0, 30, 100 and 300 mg/kg bw/day), neither for the necropsy observation nor for the reproduction parameters (see Table III.6).

Table III.6: Reproductive data

Dose level (mg/kg bw/day)	0	30	100	300
Number of females aborted	0	0	0	0
Number of dams with viable foetuses	25	25	25	24
Mean number of implantation sites	11.1	11.0	11.1	10.8
Mean pre-implantation loss (%)	3.6	6.1	5.4	5.3
Mean post implantation loss (%)	4.7	3.9	3.9	6.3
Mean early resorption	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.6
Mean late resorption	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0
Mean total resorption	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.7
Nb of dead foetuses	0	0	0	0
Mean live foetuses (females/males)	10.6 (5.2/5.4)	10.6 (5.0/5.6)	10.6 (6.0/4.6)	10.1 (4.8/5.3)

The foetus examination revealed no differences in sex distribution, placental weight and foetal body weight compared to the control group. Skeletal variations were observed at all doses. At 300 mg/kg bw/day, these variations were significant however comprised within the range of the historical control data. No treatment-related external malformations and variations nor soft tissue malformations and variations were observed.

Table III.7: Sex ratio and mean foetal weight (in g)

Dose level (mg/kg bw/day)	0	30	100	300
Sex ratio (in % females/males)	48.9/51.1	47.2/52.8	56.6/43.4	47.3/52.7
Mean placental weight	0.45	0.46	0.45	0.47
Mean weight of all viable foetuses	3.6	3.6	3.4	3.4
Mean weight of male foetuses	3.6	3.7	3.5	3.5
Mean weight of female foetuses	3.5	3.5	3.4	3.3

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 105

Table III.8: Skeletal variations data

Dose level (mg/kg bw/day)	0	30	100	300	Historical control data mean % (range)
Nb of litter	25	25	25	24	/
Nb of fetuses	137	137	140	127	/
Total skeletal variations					
Foetal incidence : nb (%)	136 (99)	135 (99)	139 (99)	127 (100)	/
Litter incidence : nb (%)	25 (100)	25 (100)	25 (100)	24 (100)	/
Mean affected fetuses/litter	99.2	98.3	98.7	100.0	/
Incidence of significant increased foetal skeletal variations (mean % of affected foetus/litter)					
Incomplete ossification of supraoccipital (unchanged cartilage)	34.1	35.2	37.6	45.2*	43.5 (10.3 – 64.3)
Dumbbell ossification of thoracic centrum (unchanged cartilage)	0.7	3.0	0.0	5.6**	6.9 (0.0 – 14.5)
Unossified sternebra (unchanged cartilage)	1.5	5.0	4.6	11.0**	8.2 (2.6 – 20.7)
Incomplete ossification of pubis (cartilage present)	0.0	0.8	2.0*	1.7	0.3 (0.0 – 2.4)
Incomplete ossification of ischium (cartilage present)	0.0	0.0	2.0*	1.7	0.2 (0.0 – 0.8)

* : p<0.05 ; ** : p<0.01

No N(L)OAEL derivation was conducted for any of the reported studies in the ECHA CLP report, 2019 (study quoted as Anonymous 19, 2014). In the registered dossier, the NOAEL for maternal toxicity is stated at 100 mg/kg bw/day and the NOAEL for prenatal developmental toxicity at 300 mg/kg bw/day (ECHA Dessimation, 2020).

A study following OECD TG 421 (Reproduction/Developmental Toxicity Screening Test) was conducted with Sprague-Dawley rats (JECDB 2001; OECD SIDS 2013; ECHA Dissemination 2020) The animals (12 males (m) + 12 females (f)/group) were gavaged with 0, 10, 60 or 300 mg/kg bw/day of BPS in 0.5% aqueous sodium carboxymethylcellulose solution with 0.1% Tween 80, starting in males 14 day prior to mating for 45 day and in females 14 day prior to mating until the 3rd day of lactation. In the high dose group, reduced food uptake and decreased weight gain and centrilobular hepatocellular hypertrophy were observed in males and females and increased liver and kidney weight in males. At 60 and 300 mg/kg bw/day a dilatation of the caecum was observed in both sexes, accompanied by a diffuse hyperplasia of the mucosal epithelium and, in males at the highest dose, with focal single cell necrosis. Exposure to 10 mg/kg bw/day resulted in no substance-related effects in parental animals compared to controls. Also, copulation index, gestation index, number of corporae luteae, gestation time, parturition and lactation were not affected. However, the mean duration of the oestrus cycle was prolonged and the implantation index reduced at the highest dose, both effects were statistically significantly altered compared to controls. Furthermore, the fertility index was lowered at the highest dose (58.3%; 7/12 animals) compared to control (91.7%; 11/12 animals), and despite lacking statistical significance we considered this effect as an adverse substance-related effect.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 106

Lower mean total number of offspring, mean number of live offspring at birth, and the number of live offspring on lactation day 4 were noted at the highest dose (300 mg/kg bw/day), probably due to the reduced implantation index. Sex ratio, anogenital distance, general condition and necropsy evaluations in pups showed no substance-related effects. The NOAEL for reproductive and developmental toxicity is considered to be 60 mg/kg bw/day based on prolongation of estrous cycle and diestrus period, decreased **fertility index** and **decreased implantation index** (OECD SIDS, 2013 and ECHA Dissemination, 2020). Based on the effects on the caecum in parental animals, the NOAEL for repeated dose toxicity is considered to be 10 mg/kg bw/day for both sexes (OECD SIDS 2013 ECHA Dissemination, 2020).

Following from a substance evaluation decision within the scope of REACH in which an extended one-generation reproductive toxicity (EOGRT) study with rats according to OECD TG 443 was requested (ECHA 2016), the results of this EOGRT study, including cohort 2A/2B and cohort 3 for developmental neuro- and immunotoxicity evaluations and with extension of cohort 1B to produce the F2 generation were submitted to ECHA in 2019.

Results of the range-finding study (similar to a combined repeated dose toxicity study with the reproduction/developmental toxicity screening test - OECD TG 422) as described in the CLH proposal (Anonymous 14, 2017 in ECHA CLP 2019) are reported below.

Sprague-Dawley rats (10 males + 10 females/dose) were gavaged with BPS at 0, 30, 100 or 300 mg/kg bw/day in carboxymethylcellulose solution. Treatment started six weeks prior to mating and was continued during the two-weeks mating period, gestation and lactation (in females) or for four weeks after the mating period (males). Additionally, a subgroup of the F1 generation was exposed for one week after weaning. Dose dependent macroscopically and histologically detectable organ changes were noted in F0 males in caecum, kidney, and liver. Furthermore, a diffuse atrophy of the mammary gland occurred at the highest dose. In females, organ-specific effects were less pronounced. Lymphoid infiltrations in kidneys and liver, mineralisation of the kidney and prolonged oestrus cycle were noted at the highest dose in F0 females (see Table III.10 and Table III.11). Compared to controls, all pregnant females (n=8) at this dose had a significantly reduced number of implantations (mean 10.4 versus control: 15.8) and significantly increased post implantation losses (34.6% versus control: 3.6%). 2 of 8 pregnant dams had a complete intrauterine loss of litter, thus significantly reducing the average litter size at this dose (10.3) compared to control (15.0). Postnatal development of pups was normal. F0 males had a significantly increased kidney weight at mid and high dose.

Based on the increased kidney weight in F0 males from 100 mg/kg bw/day observed in this range-finding study, the HBM4EU – Task 5.2 team derives a NOAEL of 30 mg/kg bw/day for systemic effects and of 100 mg/kg bw/day for developmental and reproductive toxicity (effects: reduced number of implantations, increased post-implantation losses, decrease in total number of pups delivered, decrease in mean number of pups delivered at 300 mg/kg bw/day). Based on this test, the following doses were chosen for the main study: 0, 20, 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 107

Table III.9: Organ weight data in F0 - parental animals (in g)

Dose level (in mg/kg bw/day)	Males				Females			
	0	30	100	300	0	30	100	300
Final Body Weight	548.6	530.2	546.3	497.5*	304.5	301.8	292.6	286.6
Adrenals	0.014	0.014	0.014	0.015	0.027	0.029	0.03	0.03
Kidneys	0.662	0.692	0.748**	1.013**	0.722	0.731	0.762	0.752
Liver	2.375	2.378	2.519	2.668**	2.846	2.938	3.297 ^A	2.927
Prostate	0.302	0.303	0.278	0.297	-	-	-	-
Sem. ves.	0.357	0.366	0.336	0.348	-	-	-	-
Testes	0.685	0.663	0.663	0.734	-	-	-	-
Ovaries	-	-	-	-	0.035	0.035	0.037	0.034
Uterus	-	-	-	-	0.197	0.224	0.224	0.307 ^B

* : p<0.05 ; ** : p<0.01

^A : S.d : 0.154, 0.395, 0.677 and 0.189, respectively at 0, 30, 100 and 300 mg/kg bw/day

^B : S.d : 0.026, 0.088, 0.099 and 0.152, respectively at 0, 30, 100 and 300 mg/kg bw/day

Table III.10: Microscopic data in F0 - parental animals

Dose level (in mg/kg bw/day)		Males				Females			
		0	30	100	300	0	30	100	300
Caecum	Dilatation	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0
	Thickening of wall	0	0	5	9	0	0	0	0
	Increased apoptosis	0	0	3	9	0	0	0	0
Kidneys	Degeneration/regeneration	0	0	6	10	0	0	0	0
	Mineralization	0	0	2	2	1	0	0	4
	Tubular distension	0	0	5	10	0	0	0	0
Liver	Lymphoid infiltration	10	1	2	10	10	0	0	10
	Multifocal necrosis	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
Mammary gland	Diffuse atrophy	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 108

Table III.11: Reproductive data

Dose level (in mg/kg bw/day)	0	30	100	300
Mean duration of oestrus cycle (d)	4.02	3.97	4.01	5.16**
Fertility index (%)	100	90	100	60
Mean number of implantation sites	15.8	15.0	15.5	10.4**
Females without implantation sites	0	0	0	2
% of post-implantation loss	3.6	5.2	6.5	34.6*
Mean duration of gestation (d)	22	22.1	22	22
Total number of pups delivered	152	127	145	65
Number of stillborn	2	1	3	3
Mean number of pups delivered	15.2	14.1	14.5	10.8**
Mean perinatal loss (%)	1.3	0.6	2	5.3

* $p < 0.05$; ** : $p < 0.01$

As described in the CLH proposal (ECHA CLP, 2019), the following extended one-generation reproductive toxicity study (Anonymous 13, 2019) was performed according to OECD TG 443: groups of male and female rats were given BPS at 0, 20, 60 or 180 mg/kg bw/day by gavage in 0.5% carboxy-methylcellulose (CMC) suspension in drinking water.

For the F0 parental generation, at minimum 10 weeks after the beginning of exposure, 24 males and 24 females from the same dose group were mated. F0 males were sacrificed shortly before weaning of the F1 pups, F0 females were sacrificed after weaning of the F1 pups. Before weaning on postnatal day (PND) 21, 74 F1 animals/sex/group were randomly selected and, after weaning, placed into cohorts:

- Cohort 1A was composed of 20 males and 20 females per dose group and animals were sacrificed at approximately 13 weeks of age.
- Cohort 1B was composed of 24 males and 24 females per dose group and was used to produce F2 pups. As for the F0 parental generation, at minimum 10 weeks after selection of the F1 parental animals, males and females were mated. F1 males were sacrificed shortly before weaning of F2 offspring, F1 females shortly after F2 weaning.
- Cohort 2A (neurotoxicity) was composed of 10 males and 10 females per dose group and animals were sacrificed at approximately 11 weeks of age.
- Cohort 2B (neurotoxicity) was composed of 10 males and 10 females per dose group and animals were sacrificed at approximately 3 weeks of age.
- Cohort 3 (immunotoxicity) was composed of 10 males and 10 females per dose group and animals were sacrificed at approximately 8-9 weeks of age.
- F1 pups which were not chosen for cohorts or for blood sampling on PND 4 and 22, were sacrificed after weaning.

F0 parental and F1 pups (before weaning)

Regarding the F0 parental generation, 1 female of the low dose (20 mg/kg) group was sacrificed on study day 63 due to poor general condition. Thirteen males and 6 females exposed to 180 mg/kg bw/day exhibited transient salivation during the first weeks of exposure. However, nursing behaviour was not affected during gestation and lactation periods. Food consumption of

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 109

the high-dose F0 females was statistically significantly increased during major parts of the pre-mating period and during GD 14 - 20 (up to 36% and 8%, respectively). Food consumption of the mid-dose F0 females was statistically significantly increased during pre-mating days 0 - 7, 28 - 35 and during GD 14 - 20 (up to 9%, 14% and 6%, respectively). A significant higher mean body weight value was only observed in females of the mid dose (60 mg/kg) group at D 7 and 14 of the pre-mating period (pre-mating D 7: 141.3, 144.8, 148.3* and 145.2 g respectively at 0, 20, 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day; pre-mating D 14: 162.8, 169.9, 172.4* and 169.6 g respectively at 0, 20, 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day).

Male reproduction parameters revealed a significant lower percentage of sperm motility (88, 84*, 85* and 86* % respectively at 0, 20, 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day). Other parameters were not affected (total spermatids/gram testis, total sperms/gram cauda epididymis, % of abnormal sperms, male mating index and male fertility index).

Regarding female reproduction parameters, the mean oestrus cycle duration was significantly increased at the highest dose (see Table III.12). At 20 mg/kg bw/day, 1 female exhibited a mean oestrus length of 5.3 days and one other female had a mean cycle length of 4.0 days; however, this last female showed an oestrus cycle with a dioestrus period of 9 days. Two females exposed to 180 mg/kg bw/day exhibited a mean cycle length of 4.7 and 5.0 days. This last one had one cycle with a dioestrus period of 5 days. Fertility index (96, 91, 100 and 96 % respectively at 0, 20, 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day) and duration of gestation (22.0 days in all groups) were not significantly affected. However, a decreasing trend in the mean number of implantation sites was noted (15.3, 14.8, 14.9 and 14.3 respectively at 0, 20, 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day) (see Table III.13). The mean number of post-implantation losses and the mean percentage of post implantation losses were significantly higher in the mid- and high dose groups (see Table III.14). The average litter size was dose-dependently reduced (14.9, 14.0, 13.5 and 12.7 pups/dam respectively at 0, 20, 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day).

Table III.12: Oestrus cycle data in F0

Dose level (in mg/kg bw/day)	0	20	60	180
Mean of days from oestrus to oestrus	3.9	3.9	3.9	4.1*
Mean number of days in stage : prooestrus ^A	4.7	3.5	3.8	2.2
Mean number of days in stage : oestrus ^A	5.1	5.1	5.0	5.2
Mean number of days in stage : metoestrus ^A	5.8	6.0	5.8	5.9
Mean number of days in stage : dioestrus ^A	6.3	7.4	7.7	9.0

* : p<0.05

^A : Oestrus cycle data was generated during the last 3 weeks prior to mating. These mean were calculated by the dossier submitter

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 110

Table III.13: Fertility data in females in F0 and in Cohort 1B¹⁰

Dose level (in mg/kg bw/day)	F0				Cohort 1B			
	0	20	60	180	0	20	60	180
Fertility index (in %)	96	91	100	96	100	100	96	96
Duration of gestation (d)	22	22	22	22	22	21.9	22.0	22.0
Mean number of implantation sites	15.3	14.8	14.9	14.3	15.2	14.6	15.4	13.7

Table III.14: Post implantation data in F0

Dose level (in mg/kg bw/day)	0	20	60	180
Mean number of post-implantation losses	0.5	0.8	1.3*	1.5**
Mean % of post-implantation losses	3.1	5.9	9.4*	10.5**

* : p<0.05 ; ** : p<0.01

At necropsy, enlarged caecum and enlarged kidneys were observed in males of the highest dose (respectively in 3 males and in 6 males). Absolute and relative adrenal gland's, kidney's and thymus' weights were significantly modified in males and relative liver weight was significantly higher in females.

Table III.15: Modified organ weights and microscopic findings

		Males				Females			
		0	20	60	180	0	20	60	180
Dose level (in mg/kg bw/day)		0	20	60	180	0	20	60	180
Final body weight in g		521.575	514.408	521.35	507.229	272.125	278.826	275.429	273.408
Adrenal glands	Abs (mg)	54.0	55.958	58.75*	60.625*	80.208	70.391	77.208	71.625
	Rel	0.01	0.011	0.011*	0.012**	0.029	0.025	0.028	0.026
Kidneys	Abs (g)	3.543	3.391	3.673	4.124**	2.083	2.135	2.137	2.148
	Rel	0.68	0.663	0.705	0.817**	0.767	0.768	0.776	0.787
	Incidence (Inc.) of medullar mineralization	0	0	1	21	14	2	1	15
	Inc. of nuclear crowding	0	0	0	22	0	0	0	0
	Inc. of tubular dilatation	0	0	0	13	0	0	0	0
Liver	Abs (g)	12.572	13.298	13.003	12.46	8.08	8.259	8.348	8.695
	Rel	2.413	2.575	2.491	2.455	2.968	2.964	3.029	3.181**
Thymus	Abs (mg)	250.167	283.375	283.292*	233.708	239.167	224.391	233.625	218.875
	Rel	0.048	0.056	0.054*	0.046	0.088	0.081	0.085	0.08

* : p<0.05 ** : p<0.01

Regarding offspring examination, due to the higher resorptions, the mean number of F1 pups per dam was lower at the mid and high doses and was dose-related (14.9, 14.0, 13.5, 12.7

¹⁰ Quoted from EFSA, 2020 p17-18.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 111

respectively at 0, 20, 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day). Furthermore, the number of liveborn pups was significantly reduced at the highest dose (340, 289, 322 and 285* pups respectively at 0, 20, 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day) and the number of stillborn pups was also significantly increased at the highest dose (2, 5, 3 and 8* pups respectively at 0, 20, 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day). Moreover, the mean pup body weight was significantly higher at the mid- and high dose levels (see Table III.16). Sex ratio, clinical observations, viability index, anogenital distance, vaginal opening, preputial separation and presence of areolas/nipples were not modified by exposure to the test substance (no more information is given in ECHA CLP, 2019 and in EFSA, 2020).

Table III.16: Pup body weight data (in g)

Dose level (in mg/kg bw/day)		0	20	60	180
PND 1	Males	7.1	7.4	7.7*	7.7 ^A
	Females	6.7	7.0	7.2*	7.3*
	M+F	6.9	7.2	7.5*	7.5*
PND 4 (post-culling)	Males	10.5	10.9	11.5*	11.4*
	Females	9.9	10.3	10.9*	10.9*
	M+F	10.2	10.6	11.2*	11.2*
PND 21	Males	54.0	56.8	57.4*	55.7
	Females	52.0	54.3	54.8*	53.7
	M+F	53.0	55.5	56.0*	54.7

* : p<0.05

A : S.d : 0.52, 0.76, 0.74 and 0.76

Cohort 1A:

One female of the highest dose was found dead on the first day after weaning (study day 0). Necropsy revealed a slight fibrinous inflammation in the lung, focal hyperplasia in the mammary gland and an atrophic uterus. Twelve males and 14 females of the highest dose group exhibited transient salivation immediately after dosing. Body weight was significantly higher in females exposed to 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day at D 14 and 28.

Table III.17: Body weight data (in g), in F1, Cohort 1A

Dose level (in mg/kg bw/day)	Males				Females			
	0	20	60	180	0	20	60	180
D 0	86.8	86.8	85.5	85.9	77.5	78.4	79.9	78.2
D 14	208.0	203.0	204.9	203.7	149.0	153.4	159.6*	159.6*
D 21	266.4	262.7	263.9	254.0	173.9	176.1	184.2	183.2
D 28	326.7	322.0	323.5	315.5	193.5	196.0	207.3*	207.1*
D 42	408.4	404.1	408.4	394.1	226.9	228.4	237.6	241.0
D 63	488.3	490.6	472.9	459.2	264.1	256.3	265.1	277.0

* : p<0.05

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 112

Regarding reproduction parameters, sperm was examined and did not show any modification. In females, during the 2 weeks of observation, oestrus cycle was of 4.1 days in all groups, but showed prolonged dioestrus stage, as in the other cohorts observed.

Table III.18: Oestrus cycle data, F1, Cohort 1A

Dose level (in mg/kg bw/day)	0	20	60	180
Mean of days from oestrus to oestrus	4.1	4.1	4.1	4.1
Mean number of days in stage : prooestrus ^A	2.2	2.0	2.2	1.3
Mean number of days in stage : oestrus ^A	3.5	3.6	3.5	3.2
Mean number of days in stage : metoestrus ^A	3.8	3.9	3.6	4.1
Mean number of days in stage : dioestrus ^A	4.5	4.6	4.8	5.4

* : p<0.05

^A : Oestrus cycle data was generated during the last 3 weeks prior to mating. These mean values were calculated by the dossier submitter

At the end of the exposure period (approximately 90 days), animals of the 1A cohort were sacrificed and necropsied. No macroscopic dose related findings were observed. Effects on organ weight were noted mainly at the top dose and in males only (see Table III.19). As in the F0 parental generation, histopathological changes were observed in kidneys (medullar mineralisation, nuclear crowding and tubular dilatation). Moreover, an increased incidence in atrophy of mammary gland was observed at the highest dose (in 1, 0, 2 and 7 males at 0, 20, 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day respectively).

Table III.19: Organ weight changes in F1, Cohort 1 A

Dose level (in mg/kg bw/day)	Males				Females				
	0	20	60	180	0	20	60	180	
Final body weight (g)	455.095	449.15	452.61	433.11	242.17	240.59	248.375	251.237	
Adrenal glands	Abs (mg)	65.0	63.2	63.6	70.5	69.05	69.15	71.5	76.737
	Rel	0.014	0.014	0.014	0.016**	0.029	0.029	0.029	0.031
Kidneys	Abs (g)	3.224	3.137	3.335	3.599**	1.797	1.791	1.86	1.91
	Rel	0.712	0.701	0.737	0.832**	0.745	0.745	0.747	0.759
Liver	Abs (g)	13.032	13.349	12.923	11.265**	6.828	6.725	6.906	7.238
	Rel	2.863	2.973	2.858	2.601**	2.814	2.794	2.78	2.88
Spleen	Abs (g)	0.876	0.817	0.801*	0.726**	0.524	0.494	0.529	0.502
	Rel	0.194	0.182	0.177*	0.168**	0.216	0.206	0.213	0.2
Thymus	Abs (mg)	435.7	418.45	435.35	350.85*	354.05	356.75	381.8	355.158
	Rel.	0.095	0.094	0.096	0.08	0.146	0.148	0.154	0.142
Prostate	Abs (g)	1.163	1.118	1.053*	1.046**	-	-	-	-
	Rel	0.257	0.252	0.233	0.242	-	-	-	-

* : p<0.05 ; ** : p < 0.01

Cohort 1B:

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 113

During the study period from weaning to termination, 1 female of the mid dose group was found dead on pre-mating day 3 (D3) (histopathological examination not performed). Clinical observation revealed excessive salivation immediately after exposure to the test substance in 11 males and 9 females during the in-life period and in 10 females during gestation period. Significant body weight changes were observed in both sexes during the in-life period.

Table III.20: Male body weight data (in g) in F1, Cohort 1B

Dose level (in mg/kg bw/day)		0	20	60	180
In-life period	D 0	79.8	80.1	82.3	78.9
	D 14	190.0	179.2	177.6*	173.7**
	D 21	253.9	250.3	260.4	248.4
	D 49	422.2	416.4	437.7	405.5
	D 70	489.2	481.8	502.7	466.8
Parental period	W 0	503.0	498.2	517.7	479.7
	W 5	564.3	559.2	579.7	541.6

* : p<0.05 ; ** : p<0.01

Table III.21: Female body weight data (in g) in F1, Cohort 1B

Dose level (in mg/kg bw/day)		0	20	60	180
In-life period	D 0	73.4	71.5	75.4	73.6
	D 21	170.9	170.7	185.8**	184.7**
	D 49	237.6	233.0	252.7*	258.4**
	D 70	265.6	260.9	280.9	284.4*
	Gestation period	GD 0	276.8	270.5	292.2
	GD 14	345.9	335.1	356.3	355.7
	GD 20	426.0	412.3	436.5	415.7
Lactation period	LD 0	330.6	323.8	343.8	341.3
	LD 10	359.3	350.6	371.4	367.0
	LD 21	342.3	332.9	356.6	353.0

* : p<0.05 ; ** : p<0.01

Regarding reproduction data, the fertility index in the 1B Cohort was not affected (100, 100, 96, 96 % at 0, 20, 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day respectively). However, a slightly reduced number of females with liveborn pups was observed at 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day. The oestrus cycle was also modified at the highest dose level. Furthermore, the mean number of implantation sites tended to decrease at 180 mg/kg bw/day (see Table III.22). These effects were not significant.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 114

Table III.22: Fertility and reproductive data, F1; Cohort 1B

Dose level (in mg/kg bw/day)	0	20	60	180
Female mating index (in %)	100	100	100	100
Mean mating day until day post coitum DPC 0	3.0	2.4	2.5	3.0
Female fertility index (in %)	100	100	96	96
No. of females with liveborn pups	24	24	21	21
No. of females with stillborn pups	6	2	2	6
Mean day from oestrus to oestrus	3.9	4.0	4.0	4.5
Mean number of days in stage: prooestrus ^A	4.7	2.8	2.2	1.3
Mean number of days in stage: oestrus ^A	5.4	5.2	5.4	4.6
Mean number of days in stage: metoestrus ^A	6.0	6.0	6.3	5.9
Mean number of days in stage: dioestrus ^A	6.8	8.4	9.2	11.2
Mean no. of implantation sites	15.2	14.6	15.4	13.7
Tot. number of post-implantation losses	22	18	25	76
Mean number of post-implantation losses	0.9	0.8	1.1	3.3**
% of post-implantation losses	6.4	5.3	11.1	24.6**
Duration of gestation (in days)	22.0	21.9	22.0	22.0
Mean number of pups delivered	14.3	13.8	14.9	11.4**

Statistical examination was not performed regarding the mean day of oestrus's stage; ** : p<0.01

^A : Oestrus cycle data was generated during the last 3 weeks prior to mating. These mean values were calculated by the DS

** : p<0.01

Shortly before weaning, parental animals were sacrificed. Necropsy revealed enlarged kidneys in 1 male of the mid dose and in 10 males of the highest dose. The absolute and/or relative weight of the adrenal glands, kidneys and liver were affected in males, in females only the absolute kidney weight was affected in the top dose group. All other organ weight parameters did not show significant differences. Regarding the histopathological examination, an atrophy of the mammary gland was only noted in 1 male of each group.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 115

Table III.23: Organ weight data

		Males				Females			
Dose level (in mg /kg bw/d)		0	20	60	180	0	20	60	180
Final body weight (g)		536.054	530.863	548.279	510.363	291.842	284.588	304.817*	308.2 ^A
Adrenal glands	Abs (mg)	59.792	62.625	67.708**	64.708	76.708	72.292	77.435	80.083
	Rel	0.011	0.012	0.012*	0.013**	0.026	0.026	0.025	0.026
Kidneys	Abs (g)	3.375	3.43	3.807**	4.252**	2.158	2.115	2.212	2.31*
	Rel	0.632	0.649	0.696**	0.832**	0.741	0.746	0.726	0.752
Liver	Abs (g)	14.813	15.395	14.677	13.272*	9.455	9.326	9.5	9.716
	Rel	2.758	2.902	2.669	2.6*	3.237	3.28	3.119	3.175

* : p<0.05 ; ** : p<0.01

^A: S.d : 24.228, 20.968, 15.011 and 30.56, respectively at 0, 20, 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day

Regarding offspring examination, due to the higher incidence of post-implantation losses, the number of liveborn pups was considerably reduced at the highest dose (336, 330, 311 and 234 pups respectively at 0, 20, 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day). Sex ratio, viability index, pup body weight and anogenital distance were not affected. Necropsy of pups was performed and did not reveal significant changes.

Cohort 2A (neurotoxicity):

No mortality occurred during the study period. As in the other cohorts, excessive salivation was observed immediately after exposure to the test substance in 3 males and 1 female of the highest dose. No body weight change was observed. In this cohort, neurotoxicity was examined. Auditory startle response, home cage observations, open field observations, sensorimotor tests/reflexes, motor activity measurement and learning and memory test did not show treatment-related effects.

Cohort 2B (neurotoxicity):

Necropsy examination did not reveal abnormalities.

Cohort 3 (immunotoxicity):

One female of the lowest dose was found dead on the study day 18. During the exposure period, clinical parameters and body weight were not affected. No indication of toxicity to reproduction was observed in this cohort. With regard to developmental immunotoxicity, at necropsy a significantly lower relative thymus weight was observed at the highest dose in males (0.152 versus 0.187 in control) (microscopic examination not performed). In this cohort, T-cell dependent antibody response (SRBC) was examined and revealed slight changes in the low and mid dose groups in females (13647, 8329, 9598 and 14555 U/ml in females, respectively at 0, 20, 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day and 3737, 3727, 4414 and 3599 U/ml in males, respectively at 0, 20, 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 116

Based on the evaluation of the newly generated scientific data, in particular an EOGRT with developmental neurotoxicity and developmental immunotoxicity cohorts (OECD TG 443) in rats, the EFSA WG concluded:

- The NOAEL for general systemic toxicity is 60 mg/kg bw/day based on increased kidney weight and histopathological changes in both F0 and F1 generations and both sexes at 180 mg/kg bw/day (Lowest Observed Adverse Effect Level, LOAEL).
- The NOAEL for fertility and reproductive performance is 180 mg/kg bw/day both for the F0 and F1 parental rats.
- The NOAEL for developmental toxicity is 20 mg/kg bw/day, based on increased post-implantation losses in the F1 progeny at 60 mg/kg bw per day.
- The NOAEL for developmental neurotoxicity is the high-dose tested of 180 mg/kg bw/day
- The NOAEL for developmental immunotoxicity for the F1 progeny is 20 mg/kg bw/day, based on decreased spleen weight at the mid-dose in males.

Based on the results of these OECD test guidelines: 414, 421 and 443, a classification as Repr. 1B H360FD was proposed by the dossier submitter (ECHA CLP, 2019).

3.2.6.2.2 Academic studies

Although a Klimisch or a ToxRTool approach was not applied for the evaluation of the quality of the studies, the experimental design of the available studies was scrutinised taking into account the size of the experimental group, the experimental conditions of breeding and exposure, the adequacy of the hormonal, histological and statistical analysis. Furthermore, as male reproductive function can be evaluated using two approaches (testicular analysis and sperms analysis) and as each of them can be studied using various parameters, the quality of one study largely depends on the number of measured parameters and on the methods used for their measurements. This expert-based analysis leads to a quotation as poor, acceptable, good (see Table III.24 and Table III.25).

Male reproductive studies

To the best of our knowledge, all the recent academic studies on rodents investigating the effect of BPS on testicular functions using *in vitro* and *in vivo* methods were analysed and reported below. They originated from the following 3 groups: Ullah et al., Shi et al., and Horan et al. As shown in Table III.24, these studies were grouped according to the period of exposure. In each group, they were randomly numbered. All the studies except two (# 8 and 10 in Table III.) compared BPS and BPF with BPA. Lastly, when studies also used other bisphenols (AF, B, or E), the results obtained with these BPA analogs were not reported below.

The following section is focused on BPS *in vivo* effects and the comparison with BPA.

In the study by **Ullah, Razak, et al., 2019** reference # 1 in Table III.24, BPA, BPB, BPF and BPS were administered in drinking water at concentrations of 5, 25, and 50 µg/L from GD 1 to PND 21 to pregnant Sprague-Dawley rats. Assuming an adult rat drinks about 12 mL/100 g body weight/day, it was estimated that the daily BPS intake was about 0.6, 3 and 6 µg/kg bw/day. Observations were performed in 8 F1 males per dose group on PND 16 and PND 80. Cages were made of glass and feed was soy and alfalfa free.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 117

On PND 16, androgen-dependent development (anogenital distance, nipple involution and weights of prostate, epididymis, seminal vesicle, bulbourethral gland and bubocavernosus muscles) remained unaffected by treatment.

On PND 80, anti-oxidative activities were decreased with 50 µg/L with BPA and BPF and with 25 µg and 50 µg/L BPB and BPS. Oxidative activities were increased with the four bisphenols with 50 µg/L. A decrease in plasma testosterone, LH, FSH, and an increase in plasma oestradiol were observed with 50 µg/L BPA, BPB, BPF and BPS. The weights of seminal vesicle and prostate were also reduced, statistically only for the seminal vesicle.

Histological morphometric data of the testis are puzzling because seminiferous epithelium height was increased whereas it should be decreased and because both interstitial and seminiferous spaces decreased. Thus, this morphometric analysis cannot be used for the BPS toxicity assessment. However, clear alterations of spermatogenesis were evidenced by changes in multiple endpoints. Decreases were observed in daily sperm production at 50 µg/L bisphenol, in sperm number within caput/corpus but not within cauda epididymis at 25 µg/L and 50 µg/L, in different cell types within the seminiferous tubule at 50 µg/L. Sperm motility was decreased at 50 µg/L (BPA, BPB) or 25 and 50 µg/L (BPF, BPS).

In conclusion, although the confidence to place in histological spermatogenesis analysis must be moderate, this paper clearly shows that exposure to BPA and BPS during fetal life provokes alterations in the quality and the number of sperms at adulthood.

In the study from **Shi et al., 2018**, reference # 2 in Table III.24, CD-1 mice were orally exposed to BPS, BPE and BPA (0.5, 20, or 50 µg/kg bw/day) *versus* a control group (corn oil), from GD 11 (the presence of vaginal plug was referred as GD 1) to birth. BPS (n=5/group) was administered by placing a pipette tip containing the selected dose in tocopherol-stripped corn oil into the mouth once a day. 2-3 male pups from each litter were euthanised on PND12 or PND 60.

On PND12, BPS and BPE significantly increased TUNEL positive cells in neonatal testis, following disruption of the expression of apoptosis, autophagy, and oxidative stress-related factors. The expression of methyltransferases for DNA methylation and histone modification was also affected by prenatal exposure to the bisphenol analogues in neonatal testis.

Sperm counts at PND 60 were significantly reduced by BPS, BPA at 0.5 and 20 µg/kg bw/day (not with 50 µg/kg bw/day) and by BPE only at the highest tested dose level (50 µg/kg bw/day). BPS only at 0.5 µg/kg bw/day reduced significantly sperm motility whereas this parameter was not changed with BPA. Exposure to BPS, BPA and BPE disrupted the progression of germ cell development, as morphometric analyses exhibited an abnormal distribution of stages of seminiferous cycle in epithelium: the percentage of tubules in stage VII was decreased and that in stage VIII was increased with BPS (at 50 µg/kg bw/day) and BPA at 0.5 and 20 µg/kg bw/day (not at 50 µg/kg bw/day). An increase of tubules in stage VIII was also observed with BPA at 0.5µg/kg bw/day. Furthermore, BPS with a dose of 50 µg/kg bw/day increased the level of serum estradiol-17β in adult males whereas BPA did not change this parameter.

This study considered of good quality clearly shows that exposure to BPS during fetal life provokes alterations in the quality and the number of sperms at adulthood. BPA exerted similar or lower effects.

In the study by **Horan et al., 2018**, reference # 3 in Table III.24, 129S1/SvimJ male mice were orally exposed to 20 µg/kg bw/day BPS, BPA and BPF versus a control group (corn oil), from PND 1-8. BPS (n=5/group) was administered by placing a pipette tip containing the selected dose in tocopherol-stripped corn oil into the mouth once a day.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 118

On PND 42, BPS and all other bisphenols tested significantly increased the number of MLH1 foci in meiotic germ cells evidencing an alteration of meiosis process. Furthermore, this defect was transmitted to F1 and F2 and was erased in F3 and F4.

In conclusion, this study, performed in a laboratory with a recognised-expertise in this field, is focused on one endpoint and used only one dose. However, it clearly shows an alteration of meiosis which is transmitted to the descendants.

In the study from **John et al., 2019**, reference # 4 in Table III.24, Sprague Dawley rat's pups were administered subcutaneously 0, 2 and 200 µg/kg bw/day of BPA and BPS from PND1 to PND 27 (6 animals/group). The vehicle group received olive oil. Histological analysis of testicular tissues was performed. Unfortunately, very few spermatogenic parameters were studied, the microphotographs of the testis are of poor quality, and there was an unexplained and unexpected reduction of heart weight by 60 % from the lowest BPA and BPS dose.

This paper contains too many limitations to be taken into consideration.

In the **Shi et al., 2017** study, referenced # 5 in Table III.24, CD-1 mice were exposed to BPS and BPA (50 or 10,000 µg/kg bw) from birth to PND 60 by subcutaneous injection every three days. Sperm counts in epididymis was significantly reduced by 50 and 10,000 µg BPS and BPA on PND 60 but only by 50 µg BPS on PND 90. Sperm motility in the epididymis was reduced by 50 and 10,000 µg BPS and 10,000 µg BPA on PND 60 and showed normal values on PND 90 in all treatment groups. The progression of germ cell development was also disrupted as morphometric analyses exhibited an abnormal distribution of the stages of spermatogenesis at stages VII and VIII for BPA and BPS at 10,000 µg/kg bw.

Furthermore, plasma oestradiol level was increased with 50 and 10,000 µg/kg bw/3 days BPS and with 10,000 µg/kg bw/3 days BPA on PND 60. No changes in CYP19A1 testicular expression on PND 60 were detected. Plasma testosterone level was increased with 10,000 µg/kg bw/3 days BPS and unchanged with both doses BPA.

In females, postnatal BPA and BPE exposure accelerated the onset of puberty, and increased body weight after parturition. These effects were not observed with BPS. Steroid hormone serum levels (E2 and testosterone) were significantly increased in most treatment groups (BPS, BPA and/or BPE) in females and males.

In conclusion, this study considered of good quality strengthens the deleterious effect of BPS on testicular function and also the fact that BPS exerts a reprotoxicity equal or even higher than that of BPA; however, this study can not be used for the derivation of an HBM guidance value because bisphenols were administered by subcutaneous route. Importantly, it shows that a low dose of BPS (50 µg/kg bw/3days) may be more deleterious than a high dose (10 mg/kg bw/3 days).

In the study by **Ullah, Turi, et al., 2018**, reference # 6 in Table III., Sprague-Dawley male rats were housed in cages made of steel and given free soy and alfalfa food and water in polysulfone bottles. Animals on PND 23 received drinking water containing 0, 5, 25, 50 µg/L BPS or BPF for 48 weeks (7 animals per group). BPA was used as positive control. The effects of BPB were also studied and are not be reported here. Assuming a rat drinks around 12 mL/day/100 g body weight, dosing is calculated as 0, 0.6, 3 and 6 µg bisphenol/kg bw/day. However, it is known that the daily water intake relative to body weight changes as a function of the age; we estimated that the above estimated doses must be doubled when considering young stages and reduced by half for old adults (expert judgment). On this basis, animals received from 1.2 to 0.3, from 6 to 1.5 and from 12 to 3 µg/kg bw/day from PND23 to postnatal week (PNW) 51 for the 3 treated groups respectively.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 119

At the end of the treatment, the relative weights of the testis, the epididymis and the seminal vesicle were decreased with the highest dose of BPS, BPF and BPA (50 µg/L). The reduction in prostate weight did not reach statistical significance.

Testicular concentrations of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and peroxidized lipids were increased at 50 µg/L BPS, BPF and BPA. The activities of antioxidant enzymes were decreased: superoxide dismutase (SOD) at 50 µg/L BPS, BPF and BPA, peroxidase at 25 and 50 µg/L BPS, BPF and BPA, and catalase (CAT) at 25 and 50 µg/L BPA and 50 µg/L BPS.

After treatment with BPS, BPF and BPA, there were dose-related trends towards decreases in plasma testosterone, LH and FSH and an increase in estradiol. As compared with controls, all these changes were statistically significant at 50 µg/L BPS, BPF and BPA.

Sperm production was examined. In the cauda epididymis, the motile sperm percentage were significantly reduced. BPS and BPF appear more potent than BPA, since the reduction was equal to 3, 6 and 7 % after exposure to 50 µg/L BPA, BPF and BPS respectively, and the concentration of 25 µg/L was sufficient to reach statistical significance with BPS and BPF, whereas 50 µg/L were necessary with BPA. The viable sperm percentage was unaffected by BPS, BPF and BPA. Sperm count in the testis showed that the daily sperm production was dose dependently reduced (statistical significance for 50 µg/L BPA, BPF and BPS, with a reduction by 9-10 %). In the same way, sperm number was dose-dependently decreased in the caput epididymis (significant at 25 µg/L BPS and BPA) and in the cauda epididymis (significant at 50 µg/L BPS and BPA).

Testicular histological analyses showed that height of seminal epithelium was dose-dependently decreased (statistically significant at 50 µg/L BPS, BPF and BPA, with a reduction by 13-15 %), without changes in the diameter and the relative area of seminiferous tubules. The numbers of spermatogonia, spermatocytes and spermatids were statistically significantly reduced at 50 µg/L BPS, BPF and BPA.

Histological examination of the caput and cauda regions of epididymis did not exhibit changes in the tubular diameter and the epithelial height.

In conclusion, this study considered of good quality clearly shows that chronic exposure to low doses of BPS may alter the reproductive function in the male adult rat. Both endocrine and exocrine testicular functions were disrupted. BPA exerts similar or a lower negative effect on sperm motility than did BPS. A direct effect on the testis is suggested by the observed increase in oxidative stress but this does not exclude the possibility that BPS and BPA also acted on the gonadotropic hypothalamo-pituitary system.

In the study by **Ullah, Pirzada, Afsar, et al. 2019**, reference # 7 in Table III.24, Sprague-Dawley male rats on PND 70-80 were orally (no further indication given on the mode of administration) given 0, 1, 5, 25, or 50 mg/kg bw/day BPF for 28 days (7 animals per group).

This study could strengthen the findings of other studies. However, only BPF was tested and there is insufficient confidence in these data (imprecisions in the experimental methods, inaccuracy in one figure, number of spermatoc parameters analysed too limited).

The study by **Ullah, Shaheen, et al. 2018**, reference # 8 in Table III.24, reports the effects of BPA and its analogs (BPB, BPS and BPF) on testicular functions using in vitro and in vivo approaches. Sprague-Dawley adult male rats were housed in steel cages. Endocrine disrupting properties of the diet were not characterised in this study.

In the in vitro experiment, rat testes were cut into five equal parts that were processed into slices and deposited in tubes containing the culture medium added with 0, 1, 10 or 100 ng/ml of bisphenols. After 2 hours of incubation, there was a trend of increased concentrations in reactive

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 120

oxygen species (ROS) in the tissue exposed to bisphenols which was statistically significant at 10 ng/ml BPF and 100 ng/ml BPS. Intratesticular testosterone concentration was unaffected by the exposure to bisphenols. As an important limitation of this study it must be noted that survival of the testicular cells was not assessed and cannot be guaranteed by the conditions of culture.

For the *in vivo* approach, Sprague-Dawley adult male rats aged between PND70 to 80 were exposed orally to 0, 5, 25 or 50 mg/kg bw/day bisphenol diluted in saline with a final concentration of ethanol of 0.1 - 0.5% (7 animals per group) for 28 days. With all bisphenols, after treatments with 50 mg/kg bw/day, the testicular concentrations in ROS and peroxidized lipids (LPO) were increased and the activity of the antioxidant enzyme catalase (CAT) was decreased from 5 mg/kg bw/day (BPA, BPS) or 25 mg/kg bw/d (BPF). Plasma and intratesticular testosterone concentrations were significantly reduced at all doses including the lowest tested (5 mg/kg bw/day) with all tested bisphenols. However, this effect was not dose-dependent. Histology of the testis showed that the height of the epithelium of the seminiferous tubules was significantly decreased with all bisphenols at 50 mg/kg bw/day, thus indicating that spermatogenesis was impaired. Only two other spermatogenic parameters were measured (area and diameter of seminiferous tubules) and they were not affected by treatment. Qualitative observations showed reductions in the number of elongated spermatids/sperms in the lumen of the seminiferous tubules and of the epididymis. However, this observation was not quantified, therefore, it is difficult to assess the relevance of this finding.

In conclusion, this study could strengthen findings of the other studies. Here also, BPS exerted similar effects as BPA. However, the quality of this study is poor (number of spermatogenic parameters analysed too limited) and results must be considered with caution.

In the study by **Ullah, Pirzada, Jahan, Ullah, and Khan 2019**, study reference # 9 in Table III.24, Sprague-Dawley rats on PND 70-80, bred in steel cages with soy and alfalfa-free feed and tap water in polysulfone bottles, were given 5, 25, or 50 mg/kg bw/day BPA, BPB, BPF or BPS by gavage for 28 days (7 animals per group). Observations were performed on the 29th day.

The number of studied endpoints is limited. No change in the percentage of motile sperms was observed. Using the comet assay, an increase in DNA damage was observed with the four bisphenols at 50 mg/kg bw/day but not at lower doses. The authors state that daily sperm production was decreased with the four bisphenols at 50 mg/kg bw/day and not at lower doses, but, no data are given.

In conclusion, this paper contains too many limitations to be taken into consideration.

In the study by **Ullah et al., 2016**, reference # 10 in Table III.24, Sprague-Dawley rats on PND 70-80 were orally given 0, 1, 5, 25 or 50 µg/kg bw/day BPS for 28 days (6 animals per group). **Animals were sacrificed at day 29** and observations were performed 29 days after the beginning of the treatment. The testicular anti-oxidative activities (eg. CAT, SOD, and peroxidase) and oxidative activities (eg. ROS and lipid peroxidation) were assessed *in vivo* at day 29. SOD, and peroxidase activities were decreased at 5 µg/kg bw/day and LPO oxidative activities were increased at 25 µg/kg bw/day in the testis. Epithelial height of seminiferous tubules was reduced at 25 µg/kg bw/day without changes in other morphometric testicular parameters studied, including the number of different cell types in the seminiferous tubules. Decreases in testosterone concentrations were observed in the testis at 50 µg/kg bw/day and in the plasma with 1 and 50 µg/kg bw/day without a dose-dependent relationship.

In conclusion, this paper, which is considered to be of acceptable quality, confirms the negative effect of BPS on male reproductive development.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 121

In the study by **Shi, Whorton, et al. 2019b**, reference # 11 in Table III.24, CD-1 mice received 0.5 or 50 µg/kg bw/day BPS, BPE or BPA by placing a pipette tip into the mouth *versus* a control group receiving corn oil, from GD 7 (the presence of vaginal plug = 1) to delivery. F1 mice males delivered from this treated F0 generation were mated with F1 females of the same treatment group but different litters. Male and female F2 mice from the same dose group but which were not siblings or cousins were bred together to generate the F3 generation. F3 males were examined on PND 6 and PND 60.

On PND 60, a decrease in body weight was observed in F3 males at 0.5 and 50 µg/kg bw/day BPS and at 0.5 µg/kg bw/day BPA. Testis weight remained unaffected. Multiple alterations of spermatogenesis were observed in these animals: a decrease by ≈ 50% of sperm number in cauda epididymis at 0.5 and 50 µg/kg bw/day BPA and BPS; a decrease in sperm motility in cauda epididymis at 0.5 and 50 µg/kg bw/day BPA and with 0.5 µg/kg bw/day BPS (not with 50 µg BPS/kg bw/day) and alteration of seminiferous cycle (reduction of stage IX) with 0.5 and 50 µg/kg bw/day BPA and 0.5 µg/kg bw/day BPS (not at 50 µg/kg bw/day BPS). With regard to testicular endocrinology, plasma testosterone was decreased at 50 µg/kg bw/day BPA and BPS, no change in plasma oestradiol was noticed but the expression of Cyp19a1 was increased in the testis at 0.5 and 50 µg/kg bw/day BPS (not with BPA). Lastly, on PND 6, the expressions of genes involved in methylation of DNA were increased at 50 µg/kg bw/day BPA and BPS. The expressions of many genes involved in the methylation of histones were increased from 0.5 µg/kg bw/day BPS whereas BPA had a weaker effect.

In conclusion, this study considered of good quality confirms that 0.5 µg/kg bw/day BPS could be sufficient to induce adverse effects on male reproductive function. It shows that fetal exposure induces epigenetic changes in male and/or female germ cell lineage which are transmitted to the next generations (transgenerational germline inheritance).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 122

Table III.24: Experimental data available on male reproduction function for BPS and comparison with BPA (Summary of 11 studies for identification of the NOAEL/LOAEL).

Number and reference	Species Strain Model	Routes	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported				NOAEL/ LOAEL	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
					Spermatogenesis	Endocrinology	Oxidative stress	Testicular genes expression			
Gestational exposure											
- 1 - Ullah, Razak, et al., 2019	Rat Sprague-Dawley	Drinking water	BPA, BPS, BPF, BPB, 0, 5, 25, 50 µg/L in the drinking water <i>i.e.</i> around 0.6, 3, 6 µg/kg bw/day. from GD1 to GD 21 Observation on PND 16 and PND 80	8	Multiple alterations on PND 80. With the 4 BPs: - ↓ in daily sperm production at 50 µg/L, - ↓ in sperm number in caput/corpus but not in cauda epididymis from 25 µg/L, - changes in seminiferous morphometry from 50 µg/L (3 parameters) or 25 µg/L for area % of seminiferous tubules (but this data is not solid), - ↓ in different cell types in the seminiferous tubules at 50 µg/L, - ↓ of the motility of the sperms at 50 µg/L (BPA, BPB) or from 25 µg/L (BPF, BPS).	No antiandrogenic effect on PND16. With the 4 BPs, on PND 80 ↓ in plasma testosterone, LH, FSH, and ↑ in plasma oestradiol with 50 µg/L.	On PND 80: - ↓ in anti-oxidative activities from 50 µg/L with BPA and BPF and from 25 µg/L with BPB and BPS. - ↑ in oxidative activities at 50 µg/L with the 4 BPs		NOAEL: 5 µg/L ≈ 0.6 µg/kg bw/day LOAEL : 25 µg/L ≈ 3 µg/kg bw/day	Numerous data with variable confidence	Acceptable quality except for testicular histology.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 123

Number and reference	Species Strain Model	Routes	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported				NOAEL/ LOAEL	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
					Spermatogenesis	Endocrinology	Oxidative stress	Testicular genes expression			
- 2 - Shi et al., 2018	Mouse CD-1	Oral (BPs deposited in the mouth)	BPA and BPS , 0, 0.5, 20, 50 µg/kg bw/day from GD 11 to birth Observation on PND 12 or PND 60	10 to 15 from 5 littermates . Results from the same littermate were pooled for statistic analysis.	On PND12 ↑ in the number of TUNEL ⁺ cells / tubule (X 2) with BPS from 0.5 µg/kg bw/day and not with BPA. On PND 60 : - ↓ by ≈ 40% of sperm number in cauda epididymis with 0.5 and 20 µg/kg bw/day BPA and BPS (not with 50 µg/kg bw/day), - ↓ of sperm motility in cauda epididymis only with 0.5 µg/kg bw/day BPS (not with 20 or 50 µg/kg bw/day BPS) and not with BPA. - Alteration of seminiferous cycle (↓ of stage VII and ↑ of stage VIII) with 20 µg/kg bw/day BPA and with 50 µg/kg bw/day BPS. ↑ of stage VIII also observed at 0.5 µg/kg bw/day BPA.	On PND 60, ↑ in plasma oestradiol level and in the expression of <i>Cyp19a1</i> with 50 µg/kg bw/day BPS and not with BPA. No significant changes in plasma testosterone level with BPA and BPS.	On PND 12, from 0.5 µg/kg bw/day with BPA and BPS : - ↓ in the expression of testicular anti-oxidative genes	On PND 12 from 0.5 µg/kg bw/day with BPA and BPS : - ↓ for pro-autophagic genes, - changes for pro-apoptotic genes, - changes for genes involved in methylation of histones. From 20 µg/kg bw/day BPS ↓ for genes involved in methylation of DNA. No changes with BPA.	BPS and BPA LOAEL: 0.5 µg/kg bw/day	Well-conducted study. Numerous data in different fields (cellular, hormonal and molecular)	good quality

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 124

Number and reference	Species Strain Model	Routes	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported				NOAEL/ LOAEL	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
					Spermatogenesis	Endocrinology	Oxidative stress	Testicular genes expression			
Neonatal exposure											
- 3 - Horan et al., 2018. Current Biology 28 : 2948-2954	Mouse male 129S1/Sv imJ	oral	BPA, BPS, BPF , 0, 20 µg/kg bw/day PND1 to PND8 Observation on PND42	9 – 14 male pups from 3-5 litters pending on the tested substances	Alteration of meiosis: ↓ in recombination rate measured by MLH1 foci number, with 20 µg /kg bw/day BPA, BPS and BPF					BPS, BPF and BPA: effect with the unique dose tested 20 µg/kg bw/day	Effect with 20 µg/kg bw/day Good quality
Neonatal and prepubertal exposure											
- 4 - John et al 2019	Rat Sprague-Dawley	s.c.	BPS and BPA 0, 2, 200 µg/kg bw/day PND1 to PND27 Observation on PND27	6	Histological qualitative and quantitative testicular alterations with 2 and 200 µg BPS or BPA.					Inconclusive	Poor quality: - exposure via subcutaneous route, - decrease of heart weight by 60%.
Neonatal, Prepubertal and pubertal and young adulthood exposure											
- 5 - Shi et al., 2017	Mouse CD-1	s.c.	BPA and BPS , 0, 50 and 10,000 µg/kg bw every 3 days from PND 1 to PND 60. Observation on PND 60 and PND 90.	12 to 18 from 5-6 littermates	↓ in sperm number in cauda epididymis with 50 and 10,000 µg/kg/3d BPA and BPS on PND 60, and only with 50 µg/kg bw/3d BPS on PND 90. ↓ in sperm motility in cauda epididymis with 50 and 10,000 µg/kg bw/3d BPS on PND 60, and with 10,000 µg/kg bw/3d BPA. No changes on PND 90. Alteration of seminiferous cycle	↑ in plasma oestradiol level with 50 and 10,000 µg/kg bw/3d BPS and with 10,000 µg/kg bw/3d BPA on PND 60. But no changes in CYP19A1 testicular expression on PND 60.			BPS and BPA LOAEL: 50 µg/kg bw/3d	Study not usable for the identification of the HBM-GV because BPs were given by subcutaneous route	Good quality

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 125

Number and reference	Species Strain Model	Routes	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported				NOAEL/ LOAEL	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
					Spermatogenesis	Endocrinology	Oxidative stress	Testicular genes expression			
					(increase of stage VII) with 10,000 µg/kg bw/3d BPA and BPS on PND 60.						
Pubertal and adult exposure											
- 6 - Ullah, Turi, et al. 2018	Rat Sprague-Dawley	Drinking water	BPA, BPS, BPF, BPB 0, 5, 25, 50 µg/L in the drinking water from PND 23 for 48 weeks. Average of the estimated absorbed doses: around 0, 0.6, 3, 6 µg/kg bw/day	7	<u>With the 4 BPs:</u> - ↓ of testis and epididymis relative weights at 50 µg/L, - ↓ in daily sperm production at 50 µg/L, - alterations of seminiferous morphometry at 50 µg/L: diminution of epithelial height, reduction in the number of spermatogonia, spermatocytes and spermatids, - ↓ in cauda epididymis sperm number at 50 µg/L, - ↓ in caput epididymis sperm number from 25 µg/L. <u>With BPS and BPF,</u> - ↓ in sperm motility in cauda epididymis from 25 µg/L. <u>With BPA and BPB,</u> - ↓ in sperm motility in cauda epididymis at 50 µg/L.	With the 4 BPs: - ↓ in the seminal vesicle weight at 50 µg/L, - ↓ in plasma testosterone, LH, FSH at 50 µg/L, - ↑ in plasma oestradiol at 50 µg/L	With the 4 BPs: - ↓ in anti-oxidative activities from 25 µg/L. - ↑ in oxidative activities from 25 µg/L		NOAEL: 5 µg/L ≈ 0.6 µg/kg bw /day LOAEL: 25 µg/L ≈ 3 µg/kg bw/d ay	It is known that the daily water intake referred to body weight changes as a function of the age -> the above estimated doses must be doubled when considering PND23 stages and reduced by half for old adults. Thus it can be estimated that: - NOAEL is between 0.3 and 1.2 µg/kg bw/day - LOAEL is between 1.5 6 µg/kg bw/d ay	Good quality Valuable data except the uncertainty about the daily consumption of drinking water.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 126

Number and reference	Species Strain Model	Routes	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported				NOAEL/ LOAEL	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
					Spermatogenesis	Endocrinology	Oxidative stress	Testicular genes expression			
Adult exposure											
- 7 - Ullah, Pirzada, Afsar, et al. 2019	Rat Sprague-Dawley	oral	BPF 0, 1, 5, 25, 50, 100 mg/kg bw/day PND 80-90 for 28 days. Observation on the 29 th day.	7	↓ in epithelial height of seminiferous tubules from 50 mg/kg bw/day without changes in the other 3 morphometric testicular parameters studied.	↓ of plasma testosterone, LH and FSH from 25 mg/kg bw/day.	↓ of anti-oxidative activities from 5 mg/kg bw/day. ↑ in oxidative activities from 50 mg/kg bw/d		BPF NOAEL: 25 mg/kg bw/day LOAEL: 50 mg/kg bw/day	Too few sperm parameters analysed. Fig 3 does not fit with the text.	Poor quality
- 8 - Ullah, Shaheen, et al. 2018	Rat Sprague-Dawley	oral	BPA, BPS, BPF, BPB, 0, 5, 25, 50 mg/kg bw/day PND 70/80 for 28 days. Observation on the 29 th day.	7	↓ in epithelial height of seminiferous tubules at 50 mg/kg bw/day without changes in the other two morphometric testicular parameters studied.	↓ in plasma and/or intratesticular testosterone, with 5 mg/kg bw/day with the 4 BPs.	↓ in anti-oxidative activities at 50 mg/kg bw/day (BPA) or from 5 mg/kg bw/day (BPS, BPF, BPB) ↑ in oxidative activities at 50 mg/kg bw/day with the 4 BPs.		NOAEL: 25 mg/kg bw/day LOAEL: 50 mg/kg bw/day	Too few sperm parameters analysed.	Poor quality
- 9 - Ullah, Pirzada, Jahan, Ullah, and Khan 2019	Rat Sprague-Dawley	oral	BPA, BPS, BPF, BPB, 0, 5, 25, 50 mg/kg bw/day	7	↓ in daily sperm production			DNA damage in sperms at 50 mg/kg/day with the 4 BPs		Inconclusive	Poor quality: values of the most important data (daily sperm production)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 127

Number and reference	Species Strain Model	Routes	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported				NOAEL/ LOAEL	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
					Spermatogenesis	Endocrinology	Oxidative stress	Testicular genes expression			
			PND 70/80 for 28 days. Observation on the 29 th day.								are not presented.
- 10 - Ullah et al., 2016	Rat Sprague-Dawley	oral	BPS 0, 1, 5, 25, 50 µg/kg bw/day PND 70/80 for 28 days. Observation on the 29 th day.	6	↓ of epithelial height of seminiferous tubules from 25 µg/kg bw/day without changes in other 4 morphometric testicular parameters studied including number of different cell types in the seminiferous tubules.	↓ in testosterone in the testis with 50 µg/kg bw/day and in the plasma with 1 and 50 mg/kg bw/d.	↓ in anti-oxidative activities from 5 µg/kg bw/d. ↑ in oxidative activities from 25 µg/kg bw/d.		NOAEL: 25 µg/kg bw/day LOAEL: 50 µg/kg bw/day		Acceptable quality.
Multi-generation studies											
- 11 - Shi, Whorton, et al. 2019b	Mouse CD-1	F0: Oral administration (in the mouth) of 0, 0.5, 50 µg/kg bw/day BPA or BPS , from GD7 to birth. F1 males from treated F0 x F1 females from the same treatment group to generate F2. F2 males x F2 females from the same group to generate F3. Observation of F3 males on PND 6 and PND 60.		6	On PND 60, - ↓ in body weight for 0.5 and 50 µg/kg bw/day BPS and for 0.5 µg/kg bw/day BPA without change in the testis weight. - ↓ by ≈ 50% of sperm number in cauda epididymis with 0.5 and 50 µg/kg bw/day BPA and BPS. - ↓ of sperm motility in cauda epididymis with 0.5 and 50 µg/kg/day BPA and with 0.5 µg/kg bw/day BPS (not	On PND 60: - ↓ in plasma testosterone with 50 µg/kg bw/day BPA and BPS. - no change in plasma oestradiol but ↑ in the expression of <i>Cyp19a1</i> in the testis with 0.5 and 50 µg/kg bw/day BPS.		On PND 6 with BPA and BPS: ↑ for genes involved in methylation of histones from 0.5 µg/kg bw/day. ↑ for genes involved in methylation of DNA at 50 µg/kg bw/day.	BPS and BPA LOAEL: 0.5 µg/kg bw/day	Well-conducted study which - confirms that 0.5 µg/kg bw/day BPS is sufficient to induce adverse effect on male reproductive function - shows that fetal exposure induces epigenetic changes in male and/or female germ cell lineage which are transmitted to	Good quality

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 128

Number and reference	Species Strain Model	Routes	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported				NOAEL/ LOAEL	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
					Spermatogenesis	Endocrinology	Oxidative stress	Testicular genes expression			
					with 50 µg/kg bw/day BPS). - Alteration of seminiferous cycle (↓ of stage IX) with 0.5 and 50 µg/kg bw/day BPA and with 0.5 µg/kg bw/day BPS (not with 50 µg/kg bw/day BPS).					the next generations.	

F: female; M: male; BW: body weight; GD: gestation day; PND: postnatal day; ND: no data.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 129

Conclusion on the effects of BPS on male reproductive function

Eleven papers from 3 laboratories studied the effects of BPS on male reproductive function: 7 papers from Ullah et al. numbered 1, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 in Table III.24, 3 papers from Shi et al. numbered 2, 5, 11 in Table III.24 and 1 paper from Horan et al. numbered 3 in Table III.24. The quality is poor or very poor for 4 papers (# 4, 7, 8, 9), medium for 2 papers (# 1, 10), and good for 5 papers ((# 2, 3, 5, 6, 11).

Taken together, all the papers report a coherent picture of the alterations in spermatogenesis after BPS exposure in both rat (Sprague Dawley) and mice (CD-1 and C57BL/6).

Two periods of exposure must be distinguished:

- fetal and/or neonatal: more precisely it is the period during which the germ stem cell population is established; it extends from GD 7 to PND 8 in the mouse and from GD 9 to PND 10 in the rat;
- after neonatal life i.e. after PND 8 in the mouse or PND 10 in the rat. At these development stages, meiosis process is occurring in the testis.

Taken together, a hypothetical schema of the sequential events occurring after exposure to BPS during fetal and/or neonatal life was drawn (see below).

Figure III.4: Hypothetical scheme of the sequential events on spermatogenesis occurring after exposure to BPS during fetal and/or neonatal life

Quantitative and qualitative reduction in spermatogenesis may result from increases in oxidative stress and/or in oestradiol concentration and/or a reduction in testosterone concentration and/or from an unknown pathway.

This scheme was drawn from one study with a good quality ((# 6) and another one with acceptable quality ((# 10). These studies are presented in the scheme in a blue square.

Exposure during fetal and/or neonatal life

Five papers from three different laboratories with good (# 2, 3, 5, 11) or acceptable (# 1) quality, show that fetal and/or neonatal exposure to BPS provokes qualitative and quantitative alterations of spermatogenesis at adulthood (# 1, 2, 3, 5) which is transmitted to future generations ((# 11). Two species were used. Study # 1 used the rat Sprague-Dawley as model whereas studies # 2, 5 and 11 used CD1 mice and study # 3 used C57BL/6 mice. One study (# 4) must be excluded due to toxicity of BPS and the poor quality of the methodology.

All the studies show comparable results except for the effect of BPS on plasma testosterone level as a reduction in this endpoint was observed in one study (# 1) and not in the other two (# 2, 5).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 130

The adverse effect of BPS on spermatogenesis was observed in all the studies: decreases in the daily sperm production (# 1), in the number of sperm in epididymis (# 1, 2, 5) and in sperm motility (# 1, 2, 5). Alteration of testicular histology was described in one study (# 1). Meiosis was affected as shown by changes in the percentages of specific stages VII-VIII throughout the spermatogenic cycle of the seminiferous epithelium (# 2, 5) and by the reduction in homologous recombination rate (# 3). Increase in oxidative stress was always observed when it was researched (# 1, 2). Increase in plasma estradiol level was also observed when it was measured (# 1, 2, 5). Lastly, epigenetic changes are suggested by changes in the expression of testicular genes involved in DNA or histones modification (# 2) and confirmed by transgenerational inheritance of spermatogenic defects (# 11).

Among the five papers considered of good (# 2, 3, 5, 11) or acceptable (# 1) quality, some of them cannot further be considered for HBM-GV derivations mainly due to their mode of administration (eg. subcutaneous) for study (#5) or the administration of a single dose (#3). Thus, studies (#1, 2 and 11) remain as suitable study for a N(L)OAEL derivation.

Shi et al., 2018 (# 2 in Table III.24) reported that BPS 0.5 µg/kg bw/day orally given to mice from GD11 to birth alters all the morphometric parameters of spermatogenesis studied on PND 60, except the testis weight. In this BPS-treated group, sperm number in cauda epididymis was reduced by 34% and the percentage of motile sperms by 15% as compared with controls. These parameters are physiologically important to maintain reproductive capacity. Furthermore, these disturbances are related to alteration of the development of the germ cell line: on PND 12, the number of apoptotic seminiferous cells was doubled and the expressions of numerous genes involved in apoptosis, autophagy, oxidative stress and histone methylation were observed with 0.5 µg/kg bw/day BPS (see Table III.24).

Thus, it can be concluded that 0.5 µg/kg bw/day BPS is sufficient to alter male reproductive function although the dose-response curves are often not monotonic.

This conclusion is strengthened by two studies:

Shi et al (2019a) (# 11 in Table III.24) reported that BPS at 0.5 µg/kg bw/day (the lowest tested dose in this study) orally given to F0 mice from GD7 to birth reduced the sperm number and the percentage of motile sperms in cauda epididymis, and alters the cycle of seminiferous epithelium on PND 60 in F3.

Using the rat as model, Ullah, Razak, et al. 2019 (# 1 in Table III.24), observed a reduction in sperm number and motility at adulthood after addition of 25 µg/L BPS in the drinking water of their mothers during gestation. No effect was observed with addition of 5 µg/L BPS. Assuming an adult rat drinks about 12 mL/100 g bw/day, it can be estimated that the NOAEL is about 0.6 µg/kg bw/day and the LOAEL is about 3 µg/kg bw/day.

Exposure after neonatal life

The data dealing with an exposure to BPS occurring after the onset of stem spermatogonia population are much less solid than those for fetal and/or neonatal periods. Only one paper (# 6 in Table III.24), reports a good analysis but BPS was given via drinking water, which does not allow a precise evaluation of the daily BPS intake. Another one with acceptable quality can be considered (# 10 in Table III.24). Lastly, 3 papers must be excluded because the analyses are insufficient and/or the text contains major errors (# 7, 8, 9 in Table III.24).

In **Ullah, Turi, et al., 2018** (# 6 in Table III.24), Sprague-Dawley rats were chronically exposed to BPS through drinking water (48 weeks) from PND22 onwards. The adverse effect of BPS on the

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 131

quality and number of sperms was clearly observed in this study: decreases in the daily sperm production and in the number and motility of sperm in epididymis. Furthermore, the testes showed a weight reduction and histological alterations. Because the daily water consumption was not measured in this study, the daily BPS intake can only be estimated. Assuming the average of daily water intake is 12 mL/100g body weight in the rat, it results that the NOAEL and LOAEL should be 0.3 and 1.5 µg/kg bw/day respectively. However, it is known that the daily water intake is related to body weight changes as a function of the age: the above estimated doses must be doubled when considering PND 23 stage and reduced by half for old adults. Thus it could be estimated that the NOAEL is between 0.15 and 0.6 µg/kg bw/day and the LOAEL is between 0.75 and 3 µg/kg bw/day. However, because of the uncertainty of these calculations combined with the fact that most of the deleterious effects of BPS were observed with 50 µg/L rather than with 25 µg/L, no clear-cut NOAEL and LOAEL can be derived from this paper. However, it can be noted that the LOAEL is within the same order of magnitude as that identified with fetal and/or neonatal exposure.

In **Ullah et al., 2016** (# 10 in Table III.24), BPS was orally given for four weeks to adult Sprague-Dawley rats. Only 4 spermatogenic parameters were studied and one of them (seminiferous epithelial height) was affected with BPS.

Increase of markers of oxidative stress was observed in both studies. Plasma testosterone concentration was reduced in both studies and plasma estradiol level, which was measured only in study # 6 was increased.

General conclusion

Overall, considering male reproductive function, a LOAEL of 0.5 µg/kg bw/day for BPS is proposed based on Shi, Whorton, et al. 2019b.

- **Female reproductive studies**

Thirteen studies dealing with the effect of BPS on reproductive function were identified. Among those, 3 were not further analysed because of major methodological bias or lack of relevance. Hill et al., 2017 exposed CD-1 mice to 200 µg/kg bw/day of BPS from GD 8 until PND19. The authors investigated the expression of estrogen-responsive genes in both the uterus and ovary and follicular development in pre-pubertal females at PND 22. However, due to major limitations in particular as regards statistical analysis, this study was not further considered. Demacopoulo et al., 2019 administrated BPS (1 µg/kg bw/day; sc) or dehydroepiandrosterone (DHEA, 60 mg/kg bw/day) to immature Wistar female rats for 20 days. An additional group of animals was co-exposed to DHEA and BPS. This study focused on the interaction between DHEA (as a model for polycystic ovary syndrome) and BPS. BPS was delivered at a single dose level and via sub-cutaneous route. Interpretation of the effects are limited because of major bias such as different estrous stages at termination. Thus, this study was not further considered. Lastly, Da Silva et al., 2019 provided a detailed investigation of energy homeostasis along with limited investigation of the reproductive function focused on hormonal concentrations. There is a large uncertainty on hormone concentrations because the method of euthanasia was very likely to modify them (α2 adrenergic agonist and ketamine). This study was thus not included.

The ten remaining studies were conducted by parenteral (ip, sc) or oral (gavage, drinking water, diet) routes.

- **Alteration of oocyte/follicular maturation including abnormalities at the level of meiosis and epigenetic reprogramming have been repeatedly reported in different experimental designs.**

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 132

Seven publications (oral and parenteral routes) from different laboratories report alteration of these key reproductive processes. Some of them suffer from limitations and should not be used for the determination of a guidance value. (Annex III.1, Table III. and Table III.12). Nevertheless, these studies contribute to increase the weight of evidence for an effect of BPS on oocyte maturation and/or folliculogenesis.

Studies with limitations: One study in adult female mice exposed by the parenteral route (intraperitoneal) showed a decrease of oocyte quality and a decrease in early *in vitro* embryo development, tested in a context of *in vitro* fecundation (Nourian et al., 2017) for a BPS dose of 10 µg/kg bw/day. A second study (Ijaz et al., 2019) with 28-day intraperitoneal (ip) exposure of female rats during the pubertal period showed modification of the pattern of different follicle populations with a decreased number of corpus luteum and antral follicles and an increased number of atretic follicles from 0.5 mg/kg bw/day at the lowest. Another study from the same laboratory describes similar alterations of the pattern of different follicles at PND75 following postnatal (PND1 - 10) sc treatment (Ahsan et al., 2018) at 5 mg/kg bw/day.

Studies with no limitations or only minor ones: Oral exposure of mice (20 µg/kg bw/day) during the stage of gestation corresponding to the beginning of the first division of meiosis induced abnormalities at the pachytene stage (Horan et al., 2018).

Two studies issued from a same laboratory (Prokesova et al., 2020; Nevoral et al., 2018) reported altered methylation patterns of the oocytes and also meiosis and oocytes abnormalities (abnormal spindles, abnormal chromatin) following pubertal gavage exposure to doses as low as 0.001 - 0.1 µg/kg bw/day. In one of those studies (Nevoral et al., 2018), this was observed in conjunction with alteration of the pattern of different follicle populations and decreased fertilisation rate. It is noteworthy however that the level of exposure was so low that it is very likely to be indistinguishable from background contamination for the lowest dose levels in particular because animals were housed in polysulfone cages for which BPS is known as a breakdown product (Gorence et al., 2019). Thus, although of quite good quality, those studies were not considered for guidance value determination.

Shi, Sekulovski, et al., 2019 evidenced alterations of early folliculogenesis at PND 4 in mice following maternal exposure from GD 11 until birth. This study includes the evaluation of terminal reproductive endpoints that could be related to the effects on folliculogenesis and are considered as adverse effects. In this study most of the effects of BPS were already observed at 0.5 µg/kg bw/day. In a second study, Shi, Whorton, et al. 2019a, showed that those alterations of early folliculogenesis are no more expressed in the F3 generation (exposure limited to F0).

In summary, all studies investigating follicular patterns and/or oocyte maturation reported an effect of BPS after pubertal exposure: 28 days ip exposure in rats (Ijaz et al., 2019), 28 days drinking water exposure in ICR mice (Nevoral et al., 2018), 7 days gavage in ICR mice (Prokesova et al., 2020) and, after gestational exposure of CD1 mice from GD 11 to birth (Shi, Sekulovski, et al., 2019) or during embryonic period (Horan et al., 2018). In the study from Prokesova, no terminal endpoint in terms of potential adverse effect was evaluated. The study of Nevoral showed an effect of BPS on *in vitro* fertilisation rate. In the study from Shi, Sekulovski, et al., 2019, adverse effects were seen in BPS-treated animals in terms of fertility and estrous cycle. Given the body of converging evidence, it can be considered that BPS alters oocyte maturation and/or folliculogenesis. Given the potential consequences on fertility, the alteration of oocyte maturation or folliculogenesis can be considered as an adverse effect in itself. The observed LOAEL was 0.001 µg/kg bw/day in Nevoral's study on

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 133

pubertal exposure. However, due to uncertainties in the real level of exposure, this was not retained for derivation of HBM-GVs. A LOAEL of 0.5 µg/kg bw/day for gestational exposure (Shi, Sekulovski, et al., 2019) was instead considered. This was the lowest tested dose, so no NOAEL can be derived from this study.

- **Effects on the timing of puberty have been evaluated in six studies (Shi et al., 2017; Ahsan et al., 2018; Ijaz et al., 2019; Kolla et al., 2019; Shi, Sekulovski, et al., 2019; Shi, Whorton, et al., 2019a).**

Negative results: Among those studies, two reported no effects on the timing of puberty (Kolla et al., 2019; Shi et al., 2017). In the study from Kolla et al., 2019, CD-1 mice were treated with BPS (2-200-2000 µg/kg bw/day in diet from GD8 to PND2) followed by an ethinyl estradiol (EE2) challenge at PND21 up to PND31. EE2 did not induce significant changes of the age at vaginal opening with or without BPS prenatal exposure although a non-significant decrease could be observed in vehicle control animal. In the study from Shi et al., 2017, CD-1 mice were treated by subcutaneous injection of 50 µg/kg bw and 10 mg/kg bw every 3 days from PND 0-PND 60 without showing modified age at vaginal opening.

Positive results: One study conducted in female Sprague Dawley rats (Ijaz et al., 2019), showed that pubertal parenteral (ip) exposure for 28 days at high dose (50 mg/kg bw/day) decreases the gonadosomatic index (relative ovary weight) that may be indicative of a delayed puberty¹¹. This study however presents weaknesses that preclude firm conclusions. Another study from the same laboratory (Ahsan et al., 2018) reported delayed vaginal opening in rats treated from PND1 to 10 at a high dose (50 mg/kg bw/day) but not at lower doses (0.5 and 5 mg/kg bw/day).

In the two last studies (Shi, Whorton, et al. 2019a and c) from the same research group, lower age at vaginal opening was observed in CD1 mice exposed *in utero* (dams treated from GD11 to birth) at 0.5 µg/kg bw/day, but a higher age at vaginal opening was evidenced for the dose of 20 µg/kg bw/day. Interestingly, the study from Shi, Whorton, et al., 2019a indicates that this effect of low dose of BPS with an earlier age at vaginal opening can persist to the third generation (F3) in the absence of exposure of F1 to F3 generations. **Overall, results regarding BPS effect on puberty timing are reported in some instances. Results differ according to the dose level and the mode of administration.**

In conclusion, there is strong evidence that developmental exposure to BPS can induce alteration of meiosis, oocyte maturation and folliculogenesis. The identified LOAEL from a good quality study by Shi, Sekulovski, et al., 2019 is 0.5 µg/kg bw/day. No NOAEL could be determined as it was the lowest evaluated dose. It is noteworthy that two other studies would give much lower LOAEL but with high uncertainties regarding the actual exposure as compared to possible background contamination. No study provides information that could directly argue in favor of an endocrine mode of action. Alterations of the affected processes can reflect non-endocrine molecular initiating events such as for example oocyte cytotoxicity and epigenetic mode of action (as suggested in several instances in the reviewed articles). In some instances, other effects are reported (alteration of estrous cycle, effect on puberty, reproductive organ weight...) and other effects that may be related to endocrine disruption but no reliable data regarding endocrine causality is available.

¹¹ Gonado-somatic index (GSI) determines the sexual maturity of animals and is expressed as the proportion of gonadal weight to the body weight.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 134

Table III.25: Experimental data on female reproduction function after exposure by oral route with a single dose

Reference	Species/strain	Period, dose, route of exposure	Monitored parameters		Comment/ effective dose	Study limitation	Potential impact on interpretation	Effect to be considered and effective dose
Horan et al., 2018.	129S1/SvimJ male and C57BL/6 female mice	DPC 14-15 20 µg/kg bw/day oral	MLH1 foci in pachytene stage of meiosis at DPC16.5	↑	20 µg/kg bw/day	Unbalanced groups and number of analysed cell for each group	Mild	Yes but no BMD

Table III.26: Experimental data on female reproduction function after exposure by oral route with at least two dose levels

Reference	Species/ strain	Period, dose, route of exposure	Group size	Monitored parameters		Comment/ effective dose	Study limitation	Potential impact on interpretation	Effect to be considered and effective dose
Prokesova et al., 2020	ICR mice 6-7 weeks old	0.001-0.1-10-100 µg/kg bw/day 7 days gavage	15	<p>On follicles with intact germinal vesicle: <u>During <i>in vitro</i> maturation</u> Proportions of abnormal oocytes recovered Proportion of oocytes with abnormal spindle Proportion of oocyte with abnormal chromatin</p> <p><u>On mature MII oocyte (<i>in vivo</i> maturation)</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tunel assay (MII) • Epigenetic H3K27 methylation in oocyte • Epigenetic in germinal vesicle <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5meC in germinal vesicle 	<p>↑</p> <p>↑</p> <p>-</p> <p>↑</p> <p>-</p> <p>↑</p> <p>-</p>	<p>All doses</p> <p>All doses <u>but 0.1</u></p> <p>All doses <u>but 10</u> no BPS effect vs vehicle but differences between BPS groups Dose 10</p>	<p>Polysulfone cage (new)</p> <p>No statistical analysis</p>	<p>Lowest dose: exposure very likely to be undistinguishable from background contamination</p> <p>Adverse effect??</p> <p>Not for dose but OK for mechanisms</p>	<p>Oocyte maturation 0.001 µg/kg bw/day pubertal exposure</p>

Reference	Species/ strain	Period, dose, route of exposure	Group size	Monitored parameters		Comment/ effective dose	Study limitation	Potential impact on interpretation	Effect to be considered and effective dose
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5meC in oocytes • Microarray (BPS 2 doses only) 	↑ ↑	Effect between BPS doses but not/vehicle BPS 0.1 markers of preimplantation and early embryo development			
Nevoral et al., 2018.	ICR mice 4 weeks old	0.001-0.1-10-100 µg/kg bw/day 28 days Drinking water Phytoestrogen free diet	<u>16</u>	Pubertal exposure: Volume and relative ovary weight /volume of corpus luteum Ovary medulla volume Nb primary follicles Nb preantral follicles Nb antral follicles Antral follicles volume Mean volume of atretic follicles Meiosis abnormalities (oocytes) Oocyte quality Fertilisation rate) Epigenetic (methylation H3K27)	↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↑ ↑ ↓ ↑	0.001 0.1 10 0.001 0.1 10 0.001 non-monotonic vanishes at 100 10 but increased at 100	Polysulfone cage (new):	Lowest dose: exposure very likely to be undistinguishable from background contamination	folliculogenesis: 0.001 µg/kg bw/day for more terminal endpoint: fertilisation capacity: 10 µg/kg bw/day not retained for BMD

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 136

Reference	Species/ strain	Period, dose, route of exposure	Group size	Monitored parameters		Comment/ effective dose	Study limitation	Potential impact on interpretation	Effect to be considered and effective dose
Shi, Sekulovski, et al., 2019	CD1 female mice 7-8 weeks old	0.5-20- 50 µg/kg bw/ day Oral exposure with a pipet GD11 to birth	<u>4-5</u>	<u>F1 vaginal opening</u>	↓ ↑	Earlier vaginal opening at 0.5 µg/kg bw/day Delayed vaginal opening (+2.5 days) at 20 µg/kg bw/day	Polysulfon cages		
				<u>Estrous cycle: irregular cycle</u>	↑	All doses (prolonged estrus diestrus)			Irregular estrous cycle even if not statistically significant at 0.5 µg/kg bw/day
				<u>Mating results with normal male CD- 1 mice at 3 - 6 - 9 months of age:</u>					
				Infertile female	↑	All doses at 9 month			
				Delay to get pregnant					
				Successful mating (or time to vaginal plug)	↓	At all doses at 6 and 9 months	No statistical analysis		
				<u>Pregnancy issues at 3-6-9 months of age:</u>					Effects more pronounced in aging animals (accelerated reproductive senescence)
				Nb of F2 pups/litter	↓	All doses at 9 month with a large amplitude, trend for decreased litter			

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 137

Reference	Species/ strain	Period, dose, route of exposure	Group size	Monitored parameters		Comment/ effective dose	Study limitation	Potential impact on interpretation	Effect to be considered and effective dose
						size at 6 month, but statistically significant only for dose 20 µg/kg bw/day at 9 months.			
				F2 pups bw, Sex ratio of F2 pups..)	-	No effect on bw. No effect			
				<u>Neonatal ovary histology at PND4:</u>					Altered folliculogenesis at 0.5 µg/kg bw/day
				% germ cells in nest	↑	At 0.5 and 20 dose but not at 50 µg/kg bw/day			
				% primordial follicle	-				
				% primary follicle	↓	At all doses with an effect more pronounced at dose 0.5 µg/kg bw/day			
				% secondary follicle	-				
				<u>Hormone at 2 weeks post partum:</u>					
				Estradiol-17β	-		No information on physiological status at 2 weeks post partum		

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 138

Reference	Species/ strain	Period, dose, route of exposure	Group size	Monitored parameters		Comment/ effective dose	Study limitation	Potential impact on interpretation	Effect to be considered and effective dose
				Testosterone	↑	At 9 months, statistically significant at dose 50 µg/kg bw/day only			
				<u>Ovarian gene expression at 2 weeks post partum</u>	↑	Cyp11a1 at 3 months only and at 0.5 µg/kg bw/day dose only.		High: data not considered	
Shi, Whorton, et al. 2019a	CD-1 female mice	0.5 and 50 µg/kg bw/ day Oral exposure with a pipet GD7 to birth F0	<u>4-5 litters / group</u>	On F3 only:					
				<u>Neonatal ovary histology at PND4:</u>	-	No effect on early folliculogenesis (until secondary follicles) in F3 ovaries.			
				Age at Vaginal opening	↓	At both doses.			
				Estrous cycle		Irregular at both doses, no effect on percentage of days in different stages.	No statistical analysis on the percentage of irregular		

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 139

Reference	Species/ strain	Period, dose, route of exposure	Group size	Monitored parameters		Comment/ effective dose	Study limitation	Potential impact on interpretation	Effect to be considered and effective dose
							cycles and stages.		
				At 3, 6 or 9 months of age, female pups were mated with non-exposed males:					
				Successful mating (or time to vaginal plug)	↓	At 6 and 9 months, decrease of successful mating, at 9 months of age more than 50% of all the females without plug at both doses.	No statistical analysis		
				Pregnancy outcomes	↓	Number of F4 pups/litter at 9 months 50 µg/kg bw/day			
				<u>At 2 weeks post partum in F3 female dams:</u>					
				Estradiol-17β (serum)	↑	At 50 µg/kg bw/day only at 6 months.			
				Testosterone (serum)		Not statistically significant.			
				Ovarian steroideogenic enzyme expressions (mRNA)	↑	<i>Cyp11a1</i> at 3 months, at dose	Stage of estrous cycle not specified	high high high	Absence of stat analysis on key parameters.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 140

Reference	Species/ strain	Period, dose, route of exposure	Group size	Monitored parameters		Comment/ effective dose	Study limitation	Potential impact on interpretation	Effect to be considered and effective dose
						0.5 µg/kg bw/day only			Decreased age at vaginal opening and increased age-related infertility 0.5 µg/kg bw/day
					↓	Cyp17a1 at 6 months, at 0.5 and 50 µg/kg bw/day			
Kolla and Vandenberg, 2019.	CD-1 mice	0 – 2 - 200 - 2000 µg/kg bw/day Oral with a pipet GD8 - PND2 with BPS. Then, female offspring was exposed to EE2 from PND21 up to the theoretical period of first estrus (PND31). Examination at PND31	nd	Mammary gland morphology (with whole mount analysis).					
				Expression of PGR in mammary gland with or without EE2	-				
				Expression of ERs in mammary gland without EE2	↑	At 200 µg/kg bw only			
				Expression of ERs in mammary gland with EE2	-				
				Age at vaginal opening without EE2 challenge	-				
				Age at vaginal opening with EE2 challenge	-				
				Anogenital index without EE2 challenge	-				
				Anogenital index with EE2 challenge	-				
				Relative uterine Weight without EE2 challenge	-				
				Relative uterine weight with EE2 challenge	-				

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 141

Reference	Species/ strain	Period, dose, route of exposure	Group size	Monitored parameters		Comment/ effective dose	Study limitation	Potential impact on interpretation	Effect to be considered and effective dose
				Effect of EE2 challenge on all studied parameters	-				
				Effect of BPS without EE2 challenge on all studied parameters	-				

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 142

3.2.7 Studies on other endocrine effects

In a review of studies on health effects including endocrine effects of BPS (and other bisphenols) a total of 16 human studies, 66 *in vivo* and 120 *in vitro* studies are cited (more than one activity was tested in some studies), see Pelch et al., 2019.

3.2.7.1 Data on humans

Metabolism and obesity

An association with obesity was investigated for BPS and 4,4-BPF in five US studies (Jacobson et al., 2019; Kataria et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2017; Liu B. et al., 2019; Zhang Y. et al., 2019) and in a European study (Charisiadis et al., 2018). The results from these studies are conflicting. In an analysis of NHANES 2013–2014, urinary BPS levels were positively associated with general obesity (Zhang Y. et al., 2019) especially in children and teenagers (Jacobson et al., 2019; Liu B. et al., 2019). Interestingly, only urinary BPS concentrations were higher in obese teens in NHANES 2015-2016 (Jacobson et al., 2019) while only urinary 4,4-BPF concentrations were elevated in obese teens in NHANES 2013-2014 (Liu B. et al., 2019). Urinary BPS and 4,4-BPF concentrations were also elevated in obese adults in another study, but the results were not significant after adjustments for lifestyle and socioeconomic factors (Liu et al., 2017). In a very small US cross sectional pilot study of 10–13-year olds, BPS and 4,4-BPF were not associated with body weight (Kataria et al., 2017). In contrast, Charisiadis reported that increased concentrations of BPF in brain material were associated with a decreased risk of obesity in a small autopsy cohort of twelve pairs of obese (body mass index (BMI) >30 kg/m²) and normal-weight individuals (BMI <25 kg/m²). (Charisiadis et al., 2018).

Similarly, five studies investigated the association of BPA analogues with diabetes, fasting blood glucose, or insulin resistance in three Chinese studies (Duan et al., 2018; Song et al., 2019; Zhang W. et al., 2019), in one US study (Kataria et al., 2017) and in one French study (Rancire et al., 2019). In a case-control study, urinary BPS concentrations were reportedly associated with a significantly increased risk of type 2 diabetes, (Duan et al., 2018). In an analysis of D.E.S.I.R. cohort, urinary BPS-glucuronide (BPS-G) concentrations were associated with a higher risk of incident type 2 diabetes but BPS-G were detectable only in 11% of the population (Rancire et al., 2019). Song et al., 2019 reported that serum BPS or BPF were not associated with hyperglycemia in a nested population of elderly patients living near electronic-waste recycling in China. Kataria et al., 2017 did not find associations between urinary BPS or 4,4-BPF concentrations and insulin resistance in a small cross-sectional pilot study of 10–13-year olds. In a cohort of pregnant women from Wuhan (Zhang W. et al., 2019), urinary BPS and 4,4-BPF concentrations were not associated with incident gestational diabetes.

Three studies also investigated the association of BPA analogues with urinary markers of oxidative stress in one US study (Kataria et al., 2017) and in two Chinese studies (Zhang et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2019). Urinary BPS concentrations were associated with markers of oxidative stress in a Chinese population but not in the population residing near the electronic-waste recycling facility (Zhang et al., 2016) nor in the US pilot study of 10–13-year-old children (Kataria et al., 2017).

Thyroid

Aker et al., 2018 evaluated the association of maternal urinary concentrations of BPS with thyroid hormones throughout pregnancy in US pregnant women. BPS concentrations were associated with a statistically significant increase of TSH (with a p value below 0.10), particularly at <15 weeks gestational age (GA), as well as a non-statistically significant decrease in free T4 at <15 weeks GA.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 143

In a population-based prospective study, higher 4,4-BPF concentrations were positively associated with higher free T3 levels at the beginning of pregnancy (< 14 weeks of gestation), while there were no associations between BPS and absolute TSH, free T4 or free T3 concentrations (Derakhshan et al., 2019).

Other health outcomes

Kolatorova et al., 2018 evaluated the simultaneous detection of BPS, 4,4-BPF and other bisphenols and endogenous steroids (eg. corticoids, DHEA and its metabolites, pregnenolone, 17-OH pregnenolone, androgens and progesterone) in maternal (37th week of pregnancy) and cord plasma from European (Czech nationality and middle-European origin) pregnant patients (27 healthy pregnant women). In maternal plasma, BPA was detected in 85.2% of samples but BPS and 4,4-BPF were detected in one sample only. In cord plasma, BPA was present in most samples (75.1% of samples) and on the other hand, BPF was above the lower limit of quantification in only one sample, and BPS was not detected in any sample. No association with maternal bisphenols and cord blood steroids was observed and no differences were found between the cord blood EDCs and steroids in male and female fetuses.

One study aimed to investigate the association of serum concentrations of 4,4-BPF, BPAF, or BPS on bone density and calcium-phosphate metabolism in post-menopausal women, but the plasmatic concentrations of all BPA analogues were below the limit of quantification (LOQ) (Vitku et al., 2018). In the US pilot study of 10–13-year-old children, Kataria et al., 2017 did not find an association between urinary concentrations of 4,4-BPF or BPS on blood pressure or vascular dysfunction.

3.2.7.2 Animal and in vitro data

Although a Klimisch or a ToxRTool approach was not applied for the evaluation of the quality of the studies, the experimental design of the available studies was scrutinised taking into account the size of the experimental group, the relevance of the route of exposure, as well as the adequacy of the hormonal, histological and statistical analysis. The results of this expert-based analysis are quoted in the respective summary tables (see Table III.27 and Table III.28).

In a review of studies on hormonal effects of BPS (and other bisphenols) a total of four in vivo and 18 in vitro studies are cited (more than one activity was tested in some studies). BPS demonstrated endocrine activities in all in vivo studies. Twelve of the in vitro studies indicated estrogenic activity, four studies binding of BPS to the ER. One study each pointed to an androgenic or an anti-androgenic activity. Studies in which both, BPA and BPS, were tested indicated a relative potency of BPS of 0.32 ± 0.28 (mean value \pm SD, range 0.01-0.90) compared to BPA. Further comparisons indicated a similar order of potencies for BPA and BPS with respect to androgenic, anti-androgenic, or anti-estrogenic activity (Rochester and Bolden 2015).

In its report about several bisphenols as alternatives to BPA, the US EPA also concluded that BPS shows estrogenic and anti-androgenic activity and that, based on a comparison of in vitro data, the endocrine potency of BPS seems to be lower than that of BPA (US EPA 2015).

According to a current review of the NTP, BPS showed similar binding to the ER as BPA and revealed antagonistic activity. Furthermore, it was tested whether BPS is able to induce the binding of ER to ERE (estrogen response element). It was demonstrated that BPS showed a marked selectivity to the ER β compared to ER α and that BPS is not able to induce the binding of ER to ERE over a concentration range of 0.001-10 μ M (NTP 2017).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 144

Following a three-day subcutaneous exposure of immature rats with 100 mg BPS/kg bw/d a uterotrophic effect could be observed. In simultaneously conducted *in vitro* assays binding of BPS to the ER could also be demonstrated (Yamasaki, Noda et al., 2004).

Following a single subcutaneous injection of BPS (1, 3 or 9 mg) followed by a dietary supplement containing either 50 µg/kg bw ¹⁴C-BPA or 14.5 ng ³H-E2, BPS treatment elevated ¹⁴C-BPA concentrations in blood serum and certain reproductive organs of both sexes, but reduced ³H-E2 concentrations in blood serum of females. Pollock et al. (2019) hypothesised that BPS would elevate concentrations of BPA by competing for access to metabolic enzymes.

In another study BPA, but not BPS, induced the production of estradiol in an H295R steroidogenesis assay; the formation of free testosterone was inhibited by both BPA and BPS (Goldinger et al., 2015). Further studies using this and other assays indicated that BPS, in contrast to BPA, stimulated formation of progesterone, but not of estrogens. BPS also reduced the formation of cortisol in this study (as did BPA) and of corticosterone (BPA: no effect). BPS stimulated the activity of the ER (estrogen receptor) but showed weaker activity than BPA. As in the studies mentioned above, the activity of the AR (androgen receptor) was reduced, again, BPS was less active than BPA (Rosenmai et al., 2014).

BPS inhibited the maturation of pig oocytes *in vitro* within the tested concentration range of 3 nM to 30 µM in a concentration-dependent manner for a period of 48 h, afterwards, maturation of oocytes continued. In doing so, BPS impaired the spindle apparatus in the concentration range mentioned. Further assays showed that BPS affected the supply of mRNA for ER and aromatase and the expression and distribution of ER α , ER β and aromatase during maturation (Žalmanová, Hošková et al., 2017).

BPS inhibited the basal testosterone secretion of explants from murine foetal testes tissue and in cultures of human foetal testis tissue *in vitro*. The lowest concentration of 10 nmol/l, at which this effect was observed, coincided with the concentration which had been shown as active in previous studies with BPA. 10 nmol/l BPS or BPF were as effective as BPA in mice with respect to an inhibition of the expression of insl 3 (a factor regulating the descent of the testes from the abdomen during foetal development) (Eladak, Grisin et al., 2015).

Endocrine effects (estrogen-like activity, binding to ER) were also observed *in vitro* and *in vivo* in studies with zebra fish or cell cultures from this species. Differences were noted with respect to the selectivity of binding to ER α (BPA: selective) and ER β (BPS somewhat stronger than to ER α). However, BPS only partially induced aromatase and only at the highest concentration (30 µM), thus, it was less effective than BPA (tested at 1-10 µM) (Le Fol, Aït-Aïssa et al., 2017). In a further study, BPS as BPA induced the expression of estrogen sensitive markers (Cyp19a1b) in the developing brain of zebra fish embryos (Cano-Nicolau, Vaillant et al., 2016). However, this gene is not expressed in mammalian brain (Fujiwara, Miyazaki et al., 2018).

According to Zhang et al., 2018, both BPS and BPA showed binding to the thyroid hormone receptors (TR α and TR β) in a fluorescence binding assay *in vitro*, but the potency of BPS was about one order of magnitude lower than that of BPA.

Similar to BPA, BPF and BPS at concentrations of 10 nmol/l and 10 µmol/l affected the expression of several genes in primary cultures of human adipocytes obtained from subcutaneous fat tissue of three female white donors not suffering from diabetes. According to the authors, this was regarded as a possible endocrine disruptive effect (Verbanck, Canouil et al., 2017). Exposure of differentiating human preadipocytes *in vitro* with 25 µM BPS induced an accumulation of lipids and increased the cellular levels of mRNA and proteins which are regarded as adipogenic markers. Simultaneous exposure with an ER-antagonist inhibited the effect of BPS. On the other hand, a

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 145

glucocorticoid receptor antagonist had no such effect. Further *in vitro* studies with cellular assays containing human PPARG-sensitive elements provided evidence that BPS is able to activate PPARG (Boucher, Ahmed et al., 2016). Furthermore *in vitro* studies provide evidence that the transcription profiles of BPS and BPA differ with respect to the induction of adipogenesis of preadipocytes (Boucher, Gagné et al. 2016). A recent *in vitro* study showed that BPA analogues (BPS and BPF) present a greater obesogenic capacity in the 3T3-L1 cell line (Martínez et al., 2020). The results from MTT (metabolic dye [4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl]-2,5-diphenyl tetrazolium) assay, showed a greater toxic effect of BPA at equal and even lower concentrations than its analogues. However, BPS followed by BPF showed a greater neutral lipid storage capacity than BPA, which was reflected in an increase in expression levels of C/EBP α , PPAR γ and FABP4.

The mechanisms involved are not fully characterised: Estrogen and prolactin signaling pathways are proposed, GPER involvement is hypothesised, and epigenetic mechanisms are plausible. Recently published binding studies (Grimaldi et al., 2019) showed reduced affinities (compared to BPA) of BPS (and BPF) for ER α (10X), ER β (8X), no binding to PXR, ERR γ , AR, PR, GR, MR according to their comparative *in vitro* effects on breast carcinoma cell proliferation showing higher activity for BPA than for BPF and BPS (Mesnage et al., 2017). These results suggest multiple and complex effects of bisphenols *in vivo*.

The analysis of further recent academic studies on endocrine disruption is presented in the following sections and experimental data are summarised for each endpoint in Table III.27 and Table III.27 and in Annex III.1, studies are grouped by windows of exposure.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 146

Effect on mammary gland

Table III.27: Experimental data available on mammary gland

Studies are grouped by windows of exposure and then tested species (mouse/rat/other species).

Reference	Species Strain Model	Routes	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported		NOAEL/ LOAEL	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
Gestational exposure									
Anonymous 13, 2019 (Cf. Annex I to the CLH report EC Number: 201-250-5) OECD TG 443 / GLP	Sprague-Dawley rats	gavage	0, 20, 60 and 180 mg/kg bw/day. From 10 weeks after the beginning of exposure, males and females from the same dose group were mated. Shortly before weaning of the F1 pups, the F0 males were sacrificed whereas, the F0 females were sacrificed after weaning of the F1 pups. Before weaning of the F1 pups on PND 21, 74 animals/sex/group were randomly selected and, after weaning, placed into cohorts.	24/sex/dose	An atrophy of the mammary gland was noted in males of the highest dose		LOAEL: 180 mg/kg bw/day NOAEL: 60 mg/kg bw/day estimated by EFSA, 2020.	Toxic effects that may be due to cell alteration (differentiation and apoptosis) as also observed in other organs.	Not enough information to conclude on BPS action

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 147

Reference	Species Strain Model	Routes	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported		NOAEL/ LOAEL	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
Anonymous 14, 2017 (Cf. Annex I to the CLH report EC Number: 201-250-5) OECD TG 422 GLP	Sprague-Dawley rats	gavage	0, 30, 100 and 300 mg/kg bw/day Continued exposure	10/sex/dose	Diffuse atrophy of male mammary gland in males		LOAEL: 300 mg/kg bw/day* NOAEL: 100 mg/kg bw/day*		
Tucker et al., 2018	CD1 mice	Gavage twice a day	0, 50, 500, 5000 µg/kg bw/day GD10-17	At least 10/group	<u>Mammary gland whole mount and histology:</u> Increased number of terminal end buds (TEBs) at PND20, PND 35, 3 months. Lobulo-alveolar hyperplasia, lymphoplasmatic perivascular inflammation and squamous metaplasia in 14-months old mice.	As controls	LOAEL: 50 µg/kg bw/day*	Higher and more significant differences compared to controls with the intermediate dose of 500 µg /kg/d than 50 or 5000	Good study. Comparison with BPA and BPAF effects: BPS has stronger long-term negative effects on mammary gland health than BPA and BPAF.
Perinatal exposure									
Kolla et al., 2018	CD1 mice	Oral exposure with a pipet	0, 2, 200 µg/kg bw/day GD9 - PND20	At least 10/group	<u>Mammary gland whole mount and histology:</u> Increased number of terminal end buds (TEBs) at PND20 and 3 months.		LOAEL: 2 µg /kg bw/day*		Good study. Comparison with 0.01 or 1 µg /kg bw/d EE2

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 148

Reference	Species Strain Model	Routes	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported		NOAEL/ LOAEL	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
Kolla et al., 2019	CD1 mice	Oral exposure (with wafer)	2 or 200 µg/kg bw/day GD 9 up to lactation day 20	n = 10-12	At the puberty, (PND24), dose-dependent decrease in ductal areas in the left mammary gland only (no effect in the right gland), whereas later in life, a dose-dependent increase in ductal area was mainly observed in the right mammary gland (Week 9).		LOAEL: 2 µg /kg bw/day*		
Adult exposure									
Anonymous 15, 2017 (Cf. Annex I to the CLH report EC Number: 201-250-5) corresponding to an OECD TG 407	Sprague Dawley rats		0, 100, 300 and 600 mg/kg bw/day 28 days repeated dose toxicity study	5/sex/dose	Diffuse atrophy of the mammary gland in males		LOAEL: 300 mg/kg bw/day* NOAEL: 100 mg/kg bw/day*		
Anonymous 17, 2014 (cf. Annex I to the CLH report EC Number: 201-250-5 and ECHA Dissemination, 2020) corresponding to an OECD TG 408/ GLP	Wistar rats	gavage	0, 100, 300 and 1000 mg/kg bw/day (in males the highest dose was changed to 600 mg/kg bw/day after 70 days) 90-day repeated dose toxicity study	10/sex/dose	Atrophy multifocal of the mammary gland in ♂ at the mid and high dose		LOAEL: 300 mg/kg bw/day NOAEL: 100 mg/kg bw/day estimated by the registrant (see ECHA Dissemination, 2020).	Toxic effects that may be due to cell alteration (differentiation and apoptosis) as also observed in other organs.	

F: female; M: male; BW: body weight; GD: gestation day; PND:postnatal day; ND: no data; wt: weight

*N(L)OAEL estimated by HBM4EU – Task 5.2 team.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 149

LaPlante et al., 2017 studied BPS low-dose effects on nursing behavior and mice lactating mammary gland development at different periods of lactation (LD2, LD7, LD14 and LD21). The highest BPS dose (200 µg/kg bw/day) leads to a decrease of terminal end bud (TEB) size (LD21) associated with decreased expression of progesterone receptor (PGR) and estrogen receptor 1 (ESR1) (but an increase in ER α -positive cells), consistent with involution of mammary glands, earlier described for other xenoestrogens such as PFOA (White et al., 2007). Another interesting observation was the delayed growth and development of pups born to dams exposed to BPS, suggesting a lower quality and quantity of milk production or a transfer of BPS (or its metabolites) to the milk, significant also at the lower dose of BPS (2 µg/kg bw/day). Interestingly, the time spent nursing is also increased at PND14. The authors concluded that mammary gland involution may be due to estrogenic effects of BPS (through prolactin receptor, PRLR) although mechanisms involved here were not characterised.

This study points out the effects of the lowest dose (2 µg/kg bw/day) of BPS on mammary gland physiology (mammary gland morphology) and on the nursing, suggesting a decrease in the quality and quantity of milk production with consequences on pup development. Thus, the dose of 2 µg/kg bw/day BPS should be considered an active dose on the mouse lactating mammary gland.

Tucker et al., 2018 published comparative effects of BPS, BPAF and BPA on mammary gland development and pathologies.

Exposure of mice to BPS (50, 500 and 5000 µg/kg bw/day) during fetal life (GD 8-17) has no effect on female offspring weight and no statistically significant effect on timing of vaginal opening (marker of puberty) despite a tendency to be slightly delayed in BPS groups.

At PND20, whereas all doses of BPAF induced increasing effects on all parameters measured for mammary gland development, only the middle dose of 500 µg/kg bw/day BPS significantly increased TEB number and length.

However, the most evident effects of fetal exposure to BPS on mammary glands were observed on morphology for the lowest (50 µg/kg bw/day), and the middle (500 µg/kg bw/day) doses at the puberty (PND35), and at PND56 (i.e. the theoretical end of mammary gland branching), but also later in life, through pathological development (inflammation and lobuloalveolar hyperplasia) in 3 and 14-months-old mice with the highest effects for the middle dose (500 µg/kg bw/day). Among mice diagnosed with tumorigenic lesions, 88 % were exposed to BPS, at 500 and 5000 µg/kg bw/day.

Neither hormone levels (E2, PG, T, DHEA) nor steroid receptor expression levels (ER, AR, PGR, GPER) could explain these results (except a decrease in DHEA in old mice). The mechanisms and signaling pathways involved in these effects were not investigated. The authors suggest the involvement of PRL pathway and DHEA reduction. Epigenetic regulations could not be excluded.

In this study, BPA substitutes (BPS and BPAF) displayed more effects on mammary gland than BPA did at the same doses.

In conclusion, a fetal exposure to 50 µg/kg bw/day BPS is sufficient to observe a disrupted mammary gland development and 500 µg/kg bw/day BPS lead to the most important pathological lesions namely lobulo-alveolar hyperplasia and squamous metaplasia in old mice.

Kolla et al., 2018 compared the effects of gestational/ lactational exposure to BPS and EE2 on mammary gland development. They observed a significant increase in TEBs at PND24 for mice exposed to the lowest dose of BPS (2 µg/kg bw/day), but not for mice exposed to EE2 (1 µg/kg

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 150

bw/day). This effect was not detected at PND35 but was observable again at 9 weeks where this lowest dose of BPS was the most active. An EE2-like effect was also detected in adult mammary glands presenting intra-ductal hyperplasia for both doses of BPS. These data suggest that BPS displays a complex mechanism of action different from that of EE2. Thus, it must be underlined that, as in the study of LaPlante, the lowest dose of BPS (2 µg/kg bw/day) is able to disrupt mammary gland development.

Kolla and Vandenberg, 2019 reported the BPS impact on the peripubertal disrupting effect of EE2 on mammary gland development when CD-1 mice were orally exposed to BPS (2, 200 and 2000 µg/kg bw/day) during gestation (GD9 - PND2). The female offspring has been exposed to EE2 from weaning (PND21) up to the theoretical period of first estrus (PND31). This study did not show any significant effect of BPS on mammary gland development (whole mount analyses). Such BPS exposure did not predispose the mammary gland to a possible susceptibility to subsequent pubertal exposure to EE2.

Kolla et al., 2019 reported the effects of perinatal exposures to BPS on the mammary gland development of the male offspring. The specificity and originality of this study was the comparison of mammary glands at the embryonic state (E16), puberty (PND24) and adulthood (Week 9). In a second experiment, the authors investigated the effect of a challenge with EE2, as previously described for females by Kolla and Vandenberg, 2019.

In the first experiment, pregnant CD-1 mice were orally exposed to BPS (2 or 200 µg/kg bw/day) starting on GD 9 through lactation day 20, and male mammary glands were evaluated on embryonic day 16, at puberty, and in early adulthood. The effects of BPS on mammary gland development were non-significant regarding the embryonic development of the mammary gland but decreased the number of AR positive cells in the mesenchyme in a dose dependent manner (E16). At puberty (PND24), a dose-dependent decrease in ductal areas was observed in the left mammary gland only (no effect in the right gland), whereas later in life, a dose-dependent increase in ductal area was mainly observed in the right mammary gland (Week 9). Significant effects were observed at the low 2 µg /kg bw/d dose of BPS.

In the second experiment, pregnant CD-1 mice were orally exposed to BPS (2, 200 or 2000 µg/kg bw/day) starting on pregnancy day 9 through lactational day 2. After weaning, the male pups were administered either oil (vehicle) or an estrogen challenge (1 µg EE2/kg bw/day) for ten days starting prior puberty. Challenge with EE2 from weaning (PND21) up to PND31 replicated the effects of BPS and EE2 according to the differences in left and right mammary gland development. BPS alone did not significantly affect the morphometry, except for an increase in the percentage and size of TEBs at the lowest dose of BPS (2 µg /kg bw/d). When animals were further challenged with EE2, the effects of EE2 on TEBs were higher in mice receiving the high doses (200 µg/kg bw/day) of BPS in both right and left mammary glands while the increasing effect on branching and ductal areas was only observed in the right mammary gland (less developed).

In conclusion, the lowest dose of BPS (2 µg/kg bw/day) is able to disrupt mammary gland development in males and reduces the sensitivity to estrogens suggesting a pro-estrogenic effect of low-dose BPS.

In a subchronic oral study conducted according to OECD TG 408 (see section 2.2.3.2), increased incidence in multifocal diffuse atrophy of the mammary gland were observed in males at 300 and 600/1000 mg (in males the highest dose was changed to 600 mg/kg bw/day after 70 days)/kg bw/day BPS (no effects reported for lower doses of exposure). We may expect that the effects on

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 151

mammary gland were not related to endocrine disrupting activity of BPS but rather to its ability to induce cell apoptosis at very high doses (as reported for BPA).

Conclusion on the effects of BPS on the mammary gland:

Maternal (gestational and lactational) exposure to BPS disrupts lactating mammary glands of dams and mammary gland development of pups (males and females), leading to pathological lesions diagnosed during adulthood. The most important impact (observed in two different labs) were the pathological lesions (lobulo-alveolar/intraductal hyperplasia and squamous metaplasia) in adulthood for mice exposed to 200 and 500 µg/kg bw/day during the fetal life with possible non-monotonic effects. All the studies of Vandenberg's group show a BPS effects already at 2 µg /kg bw/day on mammary gland development. All five publications described here are the only *in vivo* studies reported to date on BPS effects on mammary gland. No other studies thus neither confirm nor invalidate these results.

Metabolism and obesity

Twelve original papers which have investigated the *in vivo* metabolic effects of BPS were published until end of January 2020. The experimental results are captured in Table III.32 in Annex III.1. There is a large disparity within protocols which differ by the periods of exposure, the doses of BPS used, the species, the sex and the outcomes measured. For example, periods of exposure were restricted to pregnancy (Ullah, Razak, et al. 2019), pregnancy and lactation (Meng et al., 2019; Pu et al., 2017; Jing et al., 2019; da Silva et al., 2019) or lasted from pregnancy until adulthood (Ivry Del Moral et al., 2016; Brulport et al., 2019) or from weaning until adulthood (Azevedo et al., 2019 and 2020; Rezg et al., 2018 and 2019; Gao et al., 2020). Doses of BPS used were based on BPA toxicological values to frame Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI) and NOAEL doses and ranged from 1 µg/kg bw/day up to 5 mg/kg bw/day. Most studies used BPS at doses of 50 to 500 µg/kg bw/day. Routes of exposure included subcutaneous injections, orally gavage or through drinking water. Species used included sheep, rats (Wistar, Sprague-Dawley) or mice (Swiss albino, ICR and C57BL/6). Males and females have not been systematically analysed.

Collectively, BPS was found to significantly increase body weight in 7 out of the 11 studies reviewed with doses ranging from 25 to 500 µg/kg bw/day. Seven studies only analysed males but the one study which explored both sexes reported increased body weight only in male mice chronically exposed from gestation until adulthood receiving a high-fat (HF) diet from weaning onward (Ivry del Moral et al., 2016). Consistent with this, Meng et al., 2019 reported that the effects caused by BPS were more pronounced in mice fed a HF diet than in mice fed a low-fat diet. Apart from the study of Meng et al., 2019 where mice were orally gavaged, BPS was administered through drinking water.

Species used included male Sprague-Dawley rats gestationally exposed (Ullah, Razak, et al. 2019), Wistar rats perinatally exposed (Meng et al., 2019) or from 4 weeks until adulthood (first effects on body weight seen by 22 weeks of age; Azevedo et al., 2019 and 2020), Swiss albino male mice exposed for 10 weeks after weaning (Rezg et al., 2018 and 2019) and C57BL/6 mice chronically exposed from gestation until adulthood (Ivry del Moral et al., 2016; Brulport et al., 2019). These findings indicate that maternal exposure but also developmental exposure to BPS triggered body weight changes in males. One study reported that BPS was as efficient in increasing body weight of the male offspring as its analogs that include BPA, BPB and BPF. On the contrary, in two other studies performed in the same lab (Azevedo et al., 2019 and 2020), a group of mice was exposed to BPA and in contrast to BPS, BPA did not elicit body weight

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 152

increase. In addition, whether BPS affected food intake remains controversial (Rezg et al., 2018; Ivry del Moral et al., 2016).

Within the above studies, different outcomes were assessed in addition to body weight. However, analysis of lipid and glucose metabolism, food intake regulation and mitochondrial dysfunction in liver were not included. Conclusions favored the hypothesis of BPS acting as an obesogenic molecule in males especially when fed a high-fat diet. From the data of Ivry del Moral, a LOAEL of 1.5 µg/kg bw/day could be suggested.

Among the four other studies, the report of Gao et al., 2020 only analysed female mice (C57BL/6 mice). Exposure was through drinking water and lasted 10 weeks from weaning onward with doses of 50 and 500 µg/kg bw/day. Both BPA and BPS were used. Neither BPS nor BPA had any effect on body weight or glucose tolerance. However, the authors reported enhanced expression of Nr1h3¹² and of Fabp4¹³ in response to BPA and BPS exposure. Both bisphenols had the same activity. These data suggested lipid accumulation in liver although steatosis was probably limited because glucose tolerance was not impacted in the exposed mice.

The three other studies examined both males and females. In Da Silva et al., 2019, Wistar rats were exposed to BPS at doses of 10 and 50 µg/kg bw/d during gestation and lactation via intragastric gavage. BPS did not trigger any changes in body weight, neither in the dams, nor in the pups at weaning, nor in the adult offspring at 180 days. BPS did not disrupt glucose metabolism but lowered food intake in the adult offspring of both sexes. In females, BPS could trigger induced thermogenesis in line with reduced lipid accumulation in the brown adipose tissue (BAT) and reduced size of lipid droplets in the white adipose tissue (WAT). BPS males showed lowered visceral adiposity. It is suggested that BPS could cause dysregulation in thyroid hormone homeostasis and that BPS outcomes may be related to changes in food behavior, anxiety and locomotor activity examined in the study.

Importantly, BPS mice have increased preference for the fat-enriched diet which suggests an increased risk for obesity in the long-term. Finally, the last 2 studies were performed by the same lab on sheep male and female fetuses and both BPA and BPS were tested at the same dose of 500 µg/kg bw/day (Pu et al., 2017; Jing et al., 2019). Exposure occurred only during gestation and analyses were performed on fetuses recovered before term. Neither BPS nor BPA exerted any effect on fetus body weight. However, primary cultures of dissected perirenal adipose tissue from fetuses revealed that BPS gestational exposure led to dysfunctional adipocytes in males (reduced expression of adipogenic markers and enhanced expression of estrogen receptors (ESR1, ESR2) and glucocorticoid receptor (NR3C1)) but not in females. However, it did not alter adipocyte programming as was observed in females exposed to BPA.

The second study on sheep involved skeletal muscle development. It showed that programming is disturbed in response to a gestational exposure to BPA and BPS and that the situation is more critical in females and with BPS exposure. Although muscles play a major role in energy metabolism and insulin sensitivity, it remains to be demonstrated if these changes persist during adulthood.

In conclusion, it appears that BPS could be a metabolic disruptor targeting several metabolic organs both centrally and peripherally (liver, adipose tissue, muscle). Parameters

¹² NR1H3, the NR1 family members are key regulators of macrophage function, controlling transcriptional programs involved in lipid homeostasis and inflammation.

¹³ FABP4, fatty acid binding protein.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 153

affecting the severity of the outcomes include the sex (males are more susceptible than females), the periods and duration of exposure, and the nutritional context (effects are more often observed in animals fed a high-fat diet). Metabolic disruption endpoints may include body weight gain but also disruption of lipid metabolism and altered food intake/behavior. Modes of action are not clearly defined. Dysregulation of thyroid hormone synthesis, of plasma levels of estradiol and testosterone, and of the expression levels of estrogen and glucocorticoid receptors and mitochondrial dysfunction in liver have been reported.

Neural effects:

Six studies were analysed, three in mice (Catanese and Vandenberg, 2017; LaPlante et al., 2017; Mornagui et al., 2019) and three in rats (Castro et al., 2015; John et al., 2019; Silva et al., 2019). The study of John et al., 2019 was excluded due to the poor quality of the methodology.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 154

The following table summarises experimental evidences available on the nervous system, studies are grouped by windows of exposure and then tested species (mouse/rat/other species).

Table III.28: Experimental data on the nervous system

Ref.	Species Strain Model	Routes	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Period of analysis	Outcomes reported	Anxiety-related behavior	NOAEL/ LOAEL
						Maternal behavior		
Perinatal exposure								
Catanese and Vandenberg, 2017	CD-1 mice	Oral	2 µg/kg bw/day (BPS-2 group) 200 µg/kg bw/d (BPS-200 group) GD8/9 to lactational day (LD) 20/21	10-17 females/group	Adulthood	Infanticide and severe maternal neglect were observed for 13 % of F1 females of the BPS-2 group. Females exposed to 2 or 200 µg/kg bw/day spent less time in the nest on LD2 and LD7. Those exposed to 200 µg/kg bw/day spent more time in nest building on LD14.		LOAEL = 2 µg/kg bw/day
Silva et al., 2019	Wistar rat	Oral	10 µg/kg bw/day 50 µg/kg bw/day GD1 to PND21	9 - 10 males or females/group	Adulthood (PND160/161)		Elevated plus maze: males spent less time and lower number of entries in the open arms at both doses. No effects on females but the stage of the estral cycle not taken into account. Activity of males and females unchanged on PND160 in the open-field test	LOAEL = 10 µg/kg bw/day

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 155

Ref.	Species Strain Model	Routes	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Period of analysis	Outcomes reported	Anxiety-related behavior	NOAEL/ LOAEL
						Maternal behavior		
Adult exposure								
Laplante et al., 2017	CD-1 mice	Oral (small wafer treated with BPS or vehicle alone (70 % ethanol, allowed to dry before feeding) every day. BPS dose was adjusted for dam body weight daily.	2 µg/kg bw/day (BPS-2 group) – 200 µg/kg bw/day (BPS-200 group) F0 dams exposed from GD8/9 to lactational day (LD) 20/21	14-17 females/group		BPS-2: poor cleaning of pups, longer latency to interact with and retrieve pups on LD2, more time in the high-crouch position, associated with maximal milk ejection, smaller size nest. BPS-200: increased time on the nest and in nursing, longer latency to touch the first pup on LD14, only 50 % of litters displayed pup-initiated nursing.		LOAEL = 2 µg/kg bw/day

F: female; M: male; BW: body weight; GD: gestation day; PND: postnatal day; ND: no data; wt: weight

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 156

Maternal behavior

Two studies performed by the group of Vandenberg analysed the effects of oral exposure to BPS at 2 (BPS-2) and 200 µg/kg bw/day (BPS-200) from gestational day GD8/9 to lactational day (LD) 20/21 on maternal behavior of CD-1 mice (Catanese and Vandenberg, 2017; LaPlante et al., 2017). Maternal behavior of F0 dams and their F1 female offspring was analysed at early (LD2), mid (LD7) and end of lactation period (LD21).

F0 dams, analysed in the two studies, exhibited a moderate neglect (poor cleaning) of pups for the BPS-2 group, and increased time spent on the nest and in nursing, and a significantly longer latency to touch the first pup on LD14 for the BPS-200 group. Furthermore, F0 dams had a longer latency to interact with and retrieve pups on LD2 for the BPS-2 group.

At all three lactational stages evaluated, BPS-treated dams spent more time in the high-crouch position, associated with maximal milk ejection, compared with control females, with statistically significant differences observed on LD14 between controls and females treated with 2 µg BPS/kg bw/d. At PND14, only 50 % of litters born to dams treated with 200 µg BPS/kg bw/day displayed pup-initiated nursing while 91 % of control litters displayed these behaviors. but only 50 % of litters born to dams treated with 200 µg BPS/kg bw/d displayed these behaviors. The size of the nest was smaller in F0 dams treated with 2 µg/kg bw/day of BPS. Another interesting observation was the delayed growth and development of pups born to dams exposed to BPS, suggesting a lower quality and quantity of milk production or a transfer of BPS (or its metabolites) to the milk, significant also at the lower dose of BPS (2 µg/kg bw/day). This result was also reported above in the section dedicated to the mammary gland since maternal behavior and mammary gland physiology were analysed in the same study (LaPlante et al., 2017). The dose of 2 µg/kg bw/day BPS was active on both mouse behavior and lactating mammary gland.

In F1 dams analysed in the study of Catanese and Vandenberg, 2017, infanticide and severe maternal neglect were observed for 13 % of F1 females of the BPS-2 group. Females exposed to 2 or 200 µg/kg bw/day spent less time in the nest on LD2 and LD7. Those exposed to 200 µg/kg bw/day spent more time in nest building on LD14. In contrast, there were no significant differences in time to first touch pups between treatment groups for F1 females at any time point. F1 females that attempted retrievals had a shorter latency to interact with and retrieve pups.

In the open-field test, assessing anxiety-related behavior and activity, no effects of BPS treatment were observed on the number of grooming events and rearing (Catanese and Vandenberg, 2017). However, the time spent in the central area and the travelled distance were not measured in this study.

Maternal behavior is tightly regulated by a hormonal sequence involving at the end of gestation the decrease of progesterone levels, the increase of estradiol levels and then of oxytocin and prolactin levels. This hormonal sequence acts to synchronise parturition with the expression of maternal behavior, which is controlled by a neural circuitry including hypothalamic structures (preoptic area, arcuate nucleus) and connected with the mesolimbic reward system (ventral tegmental area). BPS treatment increased estrogen receptor ER immunoreactivity in the caudal subregion of the medial preoptic area at the dose of 200 µg/kg bw/day and reduced estradiol levels in F0 dams on LD21, but had no effects in F1 dams (LaPlante et al., 2017; Catanese and Vandenberg, 2017). Analysis on LD21 of the arcuate nucleus, involved in maternal behavior and lactation, showed no effect of BPS exposure on ERα and Stat5-immunoreactive cells in F0 dams. There were no significant effects of BPS treatment on TH immunoreactivity in the ventral tegmental area, a structure of the

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 157

reward system, in the exposed groups in either the F0 or F1 generation (Catanese and Vandenberg, 2017).

These studies show adult (F0 dams) and developmental effects (F1 dams) of BPS exposure on the expression of maternal behavior (LaPlante et al., 2017; Catanese and Vandenberg, 2017). A LOAEL of 2 µg/kg bw/day was observed for the developmental effect of BPS on maternal behavior (Catanese and Vandenberg, 2017).

For information, previous studies showed similar alterations of maternal behavior following developmental exposure to BPA at doses of 10 µg/kg bw/day in mice (Palanza et al., 2002), 5 µg/kg bw/day and 40 µg/kg bw/day in rats (Boudalia et al., 2014; Della Seta et al., 2005).

Anxiety-related behavior

The study of Silva et al., 2019 explored the effects of exposure to BPS, through oral gavage, at 10 and 50 µg/kg bw/day from gestational day 1 to PND 21 in rats. Activity of male and female offspring analysed on PND160 was unchanged in the open-field test. In contrast, analysis of anxiety state level in the elevated plus maze test showed that males spent less time in the open arms and entered it less frequently than controls for both doses. No effect was observed in females, but the stage of the estrus cycle was not taken into account in such analyses. Indeed, anxiety-related behavior is modulated by estradiol levels; females are less anxious under estrogen dominance (proestrous and estrous phases).

Mornagui et al., 2019 reported also increased anxiety-related behavior in males, although a low number of animals was used in this study. Swiss male mice were exposed to BPS at 100 µg/kg bw/day, through drinking water, from postnatal week 3 to postnatal week 10. Analyses in PNW 10 showed no effect on locomotor activity assessed in the open-field, and a reduced time spent in the open arms of the elevated plus maze test.

Anxiety-related behavior is regulated by neurotransmitters (serotonine) and modulated by hormones (sex steroids, corticosteroids, thyroid hormones...). Silva et al., 2019 reported increased plasma T4 levels in PND21 males exposed to 50 µg/kg bw/day of BPS and decreased total T3 and free T4 in adult males exposed to both BPS doses of 10 and 50 µg/kg bw/day. Whether these hormonal changes underlie the behavioral modifications reported by Silva et al., 2019 and Mornagui et al., 2019 needs further investigation.

In another study, Castro et al., 2015 analysed the effects of exposure to BPS, BPF or BPA (10 µg/kg bw/day) in female Wistar rats (GD12 to parturition, then in pups from PND1 to PND21) on the cortical expression of 5-α reductase and serotonin/dopamine systems. The 5-α reductase metabolises testosterone into 5-α dihydrotestosterone, but it is also involved in the biosynthesis of neurosteroids such as allopregnanolone, which plays a key role in neural functions.

The authors described reduced mRNA levels of 5- α reductase 3 on PND21 in females exposed to BPS or BPF, while BPA exposure reduced the mRNA and protein levels of 5-α reductase 2 and 3. Quantitative PCR array for rat dopamine and serotonin pathway showed a total of 25 genes significantly regulated by BPA, 56 genes by BPF, and 24 genes by BPS. A common change induced by the three molecules was the upregulation of Cyp2d4, which is involved in the hydroxylation of allopregnanolone and progesterone to corticosteroids (3 α 5 α - tetrahydrodeoxycorticosterone and 11-deoxycorticosterone). As this study was performed only in females, it remains to be investigated whether these modifications in the expression of 5-α reductase and dopamine/serotonine systems occur also in males.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 158

Conclusion on BPS effects on the the nervous system

These studies show developmental and prepubertal/pubertal effects of BPS exposure on anxiety-related behavior (Silva et al., 2019; Mornagui et al., 2019). A LOAEL dose of 10 µg/kg bw/day was observed in the study of Silva et al., 2019.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 159

4 Existing toxicity reference values for BPS

A proposal for Harmonised Classification and Labelling (CLH) in category Repr. 1B – H360FD based on Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 (CLP Regulation) has been submitted by the Belgian Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment for BPS (EC Number: 201-250-5). This CLH proposal includes an overview of the reproductive toxicity studies carried out on BPS according to OECD technical guidelines. No toxicological reference value has been derived in this dossier.

The following chronic Derived No-Effect Levels (DNELs) are given in the REACH registration dossier as submitted by the applicant:

General population chronic oral DNEL of 0.5 mg BPS/kg bw/day.

This derivation is based on the data from a subchronic oral toxicity study with rats (conducted according to OECD TG 408) in which a dose of 100 mg/kg bw/day) was regarded to represent the NOAEL (Anonymous 17, 2014, BASF SE, 2014, ECHA CLP, 2019 and ECHA Dissemination, 2020). At the next higher dose of 300 mg/kg bw/day), a lower body weight was observed compared to controls, as well as histopathological changes of the mammary gland in male rats. Standard extrapolation factors of 2, 10, 10, 1, 1 were used for exposure duration (subchronic to chronic), interspecies-, intraspecies-differences (general population), dose-response, quality of whole database (ECHA Dissemination 2020). The general population DNEL for oral exposure is of 100 mg/kg bw/day/(2x10x10x1x1)= 0.5 mg/kg bw/day.

General population chronic dermal DNEL of 1 mg/kg bw/day.

This derivation is based on a worst-case dermal absorption rate of 50 % which was assumed based on BPS physico/chemical data (solid, low log Pow of 1.2, water solubility of 714 mg/L; see section 1.2). This leads to a NOAEL dermal of 200 mg/kg bw/day. Standard extrapolation factors of 2, 10, 10, 1, 1 were used for exposure duration (subchronic to chronic), interspecies-, intraspecies-differences (general population), dose-response, quality of whole database (ECHA Dissemination 2020). The resulting general population DNEL for dermal exposure is of 200 mg/kg bw/day/(2x10x10x1x1)=1 mg/kg bw/day.

General population chronic inhalation DNEL of 1.7 mg/m³.

This derivation is based on the assumption of a daily exposure period of 24 hours, the oral NO(A)EL was converted into an inhalation NO(A)EC according to the following formula: inhalation NO(A)EC = oral NO(A)EL × 1/sRV(rat) × ABS_{oral}(rat)/ABS_{inhalation}(human)

with:

- oral NO(A)EL: 100 mg/kg bw/day (from subchronic study, see above)
- sRV(rat): 1.15 m³/kg bw (24 hours) [standard respiratory volume of the rat]
- ABS_{oral}(rat)/ABS_{inhalation}(human): 1 [ratio of oral absorption in the rat to inhalative absorption in the human]

High rates of bioavailability via the lung can e.g occur for substances which can penetrate into the lower/alveolar region and well solubilise in the bronchioalveolar fluid. BPS is a solid granula with a rather low solubility and only a minor share of the particles is in the respirable range (e.g. < 4µm). Larger particles deposit in the upper/thoracic region of the respiratory tract in which an effective retrograde mucocilliary transport exists. This was justifying a very conservative deviation from the

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 160

ECHA guidance factor of 0.5 by anticipating an equal bioavailability in the respiratory- in comparison to the gastrointestinal- tract.

Accordingly, the oral NO(A)EL of 100 mg/kg bw/day was transformed in an inhalation NO(A)EC of 87 mg/m³.

Standard extrapolation factors of 2, 2.5, 10, 1, 1 were used for exposure duration (subchronic to chronic), interspecies (1 for external concentration and 2.5 for remaining differences) -, intraspecies-differences (general population), dose-response, quality of whole database (ECHA Dissemination 2020).

The resulting general population DNEL inhalation is of 87 mg/m³/(2x2.5x10x1x1)= 1.7 mg/m³.

Worker chronic inhalation DNEL of 7 mg/m³

In order to derive a worker DNEL and under the assumption of a daily exposure period of 8 hours, the oral NO(A)EL was converted into an inhalation NO(A)EC according to the following formula:

$$\text{inhalation NO(A)EC} = \text{oral NO(A)EL} \times 1/\text{sRV}(\text{rat}) \times \text{ABSoral}(\text{rat})/\text{ABSinhalation}(\text{human}) \times \text{sRV}(\text{human})/\text{wRV}(\text{human})$$

with:

- oral NO(A)EL: 100 mg/kg bw/day (from subchronic study, see above)
- sRV(rat): 0.38 m³/kg bw (8 hours) [standard respiratory volume of the rat]
- ABSoral(rat)/ABSinhalation(human): 1 [ratio of oral absorption in the rat to inhalative absorption in the human], high rates of bioavailability *via* the lung can e.g occur for substances which can penetrate into the lower/alveolar region and well solubilise in the bronchioalveolar fluid. BPS is a solid granula with a rather low solubility and only a minor share of the particles is in the respirable range (e.g. < 4µm). Larger particles deposit in the upper/thoracic region of the respiratory tract in which an effective retrograde mucocilliary transport exists. This is justifying a very conservative deviation from the ECHA guidance factor of 0.5 by anticipating an equal bioavailability in the respiratory- in comparison to the gastrointestinal- tract.
- sRV(human)/wRV(human): 6.7 m³/10 m³ [ratio of human standard respiratory volume to worker respiratory volume]

Accordingly, the oral NO(A)EL of 100 mg/kg bw/day is transformed in an inhalation NO(A)EC of 176 mg/m³.

Standard extrapolation factors of 2, 2.5, 5, 1, 1 were used for exposure duration (subchronic to chronic), interspecies (1 for external concentration and 2.5 for remaining differences)-, intraspecies-differences (worker), dose-response, quality of whole database (ECHA Dissemination 2020).

The resulting worker DNEL inhalation is of 176 mg/m³/(2x2.5x5x1x1) = 7 mg/m³

As indicated, this DNEL is referring to the systemic toxicity of BPS. Since the pure substance is a granular solid a potential impairment of the respiratory tract due to exposure to the dust additionally needs to be taken into account. E.g. the German Committee for Dangerous Substances derived a general limit value for low soluble dusts of 1.5 mg/m³ for the alveolar and 10 mg/m³ for the inhalable fraction.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 161

Worker chronic dermal DNEL of 20 mg/kg bw/day

In order to derive a worker DNEL a worst-case dermal absorption rate of 50 % is assumed for BPS based on physico/chemical data (solid, low log Pow of 1.2, water solubility of 714 mg/L; see section 1.2). This leads to a NOAEL dermal of 200 mg/kg bw/day. Standard extrapolation factors of 2, 10, 5, 1, 1 were used for exposure duration (subchronic to chronic), interspecies-, intraspecies-differences (worker), dose-response, quality of whole database (ECHA Dissemination 2020). The resulting worker DNEL for dermal exposure is of $200 \text{ mg/kg bw/day} / (2 \times 10 \times 5 \times 1 \times 1) = 20 \text{ mg/kg bw/day}$.

Human Biomonitoring (HBM) values or Biomonitoring Equivalents (BEs) have not yet been published for BPS. The toxicological findings available on BPS have also not been used for the derivation of TDI values so far. BPS is currently authorised to be used as a monomer in the manufacture of plastic food contact materials (FCM) and is listed in Annex I of Commission Regulation (EU) No 10/2011¹⁴ with a Specific Migration Limit (SML) of 0.05 mg/kg.

¹⁴ Commission Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 of 14 January 2011 on plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food. Available online: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32011R0010&from=EN>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 162

5 HBM parameters

5.1 Choice of biomarkers

Similarly, to what has been observed for BPA, urinary concentration appears to be the more commonly used parameter for estimating the internal exposure to BPS. In a large majority of available studies, the urinary exposure level is estimated after enzymatic hydrolysis of the conjugates, so that the total of free plus conjugated forms is finally determined. Total urinary BPS also appears as the prioritised marker within the HBM4EU project. Although the unconjugated form is known to be the active one able to induce a given effect, the measurement of total BPS allows a better compatibility with current methodological detection limits, and is a protective exposure assessment approach considering possible endogenous deconjugation. Very few data are conversely available regarding the excretion levels of non-conjugated BPS in urine, but these confirmed a very low proportion (<1 %) of free urinary BPS (Santé Publique France, 2019). Most existing studies have determined exposure levels in spot urine samples.

5.2 Analytical methods

Mainly, the analytical determination of BPS in urine may be performed using methods well-proven in the determination of BPA. An overview of suitable methods for BPA determination is presented in the monography for BPA of the German HBM commission (HBM-Kommission 2012). Philips et al., 2018 described a method for the determination of all together eight different bisphenols including BPS. By means of HPLC and tandem mass spectrometry and use of ¹³C-labelled internal standards, limits of detection of 0.03 - 0.18 ng/ml can be achieved.

As in general for determination of bisphenols, the total concentration is determined after hydrolysis of the conjugates with glucuronidase/sulfatase. Determinations in standard samples provided results within ±15 % of the certified values (Philips, Jaddoe et al. 2018).

A method using hydrolysis of the conjugates with glucuronidase/sulfatase (which is checked by the addition of conjugated 4-methyl umbelliferone and ¹³C-methyl umbelliferone) and subsequent SPE-HPLC-MS/MS for the determination of BPS has been presented by Lehmler et al., 2018, the limit of detection reaching 0.1 µg/l BPS. Methods for the determination of BPS (and other bisphenols) in thermal paper and drinking fluids using deuterium-labelled standards have also been described (Zech et al. 2016). A currently developed method using ultraperformance liquid chromatography and tandem mass spectrometry (UPLC-MS/MS) for the determination in urine samples after previous enzymatic hydrolysis of the conjugates and dispersive liquid/liquid microextraction reaches a limit of detection of 0.01 µg/l (limit of determination 0.05 µg/l) (Jäger, Bäcker et al., 2018).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 163

6 Derivation of HBM-GVs for BPS

6.1 Derivation method

According to the methodology developed in the framework of the HBM4EU project, there are three possible options for deriving HBM-GVs (Apel et al., 2020).

The human data is insufficient for the derivation of HBM guidance values. In addition, neither toxicity reference values nor occupational exposure limits have been proposed by EU or non-EU relevant organisations so far. Regarding workers, no relationship between atmospheric concentration of BPS and urinary concentration of total BPS would be possible due to the scarcity of data on occupational exposure. Thus, the derivation method for HBM-GVs for BPS for both the general population and the workers, is based on a NOAEL or a LOAEL identified from animal experimental studies *via* oral route. As mentioned in section 3.1.3, dermal absorption of BPS is very limited < 2 % *in vivo*.

Unless results of Champmartin et al., 2020 are followed by further experimental studies to better appreciate the percentage of readily absorbable fraction of BPS, the HBM4EU Task 5.2 team assumes that the dermal route will contribute very little to the overall exposure to BPS. Lastly the relative contribution of the inhalation route may also be expected to be low, based on BPS physical-chemical properties (low vapor pressure) and by analogy with BPA risk assessments. As BPS is well absorbed by oral route, it is therefore anticipated that a 100 % oral exposure scenario is appropriate for the general population as well as for workers.

Factsheets summarising the data which are relevant to perform the derivation of the HBM-GVs, as described here below, are provided in the section 9 of this report: section 9.1 summarises the information used for the HBM-GV derivation for the general population, and section 9.2 summarises the information used for the HBM-GV derivation for workers.

6.2 Derivation of the HBM-GV for the general population

The HBM-GV_{GenPop} is derived by translating the point of departure (POD) described below into the corresponding concentrations of the selected biomarker of exposure (i.e. total BPS in urine) by using the modified PBPK model by Karrer et al. (2018) also described below.

6.2.1 Choice of a Point of Departure (POD)

The regulatory toxicology studies conducted in accordance with OECD Test Guidelines are described in section 3.2.6.2. An overview of the NOAELs/LOAELs from these studies is given in Table III.29. In addition, numerous academic studies investigating more specific parameters dedicated to endocrine disrupting effects have been published (see section 3.2.7). The most relevant studies and their corresponding NOAELs and/or LOAELs are summarised in Table III.30 below.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 164

Table III.29: Overview of LOAELs or NOAELs identified in regulatory toxicological or reproductive toxicological studies conducted on the basis of OECD technical guidelines (orally applied dose) for BPS

Species, exposure duration	Endpoint/ target organ	LOAEL (mg/ kg bw /day)	NOAEL (mg/ kg bw/day)	OECD TG number and study reference
Rat, 13 days	Kidney effects (histology and decreased weight) and other signs of toxicity (hematology, clinical chemistry, decreased liver organ weight and atrophy of the adipose tissue)		97 (in males)	ECHA CLP, 2019 quoted as Anonymous 18, 1973, and ECHA Dissemination, 2020 quoted as Eastman-Kodak, 1973
Rat, 28 days with a reversibility period	Suppressed bw gain, kidney and caecum effects	200	40	TG 407 / OECD SIDS 2013, ECHA CLP, 2019 quoted as Anonymous 16, 1999 and ECHA Dissemination, 2020
Rat, 28 days	Decreased final body weight, increased kidney, adrenal, liver weight and histopathological changes, decreased prostate and seminal vesicle weights, and diffuse atrophy of the mammary gland (in males)	100		TG 407 (or similar to) / ECHA CLP, 2019 quoted as Anonymous 15, 2017
Rat, 90 days	Decreased body weight in males	1000 (in males)		TG 408 / BASF SE, 2014/ in ECHA CLP, 2019 quoted as Anonymous 17, 2014, and ECHA Dissemination, 2020
	Mammary gland (change from the physiological lobulo-alveolar morphology to a tubulo-alveolar appearance with smaller more basophilic epithelial lining cells (atrophy) in males)	300 (in males)	100 (in males)	
	Uterus (focal squamous cell metaplasia of glandular epithelium)	1000 (in females)	300 (in females)	
	Adrenals (increase weights and cortical hypertrophy/hyperplasia)	1000 (in males)	300 (in males)	
	Liver (increase liver weight, hypertrophy and eosinophilic foci in high dose females and increase relative liver weight in high dose males with clinical pathology findings)	1000 (both sex)	300 (both sex)	

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 165

Species, exposure duration	Endpoint/ target organ	LOAEL (mg/kg bw/day)	NOAEL (mg/kg bw/day)	OECD TG number and study reference
Rat, 14 days	Maternal toxicity such as reduced food consumption and corrected (net) body weight gain		100	TG 414 ECHA CLP report, 2019 (study quoted as Anonymous 19, 2014). ECHA Dessimation, 2020).
	Prenatal development: no toxicologically relevant adverse fetal findings evident.		300	
Rat, 45 days (males) and 53 days (females)	Parental systemic toxicity		60	TG 421 / ECHA CLP, 2019 quoted as Anonymous 12, 2000, OECD SIDS 2013 and ECHA Dissemination, 2020.
	Parental effects on the caecum	60	10	
	Reproductive and developmental toxicity based on prolongation of estrous cycle and diestrus period, decreased fertility index and decreased implantation index	300	60	
Rat, 12 weeks (males) or 14 weeks (females)	Systemic effects in F0 (more pronounced in males) on kidney, liver caecum effects identified by macroscopic and histopathological examinations	100	30	TG 422 / ECHA CLP 2019 quoted as Anonymous 14, 2017, 2019
	Developmental and reproductive toxicity, reduced number of implantations, increased post-implantation losses, decrease in total number of pups delivered, decrease in mean number of pups delivered	300	100	
	Mammary gland histology (atrophy in males)	300	100	

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 166

Species, exposure duration	Endpoint/ target organ	LOAEL (mg/kg bw/day)	NOAEL (mg/kg bw/day)	OECD TG number and study reference
Rat, EOGRT with F2, DNT (cohorts 2A and 2B) and DIT (cohort 3) ¹⁵	General systemic toxicity based on increased kidney weight and histopathological changes in both F0 and F1	180	60	TG 443 / ECHA 2019, CLP quoted as Anonymous 13, 2019 and in EFSA, 2020
	Rats, developmental toxicity based on post implantation loss in the F1 progeny	60	20	
	Rats, fertility and reproductive performance for F0 and F1 parental rats		180	
	Rats, developmental neurotoxicity		180	
	Rats, developmental immunotoxicity for F1 progeny:			
	based on decreased spleen weight at the mid-dose in males		20	
	Lower mean and median anti-SRBC IgM antibody titers of the positive control group (4.5 mg/kg bw/day cyclophosphamide, oral) demonstrated that the test system worked properly.		180	

¹⁵The N(L)OAEL from the EOGRT study are quoted from the EFSA, 2020 report.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 167

Table III.30: Overview of LOAEL or NOAEL identified in BPS academic oral studies (for explanations see text)

Species, Endpoint/ target organ, exposure duration	LOAEL ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kgbw}/\text{day}$)	NOAEL ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kgbw}/\text{day}$)	Source of data
Liver effects			
Mice, liver, 56 day	5000* 6000**		Zhang, Lin et al. 2018
Male reproductive system			
CD-1 Mice : - Increase in germ cells apoptosis in neonates	0.5		Shi et al., 2018
CD-1 Mice: - gestational exposure (GD7 to birth) Important reduction in sperm number and motility in cauda epididymis in adults which are transgenerationally transmitted.	0.5		Shi, Whorton, et al. 2019b
Female reproductive system			
CD-1 Mice, oral, gestational exposure (GD11 to birth): -Pubertal timing	0.5		Shi, Sekulovski, et al. 2019
Mammary gland			
CD-1 Mice, oral (wafer), mammary gland physiology (morphology) effects and nursing behaviour showed a delayed growth and development of pups and increased time spent nursing at PND14.	2		Laplante et al., 2017
CD-1 Mice, oral (pipet), GD9 to PND20 Mammary gland whole mount and histology analysis showed increased number of TEBs at PND20 and at 3 months.	2		Kolla et al., 2018
CD-1 Mice, oral (wafer), GD 9 up to lactation day 20 At the puberty (PND24), dose-dependent decrease in ductal areas in the left mammary gland only (no effect in the right gland), whereas later in life, a dose-dependent increase in ductal area was mainly observed in the right mammary gland (Week 9).	2		Kolla et al., 2019

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 168

Species, Endpoint/ target organ, exposure duration	LOAEL (µg/kgbw/day)	NOAEL (µg/kgbw/day)	Source of data
Anxiety-related behavior			
Wistar rat, oral (gavage), GD1 to PND 21 Anxiety-related behaviour observed in male rat (in the elevated plus maze, males spent less time in the open arms and entered it less frequently than controls)	10		Silva et al., 2019
CD-1 Mice, Oral GD8/9 to PND20/21 Infanticide and severe maternal neglect. Females spent less time in the nest on LD2 and LD7 at 2 or 200 µg/kg bw/day. On LD14, those exposed to 200 µg/kg bw/day spent more time in nest building.	2		Catanese and Vandenberg, 2017

*: estimated by the authors of the study (Zhang, Lin et al. 2018) from BPS added to food and food intake assuming a food uptake of 100 g/kg bw/day. **Using standard factors according to REACH Guidance (ECHA 2012) for food consumption of mice (120 g food/kg bw/day), 1.2 fold higher values are obtained for the LOAEL and NOAEL. All the other N(L)OAEL were derived by the ANSES ED-EG.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 169

Based on this rather large dataset including repeated dose toxicity, reproductive toxicity and also specific effects on the endocrine system, two different PODs were considered, as summarised in Table III. below. These two PODs are derived from academic studies published in the peer-reviewed literature.

Studies by Kolla et al., 2018, and by Kolla et al., 2019 and Catanese and Vandenberg, 2017 were conducted by oral route with at least two dose levels and identified a common LOAEL of 2 µg/kg bw/day for mammary gland and neurobehavioral toxicity, respectively. Moreover, most of the reviewed academic studies on BPS converged to this dose level.

Table III.31: Selection of the POD - Proposal of two scenarios

	Species, exposure duration	Endpoint	POD	Reference
Scenario 1	CD-1 Mice, oral, gestational exposure	Alteration of oocyte maturation and folliculogenesis	LOAEL = 0.5 µg/kg bw/day	Shi, Sekulovski, et al. 2019
Scenario 2	CD-1 Mice, oral exposure, GD 9 to PND 20	Increased number of TEBs in the mammary gland	LOAEL: 2 µg/kg bw/day	Kolla et al., 2018
	CD-1 Mice, oral exposure, GD 9 to GD 16 or lactation day 20	Dose dependent increase in ductal area in the mammary gland.		Kolla et al., 2019
	Rat, oral exposure, GD8/9 to PND20/21	Neurobehavioral toxicity		Catanese and Vandenberg 2017

Following the consultation period and based on the comments received, it was decided to select the LOAEL of 2 µg/kg bw/day as a POD to derive the HBM guidance values. The derivation for HBM-GVs under the scenario 1 is available in Annex III.2.

Nevertheless, we are also aware of the current assessment of BPS at the EU level, which may be finalised during the next months. Depending on the conclusion of this assessment, the derivation of the HBM-GVs for BPS could be updated.

In order to derive a human equivalent dose, a constant and continuous exposure to the LOAEL/kg bw/day *via* ingestion (100 % oral exposure scenario) is assumed. Then, the modified PBPK model from Karrer et al., 2018 is used to estimate the corresponding urinary levels in humans. Different assessment factors are applied to estimate the exposure. A factor of 3 is applied for extrapolating a LOAEL to a NOAEL. The interspecies differences in toxicokinetics between animal species and humans are determined by PBPK modeling, and an assessment factor of 2.5 is applied for remaining interspecies differences (mostly for toxicodynamic differences). A factor of 10 accounting for intra-species differences is further applied to the human adjusted NOAEL. Generally, this factor is set to 5 when workers are the targeted population for which the HBM-GV is

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 170

derived, in line with ECHA's R8 guidance for deriving DNELs for worker (ECHA, 2012). However, as the most sensitive endpoint(s) to be protected from are the effects on the unborn child, no differences can be assumed between the foetuses of the general population and the workers.

6.2.2 Prediction of the total BPS urinary concentration with 100 % oral exposure

6.2.2.1 Description of the PBPK model by Karrer et al., 2018

Karrer et al., 2018 have modified the peroral adult PBPK model developed by Yang et al., 2015, that has been used by EFSA in 2015 for calculating the Human Equivalent Dose Factor (HEDF) (ratio of AUC_{Animal}/AUC_{Human}) and to further derive the t-TDI for BPA. Karrer et al., 2018 extended this previous PBPK model to BPS (see D 12.5 Deliverable Report WP 12 section 4.2.3.2 for further details).

Based on the Karrer et al., 2018 model, a PBPK model for BPS and its metabolites (BPS-G and BPS-S) was implemented by Ineris within HBM4EU. To validate the model a comparison of measured concentrations of BPS and total BPS (BPS-G + BPS) in two volunteers' studies (Oh et al., 2018a/b; Khmiri et al., 2020) with predicted concentrations by the model has been performed. The blood flow was replaced by a plasmatic flow (BPS being mostly distributed in the plasma) and a value for the haematocrit of 0.45 was used. Outputs of excreted urinary BPS quantities were also replaced by urinary BPS concentrations, by adding an estimated value for the daily 24h urinary excretion. The same daily urinary excretion rate of 0.05L/h previously used for BPA was considered. After oral administration, an absorption fraction of 100 % was considered. The schematic overview of the model is presented in Figure III.5.

Figure III.5: Schematic overview of the PBPK model for BPS and BPA (also for BPF and BPAF) and their glucuronides and sulfates (PBPK-compartments in gray, single-compartment submodules with dotted lines) (Karrer et al., 2018)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 171

“Rich”: richly perfused tissue; “slow”: slowly perfused tissue [perfusion higher/lower than 0.1 mL/min/g tissue, respectively]

6.2.2.2 Prediction for the scenario 2 with a POD of 2 µg/kg bw/day corresponding to a continuous exposure of 0.0266 µg/kg bw/day in the general population

For an adult of 70 kg

This scenario considered the results on mammary gland and neurobehavioral toxicity leading to a LOAEL of 2 µg/kg bw/day. Applying assessment factors of 75 (3x2.5x10) and assuming a constant and continuous oral exposure throughout the day of BPS leads to a constant exposure to 0.0266 µg/kg bw/day. The concentrations of free BPS in plasma estimated (for an adult of 70 kg) at this constant exposure of 0.0266 µg/kg bw/day is illustrated in III.6. The estimated maximal concentration of plasmatic free and glucuronidated BPS is 9.7×10^{-3} nmol/l (2.42 ng/l) after 24h constant exposure.

Figure III.6: Estimated free BPS and (gluco)conjugated BPS plasmatic concentrations (nmol/l) for a 70 kg adult after 24h constant and continuous oral exposure to 0.0266 µg BPS/kg bw averaged over 24h in the general population

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 172

The concentration of total BPS in urine predicted for a male adult of 70 kg after constant and continuous oral exposure is illustrated in Figure III.7. **The estimated concentration of total BPS (sum of estimated urinary glucuronidated and free BPS) in urine is 4.13 nmol/l (1030 ng/l) after 24h constant exposure to 0.0266 µg/kg bw/day . The HBM-GV_{GenPop} is rounded to 1.0 µg/l.**

Constant exposure = 0.0266 µg/kg bw/day

Figure III.7: Estimated urinary total BPS concentrations (nmol/l) for a 70 kg adult after 24h constant and continuous oral exposure to 0.0266 µg of BPS/kg bw averaged over 24h in the general population

6.3 Derivation of the HBM-GV for workers

The same approach, the same POD as well as the same modified PBPK model by Karrer et al., 2018 are used to derive the HBM-GV_{worker}.

The prediction of the total BPS urinary concentration with 100 % oral exposure with a POD of 2 µg/kg bw/day corresponding to an occupational exposure of 0.0266 µg/kg bw/day is presented below.

This scenario considered the results on alteration of mammary gland and on neurobehavioral toxicity leading to a LOAEL of 2 µg/kg bw/day. Applying an assessment factor of 75 (3x2.5x10) and assuming a constant and continuous oral exposure throughout the day of BPS would lead to a constant exposure to 0.0266 µg/kg bw/day. As occupational exposure is not continuous all over the day and week, the modelling was refined in order to reflect a continuous exposure during 8 hours per day followed by a non-exposure period of 16 hours. This 8 hour exposure and 16 hour exposure period was then repeated 4 times in order to mimic a working week. Thus, this 5 day occupational scenario includes an 8 hour exposure period with 0.0798 µg/kg bw and a non exposure period of 16h which then corresponds to an exposure all over the day (0-24 hour) of 0.0266 µg/kg bw/day.

The predicted plasmatic concentration of free BPS assuming an oral exposure to 0.0798 µg/kg bw from 0h to 8h and to 0 µg/kg bw from 8h to 24h each day during 5 days for an adult of 70 kg is illustrated in Figure III.8. **The maximum plasmatic concentration of total BPS (free and glucuronidated BPS) predicted is 28 x 10⁻³nmol/l (7.1 ng/l).**

Exposure 8h/day= 0.0798 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw/day

Average exposure 24h = 0.0266 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw/day

Figure III.8: Estimated free BPS and glucuronidated BPS plasmatic concentrations (nmol/l) for an adult of 70 kg considering an occupational scenario during 5 days with for each day an exposure from 0h to 8h to 0.0798 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw and from 8h to 24h to 0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw corresponding to an exposure all over the day (0-24hour) of 0.0266 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw/day.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 174

The concentration of total BPS in urine predicted for an adult of 70 kg assuming an oral exposure to 0.0798 µg/kg bw from 0h to 8h and to 0 µg/kg bw from 8h to 24h each day during 5 days is illustrated in Figure III.. **The estimated concentration of total BPS (sum of estimated urinary glucuronidated and free BPS) in urine is 12.1 nmol/l (3028 ng/l). The HBM-GV_{worker} is rounded to 3.0 µg/l.**

Exposure 8h/day= 0.0798 µg/kg bw
Average exposure 24h = 0.0266 µg/kg bw/day

Figure III.9: Estimated urinary total BPS concentrations (nmol/l) for an adult of 70 kg considering an occupational scenario during 5 days with for each day an exposure from 0h to 8h to 0.0798 µg/kg bw and from 8h to 24h to 0 µg/kg bw corresponding to an exposure all over the day (0-24hour) of 0.0266 µg/kg bw/day.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 175

7 Level of confidence attributed to the HBM-GVs

As mentioned in the HBM4EU concept document to derive HBM-GVs (Apel et al., 2020), it is suggested to attribute a level of confidence (low, medium or high) to each calculated HBM-GV. The level of confidence should reflect the uncertainties identified during the elaboration of the value and could constitute a good incentive to revise later on values with estimated 'lower' level of confidence.

However, it should be specified that the levels of confidence proposed in this document are not determined according to an established recognised methodology, but rather rely on expert judgment regarding the reliability of the data and the calculation method used to derive the HBM guidance values.

The level of confidence attributed to the HBM-GV for the general and working population is set to 'medium-low'. Please refer to note 2 of the factsheets presented in section 9 for explanation on this level of confidence.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 176

8 Discussion

The human data on BPS is insufficient for the derivation of HBM guidance values. In addition, neither toxicity reference values nor occupational exposure limits have been proposed by EU or non-EU relevant organisations so far. However, improved animal toxicological data have become available for BPS within recent years, with several toxicokinetic studies including one reviewed by EFSA and ECHA working group, an extended-one generation study, also assessed by the same EU working group, and academic studies investigating common endpoints associated with BPA toxicity (namely mammary gland, female reproductive, neurotoxicity and metabolism and obesity). This permits derivation of HBM-GVs on the basis of BPS experimental toxicity studies.

Toxicokinetic studies in several species, including humans, showed that BPS is well absorbed by the oral route, whereas dermal absorption is very limited (<2 % *in vivo*). As previously shown for BPA, BPS clearance is mainly driven by its glucuronidation into BPS-G, which is mainly excreted in urine. Major differences between BPA and BPS toxicokinetics were observed both in animal model and in humans with a lesser capacity for elimination and a 100-fold higher oral bioavailability compared to BPA. This means that the proportion of active (non-conjugated) BPS which is absorbed and available to produce systemic effects is 250-fold higher than for BPA after oral dosing.

During gestation, TK studies showed that the blood-placental barrier is much more efficient in limiting fetal exposure to BPS than to BPA, but the higher persistency of BPS in the fetal compartment leads to expected BPS concentrations in fetal plasma of the same order as for BPA at the same maternal exposure level. TK properties indicate that the daily intake of BPS in populations can be approximately estimated by determining total BPS excreted in urine during 24 h.

The expanding database on BPS provides convincing evidence of adverse effects on female reproduction, neurodevelopment and mammary gland. A proposal of EU classification and labelling has been recently made by the Belgium Member State with a classification as Repr. 1B H360 FD. The sensitivity to BPS is clearly dependent on the timing of exposure, with specific periods of development being critical. Disruption of estrogenic signalling is likely central in the mediation of these effects although other modes of action may be involved (Almeida et al., 2018; Le Magueresse-Battistoni et al., 2018; Mhaouty-Kodja et al., 2018). Based on the analysis of the experimental studies available, two PODs have initially been proposed: one at 0.5 µg/kg bw/day and one at 2 µg/kg bw/day.

These two PODs are derived from academic studies published in the peer-reviewed literature. Studies by Kolla et al., 2018 and by Kolla et al., 2019 and by Catanese and Vandenberg, 2017 were conducted by the oral route with at least two dose levels and identified a common LOAEL of 2 µg/kg bw/day for mammary gland and neurodevelopmental toxicity respectively. Moreover, most of the reviewed studies on BPS converged to this dose level. Therefore, and also based on the comments received during the commenting period, preference to the POD of 2 µg/kg bw/day is given in this report. This derived HBM-GV_{GenPop} is applicable to the whole general population and thereby is protective for all.

Nevertheless, we are also aware of the current assessment of BPS at the EU level, which may be finalised during the next months. Depending on the conclusion of this assessment, the derivation of the HBM-GVs for BPS could be updated. The HBM-GV_{GenPop} in this document is applicable to all groups of the general population.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 177

Regarding workers, no assessment of the relationship between atmospheric concentration of BPS and urinary concentration of total BPS is possible due to the scarcity of data on occupational exposure. Thus, the derivation method for HBM-GVs for BPS for both the general population and workers, is based on the same LOAEL identified from animal experimental studies. In addition, dermal absorption of BPS is very limited (<2 % *in vivo*) whereas BPS is well absorbed by oral route, it is therefore anticipated that the dermal route will contribute very little to the overall exposure to BPS. The relative contribution of the inhalation route may similarly be expected to be low, based on its physical-chemical properties (low vapor pressure) and by analogy with BPA risk assessments. Therefore, a 100 % oral exposure scenario was considered for the general population as well as for workers.

Although a weight of 70 kg may not be representative of women, especially non-pregnant women, this weight gives more conservative values for lighter women and seems appropriate for calculating HBV-GVs for a population including men and women. Additionally, as the most sensitive endpoint(s) to be protected from are the effects on the unborn child, the calculated HBV-GVs for men is probably highly conservative.

Consideration of the type and time of HBM sampling is crucial, because the proposed HBM-GVs should allow for direct comparison with HBM urinary data on BPS collected in general population or occupational biomonitoring studies. Within HBM4EU, it is decided to derive HBM-GVs for which interpretation of BPS exposure in a large population is possible provided spot-urine samples were collected at random times during the day, considering the arguments described below. It has to be noted though that high exposure is likely to be overestimated because spot urine sampling includes more sources of variability (e.g. within-person, within-day variability) than 24-hour urine sampling and that generic values in that case are generally used for the urinary output rate and bodyweight.

24-hour urine collections would be preferable, as both the urinary concentration of total BPS and the urinary output rate (mL/day) are measured. The geometric mean GM (or median) can directly be used as an estimate for the average exposure of the population, the 95th percentile might tend to overestimate the high exposure, as it includes not only the between-person variability but also the within-person between-day variation (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015). However, collecting 24-h urine voids in large biomonitoring studies is rarely feasible, mainly for reasons of cost and logistics.

The collection of first morning urine is a non-random, single-sample sampling that is not representative of daily variability. It may introduce a bias and may result in an over- or underestimation of average exposure, although the sparse evidence available from the literature indicates comparability of the central tendency between first morning voids, spot urine samples and 24-hour urine samples (Christensen et al., 2012; EFSA CEF Panel, 2015; Vernet et al., 2018).

The urinary concentration of total BPS in an individual spot urine sample cannot be used to arrive at a realistic estimate of daily BPS exposure, because of the non-persistent nature and short elimination half-life of BPS (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015). However, a set of spot urine samples can be used to obtain a reliable estimate of the average BPS exposure of a sufficiently large investigated population, provided that the sampling is at random in relation to meal ingestion and bladder-emptying times (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015). Vernet et al. (2018), who characterised the within-day, between-day and between-week variability of phenol urinary biomarker concentrations (e.g. BPA) during pregnancy, came to the same conclusion that for biomonitoring purposes (and not etiological studies), collecting spot biospecimens was a good option if the population was large enough.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 178

9 Factsheets

9.1 Factsheet reporting the HBM-GV_{GenPop} derivation

Bisphenol S (BPS)		Target population General population	
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
HBM-GV_{GenPop} and Status			
HBM-GV _{GenPop}	1	HBM-GV _{GenPop} for total BPS in urine: 1.0 µg/l	
Level of confidence	2	Medium-low	
HBM-GV status	3	Agreed on within HBM4EU	
HBM-GV year of issue	4	2020	
General Information			
CLP-INDEX-Nr.	5	/	
EC-Nr.	6	201-250-5	
CAS-Nr.	7	80-09-1	
Harmonised CLP classification	8	Not harmonised	
Molar mass	9	250.28 g/mol	
Biomarker(s)			
Identification	10	Total BPS in urine	
Molar mass of biomarker(s)	11	250.28 g/mol	
Half-life of selected biomarker(s)	12	Approximately 8 hours	Khmiri et al., 2020
Derivation method, starting point and assessment factors			
Type of derivation method selected	13	Translation of a POD identified from animal studies into urinary total BPS concentration	Use of the modified PBPK model of Karrer et al. 2018
Key study(ies)	14	Kolla et al., 2018, Kolla et al., 2019, Catanese and Vandenberg, 2017	
Exposure route of study	15	Oral	
Critical endpoint and POD	16	Increased number of terminal end buds in the mammary gland, dose dependent increase in ductal area in the mammary gland, neurobehavioral toxicity. (NOAEL= 2 µg/kg bw/day)	
Extrapolations and AFs	17	24h constant exposure to 0.0266 µg BPS/kg bw/d with global AF of 75	AFs: 3 for extrapolating the LOAEL to a NOAEL, 2.5 for interspecies differences; 10 for intraspecies differences

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 179

Bisphenol S (BPS)		Target population General population	
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
Calculation of HBM-GV_{GenPop}			
PBPK model for translating the selected exposure guidance value to an internal guidance value	18	Modified model from Karrer et al., 2018 PBPK Modeling of the Bisphenols BPA, BPS, BPF, and BPAF with New Experimental Metabolic Parameters: Comparing the Pharmacokinetic Behavior of BPA with its Substitutes	24h constant exposure to 0.0266 µg/kg bw (HED)
Rounded value of HBM-GVs_{GenPop}		HBM-GV_{GenPop} for total BPS in urine: 1.0 µg/l	
Additional Comments			

Explanation of notes:

1. HBM-GV_{GenPop}: numerical value of the HBM-GV_{GenPop} in µg/l
2. Level of confidence of the HBM-GV_{GenPop}:
Reflects the reliability of the proposed HBM-GV. The level of confidence takes into account the various uncertainties underlying the derivation of the HBM-GV (e.g. reliability of the key study used to derive the toxicity reference value (TRV), of toxicokinetic data on the substance of interest and of the extrapolations and calculation of the final HBM-GV). Attribution of a global level of confidence for the proposed BPS HBM-GV_{GenPop} is suggested, considering:
 - the nature and quality of the BPS epidemiological and/or toxicological data: BPS has recently replaced BPA for some specific uses and human data are limited. Some animal data have been recently published but the literature on this compound is still rapidly evolving. Moreover discrepancies have been observed in results reported in studies following OECD guidelines and in academic studies addressing more sensitive endpoints. Current assessment is on-going at EU level which may help to clarify the hazard profile of BPS → **low confidence**
 - the critical endpoint and mode of action: limited effects are reported in standard studies based on OECD guideline whereas in academic studies investigating more sensitive endpoints effects which may be related to an ED mode of action have been reported. However no robust modes of action to explain these effects have been validated yet → **low confidence**
 - the selected key study and POD: The human data is insufficient for the derivation of HBM-GVs. In addition, no toxicity reference values or occupational exposure limits have been proposed by EU or non-EU relevant organisations so far. Thus, the derivation method for HBM-GVs for BPS for the general population is based on a LOAEL identified from animal experimental studies via oral route. Studies by Kolla et al. (2018) in *Reprod. Tox.* and by Kolla et al., (2019) in *Toxicology* and by Catanese and Vandenberg, 2017 were conducted by the oral route with at least two dose levels and identified a common LOAEL of 2 µg/kg bw/day for mammary gland and neurobehavioral neurodevelopmental toxicity respectively. Moreover, most of the

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 180

reviewed studies on BPS converged to this dose level. Therefore and also based on the comments received during the commenting period, preference to the POD of 2 µg/kg bw/day is given in this report but as results obtained from OECD studies are in favour of much higher LOAEL/NOAEL (10 or 20 mg/kg bw/day), high level uncertainty is related to this POD which may be over conservative → **low confidence**

- the route-to-route, inter- and intra-species extrapolations: Unless results of Champmartin et al., 2020 are followed by further experimental studies to better appreciate the percentage of readily absorbable fraction of BPS, the HBM4EU Task 5-2 Team assumes that the dermal route will contribute very little to the overall exposure to BPS. The modified human PBPK model from Karrer et al. (2018) was used to determine the total BPS in urine. Making profit of the PBPK model that includes the oral and dermal routes of exposure, urinary total BPS values can be set according to estimated relative contributions of both routes of exposure → **medium confidence**
- the calculation of the HBM-GVs: The determination of the HBM-GV_{GenPop} is based on a continuous exposure to the 24h-average, but how this scenario reflects the environmental exposure to BPS remains uncertain. A high boundary value for total BPS in urine is proposed (consistent with a 100 % oral intake scenario), which does not completely reflect the most likely environmental exposure occurring mainly by oral, but also by inhalation and dermal absorption → **medium confidence**

Altogether, the global level of confidence for the BPS HBM-GV in the general population is set to '**medium-low**'.

3. HBM-GV_{GenPop} status: Agreed on within HBM4EU, the values were derived according to the feedback received in a consultation process.
4. HBM-GV_{GenPop} year of issue: year of setting the HBM-GV_{GenPop} in the frame of HBM4EU.
5. CLP Number: according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures, implementing the globally harmonised system of chemical classification or GHS
http://guidance.echa.europa.eu/docs/guidance_document/clp_introduutory_en.pdf
6. EC Number: under European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS), ELINCS (European List of Notified Chemical Substances) in support of Directive 92/32/EEC, the 7th amendment to Directive 67/548/EEC, NLP (No-Longer Polymers), see: ESIS: European chemical Substances Information System:
https://web.archive.org/web/20131106181548if_/http://esis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/
7. CAS Number: collection of disclosed chemical compound information by Chemical Abstracts Service. Almost all molecule databases can be searched by CAS Registry Number.
8. Harmonised CLP classification: CLP classification including CMR and other health relevant effects. In the case that classification is not harmonised, this should be stated. For self-classifications by industry the ECHA- CLP inventory can be searched at:
<http://echa.europa.eu/web/guest/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database>
9. Molar mass: mass of BPS per amount of this substance expressed in g/mol
10. Biomarker identification: the biomarker identified as relevant for interpreting exposures to BPS from population- or cohort-based biomonitoring studies is total BPS in urine.
11. Molar mass of the biomarker: mass of the selected biomarker (expressed in g/mol)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 181

12. Excretion half-life of selected biomarker: around 8h, according to volunteer-based studies from Khmiri et al., 2020.
13. The existing data base on BPS does not allow for the derivation of HBM-GVs from human data, based on a relationship between internal concentration of the selected biomarker and health effects. Therefore, the derivation method starts from an animal POD.
14. Key study: Kolla et al., 2018, Kolla et al., 2019, Catanese and Vandenberg, 2017
15. Exposure route: Oral exposure to BPS for all key studies.
16. Critical effect and POD: in the same order as in item 14 : Increased number of terminal end buds in the mammary gland, Dose dependent increase in ductal area in the mammary gland, neurobehavioral toxicity, altogether leading to a LOAEL of 2 µg/kg bw/day.
17. Extrapolations and AFs: A factor (AF) of 3 is applied for extrapolating a LOAEL to a NOAEL. The interspecies differences in toxicokinetics between animal species and human are determined by PBPK modeling, and an assessment factor of 2.5 is applied for remaining interspecies differences (mostly for toxicodynamic differences). Finally, an assessment factor of 10 is applied for intraspecies differences to take into account the variability of response in the general population
18. According to the modified Karrer et al. 2018 PBPK model, the concentrations of total BPS in urine corresponding to a 24h exposure to 0.0066 µg/kg bw/day through a 100 % oral intake are: **HBM-GV_{GenPop} for total BPS in urine: 1.0 µg/l.**

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 182

9.2 Factsheet reporting the HBM-GV_{worker} derivation

Bisphenol S (BPS)		Target population General population	
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
HBM-GV_{worker} and Status			
HBM-GV _{worker}	1	HBM-GV _{worker} for total BPS in urine: 3.0 µg/l	
Level of confidence	2	Medium-low	
HBM-GV status	3	Agreed on within HBM4EU	
HBM-GV year of issue	4	2020	
General Information			
CLP-INDEX-Nr.	5	/	
EC-Nr.	6	201-250-5	
CAS-Nr.	7	80-09-1	
Harmonised CLP classification	8	Not harmonised	
Molar mass	9	250.28 g/mol	
Biomarker(s)			
Identification	10	Total BPS in urine	
Molar mass of biomarker(s)	11	250.28 g/mol	
Half-life of selected biomarker(s)	12	Approximately 8 hours	Khmiri et al., 2020
Derivation method, starting point and assessment factors			
Type of derivation method selected	13	Translation of a POD identified from animal studies into urinary total BPS concentration	Use of the modified PBPK model of Karrer et al. 2018
Key study(ies)	14	Kolla et al., 2018, Kolla et al., 2019, Catanese and Vandenberg, 2017	
Exposure route of study	15	Oral	
Critical endpoint and POD	16	Increased number of terminal end buds in the mammary gland, dose dependent increase in ductal area in the mammary gland, neurobehavioral toxicity. (NOAEL= 2 µg/kg bw/day)	
Extrapolations and AFs	17	Estimated exposure to 0.0798 µg/kg bw from 0h to 8h and to 0 µg/kg bw from 8h to 24h each day during 5 days to mimic the work week. Global AF of 75	AFs: 3 for extrapolating the LOAEL to a NOAEL, 2.5 for interspecies differences; 10 for intraspecies differences
Calculation of HBM-GV_{worker}			
PBPK model for translating the selected exposure guidance value to an internal guidance value	18	Modified model from Karrer et al., 2018 PBPK Modeling of the Bisphenols BPA, BPS, BPF, and BPAF with New Experimental Metabolic Parameters: Comparing the Pharmacokinetic Behavior of BPA with its Substitutes	Estimated exposure to 0.0798 µg/kg bw from 0h to 8h and to 0 µg/kg bw from 8h to 24h each day during 5 days to mimic the work week which corresponds to an exposure all over the day

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 183

Bisphenol S (BPS)	Target population		
	General population		
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
			(0-24hour) of 0.0266 µg/kg bw/day.
Rounded value of HBM-GVs _{worker}		HBM-GV _{worker} for total BPS in urine: 3.0 µg/l	
Additional Comments			

Explanation of notes:

1. HBM-GV_{worker}: numerical value of the HBM-GV_{worker} in µg/l
2. Level of confidence of the HBM-GV_{worker}:
Reflects the reliability of the proposed HBM-GV. The level of confidence takes into account the various uncertainties underlying the derivation of the HBM-GV (e.g. reliability of the key study used to derive the toxicity reference value (TRV), uncertainties related to the calculation of the TRV, to toxicokinetic data on the substance of interest and to the extrapolations and calculation of the final HBM-GV). Attribution of a global level of confidence for the proposed BPS HBM-GV_{worker} is suggested, considering:
 - the nature and quality of the BPS epidemiological and/or toxicological data: BPS has recently replaced BPA for some specific uses and human data are limited. Some animal data have been recently published but the literature on this compound is still rapidly evolving. Moreover discrepancies have been observed in results reported in studies following OECD guidelines and in academic studies addressing more sensitive endpoints. Current assessment is on-going at EU level which may help to clarify the hazard profile of BPS → **low confidence**
 - the critical endpoint and mode of action: clear reproductive toxicity is observed in standard studies following OECD guidelines leading to a classification proposal as Repr. 1B H360FD by the dossier submitter whereas academic studies investigating more sensitive endpoints effects which may be related to an ED mode of action have been reported. This leads to a different set of N(L)OAE. However no robust modes of action to explain these effects have been validated yet, → **low confidence**
 - the selected key study and POD: The human data is insufficient for the derivation of HBM guidance values. In addition, no toxicity reference values or occupational exposure limits have been proposed by EU or non-EU relevant organisations so far. Regarding workers, the scarcity of data on occupational exposure does not allow to demonstrate a relationship between atmospheric concentration of BPS and urinary concentration of total BPS. Thus, the derivation method for HBM-GVs for BPS for the workers, is based on a LOAEL identified from animal experimental studies via oral route. Studies by Kolla et al., (2018) in *Reprod. Tox.* and by Kolla et al., (2019) in *Toxicology* and by Catanese and Vandenberg, 2017 were conducted by the oral route with at least two dose levels and identified a common LOAEL of 2 µg/kg bw/day for mammary gland and neurobehavioral neurodevelopmental toxicity respectively. Moreover, most of the reviewed studies on BPS converged to this dose level. Therefore and also based on the comments received during the commenting period, preference to the POD of 2 µg/kg bw/day is given in this report but as results obtained from OECD studies are in favour of

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 184

much higher LOAEL/NOAEL (10 or 20 mg/kg bw/day), high level uncertainty is related to this POD which may be over conservative → **low confidence**

- the route-to-route, inter- and intra-species extrapolations: Unless results of Champmartin et al., 2020 are followed by further experimental studies to better appreciate the percentage of readily absorbable fraction of BPS, the HBM4EU Task 5-2 Team assumes that the dermal route will contribute very little to the overall exposure to BPS. The modified human PBPK model from Karrer et al. (2018) was used to determine the total BPS in urine. Making profit of the PBPK model that includes the oral and dermal routes of exposure, urinary total BPS values can be set according to estimated relative contributions of both routes of exposure → **medium confidence**
- the calculation of the HBM-GVs: the determination of the HBM-GV_{workers} is based on a continuous exposure to the working day 8h-averaged, but how this scenario reflects the environmental exposure to BPS remains uncertain. A high boundary value for total BPS in urine is proposed (consistent with a 100 % oral intake scenario), which does not completely reflect the most likely occupational exposure occurring mainly by oral, but also by inhalation and dermal absorption → **medium confidence**

Altogether, the global level of confidence for the BPS HBM-GV in the occupational population is set to **'medium-low'**.

3. HBM-GV_{GenPop} status: Agreed on within HBM4EU, the values were derived according to the feedback received in a consultation process.
4. HBM-GV_{GenPop} year of issue: year of setting the HBM-GV_{GenPop} in the frame of HBM4EU.
5. CLP Number: according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures, implementing the globally harmonised system of chemical classification or GHS
http://guidance.echa.europa.eu/docs/guidance_document/clp_introduutory_en.pdf
6. EC Number: under European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS), ELINCS (European List of Notified Chemical Substances) in support of Directive 92/32/EEC, the 7th amendment to Directive 67/548/EEC, NLP (No-Longer Polymers), see: ESIS: European chemical Substances Information System:
https://web.archive.org/web/20131106181548if_/http://esis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/
7. CAS Number: collection of disclosed chemical compound information by Chemical Abstracts Service. Almost all molecule databases can be searched by CAS Registry Number.
8. Harmonised CLP classification: CLP classification including CMR and other health relevant effects. In the case that classification is not harmonised, this should be stated. For self-classifications by industry the ECHA- CLP inventory can be searched at:
<http://echa.europa.eu/web/guest/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database>
9. Molar mass: mass of BPS per amount of this substance expressed in g/mol
10. Biomarker identification: the biomarker identified as relevant for interpreting exposures to BPS from population- or cohort-based biomonitoring studies is total BPS in urine.
11. Molar mass of the biomarker: mass of the selected biomarker (expressed in g/mol)
12. Excretion half-life of selected biomarker: around 8h, according to volunteer-based studies from Khmiri et al., 2020.
13. The existing data base on BPS does not allow for the derivation of HBM-GVs from human data, based on a relationship between internal concentration of the selected biomarker and health effects. Therefore, the derivation method starts from an animal POD.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 185

14. Key study: Kolla et al., 2018, Kolla et al., 2019, Catanese and Vandenberg, 2017
15. Exposure route: Oral exposure to BPS for all key studies.
16. Critical effect and POD: in the same order as in item 14 : Increased number of terminal end buds in the mammary gland, Dose dependent increase in ductal area in the mammary gland, neurobehavioral toxicity, altogether leading to a LOAEL of 2 µg/kg bw/day.
17. Extrapolations and AFs: A factor of 3 is applied for extrapolating a LOAEL to a NOAEL. The interspecies differences in toxicokinetics between animal species and human are determined by PBPK modeling, and an assessment factor of 2.5 is applied for remaining interspecies differences (mostly for toxicodynamic differences). Finally, a factor of 10 accounting for intra-species differences is further applied to the human adjusted NOAEL. Generally, this factor is set to 5 when workers are the targeted population for which the HBM-GV is derived, in line with ECHA's R8 guidance for deriving DNELs for worker (ECHA, 2012). However, in case of BPS the most sensitive endpoint(s) to be protected from are the effects on the unborn child. Thus, no differences can be assumed between the foetuses of the general population and the workers.
18. According to the modified Karrer et al. 2018 PBPK model, the concentrations of total BPS in urine corresponding to a 0.0198 µg/kg bw from 0h to 8h and to 0 µg/kg bw from 8h to 24h each day during 5 days to mimic the work week, through a 100 % oral intake are: **HBM-GVworker for total BPS in urine: 3.0 µg/l**

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 186

10 References

- Ahsan, N., H. Ullah, W. Ullah and S. Jahan, 2018: Comparative effects of Bisphenol S and Bisphenol A on the development of female reproductive system in rats; a neonatal exposure study. *Chemosphere* 197, 336-343.
- Aker, A. M., L. Johns, T. F. McElrath, D. E. Cantonwine, B. Mukherjee and J. D. Meeker, 2018: Associations between maternal phenol and paraben urinary biomarkers and maternal hormones during pregnancy: A repeated measures study. *Environ Int* 113, 341-349.
- Almeida, D. L., A. Pavanello, L. P. Saavedra, T. S. Pereira, M. A. A. de Castro-Prado and P. C. de Freitas Mathias, 2019: Environmental monitoring and the developmental origins of health and disease. *Journal of developmental origins of health and disease*, 1-8.
- Apel, P., C. Rousselle, R. Lange, F. Sissoko, M. Kolossa-Gehring and E. Ougier, 2020: Human Biomonitoring initiative (HBM4EU) - Strategy to derive Human Biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) for health risk assessment. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health* 230, 113622.
- Ashrap, P., D. J. Watkins, A. M. Calafat, X. Ye, Z. Rosario, P. Brown, C. M. Velez-Vega, A. Alshwabkeh, J. F. Cordero and J. D. Meeker, 2018: Elevated concentrations of urinary triclocarban, phenol and paraben among pregnant women in Northern Puerto Rico: Predictors and trends. *Environ Int* 121, 990-1002.
- Asimakopoulos, A. G., J. Xue, B. P. De Carvalho, A. Iyer, K. O. Abualnaja, S. S. Yaghmoor, T. A. Kumosani and K. Kannan, 2016: Urinary biomarkers of exposure to 57 xenobiotics and its association with oxidative stress in a population in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. *Environ Res* 150, 573-581.
- Aung, M. T., K. K. Ferguson, D. E. Cantonwine, T. F. McElrath and J. D. Meeker, 2019: Preterm birth in relation to the bisphenol A replacement, bisphenol S, and other phenols and parabens. *Environ Res* 169, 131-138.
- Azevedo, L. F., M. F. Hornos Carneiro, C. R. P. Dechandt, J. S. Cassoli, L. C. Alberici and F. Barbosa, 2020: Global liver proteomic analysis of Wistar rats chronically exposed to low-levels of bisphenol A and S. *Environmental Research* 182, 109080.
- Azevedo, L. F., C. R. Porto Dechandt, C. Cristina de Souza Rocha, M. F. Hornos Carneiro, L. C. Alberici and F. Barbosa, Jr., 2019: Long-term exposure to bisphenol A or S promotes glucose intolerance and changes hepatic mitochondrial metabolism in male Wistar rats. *Food Chem Toxicol* 132, 110694.
- BASF, 2014: Bisphenol S study Repeated Dose 90-Day Oral Toxicity in Rodents conducted according to OECD Guideline 408.
- Bjornsdotter, M. K., W. Jonker, J. Legradi, J. Kool and A. Ballesteros-Gomez, 2017: Bisphenol A alternatives in thermal paper from the Netherlands, Spain, Sweden and Norway. Screening and potential toxicity. *Sci Total Environ* 601-602, 210-221.
- Boucher, J. G., S. Ahmed and E. Atlas, 2016: Bisphenol S Induces Adipogenesis in Primary Human Preadipocytes From Female Donors. *Endocrinology* 157, 1397-1407.
- Boucher, J. G., R. Gagné, A. Rowan-Carroll, A. Boudreau, C. L. Yauk and E. Atlas, 2016: Bisphenol A and Bisphenol S Induce Distinct Transcriptional Profiles in Differentiating Human Primary Preadipocytes. *PLoS ONE* 11, e0163318.
- Boudalia, S., R. Berges, C. Chabanet, M. Folia, L. Decocq, B. Pasquis, L. Abdennebi-Najar and M. C. Canivenc-Lavier, 2014: A multi-generational study on low-dose BPA exposure in Wistar rats: effects on maternal behavior, flavor intake and development. *Neurotoxicology and teratology* 41, 16-26.
- Brulport, A., D. Vaiman, M. C. Chagnon and L. Le Corre, 2019: Obesogen effect of bisphenol S alters mRNA expression and DNA methylation profiling in male mouse liver. *Chemosphere* 241, 125092.
- Castro, B., P. Sanchez, J. M. Torres and E. Ortega, 2015: Bisphenol A, bisphenol F and bisphenol S affect differently 5alpha-reductase expression and dopamine-serotonin systems in the prefrontal cortex of juvenile female rats. *Environ Res* 142, 281-287.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 187

- Catanese, M. C. and L. N. Vandenberg, 2017: Bisphenol S (BPS) Alters Maternal Behavior and Brain in Mice Exposed During Pregnancy/Lactation and Their Daughters. *Endocrinology* 158, 516-530.
- Cesen, M., K. Lenarcic, V. Mislej, M. Levstek, A. Kovacic, B. Cimrmancic, N. Uranjek, T. Kosjek, D. Heath, M. S. Dolenc and E. Heath, 2018: The occurrence and source identification of bisphenol compounds in wastewaters. *Sci Total Environ* 616-617, 744-752.
- Champmartin, C., F. Marquet, L. Chedik, M. J. Décret, M. Aubertin, E. Ferrari, M. C. Grandclaude and F. Cosnier, 2020: Human in vitro percutaneous absorption of bisphenol S and bisphenol A: A comparative study. *Chemosphere* 252, 126525.
- Charisiadis, P., X. D. Andrianou, T. P. van der Meer, W. F. A. den Dunnen, D. F. Swaab, B. H. R. Wolffenbuttel, K. C. Makris and J. V. van Vliet-Ostaptchouk, 2018: Possible Obesogenic Effects of Bisphenols Accumulation in the Human Brain. *Sci Rep* 8, 8186.
- Chen, D., K. Kannan, H. Tan, Z.-G. Zheng, Y.-L. Feng, Y. Wu and M. Widelka, 2016: Bisphenol Analogues Other Than BPA: Environmental Occurrence, Human Exposure, and Toxicity - A Review. *Environ Sci Technol* 50, 5438-5453.
- Chen, Y., J. Fang, L. Ren, R. Fan, J. Zhang, G. Liu, L. Zhou, D. Chen, Y. Yu and S. Lu, 2018: Urinary bisphenol analogues and triclosan in children from south China and implications for human exposure. *Environ Pollut* 238, 299-305.
- Chen, Y., L. Shu, Z. Qiu, D. Y. Lee, S. J. Settle, S. Que Hee, D. Telesca, X. Yang and P. Allard, 2016: Exposure to the BPA-Substitute Bisphenol S Causes Unique Alterations of Germline Function. *PLoS Genet* 12, e1006223.
- Christensen, K. L., M. Lorber, H. M. Koch, M. Kolossa-Gehring and M. K. Morgan, 2012: Population variability of phthalate metabolites and bisphenol A concentrations in spot urine samples versus 24- or 48-h collections. *Journal of exposure science & environmental epidemiology* 22, 632-640.
- da Silva, B. S., C. B. Pietrobon, I. M. Bertasso, B. P. Lopes, J. C. Carvalho, N. Peixoto-Silva, T. R. Santos, S. Claudio-Neto, A. C. Manhaes, E. Oliveira, E. G. de Moura and P. C. Lisboa, 2019: Short and long-term effects of bisphenol S (BPS) exposure during pregnancy and lactation on plasma lipids, hormones, and behavior in rats. *Environ Pollut* 250, 312-322.
- Della Seta, D., I. Minder, F. Dessì-Fulgheri and F. Farabolini, 2005: Bisphenol-A exposure during pregnancy and lactation affects maternal behavior in rats. *Brain research bulletin* 65, 255-260.
- Demacopulo, B. and E. L. Kreimann, 2019: Bisphenol S increases EZRIN expression and the detrimental effects induced by dehydroepiandrosterone in rat endometrium. *Molecular and cellular endocrinology* 483, 64-73.
- Derakhshan, A., H. Shu, R. P. Peeters, A. Kortenkamp, C. H. Lindh, B. Demeneix, C. G. Bornehag and T. I. M. Korevaar, 2019: Association of urinary bisphenols and triclosan with thyroid function during early pregnancy. *Environ Int* 133, 105123.
- Dissemination, E., 2018
4,4'-Sulphonyldiphenol.
- Dualde, P., O. Pardo, F. Corpas-Burgos, J. Kuligowski, M. Gormaz, M. Vento, A. Pastor and V. Yusa, 2019a: Biomonitoring of bisphenols A, F, S in human milk and probabilistic risk assessment for breastfed infants. *Sci Total Environ* 668, 797-805.
- Dualde, P., O. Pardo, F. F. S, A. Pastor and V. Yusa, 2019b: Determination of four parabens and bisphenols A, F and S in human breast milk using QuEChERS and liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry. *J Chromatogr B Analyt Technol Biomed Life Sci* 1114-1115, 154-166.
- Duan, Y., Y. Yao, B. Wang, L. Han, L. Wang, H. Sun and L. Chen, 2018: Association of urinary concentrations of bisphenols with type 2 diabetes mellitus: A case-control study. *Environ Pollut* 243, 1719-1726.
- ECHA, 2012: Guidance on information requirements and chemical safety assessment. Chapter R.8: Characterisation of dose [concentration]-response for human health.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 188

ECHA, 2014: Market Survey: Use of bisphenol A and its alternatives in thermal paper in the EU from 2014 to 2017.

ECHA. (2016a). "CORAP Substance Evaluation Decision for 4,4'-sulfonyldiphenol." 2018, from <https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/776a7a2e-1526-430a-8630-70163473dfc0>.

ECHA. (2016b). "Decision on Substance Evaluation Pursuant to Article 46(1) of Regulation (Ec) No 1907/2006 for 4,4'-sulfonyldiphenol, CAS No 80-09-1 (EC No 201-250-5)." from <https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/082378e5-a1a7-0610-a4c8-b14b6534ef0d>.

ECHA, 2016c: Regulatory management options analysis on Bisphenol S.

ECHA. (2020a). "ECHA - The use of bisphenol A and its alternatives in thermal paper in the EU during 2014 – 2022. ." from

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/23294236/bpa_thermal_paper_report_2020_en.pdf/59eca269-c788-7942-5c17-3bd822d9cba0

ECHA. (2020b). "ECHA (2020) Substance Information 4,4'-methylenediphenol." from <https://echa.europa.eu/substance-information/-/substanceinfo/100.009.691>.

ECHA, 2020c: Toxicokinetics, metabolism and distribution experimental data on Bisphenol S.

ECHA C&L Inventory. (2019, October 2019 version 2). "Classification and Labelling Inventory: Harmonised Classification - Annex VI of Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008 (CLP Regulation)." Retrieved 2019, from https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/17218/clh_rep_4-4-sulphonyldiphenol_annex_en.pdf/1394bc9e-f09b-9db0-457b-a18b7c19663c.

ECHA Dissemination. (2020, 16 July 2020). "4,4'-Sulphonyldiphenol." Retrieved 20. July 2018, 2018, from <https://echa.europa.eu/registration-dossier/-/registered-dossier/14986>.

Eckardt, M. and T. J. Simat, 2017: Bisphenol A and alternatives in thermal paper receipts - a German market analysis from 2015 to 2017. *Chemosphere* 186, 1016-1025.

EFSA, 2015: Scientific Opinion on the risks to public health related to the presence of bisphenol A (BPA) in foodstuffs: Executive summary. EFSA Panel on Food Contact Materials, Enzymes, Flavourings and Processing Aids (CEF). *The EFSA Journal* 13, 1040.

EFSA, 2020: Assessment of new information on Bisphenol S (BPS) submitted in response to the Decision 1 under REACH Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006.

Eladak, S., T. Grisin, D. Moison, M. J. Guerquin, T. N'Tumba-Byn, S. Pozzi-Gaudin, A. Benachi, G. Livera, V. Rouiller-Fabre and R. Habert, 2015: A new chapter in the bisphenol A story: bisphenol S and bisphenol F are not safe alternatives to this compound. *Fertil Steril* 103, 11-21.

Ferguson, K. K., J. D. Meeker, D. E. Cantonwine, B. Mukherjee, G. G. Pace, D. Weller and T. F. McElrath, 2018: Environmental phenol associations with ultrasound and delivery measures of fetal growth. *Environment International* 112, 243-250.

Fic, A., B. Zegura, M. Sollner Dolenc, M. Filipic and L. Peterlin Masic, 2013: Mutagenicity and DNA damage of bisphenol A and its structural analogues in HepG2 cells. *Arh Hig Rada Toksikol* 64, 189-200.

Fujiwara, Y., W. Miyazaki, N. Koibuchi and T. Katoh, 2018: The Effects of Low-Dose Bisphenol A and Bisphenol F on Neural Differentiation of a Fetal Brain-Derived Neural Progenitor Cell Line. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)* 9, 24.

Gao, C. J. and K. Kannan, 2020: Phthalates, bisphenols, parabens, and triclocarban in feminine hygiene products from the United States and their implications for human exposure. *Environ Int* 136, 105465.

Gao, P., L. Wang, N. Yang, J. Wen, M. Zhao, G. Su, J. Zhang and D. Weng, 2020: Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma (PPARgamma) activation and metabolism disturbance induced by bisphenol A and its replacement analog bisphenol S using in vitro macrophages and in vivo mouse models. *Environ Int* 134, 105328.

Gauderat, G., N. Picard-Hagen, P. L. Toutain, T. Corbel, C. Viguié, S. Puel, M. Z. Lacroix, P. Mindeguia, A. Bousquet-Melou and V. Gayrard, 2016: Bisphenol A glucuronide deconjugation is a determining factor of fetal exposure to bisphenol A. *Environ Int* 86, 52-59.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 189

Gayrard, V., M. Z. Lacroix, C. A. Gely, F. C. Grandin, R. Leandri, M. Bouchard, B. Roques, P. L. Toutain and N. Picard-Hagen, 2020: Toxicokinetics of bisphenol S in rats for predicting human bisphenol S clearance from allometric scaling. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol* 386, 114845.

Gayrard, V., M. Z. Lacroix, F. C. Grandin, S. H. Collet, H. Mila, C. Viguie, C. A. Gely, B. Rabozzi, M. Bouchard, R. Leandri, P. L. Toutain and N. Picard-Hagen, 2019: Oral Systemic Bioavailability of Bisphenol A and Bisphenol S in Pigs. *Environ Health Perspect* 127, 77005.

Gingrich, J., Y. Pu, R. Ehrhardt, R. Karthikraj, K. Kannan and A. Veiga-Lopez, 2019: Toxicokinetics of bisphenol A, bisphenol S, and bisphenol F in a pregnancy sheep model. *Chemosphere* 220, 185-194.

Goldinger, D. M., A. L. Demierre, O. Zoller, H. Rupp, H. Reinhard, R. Magnin, T. W. Becker and M. Bourqui-Pittet, 2015: Endocrine activity of alternatives to BPA found in thermal paper in Switzerland. *Regul Toxicol Pharmacol* 71, 453-462.

Gonzalez, N., S. C. Cunha, C. Monteiro, J. O. Fernandes, M. Marques, J. L. Domingo and M. Nadal, 2019: Quantification of eight bisphenol analogues in blood and urine samples of workers in a hazardous waste incinerator. *Environ Res* 176, 108576.

Gorence, G. J., H. C. Pulcastro, C. A. Lawson, R. R. Gerona, M. Friesen, T. S. Horan, M. C. Gieske, C. V. Sartain and P. A. Hunt, 2019: Chemical Contaminants from Plastics in the Animal Environment. *Journal of the American Association for Laboratory Animal Science* : JAALAS 58, 190-196.

Gramec Skledar, D. and L. Peterlin Masic, 2016: Bisphenol A and its analogs: Do their metabolites have endocrine activity? *Environ Toxicol Pharmacol* 47, 182-199.

Gramec Skledar, D., J. Troberg, J. Lavdas, L. Peterlin Masic and M. Finel, 2015: Differences in the glucuronidation of bisphenols F and S between two homologous human UGT enzymes, 1A9 and 1A10. *Xenobiotica* 45, 511-519.

Grandin, F., N. Picard-Hagen, V. Gayrard, S. Puel, C. Viguie, P. L. Toutain, L. Debrauwer and M. Z. Lacroix, 2017: Development of an on-line solid phase extraction ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography technique coupled to tandem mass spectrometry for quantification of bisphenol S and bisphenol S glucuronide: Applicability to toxicokinetic investigations. *J Chromatogr A* 1526, 39-46.

Grandin, F. C., V. Gayrard, M. Z. Lacroix, N. Picard-Hagen, H. Mila and P. L. Toutain, 2018: Comment on 'Pharmacokinetics of bisphenol S in humans after a single oral administration'. *Environ Int* 116, 29.

Grandin, F. C., V. Gayrard, N. Picard-Hagen and P. L. Toutain, 2019: Comment on "Toxicokinetics of bisphenol A, bisphenol S, and bisphenol F in a pregnancy sheep model". *Chemosphere* 227, 703-704.

Grandin, F. C., M. Z. Lacroix, V. Gayrard, G. Gauderat, H. Mila, P. L. Toutain and N. Picard-Hagen, 2018: Bisphenol S instead of Bisphenol A: Toxicokinetic investigations in the ovine materno-feto-placental unit. *Environ Int* 120, 584-592.

Grandin, F. C., M. Z. Lacroix, V. Gayrard, C. Viguie, H. Mila, A. de Place, C. Vayssiere, M. Morin, J. Corbett, C. Gayrard, C. A. Gely, P. L. Toutain and N. Picard-Hagen, 2019: Is bisphenol S a safer alternative to bisphenol A in terms of potential fetal exposure? Placental transfer across the perfused human placenta. *Chemosphere* 221, 471-478.

Grimaldi, M., A. Boulahtouf, L. Toporova and P. Balaguer, 2019: Functional profiling of bisphenols for nuclear receptors. *Toxicology* 420, 39-45.

Grumetto, L., F. Barbato and G. Russo, 2019: Scrutinising the interactions between bisphenol analogues and plasma proteins: Insights from biomimetic liquid chromatography, molecular docking simulations and in silico predictions. *Environ Toxicol Pharmacol* 68, 148-154.

Hanioka, N., T. Naito and S. Narimatsu, 2008: Human UDP-glucuronosyltransferase isoforms involved in bisphenol A glucuronidation. *Chemosphere* 74, 33-36.

Hercog, K., S. Maisanaba, M. Filipic, M. Sollner-Dolenc, L. Kac and B. Zegura, 2019: Genotoxic activity of bisphenol A and its analogues bisphenol S, bisphenol F and bisphenol AF and their mixtures in human hepatocellular carcinoma (HepG2) cells. *Sci Total Environ* 687, 267-276.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 190

Hill, C. E., S. A. Sapouckey, A. Suvorov and L. N. Vandenberg, 2017: Developmental exposures to bisphenol S, a BPA replacement, alter estrogen-responsiveness of the female reproductive tract: A pilot study. *Cogent Medicine* 4.

Horan, T. S., H. Pulcastro, C. Lawson, R. Gerona, S. Martin, M. C. Gieske, C. V. Sartain and P. A. Hunt, 2018: Replacement Bisphenols Adversely Affect Mouse Gametogenesis with Consequences for Subsequent Generations. *Current biology: CB* 28, 2948-2954.e2943.

Husoy, T., M. Andreassen, H. Hjertholm, M. H. Carlsen, N. Norberg, C. Sprong, E. Papadopoulou, A. K. Sakhi, A. Sabaredzovic and H. Dirven, 2019: The Norwegian biomonitoring study from the EU project EuroMix: Levels of phenols and phthalates in 24-hour urine samples and exposure sources from food and personal care products. *Environ Int* 132, 105103.

Ilde, E. S., S. Zamudio, J. M. Loh, Y. Zhu, J. Woytanowski, L. Rosen, M. Liu and B. Buckley, 2018: Application of a novel mass spectrometric (MS) method to examine exposure to Bisphenol-A and common substitutes in a maternal fetal cohort. *Hum Ecol Risk Assess* 24, 331-346.

Ijaz, S., A. Ullah, G. Shaheen and S. Jahan, 2019: Exposure of BPA and its alternatives like BPB, BPF, and BPS impair subsequent reproductive potentials in adult female Sprague Dawley rats. *Toxicol Mech Methods*, 1-13.

Inoue, H., S. Kemanai, C. Sano, S. Kato, H. Yokota and H. Iwano, 2016: Bisphenol A glucuronide/sulfate diconjugate in perfused liver of rats. *J Vet Med Sci* 78, 733-737.

Ivry Del Moral, L., L. Le Corre, H. Poirier, I. Niot, T. Truntzer, J. F. Merlin, P. Rouimi, P. Besnard, R. Rahmani and M. C. Chagnon, 2016: Obesogen effects after perinatal exposure of 4,4'-sulfonyldiphenol (Bisphenol S) in C57BL/6 mice. *Toxicology* 357-358, 11-20.

Iwano, H., N. Ohtani, N. Hozumi, H. Inoue and H. Yokota, 2016: Pharmacokinetic study of adverse effects in offspring caused by prenatal Bisphenol F exposure. *Toxicology Letters* 259, S113.

Jacobson, M. H., M. Woodward, W. Bao, B. Liu and L. Trasande, 2019: Urinary Bisphenols and Obesity Prevalence Among U.S. Children and Adolescents. *Journal of the Endocrine Society* 3, 1715-1726.

Jäger, T., S. Bäcker, O. Schmid, C. Ehnes and M. Bader, 2018: Entwicklung eines LC-MS/MS-Verfahrens für das Human-Biomonitoring von Bisphenol S im Urin und Ergebnisse einer Stichprobenuntersuchung zur allgemeinen Hintergrundbelastung. pp. 76-77. DGAUM: Deutsche Gesellschaft für Arbeitsmedizin und Umweltmedizin e.V., Stuttgart.

JECDB, 2001: 4,4'-Sulfonyldiphenol: Reproduction/Developmental Toxicity Screening Test (in Japanese).

Jelen, G., C. Cavelier, J. P. Protois and J. Fousseureau, 1989: A new allergen responsible for shoe allergy: chloroacetamide. *Contact dermatitis* 21, 110-111.

Jin, H., J. Xie, L. Mao, M. Zhao, X. Bai, J. Wen, T. Shen and P. Wu, 2020: Bisphenol analogue concentrations in human breast milk and their associations with postnatal infant growth. *Environ Pollut* 259, 113779.

Jin, H., J. Zhu, Z. Chen, Y. Hong and Z. Cai, 2018: Occurrence and Partitioning of Bisphenol Analogues in Adults' Blood from China. *Environ Sci Technol* 52, 812-820.

Jing, J., Y. Pu, J. Gingrich and A. Veiga-Lopez, 2019: Gestational Exposure to Bisphenol A and Bisphenol S Leads to Fetal Skeletal Muscle Hypertrophy Independent of Sex. *Toxicol Sci* 172, 292-302.

John, N., H. Rehman, S. Razak, M. David, W. Ullah, T. Afsar, A. Almajwal, I. Alam and S. Jahan, 2019: Comparative study of environmental pollutants bisphenol A and bisphenol S on sexual differentiation of anteroventral periventricular nucleus and spermatogenesis. *Reprod Biol Endocrinol* 17, 53.

Kang, S., B. H. Shin, J. A. Kwon, C. W. Lee, E. K. Park, E. Y. Park and B. Kim, 2020: Urinary bisphenol A and its analogues and haemato-biochemical alterations of pregnant women in Korea. *Environ Res* 182, 109104.

Karrer, C., T. Roiss, N. von Goetz, D. Gramec Skledar, L. Peterlin Masic and K. Hungerbühler, 2018: Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) Modeling of the Bisphenols BPA, BPS, BPF, and BPAF with

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 191

New Experimental Metabolic Parameters: Comparing the Pharmacokinetic Behavior of BPA with Its Substitutes. *Environ Health Perspect* 126, 077002.

Kataria, A., D. Levine, S. Wertenteil, S. Vento, J. Xue, K. Rajendiran, K. Kannan, J. M. Thurman, D. Morrison, R. Brody, E. Urbina, T. Attina, L. Trasande and H. Trachtman, 2017: Exposure to bisphenols and phthalates and association with oxidant stress, insulin resistance, and endothelial dysfunction in children. *Pediatr Res* 81, 857-864.

Katsikantami, I., M. N. Tzatzarakis, V. Karzi, A. Stavroulaki, P. Xezonaki, E. Vakonaki, A. K. Alegakis, S. Sifakis, A. K. Rizos and A. M. Tsatsakis, 2020: Biomonitoring of bisphenols A and S and phthalate metabolites in hair from pregnant women in Crete. *Sci Total Environ* 712, 135651.

Khmiri, I., J. Cote, M. Mantha, R. Khemiri, M. Lacroix, C. Gely, P. L. Toutain, N. Picard-Hagen, V. Gayraud and M. Bouchard, 2020: Toxicokinetics of bisphenol-S and its glucuronide in plasma and urine following oral and dermal exposure in volunteers for the interpretation of biomonitoring data. *Environ Int* 138, 105644.

Kolatorova, L., J. Vitku, R. Hampl, K. Adamcova, T. Skodova, M. Simkova, A. Parizek, L. Starka and M. Duskova, 2018: Exposure to bisphenols and parabens during pregnancy and relations to steroid changes. *Environ Res* 163, 115-122.

Kolla, S., D. B. McSweeney, A. Pokharel and L. N. Vandenberg, 2019: Bisphenol S alters development of the male mouse mammary gland and sensitises it to a peripubertal estrogen challenge. *Toxicology* 424.

Kolla, S., M. Morcos, B. Martin and L. N. Vandenberg, 2018: Low dose bisphenol S or ethinyl estradiol exposures during the perinatal period alter female mouse mammary gland development. *Reprod Toxicol* 78, 50-59.

Kolla, S. D. D. and L. N. Vandenberg, 2019: Data describing effects of perinatal exposure to bisphenol S on a peripubertal estrogen challenge in intact female CD-1 mice. *Data Brief* 25, 103862.

Kurebayashi, H., K. Okudaira and Y. Ohno, 2010: Species difference of metabolic clearance of bisphenol A using cryopreserved hepatocytes from rats, monkeys and humans. *Toxicol Lett* 198, 210-215.

LaPlante, C. D., M. C. Catanese, R. Bansal and L. N. Vandenberg, 2017: Bisphenol S Alters the Lactating Mammary Gland and Nursing Behaviors in Mice Exposed During Pregnancy and Lactation. *Endocrinology* 158, 3448-3461.

Le Fol, V., S. Ait-Aissa, N. Cabaton, L. Dolo, M. Grimaldi, P. Balaguer, E. Perdu, L. Debrauwer, F. Brion and D. Zalko, 2015: Cell-specific biotransformation of benzophenone-2 and bisphenol-s in zebrafish and human in vitro models used for toxicity and estrogenicity screening. *Environ Sci Technol* 49, 3860-3868.

Le Fol, V., S. Ait-Aissa, M. Sonavane, J. M. Porcher, P. Balaguer, J. P. Cravedi, D. Zalko and F. Brion, 2017: In vitro and in vivo estrogenic activity of BPA, BPF and BPS in zebrafish-specific assays. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf* 142, 150-156.

Le Magueresse-Battistoni, B., L. Multigner, C. Beausoleil and C. Rousselle, 2018: Effects of bisphenol A on metabolism and evidences of a mode of action mediated through endocrine disruption. *Molecular and cellular endocrinology*.

Lehmler, H. J., B. Liu, M. Gadogbe and W. Bao, 2018: Exposure to Bisphenol A, Bisphenol F, and Bisphenol S in U.S. Adults and Children: The National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey 2013-2014. *ACS Omega* 3, 6523-6532.

Li, A., T. Zhuang, W. Shi, Y. Liang, C. Liao, M. Song and G. Jiang, 2020: Serum concentration of bisphenol analogues in pregnant women in China. *Sci Total Environ* 707, 136100.

Liao, C. and K. Kannan, 2013: Concentrations and Profiles of Bisphenol A and Other Bisphenol Analogues in Foodstuffs from the United States and Their Implications for Human Exposure. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* 61, 4655-4662.

Liao, C. and K. Kannan, 2014a: A survey of alkylphenols, bisphenols, and triclosan in personal care products from China and the United States. *Arch Environ Contam Toxicol* 67, 50-59.

Liao, C. and K. Kannan, 2014b: A survey of bisphenol A and other bisphenol analogues in foodstuffs from nine cities in China. *Food Additives & Contaminants: Part A* 31, 319-329.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 192

Liu, B., H. J. Lehmler, Y. Sun, G. Xu, Y. Liu, G. Zong, Q. Sun, F. B. Hu, R. B. Wallace and W. Bao, 2017: Bisphenol A substitutes and obesity in US adults: analysis of a population-based, cross-sectional study. *Lancet Planet Health* 1, e114-e122.

Liu, B., H. J. Lehmler, Y. Sun, G. Xu, Q. Sun, L. G. Snetselaar, R. B. Wallace and W. Bao, 2019: Association of Bisphenol A and Its Substitutes, Bisphenol F and Bisphenol S, with Obesity in United States Children and Adolescents. *Diabetes & metabolism journal* 43, 59-75.

Liu, J. and J. W. Martin, 2017: Prolonged Exposure to Bisphenol A from Single Dermal Contact Events. *Environ Sci Technol* 51, 9940-9949.

Liu, J. and J. W. Martin, 2019: Comparison of Bisphenol A and Bisphenol S Percutaneous Absorption and Biotransformation. *Environ Health Perspect* 127, 67008.

Machtinger, R., T. Berman, M. Adir, A. Mansur, A. A. Baccarelli, C. Racowsky, A. M. Calafat, R. Hauser and R. Nahum, 2018: Urinary concentrations of phthalate metabolites, bisphenols and personal care product chemical biomarkers in pregnant women in Israel. *Environ Int* 116, 319-325.

Marmugi, A., S. Ducheix, F. Lasserre, A. Polizzi, A. Paris, N. Priymenko, J. Bertrand-Michel, T. Pineau, H. Guillou, P. G. Martin and L. Mselli-Lakhal, 2012: Low doses of bisphenol A induce gene expression related to lipid synthesis and trigger triglyceride accumulation in adult mouse liver. *Hepatology* 55, 395-407.

Martínez, M. Á., J. Blanco, J. Rovira, V. Kumar, J. L. Domingo and M. Schuhmacher, 2020: Bisphenol A analogues (BPS and BPF) present a greater obesogenic capacity in 3T3-L1 cell line. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 140, 111298.

Meng, Z., D. Wang, W. Liu, R. Li, S. Yan, M. Jia, L. Zhang, Z. Zhou and W. Zhu, 2019: Perinatal exposure to Bisphenol S (BPS) promotes obesity development by interfering with lipid and glucose metabolism in male mouse offspring. *Environ Res* 173, 189-198.

Mesnager, R., A. Phedonos, M. Arno, S. Balu, J. C. Corton and M. N. Antoniou, 2017: Transcriptome profiling reveals bisphenol a alternatives activate estrogen receptor alpha in human breast cancer cells. *Toxicological Sciences* 158, 431-443.

Mhaouty-Kodja, S., L. P. Belzunces, M. C. Canivenc, H. Schroeder, C. Chevrier and E. Pasquier, 2018: Impairment of learning and memory performances induced by BPA: Evidences from the literature of a MoA mediated through an ED. *Molecular and cellular endocrinology* 475, 54-73.

Mornagui, B., R. Rezg, C. Repond and L. Pellerin, 2019: Effects of bisphenol S, a major substitute of bisphenol A, on neurobehavioral responses and cerebral monocarboxylate transporters expression in mice. *Food Chem Toxicol* 132, 110670.

Mustieles, V., P. L. Williams, M. Fernandez, L. Mnguez-Alarcn, J. B. Ford, A. M. Calafat, R. Hauser and C. Messerlian, 2018: Maternal and paternal preconception exposure to bisphenols and size at birth. *Human Reproduction* 33, 1528-1537.

Nevoral, J., Y. Kolinko, J. Moravec, T. Zalmanova, K. Hoskova, S. Prokesova, P. Klein, K. Ghaibour, P. Hosek, M. Stiavnicka, H. Rimnacova, Z. Tonar, J. Petr and M. Kralickova, 2018: Long-term exposure to very low doses of bisphenol S affects female reproduction. *Reproduction* 156, 47-57.

NICNAS, 2016: Human Health Tier II Assessment for Phenol, 4,4'-sulfonylbis- (CAS Number: 80-09-1).

Nourian, A., A. Soleimanzadeh, A. Shalizar Jalali and G. Najafi, 2017: Effects of bisphenol-S low concentrations on oxidative stress status and in vitro fertilisation potential in mature female mice. *Veterinary research forum: an international quarterly journal* 8, 341-345.

NTP, 2017: NTP Research report on biological activity of Bisphenol A (BPA) Structural Analogues and functional alternatives. .

NTP, 2018: Testing Status of Bisphenol S.

OECD SIDS, 2013: SIDS Initial Assessment Report For CoCAM 4: Screening Information Data Set (SIDS) for High Production Volume Chemicals: 4,4'-Sulfonyldiphenol (BPS) Screening Information Data Set (SIDS) for High Production Volume Chemicals: 4,4'-Sulfonyldiphenol. pp. 1-27.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 193

- Oh, J., J. W. Choi, Y. A. Ahn and S. Kim, 2018a: Pharmacokinetics of bisphenol S in humans after single oral administration. *Environ Int* 112, 127-133.
- Oh, J., J. W. Choi, Y. A. Ahn and S. Kim, 2018b: Response to the Letter to the Editor. *Environ Int* 115, 395-396.
- Owczarek, K., P. Kubica, B. Kudlak, A. Rutkowska, A. Konieczna, D. Rachon, J. Namiesnik and A. Wasik, 2018: Determination of trace levels of eleven bisphenol A analogues in human blood serum by high performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry. *Sci Total Environ* 628-629, 1362-1368.
- Pal, S., K. Sarkar, P. P. Nath, M. Mondal, A. Khatun and G. Paul, 2017: Bisphenol S impairs blood functions and induces cardiovascular risks in rats. *Toxicology Reports* 4, 560-565.
- Palanza, P. L., K. L. Howdeshell, S. Parmigiani and F. S. vom Saal, 2002: Exposure to a low dose of bisphenol A during fetal life or in adulthood alters maternal behavior in mice. *Environ Health Perspect* 110 Suppl 3, 415-422.
- Philips, E. M., V. W. V. Jaddoe, A. G. Asimakopoulos, K. Kannan, E. A. P. Steegers, S. Santos and L. Trasande, 2018: Bisphenol and phthalate concentrations and its determinants among pregnant women in a population-based cohort in the Netherlands, 2004-5. *Environ Res* 161, 562-572.
- Philips, E. M., L. G. Kahn, V. W. V. Jaddoe, Y. Shao, A. G. Asimakopoulos, K. Kannan, E. A. P. Steegers and L. Trasande, 2018: First Trimester Urinary Bisphenol and Phthalate Concentrations and Time to Pregnancy: A Population-Based Cohort Analysis. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 103, 3540-3547.
- Pollock, T., L. J. Greville, R. E. Weaver, M. Radenovic and D. deCatanzaro, 2019: Bisphenol S modulates concentrations of bisphenol A and oestradiol in female and male mice. *Xenobiotica* 49, 540-548.
- Prokesova, S., K. Ghaibour, F. Liska, P. Klein, T. Fenclova, M. Stiavnicka, P. Hosek, T. Zalmanova, K. Hoskova, H. Rimnacova, J. Petr, M. Kralickova and J. Nevoral, 2020: Acute low-dose bisphenol S exposure affects mouse oocyte quality. *Reprod Toxicol* 93, 19-27.
- Pu, Y., J. D. Gingrich, J. P. Steibel and A. Veiga-Lopez, 2017: Sex-Specific Modulation of Fetal Adipogenesis by Gestational Bisphenol A and Bisphenol S Exposure. *Endocrinology* 158, 3844-3858.
- Ranciere, F., J. Botton, R. Slama, M. Z. Lacroix, L. Debrauwer, M. A. Charles, R. Roussel, B. Balkau, D. J. Magliano and D. E. S. I. R. S. Group, 2019: Exposure to Bisphenol A and Bisphenol S and Incident Type 2 Diabetes: A Case-Cohort Study in the French Cohort D.E.S.I.R. *Environ Health Perspect* 127, 107013.
- Rezg, R., A. Abot, B. Mornagui, S. Aydi and C. Knauf, 2018: Effects of Bisphenol S on hypothalamic neuropeptides regulating feeding behavior and apelin/APJ system in mice. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf* 161, 459-466.
- Rezg, R., A. Abot, B. Mornagui and C. Knauf, 2019: Bisphenol S exposure affects gene expression related to intestinal glucose absorption and glucose metabolism in mice. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int* 26, 3636-3642.
- Rochester, J. R. and A. L. Bolden, 2015: Bisphenol S and F: A Systematic Review and Comparison of the Hormonal Activity of Bisphenol A Substitutes. *Environ Health Perspect* 123, 643-650.
- Rosenmai, A. K., M. Dybdahl, M. Pedersen, B. M. Alice van Vugt-Lussenburg, E. B. Wedebye, C. Taxvig and A. M. Vinggaard, 2014: Are structural analogues to bisphenol a safe alternatives? *Toxicol Sci* 139, 35-47.
- Sakhi, A. K., A. Sabaredzovic, E. Papadopoulou, E. Cequier and C. Thomsen, 2018: Levels, variability and determinants of environmental phenols in pairs of Norwegian mothers and children. *Environ Int* 114, 242-251.
- Santé Publique France, S.-M., 2019: Imprégnation de la population française par les bisphénols A, S et F. Etude ESTEBAN. Programme national de biosurveillance, Esteban 2014-2016. . Santé publique France, septembre 2019. , 57.
- Sharma, A., K. Singh and A. Almasan, 2012: Histone H2AX phosphorylation: a marker for DNA damage. *Methods in molecular biology (Clifton, N.J.)* 920, 613-626.
- Shen, Y., T. Liu, Y. Shi, F. Zhuang, J. Lu, Q. Zhu and F. Ding, 2019: Bisphenol A analogs in patients with chronic kidney disease and dialysis therapy. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf* 185, 109684.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 194

- Shi, M., N. Sekulovski, J. A. MacLean, 2nd and K. Hayashi, 2017: Effects of bisphenol A analogues on reproductive functions in mice. *Reprod Toxicol* 73, 280-291.
- Shi, M., N. Sekulovski, J. A. MacLean, 2nd and K. Hayashi, 2018: Prenatal Exposure to Bisphenol A Analogues on Male Reproductive Functions in Mice. *Toxicol Sci* 163, 620-631.
- Shi, M., N. Sekulovski, J. A. MacLean, A. Whorton and K. Hayashi, 2019: Prenatal Exposure to Bisphenol A Analogues on Female Reproductive Functions in Mice. *Toxicol Sci* 168, 561-571.
- Shi, M., A. E. Whorton, N. Sekulovski, J. A. MacLean and K. Hayashi, 2019a: Prenatal Exposure to Bisphenol A, E, and S Induces Transgenerational Effects on Female Reproductive Functions in Mice. *Toxicol Sci* 170, 320-329.
- Shi, M., A. E. Whorton, N. Sekulovski, J. A. MacLean and K. Hayashi, 2019b: Prenatal Exposure to Bisphenol A, E, and S Induces Transgenerational Effects on Male Reproductive Functions in Mice. *Toxicol Sci* 172, 303-315.
- Silva, B. S., I. M. Bertasso, C. B. Pietrobon, B. P. Lopes, T. R. Santos, N. Peixoto-Silva, J. C. Carvalho, S. Claudio-Neto, A. C. Manhaes, S. S. Cabral, G. E. G. Kluck, G. C. Atella, E. Oliveira, E. G. Moura and P. C. Lisboa, 2019: Effects of maternal bisphenol A on behavior, sex steroid and thyroid hormones levels in the adult rat offspring. *Life Sci* 218, 253-264.
- Skledar, D. G., J. Schmidt, A. Fic, I. Klopčič, J. Trontelj, M. S. Dolenc, M. Finel and L. P. Masic, 2016: Influence of metabolism on endocrine activities of bisphenol S. *Chemosphere* 157, 152-159.
- Song, P., K. Fan, X. Tian and J. Wen, 2019: Bisphenol S (BPS) triggers the migration of human non-small cell lung cancer cells via upregulation of TGF-beta. *Toxicol In Vitro* 54, 224-231.
- Thayer, K. A., D. R. Doerge, D. Hunt, S. H. Schurman, N. C. Twaddle, M. I. Churchwell, S. Garantziotis, G. E. Kissling, M. R. Easterling, J. R. Bucher and L. S. Birnbaum, 2015: Pharmacokinetics of bisphenol A in humans following a single oral administration. *Environ Int* 83, 107-115.
- Thayer, K. A., K. W. Taylor, S. Garantziotis, S. H. Schurman, G. E. Kissling, D. Hunt, B. Herbert, R. Church, R. Jankowich, M. I. Churchwell, R. C. Scheri, L. S. Birnbaum and J. R. Bucher, 2016: Bisphenol A, Bisphenol S, and 4-Hydroxyphenyl 4-Isopropoxyphenylsulfone (BPSIP) in Urine and Blood of Cashiers. *Environ Health Perspect* 124, 437-444.
- Tucker, D. K., S. Hayes Bouknight, S. S. Brar, G. E. Kissling and S. E. Fenton, 2018: Evaluation of Prenatal Exposure to Bisphenol Analogues on Development and Long-Term Health of the Mammary Gland in Female Mice. *Environ Health Perspect* 126, 087003.
- U.S.EPA, 2015: Bisphenol A Alternatives in Thermal Paper, Chapter 4: Hazard Evaluation of Bisphenol A (BPA) and Alternatives. Final Report. pp. 1-453. Washington, DC.
- Ullah, A., M. Pirzada, T. Afsar, S. Razak, A. Almajwal and S. Jahan, 2019a: Effect of bisphenol F, an analog of bisphenol A, on the reproductive functions of male rats. *Environmental health and preventive medicine* 24, 41.
- Ullah, A., M. Pirzada, S. Jahan, H. Ullah and M. J. Khan, 2019b: Bisphenol A analogues bisphenol B, bisphenol F, and bisphenol S induce oxidative stress, disrupt daily sperm production, and damage DNA in rat spermatozoa: a comparative in vitro and in vivo study. *Toxicol Ind Health* 35, 294-303.
- Ullah, A., M. Pirzada, S. Jahan, H. Ullah, S. Razak, N. Rauf, M. J. Khan and S. Z. Mahboob, 2019c: Prenatal BPA and its analogs BPB, BPF, and BPS exposure and reproductive axis function in the male offspring of Sprague Dawley rats. *Human & experimental toxicology* 38, 1344-1365.
- Ullah, A., M. Pirzada, S. Jahan, H. Ullah, G. Shaheen, H. Rehman, M. F. Siddiqui and M. A. Butt, 2018a: Bisphenol A and its analogs bisphenol B, bisphenol F, and bisphenol S: Comparative in vitro and in vivo studies on the sperms and testicular tissues of rats. *Chemosphere* 209, 508-516.
- Ullah, A., M. Pirzada, S. Jahan, H. Ullah, N. Turi, W. Ullah, M. F. Siddiqui, M. Zakria, K. Z. Lodhi and M. M. Khan, 2018b: Impact of low-dose chronic exposure to bisphenol A and its analogue bisphenol B, bisphenol F and bisphenol S on hypothalamo-pituitary-testicular activities in adult rats: A focus on the possible hormonal mode of action. *Food Chem Toxicol* 121, 24-36.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 195

- Ullah, H., S. Jahan, Q. U. Ain, G. Shaheen and N. Ahsan, 2016: Effect of bisphenol S exposure on male reproductive system of rats: A histological and biochemical study. *Chemosphere* 152, 383-391.
- Verbanck, M., M. Canouil, A. Leloire, V. Dhennin, X. Coumoul, L. Yengo, P. Froguel and O. Poulain-Godefroy, 2017: Low-dose exposure to bisphenols A, F and S of human primary adipocyte impacts coding and non-coding RNA profiles. *PLoS One* 12, e0179583.
- Vernet, C., C. Philippat, A. M. Calafat, X. Ye, S. Lyon-Caen, V. Siroux, E. F. Schisterman and R. Slama, 2018: Within-Day, Between-Day, and Between-Week Variability of Urinary Concentrations of Phenol Biomarkers in Pregnant Women. *Environ Health Perspect* 126, 037005.
- Vinas, P., N. Campillo, N. Martinez-Castillo and M. Hernandez-Cordoba, 2010: Comparison of two derivatisation-based methods for solid-phase microextraction-gas chromatography-mass spectrometric determination of bisphenol A, bisphenol S and biphenol migrated from food cans. *Anal Bioanal Chem* 397, 115-125.
- Vitku, J., L. Kolatorova, L. Franekova, J. Blahos, M. Simkova, M. Duskova, T. Skodova and L. Starka, 2018: Endocrine disruptors of the bisphenol and paraben families and bone metabolism. *Physiological research* 67, S455-s464.
- Waidyanatha, S., S. R. Black, R. W. Snyder, Y. L. Yueh, V. Sutherland, P. R. Patel, S. L. Watson and T. R. Fennell, 2018: Disposition and metabolism of the bisphenol analogue, bisphenol S, in Harlan Sprague Dawley rats and B6C3F1/N mice and in vitro in hepatocytes from rats, mice, and humans. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol* 351, 32-45.
- Wan, Y., W. Huo, S. Xu, T. Zheng, B. Zhang, Y. Li, A. Zhou, Y. Zhang, J. Hu, Y. Zhu, Z. Chen, S. Lu, C. Wu, M. Jiang, Y. Jiang, H. Liu, X. Yang and W. Xia, 2018: Relationship between maternal exposure to bisphenol S and pregnancy duration. *Environ Pollut* 238, 717-724.
- Wang, Y. X., C. Liu, Y. Shen, Q. Wang, A. Pan, P. Yang, Y. J. Chen, Y. L. Deng, Q. Lu, L. M. Cheng, X. P. Miao, S. Q. Xu, W. Q. Lu and Q. Zeng, 2019: Urinary levels of bisphenol A, F and S and markers of oxidative stress among healthy adult men: Variability and association analysis. *Environ Int* 123, 301-309.
- Yabusaki, R., H. Iwano, S. Tsushima, N. Koike, N. Ohtani, K. Tanemura, H. Inoue and H. Yokota, 2015: Weak activity of UDP-glucuronosyltransferase toward Bisphenol analogs in mouse perinatal development. *J Vet Med Sci* 77, 1479-1484.
- Yalcin, E. B., S. R. Kulkarni, A. L. Slitt and R. King, 2016: Bisphenol A sulfonation is impaired in metabolic and liver disease. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol* 292, 75-84.
- Yamasaki, K., S. Noda, N. Imatanaka and Y. Yakabe, 2004: Comparative study of the uterotrophic potency of 14 chemicals in a uterotrophic assay and their receptor-binding affinity. *Toxicology Letters* 146, 111-120.
- Yamazaki, E., N. Yamashita, S. Taniyasu, J. Lam, P. K. S. Lam, H.-B. Moon, Y. Jeong, P. Kannan, H. Achyuthan, N. Munuswamy and K. Kannan, 2015: Bisphenol A and other bisphenol analogues including BPS and BPF in surface water samples from Japan, China, Korea and India. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* 122, 565-572.
- Yang, X., D. R. Doerge, J. G. Teeguarden and J. W. Fisher, 2015: Development of a physiologically based pharmacokinetic model for assessment of human exposure to bisphenol A. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol* 289, 442-456.
- Yang, Y., J. Guan, J. Yin, B. Shao and H. Li, 2014: Urinary levels of bisphenol analogues in residents living near a manufacturing plant in south China. *Chemosphere* 112, 481-486.
- Yang, Y., Y. Yang, J. Zhang, B. Shao and J. Yin, 2019: Assessment of bisphenol A alternatives in paper products from the Chinese market and their dermal exposure in the general population. *Environ Pollut* 244, 238-246.
- Zalko, D., A. M. Soto, L. Dolo, C. Dorio, E. Rathahao, L. Debrauwer, R. Faure and J. P. Cravedi, 2003: Biotransformations of bisphenol A in a mammalian model: answers and new questions raised by low-dose metabolic fate studies in pregnant CD1 mice. *Environ Health Perspect* 111, 309-319.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 196

Zalmanova, T., K. Hoskova, J. Nevoral, K. Adamkova, T. Kott, M. Sulc, Z. Kotikova, S. Prokesova, F. Jilek, M. Kralickova and J. Petr, 2017: Bisphenol S negatively affects the meiotic maturation of pig oocytes. *Sci Rep* 7, 485.

Zech, 2016: Analysis of bisphenols and bisphenolA diglycidyl ethers by stable isotope dilution assay liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry.

Zhang, H., Q. Quan, M. Zhang, N. Zhang, W. Zhang, M. Zhan, W. Xu, L. Lu, J. Fan and Q. Wang, 2020: Occurrence of bisphenol A and its alternatives in paired urine and indoor dust from Chinese university students: Implications for human exposure. *Chemosphere* 247, 125987.

Zhang, T., J. Xue, C. Z. Gao, R. L. Qiu, Y. X. Li, X. Li, M. Z. Huang and K. Kannan, 2016: Urinary Concentrations of Bisphenols and Their Association with Biomarkers of Oxidative Stress in People Living Near E-Waste Recycling Facilities in China. *Environ Sci Technol* 50, 4045-4053.

Zhang, W., W. Xia, W. Liu, X. Li, J. Hu, B. Zhang, S. Xu, Y. Zhou, J. Li, Z. Cai and Y. Li, 2019: Exposure to Bisphenol a Substitutes and Gestational Diabetes Mellitus: A Prospective Cohort Study in China. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)* 10, 262.

Zhang, Y., T. Dong, W. Hu, X. Wang, B. Xu, Z. Lin, T. Hofer, P. Stefanoff, Y. Chen, X. Wang and Y. Xia, 2019: Association between exposure to a mixture of phenols, pesticides, and phthalates and obesity: Comparison of three statistical models. *Environ Int* 123, 325-336.

Zhang, Y. F., X. M. Ren, Y. Y. Li, X. F. Yao, C. H. Li, Z. F. Qin and L. H. Guo, 2018: Bisphenol A alternatives bisphenol S and bisphenol F interfere with thyroid hormone signaling pathway in vitro and in vivo. *Environ Pollut* 237, 1072-1079.

Zhang, Z., L. Lin, Y. Gai, Y. Hong, L. Li and L. Weng, 2018: Subchronic bisphenol S exposure affects liver function in mice involving oxidative damage. *Regul Toxicol Pharmacol* 92, 138-144.

Zhao, C., P. Xie, T. Yong, H. Wang, A. C. K. Chung and Z. Cai, 2018: MALDI-MS Imaging Reveals Asymmetric Spatial Distribution of Lipid Metabolites from Bisphenol S-Induced Nephrotoxicity. *Anal Chem* 90, 3196-3204.

Zhou, B., P. Yang, Y. L. Deng, Q. Zeng, W. Q. Lu and S. R. Mei, 2020: Prenatal exposure to bisphenol a and its analogues (bisphenol F and S) and ultrasound parameters of fetal growth. *Chemosphere* 246, 125805.

11 Annexes

11.1 Annex 1

Table III.32: Experimental data on female reproduction function with non-conventional route of exposure (eg. subcutaneous, intra-peritoneal)

Reference	Specie/ strain	Period duration, dose, route of exposure	Monitored parameters		Comment/ effective dose	Study limitation	Potential impact on interpretation	Effect to be considered and effective dose
Shi et al., 2017	CD-1 mice	PND0-PND60 50 µg and 10 mg/kg bw every 3 days Subcutaneous	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Age at vaginal opening PND60 BW Time required to plug Gestation outcomes BW 2 weeks post parturition (PP) Uterine absolute weight PND60 diestrus Uterine absolute Weight 2 PP Diestrous 17β-estradiol levels Diestrous testosterone Ovarian Gene expression of steroidogenic enzymes 	- - - - - - ↑ ↑ -	NS, few treated ↑ time (>10 days) Both doses similarly about 2 fold High dose	Housing in PS cages (news) Values <<assay LOD	Low High: Inaccuracy	Testo 10 mg/kg Not adverse
Nourian et al. 2017. Vet res Forum., 8(4):341-345	Mice (Strain not precised)	~PND80 21 days 1-5-10-50-100µg/kg bw/day Intraperitoneal	Ovarian oxidative stress (lipid peroxidationTBAR test) In vitro fecundation yield (superovulation protocol) Early in vitro embryo development	↑ ↓ ↓	Dose dependent- For all parameters 10µg/kg bw/day Increased % of embryo with moderate cell alteration 10µg/kg bw/day	No control of estrous stage at sacrifice IVF=>epigenetic modifications	High on ovarian oxidative stress Conclusion limited to IVF context	Decreased oocyte quality on induced polyovulation 10µg/kg bw/day
Ashan et al., 2018. Chemosphere.	Rat	PND1-PND10 0.5-5-50 mg/kg bw/day	Age at vaginal opening At PND75: Ovary absolute/relative weight	↑ ↓	50 mg/kg bw/day	Unreliable estradiol dosage	Parameter non valide	Effect on absolute ovary

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 198

Reference	Specie/ strain	Period duration, dose, route of exposure	Monitored parameters		Comment/ effective dose	Study limitation	Potential impact on interpretation	Effect to be considered and effective dose
197:336-343		subcutaneous	Uterus absolute/relative weight Ovary histology : Nb CL NB antral follicles Nb atretic follicles Preovulatory follicle Hormone analysis (morning of estrus?) Estradiol Progesterone Testosterone FSH LH Conception rate Litter size	↓ ↓ ↓ ↑ - ? ↓ ↑ ↓ ↓ ↓	Absolute 5 and 50- relative 50 50 mg/kg/day 5 and 50 mg/kg bw/day/ 5 and 50 mg/kg bw/day 50 mg/kg bw/day Estrous stage unclear Not reliable/assay performances 50 mg/kg bw/day 50 mg/kg bw/day No statistic 50 mg/kg bw/day	Ovary histology: analysis every 70 µm < size of large follicle:	High : accuracy on the counts if a same follicle counted twice	weight: 5 mg/kg bw/day Effect on folliculogenesis: 5 mg/kg bw/day with high level of uncertainty

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 199

Reference	Specie/ strain	Period duration, dose, route of exposure	Monitored parameters		Comment/ effective dose	Study limitation	Potential impact on interpretation	Effect to be considered and effective dose
Ijaz et al. Tox Mecha and meth	Rat Sprague Dawley	Peripubertal exposure(90- 150g BW) 0.05-0.5 - 5 & 150 mg/kg bw/day X 28 days OECD-like 407 Intraperitoneal	-Estrous stage at D29 -Gonadosomatic index (relative ovary weight) -BW and weight gain, ovary and uterus weight (estrus) -ovarian oxidative stress Estradiol, LH, FSH, progesterone testosterone -follicular stages absolute nb Corpus luteum absolute nb antral follicles Absolute nb of atretic follicles Absolute nb of preovulatory follicle	↓ ↓↓ ↓ ↑ ↓ ↑ ↓ ↓ ↑ -	No data 5 mg/kg bw/day BPS BPF (idem BPA BPB) Absolute ovary at 5 mg/kg bw/day BPS and BPF Absolute Uterus all doses BPS- PBF 0.5 & 5 Relative uterus BPF 0.5-5-150 mg BPS 5-150 ↑ROS except dose 0.5 ↓ TBARS ↓SOD CAT -effect ROS . non monotonic BPF and BPS 0.05 BPS 0.5 to 150 and BPF 5 & 150 BPS BPF: 5-150 BPS: 0.5 to-150 BPF 5 & 150 BPS 5 & 150 BPF150 BPS -BPF 5 &150	No data Age unknown (150g) Nb of animals unclear E2 Assay not valid Stain every 70 µm< follicle diameter	Uncertainty mistakes Uncertainty High High (follicles counted twice, Uncertainty	Decreased uterus relative weight 0.5 mg/kg bw/day Ovary oxidative stress: 0.05 mg/kg bw/day many uncertainties

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 200

Table III.33: Experimental evidences available on metabolism and obesity

Reference	Species Strain Model	Route	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
Gestational exposure							
Ullah A, Pirzada M, Jahan S, Ullah H, Razak S, Rauf N, Khan MJ, Mahboob SZ Prenatal BPA and its analogs BPB, BPF, and BPS exposure and reproductive axis function in the male offspring of Sprague Dawley rats. Hum Exp Toxicol. 2019a Dec;38(12):1344-1365. doi: 10.1177/0960327119862335	Sprague-Dawley rats	Oral through drinking water	Concentrations of 5, 25, 50 µg/L from pregnancy D1 to PD21. Only the male offspring is studied. Standard diet.	A total of 13 groups with n=8 gestating mothers. The n number of male offspring studied was 2 at PND16 and 2 at PND80/litter.	The study is about the reproductive axis in males. However, several outcomes can provide information regarding metabolic health including body weight gain of dams, pups and the offspring; litter size; liver weight; adrenal weight; plasma hormone levels;	The authors observed that the highest dose of BPA and its analogs (with equal efficiency) led to enhanced body weight of the male offspring at PND80 (an average of 10 %) but not at PND16. Adrenal and liver weight did not change throughout groups. Plasma levels of testosterone significantly declined (-30 %). Plasma levels of estradiol significantly enhanced almost 3 fold. LH and FSH plasma levels also significantly declined by 30 % and 60 %, respectively.	The authors did not indicate the volume of drinking water per animal. Thus, doses of bisphenol exposure cannot be calculated with accuracy. It is expected that a rat will drink 10mL/100g and that the mean body weight of a gestating rat is of 300 g. Thus, in 3 weeks a total of 600 mL which corresponds to 3, 15 and 30 µg/kg bw/day.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 201

Reference	Species Strain Model	Route	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
Pregnancy and lactation							
Meng et al., 2019	Male mice; Polysulfone cages (BPS free); not indicated if animals were fasted before sacrifice.	Oral route (gavage), daily exposure	From GD7 to PND21 to BPS 100µg/kg bw/day (vehicle: corn oil). Primigravida pregnant ICR mice (n=6). At weaning, male offspring were divided in 2 groups of 6 males (one mice from each dam) and provided low-fat (10 kcal %fat) or high-fat diet (60 kcal %fat) for 10 weeks	n=6/group	<p>No general toxicity. No effects on the timing of birth and litter size. Enhanced body weight, liver weight and epididymal WAT weight in all groups compared to controls; the highest effects were observed in the group exposed to BPS and fed a high-fat diet</p> <p>Liver exhibited enhanced TG content in response to BPS and a HF diet. Enhanced liver cholesterol is only observed in HF fed mice. No changes of AST but enhanced ALT indicative of hepatic toxicities</p> <p>Hypertrophy of adipocytes in response to both BPS and the HF challenge</p> <p>In the liver, Ccl2 mRNA levels were enhanced in response to both challenges. A further increase was observed in the BPS and HF fed mice vs HF-fed mice. Among other markers measured TNFa and Itgam mRNA levels were enhanced in BPS and HF-fed mice, only. In WAT, enhanced mRNA levels of Itgam and F4/F80 were observed in BPS-challenged mice, only; and the response was further increased in HF-fed mice. Ccl2 mRNA levels were enhanced in HF-fed mice with a larger increase in BPS-challenged mice</p> <p>Metabolic profiles: the PCA score plots show good separation between the 4 groups and 17 metabolites were significantly altered vs control group (no BPS; no HF diet). Most</p>	The authors concluded that a BPS maternal treatment disrupted glucose and lipid metabolism and exacerbated obesity in response to a high-fat diet in adulthood	The study is of good quality. The protocol is similar as the one conducted with BPA by Wei et al 2014 on the two-hit hypothesis leading to obesity and hepatic steatosis in adulthood.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 202

Reference	Species Strain Model	Route	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
					<p>significant effects concerned glucose and lipid metabolism</p> <p>Quantification of genes related to glucose and lipid metabolism in the liver evidenced 3 groups of genes. One group included Fasn, Scd1, Dgat1, Mogat1, Shp, G6pase, all having mRNA levels enhanced in response to both challenges. A second group included Acaca, Nr1c3 (PPARG) and Glut2. The mRNA levels augmented in response to BPS and HF diet and further increased in BPS and HF fed mice vs HF fed mice. The third group included Sreb1c, Cd36, Nr1h4 (FXR), Pk1r and Gys2. The mRNA levels augmented only in BPS and HF fed mice</p> <p>Quantification of genes related to glucose and lipid metabolism in WAT evidenced 4 groups of genes. Genes upregulated in response to both challenges (Fasn, Scd1, Nr1c3, Dgat1, Dgat2, Nr1h4, SHp, Gys2). Genes upregulated in response to BPS only (Cd36, Glu2, Pk1r). One gene upregulated only in HF conditions (Acaca) and one gene down-regulated in HF and BPS conditions, only.</p>		
Pu et al., 2017	Polypay Dorsett sheep	Daily subcutaneous injections in corn oil.	From days 30 to 100 of gestation (term : 147 days); 0.5 mg/kg bw/day BPA and BPS.	3 groups of 7-8 animals of both sexes (6 groups); standard diet	No effect on body weight regardless of sex No sex-differences in adipocyte size; no differences in the gene expression levels of estrogen and glucocorticoid receptors; in females: decreased mRNA levels of Nr1c3 (PPARG) in BBS-treated samples and of Adipoq in BPA-treated cells; in males :	The authors concluded on sex-specific modulation of fetal adipogenesis by gestational exposure to BPA and BPS. Specifically, females had	The study is of good quality. Data yielded using primary cultures of adipocytes collected from perirenal adipose tissues

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 203

Reference	Species Strain Model	Route	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
					<p>reduced mRNA levels of Adipoq in BPS treated samples</p> <p>Fetal adipogenic differentiation assessed through lipid droplets measurements evidenced enhanced lipid accumulation in BPA-treated female samples. No effect is observed in males with BPA. BPS had no effect on this outcome.</p> <p>Fetal adipogenic differentiation assessed through qPCR analysis showed in females: enhanced mRNA levels of Nr1c3 (PPARG) ; J/ebpa ; LPL ; Fabp4 and Adipoq in BPA-treated samples. No effect was evidenced using BPS; in males: reduced mRNA levels of D10 Cebpa and Lpl in BPA-treated samples but enhanced Fabp4 and Adipoq mRNA levels in BPS-treated samples.</p> <p>Adipocyte proliferation was not impacted by the bisphenols A or S regardless of sex.</p> <p>Preadipocyte gene expression was differentially influenced by BPA and BPS with sex-specific differences. In I BPS enhanced mRNA levels of D5 ESR2 and NR3C1 (GR) and BPA reduced Dlk1 mRNA levels only. In D5 BPS had no effect and BPA enhanced ESR2 mRNA levels and accelerated fetal adipogenic differentiation markers. ER stress markers were also changed in BPA groups compared to controls (in females).</p>	<p>higher susceptibility to BPA than males and potentially a higher risk to develop obesity in adulthood. Males were more susceptible to BPS than females and BPS was less active at modulating proliferation and differentiation than BPA.</p>	<p>recovered from male and female fetuses of BPA and BPS treated sheep are divergent from data using freshly isolated perirenal adipose tissues. Yet, BPA and BPS have short half-lives and tissue harvest was completed 20 days after the last sc injection of BPA or BPS. To reconcile the data, the authors suggest that the differentiation cocktail used <i>in vitro</i> could constitute a second hit (the first one is the BPA or the BPS in vivo-treatment) mimicking a high fat diet.</p>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 204

Reference	Species Strain Model	Route	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
Jing et al., 2019	Polypay Dorsett sheep. Fetal skeletal muscle recovered from the hind limb vastus lateralis to evaluate fiber size, fiber type, and gene and protein expression related to myogenesis, fiber size, fiber type, and inflammation Fetal primary myoblasts were isolated to evaluate proliferation and differentiation	Daily subcutaneous injections in corn oil.	Gestational day 30 to 100 (term: 147 days); 8 sheep exposed to BPA 0.5 mg/kg/day 7 sheep exposed to BPS 0.5 mg/kg bw/day	Pregnant sheep (n=7-8/group);	During fetal life, proliferation of myogenic precursors is a critical event during skeletal muscle development. Exposure to BPA or BPS did not alter proliferation in males and females but resulted in hypertrophy. Indeed, fiber size was larger in the fetus (both sexes) of BPA-treated mothers. There was a trend for BPS. In all groups, mean fiber size was larger in females than in males. Myosin Heavy chains (MHCs) exhibit sex-dimorphism with males having slower MHC than females and females having faster MHC than males. In response to BPA, MYH1 (fast MHC) enhanced in females not in males. In response to BPS, MYH7 and MYH2 (slow MHCs) enhanced in females not in males. Myogenic differentiation is regulated by myogenic regulatory factors which dysregulation can result in muscle hypertrophy or atrophy. In response to BPS exposure, several MRFs and of inflammation-related genes had their expression enhanced in female but not in male fetuses. BPA had no effect in males and females.	Gestational exposure to BPA and BPS triggers hypertrophy of fetal skeletal muscle fiber independent of sex. Exposure to BPS alters fiber type distribution in females not in males and BPA has no impact in this outcome. It is unknown if these changes persisted during adulthood.	The study is of good quality. Skeletal muscle plays a major role in posture support, locomotion and breathing but also in energy metabolism. These functions are associated with the size and type of myofibers, insulin sensitivity and metabolic rates. Myogenesis occurs during fetal life when the number of muscle fibers is established while hypertrophy occurs post-natally. The findings presented here indicate that programming is disturbed in response to a gestational exposure to BPA and BPS. The situation is more critical in females and under BPS exposure.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 205

Reference	Species Strain Model	Route	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
Da Silva et al.. 2019	Wistar rats; Dams	Intragastric gavage every morning.	0, 10 and 50 µg/kg bw/day during gestation and lactation.	n= 10/group; 3 groups;	<p>No general toxicity ; no changes of milk composition; Dams exhibited no changes in body mass, food intake, lean to fat mass ratio ; no big changes in plasma biochemical parameters and hormone levels apart from testosterone levels lower in BPS 50 dams than in control and BPS 10 dams ; a trend for reduced estradiol levels in BPS 10 dams and reduced T3 and T4 in BPS treated dams</p> <p>Pups at weaning : no changes of body weight and fat mass ; little changes in biochemical parameters but a trend for reduced insulin and estradiol plasma levels. Specifically, BPS 50 males exhibited reduced TG and T4 levels and BPS 50 females had reduced 25(OH)D levels.</p> <p>Adult offspring: no changes in body weight despite decreased food intake for both doses in both males and females; no differences in glucose tolerance and insulin sensitivity in both males and females; lower visceral fat mass in males despite no changes in lipid droplets and adipocyte cell size and enhanced TG plasma levels and lower T3; no changes in adipocyte cell size but decreased size of lipid droplets and lowered lipid accumulation in the BAT in females. Females also had lower progesterone plasma levels in the dose 10 group and decreased Free T4 in the 10 and 50 BPS-treated groups.</p>	<p>The authors demonstrated that BPS did not influence the lipid plasma profile of dams and milk composition. Pups at weaning did not exhibit major changes. However, at adulthood, food intake was reduced in both males and females despite no changes in body weight. Little changes could be observed regarding TG plasma levels and the size of lipid droplets depending on sex. Eventually, BPS influenced T3 and T4 levels as a function of age and sex suggesting that maternal exposure to BPS would cause dysregulation in thyroid hormone homeostasis. This would induce thermogenesis which is in line with the reduced lipid accumulation in BAT.</p> <p>It is also demonstrated that BPS did not disrupt glucose metabolism.</p>	<p>The study is correct. The authors have investigated a large number of outcomes in dams but also in pups at weaning and in the adult offspring. They identified that BPS could cause disruption in thyroid metabolism which would possibly cause changes in behavior parameters such as increased preference for fat diets not reviewed herein.</p>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 206

Reference	Species Strain Model	Route	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
From pregnancy until adulthood							
Ivry Del Moral et al., 2016	C57BL/6 female mouse from Charles Rivers (L'Arbresle, France).	Drinking water.	0; 0.2; 1.5; 50 µg/kg bw/day. From GD1 to the adulthood of the offspring (22 weeks of age); at weaning, subdivision per sex and nutritional challenge (half mice fed a standard diet; half mice fed a high-fat diet). Calculations for dosages were based on estimates of 7ml water/mice of 30g/day in standard diet conditions and twice more concentrated for mice fed a high-fat diet as they drink twice less than standard-diet fed mice; Fasting 4 hours before sacrifice; weight monitoring and lean mass / fat ratio; food intake; calorimetry; lipid	45 dams subdivided in 4 groups, the control group and 3 doses. of BPS (0.2; 1.5 ; 50 µg/kg bw/day) administered through drinking water; chronic exposure from GD1 to the adulthood of the offspring (22 weeks of age); at weaning, subdivision per sex and nutritional challenge (half mice	Weight gain under a rich diet in males corresponding to an increase in fat mass at the two highest doses. Nothing in females; No effect on food intake or energy expenditure; Continuation of the study carried out only on males fed a rich diet. There is an increase in plasma insulin and leptin levels; nothing on blood sugar; increased HOMA-IR index denoting insulin resistance; no modification of plasma triglycerides but an increase in total cholesterol; a decrease in messenger RNAs for adiponectin, insulin receptor, hormone-sensitive lipase and PPARG and an increase in Socs3; nothing on ATGL and LPL lipases. All in line with the increase in weight and the development of insulin resistance. Several effects are significant with the lowest dose.	A chronic exposure to low doses of BPS triggers obesity in male mice fed a high-fat diet males but not in females.	The study is of good quality. Conclusions of the authors are coherent with the data

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 207

Reference	Species Strain Model	Route	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
			load test; biochemical analyses; qPCR assay	fed a standard diet; half mice fed a high-fat diet)			
Brulport et al., 2019.	C57BL/6 female mouse from Charles Rivers (L'Arbresle, France);	Drinking water.	12.76 ng of BPS /ml to obtain an average of 0.99 µg / kg bw / day; Fasting 4 hours before sacrifice; weight monitoring and lean mass / fat ratio; food intake; calorimetry; lipid load test; biochemical analyses; qPCR assay. The male but not the female offspring is analysed.	11 pregnant females subdivided into 2 groups including the control group (n = 15) and the treated group (n = 17); then 4 weeks after weaning, males put on a diet rich in fat and sucrose so as to have 5 mice per group / cage from 5 different litters	Increase in liver TG for the dose of 1.5 µg / kg bw / day and the weight of the perigonadic adipose tissue (indicated in not shown) Transcriptomic analysis identifies 782 up-regulated genes and 584 down-regulated genes by setting a minimum fold-change of 1.5 and a pvalue of 0.5. Hyper-methylation of DNA in sex chromosomes unlike autosomes Genes up-regulated by a factor of at least 4 include Cyp2b13, Cyp2b9, Slc22a27, Gstm3 and ApoA4 Genes down-regulated by a factor of at least 4 include Hsd3b4, Hsd3b5, Egr1 and GM10715, GM10720, GM17535, GM11168 Analysis made on the 1366 genes reveals an enrichment of the lipid sphere in agreement with the increase in hepatic TG The authors will then study whether there are differences in DNA methylation between the groups using the bisulfite sequencing method. A non-hierarchical classification makes it possible to identify 5 clusters of different methylation regions between the groups, 3 down-methylated regions and 2	Chronic exposure to low doses of BPS alters lipid homeostasis in the liver <i>via</i> transcriptional effects. Some of these effects could be the result of an alteration in the methylation profile of genomic DNA in the liver.	The study is of good quality. Conclusions of the authors are coherent with the data.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 208

Reference	Species Strain Model	Route	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
					up-methylated regions. 6.8 % of these regions are in areas rich in CpGs and 78.8 % in open sea (CpGs isolated in the genome) The search for methylation differences at the promoter level identifies 3 clusters in the group treated with BPS, 2 hyper-methylation clusters, and a hypo-methylation cluster (in which we find genes involved in lipid homeostasis). Normally, methylation at CpGs sites is accompanied by a drop in the expression of the gene concerned.		
Exposure from 4 weeks of age to adulthood							
Azevedo et al., 2019	Male Wistar rats of 3 weeks (110 g) plus 1-week accommodation;	Drinking water.	Vehicle is 0.1 % v/v ethanol; Correspond to TDI doses (US) of 50 µg/kg bw/day Administered for 38 weeks to BPS or BPA. Metabolic tests including oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) and insulin sensitivity test (IST) biochemical assays (TGs, HDL-C, AST, ALT, glycaemia, total cholesterol) in 10h-fasted animals	3 groups of 6 males;	Enhanced body weight in BPS exposed males after 20 weeks of treatment; Rats exhibited hyperglycaemia and hypertriglyceridemia. no effect of BPA on body weight, plasma TG levels and glycaemia. HDL-C was enhanced. Total cholesterol did not change in BPA or BPS groups and AST and ALT levels were in the control range indicative of no hepatotoxicity no differences in the hepatic or adipose tissue relative weights with BPA or BPS exposure Metabolic tests indicated impaired glucose tolerance in BPA and BPS exposed rats but no changes in insulin sensitivity which indicated that the liver was resistant to insulin hepatic mitochondrial metabolism showed increased O2 consumption in BPA exposed	The authors concluded that BPS but not BPA elicited enhanced body weight gain and that first significant effects were observed after 22 weeks of exposure. They also reported that BPA and BPS impaired lipid metabolism in rats and disrupted glucose metabolism homeostasis. The authors evidenced that BPA and BPS disrupted hepatic mitochondrial respiration, phosphorylation, biogenesis, ROS production and perhaps dynamics. The toxic	Conclusions of the authors are well documented and solid. It indicates that at least part of the effects linked to BPA or BPS exposure are mediated through impairment of mitochondrial metabolism and not an endocrine mode of action.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 209

Reference	Species Strain Model	Route	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
			liver oxygen consumption monitoring(to estimate respiration rate) ; citrate synthase activity assay (to estimate mitochondrial content) ; and hepatic redox state measuring mRNA expression by qPCR dosages		<p>males with a change in flux ratios. A trend was observed in BPS exposed males</p> <p>Citrate synthase activity used to estimate mitochondrial content was significantly decreased in the liver of BPA and BPS treated males</p> <p>PGC1alpha which is the master regulator of the genes involved in mitochondrial biogenesis and energy metabolism was downregulated in BPA exposed males. It was not observed in BPS-exposed males.</p> <p>However, mRNA levels of Drp1 coding dynamin related protein 1 which is a mediator of mitochondrial fission (associated with a diminution of oxygen consumption) were upregulated in the liver of BPA and BPS-treated rats. Other mediators of fission and fusion did not change.</p>	effects were more potent with BPA than those promoted by BPS exposure.	
Azevedo et al., 2020	Wistar rats of approximately 60 g at the beginning of the experiment (weaning).	Drinking water.	<p>50 and 500 µg/kg bw/day for both BPA and BPS administered for 20 weeks.</p> <p>Animals were fasted 10h before sacrifice.</p> <p>Blood and organ sampling; livers collected; biochemical</p>	Males randomly assigned to 5 groups of n=6 by 4 weeks of age.	<p>No overall toxicity; no change in AST and ALT levels; Body weight enhanced in response to BPS 500 only (not observed with BPS 50 and BPA)</p> <p>BPA caused augmentation of glycaemia and total cholesterol (BPA 50) ; HDL cholesterol augmented with both doses of BPA ; BPS 500 enhanced LDL-cholesterol and BPS 50 enhanced plasma TG level</p> <p>A total of 762 proteins were identified in liver extracts from control rats of which 30 and 34 were differentially regulated in BPA- and BPS-treated groups, respectively.</p>	The authors concluded that long-term exposure to BPA or BPS altered lipid synthesis and homeostasis (increased levels of serum lipid markers and upregulated expression of GYLK1, an enzyme involved in TG synthesis. BPS treatment had greater obesogenic properties than BPA, therefore not being a safe alternative to BPA.	<p>Data are convincing. However, these experiments do not add evidences for an endocrine mode of action for BPA and BPS.</p> <p>I could not find in the ms the % of DEPs only responding to BPA or BPS.</p>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 210

Reference	Species Strain Model	Route	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
			parameters (Triglycerides, TGs; cholesterol, AST and ALT ; HDL-C ; LDL-C) ; proteomic analysis of liver ; RT-qPCR analysis of selected genes)		<p>The majority of differentially expressed proteins (DEPs) were involved in metabolic processes (BPA : 36 % and BPS : 39 %) and in cellular processes (BPA : 34 % and BPS : 37 %)</p> <p>the distribution according to the molecular function of DEPs evidences that dysregulated proteins were with catalytic activity (BPA : 69 % and BPS : 52 %)</p> <p>there was no pathway enrichment for the DEPs according to the KEGG pathway database</p> <p>four DEPs were selected among the most highly regulated DEPs by the 2 bisphenols and mRNA levels dosed by RT-qPCR. RT-qPCR data extended proteomic data and showed up-regulation of Sdhb, Gyl1, Coq9 (encoding glucokinase activity-related sequence 1) and down-regulation of Akr1c2 (encoding aldo-keto reductase 1C family)</p> <p>Sdhb codes the succinate dehydrogenase iron-sulfur subunit mitochondrial, a complex II mitochondrial enzyme</p> <p>Gyl1 codes a protein involved in FA esterification and TG synthesis in liver</p> <p>Coq9 codes a major protein involved in the syhtesis of ubiquinone</p> <p>Enzymes of the AKR1C family are responsible for the glucocorticoid-induced inactivation of 5aDHT, an inhibitor of adipogenesis</p>	Moreover, the authors identified that exposure to BPA and BPS disrupted mitochondrial normal function in the liver potentially enhancing liver oxidative stress	

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 211

Reference	Species Strain Model	Route	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
					a high number of proteins important to detoxification were as well differentially regulated by BPA and BPS		
Rezg et al., 2018	Swiss albino mice.	Drinking water	0; 25; 50; 100 µg of BPS /kg/day based on mean daily water intake of 2mL/ 10 g mice. Body weight gain; food intake and feed efficiency; RT-qPCR dosage of various hypothalamic markers of food intake; Standard diet contained 20.5 % crude protein, 4.6 % crude fat and 52.5 % nitrogen-free extract (total calories 3.45 kcal/g)	24 male mice (10 g) divided in 4 groups of n=6;	No general toxicity; - Time-dependent increase of body weight significant at all time points studied and for all three doses with no dose-response effect except after 2 weeks of treatment. Enhanced food consumption at all time-points studied with a stronger effect for the mid-dose than for the highest dose; the lowest dose had almost no effect. Feed efficiency was the highest in mice exposed to the lowest dose. No effect was observed for the highest dose. No effect was observed on hypothalamic neuropeptide expression (Pomc, Cart, Npy) whatever the BPS doses; Enhanced Agrp mRNA levels were observed in mice treated with the highest dose of BPS Hypothalamic Expression of Apelin was not influenced in contrast to the Apelin receptor which expression was lowered at the two highest doses	BPS exposure could contribute to obesity in male mice through modulating hypothalamic neuropeptides regulating food behavior and apelin/APJ system	Based on data published in this article, the reviewer agrees with the conclusions of the authors. However, in Rezg et al., the authors observed a significant decrease in Apelin mRNA levels not found in the present article.
Rezg et al., 2019	Swiss albino mice.	Drinking water	0; 25; 50; 100 µg of BPS /kg/day based on mean daily water intake of 2ml/ 10 g mice (i.e. same protocol as in Rezg et al., 2018)	24 male mice (10 g) divided in 4 groups of n=6.	<u>Duodenum:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Decreased Glut2 and Sgl1t1 mRNA levels at all doses . decreased Apelin mRNA levels at the highest dose and of APJ at the 2 highest doses 	BPS exposure could contribute to glucose intestinal uptake disruption. It will result in enhanced expression of G6Pase and Pepck genes which encoded	The data presented in Rezg et al., 2019 did not discuss the previous data of their own, especially regarding lack of effect on Apelin

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 212

Reference	Species Strain Model	Route	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
					<p><u>Liver:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Enhanced G6Pase mRNA levels at the 2 highest doses and of Pepck at the 50 dose . no effect on the inflammatory markers Tnfa and Il1b at the mRNA levels 	proteins are involved in glucose metabolism in the liver. Collectively, it is suggested that BPS exposure disrupts glucose haemostasis.	mRNA levels in Rezg et al 2018. Therefore, there is a lack of confidence for both articles.
Gao et al., 2020	Thirty female C57BL/6 mice (4 weeks) plus 1 week accomodation; 10-week exposure starting after a 1 week acclimatation period;	Drinking water	50 µg/kg bw/day and 5000 µg/kg bw/day of BPS or BPA (calculation is based on the fact that a mouse of 20g will drink an average of 4 mL/day. Diet is not specified; Body weight weekly recorded, GTT;	30 mice divided in 5 groups.	<p>No apparent effect on mouse body weight and glucose homeostasis (GTTs)</p> <p><i>in vitro</i> data demonstrated PPARG activation and enhanced gene expression of PPARG target genes following stimulation with either BPA or BPS of a human monocyte cell line (THP-1)</p> <p>based on the <i>in vitro</i> data, the authors evaluated gene expression of Nr1c3 (PPARG), PPARG target genes and of Nr1h3 (encoding LXRA) in the liver of the BPA and BPS-exposed females. Findings: Nr1c3 mRNA levels did not change contrasting with Fabp4 (AP2) (enhanced at the highest dose of BPA and BPS) and Nr1h3 (significantly enhanced at both doses of BPA and BPS). No differences were observed between BPA and BPS –induced gene expression of Fabp4 and Nr1h3. The expression of Cd36 was not impacted by BPA and BPS.</p> <p>Analysis of the liver metabolic profiles indicated that profiles were significantly disturbed following BPA or BPS exposure. For example, there was a decreased level of glutathione (GSH) in all treated groups which</p>	BPA as well as BPS disturb hepatic metabolism <i>via</i> altering PPARG signaling	Findings indicated that BPS was as efficient as BPA at disturbing hepatic metabolism in a model of female mice exposed for 10 weeks. In contrast to the authors, I would not conclude firmly on PPARG activation. FABP4 is essentially of adipocyte origin and its levels correlate with obesity. In liver, FABP4 has been identified as a predictive gene marker for the transition from NAFL to NASH. Both PPARG and LXRA are lipid sensors, and Nr1h3 mRNA levels are strongly elevated in

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 213

Reference	Species Strain Model	Route	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion	Comments / quality of the study
					is one of the most potent intracellular anti-oxidants. There were also changes observed after BPA exposure and not after BPS exposure or vice-versa.		response to BPA and BPS suggesting that LXRA more than PPARG is involved in hepatic metabolism changes.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 214

11.2 Annex 2: Derivation of HBM-GVs for BPS under scenario 1

Derivation of the HBM-GVGenPop: Prediction of the total BPS urinary concentration with 100 % oral exposure and with a POD of 0.5 µg/kg bw/day corresponding to a continuous exposure of 0.0066 µg/kg bw/day in the general population

For an adult of 70 kg

This scenario considered the results on alteration of oocyte maturation and folliculogenesis in mice (Shi, Sekulovski, et al., 2019) leading to a LOAEL less than or equal to 0.5 µg/kg bw/day. Applying assessment factor of 75 ($3 \times 2.5 \times 10$)¹⁶ and assuming a constant and continuous oral exposure throughout the day of BPS leads to a constant exposure to 0.0066 µg/kg bw/day. The concentration of free BPS in plasma estimated for a male adult of 70 kg at this constant exposure of 0.0066 µg/kg bw/day is illustrated in Figure III.10. The maximum concentration of plasmatic free and glucuronidated BPS estimated is 2.42×10^{-3} nmol/l (0.61 ng/l) after 24 constant exposure.

Constant exposure = 0.0066 µg/kg bw/day

Figure III.10: Estimated free BPS and (gluco)conjugated BPS plasmatic concentrations (nmol/l) for a 70 kg adult after 24h constant and continuous oral exposure to 0.0066 µg BPS/kg bw averaged over 24h

¹⁶ A factor (AF) of 3 is applied for extrapolating a LOAEL to a NOAEL. The interspecies differences in toxicokinetics between animal species and human are determined by PBPK modeling, and an assessment factor of 2.5 is applied for remaining interspecies differences (mostly for toxicodynamic differences). Finally, an assessment factor of 10 is applied for intraspecies differences to take into account the variability of response in the general population.

The concentration of total BPS in urine predicted for an adult of 70 kg after constant and continuous oral exposure is illustrated in Figure III.11. The estimated urinary concentration of total BPS (sum of estimated urinary glucuronidated and free BPS) is 1.03 nmol/l (257.1 ng/l) after 24h constant exposure to 0.0066 µg/kg bw/day .

Constant exposure = 0.0066 µg/kg bw/day

Figure III.11: Estimated urinary total BPS concentrations (nmol/l) for a 70 kg adult after 24h constant and continuous oral exposure to 0.0066 µg of BPS/kg bw averaged over 24h the general population

Derivation of the HBM-GVworker: Prediction of the total BPS urinary concentration with 100 % oral exposure and with a POD of 0.5 µg/kg bw/day corresponding to an exposure of 0.0066 µg/kg bw/day - occupational exposure

This scenario considered the results on alteration of oocyte maturation and folliculogenesis in mice (Shi, Sekulovski, et al., 2019) leading to a LOAEL lower or equal to 0.5 µg/kg bw/day. Applying assessment factor of 75 ($3 \times 2.5 \times 10$)¹⁷ and assuming a constant and continuous oral exposure throughout the day of BPS, this would lead to a constant exposure to 0.0066 µg/kg bw/day. As occupational exposure is not continuous all over the day and week, the modelling was refined in order to reflect a continuous exposure during 8 hours per day followed by a non-exposure period of 16 hours. This 8 hour exposure and 16 hour exposure period was then repeated 4 times in order to mimic a working week. Thus, this 5 day occupational scenario includes an 8 hour exposure period with 0.0198 µg/kg bw and a non exposure period of 16h which then corresponds to an exposure all over the day (0-24hour) of 0.0066 µg/kg bw/day.

The predicted **plasmatic** concentration of free BPS assuming an oral exposure to 0.0198 µg/kg bw from 0h to 8h and to 0 µg/kg bw from 8h to 24h each day during 5 days for an adult of 70 kg

¹⁷ A factor of 3 is applied for extrapolating a LOAEL to a NOAEL. The interspecies differences in toxicokinetics between animal species and human are determined by PBPK modeling, and an assessment factor of 2.5 is applied for remaining interspecies differences (mostly for toxicodynamic differences). Finally, a factor of 10 accounting for intra-species differences is further applied to the human adjusted NOAEL. Generally, this factor is set to 5 when workers are the targeted population for which the HBM-GV is derived, in line with ECHA's R8 guidance for deriving DNELs for worker (ECHA, 2012). However, in case of BPS the most sensitive endpoint(s) to be protected from are the effects on the unborn child. Thus, no differences can be assumed between the foetuses of the general population and the workers.

is illustrated in Figure III.12. **The maximum plasmatic concentration of total BPS (free and glucuronidated BPS) predicted is 7×10^{-3} nmol/l (1.76 ng/l).**

Exposure 8h/day = 0.00198 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}$
 Average exposure 24h = 0.0066 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$

Figure III.12: Estimated free BPS and glucuronidated BPS plasmatic concentrations (nmol/l) for an adult of 70 kg considering an occupational scenario during 5 days with for each day an exposure from 0h to 8h to 0.0198 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}$ and from 8h to 24h to 0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}$ corresponding to 0.0066 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$ over a day (0-24h)

The concentration of total BPS in urine predicted for an adult of 70 kg assuming an oral exposure to 0.0198 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}$ from 0h to 8h and to 0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}$ from 8h to 24h each day during 5 days is illustrated in Figure III.13. The estimated urinary concentration of total BPS is 3.0 nmol/l (752 ng/l).

Exposure 8h/day = 0.00198 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw

Average exposure 24h = 0.0066 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw/day

Figure III.13: Estimated urinary total BPS concentrations (nmol/l) for an adult of 70 kg considering an occupational scenario during 5 days with for each day an exposure from 0h to 8h to 0.0198 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw and from 8h to 24h to 0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw corresponding to 0.0066 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw/day over a day (0-24h)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 218

Part IV

Substance dossier on Bisphenol F

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 219

Table of contents (Part IV)

Authors and acknowledgements	220
Abbreviations	221
1 General information on BPF	224
1.1 Identification of the substance	224
1.2 Physico-chemical properties of BPF	224
1.3 Uses of BPF	224
1.4 Existing EU classification and regulation of BPF	226
1.4.1 Harmonised classification and labelling	226
1.4.2 EU directives and regulations of BPF	227
1.5 Human exposure to BPF	227
1.5.1 Environmental and consumers exposure	227
1.5.2 Occupational exposure	233
2 Toxicological profile of BPF	235
2.1 Toxicokinetics	235
2.1.1 Toxicokinetic data in humans	235
2.1.2 Toxicokinetic data in animals and <i>in vitro</i>	235
2.2 Health effects of BPF	237
2.2.1 Acute Toxicity and Irritation	237
2.2.2 Sensitisation	238
2.2.3 Repeated dose toxicity	238
2.2.4 Genotoxicity	239
2.2.5 Carcinogenicity	240
2.2.6 Toxicity to reproduction	240
2.2.7 Studies on endocrine effects	250
2.3 Existing evaluations and derivations of tolerable doses	254
3 Conclusion on the derivation of HBM-GVs for BPF	256
4 References	257

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 220

Authors and acknowledgements

Lead authors

Claire Beausoleil (ANSES)

Contributors

ANSES Working Group on Biomarkers, especially Florence Zeman, Jean-Philippe Antignac, ANSES Working Group on Endocrine Disruptors, Sylvie Babajko, Marie-Chantal Canivenc, Nicolas Chevalier, Claude Emond, Nicole Hagen-Picard, Brigitte LeMagueresse-Batistoni and Sakina Mhaouty-Kodja, Christophe Rouselle (ANSES), Matthieu Meslin (ANSES), Petra Apel (UBA), Rosa Lange (UBA)

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank the following experts for reviewing this report:

Andreas Kortenkamp (Brunel University, London), Dirven Hubert (NIPH), María Angeles Martínez Rodríguez (IISPV), Maria Uhl (EEA), Rex FitzGerald (SCAHT), Shalenie den Braver-Sewradj (RIVM), Wieneke Bil (RIVM), Sophie Ndaw (INRS), Susana Viegas (ENSP), Teresa Borges (DGS)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 221

Abbreviations

AGP	Alpha1-acid glycoprotein
ALP	Alkaline Phosphatase
ANSES	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety
BADGE	Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether
BE	Biomonitoring Equivalent
BfR	Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung (Federal Institute for Risk Assessment)
BLV	Bundesamt für Lebensmittelsicherheit und Veterinärwesen, Schweiz (Federal Food Safety and Veterinary Office, Switzerland)
BLV	Biological Limit Value
BMDL	Benchmark Dose Lower Confidence Limit
BMI	Body Mass Index
BPA	Bisphenol A
BPAF	Bisphenol AF
BPAP	Bisphenol AP
BPB	Bisphenol B
BPC	Bisphenol C
BPE	Bisphenol E
BPF	Bisphenol F
BPM	Bisphenol M
BPs	Bisphenols
BPS	Bisphenol S
BPP	Bisphenol P
BPZ	Bisphenol Z
bw	Body weight
CEF Panel	Panel on Food Contact Materials, Enzymes, Flavourings and Processing Aids
CHL	Chinese Hamster Lung (cells)
CLP	Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures
DK	Domžale-Kamnik
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 222

EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
ER	Estrogen receptor
EU	European Union
GD	Gestation day
GPER	G protein-coupled estrogen receptor
γ GT	γ -Glutamyl transferase
HBM-GV	HBM Guidance Value
HBM-GV _{GenPop}	HBM-GV for the general population
HBM-GV _{Worker}	HBM-GV for occupationally exposed adults
HBM4EU	European Human Biomonitoring Initiative
HED	Human equivalent dose
HSA	Human serum albumin
LJ	Ljubljana
LO(A)EL	Lowest Observed (Adverse) Effect Level
LOD	Limit of Detection
LOQ	Limit of Quantification
LPO	Peroxided lipids
MS	Mass Spectrometry
NHANES	National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey
NO(A)EL	No Observed (Adverse) Effect Level
NOGE	Novolac glycidylethers
NTP	National Toxicology Program
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PACT	Public Activities Coordination Tool
PBPK	Physiologically-based pharmacokinetic
PCPs	Personal care products
PND	Postnatal day
PNW	Postnatal week
RBC	Red blood cell
REACH	Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
RMOA	Regulatory management option analysis
SOD	Superoxide dismutase

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 223

T4	Thyroxine
TDI	Tolerable Daily Intake
t-TDI	Temporary Tolerable Daily Intake
TK	Toxicokinetic
TSH	Thyroid stimulating hormone
UGT	Uridine 5'-diphospho-glucuronosyltransferase
WWs	Wastewaters
WWTPs	Wastewater treatment plants

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 224

1 General information on BPF

1.1 Identification of the substance

Bisphenol F (BPF, Bis(4-Hydroxy diphenyl)methane, 4,4'-Dihydroxy diphenyl methane, 4,4'-Methylene diphenol) is a structural analogue of BPA (Cc1ccc(O)cc1C(c2ccc(O)cc2)C3=CC=CC=C3). However, compared to BPA, only small amounts are produced. BPF does also occur naturally in plants.

Few studies are available on the toxicity of BPF; these have been summarised in some brief reports (NTP 2017, U.S. EPA 2015, BfR 2015b, BLV 2015, JECDB (without year), EFSA CEF Panel 2009, Chen et al. 2016). The substance is only preregistered under REACH yet. BPF is listed in the Public Activities Coordination Tool (PACT) of the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA). Actually, a “regulatory management option analysis” (RMOA) is performed by the Swedish Chemicals Agency, because there is concern regarding possible endocrine disruptive effects of BPF (ECHA 2020b).

Figure IV.1: Structural formula of bisphenol F (left) and bisphenol A (right) for comparison)

1.2 Physico-chemical properties of BPF

The physico-chemical properties of BPF are shown in table IV.1. At room temperature, BPF is a whitish solid which is sparingly soluble in water but soluble in alkalis, ethanol, diethyl ether and chloroform (HSDB 2013). Technical BPF is a mixture of the three isomers 2,2'-, 2,4'-, and 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane, the last-mentioned being the dominant and the technically preferred one. If not stated otherwise, the name “BPF” will be used in this evaluation for 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane or for the technical mixture mainly containing 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane. No quantitative data are available about the portion of the isomers 2,2'- and 2,4'-BPF in the technical product.

1.3 Uses of BPF

Technical BPF is produced by reaction of phenol with formaldehyde. As the structurally related BPA, which is produced and used in much larger amounts, BPF is also used in the production of epoxy resins. E.g., BPF is a precursor for Novolac glycidylethers (NOGE), which in turn are precursors for epoxy resins in lacquers. In Europe, use of such lacquers in food industry is only allowed for storage tanks with a content exceeding 10,000 liters but not for coating of food cans. Generally, compared to BPA-epoxy resins, BPF products only play a minor role (BfR 2015a). According to ECHA the substance with CAS number 1333-16-0 (Reaction mass of 4,4'-methylenediphenol and 2,2'-methylenediphenol and o-[(4-hydroxyphenyl)methyl]phenol) is used

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 225

in polymers. This substance has industrial uses as intermediate and is used for the manufacture of plastic products. Other release to the environment of this substance is likely to occur from: indoor use and outdoor use resulting in inclusion into or onto materials (e.g. binding agent in paints and coatings or adhesives). It is produced in the range of 1000 to 10000 tonnes per year in the European Economic Area (ECHA 2020).

Table IV.1: Physico-chemical properties of BPF

Substance	Bisphenol F
IUPAC Name	4,4'-Methylenediphenol
CAS No.	620-92-8 (for 4,4'-Dihydroxydiphenylmethane)
EC No.	210-658-2
Other CAS No.	2467-03-0 (2,4'-Dihydroxydiphenylmethane) 2467-02-9 (2,2'-Dihydroxydiphenylmethane) 1333-16-0 (Mixture of isomers)
Sum formula	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ O ₂ for Bisphenol F
Molar mass (g/mol)	200.24
Vapour pressure	3.7 x 10 ⁻⁷ mm Hg (calculated) and 5.5 x 10 ⁻⁷ mm Hg and 1.2 x 10 ⁻⁶ mm Hg at 20 °C and 25°C respectively for the mixture of isomers corresponding to CAS number 1333-16-0
Melting point °C	162.5
Boiling point °C	subliming
Density (g/cm³)	No data for BPF 1.279 g/cm ³ for the mixture of isomers corresponding to CAS number 1333-16-0 ^{&}
Log Kow	2.91 ^{&}
pK_a	pks1: 7.55 [*] , pks2: 10.8 [#]
Solubility in water (mg/L at 22 °C)	2,970 at 20 C ^{&}
Physical condition (20 °C, 1013 hPa)	solid
Colour	Whitish and light pink ^{&}

*: Data from US EPA (2015); #: Data from SDB (2013); &: Data from ECHA registration dossier (2020a) on CAS number: 1333-16-0.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 226

1.4 Existing EU classification and regulation of BPF

1.4.1 Harmonised classification and labelling

BPF is currently not classified under the European Union (EU) classification and labelling (CLP) Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008.

Table IV.2: BPF classification according to Annex VI of the EU Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008

International Chemical Identification	CAS No.	Classification		Labelling	
		Hazard Class & Category code(s)	Hazard statement code(s)	Pictogram, Signal Word code(s)	Hazard statement code(s)
4,4'-methylenediphenol	620-92-8	ECHA Infocard: <i>Danger!</i> According to the classification provided by companies to ECHA in CLP notifications this substance is toxic to aquatic life with long lasting effects, causes serious eye damage, causes skin irritation, may cause respiratory irritation and may cause an allergic skin reaction.			

Table IV.3: BPF self-classification proposal (ECHA Substance Information, 2020c)

International Chemical Identification	CAS No.	Self-classification and labelling propo-sal		
		Hazard Class & Category code(s)	Hazard statement code(s)	Pictogram, Signal Word code(s)
4,4'-methylenediphenol	620-92-8	Skin Irrit. 2 Skin Sens. 1 Eye Dam. 1 Eye Irrit. 2 STOT SE 3 Aquatic Chronic 2 Aquatic Chronic 3	H315 H317 H318 H319 H335 H411 H412	GHS07 Harmful GHS05 Corrosive GHS09 Environmental hazard

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 227

1.4.2 EU directives and regulations of BPF

Currently, BPF is not addressed in the following EU Directives and regulations: food contact material, cosmetic products safety, toy safety directive or occupational safety and health.

1.5 Human exposure to BPF

1.5.1 Environmental and consumers exposure

1.5.1.1 Environmental, food, and other product related external exposure

Few data are available regarding the occurrence of BPF in environmental media (Česen et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2016; Yamazaki et al., 2015).

Exploratory studies conducted in Hessian surface waters in Germany in 1999/2000 could not detect BPF in any of the 20 samples (detection limit 0.025 µg/l). Other studies cited in this report and conducted in 1998 found 0.21-0.97 ng BPF/ml in surface water (Außenalster, Hamburg) and up to 48 µg/kg dry weight in sedimented suspended matter of the river Elbe. Discharge of Hessian municipal sewage plants did not contain detectable concentrations of BPF (limit of detection (LOD) of 0.05 µg/l, n=9) (HLUG 2011).

77 % of the samples obtained from various surface waters in Germany in 1997 (n=30) contained detectable concentrations of BPF (LOD 0.1 ng/l). In 72 % of water samples (n=25) from sewage plants BPF could be detected at concentrations of 0.022 – 0.123 µg/l (LOD 0.1 ng/l). 58 % of sediment samples from sewage plants (n=7) contained 1.2 - 7.3 µg/kg (LOD 1 µg/kg dry weight). In discharge of waste dumps 0.33 or 1.13 µg/l (n=2), respectively, could be detected. Water from compost contained 1.7 resp. 2.8 µg/l (n=2). Three out of 10 samples of liquid manure contained 2.2.-62.6 µg/kg dry weight (Fromme et al., 2002).

Exploratory studies conducted on surface waters collected from Japanese, Korean, Chinese, and Indian rivers and in seawater from Tokyo Bay could detect BPF. BPF concentrations were one to two orders of magnitude higher than those of BPA in river and seawaters collected from Japan, Korea and China, which suggests that BPF is a major contaminant in surface waters in several Southeast Asian countries. BPF concentrations as high as 2850 ng/l were found in the Tamagawa River in Japan whereas BPA was found at a concentration in the range of several tens to several hundreds of ng/l in most of the rivers surveyed and some of the highest concentrations (54 - 1950 ng/l) were found in rivers in Chennai, India (Yamazaki et al., 2015).

BPF was detected in waste waters from textile cleaning companies waste water treatment plants and from two food production/processing plants located in Denmark and Slovenia. (Česen et al., 2018).

This study reports the occurrence of eight Bisphenols (BPs): bisphenol AF (BPAF), bisphenol AP (BPAP), bisphenol B (BPB), bisphenol C (BPC), bisphenol E (BPE), bisphenol F (BPF), bisphenol S (BPS) and bisphenol Z (BPZ) in wastewaters (WWs). Sample preparation involved pre-concentration with solid phase extraction cartridges (Oasis HLB), followed by derivatization using N-(tert-butyldimethylsilyl)-N-methyltrifluoroacetamide with 1% tertbutyldimethylchlorosilane. Chemical analysis was based on gas chromatography–mass spectrometry. A validated method with LODs at ng/l range was applied to WWs collected at five Slovene wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) and WW inflows from industrial, commercial and residential sources entering the sewerage systems of two catchments (Domžale-Kamnik (DK) and Ljubljana (LJ)). The presence of all BPs was confirmed in three inflows in DK and two

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 228

inflows in the LJ catchments. High cumulative concentrations of all BPs were determined in WW from food processing facilities (LJ: 3030 ng/l and DK: 599 ng/l). A high detection frequency was observed in the WW from two textile cleaning companies (6 BPs for LJ and 8 BPs for DK). The analysis of WW from WWTPs revealed that concentrations of BPF (36.7 ng/L) and BPS (40.6 ng/L) were only in the inflows greater than the LODs, whereas other BPs were detected also in the effluents. In contrast to BPA, BPF is a substance naturally occurring in plants or plant-derived foodstuffs. BPF had already been detected as natural compound in bulbs of an orchid species in 1995 which is used as natural remedy in China; and later on in other orchid species, too (Zoller et al., 2016, BLV 2015). Of particular relevance regarding the exposure of the general population in Middle Europe was the detection of this substance in mustard. The Swiss Federal Food Safety and Veterinary Office (Bundesamt für Lebensmittelsicherheit und Veterinärwesen, BLV) could detect a mean concentration of 1840 µg BPF/kg in 61 samples of mustard (maximum: 8350 µg/kg) (BLV 2015). These data could be confirmed in analyses of 11 samples of sweet (mild) and medium hot mustard in Germany in which BPF concentrations of 850-6200 µg/kg were measured. It is striking that, as in the Swiss analyses, no or very little BPF could be detected in samples from hot mustard (< 35 µg/kg) (Kielmeier 2015).

More close examinations of the BLV revealed that BPF was not a contamination originating from packaging materials but is formed during the production of mustard from glucosinolates (mustard oils) naturally occurring in mustard seed. White mustard (*Sinapis alba*) which is used for the production of mild to medium hot mustard does contain the glucosinolat glucosinalbin. During the processing of mustard, acetic acid is added and, subsequently, 4-hydroxybenzyl iso-thiocyanate and further on 4 hydroxybenzyl alcohol are formed by hydrolysis and react to produce BPF (Figure 2) in a way not finally understood yet. Black mustard (*Brassica nigra*), which is used for the production of hot mustard, does not contain glucosinalbin but other glucosinolates which do not form BPF (BLV 2015, Zoller et al. 2016). As 4 hydroxybenzyl alcohol occurs widespread in low amounts in plants, it is considered possible that small amounts of BPF may be produced in other food products from plants. Indeed, traces of BPF (about 50 µg/kg) could be detected in pickled bamboo shoots (Zoller et al., 2016).

Figure IV.2: Chemical structure of glucosinalbin (left) and possible way for the formation of BPF (right) with intermediary products (according to BLV 2016, Zoller et al., 2016)

Food is considered the main source of BPF exposure. However, no BPF could be detected in a survey of bisphenols in canned foods in 62 samples in Great Britain in 2001 (LOD 5 µg/kg for the 2,2'- and 2,4'-isomers and 10 µg/kg for the 4,4'-isomer of BPF) (BfR 2015b). Also, almost no BPF derived from epoxy resins could be detected in canned foods (this study was performed

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 229

prior to the ban of such BPF-containing coatings in the European Union in 2005) (Jordakova et al., 2003).

The level of eight bisphenol compounds were determined in 289 food samples from Chinese megacities in a study in 2012. The mean level of BPF in all examined food samples was 2.5 µg/kg fresh weight (median 0.025 µg/kg). The absolutely highest value was noticed in bamboo shoots. Excluding this, the highest values were found in fish and seafood (mean value 1.74 µg/kg) (BfR 2015b, BLV 2015). In the US, bisphenol analogues were measured in 267 food samples. Overall, the mean level for all sampled foodstuffs was 0.929 µg/kg fresh weight. Fish and seafood had the highest mean values (4.63 µg/kg fresh weight) except for a salad dressing with mustard (1130 µg/kg) (BfR 2015b, BLV 2015, Liao and Kannan 2013).

The average daily intake of BPF with food is estimated to be about 7.46 µg/kg bw/day (95th percentile 19.7 µg/kg bw/day) for adults, based on data on the BPF content in food in an US-American study. The highest burden is calculated for children aged 1-6 years (mean value 22.3 µg/kg bw/day, 95th percentile 70.2 µg/kg bw/day). The intake of BPF reaches about 11-16 % of that estimated for BPA (Liao and Kannan 2013).

Low concentrations of BPF were determined in house dust. Measurements conducted in the USA and Asian countries in indoor dust samples (n=156) provided a median value of 96 and a maximum value of 1070 µg/kg. Estimates of the daily intake based on these data provide the highest values for small children (median 0.00024 µg/kg bw, 95th percentile 0.001 µg/kg bw) (BfR 2015b).

It is discussed whether BPF could be dermally taken up from body care products. Based on bisphenol levels measured in such products in the US, dermal uptake is estimated to be around 2.96 µg/day (95th percentile) (BfR 2015b). BPF is also discussed as possible alternative to BPA in thermal papers (U.S.EPA 2015). BPF was not detected in thermal and non-thermal paper products collected in Beijing, China (Yang et al. 2019). BPF, BPA, and BPS were the major bisphenols found in feminine hygiene products collected in the Albany area of New York State in the United States (Gao et al., 2020). BPF was widely found in tampons (92 %) and panty liners (69 %) at median concentrations of 8.44 and 4.82 ng/g, respectively. Lastly, BPF and BPA were present in <50 % of non-feminine hygiene related Personal Care Products (PCPs) from the United States (Liao and Kannan 2014).

1.5.1.2 Urinary internal exposure levels

Similar to what has been observed for BPA, the urinary excretion appears to be the most commonly used parameter for estimating internal exposure to BPF. In a vast majority of available studies, the urinary exposure level is estimated after enzymatic hydrolysis of the conjugates, so that the total of free plus conjugated forms is finally determined. The determination of total urinary BPF also appears as the prioritised marker within the European Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU) project. Although the unconjugated form is likely to be the active one to induce a given effect, the measurement of total BPF allows a better compatibility with current methodological detection limits, and is a protective exposure assessment approach considering possible deconjugation. Very few data are conversely available regarding the excretion levels of non-conjugated BPF in urine, which confirmed a very low proportion (<1 %) of free urinary BPF (Santé Publique France, 2019). The vast majority of existing studies have determined exposure levels in spot urine samples.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 230

Existing data extracted from the examined studies (n=16) with regard to reported human urinary levels of BPF is presented in table IV.4. Before detailing the results of each study, their heterogeneity in terms of concentration units (i.e. µg/l, µg/g creatinine, or µg/l corrected for specific gravity), statistical descriptors for documenting the exposure distribution (e.g. mean or geometric mean, various percentiles), as well as methodological sensitivity threshold (LOD, Limit of Quantification (LOQ)) and QA/QC provisions implemented to ensure a consolidated consistency of the generated results do not permit a direct and fast comparability between these different studies. The diversity of the considered sub-populations, geographical sampling areas and year of sampling, also contribute to the difficult comparability across the reported data.

Ashrap et al. (2018) assessed the distributions, time trends, and predictors of various urinary exposure markers including 7 phenols among which BPA, BPS and BPF, measured at multiple times during pregnancy among 1003 women living in Northern Puerto Rico. Detectable concentrations among pregnant women were prevalent and tended to be lower than levels measured in women of reproductive age from the general US population. For women living in Northern Puerto Rico, the reported median value for total urinary BPF is 0.1 µg/L, the 95th percentile is 2.1 µg/L with a 41.1 % detection frequency and a LOD of 0.2 µg/L. For women from the general US population the reported median value for total urinary BPF is 0.4 µg/L, the 95th percentile is 8.8 µg/L with a 67.2 % detection frequency and a LOD of 0.2 µg/L.

Asimakopoulos et al. (2016) investigated the urinary concentrations of various xenobiotics including bisphenols in a population of 130 individuals from Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, in the scope of delineating their association with the oxidative stress biomarker 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine (8OHdG). The reported median value for total urinary BPF is 2.16 µg/l with a 9 % detection frequency and a LOD of 0.75 µg/l.

Chen et al. (2018) determined seven chemicals including BPA, BPS and BPF in 283 urine samples collected from children aged between 3 and 11 years from south China. The reported median value for total urinary BPF is 0.19 µg/l corrected for specific gravity with a 12 % detection frequency and a LOD of 0.1 µg/l.

Duan et al. (2018) conducted a case-control study to examine the associations of urinary levels of 8 bisphenols with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) for 502 Chinese individuals in total. The reported mean value (median value not communicated) of total urinary BPF is 0.101 µg/g creatinine with a 31.7 % detection frequency and a LOD not specified.

Husøy et al. (2019) provided a detailed description of the design of the EuroMix biomonitoring study, presented the initial results for five bisphenols including BPA, BPS and BPF measured in urine of 144 individuals from Norway, and described their exposure determinants from food and PCPs. The reported median value for total urinary BPF is 0.08 µg/l corrected for specific gravity with a 4 % detection frequency and a LOD of 0.07 µg/l.

Kang et al. (2020) investigated the effects of bisphenols on hemopoiesis and the serum biochemical parameters in a population of 196 Corean pregnant women from the MAKE cohort study. They measured the levels of BPA, BPF and BPS in urine samples and collected data on socioeconomic, lifestyle, and environmental factors at visits to the hospital. The reported median value for total urinary BPF is 0.2 µg/l corrected for specific gravity with an 81 % detection frequency and a LOD of 0.08 µg/l.

Lehmler et al. (2018) analysed urinary bisphenol levels in 1808 adults and 868 children participating in the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) in the U.S., and

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 231

investigated demographic and lifestyle factors associated with urinary levels of bisphenols (BPA, BPS, and BPF). The reported median value for total urinary BPF is 0.35 and 0.32 µg/l respectively for adults and children (0.46 and 0.41 µg/g creatinine, resp.) with a 66.5-65.4 % detection frequency and a LOD of 0.2 µg/l.

Liu Y et al. (2019) determined the levels of four bisphenols including BPA, BPS and BPF in urine samples collected from 80 preschool-age children in Gaochun District, China, and studied the concentrations, distribution profiles, potential sources and cumulative risk of the target compounds. The reported mean value for total urinary BPF is 0.0069 µg/l with a 21.2 % detection frequency and a LOD not specified.

Machtinger et al. (2018) quantified urinary concentrations of various biomarkers of exposure including BPA, BPS and BPF among 49 pregnant women in Israel. The reported median value for total urinary BPF is 0.2 µg/l (0.4 µg/l corrected by specific gravity) with a 51 % detection frequency and a LOD of 0.2 µg/l.

Philips, Kahn, et al. 2018 and Philips, Jaddoe, et al. 2018 described the associations of first trimester urinary concentrations of 8 bisphenols, including BPA, BPS and BPF, with time to pregnancy among 1396/877 participants in the population-based Generation R pregnancy cohort in the Netherlands. The reported median value for total urinary BPF is 0.57/0.58 µg/l with a 40.2/41.2 % detection frequency and a LOD of 0.18 µg/l. No associations of bisphenols with fecundability were found. Preconception folic acid supplementation seems to modify effects of bisphenols on fecundability. Folic acid supplements may protect against reduced fecundability among women exposed to these chemicals.

Sakhi et al. (2018) measured urinary levels of twelve different environmental phenols including BPS and BPF in healthy 48 mothers and paired 54 children in Norway. The reported median value for total urinary BPF is <LOD, with a LOD of 0.07 µg/l. Among the emerging bisphenols, BPS was detected most frequently in the urine samples (42-48 %) followed by BPF (4-15 %).

Yang et al. (2014) measured the concentrations of seven bisphenols, including BPA, BPS and BPF, in human urine samples from a cohort of 94 residents living close to an area where electronic scrap is recycled in south China. BPS, BPF, BPA and Bisphenol AF (BPAF) were detected in urine samples at concentrations ranging from <LOQ to a few µg/l. The reported geometric mean value (median value not communicated) for total urinary BPF is 0.228 µg/l (0.214 µg/g creatinine), with a non-communicated detection frequency and a LOD of 0.1 µg/l.

Zhang H et al. (2020) detected concentrations of seven BPs, including BPA, BPS and BPF, in paired urine (n = 160 university students from South China) and indoor dust samples (n = 40 dormitories). The reported geometric mean value (median value not communicated) for total urinary BPF is 0.16 µg/l, with an 80 % detection frequency and a LOD of 0.01 µg/l.

Zhou et al. (2020) measured urinary BPA, BPF, and BPS concentrations among 322 pregnant women during late pregnancy from a cohort study in Wuhan, China. The reported median value for total urinary BPF is 0.08 µg/l (0.09 µg/g creatinine) with a 79.8 % detection frequency and a LOD of 0.03 µg/l. Prenatal exposure to BPA but not BPF and BPS was found sex-specifically associated with certain fetal growth parameters.

Measurements of BPF were performed in the framework of the French biomonitoring (Esteban study), including 900 adults from 18 to 74 years old and 500 children from 6 to 17 years old. The observed median value for total urinary BPF was 0.307 µg/l (0.423 µg/g creatinine) for adults,

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 232

and 0.340 µg/l (0.339 µg/g creatinine) for children. The detection frequencies were 100 and 99.9 % for adults and children respectively and the LOD was 0.005 µg/l.

1.5.1.3 Blood, plasma and serum internal exposure levels

Existing data extracted from the examined studies with regard to reported human blood (including whole blood, plasma or serum) levels of BPF is presented in table IV.5. Conversely to what is observed for urinary analyses where a systematic hydrolysis of conjugated metabolites is operated prior to detection, analytical protocols for blood analysis appear more heterogenous as some of them are reporting the levels of the free form while others sometimes apply a double analysis to separately determine the free and the total of free plus conjugated forms. Globally, it must be mentioned that the analysis of bisphenols in human blood is remaining clearly less common than in urine, one reason explaining this observation being linked to the higher analytical difficulty and need for enhanced sensitivity of the detection systems.

Ihde et al. (2018) explored the *in utero* exposure to 6 bisphenols including BPA, BPS and BPF in 30 mother-child pairs recruited in the US. The detection frequency of BPF was 17 % in maternal urine and 50 % in fetal cord blood.

Jin H et al. (2018) quantified nine bisphenols including BPA, BPS and BPF in 81 pairs of plasma and red blood cell (RBC) samples from Chinese participants. The predominant BPs in the plasma samples were BPA (detection frequency 46 %), BPS (detection frequency 56 %), and BPAF (detection frequency 31 %), with mean concentrations of 0.40, 0.15, and 0.073 ng/ml, respectively. BPA and BPS were the major BPs in the RBC fraction (detection frequencies 44 % and 76 %, respectively). BPF was only detected in one plasma sample (0.32 ng/ml) and completely absent in RBCs.

Li et al. (2020) measured a range of ten bisphenols including BPS and BPF in 181 serum samples from pregnant Chinese women. The reported median value for BPF is <LOD with a 20.4 % detection frequency and a LOD of 0.005 µg/l.

Owczarek et al. (2018) described a methodological protocol for simultaneous extraction and determination of eleven bisphenols including BPA, BPS and BPF in human blood samples and applied the developed method to 245 adult women in Poland. The reported median value for BPF is 0.115 µg/l with a 65 % detection frequency and a LOD of 0.012 µg/l.

Shen et al. (2019) evaluated the bisphenol load of patients with severe renal failure, some of whom were on a renal supply (hemodialysis and peritoneal dialysis). The authors showed that patients on hemodialysis had higher levels of BPA, Bisphenol B (BPB), BPF, and BPS than the healthy controls and peritoneal dialysis patients. In this study, the serum levels of BPA and BPS were negatively correlated with estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR). BPF did not show a correlation with eGFR which might be - according to the authors - due to a possible alternative metabolic pathway or a relative short half-life period (Shanghai, China).

The remaining examined study (Gonzalez et al. 2019) did not report sufficiently documented data for BPF in serum to be considered.

1.5.1.4 Exposure levels in other human matrices

Dualde et al. (2019a/b) addressed the presence of BPA, BPS and BPF in milk of 120 mothers living in Valencia (Spain) and participating in the BETTERMILK project. The determinant of exposure and the risk for breast fed infants were also studied. The frequency of detection was

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 233

much lower for total BPF (22 %) and total BPS (1.1 %) than for total BPA (around 80 %). The reported median value for BPF is however <LOQ (0.13 µg/l).

Jin et al. (2020) determined the levels of BPA, BPS, BPF and BPAF in breast milk samples collected from 190 women in Hangzhou, China and investigated the effects of BPA on postnatal growth of infants through breastmilk consumption. The reported mean value (median value <LOD) for BPS is 0.19 µg/l with a 44 % detection frequency and a LOD of 0.1 µg/l. BPF was not detected in all breastmilk samples.

1.5.2 Occupational exposure

No studies on occupational exposure to BPF have been reported (among the 11 articles selected) highlighting the lack of data. At first sight, there is a need to bridge the gap in terms of exposure assessment to BPA analogs in order to acquire data at European level and improve risk assessment. This is of particular relevance since regulatory actions were taken to reduce BPA but an increase was observed in the use and applications of BPS and BPF (quoted from Deliverable Report D8.5 WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level Upload by Coordinator: 26 March 2019).

The registration dossier (CAS number 1333-16-0) refers to manufacture, use and exposure: <https://echa.europa.eu/de/registration-dossier/-/registered-dossier/26309/7/6/2>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 234

Table IV.4: Summary of information extracted from the examined studies with regard to the BPF concentration levels reported in human urine

Reference	Sampling country	Sampling year	Population	Number of analysed samples	Detection frequency (%)	Concentration unit	LOD	LOQ	Mean	Min	p25	p50	p75	p90	p95	Max	Sample amount for analysis	Deconjugation	Detection method
Ashrap et al., 2018	Porto Rico	2010-2016	General (pregnant women)	1003	41	µg/L	0.2	-	0.3	-	0.1	0.1	0.4	-	2.1	-	100 µL	Yes	LC-MS/MS
Asimakopoulos et al., 2016	Saudi Arabia	2014	General	130	9	-	0.57	-	2.04	0.72	-	2.16	-	-	-	4.56	-	-	LC-MS/MS
Chen et al., 2018	China	2015	General (Child 3-11, Shenzhen and Guangzhou)	283	12	µg/L	0.1	-	0.2	<LOQ	-	0.19	-	-	0.19	0.93	4 mL	Yes	LC-MS/MS
Duan et al., 2018	China	2016-2017	General (Control-Case Type 2 diabetes)	502	32	(µg/g creat.)	-	-	(0.101)	-	-	nd	-	-	-	-	500 µL	Yes	LC-MS/MS
Gonzalez et al., 2019	Spain	?	Occupational (e-waste, Tarragone)	29	0	µg/L	0.03	-	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	5mL	Yes/No	GC-MS
Husoy et al., 2019	Norway	2016-2017	General (Euromix Project)	144	4	[µg/L SG cor.]	0.07	0.2	[0.1]	<LOD	<LOD	[0.08]	[0.11]	[0.13]	[1.15]	[9.92]	200 µL	Yes	LC-MS/MS
Kang et al., 2020	Corea	2017-2019	General (Mother-Child, Seoul)	196	81	[µg/L SG cor.]	0.08	-	[0.2]	-	[0.1]	[0.2]	[0.4]	-	[1.4]	[18]	?	Yes	LC-MS/MS
Lehmle et al., 2018	USA	2013-2014	General (NHANES) - Adults	1808	67	µg/L (µg/g creat.)	0.2	-	-	-	0.14 (0.21)	0.35 (0.46)	1.11 (1.06)	-	-	-	-	Yes	LC-MS/MS
Lehmle et al., 2018	USA	2013-2014	General (NHANES) - Child	868	65	µg/L (µg/g creat.)	0.2	-	-	-	0.14 (0.17)	0.32 (0.41)	0.99 (1.08)	-	-	-	-	Yes	LC-MS/MS
Liu Y et al., 2019	China	2016	General Child, Gaochun	80	21	µg/L	-	0.015	0.0069	<LOD	-	<LOD	-	-	0.048	-	10 mL	Yes	LC-MS/MS
Machtinger et al., 2018	Israel	2015-2016	General (pregnant women)	49	51	µg/L [µg/L SG cor.]	0.2	-	-	-	-	0.2 [0.4]	-	[1.6]	2.4 [3.3]	-	200 µL	Yes	LC-MS/MS
Philips et al., 2018a	Netherlands	2004-2005	General (pregnant women - Generation R study)	1396	40	µg/L	0.18	0.59	-	-	0.3	0.57	1.29	-	-	-	150 µL	Yes	LC-MS/MS
Philips et al., 2018b	Netherlands	2004-2005	General (pregnant women - Generation R study)	877	41	µg/L	0.18	0.59	-	-	0.29	0.58	1.3	-	-	-	150 µL	Yes	LC-MS/MS
Sakhi et al., 2018	Norway	2012	General (couples Mother-Child) - Mother	48	15	[µg/L SG cor.]	0.07	-	[0.08]	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	[4.33]	[7.18]	[7.67]	200 µL	Yes	LC-MS/MS
Sakhi et al., 2018	Norway	2012	General (couples Mother-Child) - Child	54	4	[µg/L SG cor.]	0.07	-	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	[1.88]	[39.2]	-	200 µL	Yes	LC-MS/MS
Yang et al., 2014	China	2013	General (Near BPAF production site)	94	-	µg/L (µg/g creat.)	0.1	0.31	0.228 (0.214)	<LOD	-	-	-	-	-	1.368 (1.207)	2 mL	Yes	LC-MS/MS
Zhang H et al., 2020	China	2018	General (Students Jinan)	160	80	µg/L	-	0.01	0.13	<LOQ	-	0.16	-	-	-	1.28	3 mL	Yes	LC-MS/MS
Zhou et al., 2020	China	2011-2012	General (Mother-Child, Wuhan)	322	79.8	µg/L (µg/g creat.)	0.03	-	0.11 (0.13)	-	0.03 (0.04)	0.08 (0.09)	0.18 (0.23)	0.76 (1.36)	-	-	500 µL	Yes	LC-HRMS

Table IV.5: Summary of information extracted from the examined studies with regard to the BPF concentration levels reported in human blood and other matrices

Reference	Analysed sample type	Sampling country	Sampling year	Population	Number of analysed samples	Detection frequency (%)	Concentration unit	LOD	LOQ	Mean	Min	p25	p50	p75	p90	p95	Max	Sample amount for analysis	Deconjugation	Detection method
Dualde et al., 2019	Milk	Spain	2015	General (Breastfeeding women, Valencia)	91	22	µg/L	-	0.13	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.21	0.46	10 mL	Yes	LC-MS/MS
Gonzalez et al., 2019	Whole blood	Spain	?	Occupational (e-waste, Tarragone)	29	0	µg/L	?	-	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	500 µL	Yes/No	GC-MS
Li et al., 2020	Serum	China	2016	General (pregnant women)	181	20.4	µg/L	0.04	0.134	-	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	-	0.228	0.446	500 µL	No	LC-MS/MS
Owczarek et al., 2018	Serum	Poland	2018 (?)	General (Adult women)	245	65	µg/L	0.012	0.037	-	0.052	-	0.115	-	-	-	0.845	500 µL	No	LC-MS/MS

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 235

2 Toxicological profile of BPF

2.1 Toxicokinetics

2.1.1 Toxicokinetic data in humans

The excretion of BPF was studied in a group of volunteers (study of the Swiss Federal Food Safety and Veterinary Office; only published in a summary report). After eating mustard with a known concentration of BPF, the urine of these volunteers was collected over a longer time period (22h graphed) and the concentration of BPF (4,4'-isomer) was determined after enzymatic hydrolysis. According to the summary data, BPF is very rapidly absorbed and also very rapidly and completely excreted. The highest concentration of BPF in urine was observed within 2-3 h after intake (for one individual a value of about 650 ng/ml can be read from the data presented in a figure). Unfortunately quantitative data are not reported (BLV 2015).

A very high to complete oral absorption may be assumed based on the data reported by the BLV (2015). No data are available regarding the uptake of BPF from other routes, especially by dermal contact.

2.1.2 Toxicokinetic data in animals and *in vitro*

2.1.2.1 Absorption

No data regarding the absorption of BPF in animals or *in vitro* have been retrieved.

2.1.2.2 Binding of BPF to plasma proteins

Once the bisphenols are absorbed, they reach the systemic circulation and are distributed in different tissues including the target organs. Bindings to plasma proteins of bisphenols modulates the biodistribution process and the fraction unbound to plasma proteins.

Grumetto et al. (2019) investigated the interactions between eight bisphenols (BPA, BPS, BPF, Bisphenol E (BPE), BPB, BPAF, Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (BADGE) and Bisphenol M (BPM)) and two plasma proteins, human serum albumin (HSA) and alpha1-acid glycoprotein (AGP) by using three approaches, biomimetic liquid chromatography, molecular docking simulations and *in silico* predictions. They showed that the interactions of bisphenols with human serum albumin (HSA) and AGP were found non-specific and lipophilicity driven. BPA analogues with higher lipophilicity (BPM and BPAF) exhibited a higher affinity for both plasma proteins. For BPB, both *in vitro* and *in silico* approaches demonstrated consistent results and the interaction of BPB with plasma proteins (HSA and AGP) is very similar to BPA, whereas BPF exhibited a lower binding to HSA and AGP compared to BPA.

In conclusion, the interactions of bisphenols with plasma proteins (HSA and AGP) were found to be non-specific and lipophilicity-driven. BPF exhibited a lower binding to HSA and AGP compared to BPA whereas BPS exhibited a higher binding to HSA compared to BPA.

2.1.2.3 Distribution of BPF in the materno-fetal unit

The fetal exposure to bisphenols results from a complex interplay between bidirectional placental clearances and fetal metabolism.

Gingrich et al. (2019) determined the time courses of total BPA, BPS and BPF (conjugated and non-conjugated) in the plasma of pregnant sheep following subcutaneous exposure to 0.5 mg/kg bw. Only total BPA, BPS and BPF were measured after incubation of samples with beta-

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 236

glucuronidase. The TK comparison between three bisphenols would have been relevant if the authors had evaluated both, unconjugated and conjugated bisphenols plasma concentrations, rather than only total BPs concentrations. But the computation of TK parameters is erroneous because the TK parameters were calculated using the plasma concentrations of total BPA, BPS or BPF. The maternal C_{max} for total BPS (643 ± 29.9 ng/ml) is an order of magnitude higher than for BPA and BPF (66.7 ± 1.7 ng/ml). The area under the curve of the total maternal BPS concentrations was significantly higher than those of BPA and BPF. Nine hours after bisphenol administration, maternal urine concentrations for BPA, BPS and BPF were 1300±210 ng/ml, 3870±888 ng/ml and 3.9±3.4 ng/ml respectively. These differences in urine excretion are difficult to interpret because the spot urine sampling at 9 h post-dosing was too late. The fetal /maternal ratio was 1.31, 0.03 and 0.42 for total BPA, BPS and BPF, respectively. In fetal compartment, the total BPS concentrations decreased much slower compared to those of BPA and BPF. Yet again, it is not possible to understand the mechanism determining BPS and BPF fetal exposure because only total plasma bisphenol's concentrations profiles were described.

2.1.2.4 Metabolism

Studies with subcellular hepatic fractions (S9 fraction and microsomes) from human liver (pooled samples from 10 donors) and from rat liver have shown that [3H]-BPF (4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl-methane labelled as described above) is oxidised to various hydroxylated but also to structurally related less polar metabolites. Additionally, BPF-glucuronide and –sulfate could be detected. Oxidation mainly led to (referred to the already existing hydroxyl group) meta- and ortho-hydroxylated metabolites and was catalysed by P450 monooxygenases, as was the formation of less polar BPF dimers. A comparison of the activity in rat and human liver microsomes (the latter from female and male donors each) revealed a somewhat higher K_m in human than in rat liver microsomes, but overall no species- or sex-specific differences in K_m and V_{max} (Cabaton et al., 2008).

BPF was glucuronidated and sulfated in isolated rat liver. The glucuronide, the sulfate and the “mixed conjugate” BPF-glucuronide-sulfate could be detected (Iwano et al., 2016).

BPF was mainly conjugated with sulfate in the human hepatoma cell line HepG2. Cryopreserved human hepatocytes, in contrast, synthesised the sulfate and the glucuronide, revealing interindividual differences in the conjugate pattern (Dumont et al., 2011). Studies with recombinant UDP-glucuronyl transferases (UGT) showed a high activity of UGT1A10, a predominantly intestinal enzyme, towards BPF, UGT2A1, an enzyme mainly expressed in the respiratory tract, had a high activity towards BPF and BPS (and also BPA) (Gramec Skledar et al., 2015).

Studies on the isolated perfused gravid uterus of rats on gestation day (GD) 18 indicated that especially the sulfate conjugate of BPS permeates the placenta barrier (Iwano et al., 2016). Studies on the activity of the UDP-glucuronyl transferase (UGT) in microsomes from liver of pregnant C57BL/6 mice on GD 18.5 and postnatally in male and female offspring (GD 18.5 to Postnatal Day (PND) 7) did not reveal sex-specific differences. However, the activity of the UGT towards BPF was lower in fetuses and offspring than in dams and increased postnatally (Yabusaki et al., 2015).

2.1.2.5 Distribution and excretion

Cabaton et al. (2006) studied the distribution and excretion of BPF (4,4'-isomer) in pregnant and non-pregnant Sprague Dawley female rats (aged 8 to 10 weeks old). After oral administration of

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 237

7 or 100 mg [3H]-BPF/kg bw (labelled in 3-position of one of the phenolic rings), the excretion of labelled compounds was followed for 96 h. The total radioactivity recovered over the 96 h, expressed as a percentage of the administered dose, was equal to 79.4 ± 11.7 %. Most of the excreted radioactivity was recovered in urine. About 50 % of the administered dose (range between 43 - 54 %) was excreted in urine and 15 – 20 % in the faeces. Following 96 h post exposure, BPF (strictly speaking: 3H) was detected in all organs studied but at less than 1 % of the administered dose, mostly in the liver with 0.5 %. 8 - 10 % of the dose was detected in the gastrointestinal tract and 6 - 8.4 % in the carcass. At least six different metabolites were detected in urine. The sulfo-conjugate represented the main metabolite excreted with 50 %. Animals with a bile duct cannula excreted 46 % of the distributed activity of a single dose of [3H]-BPF via bile within 6 h. The authors concluded that BPF or its metabolites undergo enterohepatic circulation. This could also explain the high amount of radioactivity which was excreted even after 96 h. Concerning the pregnant rats exposed on GD17, BPF was detected in uterus, amniotic fluid, and the foetus (ratios from 0.9 to 1.3 % of the applied dose) which means that BPF can cross the placental barrier (Cabaton et al., 2006).

2.2 Health effects of BPF

2.2.1 Acute Toxicity and Irritation

2.2.1.1 Data on humans

No case reports or studies are available on acute toxic effects or on irritation due to BPF in humans.

2.2.1.2 Animal data

According to the results of a rather old study with rats (LD50: 4950 mg/kg bw) the acute toxicity to rat is very low (U.S.EPA 2015, Smyth et al., 1962). A much more recent acute oral toxicity study conducted in accordance with the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Guideline 423 (Acute Oral toxicity - Acute Toxic Class Method) with Sprague-Dawley rats did not show lethality with 300 and 2,000 mg/kg bw of Bisphenol-F (Reaction mass of 2,2'-methylenediphenol and 4,4'- methylenediphenol and o-[(4-hydroxyphenyl)methyl]phenol) corresponding to CAS N 1333-16-0. The LD50 was greater than 2000 mg/kg bw (ECHA Registration Dossier, 2020a). No data are available regarding the acute toxicity of BPF via other routes of exposure.

Severe eye irritation with marked cornea damage has been observed in studies with animals (U.S.EPA 2015, Smyth et al. 1962). In an in vivo eye irritation study conducted according to OECD Guideline 405 with New Zealand White rabbits, Bisphenol-F (Reaction mass of 2,2'-methylenediphenol and 4,4'-methylenediphenol and o-[(4-hydroxyphenyl)methyl]phenol corresponding to CAS N 1333-16-0) showed signs of eye corrosion in rabbit eyes under the conditions of this study (ECHA Registration Dossier, 2020a).

In an in vivo skin irritation study with New Zealand White rabbits, Bisphenol-F (Reaction mass of 2,2'-methylenediphenol and 4,4'-methylenediphenol and o-[(4-hydroxyphenyl)methyl]phenol corresponding to CAS N 1333-16-0) did not show any evidence of skin irritation or corrosion under the conditions of this study (ECHA Registration Dossier, 2020a).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 238

2.2.2 Sensitisation

2.2.2.1 Data on humans

Nine of 16 individuals with a contact allergy against phenol-formaldehyde resins showed a positive reaction in a patch test against at least one of the three tested isomers (2,2'-, 2,4'- and 4,4'-BPF). All of these 9 individuals reacted positive against 2,4'-BPF, three against 2,4'- and 4,4'- and one of them against all of the three -isomers. No such reaction could be observed in the corresponding control group of 100 individuals. Cross reactions were observed in two of eight tested individuals against the structurally similar substances 4-hydroxy-diphenyl-methane, BPA (one individual) and diethylstilbestrol (Bruze and Zimerson, 1985).

Two other human studies reported information on exposure to BPA analogues and contact dermatitis (Hayakawa et al., 1985; Shmidt et al., 2010). In these studies, dermal patch testing with BPF (both the 2,2- and 4,4-isomers) caused some reactions in patients or workers.

2.2.2.2 Animal data

4,4'-BPF and 2,4'-BPF were not sensitising in a maximisation test with guinea pigs. For 2,2'-BPF a weakly sensitising potential was described in an overall evaluation from the data of two studies (Bruze, 1986). BPF (Reaction mass of 2,2'-methylenediphenol and 4,4'-methylenediphenol and o-[(4-hydroxyphenyl) methyl]phenol corresponding to CAS N 1333-16-0), was considered to be a sensitizer in a Local Lymph Node Assay on CBA/J mice (ECHA Registration Dossier, 2020a).

2.2.3 Repeated dose toxicity

2.2.3.1 Data on humans

A case-control study conducted with 212 adult women in Romania and Cyprus found no correlation between the excretion of BPF in urine and the level of thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) in serum or the diagnosis of thyroidal nodules (Andrianou et al., 2016).

A cross-sectional study looked into relationships between the excretion of BPF, BPA and BPS and obesity (BMI \geq 30) in US-American adults (age \geq 20 y, non-pregnant, no existing neoplasia). Overall, data from 1521 participants could be evaluated. It was observed that obese had higher median values of all three bisphenols in urine than non-obese. Adjusting for demographic, socioeconomic and lifestyle factors retained the relationship with BPA but not for BPS and BPF (OR 1.05, 95 % confidence interval 0.68-1.63) (Liu B. et al., 2017).

2.2.3.2 Animal data

Sprague-Dawley rats (10 males + 10 females/dose) were exposed in a subacute feeding study (28 days, following OECD draft guideline 407) by gavage to 0, 20, 100 or 500 mg BPF/kg bw/day (100 % 4,4-dihydroxydiphenyl methane) in olive oil (Higashihara et al., 2007; ECHA Registration Dossier, 2020a). At the end of exposure, the body weight of females was significantly lower compared to controls at all dose levels (-12 to -13 %). In males exposed to BPF, the body weight also showed a dose-dependent decrease compared to controls, however, the difference was smaller than in females at the two lower doses (-4 to -14 %), and the effect was significant only at the highest dose. In females, relative kidney and brain weight were increased from the middle dose on; in males, relative testis and thyroid weight were increased at the highest dose. Thyroid weight also showed a numerical increase in females at all doses, but the changes were not dose-dependent and not significant. The relative liver weight was increased in females and males at the highest concentration (the absolute organ weights were not reported).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 239

Histopathological effects could not be detected in any organ, except for dilated lymph nodes in two males at the highest dose. Starting with the lowest dose, females showed decreased serum levels of total cholesterol, albumin, and glucose. Haemoglobin concentration, haematocrit and cholin esterase activity also decreased with increasing dose of BPF, but the effects were not significant at the lowest dose. γ -glutamyl transferase (γ GT) and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) in serum were increased at the highest dose. Regarding thyroid hormone levels, both sexes showed a decrease of T3 and an increase in thyroxine (T4) in serum. The effect on T4 was significant in females already at the lowest concentration (+17 %). No dose-dependent effect on TSH could be observed in males; in females, a non-significant dose-dependent increase was noted. No effects on oestrus cycle or sperm parameters occurred. The authors of the study concluded that there is no clear evidence for a possible endocrine disruptive effect of BPF. A lowest observed adverse effect level (LOAEL) for systemic effects of 20 mg/kg bw/day is obtained in this study but no No Observed Adverse Effect Level (NOAEL) was derived.

In the dose-finding part of the described study, changes in body and organ weights, in haematological parameters and clinical chemistry were observed after 14 days of feeding 500 mg BPF/kg bw/day, but not at 250 mg/kg bw/day (Higashihara et al., 2007; ECHA Registration Dossier, 2020a). A study of the Japanese Hatano Research Institute is available in Japanese with a brief English summary: Reduced total cholesterol, increased liver and adrenal weight and diffuse hypertrophy of cortical zona fascicularis cells were noted following subacute oral exposure of rats. A dose of 60 mg/kg bw/day is reported as a NOAEL, but no details of the study are available (BLV 2015, JECDB 2004c and JECDB (without year)).

To our knowledge, no data are available from studies with subchronic or chronic exposure.

2.2.4 Genotoxicity

BPF was not mutagenic in bacteria in Ames tests in the absence or presence of exogenous metabolising system (S9) in all strains examined (*Salmonella typhimurium* TA98, TA100, TA1535, TA1537), in a test with *Escherichia coli* W2 uvrA pKM101 and in an umu-test with *Salmonella typhimurium* TA1537 (U.S.EPA 2015, JECDB 2004a, ECHA Registration Dossier, 2020a).

Also, no evidence was observed for mutagenic activity in mammalian cells (Na/K-ATPase and HGPRT locus in SHE cells) when BPA was tested without or with exogenous metabolising system or for clastogenic effects (chromosomal aberrations in SHE cells, micronuclei in Hep G2 cells) (U.S.EPA 2015). However, an increase in structural chromosomal aberrations at the highest test concentrations (0.19 mg/L) without or with exogenous metabolic activation was mentioned in a study (following OECD guideline 473) with CHL/IU cells from Chinese hamsters after short-term exposure. The study is only available in Japanese with English tables and figures. The number of polyploid cells was increased following short-term exposure starting at the mid concentration (0.12 mg/L) (JECDB (without year) and 2004b).

A comet assay with Hep G2 cells provided no evidence of DNA strand breaks up to a concentration of 10 μ mol BPF/L (U.S.EPA 2015, Tsutsui et al., 2000); in a further test single- and double-strand breaks were described in Hep G2 cells at sub-cytotoxic concentrations (78.7 μ mol/L) (U.S.EPA 2015, Cabaton et al., 2009). Furthermore, alterations of the histone H2AX were observed in Hep G2 cells in a histone phosphorylation assay (Audebert et al., 2011); such an alteration is also seen as evidence for DNA strand breaks (Sharma, Singh, and Almasan 2012). Those results were supported by those of Hercog et al. (2019) in Hep G2 cells wherein

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 240

BPF and BPAF exerted stronger genotoxic potential than BPA. Lastly, a comet assay with human peripheral blood cells suggested that BPF and BPB are genotoxic (Ikhlas et al., 2019). No clastogenic activity of BPF was noted in a micronucleus test with mice; the study is only available in Japanese with English tables and figures (JECDB 2012). Further *in vivo* data for BPF are not available.

2.2.5 Carcinogenicity

No data are available regarding the carcinogenicity of BPF in humans or animals. An *in vitro* cell transformation assay with SHE cells was negative (Tsutsui et al., 2000).

2.2.6 Toxicity to reproduction

2.2.6.1 Data on humans

Philips, Jaddoe, et al. (2018) evaluated the impact of BPA analogues on fecundability among 877 of the 8879 participants from the population-based Generation R pregnancy cohort (EU cohort). They reported no association of urinary concentrations of bisphenol analogues including 4,4-BPF with fecundability, but that total bisphenols (including 4,4-BPF, BPS, BPB, BPP, BPAF, BPAP, or BPZ) could be associated with a longer time to pregnancy in women with inadequate or without folic acid supplement use before pregnancy (Philips, Jaddoe, et al., 2018). However, the association is not statistically significant.

2.2.6.2 Animal data

No standard reproduction or fertility studies according to or following OECD guidelines or comparable guidelines are available. No effects on sperm parameters and oestrus cycle were observed in a 28-day study with oral administration of BPF to rats (see chapter 2.2.3.2) (Higashihara et al. 2007).

Pregnant C57BL/6 mice were gavaged on GD 11.5-18.5 with 0 or 10 mg BPF/kg bw/day. Their offspring were tested for neurobehavioral alterations in week 10 after birth. It was observed that offspring of BPF-treated dams showed deviations in behavioral patterns which were described as increased anxiety and increased depressive reactions. Motor activities were unchanged (Ohtani et al., 2017, Ohtani et al., 2016).

Pregnant Wistar rats were exposed to 10 µg BPF/kg bw/day from GD 12 to parturition and, subsequently, their female offspring with the same dose until PND 21 (no further details noted). A decreased level of 5α-R3 mRNA, an altered gene expression, and an induction of cytochrome 2D4 in the prefrontal cortex of female offspring was described on PND 21 (Castro et al., 2015).

Male reproductive studies- Analysis

Although Klimisch criteria or the ToxRTTool were not applied for the evaluation of the quality of the studies, the experimental design of the available studies was scrutinised taking into account the size of the experimental group, the experimental conditions of breeding and exposure, as well as the adequacy of the hormonal, histological and statistical analysis. Furthermore, as male reproductive function can be evaluated using two approaches (testicular analysis and sperms analysis) and as each of them can be studied using various parameters, the quality of one study largely depends on the number of measured parameters and on the methods used for their measurements. This expert-based analysis lead to a quotation as limited, acceptable, good, very good (see Table IV.6).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 241

Many recent studies on rodents investigated the effect of BPF and BPS on testicular functions using in vitro and in vivo methods. They originated from the 3 groups: Ullah et al, Shi et al and Horan et al. Importantly, all the studies except Ullah et al. 2019a (study # 4 in table IV.6) compared BPF and BPS with BPA. Some studies also used other bisphenols (AF, B or E); the results obtained with these BPA analogs are not reported below.

The following section is focused on both BPF in vivo effects and the comparison with BPA.

In the study by Ullah et al. (2019c), reference # 1 in table IV.6, BPA, BPB, BPF, and BPS were administered in drinking water at concentrations of 5, 25, and 50 µg/L from GD 1 to PND 21 to pregnant Sprague-Dawley rats. Since an adult rat drinks about 6 ml/100 g body weight/day it can be estimated that the daily bisphenols intake was about 0.3, 1.5 and 3 µg/kg bw/day.

Observations were performed in male F1 using 8 males per group on PND 16 and PND 80.

Cages were made of glass and feed was soy and alfalfa free.

On PND 16, not any prenatal exposure affects various androgen-dependent developments (anogenital distance, nipple involution and weights of prostate, epididymis, seminal vesicle, bulbourethral gland and bulbocavernosus muscles).

On PND 80, anti-oxidative activities were decreased with 50 µg/l with BPA and BPF and with 25 µg and 50 µg/l BPB and BPS. Oxidative activities were increased with the four bisphenols with 50 µg/L. A decrease in plasma testosterone, LH, FSH, and an increase in plasma oestradiol were observed with 50 µg/l. However, the weights of seminal vesicle and prostate were not diminished.

Dealing with spermatogenesis, histological morphometric data of the testis are puzzling because seminiferous epithelium height is increased whereas it should be decreased and because both interstitial and seminiferous spaces decreased. Thus, this morphometric analysis cannot be used for the BPF toxicity assessment. However, clear alterations of spermatogenesis were evidenced by changes in multiple end points. For the 4 bisphenols decreases were observed in daily sperm production with 50 µg/l, in sperm number within caput/corpus but not within cauda epididymis with 25 µg/l and 50 µg/l, in different cell types within the seminiferous tubule with 50 µg/l. Sperm motility was decreased with 50 µg/l (BPA, BPB) or 25 and 50 µg/l (BPF, BPS).

In conclusion, although the confidence placed in histological spermatogenesis analysis must be moderate, this paper clearly shows that exposure to BPA, BPF and BPS during fetal life provokes alterations in the quality and the number of sperms at adulthood.

In the study by Horan et al. (2018), reference # 2 in table IV.6, 129S1/SvimJ mice were orally exposed to 20 µg/kg bw/day BPF, BPA, BPS, BPAF or BPA versus a control group (corn oil), from GD 11 (the presence of vaginal plug = 1) to birth. BPF(n=5/group) was given orally, by placing a pipette tip containing the selected dose in tocopherol-stripped corn oil into the mouth once a day. Male pups, 2–3 from each litter, were euthanised on PND 12 or PND 60.

On PND 42, BPS and all others bisphenols tested significantly increased the number of MLH1 foci in meiotic germ cells evidencing an alteration of meiosis process. Furthermore, this defect was transmitted to F1 and F2 and was erased in F3 and F4.

In conclusion, this study, performed in a laboratory with recognised expertise in this field, is focused on one end-point and used only one dose. But it clearly shows an alteration of meiosis which is transmitted to the descendants.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 242

In the study by Ullah et al. (2018b), reference # 3 in table IV.6, Sprague-Dawley male rats were housed in cages made of steel and given free soy and alfalfa food and water in polysulfone bottles. Animals on PND 23 received drinking water containing 0, 5, 25, 50 µg/l BPF or BPS for 48 weeks (7 animals per group). BPA was used as positive control. The effects of another bisphenol (BPB) were also studied and will not be reported here. As a rat drinks around 6 mL/day/100 g body weight, they received around 0, 0.3, 1.5 and 3 µg/kg bw/day bisphenols. However, it is known that the daily water intake referred to body weight changes as a function of the age. Thus, the above estimated doses must be doubled when considering young stages and reduced by half for old adults. Thus, animals received from 0.6 to 0.15, from 3 to 0.75 and from 6 to 1.5 µg/kg bw/day from PND 23 to Postnatal Week (PNW) 51 for the 3 treated groups respectively.

At the end of the treatment, the relative weights of the testis, the epididymis, the seminal vesicle were decreased with the highest dose of BPS, BPF and BPA (50 µg/l) respectively. The reduction in prostate weight did not reach statistical significance.

The testicular concentrations of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and peroxidized lipids (LPO) were increased for 50 µg/l BPS, BPF and BPA respectively. The activities of antioxidant enzymes were decreased: superoxide dismutase (SOD) for 50 µg/l BPS, BPF and BPA, peroxidase (POD) for 25 and 50 µg/L BPS, BPF and BPA, catalase (CAT) for 25 and 50 µg/l BPA and 50 µg/L BPS.

After treatment with BPS, BPF or BPA, there were dose-related trends towards decreases in testosterone, LH and FSH concentrations and an increase in estradiol concentration in plasma. As compared with controls, all these changes were statistically significant with 50 µg/l BPS, BPF and BPA respectively.

Sperm production was examined. In the cauda epididymis, the motile sperm percentage was significantly reduced. BPS and BPF appear more potent than BPA and the concentration of 25 µg/l was sufficient to reach statistical significance with BPS and BPF, whereas 50 µg/l were necessary with BPA. The viable sperm percentage was unaffected with BPS, BPF and BPA. Sperm count in the testis showed that the daily sperm production was dose dependently reduced (statistical significance for 50 µg/l BPA, BPF and BPS, with a reduction by 9 - 10 %). In the same way, the sperm number was also dose-dependently decreased in the caput epididymis (significance from 25 µg/l BPF, BPS and BPA) and in the cauda epididymis (significance for 50 µg/l BPF, BPS and BPA).

Testicular histological analyses were performed. The height of seminal epithelium was dose-dependently decreased (statistical significance for 50 µg/l BPS, BPF and BPA, with a reduction by 13 - 15 %) without changes in the diameter and the relative area of seminiferous tubules. The numbers of spermatogonia, spermatocytes and spermatids were statistically reduced after chronic exposure to 50 µg/l BPS, BPF and BPA respectively in the drinking water.

Histological examination of the caput and cauda regions of epididymis did not exhibit changes in the tubular diameter and the epithelial height.

In conclusion, this good quality study, clearly evidences that a chronic exposure to low doses of BPF alters the reproductive function in the male adult rat. Both endocrine and exocrine testicular functions were disrupted. BPA exerts similar or lower effects. A direct effect on the testis is suggested by the observed increase in oxidative stress but this does not exclude that BPF and BPA also acted on the gonadotropic hypothalamo-pituitary system.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 243

In the study by Ullah et al. (2019a), reference # 4 in table IV.6, Sprague-Dawley male rats on PND 70 - 80 were orally (no further indication given on the mode of administration) given 0, 1, 5, 25, and 50 mg/kg bw/day BPF for 28 days (7 animals per group). Observation was performed on the 29th day. There were reduced anti-oxidative activities from 5 mg/kg bw/day.

Testicular oxidative activities (eg. ROS and lipid peroxidation) were increased with 50 mg/kg bw/day and anti-oxidative (eg. CAT, SOD, and peroxydase) were decreased from 5 mg/kg bw/day BPF. A diminution in the epithelial height of seminiferous tubules was observed with 50 mg/kg bw/day without changes in the other 3 morphometric testicular parameters studied. Lastly, diminutions of plasma testosterone, LH and FSH were observed from 25 mg/kg bw/day (BPF).

In conclusion, this study could strengthen the other studies. However, its quality is too limited to have sufficient confidence in these data (imprecisions in the experimental methods, inaccuracy in one figure, number of spermatic parameters analysed too much limited).

The study by Ullah et al. (2018a) reference # 5 in table IV.6 reports the effects of BPA and its analogs (BPB, BPS and BPF) on testicular functions using in vitro and in vivo approaches. Sprague-Dawley adult male rats were housed in steel cages. Endocrine disrupting properties of the diet were not characterised in this study.

In the in vitro experiment, the testes were cut into five equal parts that were cut into slices and deposited in tubes containing the culture medium added with 0, 1, 10 or 100 ng/ml of bisphenols. After 2 hours of incubation, there was a trend of increased concentrations in reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the tissue exposed to bisphenols which was statistically significant at 10 ng/ml BPF and 100 ng/ml BPS. Intratesticular testosterone concentration was unaffected by the exposure to bisphenols. As an important limitation of this study it must be noted that the conditions of culture do not guarantee the survival of the testicular cells.

For the in vivo approach, Sprague-Dawley adult male rats aged between PND 70 to 80 were exposed orally to 0, 5, 25 and 50 mg/kg bw/day bisphenols (7 animals per group) for 28 days. With all bisphenols, after treatments with 50 mg/kg bw/day, the testicular concentrations in ROS and peroxidized lipids (LPO) were increased and the activity of catalase (CAT), one antioxidant enzyme, was decreased from 5 mg/kg bw/day (BPA, BPS) or 25 mg/kg bw/day (BPF). The activity of peroxidase was decreased from 5 mg/kg bw/day (BPF). Plasma and intratesticular testosterone concentrations were significantly reduced from the lowest tested dose level (5 mg/kg bw/day) with all tested bisphenols. However, this effect was not dose dependent. Lastly, histology of the testis showed that the height of the epithelium of the seminiferous tubules was significantly decreased with all bisphenols at 50 mg/kg bw/day, thus indicating that spermatogenesis was impaired. Only two other spermatogenic parameters were measured (area and diameter of seminiferous tubules) and they were not affected by bisphenol treatments. Qualitative observations showed reductions in the number of elongated spermatids/sperms in the lumen of the seminiferous tubules and of the epididymis. However, this observation was not quantified, therefore, it is difficult to assess the relevance of this finding.

In conclusion, this study could strengthen the other studies. Here also, BPS and BPF exerted similar effects as BPA. However, the quality of this study is limited (number of spermatic parameters analysed too much limited) and results must be considered with caution.

In the study by Ullah et al. (2019b) reference # 6 in table IV.6 Sprague-Dawley rats on PND 70-80, bred in steel cages with soy and alfalfa-free feed and tap water in polysulfone bottles, were

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 244

given 5, 25, and 50 mg/kg bw/day BPA, BPB, BPF or BPS by gavage for 28 days (7 animals per group). Observations were performed on the 29th day.

The number of studied endpoints is limited. No change in the percentage of motile sperms was observed. Using the comet assay, an increase in DNA damage was observed with the four bisphenols at 50 mg/kg bw/day but not at lower doses. It is written that daily sperm production was decreased with the four bisphenols at 50 mg/kg bw/day and not at lower doses, but, surprisingly for such an important endpoint, no data are given.

In conclusion, this paper contains too many limitations to be taken into consideration.

The following table summarises experimental evidence available on male reproduction function. For experimental data, studies are grouped by windows of exposure and then tested species (mouse / rat / other species).

Table IV.6: Experimental data available on effects of BPF on male reproduction function and comparison with BPA

Number and reference	Species Strain Model	Routes	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion			Comments / quality of the study	
					Spermatogenesis	Endocrinology	Oxidative stress	Testicular genes expression		
- 1 - Ullah et al., 2019c Human exp Toxicol <u>38</u> , 1344-1365	Rat Sprague-Dawley	Drinking water	BPA, BPS, BPF, BPB, 0, 5, 25, 50 µg/l in the drinking water <i>i.e.</i> around 0.3, 1.5, 3 µg/kg bw/day from GD 1 to GD 21 Observation on PND 16 & PND 80	8	Multiple alterations on PND 80 with the 4 BPs: - ↓ in daily sperm production at 50 µg/l, - ↓ in sperm number in caput/corpus but not in cauda epididymis from 25 µg/l, - changes in seminiferous morphometry from 50 µg/l (3 parameters) or 25 µg/l for area % of seminiferous tubules (but this data is not solid), - ↓ in different cell types in the seminiferous tubules at 50 µg/l,	No antiandrogenic effect on PND16. With the 4 BPs, on PND 80, ↓ in plasma testosterone, LH, FSH, and ↑ in plasma oestradiol with 50 µg/L.	On PND 80: - ↓ in anti-oxidative activities from 50 µg/L with BPA and BPF and from 25 µg/L with BPB and BPS. - ↑ in oxidative activities at 50 µg/L with the 4 BPs		Numerous data with variable confidence	Acceptable quality except for testicular histology.

Number and reference	Species Strain Model	Routes	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion			Comments / quality of the study	
					Spermato-genesis	Endocri-nology	Oxidative stress	Testicular genes expression		
					- ↓ of the motility of the sperms at 50 µg/l (BPA, BPB) or from 25 µg/l (BPF, BPS).					
- 2 - Horan et al., 2018 Current Biology 28: 2948-2954	Mouse C57Bl6	oral	BPA, BPS, BPF 0, 20 µg/kg bw/day PND 1 to PND 8 Observation on PND 42	9 - 14	Alteration of meiosis: ↓ in recombination rate measured by MLH1 foci number, with 20 µg/kg bw/day BPA, BPS and BPF				Effect with 20 µg/kg bw/ day	Good quality
- 3 - Ullah et al., 2018b Food Chem Toxicol 121, 24-36	Rat Sprague- Dawley	Drinking water	BPA, BPS, BPF, BPB, 0, 5, 25, 50 µg/l in the drinking water from PND 22 for 48 weeks. Average of the estimated absorbed doses: around 0, 0.3, 1.5,3 µg/kg	7	<u>Each of the 4 BPs:</u> - ↓ of testis and epididymis relative weights at 50 µg/l, - ↓ in daily sperm production at 50 µg/l, - alterations of seminiferous morphometry at 50 µg/l: diminution of epithelial height,	Each of the 4 BPs: - ↓ in the seminal vesicle weight at 50 µg/l, - ↓ in plasma testosterone, LH, FSH at 50 µg/l,	Each of the 4 BPs: - ↓ in anti- oxidative activities from 25 µg/l. - ↑ in oxidative activities from 25 µg/l		It is known that the daily water intake referred to body weight changes as a function of the age -> the above estimated doses must be doubled	Good quality Valuable data except the uncertainty about the daily consumption of drinking water.

Number and reference	Species Strain Model	Routes	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion			Comments / quality of the study	
					Spermatogenesis	Endocrinology	Oxidative stress	Testicular genes expression		
			bw/day		<p>reduction in the number of spermatogonia, spermatocytes and spermatids,</p> <p>- ↓ in cauda epididymis sperm number at 50 µg/l,</p> <p>- ↓ in caput epididymis sperm number from 25 µg/l.</p> <p><u>With BPS and BPF.</u></p> <p>- ↓ in sperm motility in cauda epididymis from 25 µg/l.</p> <p><u>With BPA and BPB.</u></p> <p>- ↓ in sperm motility in cauda epididymis at 50 µg/l.</p>	- ↑ in plasma oestradiol at 50 µg/l,			<p>when considering PND23 stages and reduced by half for old adults.</p> <p>Thus, it can be estimated that:</p> <p>- NOAEL is between 0.15 and 0.6 µg/kg bw/day.</p> <p>- LOAEL is between 0.75 and 3 µg/kg bw/day</p>	

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 248

Number and reference	Species Strain Model	Routes	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion			Comments / quality of the study	
					Spermatogenesis	Endocrinology	Oxidative stress	Testicular genes expression		
- 4 - Ullah et al., 2019a Env Health Prev Medicine <u>24</u> , 41	Rat Sprague-Dawley	oral	BPF 0, 1, 5, 25, 50, (100) mg/kg bw/day PND 80-90 for 28 days. Observation on the 29 th day.	7	↓ in epithelial height of seminiferous tubules from 50 mg/kg bw/day without changes in the other 3 morphometric testicular parameters studied.	↓ of plasma testosterone, LH and FSH from 25 mg/kg bw/day.	↓ of anti-oxidative activities from 5 mg/kg/day. ↑ in oxidative activities from 50 mg/kg bw/day		Too few sperm parameters analysed. Fig 3 does not fit with the text.	Limited quality
- 5 - Ullah et al., 2018a Chemosphere <u>209</u> , 508-16	Rat Sprague-Dawley	oral	BPA, BPS, BPF, BPB, 0, 5, 25, 50 mg/kg bw/day PND 70/80 for 28 days. Observation on the 29 th day.	7	↓ in epithelial height of seminiferous tubules at 50 mg/kg bw/day without changes in the other two morphometric testicular parameters studied.	↓ in plasma and/or intratesticular testosterone with 5 mg/kg bw/day with each of the 4 BPs.	↓ in anti-oxidative activities at 50 mg/kg bw/day (BPA) or from 5 mg/kg bw/day (BPS, BPF, BPB) ↑ in oxidative activities at 50 mg/kg bw/day with each of the 4 BPs.		Too few sperm parameters analysed.	Limited quality

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 249

Number and reference	Species Strain Model	Routes	Dose Exposure period	Group size	Outcomes reported	Conclusion			Comments / quality of the study		
					Spermato-genesis	Endocri-nology	Oxidative stress	Testicular genes expression			
- 6 - Ullah et al 2019b Toxicol Industrial Health <u>209</u> ,1- 10	Rat Sprague- Dawley	oral	BPA, BPS, BPF, BPB, 0, 5, 25, 50 mg/kg bw/day PND 70/80 for 28 days. Observation on the 29 th day.	7	↓ in daily sperm production				DNA damage in sperms at 50 mg/kg bw/ day with the 4 BPs	Inconclusive	Limited quality: values of the most important data (daily sperm production) are not presented.

F: female; M: male; BW: body weight; GD: gestation day; PND: postnatal day; ND: no data.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 250

Conclusion on the effects of BPF on male reproductive function

The number of studies on BPF toxicity is much smaller than for BPS. Two papers with good quality from Ullah et al. (# 3 in table IV.6) and Horan et al. (# 2 in table IV.6) and one paper with medium quality (# 1 in table IV.6) from Ullah et al. studied the effects of BPF on male reproductive function. Studies # 1 and # 3 used the rat Sprague-Dawley as model whereas study # 2 used C57Bl6 mice.

As detailed above (see also table IV.6) in these three studies BPF had exactly the same effects as BPS on male reproductive function. However, none of these three studies allows the reliable determination of NOAEL and LOAEL. In studies # 1 and 3, BPF is given in the drinking water with the uncertainty described above to measure the exact BPF daily intake. In study # 2, only one dose of BPF was used.

In conclusion, no NOAEL and LOAEL can be directly determined from the studies presently available. However, because of the similarity in the effects observed with BPF and BPS in three studies, it is considered highly probable that the NOAEL and LOAEL of BPF are the same as those of BPS considering male reproductive function.

2.2.7 Studies on endocrine effects

In a review of studies on health effects including endocrine effects of BPF (and other bisphenols) a total of 15 human studies, 42 in vivo and 104 in vitro studies are cited (more than one activity were tested in some studies); see Pelch et al. (2019).

2.2.7.1 Data on humans

Metabolism and obesity

An association with obesity was investigated for BPS and 4,4-BPF in five US studies (Jacobson et al., 2019; Kataria et al., 2017; Liu B. et al., 2017 and 2019; Zhang Y. et al., 2019) and in a European study (Charisiadis et al., 2018). The results from these studies are conflicting. Interestingly, only urinary BPS concentrations were higher in obese teens in NHANES 2015-2016 (Jacobson et al., 2019) while only urinary 4,4-BPF concentrations were elevated in obese teens in NHANES 2013-2014 (Liu B. et al., 2019). Urinary BPS and 4,4-BPF concentrations were also elevated in obese adults but the results were not significant after adjustments for lifestyle and socioeconomic factors (Liu B. et al., 2017). In a very small US cross sectional pilot study of 10 - 13-year-old children, BPS and 4,4-BPF were not associated with body weight (Kataria et al., 2017). In contrast, Charisiadis reported that increased concentrations of 4,4-BPF in brain matter were associated with a decreased risk of obesity in a small autopsy cohort (Charisiadis et al., 2018).

Similarly, three Chinese studies investigated the association of BPF with diabetes, fasting blood glucose, or insulin resistance (Duan et al., 2018; Song et al., 2019; Zhang W. et al., 2019) and also one US study (Kataria et al., 2017). In a case-control study, urinary BPF concentrations were not reportedly associated with a significant increased risk of type 2 diabetes (Duan et al., 2018). Song et al. (2019) reported that serum BPF was not associated with hyperglycemia in a nested population of elderly patients living near e-waste recycling in China. Kataria et al. (2017) did not find associations between urinary 4,4-BPF concentrations and insulin resistance in a small cross-sectional pilot study of 10 - 13-year-old children. In a cohort of pregnant women from Wuhan (Zhang W. et al., 2019), urinary BPS and 4,4-BPF concentrations were not associated with incident gestational diabetes.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 251

Also investigated was the association of BPF with urinary markers of oxidative stress in one US study (Kataria et al., 2017) and in two Chinese studies (Zhang T. et al., 2016; Wang Y.X. et al., 2019). Urinary BPF concentrations were not associated with markers of oxidative stress in a Chinese population residing near the e-waste recycling facility (Zhang T. et al., 2016), nor in the US cross-sectional pilot study of 10 - 13-year-old children (Kataria et al., 2017), whereas elevated urinary BPA and BPF concentrations were associated with significantly higher levels of oxidative stress markers in a Chinese volunteer study (Wang Y.X. et al., 2019).

Thyroid

In a European case control study of adult non-pregnant women from Romania and Cyprus, no association was found for urinary concentrations of 4,4-BPF and TSH or thyroid nodule disease (Andrianou et al., 2016).

In a population-based prospective study, higher 4,4-BPF concentrations were positively associated with higher free T3 levels at the beginning of pregnancy (< 14 weeks of gestation), while there was no association between BPS and absolute TSH, free T4 nor free T3 concentrations (Derakhshan et al., 2019).

Other health outcomes

Kolatorova et al. (2018) evaluated the simultaneous detection of 4,4-BPF, BPS and other bisphenols and endogenous steroids in maternal (37th week of pregnancy) and cord plasma from European (Czech nationality and middle-European origin) pregnant patients. In maternal plasma, BPA was detected in 85.2 % of samples but BPS and 4,4-BPF were detected in one sample only. In cord plasma, BPA was present in most samples (75.1 % of samples) and on the other hand, BPF was above the lower limit of quantification in only one sample, and BPS was not detected at all.

One study aimed to investigate the association of serum concentrations of 4,4-BPF, BPAF, or BPS on bone density and calcium-phosphate metabolism in post-menopausal women, but the plasmatic concentrations of all BPA analogues were below the limit of quantification (LOQ) (Vitku et al., 2018). In the US pilot study of 10 - 13-year-old children, Kataria et al. (2017) did not find an association between urinary concentrations of 4,4-BPF or BPS on blood pressure or vascular dysfunction.

2.2.7.2 Animal and in vitro data

In a review of studies on hormonal effects of BPF (and other bisphenols) a total of five in vivo and 19 in vitro studies are cited (more than one activity was tested in some studies). BPF demonstrated estrogenic, androgenic or thyroidogenic activities in four of five in vivo studies. Twelve of the in vitro studies indicated estrogenic activity of BPF; one study revealed no such activity, and one provided evidence of an anti-estrogenic activity. Six assays demonstrated anti-androgenic activity and some further other specific or non-specific effects on cellular metabolism; studies in which both BPF and BPA were tested showed a relative potency of BPF compared to BPA of 1.07 ± 1.20 (mean \pm SD, range 0.10-4.83). Further comparisons indicated that BPF and BPA have potencies of the same order of magnitude with respect to androgenic, anti-androgenic, and anti-estrogenic activity (Rochester and Bolden 2015).

In its report about several bisphenols as alternatives to BPA the US EPA also concluded that BPF shows both estrogenic and anti-androgenic activity and that the estrogenic potency of BPF seems to be similar or slightly lower than that of BPA (U.S.EPA 2015).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 252

According to a current review by the National Toxicology Program (NTP), BPF showed a similar binding to the ER (estrogen receptors) as BPA and revealed antagonistic activity. Furthermore, it was tested whether BPF is able to induce the binding of ER to ERE (estrogen response element). It was demonstrated that BPF showed a marked selectivity to the ER β compared to ER α and that BPF is not able to induce the binding of ER to ERE over a concentration range of 0.001-10 μ M (NTP 2017).

In a study with immature Wistar rats, 4 d oral exposure to 100 mg BPF/kg bw/day but not to 50 mg/kg bw/day led to an increase in uterus weight and an increased formation of superficial cells in vaginal smear. Other bisphenols were not studied (Stroheker et al., 2003). Similarly, 3 d of subcutaneous exposure to 100 mg BPF/kg bw/day of immature rats had an uterotrophic effect; binding to the ER in vitro was also demonstrated in this study (Yamasaki et al., 2004). In another study from the same research group, BPF had an uterotrophic effect following subcutaneous injection of 200 mg BPF/kg bw/day from PND 20 to 22, but not of 2 or 20 mg/kg bw/day (Yamasaki et al., 2002).

Like BPA, BPF showed endocrine activity in the E-screen test with MCF7 breast cancer cells in vitro. In that study, the binding affinity of BPF to the ER was 3fold higher than that of BPA but had only 1/10 of the relative proliferative potency and the protein-synthesis inducing potency of BPA (Perez et al., 1998).

In a more recent in vitro H295R steroidogenesis assay BPF induced the production of estradiol similarly to BPA, but only BPA (and BPS) but not BPF inhibited the formation of free testosterone (Goldinger et al., 2015). In a similar assay BPF but not BPA stimulated the synthesis of progestogens and (as did BPA) the synthesis of estrogens. Furthermore, in this study BPF increased the formation of cortisol (as did BPA) and of corticosterone (BPA: no effect). BPF also stimulated the activity of the ER but was less active than BPA. The activity of the AR (androgen receptor) was diminished (Rosenmai et al., 2014).

BPF inhibited basal testosterone secretion in vitro in explants of foetal murine testes tissue and in cultures of foetal human testes tissue. The minimum effective concentration was 1,000 nmol/l for BPF and BPA and 100 nmol/L for BPS. 10 nmol/L BPF or BPA inhibited the expression of insl 33 (a factor regulating the descent of the testes from the abdomen during foetal development) in mice (Eladak et al. 2015).

Endocrine effects (estrogen-like activity, binding to ER) were also observed in vitro and in vivo in studies with zebrafish or cell cultures from this species (Le Fol et al., 2017, Yang et al., 2017). BPF, as BPA, induced the expression of estrogen-sensitive markers (Cyp19a1b) in the developing brain of embryonic zebrafish (Cano-Nicolau et al., 2016). However, this gene is not expressed in mammalian brain (Fujiwara et al., 2018). The expression of neural marker proteins in differentiating cells of an immortalised neural cell line from human foetal brain tissue (ReNcell VM) was affected by BPA (and estradiol) in vitro, while BPF caused no such effects in this study (Fujiwara et al., 2018).

According to Zhang Y.F. et al. (2018), BPF bound to the thyroid hormone receptors (TR α and TR β) in a fluorescence binding assay in vitro as did BPA, but the potency of BPF was about one order of magnitude lower than that of BPA. Similar to BPA, BPF and BPS at concentrations of 10 nmol/L and 10 μ mol/L affected the expression of several genes in primary cultures of human adipocytes obtained from subcutaneous fat tissue of three female white donors not suffering

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 253

from diabetes. According to the authors, this was regarded as a possible endocrine disruptive effect (Verbanck et al., 2017).

Mammary gland

Currently, there are no published studies investigating *in vivo* effects of BPF on the development of the mammary gland.

Anxiety-related behavior

Two studies analysed the effects of BPF exposure in mice (Ohtani et al., 2017) and rats (Castro et al., 2015).

Ohtani et al. (2017) exposed C57BL/6 mice (oral gavage) from GD 11.5 to GD 18.5 to BPF or BPA at 10 mg/kg bw/day. Males and females of the F1 generation were analysed on PNW 10 for their activity (open-field test), anxiety-related behavior (elevated plus maze test) and depressive-like behavior (forced swim test). In the open-field, the total distance travelled was not affected by the treatment in males and females, but the time spent in the central area was decreased in females exposed to BPF or BPA. In the elevated plus maze test, a decreased time spent in the open arms was observed for both treatments in males and females. In the forced swim test, there was an increased time in immobility for females, but not for males, exposed to BPF; no effects were induced by BPA.

Castro et al. (2015) analysed the effects of exposure to BPF, BPS or BPA (subcutaneous, 10 µg/kg bw/day) in female rats (GD12 to parturition, then pups exposed from PND 1 to PND 21) on the cortical expression of 5-α reductase and serotonin/dopamine systems. The 5-α reductase metabolises testosterone into 5-α dihydrotestosterone, but it is also involved in the biosynthesis of neurosteroids such as allopregnanolone, which plays a key role in neural functions. The authors described reduced mRNA levels of 5-α reductase 3 on PND 21 in females exposed to BPS or BPF, while BPA exposure reduced the mRNA and protein levels of 5-α reductase 2 and 3. Quantitative PCR array for rat dopamine and serotonin pathway showed a total of 25 genes significantly regulated by BPA, 56 genes by BPF, and 24 genes by BPS. A common change induced by the three molecules was the upregulation of Cyp2d4, which is involved in the hydroxylation of allopregnanolone and progesterone to corticosteroids (3 α-5 α-tetrahydrodeoxycorticosterone and 11-deoxycorticosterone). As this study was performed only in females, it remains to be investigated whether these modifications in the expression of 5-α reductase and dopamine/serotonin systems occur also in males.

No NOAEL or LOAEL can be determined from these studies, where only one dose of BPF was used.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 254

2.3 Existing evaluations and derivations of tolerable doses

Existing basics for the evaluation of BPF are summarised in table IV.7.

Table IV.7: Basis for the evaluation of BPF regarding the protection of the general population against chronic continuous exposure (for explanation, see text)

Species, endpoint/target organ	Extrapolation factor								Guide value (µg kg bw/day)	Organisation, year (Ref.)
	LOAEL (mg/kg bw/day)	NOAEL (mg/kg bw/day)	LOAEL to NOAEL	Time	Inter species	Intra species	Data basis	Total factor		
Rat, bw, haematology, serum parameters	20	-	3	6	10	10		1800	11	(Zoller et al., 2016, BLV 2015)
Adoption of t-TDI for BPA		HED: 0.609*	-	1	2.5	10	6	150	4	(BfR 2015b)

*: HED: human equivalent dose, calculated from the BMDL₁₀ for systemic effects in a multi-generation study with mice (EFSA 2015)

In view of the limited data base on the toxicity of BPF, the Swiss Federal Food Safety and Veterinary Office (BLV) has considered it inappropriate to derive a daily tolerable intake (BLV 2015, Zoller et al., 2016). Instead, a MoE approach (MoE: Margin of Exposure) has been applied. The LOAEL of 20 mg/kg bw/day from the subacute feeding study with rats (Higashihara et al., 2007) served as the basis. A standard factor of 3 for the extrapolation of a NOAEL from a LOAEL and standard factors for time extrapolation (6), inter- and intraspecies extrapolation (10 each) were taken into account. Consequently, according to the BLV (2015), the MoE between LOAEL and exposure level should at least amount to 1800. The BLV notes that this formally corresponds to a tolerable daily intake (TDI) of 11 µg/kg bw/day. Dietrich and Hengstler (2016) have adopted this approach.

Zoller et al. (2016) have pointed to the issue that the described derivation only presents a very basic approach and that the disproportionately more comprehensive database about the toxicity of BPA should be taken into account. The same view has been presented by the BfR (2015b). The BfR further states that toxicokinetic (TK) and mechanistic studies indicate a risk potential of BPF similar to that of BPA. Thus, for the toxicological evaluation of BPF the BfR has alternatively used the temporary tolerable daily intake t-TDI for BPA of 4 µg/kg bw/day which has been derived by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) *Panel on Food Contact Materials, Enzymes, Flavourings and Processing Aids (CEF)* (EFSA 2015).

The t-TDI for BPA derived by the EFSA CEF Panel is based on renal effects which have been observed in a multi-generation study with mice. A benchmark calculation led to a BMDL₁₀ of 8960 µg/kg bw/day for an increase in kidney weight in mice observed in a 2-generation study (Tyl et al. 2008). By means of Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modelling a human equivalent oral dose (HED) of 609 µg/kg bw/day has been calculated from the BMDL₁₀ by the CEF Panel (2015). Since species-specific differences in TK are already included in the modelling, an interspecies factor of 2.5 for remaining (toxicodynamic) differences was used. Intraspecific variability was accounted for by a factor of 10. Additionally, a factor of 6 was used in the derivation of the t-TDI to account for uncertainties regarding possible effects on mammary

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 255

gland and reproductive organs and on the nervous, immune and metabolic system. Thus, from the HED a t-TDI of 4 µg/kg bw/day is derived by taking into account a total extrapolation factor of 150. The TDI was marked as “preliminary” since the results of an ongoing long-term study in rats with pre- and postnatal exposure had not been available at the time of evaluation (EFSA 2015).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 256

3 Conclusion on the derivation of HBM-GVs for BPF

The data on toxicity and TK are limited for BPF up to now. A derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for BPF based on human data providing evidence of a relationship between internal concentrations of BPF and the occurrence of adverse effects is not possible due to the lack of data. No external toxicity reference value for the general population or occupational exposure limit for the occupational health of workers has been proposed for BPF by EU or non-EU relevant organisations so far. Toxicity animal studies with chronic or subchronic exposure to BPF are not available, nor carcinogenicity or standard reproduction and fertility studies. Data on TK for BPF are incomplete in humans and in animals. Even if a very high to complete oral absorption is assumed, no data are available regarding the uptake of BPF from other routes, especially by dermal contact. In addition, for BPF, it has not been possible to calibrate the PBPK model proposed by Karrer et al. (2018) for BPA and its substitutes due to the lack of experimental data.

Therefore, at the moment, it is not possible to derive and recommend HBM-GVs for the monitoring of the health risks related to BPF in the general population nor in the practice of occupational health. However, it could be expected that data and knowledge will be published in the near to medium term as it is the case for other bisphenols, and those new data will certainly be of significant help to consider deriving HBM-GVs in the future. A weight of evidence approach should be considered to bridge the gaps of the BPF data package. Therefore, in the near future, a read-across with BPA and BPS studies could also be applied, namely, to consider TK specificities of BPS.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 257

4 References

- Andrianou, X. D., Gangler, S., Piciu, A., Charisiadis, P., Zira, C., Aristidou, K., Makris, K. C. (2016). Human Exposures to Bisphenol A, Bisphenol F and Chlorinated Bisphenol A Derivatives and Thyroid Function. *PLoS One*, 11(10), e0155237. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0155237
- Ashrap, P., Watkins, D. J., Calafat, A. M., Ye, X., Rosario, Z., Brown, P., Meeker, J. D. (2018). Elevated concentrations of urinary triclocarban, phenol and paraben among pregnant women in Northern Puerto Rico: Predictors and trends. *Environ Int*, 121(Pt 1), 990-1002. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2018.08.020
- Asimakopoulos, A. G., Xue, J., De Carvalho, B. P., Iyer, A., Abualnaja, K. O., Yaghmoor, S. S., Kannan, K. (2016). Urinary biomarkers of exposure to 57 xenobiotics and its association with oxidative stress in a population in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. *Environ Res*, 150, 573-581. doi:10.1016/j.envres.2015.11.029
- Audebert, M., Dolo, L., Perdu, E., Cravedi, J. P., & Zalko, D. (2011). Use of the γ H2AX assay for assessing the genotoxicity of bisphenol A and bisphenol F in human cell lines. *Archives of Toxicology*, 85(11), 1463. doi:10.1007/s00204-011-0721-2
- BfR. (2015a). BfR (2015) Fragen und Antworten zu Bisphenol F in Senf. FAQ des BfR vom 17. November 2015. Retrieved from Berlin: <http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/fragen-und-antworten-zu-bisphenol-f-in-senf.pdf>
- BfR. (2015b). Bisphenol F in Senf: das Auftreten von unerwünschten Wirkungen auf die Gesundheit durch gemessene BPF-Gehalte ist unwahrscheinlich. Stellungnahme Nr. 044/2015 des BfR vom 8. Juni 2015. Retrieved from Berlin: <http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/bisphenol-f-in-senf-das-auftreten-von-unerwuenschten-wirkungen-auf-die-gesundheit-durch-gemessene-bpf-gehalte-ist-unwahrscheinlich.pdf>
- BLV (2015). Bisphenol F in Senf – Fakten und Risikobewertung des BLV. Retrieved from Bern, Schweiz: https://www.blv.admin.ch/dam/blv/de/dokumente/lebensmittel-und-ernaehrung/lebensmittelsicherheit/stoffe-im-fokus/bisphenol-f-senf-fakten-risikobewertung-blv.pdf.download.pdf/Bisphenol_Risikobewertung_BLV_DE.pdf
- Bruze, M. (1986). Sensitizing capacity of dihydroxydiphenyl methane (bisphenol F) in the guinea pig. *Contact Dermatitis*, 14(4), 228-232.
- Bruze, M., & Zimerson, E. (1985). Contact allergy to dihydroxydiphenyl methanes (bisphenol F). *Derm Beruf Umwelt*, 33(6), 216-220.
- Cabaton, N., Chagnon, M.-C., Lhuguenot, J.-C., Cravedi, J.-P., & Zalko, D. (2006). Disposition and Metabolic Profiling of Bisphenol F in Pregnant and Nonpregnant Rats. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 54(26), 10307-10314. doi:10.1021/jf062250q
- Cabaton, N., Zalko, D., Rathahao, E., Canlet, C., Delous, G., Chagnon, M. C., Perdu, E. (2008). Biotransformation of bisphenol F by human and rat liver subcellular fractions. *Toxicol In Vitro*, 22(7), 1697-1704. doi:10.1016/j.tiv.2008.07.004
- Cabaton, N., Dumont, C., Severin, I., Perdu, E., Zalko, D., Cherkaoui-Malki, M., & Chagnon, M. C. (2009). Genotoxic and endocrine activities of bis(hydroxyphenyl)methane (bisphenol F) and its derivatives in the HepG2 cell line. *Toxicology*, 255(1-2), 15-24. doi:10.1016/j.tox.2008.09.024
- Cano-Nicolau, J., Vaillant, C., Pellegrini, E., Charlier, T. D., Kah, O., & Coumilleau, P. (2016). Estrogenic Effects of Several BPA Analogs in the Developing Zebrafish Brain. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 10, 112.
- Castro, B., Sánchez, P., Torres, J. M., & Ortega, E. (2015). Bisphenol A, bisphenol F and bisphenol S affect differently 5 α -reductase expression and dopamine–serotonin systems in the prefrontal cortex of juvenile female rats. *Environmental Research*, 142, 281-287. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2015.07.001>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 258

Cesen, M., Lenarcic, K., Mislej, V., Levstek, M., Kovacic, A., Cimrmancic, B., Heath, E. (2018). The occurrence and source identification of bisphenol compounds in wastewaters. *Sci Total Environ*, 616-617, 744-752. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.10.252

Charisiadis, P., Andrianou, X. D., Van Der Meer, T. P., Den Dunnen, W. F. A., Swaab, D. F., Wolffenbuttel, B. H. R., Van Vliet-Ostapchouk, J. V. (2018). Possible obesogenic effects of bisphenols accumulation in the human brain. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1). doi:10.1038/s41598-018-26498-y

Chen, D., Kannan, K., Tan, H., Zheng, Z.-G., Feng, Y.-L., Wu, Y., & Widelka, M. (2016). Bisphenol Analogues Other Than BPA: Environmental Occurrence, Human Exposure, and Toxicity - A Review. *Environ Sci Technol*, 50, 5438-5453. doi:10.1021/acs.est.5b05387

Chen, Y., Fang, J., Ren, L., Fan, R., Zhang, J., Liu, G., Lu, S. (2018). Urinary bisphenol analogues and triclosan in children from south China and implications for human exposure. *Environ Pollut*, 238, 299-305. doi:10.1016/j.envpol.2018.03.031

Derakhshan, A., Shu, H., Peeters, R. P., Kortenkamp, A., Lindh, C. H., Demeneix, B., Korevaar, T. I. M. (2019). Association of urinary bisphenols and triclosan with thyroid function during early pregnancy. *Environ Int*, 133(Pt A), 105123. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2019.105123

Dietrich, D., & Hengstler, J. (2016). From bisphenol A to bisphenol F and a ban of mustard due to chronic low-dose exposures? *Arch. Toxicol*, 90, 3.

Dualde, P., Pardo, O., Corpas-Burgos, F., Kuligowski, J., Gormaz, M., Vento, M., Yusa, V. (2019). Biomonitoring of bisphenols A, F, S in human milk and probabilistic risk assessment for breastfed infants. *Sci Total Environ*, 668, 797-805. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.03.024

Dualde, P., Pardo, O., S, F. F., Pastor, A., & Yusa, V. (2019). Determination of four parabens and bisphenols A, F and S in human breast milk using QuEChERS and liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry. *J Chromatogr B Analyt Technol Biomed Life Sci*, 1114-1115, 154-166. doi:10.1016/j.jchromb.2019.03.004

Duan, Y., Yao, Y., Wang, B., Han, L., Wang, L., Sun, H., & Chen, L. (2018). Association of urinary concentrations of bisphenols with type 2 diabetes mellitus: A case-control study. *Environ Pollut*, 243(Pt B), 1719-1726. doi:10.1016/j.envpol.2018.09.093

Dumont, C., Perdu, E., de Sousa, G., Debrauwer, L., Rahmani, R., Cravedi, J.-P., & Chagnon, M.-C. (2011). Bis(hydroxyphenyl)methane-bisphenol F-metabolism by the HepG2 human hepatoma cell line and cryopreserved human hepatocytes. *Drug and Chemical Toxicology*, 34(4), 445-453. doi:10.3109/01480545.2011.585651

ECHA. (2020a). ECHA Registration Dossier on Bisphenol F (CAS number 1333-16-0). Retrieved from <https://echa.europa.eu/de/registration-dossier/-/registered-dossier/14986>

ECHA. (2020b). ECHA RMOA List. Retrieved from <https://echa.europa.eu/rmoa>

ECHA. (2020c). ECHA Substance Information 4,4'-methylenediphenol. Retrieved from <https://echa.europa.eu/substance-information/-/substanceinfo/100.009.691>

EFSA CEF Panel. (2009). Scientific Opinion: 24th list of substances for food contact materials. Scientific Opinion of the Panel on food contact materials, enzymes, flavourings and processing aids (CEF). *The EFSA Journal*, 1157-1163, 1-28.

EFSA. (2015). Scientific Opinion on the risks to public health related to the presence of bisphenol A (BPA) in foodstuffs: Executive summary. EFSA Panel on Food Contact Materials, Enzymes, Flavourings and Processing Aids (CEF). *The EFSA Journal*, 13(1), 1040.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 259

Eladak, S., Grisin, T., Moison, D., Guerquin, M.-J., N'Tumba-Byn, T., Pozzi-Gaudin, S., Habert, R. (2015). A new chapter in the bisphenol A story: bisphenol S and bisphenol F are not safe alternatives to this compound. *Fertility and Sterility*, 103(1), 11-21. doi:10.1016/j.fertnstert.2014.11.005

Fromme, H., Kuchler, T., Otto, T., Pilz, K., Muller, J., & Wenzel, A. (2002). Occurrence of phthalates and bisphenol A and F in the environment. *Water Research*, 36(6), 1429-1438. doi:[http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354\(01\)00367-0](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354(01)00367-0)

Fujiwara, Y., Miyazaki, W., Koibuchi, N., & Katoh, T. (2018). The Effects of Low-Dose Bisphenol A and Bisphenol F on Neural Differentiation of a Fetal Brain-Derived Neural Progenitor Cell Line. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)*, 9, 24. doi:10.3389/fendo.2018.00024

Gao, P., Wang, L., Yang, N., Wen, J., Zhao, M., Su, G., Weng, D. (2020). Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma (PPARgamma) activation and metabolism disturbance induced by bisphenol A and its replacement analog bisphenol S using in vitro macrophages and in vivo mouse models. *Environ Int*, 134, 105328. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2019.105328

Gingrich, J., Pu, Y., Ehrhardt, R., Karthikraj, R., Kannan, K., & Veiga-Lopez, A. (2019). Toxicokinetics of bisphenol A, bisphenol S, and bisphenol F in a pregnancy sheep model. *Chemosphere*, 220, 185-194. doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.12.109

Goldinger, D. M., Demierre, A.-L., Zoller, O., Rupp, H., Reinhard, H., Magnin, R., Bourqui-Pittet, M. (2015). Endocrine activity of alternatives to BPA found in thermal paper in Switzerland. *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 71(3), 453-462. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yrtph.2015.01.002>

Gonzalez, N., Cunha, S. C., Monteiro, C., Fernandes, J. O., Marques, M., Domingo, J. L., & Nadal, M. (2019). Quantification of eight bisphenol analogues in blood and urine samples of workers in a hazardous waste incinerator. *Environ Res*, 176, 108576. doi:10.1016/j.envres.2019.108576

Gramec Skledar, D., Troberg, J., Lavdas, J., Peterlin Masic, L., & Finel, M. (2015). Differences in the glucuronidation of bisphenols F and S between two homologous human UGT enzymes, 1A9 and 1A10. *Xenobiotica*, 45(6), 511-519. doi:10.3109/00498254.2014.999140

Grumetto, L., Barbato, F., & Russo, G. (2019). Scrutinizing the interactions between bisphenol analogues and plasma proteins: Insights from biomimetic liquid chromatography, molecular docking simulations and in silico predictions. *Environ Toxicol Pharmacol*, 68, 148-154. doi:10.1016/j.etap.2019.02.008

Hayakawa, R., Matsxмага, K., Takeuchi, Y., Tatsumi, H., & Masamoto, Y. (1985). Occupational Contact Dermatitis from Bisphenol F. *Skin Research*, 27(3), 494-500. doi:10.11340/skinresearch1959.27.494

Hercog, K., Maisanaba, S., Filipic, M., Sollner-Dolenc, M., Kac, L., & Zegura, B. (2019). Genotoxic activity of bisphenol A and its analogues bisphenol S, bisphenol F and bisphenol AF and their mixtures in human hepatocellular carcinoma (HepG2) cells. *Sci Total Environ*, 687, 267-276. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.05.486

Higashihara, N., Shiraishi, K., Miyata, K., Oshima, Y., Minobe, Y., & Yamasaki, K. (2007). Subacute oral toxicity study of bisphenol F based on the draft protocol for the "Enhanced OECD Test Guideline no. 407". *Archives of Toxicology*, 81(12), 825-832. doi:10.1007/s00204-007-0223-4

HLUG. (2011). *Bewertungen von Stoffen/Stoffgruppen: Landesweite Untersuchung auf organische Spurenverunreinigungen in hessischen Fliegewassern, Abwassern und Klarschlammern (Kapitel 6)*. Retrieved from https://www.hlnug.de/fileadmin/dokumente/wasser/fliessgewaesser/gewaesserbelastung/orientierende_messungen/kapitel_6_alle_stoffe.pdf

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 260

- Horan, T. S., Pulcastro, H., Lawson, C., Gerona, R., Martin, S., Gieske, M. C., Hunt, P. A. (2018). Replacement Bisphenols Adversely Affect Mouse Gametogenesis with Consequences for Subsequent Generations. *Curr Biol*, 28(18), 2948-2954.e2943. doi:10.1016/j.cub.2018.06.070
- HSDB. (2013). Bisphenol F. from Hazardous Substances Data Bank, National Institutes of Health, National Library of Medicine <http://toxnet.nlm.nih.gov/>
- Husøy, T., Andreassen, M., Hjertholm, H., Carlsen, M. H., Norberg, N., Sprong, C., Dirven, H. (2019). The Norwegian biomonitoring study from the EU project EuroMix: Levels of phenols and phthalates in 24-hour urine samples and exposure sources from food and personal care products. *Environ Int*, 132, 105103. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2019.105103
- Ihde, E. S., Zamudio, S., Loh, J. M., Zhu, Y., Woytanowski, J., Rosen, L., Buckley, B. (2018). Application of a novel mass spectrometric (MS) method to examine exposure to Bisphenol-A and common substitutes in a maternal fetal cohort. *Hum Ecol Risk Assess*, 24(2), 331-346. doi:10.1080/10807039.2017.1381831
- Ikhlas, S., Usman, A., & Ahmad, M. (2019). In vitro study to evaluate the cytotoxicity of BPA analogues based on their oxidative and genotoxic potential using human peripheral blood cells. *Toxicol In Vitro*, 60, 229-236. doi:10.1016/j.tiv.2019.06.001
- Iwano, H., Ohtani, N., Hozumi, N., Inoue, H., & Yokota, H. (2016). Pharmacokinetic study of adverse effects in offspring caused by prenatal Bisphenol F exposure. *Toxicology Letters*, 259, S113. doi:10.1016/j.toxlet.2016.07.288
- Jacobson, M. H., Woodward, M., Bao, W., Liu, B., & Trasande, L. (2019). Urinary Bisphenols and Obesity Prevalence Among U.S. Children and Adolescents. *J Endocr Soc*, 3(9), 1715-1726. doi:10.1210/js.2019-00201
- JECDB. (2004a). 4,4'-Methylenediphenol: Bacterial reverse mutation test (in Japanese). Retrieved from http://dra4.nihs.go.jp/mhlw_data/home/pdf/PDF620-92-8e.pdf
- JECDB. (2004b). 4,4'-Methylenediphenol: In Vitro mammalian chromosome aberration test (in Japanese). Retrieved from http://dra4.nihs.go.jp/mhlw_data/home/pdf/PDF620-92-8f.pdf
- JECDB. (2004c). 4,4'-Methylenediphenol: Repeated Dose 28-day oral toxicity study (in Japanese). Retrieved from http://dra4.nihs.go.jp/mhlw_data/home/pdf/PDF620-92-8b.pdf
- JECDB. (2012). 4,4'-Methylenediphenol: Micronucleus test (in Japanese). Retrieved from http://dra4.nihs.go.jp/mhlw_data/home/pdf/PDF620-92-8g.pdf
- JECDB. (without year). 4,4'-Methylenediphenol (English Summary). Retrieved from http://dra4.nihs.go.jp/mhlw_data/home/file/file620-92-8.html
- Jin, H., Xie, J., Mao, L., Zhao, M., Bai, X., Wen, J., Wu, P. (2020). Bisphenol analogue concentrations in human breast milk and their associations with postnatal infant growth. *Environ Pollut*, 259, 113779. doi:10.1016/j.envpol.2019.113779
- Jin, H., Zhu, J., Chen, Z., Hong, Y., & Cai, Z. (2018). Occurrence and Partitioning of Bisphenol Analogues in Adults' Blood from China. *Environ Sci Technol*, 52(2), 812-820. doi:10.1021/acs.est.7b03958
- Jordakova, I., Dobias, J., Voldrich, M., & Poustka, J. (2003). Determination of Bisphenol A, Bisphenol F, Bisphenol A Diglycidyl Ether and Bisphenol F Diglycidyl Ether Migrated from Food Cans using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry. *Czech J. Food Sci.*, 21, 6.
- Kang, S., Shin, B. H., Kwon, J. A., Lee, C. W., Park, E. K., Park, E. Y., & Kim, B. (2020). Urinary bisphenol A and its analogues and haemato-biochemical alterations of pregnant women in Korea. *Environ Res*, 182, 109104. doi:10.1016/j.envres.2019.109104

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 261

- Karrer, C., Roiss, T., von Goetz, N., Gramec Skledar, D., Peterlin Masic, L., & Hungerbuhler, K. (2018). Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) Modeling of the Bisphenols BPA, BPS, BPF, and BPAF with New Experimental Metabolic Parameters: Comparing the Pharmacokinetic Behavior of BPA with Its Substitutes. *Environ Health Perspect*, 126(7), 077002. doi:10.1289/EHP2739
- Kataria, A., Levine, D., Wertenteil, S., Vento, S., Xue, J., Rajendiran, K., Trachtman, H. (2017). Exposure to bisphenols and phthalates and association with oxidant stress, insulin resistance, and endothelial dysfunction in children. *Pediatr Res*, 81(6), 857-864. doi:10.1038/pr.2017.16
- Kielmeier, U. (2015). Bisphenol F in Senf - wie kommt der Bisphenol A-ähnliche Stoff in die Würste? Retrieved from <https://www.analytik-news.de/Fachartikel/Volltext/cvuas17.pdf>
- Kolatorova, L., Vitku, J., Hampl, R., Adamcova, K., Skodova, T., Simkova, M., Duskova, M. (2018). Exposure to bisphenols and parabens during pregnancy and relations to steroid changes. *Environ Res*, 163, 115-122. doi:10.1016/j.envres.2018.01.031
- Le Fol, V., Ait-Aïssa, S., Sonavane, M., Porcher, J.-M., Balaguer, P., Cravedi, J.-P., Brion, F. (2017). In vitro and in vivo estrogenic activity of BPA, BPF and BPS in zebrafish-specific assays. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 142(Supplement C), 150-156. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2017.04.009>
- Lehmler, H.-J., Liu, B., Gadogbe, M., & Bao, W. (2018). Exposure to Bisphenol A, Bisphenol F, and Bisphenol S in U.S. Adults and Children: The National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey 2013–2014. *ACS Omega*, 3(6), 6523-6532. doi:10.1021/acsomega.8b00824
- Li, A., Zhuang, T., Shi, W., Liang, Y., Liao, C., Song, M., & Jiang, G. (2020). Serum concentration of bisphenol analogues in pregnant women in China. *Sci Total Environ*, 707, 136100. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.136100
- Liao, C., & Kannan, K. (2013). Concentrations and Profiles of Bisphenol A and Other Bisphenol Analogues in Foodstuffs from the United States and Their Implications for Human Exposure. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 61(19), 4655-4662. doi:10.1021/jf400445n
- Liao, C., & Kannan, K. (2014). A survey of alkylphenols, bisphenols, and triclosan in personal care products from China and the United States. *Arch Environ Contam Toxicol*, 67(1), 50-59. doi:10.1007/s00244-014-0016-8
- Liu, B., Lehmler, H. J., Sun, Y., Xu, G., Liu, Y., Zong, G., Bao, W. (2017). Bisphenol A substitutes and obesity in US adults: analysis of a population-based, cross-sectional study. *Lancet Planet Health*, 1(3), e114-e122. doi:10.1016/S2542-5196(17)30049-9
- Liu, B., Lehmler, H. J., Sun, Y., Xu, G., Sun, Q., Snetselaar, L. G., Bao, W. (2019). Association of Bisphenol A and Its Substitutes, Bisphenol F and Bisphenol S, with Obesity in United States Children and Adolescents. *Diabetes Metab J*, 43(1), 59-75. doi:10.4093/dmj.2018.0045
- Liu, Y., Yan, Z., Zhang, Q., Song, N., Cheng, J., Torres, O. L., Guo, R. (2019). Urinary levels, composition profile and cumulative risk of bisphenols in preschool-aged children from Nanjing suburb, China. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf*, 172, 444-450. doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2019.02.002
- Machtinger, R., Berman, T., Adir, M., Mansur, A., Baccarelli, A. A., Racowsky, C., Nahum, R. (2018). Urinary concentrations of phthalate metabolites, bisphenols and personal care product chemical biomarkers in pregnant women in Israel. *Environ Int*, 116, 319-325. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2018.04.022
- NTP (2017). NTP Research report on biological activity of Bisphenol A (BPA) Structural Analogues and functional alternatives (RR4). Retrieved from https://ntp.niehs.nih.gov/ntp/results/pubs/rr/reports/rr04_508.pdf

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 262

Ohtani, N., Iwano, H., Hozumi, N., Inoue, H., & Yokota, H. (2016). The mechanism of influences on the next-generation of mice caused by prenatal Bisphenol F exposure. *Toxicology Letters*, 259, S113.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2016.07.288>

Ohtani, N., Iwano, H., Suda, K., Tsuji, E., Tanemura, K., Inoue, H., & Yokota, H. (2017). Adverse effects of maternal exposure to bisphenol F on the anxiety- and depression-like behavior of offspring. *J Vet Med Sci*, 79(2), 432-439. doi:10.1292/jvms.16-0502

Owczarek, K., Kubica, P., Kudlak, B., Rutkowska, A., Konieczna, A., Rachon, D., Wasik, A. (2018). Determination of trace levels of eleven bisphenol A analogues in human blood serum by high performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry. *Sci Total Environ*, 628-629, 1362-1368.

doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.02.148

Pelch, K., Wignall, J. A., Goldstone, A. E., Ross, P. K., Blain, R. B., Shapiro, A. J., Thayer, K. A. (2019). A scoping review of the health and toxicological activity of bisphenol A (BPA) structural analogues and functional alternatives. *Toxicology*, 424, 152235. doi:10.1016/j.tox.2019.06.006

Perez, P., Pulgar, R., Olea-Serrano, F., Villalobos, M., Rivas, A., Metzler, M., Olea, N. (1998). The estrogenicity of bisphenol A-related diphenylalkanes with various substituents at the central carbon and the hydroxy groups. *Environ Health Perspect*, 106(3), 167-174.

Philips, E. M., Jaddoe, V. W. V., Asimakopoulos, A. G., Kannan, K., Steegers, E. A. P., Santos, S., & Trasande, L. (2018). Bisphenol and phthalate concentrations and its determinants among pregnant women in a population-based cohort in the Netherlands, 2004–5. *Environmental Research*, 161, 562-572. doi:10.1016/j.envres.2017.11.051

Philips, E. M., Kahn, L. G., Jaddoe, V. W. V., Shao, Y., Asimakopoulos, A. G., Kannan, K., Trasande, L. (2018). First Trimester Urinary Bisphenol and Phthalate Concentrations and Time to Pregnancy: A Population-Based Cohort Analysis. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*, 103(9), 3540-3547. doi:10.1210/jc.2018-00855

Rochester, J. R., & Bolden, A. L. (2015). Bisphenol S and F: A Systematic Review and Comparison of the Hormonal Activity of Bisphenol A Substitutes. *Environ Health Perspect*, 123(7), 643-650.

doi:10.1289/ehp.1408989

Rosenmai, A. K., Dybdahl, M., Pedersen, M., Alice van Vugt-Lussenburg, B. M., Wedebye, E. B., Taxvig, C., & Vinggaard, A. M. (2014). Are structural analogues to bisphenol a safe alternatives? *Toxicol Sci*, 139(1), 35-47. doi:10.1093/toxsci/kfu030

Sakhi, A. K., Sabaredzovic, A., Papadopoulou, E., Cequier, E., & Thomsen, C. (2018). Levels, variability and determinants of environmental phenols in pairs of Norwegian mothers and children. *Environ Int*, 114, 242-251. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2018.02.037

Santé Publique France, S.-M. (2019). Imprégnation de la population française par les bisphénols A, S et F. Etude ESTEBAN. Programme national de biosurveillance, Esteban 2014-2016. . ACS Omega, Santé publique France, septembre 2019. , 57.

Sharma, A., Singh, K., & Almasan, A. (2012). Histone H2AX Phosphorylation: A Marker for DNA Damage. In L. Bjergbæk (Ed.), *DNA Repair Protocols* (pp. 613-626). Totowa, NJ: Humana Press.

Shen, Y., Liu, T., Shi, Y., Zhuang, F., Lu, J., Zhu, Q., & Ding, F. (2019). Bisphenol A analogs in patients with chronic kidney disease and dialysis therapy. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf*, 185, 109684.

doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2019.109684

Shmidt, E., Farmer, S. A., & Davis, M. D. (2010). Patch-testing with plastics and glues series allergens. *Dermatitis*, 21(5), 269-274.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 263

Smyth, H. F. J., Carpenter, C. P., Weil, C. S., Pozzani, D. C., & Striegel, J. A. (1962). Range-Finding Toxicity Data: List VI. *Am. Ind. Hyg. Assoc.*, 23, 95-107.

Song, S., Duan, Y., Zhang, T., Zhang, B., Zhao, Z., Bai, X., Sun, H. (2019). Serum concentrations of bisphenol A and its alternatives in elderly population living around e-waste recycling facilities in China: Associations with fasting blood glucose. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 169, 822-828. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2018.11.101>

Stroheker, T., Chagnon, M.-C., Pinnert, M.-F., Berges, R., & Canivenc-Lavier, M.-C. (2003). Estrogenic effects of food wrap packaging xenoestrogens and flavonoids in female Wistar rats: a comparative study. *Reproductive Toxicology*, 17(4), 421-432. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0890-6238\(03\)00044-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0890-6238(03)00044-3)

Tsutsui, T., Tamura, Y., Suzuki, A., Hirose, Y., Kobayashi, M., Nishimura, H., Barrett, J. C. (2000). Mammalian cell transformation and aneuploidy induced by five bisphenols. *Int J Cancer*, 86(2), 151-154.

Tyl, R. W., Myers, C. B., Marr, M. C., Sloan, C. S., Castillo, N. P., Veselica, M. M., Waechter, J. J. M. (2008). Two-Generation Reproductive Toxicity Study of Dietary Bisphenol A in CD-1 (Swiss) Mice. *Toxicological Sciences*, 104(2), 362-384. doi:10.1093/toxsci/kfn084

U.S.EPA. (2015). Bisphenol A Alternatives in Thermal Paper, Chapter 4: Hazard Evaluation of Bisphenol A (BPA) and Alternatives. Final Report. Retrieved from Washington, DC: https://www.epa.gov/sites/production/files/2015-09/documents/bpa_ch4.pdf

Ullah, A., Pirzada, M., Afsar, T., Razak, S., Almajwal, A., & Jahan, S. (2019a). Effect of bisphenol F, an analog of bisphenol A, on the reproductive functions of male rats. *Environ Health Prev Med*, 24(1), 41. doi:10.1186/s12199-019-0797-5

Ullah, A., Pirzada, M., Jahan, S., Ullah, H., & Khan, M. J. (2019b). Bisphenol A analogues bisphenol B, bisphenol F, and bisphenol S induce oxidative stress, disrupt daily sperm production, and damage DNA in rat spermatozoa: a comparative in vitro and in vivo study. *Toxicol Ind Health*, 35(4), 294-303. doi:10.1177/0748233719831528

Ullah, A., Pirzada, M., Jahan, S., Ullah, H., Razak, S., Rauf, N., Mahboob, S. Z. (2019c). Prenatal BPA and its analogs BPB, BPF, and BPS exposure and reproductive axis function in the male offspring of Sprague Dawley rats. *Hum Exp Toxicol*, 38(12), 1344-1365. doi:10.1177/0960327119862335

Ullah, A., Pirzada, M., Jahan, S., Ullah, H., Shaheen, G., Rehman, H., Butt, M. A. (2018a). Bisphenol A and its analogs bisphenol B, bisphenol F, and bisphenol S: Comparative in vitro and in vivo studies on the sperms and testicular tissues of rats. *Chemosphere*, 209, 508-516. doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.06.089

Ullah, A., Pirzada, M., Jahan, S., Ullah, H., Turi, N., Ullah, W., Khan, M. M. (2018b). Impact of low-dose chronic exposure to bisphenol A and its analogue bisphenol B, bisphenol F and bisphenol S on hypothalamo-pituitary-testicular activities in adult rats: A focus on the possible hormonal mode of action. *Food Chem Toxicol*, 121, 24-36. doi:10.1016/j.fct.2018.08.024

Verbanck, M., Canouil, M., Leloir, A., Dhennin, V., Coumoul, X., Yengo, L., Poulain-Godefroy, O. (2017). Low-dose exposure to bisphenols A, F and S of human primary adipocyte impacts coding and non-coding RNA profiles. *PLoS One*, 12(6), e0179583. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0179583

Vitku, J., Kolatorova, L., Franekova, L., Blahos, J., Simkova, M., Duskova, M., Starka, L. (2018). Endocrine disruptors of the bisphenol and paraben families and bone metabolism. *Physiol Res*, 67(Suppl 3), S455-s464. doi:10.33549/physiolres.934005

Wang, Y. X., Liu, C., Shen, Y., Wang, Q., Pan, A., Yang, P., Zeng, Q. (2019). Urinary levels of bisphenol A, F and S and markers of oxidative stress among healthy adult men: Variability and association analysis. *Environ Int*, 123, 301-309. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2018.11.071

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 264

Yabusaki, R., Iwano, H., Tsushima, S., Koike, N., Ohtani, N., Tanemura, K., Yokota, H. (2015). Weak activity of UDP-glucuronosyltransferase toward Bisphenol analogs in mouse perinatal development. *J Vet Med Sci*, 77(11), 1479-1484. doi:10.1292/jvms.15-0197

Yamasaki, K., Noda, S., Imatanaka, N., & Yakabe, Y. (2004). Comparative study of the uterotrophic potency of 14 chemicals in a uterotrophic assay and their receptor-binding affinity. *Toxicology Letters*, 146(2), 111-120. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2003.07.003>

Yamasaki, K., Takeyoshi, M., Yakabe, Y., Sawaki, M., Imatanaka, N., & Takatsuki, M. (2002). Comparison of reporter gene assay and immature rat uterotrophic assay of twenty-three chemicals. *Toxicology*, 170(1-2), 21-30.

Yamazaki, E., Yamashita, N., Taniyasu, S., Lam, J., Lam, P. K. S., Moon, H.-B., Kannan, K. (2015). Bisphenol A and other bisphenol analogues including BPS and BPF in surface water samples from Japan, China, Korea and India. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 122, 565-572. doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2015.09.029

Yang, Y., Guan, J., Yin, J., Shao, B., & Li, H. (2014). Urinary levels of bisphenol analogues in residents living near a manufacturing plant in south China. *Chemosphere*, 112, 481-486. doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2014.05.004

Yang, Q., Yang, X., Liu, J., Ren, W., Chen, Y., & Shen, S. (2017). Effects of BPF on steroid hormone homeostasis and gene expression in the hypothalamic–pituitary–gonadal axis of zebrafish. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 24(26), 21311-21322. doi:10.1007/s11356-017-9773-z

Yang, Y., Yang, Y., Zhang, J., Shao, B., & Yin, J. (2019). Assessment of bisphenol A alternatives in paper products from the Chinese market and their dermal exposure in the general population. *Environ Pollut*, 244, 238-246. doi:10.1016/j.envpol.2018.10.049

Zhang, H., Quan, Q., Zhang, M., Zhang, N., Zhang, W., Zhan, M., Wang, Q. (2020). Occurrence of bisphenol A and its alternatives in paired urine and indoor dust from Chinese university students: Implications for human exposure. *Chemosphere*, 247, 125987. doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.125987

Zhang, T., Xue, J., Gao, C. Z., Qiu, R. L., Li, Y. X., Li, X., Kannan, K. (2016). Urinary Concentrations of Bisphenols and Their Association with Biomarkers of Oxidative Stress in People Living Near E-Waste Recycling Facilities in China. *Environ Sci Technol*, 50(7), 4045-4053. doi:10.1021/acs.est.6b00032

Zhang, W., Xia, W., Liu, W., Li, X., Hu, J., Zhang, B., . . . Li, Y. (2019). Exposure to Bisphenol a Substitutes and Gestational Diabetes Mellitus: A Prospective Cohort Study in China. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)*, 10, 262. doi:10.3389/fendo.2019.00262

Zhang, Y.-F., Ren, X.-M., Li, Y.-Y., Yao, X.-F., Li, C.-H., Qin, Z.-F., & Guo, L.-H. (2018). Bisphenol A alternatives bisphenol S and bisphenol F interfere with thyroid hormone signaling pathway in vitro and in vivo. *Environmental Pollution*, 237, 1072-1079. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2017.11.027>

Zhang, Y., Dong, T., Hu, W., Wang, X., Xu, B., Lin, Z., Xia, Y. (2019). Association between exposure to a mixture of phenols, pesticides, and phthalates and obesity: Comparison of three statistical models. *Environ Int*, 123, 325-336. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2018.11.076

Zhou, B., Yang, P., Deng, Y. L., Zeng, Q., Lu, W. Q., & Mei, S. R. (2020). Prenatal exposure to bisphenol a and its analogues (bisphenol F and S) and ultrasound parameters of fetal growth. *Chemosphere*, 246, 125805. doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2019.125805

Zoller, O., Bruschiweiler, B. J., Magnin, R., Reinhard, H., Rhyn, P., Rupp, H., Felleisen, R. (2016). Natural occurrence of bisphenol F in mustard. *Food Addit Contam Part A Chem Anal Control Expo Risk Assess*, 33(1), 137-146. doi:10.1080/19440049.2015.1110623

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 265

Part V

Derivation of N-dimethylformamide (DMF)

HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs):

DMF HBM-GV_{Worker} for occupationally exposed adults

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 266

Table of contents (Part V)

Authors and acknowledgements	269
Abbreviations	270
1 Introduction	272
1.1 Objectives	272
1.2 Methodological aspects of the HBM-GVs derivation for DMF	272
2 General information on DMF	273
2.1 Identification of the substance	273
2.2 Physico-chemical properties of DMF	273
2.3 Uses of DMF	274
2.4 Existing EU classification and regulation of DMF	274
2.4.1 Harmonised classification and labelling	274
2.4.2 IARC classification	275
2.4.3 EU directives and regulations of DMF	275
2.5 Human exposure to DMF	276
2.5.1 Environmental and consumers exposure	276
2.5.2 Occupational exposure	276
3 Toxicological profile of DMF	277
3.1 Toxicokinetics	277
3.1.1 Absorption	277
3.1.2 Distribution	278
3.1.3 Metabolism	278
3.1.4 Excretion	280
3.2 Health effects of DMF	281
3.2.1 Acute toxicity	281
3.2.2 Skin, eye and respiratory tract irritation	283
3.2.3 Chronic toxicity	283
3.2.4 Genotoxicity	287
3.2.5 Carcinogenicity	289
3.2.6 Reproductive and developmental effects	291
4 Existing toxicity reference values for occupationally exposed workers to DMF	295
4.1 Scientific committee on occupational exposure limit values (SCOEL)	295
4.1.1 8h-TWA (Time-Weighted Average)	295

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 267

4.1.2	STEL (Short Term Exposure Level)	295
4.1.3	BLV (Biological Limit Value)	295
4.1.4	Notation	295
4.2	DFG (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft).....	296
4.2.1	MAK value (maximale Arbeitsplatz-Konzentration).....	296
4.2.2	BAT value (Biologischer Arbeitsstoff Toleranzwert).....	296
4.3	ACGIH (American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists)	296
4.3.1	TLV-TWA (Threshold Limit Value – Time-Weighted Average).....	296
4.3.2	BEI (Biological Exposure Index)	296
4.4	ECHA (European Chemicals Agency) – DNELinhalation (Derived No Effect Level – inhalation route)	297
4.5	Summary of the existing values for DMF	298
4.5.1	Summary of the existing OEL values for DMF	298
4.5.2	Summary of the existing internal toxicity reference values for DMF	299
4.6	Conclusion	300
5	HBM parameters	301
5.1	Choice of biomarkers	301
5.1.1	DMF in urine	301
5.1.2	Total NMF in urine.....	301
5.1.3	AMCC in urine.....	301
5.1.4	MCV _{al} in blood.....	302
5.1.5	Formamide in urine	302
5.1.6	Summary of the advantages and disadvantages of the BME	303
5.1.7	Conclusion	303
5.2	Analytical methods	304
6	Derivation of HBM-GVs for workers.....	305
6.1	Derivation method.....	305
6.2	Choice of the critical effects	305
6.3	Choice of the key study and derivation of HBM-GV _{workers}	305
7	Discussion.....	307
8	Level of confidence attributed to the HBM-GVs	309
9	Factsheet reporting the HBM-GV _{worker} derivation	310
10	References.....	314

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 268

11 Annexes	323
11.1 Annex 1: Exposure	323
11.2 Annex 2: Chronic toxicity	328
11.3 Annex 3: HBM parameters	334

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 269

Authors and acknowledgements

Lead authors

Farida Lamkarkach (ANSES), Matthieu Meslin (ANSES)

Contributors

ANSES Working Group on Biomarkers, especially Robert Garnier and Claude Viau, Christophe Rousselle (ANSES), Petra Apel (UBA)

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the experts who provided us feedback on this work during the consultation period. Comments were taken as far as possible into consideration for the finalisation of this report.

The responses to the comments formulated by the T5.2 partners ANSES and UBA will be sent to the contributing experts.

Entity	Contributing expert
NH Austria	Ilse Mauritz (EAA)
NH Portugal	Teresa Borges (DGS), Susana Viegas (ENSP)
NH Switzerland	Rex Fitzgerald (SCAHT), Nancy Hopf (UNISANTE)
NH Netherlands	Floris Groothuis (RIVM)
NH United Kingdom	Kate Jones (HSE)
NH Sweden	Jonas Tägt (KEMI)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 270

Abbreviations

ADI	Acceptable Daily Intake
ADME	Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion
AF	Assessment Factor
AF _A	Assessment Factor for interspecies differences
AF _H	Assessment Factor accounting for intraspecies differences
ALT	Alanine aminotransferase
AMCC	N-Acetyl-S-(N-methylcarbamoyl) cystein
ANSES	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety
AP	Alkalinephosphatase
AST	Aspartate aminotransferase
BAT	Biological Tolerance Values (Biologische Arbeitsstofftoleranzwerte)
BEI	Biological Exposure Index
BLV	Biological Limit Value
BMD	Benchmark Dose
BMDL	Benchmark Dose Lower Confidence Limit
BME(s)	Biomarker(s) of exposure
BW	Body Weight
BWG	Body Weight Gain
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging
CMR	Carcinogenic, Mutagenic, and Reprotoxic
DFG	German Research Foundation
DMF	Dimethylformamide
DNEL	Derived No-Effect Level
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EU	European Union
FC	Food consumption
HBM-GV	HBM Guidance Value
HBM-GV _{Worker}	HBM-GV for occupationally exposed adults
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU	European Human Biomonitoring Initiative
HMF	N-hydroxymethylformamide
HMMF	N-hydroxymethyl-N-methylformamide
γGT	Gamma glutamyltransferase

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 271

GC-MS	Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry
GI	Gastrointestinal
GM	Geometric Mean
IARC	International Agency for Research on Cancer
MAK	Maximum Workplace Concentration (Maximale Arbeitsplatz-Konzentration)
MCVal	N-methylcarbamoyl adduct at haemoglobin
MIC	Methyl Isocyanate
MoA	Mode of Action
NIOSH	National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (United States of America)
NO(A)EC	No Observed (Adverse) Effect Concentration
NO(A)EL	No Observed (Adverse) Effect Level
OEL	Occupational Exposure Limit
PBPK/PBTK	Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic/Toxicokinetic
POD	Point of Departure
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction
RIVM	Netherlands National Institute for Public Health and the Environment
SCOEL	Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limit Values (European Commission)
SVHC	Substance of Very High Concern
tNMF	Total N-methylformamide
TRV	Toxicity Reference Value
TWA	Time Weighted Average

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 272

1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives

Within the framework of Task 5.2 of the European Joint Programme, HBM4EU, Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) are derived for HBM4EU priority substances.

The methodology applied to derive these values is described in the concept paper released in the HBM4EU task 5.2 workframe (HBM4EU concept paper) and published in a peer-reviewed journal (Apel et al., 2020).

For the time being, HBM-GVs are derived in HBM4EU under inclusion of experts from the 30 partner countries. Future use and implementation will be discussed among partners and the EU Commission but are without prejudice to existing or ongoing risk assessment work in order to inform EU policy-making.

In the current report, HBM-GVs for the occupational population are derived and discussed for the aprotic solvent N-N, dimethylformamide (DMF).

1.2 Methodological aspects of the HBM-GVs derivation for DMF

A detailed overview of the studies is provided e.g. by the IARC (2018), the European Chemical Agency (ECHA, 2019), the American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH, 2017 and 2018), the German Research Foundation (DFG, 2006 and 2019) and the Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limit Values (SCOEL, 2006).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 273

2 General information on DMF

2.1 Identification of the substance

Table V.1: DMF Chemical identification

Name	N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF)
IUPAC Names	N,N-dimethylformamide, N,N-dimethyl formamide, N,N Dimethylmethanamide, Dimethylformamide, Dimethyl formamide
CAS Number	68-12-2
EC /List no.	200-679-5
Molar mass weight	73.09 g/mol
Molecular formula	C ₃ H ₇ NO
Conversion factor (25°C)*	1 ppm = 2.99 mg/m ³ 1 mg/m ³ = 0.335 ppm
Structural formula	

* ACGIH 2018

2.2 Physico-chemical properties of DMF

N,N-dimethylformamide is a colourless or pale yellow, high-boiling, strongly polar and hygroscopic liquid with a faint amine odour. It is a flammable liquid and miscible with water and many lipophilic solvents (ACGIH, 2017 and 2018). Key physico-chemical property values are presented in Table V.2.

Table V.2: Overview of physico-chemical properties of DMF¹⁸

Physical state	Liquid at 20°C and 1013 hPa
Melting point	-61 °C at 1013 hPa
Boiling point	152 °C at 1013 hPa
Relative density	0.95 g/ml at 20 °C
Vapour pressure	3.77 hPa at 20 °C
Partition coefficient n-octanol/water (log Kow)	-0.85 at 25 °C
Water solubility	1000 g/L at 20 °C
Dissociation constant (pKa value)	-0.3 at 20 °C

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 274

2.3 Uses of DMF

DMF is used in many applications in the chemical industry. The amount of DMF manufactured and/or imported into the EU is, according to registration data, in the range of 10,000 - 100,000 t/y¹⁸.

It is predominantly used as an industrial solvent in the synthesis of fine chemicals (e.g. active pharmaceutical ingredients and crop protection ingredients) and in the production of polyurethane coated textiles, for example, artificial leather, rain and protection wear, footwear, medical mattress covers, surgical incise films etc. DMF is also used as a solvent in the production of synthetic fibers and in other applications such as the electronic industry, in formulation of mixtures, as gas stabiliser in acetone cylinders, in the production of medical devices, as cleaning solvent, as intermediate, as laboratory chemical, etc. (ECHA, 2014).

Only the uses as solvent in the production of chemicals, cleaning solvent, intermediate for the synthesis of other substances, formulation in industrial settings or as a laboratory chemical are intended in the EU according to information from registrations in ECHA's dissemination database¹⁹. Other uses of DMF should therefore not exist anymore in the EU, although it cannot be excluded in practice. The theoretically obsolete uses include any professional uses in non-industrial settings (except laboratories) exceeding 0.3 % in preparations (e.g. in paints, inks, adhesives, coatings, pesticides) and in particular any uses by the general population.

2.4 Existing EU classification and regulation of DMF

2.4.1 Harmonised classification and labelling

According to the harmonised classification and labelling (CLP Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008), DMF may damage the unborn child, is harmful in contact with skin, causes serious eye irritation and is harmful if inhaled (Table V.3).

Table V.3: Harmonised classification according to Annex VI of the EU Regulation (EC)

Classification		Labelling	
Hazard Class & Category code(s)	Hazard statement code(s)	Pictogram, Signal Word code(s)	Hazard statement code(s)
Repro 1B* Acute Tox 4** Eye irrit.2 Acute Tox 4**	H360D – May damage unborn child H312 – Harmful with contact with skin H319 – Causes serious eye irritation H332 – Harmful if inhaled	Danger GHS08 Exclamation mark	H360D H312 H319 H332

* "In order not to lose information from the harmonised classification for fertility and developmental effects under Directive 67/548/EEC, the classifications have been translated only for those effects classified under that Directive"

** "Manufacturers or importers must apply at least this minimum classification, but must classify in a more severe hazard category in the event that further information is available which shows that the hazard(s) meet the criteria for classification in the more severe category"

¹⁸ ECHA website: <https://echa.europa.eu/en/registration-dossier/-/registered-dossier/15093> accessed 31 March 2020

¹⁹ <https://echa.europa.eu/fr/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database/-/discli/details/2384> (accessed 27 January 2020)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 275

2.4.2 IARC classification

Until 2018, DMF was not classified as to its carcinogenicity to humans (Group 3) because of inadequate evidence in humans and evidence suggesting lack of carcinogenicity in animal studies (IARC, 1999).

However, in 2018, the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), in a recent assessment, concluded that DMF is probably carcinogenic (Group 2A) based on limited evidence in humans (with a positive association observed between DMF exposure and cancer of the testes) and sufficient evidence in experimental animal studies (IARC, 2018).

2.4.3 EU directives and regulations of DMF

2.4.3.1 REACH regulation

DMF is registered under REACH regulation (in the range of 10,000 – 100,000 t/y). Because it is toxic for reproduction, DMF is identified as a Substance of Very High Concern (SVHC)²⁰.

In 2019, the Risk Assessment Committee (RAC) and the Socio-economic Analysis Committee (SEAC) proposed in an opinion (ECHA, 2019) a restriction for DMF on its own or in mixtures in a concentration equal or greater than 0.3 % for DMF placed on the market or used for supply to the general public. For workers, a DNEL of 6 mg/m³ was derived for long-term inhalation exposure and a DNEL of 1.1 mg/kg bw/d for long-term dermal exposure (ECHA, 2019). Moreover, in its assessment, the RAC recommended to derive a DNEL_(biomarker) because DMF can be readily absorbed via exposed skin.

Furthermore, DMF is included in the priority list of chemicals developed within the EU-strategy for Endocrine Disruptors and placed in category 3 (no evidence of endocrine disrupting activity or no data available) and listed in Annex 13 (List of 146 substances with ED categorisation prepared in the Expert meeting)²¹.

2.4.3.2 OSH legislation

In 2006, the European Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limits (SCOEL, 2006) recommended occupational exposure limits (OEL) for DMF:

- 8h-TWA (time weighed average): 5 ppm (15 mg/m³)
- 15min-STEEL (short term exposure level): 10 ppm (30 mg/m³)
- Notation: 'skin'
- BLV (biological limit value): 15 mg N-methylformamide (NMF)/L urine (post-shift)²²

In 2009, the European Commission set the 8h-TWA and 15min-STEEL as indicative OEL values through the Directive 2009/161/EU²³. The "skin" notation is integrated in the document.

2.4.3.3 Other EU regulations

The Toy Safety Directive prohibits CMR substances under Annex II part 3, although exemptions may apply when the conditions laid down in Annex II part 3 are met. DMF is listed in Annex II (list of substances prohibited in cosmetic products - entry 355).

²⁰ ECHA website: <https://echa.europa.eu/en/substance-information/-/substanceinfo/100.000.617>, accessed 14-Oct-2020]

²¹ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/chemicals/endocrine/strategy/substances_en.htm

²² In the SCOEL document it is not indicated if it concerns total NMF, but according to analytical techniques available, it is expected to be.

²³ Commission Directive of 17 December 2009 establishing a third list of indicative occupational exposure limit values in implementation of Council Directive 98/24/EC and amending Commission Directive 2000/39/EC

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 276

DMF is used in the production of medicinal products and is therefore subject to the provisions of Directives 2001/83/EC on medicinal products for human use and 2001/82/EC on veterinary medicinal products, as well as those of Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 1252/2014 on principles and guidelines of good manufacturing practice for active substances for medicinal products for human use.

In the workplace, pregnant workers²⁴ and workers who have recently given birth or are breastfeeding, as well as young people (under 18 years) should not be exposed to DMF according to Directives 92/85/EEC and 94/33/EC respectively.

2.5 Human exposure to DMF

2.5.1 Environmental and consumers exposure

DMF is not found as a natural product. The environmental presence is due to industrial releases into the air (where it appears to be considerably more represented than in other environmental media). DMF in air is degraded and its half-life is estimated to be several days. DMF can also reach the aquatic environment and soil (during periods of rain) with a relatively rapid biodegradation half-life of 18 - 36 hours (IARC, 2018).

In river, lakes, and bays, DMF concentrations in 47 water samples ranged from undetected to 0.53 µg/L in Japan (Ministry of Japan 2012 quoted by IARC, 2018) (Annex 1).

In a study by Wang et al. (2014), the adverse health effects of DMF exposure for residents living near synthetic leather factories in China were investigated. Airborne concentrations of DMF ranged from 180 to 565 µg/m³. In the same region, but away from the factories, mean concentration in 366 samples was 98.3 µg/m³ (IARC, 2018).

2.5.2 Occupational exposure

Exposure to DMF mainly occurs by both inhalation and dermal contact. DMF exposure in the workplace has been assessed by both air monitoring and biomonitoring since 1970 (IARC, 2018). Metabolites of DMF were measured in several occupational studies in association with airborne DMF levels in the air of the workplace. Some authors showed differences in the excretion of metabolites according to the route of absorption (inhalation vs. inhalation+dermal route) (Yang et al., 2000). These data are described in Annex 1 of this chapter (Table V.9).

In a recent study by Kilo et al. (2016), biomonitoring values were on average distinctly lower than the values reported previously in the literature. According to the authors, this could indicate that industrial hygiene measures implementation has further improved and that DMF exposure has been reduced (Annex 1).

²⁴ According to the directive: pregnant worker shall mean a pregnant worker who informs her employer of her condition, in accordance with national legislation and / or national practice

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 277

3 Toxicological profile of DMF

3.1 Toxicokinetics

3.1.1 Absorption

DMF is readily absorbed via all exposure routes in humans and animals.

3.1.1.1 In humans

Inhalation route

In the study by Brugnone et al. (1980), DMF was determined every hour during the eight-hour work shift in the alveolar air of eight workers employed in an artificial leather factory, and the alveolar ventilation of each worker was measured for 10 minutes during the work shift. Under steady-state conditions, they reported that 64-83 % of the DMF absorbed by inhalation is retained in the alveoli resulting in the distribution throughout the organism via the systemic circulation. A study by Mráz and Nohová (1992a) reported >90 % retention in the respiratory tract in 10 volunteers exposed via inhalation for 8 hours at concentrations of 10, 30 and 60 mg/m³.

Dermal route

Studies have described rapid penetration of DMF through the skin. Mráz and Nohová (1992b) investigated percutaneous absorption in volunteers from liquid or vapours. Liquid DMF was rapidly absorbed through the skin at a mean rate of 9.4 mg/cm²/h after dipping one hand in pure DMF for 2-20 min. The period of exposure to DMF vapours (50 mg/m³) was 4h in an exposure chamber. Volunteers were wearing light cotton lab trousers and shirts with short sleeves, and a gas mask for the experiments with percutaneous-only exposure. Volunteers participating in the reference experiment had the same equipment except for the gas mask so that exposure took place both through respiration as well as the percutaneous route. Percutaneous absorption of DMF vapours was estimated to be 13 - 36 % of the total uptake in persons with low pulmonary ventilation (10 L/min), which is very close to the 13 - 39 % measured by Maxfield et al. (1975). Percutaneous absorption of DMF vapour depended strongly on ambient temperature and humidity. This was also shown in a study on 193 workers evaluating seasonal difference in DMF percutaneous absorption. Urinary DMF metabolites were higher in summer, attributed to increased percutaneous absorption resulting from increased amounts of water-soluble DMF absorbed through sweaty skin due to higher room temperature and humidity than in winter. Percutaneous absorption was found to be the principal route of exposure to DMF for workers wearing respiratory protection (Tsuda et al., 2014).

An earlier study concluded that, if no personal protective devices are used (no gloves, no barrier cream), the amount of DMF absorbed through the skin may be more than twice that absorbed by inhalation (Lauwerys et al., 1980). However, the difference between the absorption of DMF vapour through the skin and by inhalation was also evaluated in a study from Nomiyama et al. (2001). In this study, it was estimated that skin and lung absorption contributed for 40.4 % and 59.6 % of total absorption, respectively. Other cases of significant dermal absorption of DMF in workers without personal protective equipment were reported (Wrbitzky and Angerer, 1998, Yang et al., 2000).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 278

Oral route

No data have been found on oral absorption in humans.

3.1.1.2 In animals

Male and female cynomolgus monkeys were exposed to DMF at concentrations of 30, 100 or 500 ppm (90, 300 or 1500 mg/m³) by whole-body inhalation for 6 hours per day on 5 days per week for 13 weeks. DMF plasma values showed a 19-37-fold increase in male monkeys and even higher (35–54-fold) in females when the atmospheric concentrations increased fivefold (from 100 to 500 ppm) (Hundley et al., 1993b). In rats and mice, AUC values and peak plasma levels after a single exposure to 500 ppm were greater than the respective values in monkeys after a similar exposure (Hundley et al., 1993a).

In a study by Hurtt et al. (1991), cynomolgus monkeys were exposed either by head-only or whole-body inhalation to 500 ppm for 6 hours per day for 5 days per week over 2 weeks. This study showed that after the first and the tenth exposure, the plasma value in the monkeys exposed by whole-body inhalation was respectively three times and six times higher, indicating considerable absorption by non-inhalation routes.

Rapid absorption was observed in pregnant rats following a single oral dose of 100 mg/kg bw of radioactive [¹⁴C]-DMF, on gestation days 12 and 18 (Saillenfait et al., 1997). The radioactivity in plasma peaked within 1 hour after treatment.

In the study by Brand et al., (2006), rats were exposed to ethanol by a single drinking episode. Then the rats were euthanised and their skin were isolated for an in vitro assay. It was observed that the in vitro dermal absorption of DMF was significantly increased by ethanol exposure.

3.1.2 Distribution

3.1.2.1 In humans

DMF is distributed throughout the organism via the systemic circulation and its target organ is the liver (ACGIH, 2017).

3.1.2.2 In animals

Concentrations of DMF and its biotransformation product N-methylformamide (NMF) were measured in blood and in tissues of rats exposed to vapours of DMF (Lundberg et al., 1983). Both DMF and NMF were distributed quite uniformly in the different tissues, blood and kidneys usually having the highest concentrations. In another study with rats exposed by inhalation to DMF vapour, an assumption was made that the lungs might also be a potential target organ of DMF exposure (DuPont Co., 1990).

In some studies, it has been found that DMF is able to cross the placenta in pregnant rats after exposure by inhalation (Sheveleva et al., 1977; Shumilina, 1991, as cited in WHO, 2001). In the Saillenfait et al. (1997) study, levels of radioactivity in embryonic and fetal tissues were nearly the same as those in maternal plasma up to 8 and 24 hours, respectively, but were higher thereafter.

3.1.3 Metabolism

DMF is rapidly metabolised in the liver. N-hydroxymethyl-N-methylformamide (HMMF) arises from DMF mainly through enzymatic oxidation by the cytochrome P450 enzyme system (CYP2E1) (Mráz et al., 1993). Then, demethylation leads to the formation of NMF. The concentrations of HMMF and NMF in urine are grouped as total NMF (tNMF) due to thermal

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 279

decomposition of the hydroxyl derivatives in the injection port of the gas chromatograph (Scailteur et al., 1984; Kawai et al., 1992).

Another oxidative demethylation of NMF gives formamide with N-hydroxymethylformamide (HMF) as an intermediate. In addition, N-acetyl-S-(N-methylcarbamoyl)cysteine (AMCC) is another metabolite formed after exposure to DMF (Mráz and Tureček, 1987). AMCC is the end product of the enzymatic breakdown of S-(N-methylcarbamoyl)glutathione. The latter is formed by the reaction between glutathione and the possible reactive metabolic intermediate, methyl isocyanate (MIC) (Mráz and Nohová, 1992a; Mráz and Turecek, 1987). Unlike in rodents, AMCC is a major metabolite of DMF in humans (Mráz et al., 1989). (Figure V.1).

Furthermore, after DMF exposure, at the N-terminal position of the globin chains of hemoglobin, the adduct N-methylcarbamoylvaline (MCVal) is formed, which is also regarded as the reaction product of an intermediate methyl isocyanate (Angerer et al., 1998; Käfferlein et Angerer, 2001). A lysine adduct N ϵ -(N-methylcarbamoyl) lysine was also identified in globin samples of humans occupationally exposed to DMF (Mráz et al., 2006).

The metabolism of DMF has been reported to be saturable (Hundley et al., 1993a and 1993b; Greim et al., 1992).

The interactions of DMF with ethanol in the body were also studied. The volunteers, who received an oral administration of ethanol before being exposed to DMF vapors for 2 hours at concentrations of 50-80 ppm, excreted slightly elevated urine concentrations of unchanged DMF and had lower tNMF blood levels due to the inhibition of DMF metabolism (Eben and Kimmerle, 1976). In a study by the same authors, delayed metabolism of DMF was observed in rats and dogs after oral administration of 2 g/kg bw ethanol prior to inhalation. During repeated exposure and daily pretreatment with ethanol, the metabolism of DMF was also inhibited. However, the metabolism of ethanol seemed to be influenced by DMF. There is limited data showing that urinary levels of AMCC are more reduced compared to the concentration of tNMF after alcohol consumption due to the inhibition of DMF metabolism (Kim and Kim, 2011 as cited by ACGIH 2017).

Ethanol and probably acetaldehyde have been shown to inhibit the breakdown of DMF. Conversely, DMF inhibits the metabolism of ethanol. Ethanol is capable of inducing CYP2E1, which facilitates DMF initial hydroxylation (as reported in ECHA, 2019). DMF is also capable of inducing the expression of CYP2E1 in rats after intraperitoneal doses of 450, 900 and 1800 mg/kg bw/d for three days (Kim and Chung, 2013). In 1978, Chivers reported a case in which simultaneous exposures to DMF with alcohol consumption caused intolerance to alcohol, possibly resulting from the accumulation of acetaldehyde following the blocking of aldehyde dehydrogenase activity.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 280

Figure V.1: Metabolic pathways of DMF (Li et al., 2019)

3.1.4 Excretion

3.1.4.1 In humans

The hepatic biotransformation of DMF and the urinary excretion of its metabolites are the main elimination pathway of DMF. After exposure of 9 volunteers to 30 mg/m³ of DMF, tNMF accounted for about 22 % of the dose absorbed via the respiratory tract during an 8 hours exposure, while HMMF and AMCC accounted for about 13 % each and DMF about 0.3 % (Mràz and Nohovà, 1992a). HMMF was confirmed to be the most abundant urinary metabolite in humans (Sohn et al., 2005). There is no study result evaluating the pulmonary elimination. This can be due to strong adsorption of DMF on the walls of the measuring device (Mràz and Nohovà, 1992a).

According to the study by Mràz and Nohovà (1992a), the half-lives of urinary excretion for tNMF, formamide, and AMCC were respectively 4, 7 and 23 hours, after a single exposure to 30 mg DMF per m³. A small amount of unchanged urinary DMF was also detected with a half-life of excretion of 2 hours. After repeated exposure to DMF for 8 hours per day, at the same concentration of 30 mg/m³, for five consecutive days, a significant accumulation of AMCC was observed with the steady-state being reached on the fourth day.

A slower elimination, without significant accumulation over the workweek, was reported after skin exposure of volunteers to liquid DMF (Mràz et al., 1992b; Maxfield et al., 1975); an average half-life of 7 - 8 hours was reported for tNMF. Chang et al. (2005) described an increasing trend

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 281

of urinary tNMF over five consecutive days in a group of workers in a synthetic leather factory with a high dermal exposure, contrary to another group of workers in a copper laminate circuit board factory with a lower skin exposure. Therefore, Chang et al. hypothesise that there is a risk of accumulation in the case of repeated skin contact only. This could result from a cutaneous retention but this remain a weakly supported hypothesis relying on a single observation in which, in addition, the respiratory and skin exposures of workers producing synthetic leather are higher at the end of the week than at the beginning of the week. This is in contradiction with the results of a previous study by Lauwerys et al. (1980).

3.1.4.2 In animals

In monkeys exposed to 30, 100, or 500 ppm for 6 hours a day, 5 days a week over a 13-week period (whole-body), estimated plasma half-lives ranged from 1 to 2 hours for DMF and 4 to 15 hours for tNMF (Hundley et al., 1993). DMF was rapidly converted to NMF following 30 ppm exposures, with NMF plasma concentrations higher than DMF plasma concentrations at the 0.5-hour timepoint.

In the study by Saillenfait et al. (1997) who treated lactating rats with a single oral dose of 100 mg/kg bw [¹⁴C]-DMF on lactation day 14; DMF, HMMF and NMF were found in the milk at concentrations equal to those in the plasma. In addition, they noted that 60 - 70 % of the absorbed dose of [¹⁴C]-DMF was excreted in the urine and 3 - 4 % in the faeces.

3.2 Health effects of DMF

A detailed overview of the studies is provided e.g. by IARC (2018), the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA, 2019), the American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH, 2017 and 2018), the German Research Foundation (DFG, 2006 and 2019) and the Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limit Values (SCOEL, 2006).

3.2.1 Acute toxicity

3.2.1.1 In humans

The liver is the main target for toxicity after acute exposure to DMF.

Acute high dose exposure to DMF can damage the liver and even lead to death, but in most cases, the damage is reversible (Li et al., 2019). Several case studies reporting voluntary DMF intoxications via a veterinary euthanasia drug containing DMF as solvent (T-61®) showed effects on liver due to DMF exposure, in addition to effects of the active ingredients. Hepatotoxicity is generally observed 2-3 days after oral administration of the drug (Lelièvre et al., 2014).

Buylaert et al. (1996) reported hepatotoxic effects on patients before they were treated with therapeutic N-acetylcysteine. The study showed a transient increase in liver enzymes with a full recovery. In 2010, Hantson et al. observed mild signs of liver injury after attempted suicide in two veterinarians. Trevisani et al. (1993) described a case of acute hepatic failure following ingestion of the veterinarian euthanasia drug T-61. The authors observed, two days after a high dose (1.2 g/day) intravenous administration, acute liver failure with encephalopathy, jaundice, and a severe coagulopathy. They reported that a normalisation of all liver function tests was achieved within two months. They noted that these results stood in contrast to the previous cases for which the intoxication inducing hepatic failure was lethal (Trevisani et al., 1993). Moreover, a patient developed fulminant hepatic failure 48 h after the ingestion of T-61 due to the high dose (0.6 ml/kg) oral ingestion of DMF (Nicolas et al., 1990).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 282

In addition, case studies have been published describing effects from occupational acute exposure to DMF.

For example, Lei et al. (2017) presented a case of acute hepatic failure following exposure to a toxic dose of DMF via inhalation and skin absorption. The authors added that the factory was shut down after it was found that the atmospheric DMF air concentration was 2 to 3fold above the national standard (i.e. 20 mg/m³). The patient, who worked in the synthetic leather factory that manufactured belts using DMF as solvent, presented common clinical symptoms of DMF poisoning (fatigue, poor appetite, abdominal distention, nausea, and jaundice). He recovered following artificial liver support therapy and pharmacological agents to protect the liver. However, acute hepatic failure is generally associated with high mortality (Liu et al., 2014; Ding et al., 2011; Tong et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2015). Lei et al. (2017) noted that the severity of liver damage induced by DMF is directly associated with the exposure dosage and duration.

3.2.1.2 In animals

ECHA concluded that DMF has a low acute toxicity in animals (Table V.4). As for humans, the main target organ is the liver.

Table V.4: Acute toxicity of DMF in animals

Route	Species	LD50 or LC50	Observations	References
Oral	Rats (male and female)	LD50: 3010 mg/kg bw/d [95 % confidence interval: 2 480 – 3 650]	Discolored livers were seen. in every animal	ECHA website (registration ²⁵ dossier) (consulted in January 2020)
Oral	Mice	LD50: 6019 mg/kg bw/day	Intoxication symptoms: torpidity, ataxia, cyanosis, convulsion, dyspnea, + plasma AST, ALT and LDH increased.	Kennedy et al., 2012
Dermal	Rats (male and female)	LD50> 3160 mg/kg bw/d	Duration of observation period following administration: 14 days 1/4 animals died (1 male) on day 4 of the observation period, however, gross necropsy revealed no substance related effect. Among the remaining animals, no signs of systemic toxicity or percutaneous absorption were observed.	ECHA website (registration dossier) ²⁶ (consulted in January 2020)
Inhalation	Rats (male and female)	LC50> 5900 mg/m ³ Exposure: 4 hours Animals observed for 14 days	5.1 mg/l: all animals survived 5.85 mg/l: 3/10 males and no female animal died. The surviving animals recovered 6 -7 days after exposure. These animals did not show any gross lesions at necropsy, whereas the animals that died during the study had some organ findings, e.g. discoloration of the liver, hemorrhage in thymus and punctate hemorrhage in pancreas and in the gastric mucous membrane.	ECHA website (registration dossier) ²⁷ (consulted in January 2020)

²⁵ <https://echa.europa.eu/fr/registration-dossier/-/registered-dossier/15093/7/3/2>

²⁶ <https://echa.europa.eu/fr/registration-dossier/-/registered-dossier/15093/7/3/4>

²⁷ <https://echa.europa.eu/fr/registration-dossier/-/registered-dossier/15093/7/3/3>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 283

According to Kennedy et al. (2012), the higher metabolic capacity of mice made this species more responsive to DMF than rats. They noted that in mice a single dose of DMF lead to liver necrosis and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) activity increase, whereas in rats there was no hepatic damage or elevation of plasma transaminases. According to the authors (based on a study by Chieli et al. 1995), this can be explained in part by the higher enzymatic affinity of mouse CYP 2E1.

3.2.2 Skin, eye and respiratory tract irritation

3.2.2.1 In humans

Garnier et al. (1992) reported 30 cases of DMF poisoning at the workplace. Effects such as chemical burns of the skin and eyes were described. The American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH, 2018) reports a study from Tomasini et al. (1983) were 14 workers of a synthetic leather factory, exposed to DMF (approximately 10 ppm, up to 20 ppm), suffered from eye and upper airway irritation.

3.2.2.2 In animals

Lynch et al. (2003) observed mild irritation in rats exposed to 400 and 800 ppm (6h/day, 5 days/week for 13 weeks), as evidenced by occasional nasal and ocular discharges.

In 1986, Kennedy and Sherman (1986) exposed rabbits to a direct instillation of 0.1 ml undiluted DMF in the conjunctival sac of the eye and observed a moderate eye irritation with the corneal response clearing in 2 to 4 weeks. In the same study, the authors exposed male mice to 0, 55, 154, 550, 1658 or 2100 ppm DMF by inhalation during 10 min (head only) and observed reduced respiratory rates at 1658 and 2100 ppm (Kennedy and Sherman, 1986, as reported by ACGIH, 2018).

3.2.3 Chronic toxicity

3.2.3.1 Effects on liver, gastro-intestinal effects, alcohol intolerance

In humans

DMF exposure is known to induce hepatotoxicity as the main effect in several occupational studies. He et al. (2010) observed that DMF could trigger acute toxic hepatitis but also chronic hepatic damage such as hepatic cirrhosis. More recently, Wu et al. (2017) reported that the most common liver diseases in DMF-exposed workers include hepatitis, fibrosis, and cirrhosis. Moreover, chronic toxicity is characterised by various reactions including alcohol flush reaction, gastrointestinal disturbances, nausea and headache (Kilo et al., 2016).

Occupational studies reporting chronic effects are described in Annex 2, Table V.12. DMF exposure is mostly assessed via airborne DMF measures and via biomonitoring (mainly tNMF in urine and AMCC and less often MCV_{al} in blood). External exposure is not always consistently associated with the occurrence of health effects (He et al., 2010). In Table V.11 (Annex 2), levels of DMF metabolites are described in regards with health effects (increased levels of serum hepatic enzymes, antabuse and gastrointestinal effects).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 284

Effects on liver

The mechanism by which DMF induces hepatotoxicity remains unknown. In their review (Li et al. 2019) provide some hypotheses such as depletion of GSH after having formed adducts with MIC, oxidative stress, involvement of caspase-mediated apoptosis, disturbance of cellular Ca²⁺ homeostasis, alteration of gut microbiota, etc. as summarised in Figure V.2.

Figure V.2: Scheme for the possible mechanisms of the hepatotoxicity induced by DMF (Li et al. 2019)

Liver enzymes are released from impaired or damaged cells. Enzymes located inside (i.e. gamma-glutamyltransferase, γ GT) or near (i.e. alanine aminotransferase, ALT) the cell membrane are released earlier in the course of liver cell damage whereas enzymes located for example in the mitochondria (i.e. aspartate aminotransferase, AST) are liberated when the damage is more severe (Kilo et al., 2016).

According to the MAK commission (DFG, 2006), an increase of the transaminases AST and ALT in serum is a suitable parameter for detecting DMF-induced effects on the liver.

Many authors investigated liver function via serum liver enzyme concentrations (AST, ALT and γ GT), or subjective symptoms, and clinical signs (palpable liver) in workers exposed to DMF. The results are consistent across occupational studies, with increases in serum hepatic enzymes observed at concentrations less than 10 ppm (Catenacci et al., 1984; Lauwerys et al., 1980; Yonemoto and Suzuki, 1980; Qi et al., 2017; Cai et al., 1992; Sakai et al., 1995; He et al., 2015).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 285

Some authors considered confounding factors e.g. alcohol consumption (based on questionnaires, in almost all cases). Workers who did not consume alcohol tolerated much higher concentrations of DMF without changes in liver functions (Wrbitzky and Angerer, 1998; Wrbitzky, 1999).

In Lauwerys et al. (1980), the authors measured tNMF concentrations in urine and concluded that there was no effect on liver enzyme concentrations in workers at 40-50 mg/g creatinine (cr) during a working week of five consecutive days. The authors underlined that in the factory, the selection criteria (not precised) at the beginning of employment were rather severe and can lead to a recruitment bias in which results may not reflect responses in other workers (ACGIH, 2017).

Fiorito et al. (1997) reported a geometric mean tNMF of 13.6 mg/l urine in 22 workers who had a significant increase in liver enzyme concentration. SCOEL (2006) and ACGIH (2017) considered that this concentration may be underestimated because of the analytical method used for measuring tNMF. Two studies by Wrbitzky and Angerer (1998) and Wrbitzky (1999) conducted on the same cohort (126 workers) showed that a concentration of tNMF of less than 9.4 mg/l did not lead to an increase in liver enzymes in serum. In the recent study of Kilo et al. (2017), the authors measured liver enzymes and the levels of three metabolites (tNMF, AMCC in urine and MCVaI in blood). They presented mean and median values for concentrations of each metabolite at which they did not find any effect on liver enzymes. The means were around 8 mg/l, 9 mg/g cr and 80 nmol/g globin, for respectively tNMF and AMCC in urine and MCVaI in blood, and the medians were around 5 mg/l, 5 mg/g cr and 60 nmol/g globin.

Some studies conducted on Asian people reported values for the main metabolites linked to effects on liver. Sakai et al. (1995) measured serum liver enzymes (AST, ALT, AP) and tNMF and AMCC in urine in 10 workers for 3 years. The authors reported no effects on enzyme levels at or below 25 mg/g cr for tNMF and 22 mg/g cr for AMCC in urine (mean values over 3 years). In contrast to almost all other studies, Sakai et al. did not describe any data on alcohol behavior or interaction with the consumption of alcohol. He et al. (2010) also reported concentrations of the two metabolites for which they observed increased hepatic enzymes (ALT, AST, γ GT) in serum. For tNMF, when workers were divided into two groups (< and > 15 mg tNMF/g cr) the authors reported no statistically significant differences between groups in liver function. The results showed that an average level of 26.5 mg tNMF/g cr does not cause effects on liver. For AMCC, when workers are divided into two groups (< and >40 mg AMCC/g cr), He et al., (2010) reported a statistical difference between groups in the proportion of workers with abnormal values of liver enzymes. They also reported effects on liver in workers with an average concentration of 25.35 mg AMCC/g cr.

Recently, Wu et al. (2017) concluded that there was a good dose-response relationship between median tNMF, AMCC, and MCVaI concentrations and liver injury rates. The authors also noted that male workers had significantly higher liver injuries than female (i.e. 4 - 5-fold increased prevalence), and suggested that this may be due to higher DMF exposure in male workers. Wu et al. concluded that tNMF correlates the best with liver injury, while MCVaI may be the most stable indicator because of its longer half-life. They calculated a Benchmark Dose (BMD) with a Benchmark Response (BMR) of 10 % above the adverse response rate of liver injury seen in the control group. Median values of tNMF and AMCC in urine and MCVaI in blood in DMF-exposed workers were 4.43 mg/l, 4.84 mg/L, and 60.5 nmol/g globin, respectively, while all three DMF biomarkers were undetectable in non DMF-exposed workers.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 286

Alcohol intolerance reactions

Exposure to DMF in combination with subsequent alcohol consumption can induce an alcohol intolerance reaction (with flushing of the facial skin and arms) which results from the accumulation of acetaldehyde following the inhibition of aldehyde dehydrogenase (Lyle et al., 1979; DFG, 2006). Alcohol intolerance has been observed in both rat and human (Lyle et al., 1979; Hanasono et al. 1977).

In occupational studies, Antabuse-induced symptoms of alcohol intolerance²⁸, in combination with exposure to DMF, have been studied. Authors reported that these effects generally occur at DMF exposure levels less than or equal to those at which effects on the liver (increased liver enzymes) occurred (Lauwerys et al., 1980; Kilo et al. 2016).

According to Kilo et al. (2017), since the liver is also the main target for toxic effects of alcohol, it is important to distinguish between alcohol-related and DMF-related hepatic effects. The authors used the non-oxidative direct ethanol metabolites ethylglucuronide (EtG) and ethylsulfate (EtS) as markers to assess regular alcohol consumption (other authors usually used questionnaires). They observed signs of alcohol intolerance (flush reaction) in almost half of the workers at 4.43 mg/l, 4.84 mg/l, and 60.5 nmol/g globin for respectively tNMF, AMCC and MCVal.

Wolff (1972) reported that 83 % of East Asian subjects (Japanese, Taiwanese and Koreans), after drinking small amounts of alcohol, responded with a marked visible facial flushing. In contrast, only one of 34 Caucasian subjects (3 %) showed visible flushing. Thus, Antabuse effects reported in occupational studies have to be interpreted in the light of the differences in alcohol sensitivity (based on genetic polymorphisms of the enzymes alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase) (Chan, 1986).

Gastro-intestinal disease

Several studies have reported DMF-related disorders of the digestive system; the symptoms included abdominal pain, anorexia, and jaundice, as well as nausea, vomiting, and diarrhea (WHO, 2010).

In the general population residing near synthetic factories, Wang et al. (2014) looked at the increase in hospitalisation for total digestive system diseases, liver disease, and gastrointestinal tract disease as a result of consistent exposure to low levels of DMF in the air. They noted that women were more vulnerable than men. Moreover, the authors reported a significant association between DMF exposure and liver disease hospitalisation, but not for gastro-intestinal disease.

In occupational studies, authors reported DMF-related effects on the gastro-intestinal tract. Cai et al. (1992), found a dose-dependent increase in subjective symptoms, especially during work, and in digestive system-related symptoms such as nausea and abdominal pain in the past 3-month period with DMF exposure of up to 7 ppm.

In the study by Fiorito et al. (1997), a high percentage of workers (50 %) reported gastro-intestinal symptoms (stomach pain, nausea, loss of appetite) at a DMF airborne level of 20 mg/m³ (6.7 ppm). Kilo et al. (2016) reported only loss of appetite in DMF exposed workers at a DMF airborne level about 6 mg/m³ (2 ppm).

²⁸ Antabuse (disulfiram) inhibits acetaldehyde dehydrogenase, producing very unpleasant acetaldehyde-induced side effects (such as fast heartbeat, chest pain, nausea, dizziness, flushing, and thirst) when combined with alcohol in the body

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 287

In animals

As in humans, the main effects of DMF exposure reported in animals are observed in liver (e.g. hepatocellular necrosis, increased absolute and relative liver weights, and hepatic enzyme elevations) (see Annex 2). Senoh et al. (2004) found that inhalation exposures to DMF on rats or mice (both sexes), induce adverse effects on the liver but no other organs were histopathologically affected.

Malley et al. (1994) published a study on 696 rats and 624 mice exposed to 0, 25, 100 or 400 ppm DMF for 6h per day and 5 days/week (for 18 months in rats and 2 years in mice). In rats, DMF increased relative liver weights, centrilobular hepatocellular hypertrophy, lipofuscin/hemosiderin accumulation in Kupffer cells at 100 and 400 ppm, and centrilobular single cell necrosis only at 400 ppm. In mice, DMF increased liver weights at 100 ppm in males and 400 ppm for both sexes and centrilobular hepatocellular hypertrophy, accumulation of lipofuscin/hemosiderin in Kupffer cells and centrilobular single cell necrosis in all exposure groups. As reported by the authors in the study, the no-observed effect level (NOEL) in rats was 25 ppm based on body weight changes, clinical chemistry changes and hepatotoxic effects.

Senoh et al. (2004) studied DMF exposure in rats and mice during 2 weeks and 13 weeks. The authors concluded that increased relative liver weight and hepatocellular hypertrophy are more sensitive, biologically significant and relevant to worker's health. They reported significantly increased relative liver weight in rats (both sexes) at 1600 ppm, in male mice at 400 ppm and in female mice at 200 ppm, after 2 weeks. The authors calculated a BMD_{10L90} of 1 ppm for the relative liver weight and of 17 ppm for the incidence of hepatocellular hypertrophy in the 13-week study (see Table V.13, Annex 2).

Lynch et al. (2003), exposed female and male rats and mice to DMF (whole body inhalation exposure) for 13 weeks (6 hours a day, 5d/week) at concentrations of 0, 50, 100, 200, 400 or 800 ppm, and evaluated histopathology (liver), sperm morphology, vaginal cytology (in both species) and cardiovascular and renal function in rats. The liver was the only target organ identified; no changes were observed in any other organs or tissues. Microscopic liver lesions occurred in both sexes at doses higher than 200 ppm. In female mice, the NOAEL was 50 ppm upon the absence of microscopic liver lesions, while in male, effects (centrilobular hepatocellular hypertrophy and increased liver weights) were reported at all concentrations, i.e. LOAEL was 50 ppm.

3.2.4 Genotoxicity

The evidence that DMF is genotoxic is considered as moderate (IARC, 2018). Chromosomal and DNA damage have been observed in several studies in occupationally exposed humans, but results were considered as equivocal. The results of studies of genotoxicity in various experimental systems *in vivo* and *in vitro* were mostly negative or inconclusive.

3.2.4.1 In humans

IARC (2018) reviewed an extensive body of data to assess the genotoxicity of DMF:

Hennebrüder and Angerer (2005) analysed urine samples from male workers exposed to DMF vapours; DNA adducts such as N⁴-(N-methylcarbamoyl)cytosine were detected in 10 of 32 occupationally exposed workers and not in unexposed subjects.

Chen (2004) reported significantly more DNA damage (strand breaks measured by comet assay) in workers occupationally exposed to DMF for 6 to 7 years than in controls.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 288

The potential of DMF to induce DNA damage was also studied by Shieh et al. (2007). In blood leukocytes, changes (deletion in mitochondrial DNA and in mitochondrial DNA copy numbers) in 13 male synthetic-leather factory workers were significantly higher in DMF-exposed subjects than in controls. Changes were apparently exposure-dependent, based on comparison of subjects exposed to concentrations higher and lower than 10 ppm.

Seiji et al. (1992) reported positive results for chromosomal damage. Rates of sister-chromatid exchange were determined in peripheral blood lymphocytes of 22 non-smoking women exposed to DMF when working in a synthetic-leather manufacturing plant for 1.1 to 9.9 years. The exposure group was divided into 3 subgroups according to the exposure levels: low, intermediate and high. A co-exposure to low concentrations of toluene (0.9 ppm) was reported for the intermediate exposure group. However, the authors concluded that it appeared unlikely that toluene plays any significant role in inducing sister-chromatid exchange rates among the workers studied. A dose-dependent increase in sister-chromatid exchanges was seen in the intermediate and high exposure groups. However, the mean sister-chromatid exchange rate value in the low exposure subgroup was lower than that in controls.

Increases in chromosomal aberrations were also found in two other field studies in humans exposed to DMF (Major et al., 1998; Koudela and Spazier, 1981). Major et al. (1998) also reported increases in aneuploidy, sister-chromatid exchange and unscheduled DNA synthesis. Nevertheless, the IARC working group noted that the genotoxic effects observed in the Major et al. study may not be related to DMF because of co-exposure with high concentrations of acrylonitrile. In the Koudela and Spazier (1981) study, the IARC working group also noted that no data on smoking and co-exposure with other chemicals at the workplace were available.

In a study by Cheng et al. (1999), DMF exposure did not alter the frequency of sister chromatid exchanges in exposed workers. However, no unexposed control group was used and the exposure history of the subjects was not reported.

3.2.4.2 In human cells in vitro

In 2018, the IARC working group also reviewed data in human cells *in vitro*:

DMF gave negative results in an unscheduled DNA synthesis assay in human hepatocytes (McQueen et al., 1988) as well as in the GreenScreen HC GADD45 α -GFP genotoxicity assay performed by Hastwell et al. (2006). In addition, Antoine et al. (1983) did not observe an increase in the frequency of sister-chromatid exchange in human lymphocytes incubated *in vitro* with DMF.

Positive results were reported for double-strand breaks in human liver cell DNA treated with DMF with use of phosphorylated histone H2AX (γ H2AX) as a biomarker (Xuan et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2015). Wang et al. (2015) also observed an increase in DNA damage following an increase in 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine (a biomarker of oxidative DNA damage) detected by ELISA in human liver cells exposed to DMF *in vitro*.

3.2.4.3 In animals and experimental systems

In 1999, IARC comprehensively reviewed genotoxicity data *in vitro* and *in vivo* available at the time.

More recent *in vitro* studies have shown predominantly negative results. Xing et al. (2014) exposed rats by gavage once per day to 50, 100 and 200 mg/kg bw of DMF for 14 consecutive days. This study showed positive results for DNA strand breaks with a comet assay in lymphocytes showing significantly increased comet tail, average tail length and tail moment. However, an RAD54-GFP assay performed on yeast by Knight et al. (2007) gave negative

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 289

results for DNA damage for concentrations of DMF up to 257 mM. Moreover, DMF was not mutagenic in the *umu*-test on *Salmonella typhimurium* TA1535 (Degirmenci et al., 2000).

Midorikawa et al. (2000) studied the combined action of DMF at a concentration of 0.5 to 4 % and hydrogen peroxide at 50 µM in the presence of copper (Cu(II)) at 20µM. DNA strand breaks and 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine were enhanced by DMF.

Moreover, formaldehyde and MIC (products of DMF metabolism), can cause chromosomal damage (Goswami, 1986; Tice et al., 1987; IARC, 2006).

3.2.5 Carcinogenicity

According to IARC (2018), there is sufficient evidence of carcinogenicity for the DMF in experimental animals.

However, neoplastic lesions in available animal studies were only located in the liver and not in the testes as suggested in human studies. Moreover, no increased risk of developing hepatic tumors has been shown in humans. There is insufficient (only moderate) evidence that DMF is genotoxic. Therefore, it could not be ruled out that the carcinogenicity observed in animals results from the hepatotoxicity of DMF with a dose threshold effect.

Nevertheless, despite this consideration and reporting limited evidence in human studies, the IARC working group classified DMF in group 2A, probably carcinogenic to humans.

3.2.5.1 In humans

The article by Ducatman et al. (1986) suggested but did not prove the hypothesis of an association between repeated DMF exposure and the development of testicular cancer. The authors reported a cluster of three cases of cancer of the testis among 153 aircraft-repair workers in the USA. These cases were exposed to a mixture of chemicals including DMF. The article also describes a cluster of four cases of cancer of the testes among 680 men in a further study in another aircraft-repair facility with a history of extended exposure to DMF together with other substances, while no case of testicular tumor was detected among workers without exposure to DMF in the same facility.

Levin et al. (1987) also reported a cluster of three cases of testicular cancers in a leather tannery using DMF and many other chemical substances, after long-term exposure. A team including personnel from the United States National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) conducted a standardised incidence ratio study (SIR) of a cohort of 80 workers at the tannery. The incidence of testis cancer (n=3/80) was compared with the expected value determined with the data of the New York State cancer registry. The resulting standardised incidence ratio (40.5 (95 % CI, 8.1–118.4) was significantly increased (CDC, 1989). However, no additional cancers were reported in a screening effort to identify additional testicular cancers in 51 of the 83 workers at the leather tannery where the three cases were reported. This investigation confirmed an excess of testicular cancer at a tannery (Calvert et al., 1990).

A subsequent case-control study in the county of this tannery found seven other cases of testis cancers. Five of these ten cases had a history of leather-related employment (CDC, 1989).

In addition, a retrospective cohort study studying cancer incidence and cancer mortality in workers from a US acrylic-fibre factory (Chen et al., 1988a; 1988b), and a subsequent case-control study including that factory and three others (Walrath et al., 1989), all of which using DMF and other chemicals, reported 11 cases with testis cancer of which three were exposed to DMF. No statistical excess in cases was observed.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 290

The IARC working group (2018) reported that there was a positive association between exposure to DMF and cancer of the testis from the data on aircraft-repair and leather workers, but chance and confounding by other occupational exposures could not be ruled out. Therefore, the working group concluded that there is limited evidence in humans for the carcinogenicity of DMF.

3.2.5.2 In animals

In a study by Malley et al. (1994), rats and mice were exposed by inhalation to DMF for 6 hours per day, 5 days per week for 18 months (mice) or 2 years (rats) at 0, 25, 100, or 400 ppm. DMF induced hepatic toxicity as previously reported but did not produce any oncogenic response in either species.

In a whole-body inhalation study by Senoh et al. (2004), groups of 50 rats and mice of both sexes were exposed to 0, 200, 400 or 800 ppm DMF for 6 hours a day, 5 days per week for 2 years. This study, conducted in compliance with Good Laboratory Practice (GLP), reported multiple hepatocellular tumors in the treated rats and mice.

In rats, there were significantly increased incidences of hepatocellular adenomas at 400 and 800 ppm, and of carcinomas at 800 ppm. Hepatocellular adenomas were not increased significantly in females at 400 ppm, but their incidence exceeded the range of historical control data in the Japan Bioassay Research Center (JBRC). In mice, hepatocellular adenoma and carcinoma incidences were significantly increased in all groups exposed to DMF. Incidence of hepatoblastomas significantly increased in the 200 and 400 ppm-exposed male mice, and 4 cases of hepatoblastomas in the 400 ppm-exposed female mice and the 800 ppm-exposed male mice exceeded the range of historical control data of the JBRC

Moreover, incidences of altered cell foci increased concentration-relatedly in the liver of exposed rats and mice, and these foci were considered causally related to the hepatocellular tumors. Liver weights increased in both rats and mice exposed to DMF at 200 ppm and above. In addition, increased levels of γ -glutamyltransferase, ALT, AST and total bilirubin in exposed rats of both sexes and AST and ALT in exposed mice of both sexes were noted.

Except for the liver, no DMF related neoplastic or non-neoplastic lesions were found.

Ohbayashi et al. (2009) exposed a group of 50 male rats by inhalation to 0, 200 or 400 ppm of DMF (6h/day and 5 days per week during 104 weeks), or via drinking water (0, 800 or 1600 ppm) *ad libitum*, or both. The authors observed a significant increase in the incidences of hepatocellular adenomas and carcinomas as well as their combined incidences, when compared to the untreated control group or each of the inhalation-alone and oral-alone groups. The incidences of hepatocellular adenomas and carcinomas induced by the combined exposures were greater than the sum of the two incidences induced by the single route exposures (inhalation and ingestion).

Therefore, according to Ohbayashi et al. (2009) combined inhalation and oral exposure enhances the incidence (and malignancy) of hepatocellular tumors and may suggest a possible synergistic effect.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 291

3.2.6 Reproductive and developmental effects

DMF is a known reproductive toxicant and classified as toxic for reproduction 1B under CLP regulation. This has been demonstrated by numerous studies in rodents, but less data is available in humans.

3.2.6.1 In humans

The study by Chang et al. (2004b) on 12 workers in a synthetic leather factory exposed to DMF showed that workers had a reduction in sperm mobility compared to the 8 controls. This decrease was proportional to the urinary tNMF concentration but not to the concentration of DMF in the air. However, taking into account the small group size of only 12 workers, and the fact that the number of exposed persons who consumed alcohol (8/12; 66.7 %) was significantly above that of the control persons (3/8; 37.5 %), the finding needs to be confirmed in further investigations.

3.3.6.2 In animals

Animal studies reporting reproductive and developmental effects are described in the Table V.5 below.

Table V.5: Results of animal studies for reproductive and developmental effects due to DMF (adopted from ECHA, 2019, Annex to background document)

Reference	Species and population	DMF concentration & exposure duration	Results
Oral			
Fail et al. 1998 Two generation study	Mice: 20 pregnant females / dose group.	1000, 4000, 7000 ppm (ca. 219, 820 and 1455 mg/kg/d) <i>via</i> drinking water Continuous breeding protocol up to 21 day of lactation phase of F1 animals	NOAEL for fertility (F0, F1) and developmental toxicity (F1): 219 mg/kg bw/d <u>7000 ppm (1455 mg/kg bw/d) and 4000 ppm (820 mg/kg bw/d):</u> Dams F0: liver weights ↑, fertility ↓, BW ↓, FC ↓, Litter size ↓, estrous cycle ↑ Foetuses F1: liver weights ↑, malformations ↑ (external, craniofacial and sternebral), BW ↓, estrous cycle length ↑, relative prostate weight ↓, spermatozoa concentration ↓, mating index ↓, pregnancy index ↓. Foetuses F2: malformations ↑ (external, craniofacial and sternebral); BW ↓, <u>1000 ppm (219 mg/kg bw/d):</u> Dams F0: liver weights ↑ Foetuses F1: liver weights ↑ Foetuses F2: malformations ↑ (external, craniofacial and sternebral); BW ↓
Hellwig et al. 1991 Developmental study	Rats: 19 untreated control, 23 pregnant females/dose group.	166, 503 and 1510 mg/kg bw/d by gavage. GD 6 - 15 for 6 hours/day	NOAEL for maternal, embryo/foetotoxicity and teratogenicity: 166 mg/kg bw/d <u>503 and 1510 mg/kg bw/d:</u> Dams: one animal dead (1510 mg/kg bw), BW ↓, resorptions ↑ Foetuses: BW ↓, skeletal malformations, variations, retardations ↑ <u>166 mg/kg bw/d:</u> Dams: no maternal effects, resorptions ↑ (slightly) Foetuses: placental weight ↓ (slightly)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 292

Reference	Species and population	DMF concentration & exposure duration	Results
	Mice: 23 untreated control, 24 treated pregnant females/dose	182 and 548 mg/kg bw/d by gavage. GD 6 - 15 for 6 hours/day	LOAEL for maternal, embryo/foetotoxicity and teratogenicity: 182 mg/kg bw/d <u>548 mg/kg bw/d:</u> Dams: no maternal effects; liveborn foetuses ↓ Foetuses: BW↓, retardations and variations ↑, skeletal malformations ↑ <u>182 mg/kg bw/d:</u> Dams: no maternal effects; liveborn foetuses ↓ Foetuses: BW ↓, retardations and variations ↑, skeletal malformations ↑ (slightly)
Saillenfait et al. 1997 Developmental study	Rats: 22-24 pregnant females/group	50, 100, 200, 300 mg/kg bw/d by gavage GD: 6 - 20	NOAEL for maternal toxicity and embryo/fetotoxicity: 50 mg/kg bw/d NOAEL for teratogenicity: 300 mg/kg bw/d <u>100, 200, and 300 mg/kg bw/d:</u> Dams: BWG ↓, FC ↓ Foetuses: BW↓, single occurrence of external and visceral malformations. No specific pattern of malformations; incidence of two skeletal variations ↑ <u>50 mg/kg bw/d</u> Dams: no effects Foetuses: no effects; skeletal variations ↑ (not statistically significant)
Merkle and Zeller, 1980 Developmental study	Rabbits: 24, 12, 18, and 11 females for untreated control, low, mid, and high dose group, respectively.	46.4, 68.1 and 200 µL/kg bw/d (about 44.1, 65 and 190 mg/kg bw/d) by gavage. GD: 6 - 18	NOAEL for maternal toxicity and embryo/fetotoxicity: 65 mg/kg bw/d NOAEL for teratogenicity: 44.1 mg/kg bw/d <u>190 mg/kg bw/d</u> Dams: BW ↓, BWG ↓, FC ↓, abortion↑ Foetuses: BW↓, placental weight ↓, malformations ↑ <u>65 mg/kg bw/d:</u> Dams: no maternal effects, FC ↓ (slightly) Foetuses: skeletal malformations ↑ (slightly)
Inhalation			
Hellwig et al. (1991) Developmental study	Rabbits: 15 females / dose group	50, 150 and 450 ppm (150, 450 and 1360 mg/m ³) by vapour inhalation (whole body) GD: 7 - 19 for 6 hours/day	NOAEL for maternal toxicity, embryo/fetotoxicity and teratogenicity: 50 ppm (ca. 150mg/m ³). <u>450 ppm (1360 mg/m³):</u> Dams: BW ↓ (d 7-10), BWG↓, no clinical signs Foetuses: BW↓, malformations (external, skeletal, visceral)↑ <u>150 ppm (450 mg/m³):</u> Dams: BW static, no clinical signs Foetuses: one foetus with hernia umbilicalis, sternal variations ↑ <u>50 ppm (150 mg/m³):</u> Dams: BW↑, no clinical signs Foetuses: no effects

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 293

Reference	Species and population	DMF concentration & exposure duration	Results
	Rats: 30 pregnant females / dose group	0 or 287 ppm by vapour inhalation (whole body) Experiment I: exposure on GD 0-1, 4-8, 11-15 and 18-19 for 6 hours/day Experiment II: exposure on GD 0-3, 6-10, and 11-18 for 6 hours/day.	No NOAEC established (LOAEC =287 ppm based on foetotoxicity and embryoletality) <u>287 ppm:</u> Dams: BW↓, early resorptions ↑, dead implantations ↑ Foetuses: BW↓, variations ↑, retardations ↑
TSCATS: OTS 0516779 (1978) Developmental study	Rats: 21 pregnant females / dose group	30 or 300 ppm (90 and 910 mg/m ³) by inhalation GD 6 - 15 for 6 hours/day	NOAEC for maternal toxicity and fetotoxicity: 30 ppm (90 mg/m ³) NOAEC for teratogenicity: 300 ppm (910 mg/m ³) <u>300 ppm:</u> Dams: BWG↓ (GD 5-16) Foetuses: BW↓, ossification variations ↑ <u>30 ppm:</u> Dams: no treatment related effects Foetuses: no treatment related effects
Kimmerle and Machemer (1975) Developmental study	Rats: 22-23 females / dose group	18 or 172 ppm (about 55 and 520 mg/m ³) by inhalation GD 6 - 15 for 6 hours/day	NOAEC for maternal toxicity and teratogenicity: 172 ppm (520 mg/m ³) NOAEC for fetotoxicity: 18 ppm (55 mg/m ³) <u>172 ppm:</u> Dams: no signs of maternal toxicity Foetuses: BW↓
Dermal			
Hellwig et al. (1991) Developmental study	Rabbits: 15 females / dose group	100, 200 and 400 mg/kg bw/d Application on shaved area of dorsal skin: semi-occlusive GD 6 - 18 for 6 hours	No NOAEL could be established. LOAEL for maternal, embryo/foetotoxicity and teratogenicity: 100 mg/kg bw/d <u>400 mg/kg bw/d:</u> Dams: significant skin irritation, BWG↓ (GD 16-18), preimplantation losses (not significant) Foetuses: BW not affected, skeletal and visceral malformations ↑ <u>200 mg/kg bw/d:</u> Dams: no treatment related effects Foetuses: no treatment related effects <u>100 mg/kg bw/d</u> Foetuses: sternal malformation and gall bladder agenesis
	Rats: 21-22 females / dose group	94, 472 and 944 mg/kg bw Application on a clipped dorsal area: open epicutaneous system GD 6 - 10, 13-15 for 3 hours /day	No NOAEL could be established <u>944 mg/kg bw:</u> Dams: BWG↓ (GD 0-15), placental weights↓ Foetuses: BW not affected, foetal lengths ↓, skeletal and visceral malformations ↑, variations and retardations↑ <u>472 and 94 mg/kg bw:</u> Dams: placental weights↓ Foetuses: foetal lengths ↓ (not significant), variations and retardations↑

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 294

Generally, embryo/foetotoxicity resulted in reduced body weights of pups and reduced number of litters, while teratogenicity resulted in a variety of skeletal malformations. In the studies in rats, embryo/foetotoxicity mostly appeared at maternal toxic doses or concentrations, and teratogenicity was not reported in absence of maternal toxicity. However, in mice and rabbits, embryo/foetotoxicity and/or signs of teratogenicity were observed at dose levels not generating evidence for maternal toxicity. Based on these findings, RAC concluded that DMF seems to affect the skeletal system in all three species, with the rabbit as the most sensitive species to the developmental toxicity of DMF, and that relevance to humans must be assumed (ECHA, 2019).

Following these results, RAC decided to base the starting points for developmental effects on the study by Hellwig et al. (1991) on Himalayan rabbits. As first signs of malformations, sternal malformations and gallbladder agenesis were found at dermal doses of 100 mg/kg bw/d and umbilical hernia and sternal malformations following inhalation exposure to 150 ppm (ca 450 mg/m³). RAC states that sternal malformations, umbilical hernia and gallbladder agenesis are serious effects supporting using 100 mg/kg/day as LOAEL for dermal developmental toxicity and 150 ppm as LOAEC for inhalation developmental toxicity (NOAEC: 50 ppm = 150 mg/m³) (ECHA, 2019).

Case reports and epidemiological studies have reported deleterious effects of DMF on the liver and digestive system among workers exposed to high levels of DMF. The immune system can also be affected by DMF exposure but the establishment of a relationship between health effect and exposure to DMF requires more data (Kennedy et al., 2012).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 295

4 Existing toxicity reference values for occupationally exposed workers to DMF

Assessments on DMF were conducted by nationally and internationally recognised agencies to derive threshold airborne and biological values.

4.1 Scientific committee on occupational exposure limit values (SCOEL)

4.1.1 8h-TWA (Time-Weighted Average)

In 2006, SCOEL recommended an 8h-OEL based on an animal study conducted by Malley et al. (1994) on 87 rats/sex/group and 78 mice/sex/group exposed to 0, 25, 100, or 400 ppm DMF. Based on liver effects (described in Annex 2), the dose of 25 ppm was identified by the committee as a NOAEC for rats and a LOAEC for mice²⁹.

The SCOEL performed a BMD calculation (based on 5 % extra risk of centrilobular hepatocellular hypertrophy in male and female combined) and calculated a BMDL of 7.8 ppm and a BMD of 14.7 ppm. Thus, the experts of the committee proposed an OEL of 5 ppm, estimating that this value also protects against developmental toxicity (for which the committee identified a NOAEL of 50 ppm).

However, it was added that exposure to DMF below 7 ppm in combination with alcohol consumption can elicit intolerance reactions such as highly visible facial flushing (with subjective symptoms of discomfort). It was reported that sensitive individuals (about 5 % of European populations and up to 90 % of Asian people) have higher risk for alcohol reactions even at a concentration of 4 ppm.

4.1.2 STEL (Short Term Exposure Level)

In addition to the 8h-OEL, SCOEL (2006) recommended a STEL of 10 ppm, considering this value protective against local irritation (based on experimental studies on volunteers).

4.1.3 BLV (Biological Limit Value)

SCOEL analysed available studies carried out at the workplace (Table V.6) showing correlations between atmospheric exposure and concentrations of tNMF in urine. Based on the results, SCOEL concluded that 5 ppm (8h-TWA) would correspond to 9 to 25 mg NMF/l urine, in mean to about 15 mg NMF/l urine

Moreover, the experts mentioned the monitoring of AMCC in urine but no value was recommended because of insufficient data at the time.

4.1.4 Notation

Due to the contribution of dermal uptake to systemic toxicity, the SCOEL committee proposed a “skin” notation.

²⁹ Malley et al. 1995 identified a NOEL of 25 ppm in rats.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 296

4.2 DFG (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft)³⁰

4.2.1 MAK value (maximale Arbeitsplatz-Konzentration)³¹

In 2006, the MAK commission recommended a MAK value of 5 ppm to protect workers against changes in liver parameters (DFG, 2006). This value was based on an animal study (Malley et al. 1994). The same value of the BMDL as presented above (SCOEL 2006 recommendation) was proposed. Whereas a robust study carried out at the workplace gave the same POD for hepatotoxic effects (Wribitzky, 1999; Wribitzky and Angerer, 1998), the experts estimated that it was difficult to derive a threshold concentration in air based on this study because of the important contribution of dermal uptake.

4.2.2 BAT value (Biologischer Arbeitsstoff Toleranzwert)³²

In 2006, the MAK commission recommended a BAT value of 35 mg/L of tNMF in urine. This value was based on occupational studies (Lauwerys et al., 1980; Sakai et al., 1995; Wribitzky, 1999; Wribitzky and Angerer, 1998). The commission reported a value of 37.1 mg/l for tNMF in urine for which there was no indication of liver damage, thus the BAT value in 2006 was based on a direct relationship between tNMF concentrations in urine and hepatotoxicity. According to the experts, this BAT value does not include the possible occurrence of alcohol intolerance. Moreover, no evaluation of a BAT value for urinary AMCC or MCV_{al} in blood was recommended due to insufficient knowledge of the relationship between internal AMCC and MCV_{al} exposure and hepatotoxicity.

However, in 2019, the commission updated this evaluation. The experts proposed BAT values based on the MAK value (5 ppm) and the correlation between biomarkers of exposure (BMEs) and atmospheric DMF. They used data from Seitz et al. (2018) which provide equations for each BME (tNMF, AMCC and MCV_{al}). These equations are detailed in Annex 3 (Table V.15). The new BAT values recommended by the MAK commission are 20 mg/l for urinary tNMF and 25 mg/g cr for urinary AMCC.

Moreover, the MAK commission proposed the monitoring of MCV_{al} in blood as a biomarker of aggregate exposure during recent working days.

4.3 ACGIH (American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists)

4.3.1 TLV-TWA (Threshold Limit Value – Time-Weighted Average)

In 2018, the ACGIH recommended a TLV-TWA of 5 ppm (15 mg/m³) for DMF. This value is based on the same key study as selected by the SCOEL and the MAK commission in 2006 i.e. Malley et al. (1994). According to ACGIH, several factors support the results reported by the authors (NOAEL of 25 ppm). ACGIH also noted human and animal studies which reported eye and upper respiratory tract irritation at concentrations of 10 ppm DMF or less.

4.3.2 BEI (Biological Exposure Index)

In 2017, based on workplace studies with acknowledged limitations, ACGIH proposed a conservative BEI of 30 mg/l for urinary tNMF to protect workers against effects on liver. This

³⁰ German Research Foundation

³¹ Maximum Workplace concentration

³² Concentration for which there is no impact on human health (for non-carcinogenic substances)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 297

value is based on several occupational studies (Lauwerys et al., 1980; Sakai et al., 1995; Fiorito et al., 1997; Wrbitzky et al., 1999; He et al., 2010) which reported no adverse effects on liver function at 25- 60 mg/l. The committee noted that alcohol intolerance (flushing) with DMF exposure occurred at or below the BEI. However, the committee did not consider this as a health effect endpoint.

Despite limited data, the committee derived a BEI of 30 mg/g creatinine for another relevant biomarker, urinary AMCC, based on data from Sakai et al. (1993) suggesting a no effect level of 31 mg/l and from He et al. (2010) reporting limited liver changes at 35.5 mg/l.

4.4 ECHA (European Chemicals Agency) - DNEL_{Inhalation} (Derived No Effect Level – inhalation route)

In its opinion on a restriction dossier for DMF (ECHA, 2019), the Risk Assessment Committee (RAC) of ECHA preferred deriving the DNEL_{Inhalation} value for workers from the Kilo et al. (2016) study, conducted at workplace with 220 exposed workers and 175 controls. The mean value of airborne DMF level for exposed workers was 6.2 ± 7.6 mg DMF/m³ (mean \pm SD) (range < 0.08-46.85 mg/m³). None of the tested liver enzyme activities showed a positive association with any of the exposure markers tested. According to the committee, this mean value can be considered as a NOAEC for hepatic effects. They did not apply any assessment factor and recommended a DNEL for inhalation route of about 6 mg/m³ (i.e. 2 ppm). To protect workers against reproductive effects, the committee used data from a rabbit developmental toxicity study (Hellwig et al., 1991) to support this value. The NOAEC was 150 mg/m³ (malformations, e.g. umbilical hernia). The experts applied an exposure correction to human exposure (6/8 hours \times 6.7/10 m³) and uncertainty factors of 2.5 for interspecies and 5 for intraspecies differences to derive a DNEL of 6 mg/m³, the same value as the DNEL based on hepatic effects.

In addition, RAC derived a DNEL for dermal exposure (DNEL_{dermal}) based on a LOAEL of 100 mg/kg/d (Hellwig et al 1991) on developmental effects and the following factors:

- 2.4 (allometric adjustment) and 2.5 (interspecies differences)
- 5 for intraspecies differences
- 3 for the conversion of LOAEL to NOAEL

A DNEL_{dermal} of 1.1 mg/kg/d (100/90) is thus suggested by RAC to be used for dermal exposure.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 298

4.5 Summary of the existing values for DMF

4.5.1 Summary of the existing OEL values for DMF

Table V.6: Overview of existing OELs for DMF derived for the occupational field

Agency	Key study Description	Endpoint	POD	Assessment factors (AF)	Reference values
SCOEL, 2006	Malley <i>et al.</i> 1994 Experimental study Rats and mice	Effects on liver	BMD ₅ L ₉₅ = 7,8 ml/m ³	None	8h-TWA 5 ppm (15 mg/m ³)
DFG, 2006	Malley <i>et al.</i> 1994 Experimental study	Effects on liver	BMD ₅ L ₉₅ = 7,8 ml/m ³	None	MAK value 5 ppm (15 mg/m ³)
ACGIH, 2018	Malley <i>et al.</i> 1994 & Tomasini 1983 & Cirla 1984 & Cai 1992 Experimental study and occupational study	Effects on liver and irritation (eyes and upper respiratory tract)	NOAEL = 25 ppm <10 ml/m ³	None	TLV-TWA 5 ppm (15 mg/m ³)
ECHA, 2019	Kilo <i>et al.</i> 2016 Occupational study	Effects on liver	NOAEC = 6.2 mg/m ³	None	DNEL _{inhalation} = 6 mg/m ³ (2 ppm)
	Hellwig <i>et al.</i> 1991 Experimental study Rabbit	Developmental toxicity	NOAEC = 150 mg/m ³	1- Correction to human exposure NOAEC x 6/8 x 6.7/10m ³ = 75.4 2- Human NOAEC/(AF _H *AF _A) = 75.4 /(2.5x5)	

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 299

4.5.2 Summary of the existing internal toxicity reference values for DMF

Table V.7: Overview of existing biological values for DMF derived for the occupational field

Agency	Biomarkers	Approach/End point	Key studies	Internal toxicity reference values and sampling time
SCOEL, 2006	tNMF in urine	Correlation based on the OEL of 5 ppm	Kawai et al., 1992 Yang et al., 2000 Wang et al., 2004 Kim et al., 2004 Sakai et al., 1995 Wrbitzky and Angerer, 1998 Käfferlein et al., 2000 Imbriani et al., 2002	BLV = 15 mg/l Post-shift
ACGIH, 2017	tNMF in urine	Relation between BMEs levels and effects on liver	Lauwerys et al., 1980 & Sakai et al., 1995 & Wrbizki, 1999 & He et al., 2010)	BEI = 30 mg/l End of shift;
	AMCC in urine	Relation between BMEs levels and effects on liver	Sakai et al., 1995 He et al, 2010	BEI = 30 mg/l End of shift or end of workweek
DFG, 2019	tNMF in urine	Correlation based on the MAK value of 5 ppm	Seitz et al. 2018	BAT = 20 mg/l End of exposure or end of shift.
	AMCC in urine			BAT = 25 mg/g cr End of exposure or end of shift; Long-term exposure: at the end of the shift after several previous shifts

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 300

4.6 Conclusion

Recent derivations of biological values for the monitoring of DMF exposure, referred to tNMF and AMCC in urine.

Two approaches have been used for deriving internal toxicity reference values:

- relationships between health effects and BME concentrations (ACGIH, 2018)
- correlation between DMF levels in air and BME concentrations (DFG, 2019)

Measurement of DMF only in air is not sufficiently protective against systemic effects because of the potential contribution of the dermal exposure route. Therefore, the calculation of a BEI using the correlation between atmospheric level of DMF and biological concentrations of BME is considered inadequate (ACGIH, 2018). In 2006, the MAK commission estimated that the BAT value must be derived independently from the MAK value (5 ppm) because DMF is readily absorbed through the skin. However, in 2019, the MAK commission revised its appraisals and proposed BAT values for tNMF and AMCC in urine based on the relationship between internal and external concentrations.

Despite the different methods of derivation, the values recommended by the two committees are very similar.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 301

5 HBM parameters

5.1 Choice of biomarkers

5.1.1 DMF in urine

Unchanged DMF can be detected in the urine of occupationally exposed persons. However, unchanged DMF is excreted only at low levels. In addition, measurement of DMF in urine of workers is not likely to provide any advantage over measurements of tNMF.

5.1.2 Total NMF in urine

Excretion of tNMF in urine, which is the sum of N-hydroxymethyl-N-methylformamide and N-methylformamide, has a short half-life (4 hours). Therefore, the concentration of urinary tNMF represents the exposure of a working day, and the sample should be collected at the end of a shift or exposure. The suitability of this biomarker for the derivation of an HBM-GV_{workers} has been confirmed by the observed positive relationship between tNMF concentration in urine and health effects in workers, reported by several studies over several decades. These studies are described in Table V.2 providing data on tNMF levels in urine linked to effects on liver (Lauwerys et al., 1980; Catenacci et al., 1984; Sakai et al., 1995; Fiorito et al., 1997; Wrbitzky, 1999; He et al., 2010; Wu et al., 2017; Kilo et al., 2016). Wu et al. (2017) concluded that tNMF is the best biomarker for predicting liver injury, based on the statistical significance of differences between DMF exposed workers with and without liver injury, for tNMF, AMCC in urine, and MCV_{al} in blood (P=(0.001, 0.054, and 0.043, respectively).

A good correlation between tNMF in urine and individual exposure to airborne concentration of DMF, has been reported by some authors, as listed in Annex 2.

Urinary tNMF could not be detected using gas chromatography with a LOD of 0.1 mg/l in people who were not exposed to DMF according to Will et al. (1997). That makes urinary tNMF a good specific biomarker of DMF occupational exposure especially as non-occupational exposure is rare. However, it should be noted that elimination may be delayed after skin absorption, as shown by Mràz and Nohovà (1992), although they found no significant accumulation over the workweek. In addition, delayed excretion is also observed after alcohol intake as it inhibits the metabolism of DMF. This also has an impact on tNMF in urine with a decrease in the level detected.

5.1.3 AMCC in urine

AMCC has a longer half-life of urinary excretion (23 hours) than tNMF. This results in the progressive elevation of AMCC urinary concentration over consecutive days of exposure. Therefore, the urine sample should be collected at the end of the shift at the end of the workweek (or at least after several previous shifts) to reflect the cumulative DMF load of the preceding days of work.

AMCC exposure is associated with health effects (see Annex 3, Table V.15) especially for the liver; it is directly related to methyl isocyanate, the presumed reactive intermediate of DMF. AMCC elimination in urine is not delayed by skin exposure (ACGIH, 2018). Occupational studies showed positive associations between levels of urinary AMCC and abnormal liver function. According to He et al. (2010), AMCC could be used as an ideal biomarker of exposure in health risk assessments following exposure to DMF.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 302

Nevertheless, AMCC can be found in urine of the general population at low levels, as reported by Käfferlein and Angerer (1999) and Schettgen et al. (2008). This is most likely due to endogenous biochemical reactions in the human body rather than environmental exposure. These reactions can be responsible for slightly higher levels in smokers (Schettgen et al., 2008). There are limited data showing that, after alcohol consumption, AMCC urinary levels are more reduced compared to the concentration of tNMF in urine, due to the inhibition of DMF metabolism (Kim and Kim, 2011 as cited by ACGIH 2017).

5.1.4 MCVaI in blood

MCVaI, has emerged as another possible biomarker of exposure and possibly of effect for DMF. Since adducts accumulate over the lifetime of the erythrocyte, MCVaI can reflect DMF exposure over the preceding 4 months. However, due to its kinetics, MCVaI requires approximately 100 days to reach steady-state. It is therefore a long-term parameter for which sampling should only be conducted after several months of exposure.

According to some authors (Mraz et al., 2002; He et al., 2010; Wu et al., 2017), despite practical difficulty of blood sampling, MCVaI is the best biomarker reflecting DMF accumulation and potential hepatotoxicity in the body. The stability of MCVaI (compared to tNMF and AMCC) is very important in some scenarios for risk assessment (episodic or irregular exposure, residents living around factories or workers recently losing or leaving their jobs). Indeed, hepatic damage occurs occasionally days or weeks after DMF exposure. For example, Wu et al. (2017) observed 5 workers with abnormal liver enzyme activities who had low levels of tNMF but high concentration of MCVaI.

Two recent studies reported a positive relationship between MCVaI and liver effects (Wu et al., 2017 and Kilo et al., 2017).

Seitz et al. (2019) reported a correlation between levels of MCVaI in workers and airborne concentration of DMF, as reported in Table V.15 (Annex 3). As with AMCC, the formation of MCVaI is directly linked to the presumed reactive intermediate, methyl isocyanate, and may therefore be conservative regarding liver effects of DMF.

5.1.5 Formamide in urine

There is limited data for formamide as a biomarker for DMF exposure. Moreover, formamide can be detected in control workers not exposed to DMF as shown by Mráz and Nohová (1992b), suggesting that formamide is not a specific biomarker of DMF exposure.

5.1.6 Summary of the advantages and disadvantages of the BME

Table V.8: Advantages and disadvantages of relevant biomarkers of DMF exposure

Analyte	Biological matrix	Advantages	Disadvantages
Total NMF	Urine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Short half-life: daily exposure estimate - Good specificity - Not found in the general population - Good correlation with DMF presence in the workplace air 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delayed excretion after skin absorption (Mráz & Nohová, 1992) Influenced by alcohol consumption and analytical methods
AMCC	Urine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good correlation with DMF presence in the workplace air - Elimination not delayed by skin exposure - Directly linked to MIC formation and hepatotoxic effects - Estimates weekly exposure: (accumulation over 3-4 days) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Influenced by alcohol and tobacco consumption Might be found in general population
MCVal	Blood	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Very stable, estimates long-term exposure - Directly linked to MIC formation - Good correlation with DMF presence in the workplace air 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited data Limitations due to matrix accessibility
DMF	Urine	Specific	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited data Very short half-life (2 hours) Only low levels excreted at high absorbed doses.
Formamide	Urine	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not specific, can be found in the absence of DMF exposure. Limited data

5.1.7 Conclusion

Total NMF and AMCC in urine are recommended by many countries for biological monitoring of occupational exposure to DMF. These two biomarkers present many advantages; they are the most studied biomarkers to assess DMF exposure and health effects of DMF at workplace. Thus, they are selected for deriving HBM-GV_{workers} for DMF biomonitoring.

Despite the advantages presented by MCVal, the lack of data and the invasiveness do not allow the selection of this BME for deriving biological values with the same level of confidence. Up to now, MCVal has rarely been measured and no reference value has been derived.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 304

5.2 Analytical methods

Within the HBM4EU project, the published deliverable D9.5 “Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 2nd prioritisation round of substances” gives an insight into the analytical protocols and methods for HBM measurement of DMF in HBM4EU participants' member states.

Gas chromatographic methods are commonly used for the analysis of tNMF in urine samples of exposed workers. Use of gas chromatography with nitrogen phosphorus detector (GC-NPD), or combined with mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and of gas chromatography with flame photometric detector (GC-FPD), have been documented. Kawai et al. (1992) reported that results can be affected by the temperature of the GC injection port. Therefore, the ACGIH recommended a temperature of 250°C or above to obtain complete degradation of HMMF into NMF. Limits of detection were between 0.2 (GC-NPD; Seitz et al., 2018; Will et al., 2016) and 0.5 mg/l (GC-MS; He et al., 2010). For the GC-FPD, the LOD is reported in µg/injection; the reported method details do not allow a back calculation to the LOD in urine (Chang et al., 2003).

AMCC in urine samples have been analysed by a combination of liquid chromatography with mass spectrometry, LC-MS/MS after solid phase extraction (Seitz et al., 2018; Udeni Alwis et al., 2012). LODs of 5 and 5.5 µg/l were achieved. In Imbriani et al. (2002a and 2002b), AMCC was measured in urine samples by LC with UV detection, achieving only a very high LOD of 0.9 mg/l.

The DFG recommends a capillary gas chromatography procedure using nitrogen selective detection capable of measuring tNMF (LOD=1.0 mg/l urine; LOQ=3.0 mg/l urine) as well as other DMF metabolites such as AMCC (LOD=0,5 mg/l urine; LOQ=1.5 mg/l urine) (Käfferlein and Angerer, 2013).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 305

6 Derivation of HBM-GVs for workers

6.1 Derivation method

According to the methodology developed in the framework of the HBM4EU project, there are three possible options for deriving HBM-GV (Apel et al., 2020).

1. The 1st option to explore is whether HBM-GVs can be derived on the basis of relevant human data, providing evidence of a relationship between concentrations of a substance/its metabolites in human biological media and the occurrence of adverse effects.
2. If derivation is not possible with the 1st option, the 2nd possible option is to derive HBM-GVs based on external limit values proposed by EU or relevant non-EU bodies.
3. If derivation is not possible with the two previous options, the 3rd possible option to consider is to derive HBM-GVs based on critical effects observed in animal toxicological studies.

Based on the available data on DMF, the relationships between health effects and BME levels allow the derivation of HBM-GV_{Workers} following the 1st option. As described in Table V.12 (Annex 3), the literature provides several values of BME concentrations linked to health effects on workers (hepatotoxic and antabuse effects).

Some studies report a correlation between DMF presence in the workplace air and BME concentrations (tNMF, AMCC in urine and more recently for MCV_{al} in blood), but the external exposure dose is not always consistent with the occurrence of occupational disease, because dermal exposure, can represent an important route of exposure which cannot be estimated by only measuring airborne DMF (ACGIH, 2017).

6.2 Choice of the critical effects

Studies conducted in the workplace report relationships between health effects and concentration levels of tNMF and AMCC in urine and MCV_{al} in blood.

The most sensitive effects are observed on liver, mainly as increased hepatic enzymes (ALT, AST and γ GT). In some studies, antabuse effects are reported even at low level of exposure, however it is difficult to establish a threshold value due to high individual variability.

Thus, effects on liver function defined by abnormal increase of hepatic enzymes, e.g. ALT, AST and γ GT, are selected as the critical effect for deriving HBM-GV_{Workers}.

Currently, the consensus of national or international organisations support this endpoint for deriving occupational values (atmospheric as well as biological values).

6.3 Choice of the key study and derivation of HBM-GV_{workers}

Table V.2 details the relations between the three biomarkers (tNMF and AMCC in urine) and effects on liver function in the most relevant occupational studies.

Total NMF in urine

There is an extensive database of studies reporting tNMF measurements and hepatic effects. Mean values for urinary tNMF concentration were between 7.75 and 22.3 mg/l and/or between 6.7 and 50 mg/g creatinine for groups without hepatotoxic effects and between 13.6 and 14.9 mg/l and/or 9.1 and 13.4 mg/g cr, for groups with hepatic effects. Hepatic effects were noted for

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 306

lower exposure (tNMF urine concentration: 4.5 mg/l) in people with alcoholic beverage consumption.

Based on these data it seems appropriate to recommend an **HBM-GV_{workers} of 10 mg/l urine or 10 mg/g creatinine to prevent effects on liver.**

AMCC in urine

AMCC in urine has been shown to be a relevant BME for assessment of the cumulative exposure of the previous working days; moreover, it is linked to the presumed toxic intermediate MIC. Few studies have tried to characterise the relationship between urinary AMCC concentration and effects on liver. In a German study (Kilo et al., 2016), no effects on liver enzymes were observed at a mean AMCC urine concentration of 9.42 ± 10.42 mg/g cr. In a Chinese study (Wu et al., 2017), a BMDL₁₀ of 155 mg/l (119 mg/l in male workers) was calculated in a group of workers with an increased incidence of liver injury.

Due to the paucity of data, it is uncertain whether the recommendation of an HBM-GV_{worker} for urine AMCC would be appropriate. However, based on the results of the study by Kilo et al. (2016), a 10 mg/g cr threshold would be conservative.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 307

7 Discussion

Literature on DMF biomonitoring offers a large database on robust relationships between health effects and BME levels. Several occupational studies report urinary concentrations of tNMF and AMCC (and a few on MCV_{al}) linked to hepatic effects, antabuse effects, or effects on gastrointestinal tract. Recent studies observed lower threshold values regarding these effects than those proposed by SCOEL, ACGIH or DFG (15 mg/l to 30 mg/l).

For tNMF, the studies are consistent with an HBM-GV_{worker} of 10 mg/l. Considering the half-life time, end-of-shift urine sampling can be performed for this biomarker.

The analytical method could also influence measurements of tNMF in urine, indeed it is recommended a temperature of 250°C or above to obtain a complete degradation of HMMF into NMF.

In addition to this recommendation, an HBM-GV_{worker} has been derived for AMCC (cumulative exposure). However, as previously explained, it is important to note that tNMF is considered as the most reliable biomonitoring biomarker for DMF exposure.

For AMCC, the results are not sufficient and reliable to recommend an HBM-GV_{worker} with certainty; a value of 10 mg/g or would be conservative. End-of-shift and end of work-week urine sampling is recommended.

Alcohol consumption must be considered for interpretation of tNMF and AMCC in urine. Therefore, this information should also be collected to allow the correct data analyses.

Since dermal intake can be important depending on the worker's activities results must be interpreted with regards to the actual exposure scenario (to identify an excess exposure via the dermal route for example).

Despite the suitability of DMF biomonitoring via the measurement of MCV_{al}, the lack of data on this biomarker did not allow the derivation of an HBM-GV_{worker}. Moreover, this biomarker presents limitations due to matrix accessibility (blood sampling).

Although liver effects are the most sensitive, DMF is classified as Reprotoxic Cat 1B (H360D), thus this effect must be considered in the workplace. In 2019, ECHA derived a DNEL_{inhalation} which, based on current data, protects from adverse liver effects but also developmental effects. Indeed, the European committee calculated a DNEL and found similar values (around 6 mg/m³) for both effects. Moreover, DMF is listed in Directive 92/85/EEC, which aims to encourage improvements in the safety and health at work of pregnant workers and workers who have recently given birth or are breastfeeding. According to this directive, employers must take special measures to assess and to avoid any risk of exposure for breastfeeding and pregnant workers to dangerous chemicals.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 308

The proposed HBM-GV_{worker} do not take into account the possible cancer risk associated with DMF. It should however, be emphasised that:

- there is no sufficient evidence of DMF genotoxicity;
- the three reported clusters of testis cancer do not constitute a sufficient evidence of DMF carcinogenicity in humans;
- in animals, increased incidences of hepatic tumours were always seen together with signs of hepatotoxicity, and DMF induced tumours in no other sites.

From these observations it can be inferred that a limit value protecting against hepatic damage is most probably also protective against a possible cancer risk.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 309

8 Level of confidence attributed to the HBM-GVs

As mentioned in the HBM4EU concept paper to derive HBM-GVs (Apel et al., 2020), a level of confidence (low, medium or high) could be attributed to each calculated HBM-GV. The level of confidence should reflect the uncertainties identified during the derivation of the value and could constitute a good incentive to later revise values with estimated 'lower' level of confidence.

However, it should be specified that the levels of confidence proposed in this document are not determined according to an established recognised methodology, but rather rely on expert judgment regarding the reliability of the data and the calculation method used to derive the HBM-GV values.

The levels of confidence attributed to the HBM-GVs_{workers} are set to 'high' for tNMF and 'medium-low' for AMCC³³.

³³ Please refer to note n°2 of the factsheet presented in section 9 for explanation on this level of confidence

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 310

9 Factsheet reporting the HBM-GV_{worker} derivation

		Target population Workers	
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
HBM-GV_{worker} and Status			
HBM-GV _{worker}	1	tNFM: 10 mg/l (or 10 mg/g cr) AMCC: 10 mg/g cr	See note for explanation
Level of confidence	2	tNMF: high AMCC: medium-low	
HBM-GV status	3	tNFM: agreed on within HBM4EU AMCC: provisional	
HBM-GV year of issue	4	2020	
CLP-INDEX-Nr.			
CLP-INDEX-Nr.	5		
EC-Nr.	6	200-679-5	
CAS-Nr.	7	68-12-2	
Harmonised CLP classification	8	Repro 1B (H360) Acute Tox 4* (H312) Eye irrit. 2 (H319) Acute Tox 4* (H332)	
Molar mass	9	73 g/mol	
Biomarker(s)			
Identification	10	Total NMF in urine (tNMF) AMCC in urine	
Molar mass of biomarker(s)	11	tNMF in urine: 59 AMCC in urine: 220	
Half-life of selected biomarker(s)	12	tNMF: 4-5h AMCC: 23h	
Derivation method, starting point and assessment factors			
Type of derivation method selected	13	Based on the relationship between biomarkers and liver effects (option 1)	
Key study	14	tNMF: several studies carried out at workplace AMCC: Kilo et al., 2016	
Exposure route of study	15	Inhalation and dermal	
Critical endpoint and POD	16	Liver effects (increase of liver enzymes: ALT, AST, γ GT)	
Extrapolations and AFs	17	None	

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 311

Target population Workers			
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
Calculation of HBM-GV_{worker}			
PBPK model for translating the selected exposure guidance value to an internal guidance value	18	Not applicable	
Additional Comments			

1. HBM-GV_{Worker}: numerical values for 2 biomarkers of exposure (tNMF and AMCC)
Monitoring of AMCC is recommended in addition to the monitoring of tNMF, which is considered as the most reliable BME.
2. Level of confidence of the HBM-GV_{worker}:
The level of confidence takes into account the various uncertainties underlying the derivation of the HBM-GV (e.g. reliability of the key study, uncertainties related to toxicokinetic data on the substance of interest, to the extrapolations and calculation of the final HBM-GV).

An attribution of a global level of confidence is suggested for the proposed tNMF HBM-GV_{Worker}, considering the assessment of the various uncertainties:

regarding the nature and quality of the toxicological data: the database on DMF is based on a large number of both human and animal studies and data on tNMF are robust and consistent → **high**

- regarding the critical endpoint and mode of action: the confidence in the evidence of effects on the liver function is high. The effects on liver after DMF exposure are well studied in humans (workplace) and animals → **high**
- regarding the selected key study for identification of the POD: the database gives several robust occupational studies with many subjects. The approach consists in the selection of a pool of studies (from 1980 to 2017) carried out on Asians and Caucasian people (to consider the genetic variability due to ethnicity) → **high**

The global level of confidence for tNMF HBM-GV in the occupational field is set to “**high**”

An attribution of a global level of confidence is suggested for the proposed AMCC HBM-GV_{worker}, considering the assessment of the various uncertainties:

- regarding the nature and quality of the toxicological data: the database on DMF is based on a large number of both human and animal studies but available studies reporting results for AMCC are limited → **medium**
- regarding the critical endpoint and mode of action: the confidence in the evidence of effects on the liver function is high. The effects on liver after DMF exposure are well studied (in humans and animals) → **high**
- regarding the selected key study for identification of the POD: the HBM-GV_{worker} is based on a recent study with a large number of workers but the results concerning

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 312

levels of AMCC linked to effects on liver which are reported in occupational studies are not consistent. Thus, the HBM-GV_{worker} must be interpreted with caution and in addition to the tNMF HBM-GV_{worker} → **low**

The global level of confidence for AMCC HBM-GV in the occupational field is set to **“medium-low”**

3. HBM-GV_{worker} status: for tNMF the value was agreed on within HBM4EU. . For AMCC HBM-GV_{worker}, the status is fixed to “provisional”, reflecting that this value could be revised later, if uncertainties are resolved
4. HBM-GV_{worker} year of issue: year of setting the HBM-GV_{worker} in the HBM4EU workframe
5. CLP Number: according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures, implementing the globally harmonised system of classification and labelling of chemicals (GHS):
http://guidance.echa.europa.eu/docs/guidance_document/clp_introduutory_en.pdf
6. EC Number: under European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS), ELINCS (European List of Notified Chemical Substances) in support of Directive 92/32/EEC, the 7th amendment to Directive 67/548/EEC, NLP (No-Longer Polymers), see: ESIS; European chemical Substances Information System:
https://web.archive.org/web/20131106181548if_/http://esis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/
7. CAS Number: collection of disclosed chemical compound information by Chemical Abstracts Service. Almost all molecule databases can be searched by CAS Registry Number.
8. Harmonised CLP classification: CLP classification including CMR and other health-relevant effects. In the case that classification is not harmonised, this should be stated.
9. Molar mass: mass of NMP per amount of this substance expressed in g/mol
10. Biomarker(s) identification: the biomarkers identified as relevant for assessing the exposure to DMF are tNMF and AMCC. Consequently, those 2 metabolites are selected for the HBM-GV derivation.
11. Molar mass of the biomarker(s): mass of the selected biomarkers (expressed in g/mol)
12. Half-life of biomarker: estimated elimination half-lives for the DMF biomarkers of exposure
13. Derivation method: the existing database on DMF allows for the derivation of health-based guidance values from human data, based on internal concentration and health effects relationship which is the first option (Concept document)
14. Key study:
 - a. tNMF: the large amount of occupational studies giving a relationship between effects on liver and increased concentration of tNMF has led to the selection of a pool of studies. Almost all studies retained for the derivation of HBM-GV_{worker} were selected for evaluation by national or international organisations (e.g. ACGIH, SCOEL).
 - b. AMCC: the results reported in occupational studies are not consistent, thus for this BME, a single study is selected. The study by Kilo et al. 2016 (N = 220) observed effects from 9.42 mg/g cr.
15. Exposure route of study
At workplace, workers are exposed to DMF by inhalation and via dermal route.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 313

16. Critical endpoint and POD: The critical systemic effects considered relevant are the effects on liver function assessed in studies by measurement of liver enzymes (ALT, AST, γ GT). In the key studies (Table V.13), the authors compared exposed and non-exposed workers and reported statistically significant differences in enzyme levels between the two groups.
17. Extrapolations and AFs: the key studies are epidemiological studies carried out in the workplace, i.e., on the population of interest, no AF is required here.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 314

10 References

American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH) (2017). Biological Exposure Index documentation for N,N-Dimethylformamide. Cincinnati, United States.

American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH) (2018). N,N-Dimethylformamide. Cincinnati, United States.

Apel P, Rousselle C, Lange R., Sissoko F, Kolossa-Gehring M, Ougier E. (2020). Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU) - Strategy to derive Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for health risk assessment. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health* 230 (2020) 113622.

Brand MR, Jendrzewski JL, Henery EM, Charron AR. (2006). A Single Oral Dose of Ethanol Can Alter Transdermal Absorption of Topically Applied Chemicals in Rats. *Toxicological Sciences*, 92 (2), 349–355.

Brindley C, Gescher A, Ross D. (1983). Studies on the Metabolism of Dimethylformamide in Mice. *Chem. - Biol. Interactions*, 45 (1983) 387 - 392.

Brugnone F, Perbellini L, Gaffuri E. (1980) N-N-dimethylformamide concentration in environmental and alveolar air in an artificial leather factory. *British Journal of Industrial Medicine*, 01 May 1980, 37(2):185-188

Buylaert W, Calle P, De Paepe P, Verstraete A, Samyn N, Vogelaers D, Vandenbulcke M, Belpaire F (1996). Hepatotoxicity of N, N-dimethylformamide (DMF) in acute poisoning with the veterinary euthanasia drug T-61. *Hum Exp Toxicol*, 15(8):607-11

Cai, S.-X., Huang MY, Xi, LQ, Li YL, Qu JB, Kawai T, Yasugi T, Mizunuma K, Watanabe T, Ikeda M. (1992). Occupational dimethylformamide exposure & Health effects of dimethylformamide after occupational exposure at low concentrations. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health* (1992) 63:461-468.

Calvert GM, Fajen JM, Hills BW, Halperin WE. (1990). Testicular cancer, dimethylformamide, and leather tanneries. *Lancet*, 336(8725):1253–4.

Catenacci G, Grampella D, Terzi R, Sala A and Pollini G. (1984). Hepatic function in subjects exposed to environmental concentrations of DMF lower than the actually proposed. *G Ital Med Lav. May-Jul 1984;6(3-4):157-8.*

Centers for Disease Control (CDC) (1989). Testicular cancer in leather workers—Fulton County, New York. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep*, 38(7):105–6, 111–4.

Centers for Disease Control (CDC) (2019). “Fourth National Report on Human Exposure to Environmental Chemicals Updated Tables, January 2019, Volume One”. US. Department of Health and Human Services. p 868

Centers for Disease Control (CDC) (2019). “Fourth National Report on Human Exposure to Environmental Chemicals Updated Tables, January 2019, Volume Two”. US. Department of Health and Human Services. p 994

Chan AWK. (1986). Racial differences in alcohol sensitivity. *Alcohol and Alcoholism*. 21(1): 93-104.

Chang, HY, Tsai, CY, Lin, YQ, Shih, TS, and Lin, YC (2004a). Urinary biomarkers of occupational N, N-dimethylformamide (DMF) exposure attributed to the dermal exposure. *Journal of Exposure Analysis and Environmental Epidemiology* 14, 214–221.

Chang HY, Shih TS, Leon Guo Y, Tsai CY, Hsu PC. (2004b). Sperm function in workers exposed to N,N-dimethylformamide in the synthetic leather industry. *Fertil Steril Actions*, 81(6):1589-94.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 315

Chang HY, Shih TS, Cheng CC, Tsai CY, Lai JS, Wang VS. (2003). The effects of co-exposure to methyl ethyl ketone on the biological monitoring of occupational exposure to N,N-dimethylformamide. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health*, 76(2):121-8.

Chang HY, Tsai CY, Lin YQ, Shih TS, Lin WC. Chang HY, (2005). Total body burden arising from a week's repeated dermal exposure to N,N-dimethylformamide. *Occup Environ Med*, 62(3):151-6.

Chemicals Inspection & Testing Institute Japan (1992). Biodegradation and Bioaccumulation Data of Existing Chemicals Based on the CSCL Japan. Japan Chemical Industry Ecology-Toxicology & Information Center (JETOC).

Chen JL, Fayerweather WE, Pell S. (1988a). Cancer incidence of workers exposed to dimethylformamide and/or acrylonitrile. *J Occup Med*. 30(10):813-818.

Chen JL, Fayerweather WE, Pell S. (1988b). Mortality study of workers exposed to dimethylformamide and/or acrylonitrile. *J Occup Med*. 30(10):819-821.

Chen Y (2004). Induction of DNA strand breakage of human peripheral blood cells by N,N-dimethylformamide. *Chinese Journal of Health Laboratory Technology*, 14:166–8.[Chinese]

Cheng TJ, Hwang SJ, Kuo HW, Luo JC, Chang MJ (1999). Exposure to epichlorohydrin and dimethylformamide, glutathione S-transferases and sister chromatid exchange frequencies in peripheral lymphocytes. *Arch Toxicol*, 73(4-5):282–7.

Chivers CP. (1978). Disulfiram effect from inhalation of dimethylformamide. *Lancet*. 11; 1(8059):331.

Cirla, AM, Pisati G, Invernizzi E, Torricelli P. (1984). Epidemiological study on workers exposed to low dimethylformamide concentrations. *G. Ital. Med. Lav*. 6: 149-156.

COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) No 1252/2014 of 28 May 2014 supplementing Directive 2001/83/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to principles and guidelines of good manufacturing practice for active substances for medicinal products for human use.

COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) No 895/2014 of 14 August 2014 amending Annex XIV to Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH).

Council Directive 98/24/EC of 7 April 1998 on the protection of the health and safety of workers from the risks related to chemical agents at work (consolidated version 28-6-2007) - Chemical Agents Directive.

COUNCIL DIRECTIVE of 21 December 1989 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to personal protective equipment (89/686/EEC)

Cox NH and Nustchin CP. (1969). Prolonged spontaneous and alcohol-induced flushing due to the solvent dimethylformamide. *Contact dermatitis*. 1991;24:69.

Craig DK, Weir RJ, Wagner W, Groth D. (1984). Subchronic Inhalation Toxicity of Dimethylformamide in Rats and Mice, *Drug and Chemical Toxicology*, 7:6, 551-571

Degirmenci E, Ono Y, Kawara O, Utsumi H (2000). Genotoxicity analysis and hazardousness prioritization of group of chemicals. *Water Sci Technol*, 42:125–31.

DFG. (2006). MAK Commission. Käfferlein HU. Addendum zu N,N-Dimethylformamid. In: Drexler H, Greim H (Hrsg) *Biologische Arbeitsstoff-Toleranz-Werte (BAT-Werte) und Expositionsäquivalente für krebs-erzeugende Arbeitsstoffe (EKA) und Biologische Leitwerte (BLW)*, 14. Lieferung, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim; <https://doi.org/10.1002/3527600418.bb6812d0014>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 316

DFG. (2017). MAK Commission. Hartwig A (Hrsg.) (2017) N,N-Dimethylformamid. Gesundheitsschädliche Arbeitsstoffe. Toxiko-logisch-arbeitsmedizinische Begründung von MAK-Werten. 62. Lieferung. Wiley-VCH, Weinheim; <https://doi.org/10.1002/3527600418.mb6812d0062>

DFG. (2019). MAK Commission Göen T, Drexler H, Hartwig A. (2019). Addendum to N,N-Dimethylformamide [N,N-Dimethylformamid, Addendum] BAT value documentation in German. doi:10.1002/3527600418.bb6812d0024

Ding YL, Ying GX and Jin LP. (2011). Occupational DMF poisoning causes death: A case report. *Occup Health Emerg Rescue* 29: 107-108.

DIRECTIVE 2001/83/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL OF 6 NOVEMBER 2001 ON THE COMMUNITY CODE RELATING TO MEDICINAL PRODUCTS FOR HUMAN USE

Ducatman AM, Conwill DE, Crawl J (1986). Germ cell tumors of the testicle among aircraft repairment. *J Urol*, 136(4):834–6.

DuPont Co. Report (1990). Pharmacokinetic and cell proliferation evaluations in rats and mice following single and multiple (10) inhalation exposure to N-N-Dimethylformamide. Testing laboratory: Haskell Laboratory for Toxicology and Industrial Medicine. Report no.: HL-150-90. Owner company: E. I. DuPont de Nemours and Company. Study number: 68-12-2-H-76. Report date: 1990-05-22.

Eben A, Kimmerle G. (1976). Metabolism Studies of N, N-Dimethylformamide (III. Studies about the Influence of Ethanol in Persons and Laboratory Animals). *Int Arch Occup Environ Hlth* 36,243-265 (1976).

European Chemical Agency (ECHA) (2019). Opinion of the Committee for Risk Assessment and Opinion of the committee for Socio-economic Analysis on an Annex XV dossier proposing restrictions of the manufacture, placing on the market or use of a substance within the EU

European Chemical Agency (ECHA) (2019b). Opinion of the Committee for Risk Assessment and Opinion of the committee for Socio-economic Analysis on an Annex XV dossier proposing restrictions of the manufacture, placing on the market or use of a substance within the EU. Annex to background document

Fail PA, George JD, Grizzle TB, Heindel JJ (1998). Formamide and dimethylformamide: reproductive assessment by continuous breeding in mice. *Reprod Toxicol*, 12(3):317–32.

Fiorito A, Larese F, Molinari S and Zanin T. (1997). Liver function alterations in synthetic leather workers exposed to dimethylformamide. *Am. J. Ind. Med.* 32: 255-260.

Garnier R, Chataigner D, Perez-Trigalou B, Efthymiou M.L. Intoxications

professionnelles par le dimethylformamide, *Archives des maladies professionnelles*, 1992, 53, n°2, pp. 111-120.

Goswami HK (1986). Cytogenetic effects of methyl isocyanate exposure in Bhopal. *Hum Genet*, 74(1):81–4.

Greim H. (1992). Occupational Toxicants. Critical Data Evaluation for MAK Values and Classification of Carcinogens, Vol.8. Wiley-VCH, ISBN 978-3527270385

Hanasono, G. K., Fuller, R. W., Broddle, W. D., and Gibson, W. R. (1977). Studies on the effects of N, N-dimethylformamide on ethanol disposition and monoamine oxidase activity in rats. *Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology*, 39, 461-472.

Hantson P, Galloy AC, Negri S, Esabon G, Lambiotte F, Haufroid V, Garnier R. 2010. Dimethylformamide metabolism following self-harm using a veterinary euthanasia product. *Clin Toxicol (Phila)*;48(7):725-9.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 317

Hastwell PW, Chai L-L, Roberts KJ, Webster TW, Harvey JS, Rees RW et al. (2006). High-specificity and high-sensitivity genotoxicity assessment in a human cell line: validation of the GreenScreen HC ADD45a-GFP genotoxicity assay. *Mutat Res*, 607(2):160–75.

He J, Wang P, Zhu JQ, Wu G, Ji JM, Xue Y (2010). Role of urinary biomarkers of N,N-dimethylformamide in the early detection of hepatic injury among occupational exposed workers. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health*, 83(4):399–406.

Health Canada (1999). Canadian Environmental Protection Act, 1999. Priority Substance List Assessment Report. N,N-Dimethylformamide. Environment Canada. Health Canada, February 2001.

Hellwig J, Merkle HJ, Klimisch RJ. (1991). Studies on the prenatal toxicity of N, N-Dimethylformamide in mice, rats and rabbits. *Fd. Chem. Tox.* (29):193-201.

Hennebruder K, Angerer J (2005). Determination of DMF modified DNA base N4-methylcarbamoylcytosine in human urine using off-line sample clean-up, two-dimensional LC and ESI-MS/MS detection. *J Chromatogr B Analyt Technol Biomed Life Sci*, 822(1-2):124–32.

Hundley SG, Lieder PH, Valentine R, Malley LA, and Kennedy GL. (1993a). Dimethylformamide Pharmacokinetics Following Inhalation Exposure to Rats and Mice. *Drug and Chem. Toxicol.* 16(1), 21-52.

Hundley SG, McCooley KT, Lieder PH., Hurtt ME, and Kennedy GL. (1993b). Dimethylformamide Pharmacokinetics Following Inhalation Exposure in Monkeys. *Drug and Chem. Toxicol.* 16 (1), 53-79.

Hurtt ME, McCooley KT, Placke ME, Kennedy GL. (1991). Ten-day repeated-exposure inhalation study of dimethylformamide (DMF) in cynomolgus monkeys. *Toxicol Lett.* 59(1-3):229-37.

IARC (2006). Formaldehyde, 2-butoxyethanol and 1-tert-butoxypropan-2-ol. IARC Monogr Eval Carcinog Risks Hum, 88:1–478. PMID:17366697. Available from: <http://monographs.iarc.fr/ENG/Monographs/vol88/index.php>

International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) (1999). IARC Monographs on the Evaluation of Carcinogenic Risks to Humans, Volume 71, Part Two World Health Organization, Lyon.

International Agency for Research on Cancer (Wang) (2018), Volume 115: Some chemicals. IARC monographs on the evaluation of carcinogenic risks to humans. World Health Organization, Lyon.

IPCS (International Programme on Chemical Safety) (1991). Environmental Health Criteria 114 "Dimethylformamide". |United Nations Environment Programme, 1-124, 1991. United Nations Environment Programme, International Labour Organisation, World Health Organization; 1-124, 1991.

Käfferlein HU and Angerer J. (2013). N-Acetyl-S-(N-methylcarbamoyl)-cysteinr (AMCC), N-hydroxymethyl-N-methylformamide (HMMF) and N-methylformamide (NMF) in urine. In the MAK collection of occupational Health and safety. Hartwig A, Drexler H. Wiley-VCH, Weinheim

Käfferlein HU, Ferstl C, Burkhart-Reichl A, Hennebrueder K, Drexler H, Bruening T, Angerer J. (2005). The use of biomarkers of exposure of N,N-dimethylformamide in health risk assessment and occupational hygiene in the polyacrylic fibre industry. *Occup Environ Med* 2005;62:330–336.

Käfferlein HU, Göen T, Müller J, Wrbitzky R., Angerer J. (2000). Biological monitoring of workers exposed to N,N-dimethylformamide in the synthetic fibre industry. *Int. Arch. Occup. Environ. Health* 73, 113–120

Käfferlein HU and Angerer J (1999). Determination of n-Acetyl-S-(n-methylcarbamoyl)-cysteine AMCC) in the general population using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *J Environ Monit* 1(5):465-469

Kawai T, Yasugi T, Mizunuma K, Watanabe T, Cai SX, Huang MY et al. (1992). Occupational dimethylformamide exposure. 2. Methylformamide excretion in urine after occupational dimethylformamide exposure. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health*, 63(7):455–60.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 318

Kennedy and Sherman (1986). Acute and subchronic toxicity of dimethylformamide and dimethylacetamide following various routes of administration. *Drug Chem Toxicol*, 1986;9(2):147-70

Kennedy GL. (2012). Toxicology of dimethyl and monomethyl derivatives of acetamide and formamide: a second update. *Crit Rev Toxicol*, 42(10):793-826.

Kestell P, Gledhill AP, Threadgill MD, Gescher A. (1986b). S-(N-methylcarbonyl)-N-acetylcysteine: A Urinary Metabolite of the Hepatotoxic Experimental Antitumor Agent N-methylformamide (NSC 3051) in Mouse, Rat and Man. *Biochemical Pharmacology*, Vol. 35, No. 14, pp. 2283-2286, 1986 (also cited in BUA-Stoffdossier N, NDimethylformamid, Stand 04/91).

Kestell P, Threadgill MD, Gescher A, Gledhill AP, Shaw AJ, Farmer PB (1987). An investigation of the relationship between the hepatotoxicity and the metabolism of N-alkylformamides. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther*. 1987 Jan; 240(1):265-70.

Kilo S, Göen T, Drexler H. (2016). Cross-sectional study on effects on liver and alcohol intolerance N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF). *Int Arch Occup Environ Health*. 89(8):1309-1320.

Kim KW & Chung YH. (2013). Hepatotoxicity in rats treated with dimethylformamide or toluene or both. *Toxicol Res* 29, 187-193

Kimmerle G, and Macheimer L. (1975). Studies with N,N-dimethylformamide for embryotoxic and teratogenic effects on rats after dynamic inhalation. *Int. Arch. Arbeitsmedizin* 34, 167-175.

Knight AW, Billinton N, Cahill PA, Scott A, Harvey JS, Roberts KJ et al. (2007). An analysis of results from 305 compounds tested with the yeast RAD54-GFP genotoxicity assay (GreenScreen GC)-including relative predictivity of regulatory tests and rodent carcinogenesis and performance with autofluorescent and coloured compounds. *Mutagenesis*, 22(6):409–16.

Koudela K, Spazier K (1981). Results of cytogenetic examination of persons working in an environment of increased concentration of dimethylformamide vapours in the atmosphere. *Prac Lek*, 33:121–3.

Lauwerys RR, Kivits A, Lhoir M, Rigolet P, Houbeau D, Bouchet JP, Roels HA (1980). Biological Surveillance of Workers Exposed to Dimethylformamide and the Influence of Skin Protection on Its Percutaneous Absorption. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health* 45, 189-203 (1980).

Lei Y, Xiao S, Chen S, Zhang H, Li H, Lu Y. (2017). N dimethylformamide induced acute hepatic failure: A case report and literature review. *EXPERIMENTAL AND THERAPEUTIC MEDICINE* 14: 5659-5663, 2017.

Lelièvre B, et al. Two case-reports of intoxication with T61®, a mixture used in veterinary medicine. *Toxicologie Analytique et Clinique*. 2014;26(2):S24.

Levin, S.M., D.B. Baker, P.J. Landrigan, S.V. Monaghan, E. Frumin, M. Braithwaite and W. Towne. (1987). Testicular cancer in leather tanners exposed to dimethyl-formamide. *Lancet* ii: 1153.

Li MJ, Zeng T. (2019). The deleterious effects of N,N-dimethylformamide on liver: A mini-review. *Chemico-Biological Interactions* 298 (2019) 129–136.

Liu Q, Du F, Tan L, Wang BW and Zhou YW. (2011). Occupational DMF poisoning causes death: A case report. *Chin J Forensic Med* 24: 60-61, Lobanowa, K.P. (1958): *Gig. Sanit.* 23 (5), (1958); cited in: Henschler, D.: *MAKWertbegruendung Dimethylformamid*, Weinheim, (1990) (cited also in *OECD SIDS*, 2004).

Lundberg I, Pehrsson A, Lundberg S, Kronevi T, Lidums V. (1983). Delayed Dimethylformamide Biotransformation after High Exposures in Rats. *Toxicol. Letters* 17, 29-34.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 319

Luo JC, Kuo HW, Cheng TJ, Chang MJ. Abnormal liver function associated with occupational exposure to dimethylformamide and hepatitis B virus. *J Occup Environ Med.* 2001 May;43(5):474-82.

Lyle WH, Spence TWM, McKinneley WM, Duckers K. (1979). Dimethylformamide and alcohol intolerance. *British Journal of Industrial Medicine*, 1979, 36, 63-66.

Lynch DW, Placke ME, Persing RL, Ryan MJ (2003). Thirteen-Week Inhalation Toxicity of N, N-Dimethylformamide in F344/N Rats and B6C3F1 Mice. *Toxicological Sciences* 72, 347–358.

Major, J, Hudak A, Kiss G, Jakab MG, Szaniszló J, Naray N, Nagy I, Tompa A (1998). Follow-up biological and genotoxicological monitoring of acrylonitrile-and dimethylformamide-exposed viscose rayon plant workers. *Environ. Mol. Mutagen.* 31:301-310.

Malley LA, Slone TW Jr, Van Pelt C, Elliott GS, Ross PE, Stadler JC, Kennedy GL Jr. (1994). Chronic toxicity/oncogenicity of dimethylformamide in rats and mice following inhalation exposure. *Fundam Appl Toxicol.* 1994 Aug;23(2):268-79.

McQueen CA, Way BM, Williams GM (1988). Genotoxicity of carcinogens in human hepatocytes: application in hazard assessment. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol*, 96(2):360–6.

Merkle, J. und Zeller, H (1980). *Arzneimittel-Forsch. (Drug Res.)* 30, 9, 1557-1562.

Midorikawa K, Murata M, Oikawa S, Tada-Oikawa S, Kawanishi S (2000). DNA damage by dimethylformamide: role of hydrogen peroxide generated during degradation. *Chem Res Toxicol*, 13(4):309–15.

Miyauchi H, Minozoe A, Tanaka S, Arito H, Tsukahara T (2014). Seasonal difference in percutaneous absorption of N,N-dimethylformamide as determined using two urinary metabolites. *J Occup health*, 56(4):252–9.

Miyauchi H, Tsuda Y, Minozoe A, Tanaka S, Arito H, Tsukahara T et al. (2014). Occupational exposure to N,N-dimethylformamide in the summer and winter. *Ind Health*, 52(6):512–20.

Mráz J, Cross H, Gescher A, Threadgill MD, Flek J (1989) Differences between Rodents and Humans in the Metabolic Toxicification of N,N-Dimethylformamide. *Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology*. 98, 507-516.

Mráz J, Gescher A, Cross H, Shaw AJ, Flek J (1991). New Findings in the Metabolism of N,N-dimethylformamide – Consequences for Evaluation of Occupational Risk. *The Science of the Total Environment*, 101 (t 99 t) 131 – 134.

Mráz J, Jheeta P, Gescher A, Hyland R, Thummel K, Threadgill MD (1993). Investigation of the Mechanistic Basis of N,N-Dimethylformamide Toxicity. *Metabolism of N,N-Dimethylformamide and Its Deuterated Isotopomers by Cytochrome P450* *Chem. Res. Toxicol.* 6, 197-207.

Mráz J, Nohová H (1992a). Absorption, metabolism and elimination of N, dimethylformamide in humans. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health* (1992) 64:85-92.

Mráz J, Nohová H (1992b). Percutaneous absorption of N,N-dimethylformamide in humans. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health* (1992) 64:79-83. Testing laboratory: Institute of Hygiene and Epidemiology, Srobárova 48, 100 42 Prague 10, Czechoslovakia.

Mráz J, Turecek F (1987). Identification of N-acetyl-S-(N-methylcarbamoyl)cysteine, a human metabolite of N,N-dimethylformamide and N-methylformamide. *J Chromatogr*: 6;414 (2): 399-404.

Natarajan AT, Kesteren-van Leeuwen AC (1981). untitled (carcinogenicity study). *Progress in Mutation Research*, Vol. 1, 551-559, 1981 (in de Serres and Ashby: Evaluation of short-term tests for carcinogens).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 320

Nicolas F, Rodineau P, Rouzioux GM, Tack I, Chabac S, Meram D (1990). Fulminant hepatic failure in poisoning due to ingestion of T61, a veterinary euthanasia drug. *Crit Care Med* 18:573–575.

Nomiyama T, Nakashima H, Chen LL, Tanaka SH, Miyauchi T, Yamauchi H, Sakurai, Omae K (2001). N, N-dimethylformamide: significance of dermal absorption and adjustment method for urinary N-methylformamide concentration as a biological exposure item. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health* (2001) 74:224-228.

Ohbayashi H, Umeda Y, Senoh H, Kasai T, Kano H, Nagano K, Arito H, Fukushima S (2009). Enhanced hepatocarcinogenicity by combined inhalation and oral exposures to N,N-dimethylformamide in male rats. *J. Toxicol. Sci.* 34, 53–63.

Ohbayashi H, Yamazaki K, Aiso S, Nagano K, Shoji F, Ohta H (2008). Enhanced proliferative response of hepatocytes to combined inhalation and oral exposures to N,N-dimethylformamide in male rats. *J. Toxicol. Sci.* 33, 327–338.

Qi C, Gu Y, Sun Q, Gu H, Xu B, Gu Q, Xiao J, Lian Y (2017). Low-Dose N,N-Dimethylformamide Exposure and Liver Injuries in a Cohort of Chinese Leather Industry Workers. *J Occup Environ Med.* 59(5):434-439..

Redlich Beckett CA, Sparer J, Barwick KW, Riely CA, Miller H, Sigal SL, Shalat SL and Cullen MR (1988). Liver disease associated with occupational exposure to the solvent dimethylformamide. *Ann. Intern. Med.* 108: 680-686.

Redlich CA, West AB, Fleming L, True LD, Cullen MR, Riely CA (1990). Clinical and pathological characteristics of hepatotoxicity associated with occupational exposure to dimethylformamide. *Gastroenterology* 99: 748-757.

REGULATION (EC) No 1223/2009 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 30 November 2009 on cosmetic products. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32009R1223&from=FR> accessed in June 2020

Saillenfait, AM, Payan JP, Beydon D, Fabry JP, Langonne I, Sabate JP, Gallissot F (1997). Assessment of the developmental toxicity, metabolism, and placental transfer of N, N-dimethylformamide administered to pregnant rats. *Fund. and Appl. Toxicol.*, 39 (1), 33-43, 1997.

Sakai T, Kageyama H, Araki T, Yosida T, Kuribayashi T, Masuyama Y (1995). Biological monitoring of workers exposed to N,N-dimethylformamide by determination of the urinary metabolites, N-methylformamide and N-acetyl-S-(N-methylcarbamoyl) cysteine. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health*, 67(2):125–9.

Scailteur V, de Hoffmann E, Buchet JP, Lauwerys R (1984). Study on in vivo and in vitro Metabolism of Dimethylformamide in Male and Female Rats. *Toxicology*, 29 (1984) 221-234.

SCOEL 2006. Recommendation from the Scientific Committee for Occupational Exposure Limits on N,N-Dimethylformamide. SCOEL/SUM/121.

<https://www.ser.nl/api/Mfiles/DownloadFirstDocument?Id=a82bb486-811a-47c3-b095-1ce8f3c2f1ac>, downloaded 2020-10-16

Seiji K, Inoue O, Cai SX, Kawai T, Watanabe T, Ikeda M (1992). Increase in sister chromatid exchange rates in association with occupational exposure to N,N-dimethylformamide. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health*, 64(1):65–7.

Senoh H, Aiso S, Arito H, Nishizawa T, Nagano K, Yamamoto S, Matsushima T. (2004). Carcinogenicity and chronic toxicity after inhalation exposure of rats and mice to N,N-dimethylformamide. *J. Occup. Health* 46, 429–439.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 321

Senoh, H., Katagiri, T., Arito, H., Nishizawa, T., Nagano, K., Yamamoto, S., and Matsushima, T. (2003). Toxicity due to 2- and 13-wk Inhalation Exposures of Rats and Mice to N, N-Dimethylformamide. *J Occup Health* 2003; 45: 365–375. Testing laboratory: Japan

Shieh DB, Chen CC, Shih TS, Tai HM, Wei YH, Chang HY. (2007). Mitochondrial DNA alterations in blood of the humans exposed to N,N-dimethylformamide. *Chem Biol Interact*, 165(3):211–9.

Sohn JH, Han MJ, Lee MY, Kang SK, Yang JS. (2005). Simultaneous determination of N-hydroxymethyl-N-methylformamide, N-methylformamide and N-acetyl-S-(N-methylcarbamoyl)cystein in urine samples from workers exposed to N,N-dimethylformamide by liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry. *J Pharm Biomed Anal*, 37(1):165–70.

Tice RR, Austin CP, Kavlock RJ, Bucher JR. (2013). Improving the human hazard characterization of chemicals: a Tox21 update. *Environ Health Perspect*, 121(7):756–65.

Tomasini, M., A. Todaro, M. Piazzoni and G.F. Peruzzo (1983): [Exposure to dimethylformamide: study of 14 cases.] *Med. Lav.* 74: 217-220 (in Italian, with English abstract).

Tong Z, Shi J, Zhu X and Zhu B: Death after exposure to dimethylformamide. (2014). A case report. *Chin J Ind Hyg Occup Dis* 32: 285-286.

Trevisani F, Trame MR, Bernardi N. (1993). Severe hepatic failure occurring with T61 ingestion in an attempted suicide. *Dig DisSci*;38:752-6.

Walrath J, Fayerweather WE, Gilby PG, Pell S (1989). A case-control study of cancer among Du Pont employees with potential for exposure to dimethylformamide. *J Occup Med* 31(5), 432-438.

Wang C, Huang C, Wei Y, Zhu Q, Tian W, Zhang Q (2014). Short-term exposure to dimethylformamide and the impact on digestive system disease: an outdoor study for volatile organic compound. *Environ Pollut*, 190:133–8.

Wang C, Yang J, Lu D, Fan Y, Zhao M, Li Z. (2015). Oxidative stress-related DNA damage and homologous recombination repairing induced by N,N-dimethylformamide. *J Appl Toxicol*, 36(7):936–45.

Wang JD, Lai MY, Chen JS, Lin JM, Chiang JR, Shiao SJ, Chang WS (1991). Dimethylformamide-induced liver damage among synthetic leather workers. *Archives of Environmental Health: An International Journal*. Volume 46, Issue 3, pp. 161-166.

Wang VS, Shih TS, Cheng CC, Chang HY, Lai JS, Lin CC. (2004). Evaluation of current biological exposure index for occupational N, N-dimethylformamide exposure from synthetic leather workers. *J Occup Environ Med*, 46(7):729–36.

Wolff, PH (1972). Ethnic differences in alcohol sensitivity. *Science* 175, 449-45.

Wrbitzky R, Angerer J (1998). N, N- Dimethylformamide influence of working conditions and skin penetration on the internal exposure of workers in synthetic textile production. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health* (1998) 71: 309-316.

Wrbitzky R (1999). Liver function in workers exposed N, N-dimethylformamide during the production of synthetic textiles. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health* (1999) 72: 19-25.

Wu Z, Liu Q, Wang C, Xu B, Guan M, Ye M, Jiang H, Zheng M, Zhang M, Zhao W, Jiang X, Leng S, Cheng J. (2017). A comparative benchmark dose study for N, N-Dimethylformamide induced liver injury in a Chinese occupational cohort.

Xing M, Chen Q, Lou X, Zhang M, Cai D, Xia Y (2014). [Toxicity of intragastrically administered N, N-dimethylformamide in female Wistar rats] *Zhonghua Lao Dong Wei Sheng Zhi Ye Bing Za Zhi*, 32(5):370–3. [Chinese]

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 322

Yang JS, Kim EA, Lee MY, Park IJ, Kang SK (2000). Biological monitoring of occupational exposure to N,N-dimethylformamide—the effects of co-exposure to toluene or dermal exposure. *Int Arch Occup Environ health*, 73(7):463–70.

Yang C, Ger J, Lin S, Yang G, Deng J (1994). Abdominal colic occurred in workers in a dye manufacturing plant. *Vet. Hum. Toxicol.* 36: 345 (cited in Health Canada, 1999).

Yonemoto J, Suzuki S (1980). Relation of exposure to dimethylformamide vapor and the metabolite, methylformamide, in urine of workers. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health*, 46(2):159-65.

Zhang H, Liu Q, Duan Y, Dong H and Zhou Y (2015). Chronic occupational N,N dimethylformamide poisoning induced death: A case report. *Forensic Sci Med Pathol* 11: 584 588.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 323

11 Annexes

11.1 Annex 1: Exposure

Environmental exposure

Levels of DMF measured in air and levels of DMF metabolites found in urine in the general population are presented in the tables below.

Table V.9: Atmospheric levels of DMF in two studies (IARC, 2018)

Country	Subjects	DMF in air ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	N-Methylformamide (total) in urine (mg/g cr):	Reference
China	Unpolluted area (N=366)	Mean = 98.3 (range 4.4-678.3)	-	Wang et al. 2014
	Near synthetic leather factories (N=133)	Mean = 180 to 565	1.5 to 23.4	
Japan	On 35 sites all over Japan	Geometric mean = 0.092 (n=105)	-	Ministry of Environment Japan (2012)

Table V.10: Concentrations of AMCC (a metabolite of DMF) found in the general population in USA, (campaign 2013-2014 of the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, NHANES by the Center of Disease Control (CDC, 2019 vol.1 and vol.2)

Subjects	N-Acetyl-S-(N-methylcarbamoyl) cystein levels in Urine (AMCC): Geometric mean (95 % conf. interval)
All (N= 2629)	124 (112-136) $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ and 143 (129-159) $\mu\text{g}/\text{g cr}$
Age 6-11 years (N=396)	53.4 (47.7-59.7) $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ and 79.9 (72.4-88.2) $\mu\text{g}/\text{g cr}$
Age 11-19 years (N=448)	87.7 (71-108) $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ and 79.5 (69.2-91.4) $\mu\text{g}/\text{g cr}$
Age 20 + years (N=1785)	142 (128-158) $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ and 166 (148-186) $\mu\text{g}/\text{g cr}$
Non smokers (adult) N=1370	108 (97.7-119) $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ and 129 (115-145) $\mu\text{g}/\text{g cr}$
Cigarette smokers (adult) N=908	423 (358-499) $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ and 431 (357-521) $\mu\text{g}/\text{g cr}$

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 324

Occupational exposure

Table V.11: Levels of atmospheric DMF and concentrations of its metabolites

	DMFair		Metabolites		Reference
	Number of subjects	Concentration Mean/median/ Geometric Mean (GM) (range or deviation standard (SD))	Number of subjects	Concentration Mean/median/ Geometric Mean (GM) (range or deviation standard (SD))	
Leather production	43	GM: 7 ppm			Cai et al. 1992
Polyurethane production	65	GM: 2.3 ppm			
Shoe sole production	17	GM: 0.6 ppm			
Laboratory A				-	
Laboratory B	23	GM: 0.3 ppm			
Leather printing	59	GM: 0.1 ppm			
Resin production	52	GM: 2.1 ppm			
	59	GM: 0.3 ppm			
Polyacrylic fibre	63	Median: 1.47 ppm (<0.1-159.8)	92	tNMF (End of shift, ES) Mean (+/- SD): 13.1 (+/- 19.66) mg.L ⁻¹ (median: 6.44) AMCC (ES): Mean (+/- SD): 14,3 (+/- 15.60) mg.g ⁻¹ cr (median: 8,8 mg.g ⁻¹ cr)	Käfferlein et al. 2000
Polyacrylic fibre	-	-	34	tNMF (median (Min-Max)): ES, end of week (ES/EW) 10.2 (1.6-59.7) mg/L 9.6 (2.5-72.8) mg/g cr AMCC (median (Min-Max)); ES/EW: 11.3 (0.6-116.5) mg/L 8.5 (1.3-56.2) mg/g cr	Käfferlein et al. 2005

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 325

	DMFair		Metabolites		Reference
	Number of subjects	Concentration Mean/median/ Geometric Mean (GM) (range or deviation standard (SD))	Number of subjects	Concentration Mean/median/ Geometric Mean (GM) (range or deviation standard (SD))	
				MCVal (median) ; ES/EW: 121.1 (21.3-464.9) nmol/g globin	
Polyacrylic fibre	118	Mean: 12.5 (nd-115.2)	125	tNMF (Mean); ES: 4.7 (0.4-62.3) mg/g cr 7.1 (0.86-100)mg/L	Wrbitzky and Angerer 1998
Synthetic leather	100	Mean: 22 (8-58) mg/m ³			Cirla et al. 1984
Synthetic leather	125	Geo. Mean: 8.9 mg/m ³ (0.4-75.2)	125	tNMF (Geo. Mean); ES/EW: 12.87 (2.80–61.40) mg/L AMCC (Geo. Mean); ES/EW: 18.15 (4.1-59.8) mg/L	Imbriani et al 2002
Synthetic resin Winter	142	Geo. mean: 3 mg/m ³	142	tNMF Geo. Mean (GSD); ES/EW: 1.4 (4.1) mg/L 2.1 (4.7) mg/g cr AMCC Geo. Mean (GSD); Before workshift (BS/EW): 2.7 (3.8) mg/L 4.9 (4.7) mg/g cr	Miyauchi et al. 2014
Synthetic resin Summer	128	Geo. mean: 5.2 mg/m ³	128	tNMF Geo. Mean (GSD); ES/EW: 4.1 (4.8) mg/L 3.1 (4.7) mg/g cr	

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 326

	DMFair		Metabolites		Reference
	Number of subjects	Concentration Mean/median/ Geometric Mean (GM) (range or deviation standard (SD))	Number of subjects	Concentration Mean/median/ Geometric Mean (GM) (range or deviation standard (SD))	
				AMCC <u>Geo. Mean (GSD)</u> ; BS/EW: 5.2 (3.0) mg/L 6.7 (3.6) mg/g cr	
Synthetic leather	116	<u>Geo. Mean (+/- SD)</u> : 8.8 ppm (3.2)	143 144	<u>tNMF Geo. Mean (+/- GSD)</u> ; ES: 47.5 (+/- 2.3) mg/L <u>AMCC Geo. Mean (+/- GSD)</u> ; ES: 7.3 (+/- 3.1)mg/L	Kim et al. 2004
Synthetic leather	75	<u>Geo. Mean (+/- SD)</u> 1.51 ppm (+/- 4.81) (0.02–19.37)	75	<u>tNMF Geo. Mean (+/- SD)</u> ; ES: 0.47 (+/- 12.68) mg/L (0.03-104.39) <u>DMF in urine (Geo. Mean (+/- SD)</u> ; ES: <u>0.38 (+/-9.21) mg/L (0.02-15.28)</u>	Chang et al. 2004a
Synthetic leather	13	Median: 10.6 ppm (6.65–34.48)	13	<u>tNMF (Median)</u> ; ES: 13.8 mg/L (7.5-73.7) <u>AMCC (Median)</u> ; BS: 40.7 mg/L (6.8-442.2)	Shieh et al. 2007

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 327

	DMFair		Metabolites		Reference
	Number of subjects	Concentration Mean/median/ Geometric Mean (GM) (range or deviation standard (SD))	Number of subjects	Concentration Mean/median/ Geometric Mean (GM) (range or deviation standard (SD))	
Synthetic leather	All 335	<u>Geo. mean</u> 2.62 ppm (5.30)	All 335	<u>tNMF Geo. Mean (GSD); ES:</u> 14.50 (3.9) mg/L	Yang et al. 2000
	178 (inhalation +dermal)	<u>Geo. mean</u> 6.27 (2.85) ppm	178 (inhalation +dermal)	<u>tNMF Geo. Mean (GSD); ES:</u> 24.39 (3.09) mg/L End-shift	
	37 (inhalation only)	<u>Geo. mean</u> 2.07 ppm (4.17)	37 (inhalation only)	<u>tNMF Geo. Mean (GSD); ES:</u> 8.23 (3.52) mg/L	
Synthetic fibres industry	220 EW 175 C	Mean (+/- SD) 6.2 +/- 7.6 mg/m ³ Median (min-max) 3.31 mg/m ³ (0.08-46.9)	220 EW 175 C	<u>tNMF; ES:</u> Mean = 7.75 (+/- 8.82) mg/L Median = 4.83 mg/L (>LOD-50.55) <u>AMCC; ES:</u> Mean = 9.42 (+/- 10.42) mg/g cr Median = 4.84 (0.006-49.6) mg/g cr <u>McVal ; ES:</u> Mean = 83.3 (+/- 83.1) nmol/g globin Median = 60.5 (0.5-414) nmol/g globin	Kilo et al. 2016

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 328

11.2 Annex 2: Chronic toxicity

In humans

Table V.12: Chronic toxicity reported in occupational studies (SCOEL, 2006 and ECHA, 2019)

Reference	Subjects	Exposure DMF in the air (DMFa) (Mean/Median/range) Metabolites (Mean/Median or range)	Results/observations
Lyle et al., 1979 <i>England</i>	Workers (DMF used as solvent) N=102) Case report	<u>DMFa</u> Range: >10 to 200 ppm <u>tNMFu</u> in urine (tNMFu) Range: <10 to 77µl/l (9.5 to 73 mg/L*)	Alcohol intolerance reactions Facial flushing and other symptoms in 19 workers. 26 of the 34 episodes occurred after the workers had consumed alcoholic drinks (liver function not investigated)
Yonemoto and Suzuki, 1980 <i>Japan</i>	Workers (synthetic leather factory) N=9 Case report	<u>DMFa</u> 0-5 ppm (TWA) Post-Shift (PS) <u>tNMFu</u> Range: 0.4–19.56 mg/d	No effect on serum biochemistry (enzymes liver). Alcohol intolerance (6/11 workers less tolerant than before but no typical signs of alcohol intolerance)
Lauwerys <i>et al.</i> , 1980 <i>Belgium</i>	Workers in acrylic fibre factory N= 22 (+ 28 controls) Cohort study	<u>DMFa</u> Median 13 mg/m ³ (1.3-46.6 mg/m ³), (4.5 (0.4-15.3) ppm) Stationary sampling <u>tNMFu</u> <40-50 mg.g ⁻¹ cr (PS)	No abnormal effects on serum biochemistry. Signs of alcohol intolerance in some workers.
Tomasini <i>et al.</i> , 1983 <i>Italy</i>	Workers in synthetic leather production N=13 Case report	<u>DMFa</u> 5-20 ppm (15-60 mg/m ³)	Main symptoms: irritation of eyes and upper airways, digestive tract (11/13) Increase of hepatic enzymes (2/13) Hepatic pain and palpable liver (4/13) Alcohol intolerance (8/13)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 329

Reference	Subjects	Exposure DMF in the air (DMFa) (Mean/Median/range) Metabolites (Mean/Median or range)	Results/observations
Catenacci <i>et al.</i> , 1984 <i>Italy</i>	N=54 (employed >5 y) acrylic fiber plant 2 groups exposed + (+54 controls)	Group 1 (N=28) <u>DMFa</u> : 6 (4-8) ppm <u>tNMFu</u> : 22.3 mg/l Group 2 (N=26): <u>DMFa</u> : 1 (0.6-1.6) ppm <u>tNMFu</u> : 7 mg/l	No significant effects on liver enzymes in the 2 groups
Cirla <i>et al.</i> , 1984 <i>Italy</i>	N= 100 (+100 controls)	DMFa: TWA 7 (2.6-19) ppm, (9-60) mg/m ³ .	Abnormal values of liver enzymes (not significant). Alcohol intolerance (39/100) and reduced alcohol consumption. Symptoms (headache, nausea, dizziness, eye irritation, gastritis).
Wang <i>et al.</i> , 1991 <i>China</i>	Workers Synthetic leather factory N = 183 Categorised into 3 groups of exposure	DMFa: <10 ppm	ALT increased in 6.4 % of the workers with alcohol consumption >24 g/d
		DMFa: 10-40 ppm	ALT increased CPK increased (indicator of muscle damage); 3.7 % of the workers with alcohol consumption >24 g/d
		DMFa: 25-60 ppm	ALT increased (p=0.01); Incidence of abnormal ALT values sign. increase (>35 IU/l); CPK increased; no workers with alcohol consumption >24 g/d
Cai <i>et al.</i> , 1992 Workers N=207 (production China	Workers in production of polyurethane plastics N=207	DMFa: 4.5 ppm (stationary sampling)	Symptoms such as: eye irritation, nasal irritation, sore throat, unusual taste, nausea, vomiting, shortage of breath, abdominal pain, dry mouth, frequent cough). Liver enzymes for some cases above normal range
	Workers in laboratories N=82	DMFa: 0.2 ppm and 1.9 ppm	No increased alcohol intolerance
	Shoe-sole production N=17	DMFa: 0.7 ppm	No increased alcohol intolerance

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 330

Reference	Subjects	Exposure DMF in the air (DMFa) (Mean/Median/range) Metabolites (Mean/Median or range)	Results/observations
	Polyurethane production N= 65	DMFa: 3.9 ppm	Increased alcohol intolerance (71 %)
Yang et al., 1994 Taiwan	Workers (N=13) Case report	DMFa: 10.3-42.1 ppm (STEL 15m) PS	Abdominal colic (7/13) Abnormal liver function and facial flushing (3/13)
Sakai et al., 1995 Japan	Workers (N=10) Case report	DMFa: Geometric mean: 2.5 – 10.4 ppm PS tNMFu: 24.7+/- 5.4 mg/g cr	No effects on liver enzymes
Fiorito <i>et al.</i> , 1997 (Italy)	N=75 Factory of synthetic leather And 75 controls (unexposed workers)	Group 1 (Washing) N=10 <u>DMFa</u> : GM (+/-GSD): 21.5 (+/- 2) mg.m ⁻³ Range 5-40 Group 2 (Production) N=22 GM (+/-GSD): 18.7 (+/- 1.8) mg.m ⁻³ Range 5-40 tNMFu (N=22): 13.6+/-3.3 mg/L or 13.4+/-3.2 mg/g cr PS	Effects on liver enzymes (12/75) Abnormal liver function (12/75 with increased of 2 liver enzymes levels compared to controls – p<0.01) Alcohol intolerance (in 50 % exposed workers) with such as face flushing (38 %), palpitations (30 %), headache (22 %), body flushing (15 %), and tremors (14 %) 50 % reported gastrointestinal symptoms (stomach pain, nausea, loss of appetite)
Wrbitzky and Angerer, (1998); Wrbitzky, (1999) Germany	all workers in acrylic plant N=126	DMFa: 4.1+/-7.4 (<0.1-37.9) ppm tNMFu: 14.9+/-18.7 (0.9-100) mg/l (9.1+/-11.4 (0.5-62.3) mg/g cr	Synergetic effect with alcohol Effects on liver enzymes
	Finishing N=55	DMFa: 14.2+/-2.2 (>0.1-13.7) ppm tNMFu: 4.5+/-4.3	Effects on liver enzymes in workers drinking alcohol
	Dyeing N=12	DMFa: 2.5+/-3.1 (0.1-9.8) ppm tNMFu: 6.7+/-5.4 (0.8-17.2) mg/g cr	No effects on liver enzymes? in workers not drinking alcohol Reduced alcohol consumption in workers drinking alcohol
	Dry spinning N=28	DMFa: 6.4-9.6 (0.8-36.9) ppm tNMFu: 11.6+/-13.1 (0.9-62.3) mg/g cr	

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 331

Reference	Subjects	Exposure DMF in the air (DMFa) (Mean/Median/range) Metabolites (Mean/Median or range)	Results/observations
	Wet spinning N=30	DMFa: 7.3+/-10.2 (0.3-37.9) ppm tNMFu: 16.0+/-15.9 (0.4-54.0) mg/g cr	
Wrbitzky 1999	126 +and 54 controls Factory of synthetic leather	DMFa: 0.1 to 37.9 ppm (median: 1.2)	AST and γ GT levels were significantly elevated among DMF exposed workers. Under the given workplace conditions, the hepatotoxic effects of alcohol were more pronounced than those of DMF.
Luo et al., 2001 Tawain	Workers synthetic leather and resins factory N=176	2.9 +/-1.1 (0.1-5) ppm	Abnormal liver function (18 %)
		6.4+/- 0.7 (5.9-8.2) ppm	Abnormal liver function (27 %)
		24.6+/- 15.6 (11.2-86.6) ppm	Abnormal liver function (37 %) Significant effect on individual liver enzymes, chronic liver diseases
Kim et al., 2004	N= 144	10 ppm	Alcohol intolerance?
He et al., 2010 China	Organic chemical factory N=79 (58 men and 21 women)	Group1 (N=33): Low exposure (GM+/-GSD) DMFa: < 4.55 mg.m ⁻³ DMFu: 0.26 (0.32) mg.g ⁻¹ creatinine tNMFu: 1.80 (3.24) mg.g ⁻¹ creatinine AMCCu: 4.25 (3.78) mg.g ⁻¹ creatinine Group2 (N=24): Medium exposure (GM+/-GSD) DMFa: 9 - 19.45 mg.m ⁻³ DMFu: 0.53 (0.42) mg.g ⁻¹ creatinine tNMFu: 9.6 (10.36) mg.g ⁻¹ creatinine AMCCu: 25.4 (12.45) mg.g ⁻⁶ creatinine Group3 (N=22): high exposure (GM+/-GSD) DMFa: 36 mg.m ⁻³ DMFu: 1.78 (2.79) mg.g ⁻⁶ creatinine	About 60 % of subjects with urine AMCC concentration above 40 mg/g creatinine had raised liver enzymes activities

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 332

Reference	Subjects	Exposure DMF in the air (DMFa) (Mean/Median/range) Metabolites (Mean/Median or range)	Results/observations
		tNMFu: 26.5 (23.4) mg.g ⁻⁶ creatinine AMCCu: 45.5 (19.6) mg.g ⁻⁶ creatinine	
Kilo et al., 2016 Germany	N=220 workers (+175 Controls)	DMFa: 6.2 +/- 7.6 mg/m ³ (mean+/- SD) tNMFu: Mean = 7.75 (+/- 8.82) mg/l AMCCu: Mean = 9.42 (+/- 10.42) mg/g cr McVal: Mean = 83.3 (+/- 83.1) nmol/g globin	None of the tested liver enzyme activities showed a positive association with any of the three exposure markers Alcohol intolerance reactions (not influencing alcohol consumption behavior)
Wu et al., 2017 China	Poylurethane synthetic factory (China) N=698 (508 M and 190 F) (+188 Controls)	Moderate exposure (N=325): DMFa: 6.3 and 9.6 mg.m ⁻³ High exposure (N=325): DMFa > 30 mg.m ⁻³ tNMFu: 1.75 mg/l AMCCu: 44.09 mg/l MCVal in blood: 46 nmol/g globin	Liver injury assessed by measurement of liver enzymes levels and compared to reference values range (AST and ALT: 0-45, γGT: 8-58U/L) tNMF: BMDL ₁₀ =14 mg/L; AMCC = 155 mg/L and MCVal = 93.3 nmol/g Male workers: tNMF: BMDL ₁₀ =10.9 mg/L; AMCC = 119 mg/L and MCVal = 97 nmol/g
Qi et al., 2017 China	N=429	7 (3-21.6) mg/m ³ TWA	Increased incidence of liver injury (ALT or AST at twice the normal upper limit)

* calculated

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 333

In animals

Table V.13: Liver toxicity studies in animals

Reference	Species – route - doses	Results
Craig et al. 1984	Rats and mice (N= n/a) 0, 150, 300, 600, 1200 ppm for 6h/d, 5h/w for 12 weeks inhalation	Depression in body weight gain in rats significant at 1200 ppm Liver identified as the target organ (clinical chemistry (in rats only) and gross necropsy observations, and histopathology) NOAEL = 150 ppm
Malley et al. 1994	Rat and mice - (Rats: N=87/sex/gp and Mice: N= 78/sex/gp) 0, 25, 100, or 400 ppm DMF for 6 hr/day, 5 days/week for 18 months (mice) or 2 years (rats) by inhalation (whole body)	Rats and mice: 100 and 400 ppm produced increased relative liver weights, centrilobular hepatocellular hypertrophy, lipofuscin/hemosiderin accumulation in Kupffer cells NOEL = 25 ppm (80 mg/m ³)
Senoh et al. 2003	Rats and mice (N=10/sex/gp) 0, 100, 200, 400, 800, 1600 ppm – 6 h/d, 5d/w for 2 weeks 0, 100, 200, 400, 800, 1600 ppm for 13 weeks study inhalation	Increased relative liver weight (rats and mice) : BMDL ₁₀ = 1 ppm Hepatocellular hypertrophy (male mice): BMDL ₁₀ = 17 ppm
Lynch et al. 2003	Rats (N=30/sex/gp) and mice (N=10/sex/gp) inhalation exposure: 0, 50, 100, 200, 400, 800 ppm (6h/day, 5 days/week)	Rats: Decreased body weights gains (47-65 % in rats exposed to 800 ppm) Increased relative testis weight (400 and 800 ppm) Minimal to moderate centrilobular hepatocellular necrosis (both sexes at 400 ppm) NOAEC = 200 ppm Mice: Increased liver weight at 50 ppm

11.3 Annex 3: HBM parameters

Table V.14: Relationships between effects and BME levels

Ref	Reported health effects	Concentrations of total NMF in urine		Concentrations of AMCC in urine		Concentration of MCV _{al} in blood
		End of shift				
		mg/g cr	mg/l	mg/g cr	mg/l	
Lauwerys <i>et al.</i> , 1980 <i>N= 22 exposed and 28 controls</i>	No effects on liver function: bilirubin, transaminases (ALT and AST), alkaline phosphatase (AP), γ -glutamyl transpeptidase (γ GT) Signs of alcohol intolerant in some workers	40-50 mg/g cr	56-70 mg/l* (ACGIH)	Not investigated		Not investigated
Sakai <i>et al.</i> , 1995 <i>N= 10 exposed</i>	No effects on liver function: glutamic-oxaloacetic transaminase, glutamicpyruvic transaminase, and alkaline phosphatase activity	24.7+/- 5.4 mg/g cr	35 mg/l* (ACGIH)	Before shift 22 +/- 4,6 mg/g cr	31 mg/l	Not investigated
Fiorito <i>et al.</i> , 1997 <i>N=75 exposed and 75 controls</i>	Increased liver enzymes AST, ALT, γ GT, AP, bile acids (BA), bilirubin Alcohol intolerance Alcohol consumption reduced	13.4+/-3.2 mg/g cr	13.6+/-3.3 mg/l	Not investigated		Not investigated
Wrbitzky and Angerer (1998) and Wrbitzky (1999) <i>N = 71</i>	<u>No effects on liver function</u> AST, ALT, γ GT, cholinesterase albumin, prothrombin time and AP.	6.7 mg/g cr	9.4 mg/l* (ACGIH)	Not investigated		Not investigated

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 335

Ref	Reported health effects	Concentrations of total NMF in urine		Concentrations of AMCC in urine		Concentration of MCV _{al} in blood
		End of shift		End of shift (end of week)		
		mg/g cr	mg/l	mg/g cr	mg/l	
He <i>et al.</i> , 2010 <i>N= 79 exposed</i>	No effects on liver function: AST, ALT, γ GT + hyaluronidase (HA), laminin (LN), serum pro-collagen type III (PC-III), and collagen IV and SBA	26,5 mg/g cr	35 mg/l* (ACGIH)	End of shift (end of week)		Not investigated
				25.35 mg/g cr	35.5 mg/l	
Wu <i>et al.</i> , 2017 <i>N=698 exposed and 188 controls</i>	Increased liver enzymes AST, ALT, γ GT BMDL ₁₀		BMDL ₁₀ 14 mg/l (in males only: 10.9 mg/l)		BMDL ₁₀ 155 mg/l (in males only: 119 mg/l)	BMDL ₁₀ 93.3 nmol/g (in males only: 97 nmol/g)
Kilo <i>et al.</i> , 2016 <i>N=220 workers (+175 Controls)</i>	No effect on liver function AST, ALT, γ GT		<i>Mean (+/- SD):</i> 7.75 +/- 8.82 mg/l <i>Median (range):</i> 4.83 (0.20-50.55) mg/l	<i>Mean (+/- SD):</i> 9.42 +/- 10.41 mg/ g cr <i>Median (range):</i> 4.84 (0.006-49.6) mg/g cr		<i>Mean (+/- SD):</i> 83.8 +/- 83.1 <i>Median (range):</i> 60.5 (0.5-414)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 336

Table V.15: Correlation between airborne DMF and BMEs

Réf	Equation tNMF in urine	Equation AMCC in urine	Equation MCVal in blood
Lauwerys et al., 1980	N=22 $C_{tNMF} (mg/g \text{ creatinine}) = 0.67 \times C_{DMF(mg/m^3 \times h)} - 75r^2$ (r= 0,91 p=0.001) post-shift	-	-
Kawai et al., 1992	N=116 $C_{tNMF} (mg/L) = 1.65 C_{DMF(ppm)} + 1.69$ (r ² r = 0.723, P< 0 01)	-	-
Casal Lareo and Perbellini, 1995	N= 52 $C_{tNMF(mg/L)} = 1.2 \times C_{DMF(mg/m^3)} + 3.6$ r = 0.233 P<0.001	-	-
Sakai et al., 1995	N=10 $C_{NMF} (mg/g \text{ creatinine}) = 6.65 C_{DMF(ppm)} - 4.6$ r ² (= 0.89) Post-shift	N= 20 <u>Post shift</u> $C_{AMCC} = 3.38 \times DMF (mg/m^3) + 21$ (r = 0.43) <u>Before shift-</u> $C_{AMCC} = 7.06 \times DMF (mg/m^3) + 12$ (r= 0.69)	-
Käfferlein et al., 2000	N= 23 $C_{NMF(mg/L)} = 2.727 \times C_{DMF(ppm)} + 0.73$ r ² = 0.972 P<0.001	N= 12 <u>Before shift- mid of week</u> $C_{AMCC} (mg/L) = 6.999 \times C_{DMF(ppm)} - 0.783$ r ² = 0.818 et p< 0.001 <u>Post shift</u> $\text{Log } C_{AMCC} (mg/L) = 0.4041 \text{ log } C_{DMF} (mg/m^3) + 0.820$ r ² = 0.212 p>0.0001	-
Yang et al., 2000	N= 125 $C_{tNMF} (mg/g \text{ cr}) = 0.936 \times C_{DMF(mg/m^3)} + 7.306$ r ² = 0.522 P<0.001	-	-

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 337

Réf	Equation tNMF in urine	Equation AMCC in urine	Equation MCV _{Val} in blood
Imbriani et al., 2002	<p>N= 25</p> <p>$C_{tNMF} \text{ (mg/g creatinine)} = 0,936 \times DMF \text{ (mg/m}^3\text{)} + 7.306; r^2 = 0.522$ ($P < 0.0001$)</p> <p>$C_{tNMF} \text{ (mg/L)} = 1.101 \times DMF \text{ (mg/m}^3\text{)} + 8.744$</p>	<p><u>Before shift- end of week</u></p> <p>$C_{AMCC} \text{ (mg/L)} = 1.384 \times DMF \text{ (mg/m}^3\text{)} + 8.708.$ $r^2 = 0.47; P < 0.008$</p> <p>$C_{AMCC} \text{ (mg/g cr)} = 0.858 \times DMF \text{ (mg/m}^3\text{)} + 11.239$ $r^2 = 0.253; P < 0.0123$</p> <p><u>Post shift- end of week</u></p> <p>$C_{AMCC} \text{ (mg/L)} = 1.041 \times C_{DMF} \text{ (mg/m}^3\text{)} + 10.206$ $r^2 = 0.285; P < 0.006$</p> <p>$C_{AMCC} \text{ (mg/g cr)} = 0.872 \times C_{DMF} \text{ (mg/m}^3\text{)} + 7.974$ $r^2 = 0.353; P < 0.0017$</p>	-
Seitz et al., 2018	<p>N= 156 workers (non mask)</p> <p>$C_{tNMF} \text{ (mg/L)} = 1.21 \times C_{DMF} \text{ (mg/m}^3\text{)} + 1.12$ $r^2 = 0.636$</p>	<p>138 workers (no mask)</p> <p>$C_{AMCC} \text{ (mg/g creatinine)} = 1.57 \times C_{DMF} \text{ (mg/m}^3\text{)} + 2.51$ $r^2 = 0.494$</p>	<p>N= 71 workers (no mask)</p> <p>$C_{MCVal} = 10.7 \times C_{DMF} + 15.8$ $r^2 = 0.548$</p> <p>N= 18 workers (no mask)</p> <p>$C_{MCVal} = 8.33 \times C_{AMCC_average} \text{ (mg/g crea)} - 8.77$ $r^2 = 0.721$</p>
	<p>N= 198 workers (with or without mask)</p> <p>$C_{tNMF} \text{ (mg/L)} = 0.90 \times C_{DMF} \text{ (mg/m}^3\text{)} + 2.21$ $r^2 = 0.585$</p>	<p>$C_{AMCC} \text{ (mg/g creatinine)} = 0.88 \times C_{DMF} \text{ (mg/m}^3\text{)} + 4.77$ $r^2 = 0.400$</p>	<p>N=197 workers (with or without mask)</p> <p>$C_{MCVal} \text{ (nmol/g globin)} = 5.84 \times C_{DMF} \text{ (mg/m}^3\text{)} + 46.3$ $R^2 = 0.302$</p> <p>79 workers</p> <p>With and without mask</p> <p>$C_{MCVal} \text{ (nmol/g globin)} = 5.12 \times C_{AMCC_average} \text{ (mg/g crea)} + 12.0 R$ $r^2 = 0.666$</p>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 338

Part VI

Derivation of N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAC) HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs): HBM-GV_{Worker} for occupationally exposed adults

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 339

Table of contents (Part VI)

Authors and acknowledgements	341
Abbreviation	342
1 Introduction	344
1.1 Objectives	344
1.2 Methodological aspects of the HBM-GVs derivation for DMAC	344
2 General information on DMAC	345
2.1 Identification of the substance	345
2.2 Physico-chemical properties of DMAC	345
2.3 Use of DMAC	346
2.4 Existing EU classification and regulation of DMAC	346
2.4.1 Harmonised classification and labelling	346
2.4.2 IARC classification	347
2.4.3 EU directives and regulations of DMAC	347
2.5 Human exposure to DMAC	347
2.5.1 Environmental and consumers exposure	347
2.5.2 Occupational exposure	348
3 Toxicological profile of DMAC	349
3.1 Toxicokinetics	349
3.1.1 Absorption.....	349
3.1.2 Distribution.....	349
3.1.3 Metabolism	350
3.1.4 Excretion.....	351
3.2 Health effects of DMAC.....	352
3.2.1 Acute toxicity.....	352
3.2.2 Skin and eye irritation and respiratory tract irritation.....	353
3.2.3 Skin sensitisation	354
3.2.4 Sub-chronic and chronic toxicity.....	354
4 Existing toxicity reference values for DMAC for occupationally exposed workers	363
4.1 Scientific committee on occupational exposure level (SCOEL).....	363
4.2 Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG).....	363
4.2.1 MAK (maximale Arbeitsplatz Konzentration) value	363
4.2.2 BAT value (Biologischer Arbeitsstoff Toleranzwert).....	363

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 340

4.3	American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH)	364
4.3.1	Threshold limit value - Time Weighted Average (TLV-TWA)	364
4.3.2	Biological Exposure Index	364
4.4	Summary of the existing values for DMAC	365
4.4.1	Summary of the existing occupational exposure level (OEL) values for DMAC	365
4.4.2	Summary of the existing internal toxicity reference values for DMAC	365
4.5	Conclusion	366
5	HBM parameters	367
5.1	Choice of biomarkers	367
5.2	Analytical methods	368
6	Derivation of HBM-GVs for workers.....	369
6.1	Derivation method	369
6.2	Calculation of the “TRV-like value”	369
6.3	Calculation of HMB-GV _{worker}	370
7	Level of confidence attributed to the HBM-GVs	373
8	Discussion.....	374
9	Factsheet reporting the HBM-GV _{Worker} derivation.....	375
10	References.....	378
11	Annexes	383
11.1	Annex 1: Genetic and related effects of DMAC and its metabolite acetamide in human cell <i>in vitro</i> and in experimental systems (IARC, 2020).....	383
11.2	Annex 2: Exposure at workplace and relation between airborne DMAC and total NMAC in urine	385

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 341

Authors and acknowledgements

Lead authors

Matthieu Meslin (ANSES), Farida Lamkarkach (ANSES)

Contributors

Christophe Rousselle (ANSES), Robert Garnier (ANSES Working Group on Biomarkers), Petra Apel (UBA)

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the experts who provided us feedback on this work during the consultation period. Comments were taken as far as possible into consideration for the finalisation of this report.

The responses to the comments formulated by the T5.2 partners ANSES and UBA will be sent to the contributing experts.

Entity	Contributing expert
NH Portugal	Teresa Borges (DGS)
NH Switzerland	Rex Fitzgerald (SCAHT)
NH Netherlands	Floris Groothuis (RIVM)
NH Switzerland	Nancy Hopf (Unisanté, CH)
NH United Kingdom	Kate Jones (UK LTP, HSE)
NH Austria	Ilse Maurtiz (EAA)
NH Portugal	Susana Viegas (ENSP-UNL)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 342

Abbreviation

ACGIH	American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists
AF	Assessment Factor
AF _A	Assessment Factor accounting for interspecies differences
AF _H	Assessment Factor accounting for intraspecies differences
ALT	Alanine aminotransferase
AMMA	S-acetamidomethyl-mercapturic acid
ANSES	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety
AST	Aspartate aminotransferase
BAT	German biological tolerance value
BEI	Biological exposure index
BLV	Biological Limit Value
BME	Biomarker(s) of exposure
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging
DFG	German Research Foundation
DMAC	N,N Dimethylacetamide
DMF	N,N Dimethylformamide
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
ED10	Effective Dose with a 10 % effect level above the background
EU	European Union
GC	Gas Chromatography
GLP	Good laboratory practice
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU	European Human Biomonitoring Initiative
HBM-GV	Human Biomonitoring Guidance Value
HMAC	N-hydroxymethylacetamide
HMMAC	N-hydroxymethyl-N-methylacetamide
IARC	International Agency for Research on Cancer
JRBC	Japan Bioassay Research Center
LC-MS / MS	Liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry
LOAEL	Lowest Adverse Effect Concentration
MAK	German maximum workplace concentration

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 343

MTD	Maximum Tolerated Dose
MIC	Methyl isocyanate
NMR	Nuclear magnetic resonance
NOAEC	No Observed Adverse Effect Concentration
NOAEL	No Observed Adverse Effect Level
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OEL	Occupational Exposure Limit
POD	Point of departure
PS	Personal air sampler
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction
SCOEL	Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limit Values (European Commission)
SD	Standard deviation
STEL	Short term exposure limit
SVHC	Substance of Very High Concern
TLV	Threshold limit value
TWA	Time Weighted Average
tNMAC	(total) N-methylacetamide
UBA	German Environment Agency
US EPA	Unites States Environmental Protection Agency
γ-GT	Gamma glutamyltransferase

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 344

1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives

Within the framework of task 5.2 of the European Joint Programme HBM4EU, Human Biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) are derived for HBM4EU priority substances. The methodology applied to derive these values is described in the concept paper released in the HBM4EU task 5.2 workframe (Apel et al. 2020).

For the time being, HBM-GVs are derived in HBM4EU under inclusion of experts from the 30 partner countries. Future use and implementation will be discussed among partners and the EU Commission but are without prejudice to existing or ongoing risk assessment work in order to inform EU policy-making.

In the current report, an HBM-GV for workers is derived and discussed for the aprotic solvent N-N, dimethylacetamide (DMAC).

1.2 Methodological aspects of the HBM-GVs derivation for DMAC

A detailed overview of the studies considered is provided by the IARC (2020), the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA, 2019), the American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH, 2011 and 2018), the German Research Foundation (DFG, 2019) and the Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limit (SCOEL, 1994).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 345

2 General information on DMAC

2.1 Identification of the substance

Table VI.1: DMAC Chemical identification

Name and synonyms	N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAC)
IUPAC Names	N,N-dimethylacetamide
CAS Number	127-19-5
EC /List no.	204-826-4
Molecular weight	87.12 g/mol
Molecular formula	C ₄ H ₉ NO
Conversion factor (25°C)*	1 ppm = 3.56 mg/m ³ 1 mg/m ³ = 0.281 ppm
Structural formula	

*ACGIH 2018

2.2 Physico-chemical properties of DMAC

At room temperature, DMAC is a colourless liquid of weak, ammonia-like odour detectable above 45 ppm¹. DMAC is miscible with water and most organic solvents (ACGIH, 2011).

Key physico-chemical property values are presented in Table VI.2.

Table VI.2: Overview of physico-chemical properties of DMAC³⁴

Physical state	Liquid at 20°C and 1013 hPa
Melting point	-20°C at 1013 hPa
Boiling point	166°C at 1013 hPa
Relative density	0.94 g/cm ³ at 20 °C
Vapour pressure	2 hPa at 21.7 °C
Partition coefficient n-octanol/water (log Kow)	-0.77 at 25 °C
Water solubility	1000 g/l at 20 °C
Dissociation constant (pKa value)	-0.19 at 25 °C

³⁴ <https://www.echa.europa.eu/web/quest/registration-dossier/-/registered-dossier/15266/4/2> (consulted on September 9th,2020)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 346

2.3 Uses of DMAC

According to the registered dossier available on ECHA's website³⁵, the total annual consumption of DMAC in the EU, as process chemical and for formulation of mixtures, is estimated at 1000+ tonnes per annum.

In the EU, DMAC is predominantly used in the production of agrochemicals (fertilisers, pesticides etc.), pharmaceuticals (e.g. antibiotics and novel contrast media) and fine chemicals, accounting for 65 - 70 % of tonnage.

About 20 - 25% of EU tonnage is used in the production of man-made fibres which are mainly used for the production of clothing. DMAC is also used as a solvent in coatings for industrial use (approximately 3 - 5 % of EU tonnage). It is also involved in the production of films and resins, paint strippers and various other applications such as petrochemicals applications and laboratory use for example (ECHA, 2012).

2.4 Existing EU classification and regulation of DMAC

2.4.1 Harmonised classification and labelling

According to the **harmonised classification and labelling** (CLP Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008), DMAC may damage the unborn child, is harmful if inhaled and in contact with skin (Table VI.3).

Table VI.3: Harmonised classification according to Annex VI of the EU Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008³⁶

Classification		Labelling	
Hazard Class & Category code(s)	Hazard statement code(s)	Pictogram, Signal Word code(s)	Hazard statement code(s)
Repr. 1B*	H360D - May damage unborn child	Danger GHS08	H360D
Acute Tox 4**	H332 – Harmful if inhaled	GHS07	H332
Acute Tox 4**	H312 – Harmful with contact with skin		H312

*"In order not to lose information from the harmonised classification for fertility and developmental effects under Directive 67/548/EEC, the classifications have been translated only for those effects classified under that Directive"

**"Manufacturers or importers must apply at least this minimum classification, but must classify in a more severe hazard category in the event that further information is available which shows that the hazard(s) meet the criteria for classification in the more severe category"

Additionally, the self-classifications provided by companies to ECHA identified that this substance causes serious eye irritation (H319).

³⁵ <https://www.echa.europa.eu/web/guest/registration-dossier/-/registered-dossier/15266/1> (consulted on September 9th,2020)

³⁶ <https://echa.europa.eu/fr/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database/-/discli/details/116425> (consulted on September 9th, 2020)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 347

2.4.2 IARC classification

In 2020, the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) concluded that DMAC is possibly carcinogenic to humans (Group 2B) based on sufficient evidence in experimental animals but inadequate evidence in humans (IARC, 2020).

2.4.3 EU directives and regulations of DMAC

2.4.3.1 REACH regulation

DMAC is registered under the REACH regulation and has a harmonised classification for reproductive toxicity (Repr. 1B H360D). Consequently, DMAC has been identified as a Substance of Very High Concern (SVHC) but not included in Annex XIV so far (ECHA, 2011).

2.4.3.2 OSH legislation

The EU directive 2000/39/EC set the following occupational exposure limit values:

- 8h-TWA (time weighed average): 10 ppm (36 mg/m³)
- 15 min-STEEL (short term exposure level): 20 ppm (72 mg/m³)
- Notation: 'skin'

France and Germany set lower regulatory values for DMAC. France set a binding 8h-OEL of 2 ppm and a 15 min-STEEL of 10 ppm in 2006³⁷. In Germany, the 8h-OEL has been set at 5 ppm and the 15 min-STEEL at 10 ppm³⁸.

2.4.3.3 Other EU regulations

Since 2009, DMAC has been banned in any cosmetic products marketed for sale or use in the European Union (1223/2009/EU amended by regulation 2019/1966/EU).

In the workplace, pregnant workers³⁹ and workers who have recently given birth or are breastfeeding, as well as young people (under 18 years) should not be exposed to DMAC according to Directives 92/85/EEC and 94/33/EC respectively.

2.5 Human exposure to DMAC

2.5.1 Environmental and consumers exposure

Non-occupational exposure to DMAC is uncommon. However, according to OECD-SIDS (2001) and ECHA (2012), releases of DMAC to the environment and possible exposure via environment can still be expected, related to the treatment of waste water and incineration of solid wastes, to fiber production via exhaust gas in air, and as a result of residues in fibres.

DMAC is subject to rapid photochemical degradation in the atmosphere, with a half-life of 6.1 hours. It has also a low bioconcentration factor, which indicates low bioaccumulation in aquatic species, and a low adsorption coefficient resulting in an assumed low adsorption to soils and sediments. DMAC does not hydrolyse in aqueous solutions, even at elevated temperature, but it is inherently biodegradable. If released into the air, DMAC is likely to be transported in water and soil. In water, it will not adsorb to sediment and suspended matter or volatilise from water. DMAC is highly miscible with water, meaning that in moist soil it will display very high mobility

³⁷ Décret N°2006-133 du 9 février 2006 fixant des valeurs limites d'exposition professionnelle

³⁸ GESTIS website : https://limitvalue.ifa.dguv.de/WebForm_ueliste2.aspx accessed in July 2020

³⁹ According to the directive: pregnant worker shall mean a pregnant worker who informs her employer of her condition, in accordance with national legislation and / or national practice

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 348

and will not volatilise. In a dry soil, the volatilisation to the atmosphere will be slow (OECD-SIDS, 2001).

Results from migration tests, with simulated sweating on a textile article containing DMAC residues, suggested a negligible exposure for the consumer (OECD-SIDS, 2001). However, DMAC is used as a carrier in the formulation of some intravenously administered drugs, especially busulfan, an alkylating agent. DMAC was therefore detected in children given a single daily dose of busulfan, with DMAC concentrations ranging from 110 to 198 µg/mL (Cendana et al., 2017).

No HBM data were available in the HBM4EU repository.

2.5.2 Occupational exposure

Human exposure to DMAC occurs mostly at workplace where the substance is used downstream of its primary manufacture (IARC, 2020). Occupational DMAC exposure mainly occurs by inhalation and dermal routes. DMAC can be measured in air and in biological media (e.g. urine). The main metabolite reported in occupational studies is total N-methylacetamide (tNMAC) in urine. Spies et al. (1995a) observed a positive association between DMAC in air and total N-methylacetamide in urine (IARC 2020). Perbellini et al. (2003) showed that skin uptake of DMAC is very high and increases with high humidity and high temperature. An overview of available workplace studies is presented in Annex 2.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 349

3 Toxicological profile of DMAC

3.1 Toxicokinetics

3.1.1 Absorption

3.1.1.1 In humans

DMAC is readily absorbed after inhalation, oral and dermal exposure (OECD-SIDS 2001). Respiratory and dermal absorption are the major routes encountered in the workplace (ACGIH 2011).

In a study by Nomiya et al. (2000), twelve healthy men were exposed to DMAC at mean concentration of 6.1 +/- 1.3 (SD) ppm for 4 hours. These volunteers were exposed under two distinct experimental conditions: either in a whole-body exposure chamber wearing only cotton pants (90% of their skin surfaces were naked) and inhaling fresh air via a respirator to estimate the dermal absorption or by sitting outside the chamber and inhaling chamber air to estimate the inhalation absorption, both in terms of urinary AUCs. The mean inhalation absorption was 59.6% of the total DMAC uptake (i.e. of summed dermal and inhalation urinary AUCs), while mean dermal absorption was 40.4 %.

An earlier study by Maxfield et al. (1975) also studied DMAC absorption in two male volunteers *via* inhalation and dermal routes in an exposure chamber with most of the body naked, or only *via* the dermal route, breathing normal air via a face-mask. DMAC absorption was estimated to be 30 % *via* the dermal route and 70 % *via* the lung. The authors also studied the dermal uptake of liquid DMAC in 4 subjects after applying 375 mg on their forearm under occlusive conditions for two hours, corresponding approximately to what would be inhaled after exposure to 10 ppm of DMAC for 8 hours. The urinary level of the excreted metabolite N-methylacetamide (NMAC) was similar to that obtained after 2 x 3 hours skin-only exposure to DMAC vapors (as summarised in ACGIH, 2011).

Dermal absorption in workers was also studied by Borm et al. (1987) and was estimated to be 13-30 % of the total uptake (as summarised in IARC 2020).

Therefore, it can be concluded that dermal absorption of DMAC vapors contributes significantly to the total uptake under workplace conditions.

3.1.1.2 In animals

Sherman and Barnes (1986), (as referenced by ACGIH, 2011) treated rats orally with radioactive labelled ¹⁴C-DMAC. Systemic absorption represented at least 93 % of the ingested dose as measured by urinary excretion of the radioactive compound; only 5 % of the radioactivity was detected in the feces.

3.1.2 Distribution

According to ACGIH (2011), it seems plausible that DMAC is rapidly metabolised like structurally closely related N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF). In addition, it seems unlikely that DMAC accumulates in the body due to its low octanol/water partition coefficient (-0.77 at 25°C).

Following an experiment conducted on 3 male rats which were exposed to 5 ppm of ¹⁴C-DMAC for 12 hours, the carcass and tissues contained about 22 % of the total ¹⁴C. Fat and muscles were major sites of retention (DuPont, 1988, as reported in OECD-SIDS, 2001).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 350

3.1.3 Metabolism

3.1.3.1 In humans

The metabolism of DMAC is analogous to that of DMF (Barnes and Ranta, 1972; Lauwerys and Hoet, 1993; Palmen et al., 1993). However, methyl isocyanate (MIC), a toxic intermediate, is only produced by the metabolism of DMF but not of DMAC, thus DMAC could be less toxic in humans and animals in terms of hepatic effects (Princivalle et al., 2010; Perbellini et al., 2003).

DMAC is metabolised for the most part in the liver and is rapidly eliminated mainly through the urine (Yamamoto et al., 2018). Brindley et al. (1983) were the first to describe the N-methylhydroxylation of DMF. DMAC metabolism successively produces N-hydroxymethyl-N-methylacetamide (HMMAC) which is then easily degraded to N-methylacetamide (NMAC). NMAC then undergoes an enzymatic N-methyl oxidation to produce N-hydroxymethylacetamide (HMAC) from which results acetamide (Yamamoto et al., 2018).

The metabolic pathways are shown in Figure VI.2.

Figure VI.2: Metabolic pathways of DMAC as proposed by Perbellini et al. 2003 (taken from DFG, 2019)

The most commonly used method to measure NMAC in urine, based on gas chromatography (GC) coupled to nitrogen-phosphorous detector was first reported by Barnes and Henry, 1974. This method uses an injection port temperature of 200°C. However, Kawai et al. (1997) further reported that HMMAC thermally decomposes into NMAC at this temperature. As a result, the major urinary detected metabolite using this GC method is total NMAC (tNMAC), which is the sum of HMMAC and NMAC. To overcome this problem, Yamamoto et al. (2018) have developed a new method capable of measuring low concentrations of DMAC and its metabolites in urine using liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 351

In 2003, Perbellini et al. identified, by nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), S-acetamidomethyl-mercaptopuric acid (AMMA) as a metabolite of DMAC, presumably formed from NMAC and involving a reaction with glutathione (without involvement of the toxic isocyanate according to Princivalle et al. (2010)). By analogy with DMF, ethanol could competitively inhibit the metabolism of DMAC into NMAC (ACGIH, 2011). On the other hand, ethanol or acetone induction of microsomal enzymes increases DMAC demethylation (Menicagli et al., 1994).

3.1.3.2 In animals

The same metabolites were observed in rats and in humans. Barnes and Ranta (1972) observed NMAC and acetamide in rats given 300 mg of DMAC for 2 days by subcutaneous injection. This suggests that NMAC undergoes successive N-demethylation to give acetamide as in humans. Moreover, according to US EPA (1995), a single oral administration of ¹⁴C-DMAC resulted in metabolism to NMAC, HMAc and acetamide within 72 hours.

Shrivastava et al. (1974) studied the metabolic fate of ¹⁴C-DMAC in rats, after a single oral 33 or 92 mg dose by gavage (as cited in ACGIH, 2018). The primary metabolic pathways were N-demethylation and N-hydroxylation and urine contained at least nine different radioactive compounds, including NMAC, HMAc and acetamide.

3.1.3.3 In vitro

Tolando et al. (2001) have shown that DMAC is metabolised *in vitro* by cytochrome P450, probably CYP2E1.

3.1.4 Excretion

The principal elimination pathway after the metabolism of DMAC is urinary excretion, other existing pathways being quantitatively less relevant (ACGIH, 2011).

3.1.4.1 In humans

In the study by Borm et al. (1987), it was estimated that 6 out of 8 workers studied excreted around 13 % (ranging from 7.7 % to 32.5 % in all workers) of the absorbed amount of DMAC as tNMAC metabolite in urine, after comparing urinary excretion levels to pulmonary intake, assuming a retention rate of 100 %. Moreover, they calculated a half-life of 16 hours for urinary tNMAC, suggesting a potential NMAC accumulation over the workweek (ACGIH, 2011).

Nomiyama et al. (2000) estimated the mean biological half-lives of urinary tNMAC to be of 9.0 +/- 1.4 and 5.3 +/- 1.3 hours after dermal and lung absorption, respectively. According to the study by Princivalle et al. (2010) in 13 workers, the half-lives of tNMAC and AMMA were respectively estimated as 8.7 +/- 1.9 and 29.4 +/- 6.6 hours.

DMAC is used as a carrier for the formulation of some drugs that are administered intravenously, such as busulfan. Therefore, several publications studied the pharmacokinetics of DMAC, modelled using a one compartment model (Hempel et al., 2007; Trame et al., 2013). Hempel et al. (2007) estimated a mean plasma half-life of 3.74 hours decreasing to 0.83 after 96 hours, due to a subsequent increase in clearance over the 4 days of treatment.

3.1.4.2 In animals

In the previously mentioned experiment by DuPont (1988) in which 3 male rats were exposed to ¹⁴C-DMAC by inhalation, 41 % of total ¹⁴C was recovered in the urine, 14 % in the faeces 15 % in expired air. According to Sherman and Barnes (1986), about 93 % of the absorbed amount of DMAC in rats is excreted in the urine.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 352

Shrivastava et al. (1974) showed that 80 - 87 % of orally dosed radioactivity was retrieved in urine versus 5 - 10 % in the feces, up to 24 hours after dosing. At 72 hours, 93 % were found in urine, 5 % in feces, 2 % in remaining tissues and less than 1% was expired as ¹⁴CO₂. They also estimated that 69 - 70 % of the radioactive DMAC metabolites corresponded to tNMAC, 7 - 10 % to HMAC and 7 - 10 % to acetamide.

Hundley et al. (1994) reported a plasma half-life of DMAC between 0.6 and 1.5 hours in rats exposed by whole-body inhalation, while Princivalle et al. (2010) reported urinary half-lives in rats of about 2.5 and 6.5 hours for tNMAC and AMMA respectively, after an exposure to 200 mg/kg bw/d of DMAC, administered by gavage (from an initial unpublished study).

3.2 Health effects of DMAC

3.2.1 Acute toxicity

3.2.1.1 In humans

Su et al. (2000) reported the case of a 27-year-old employee of a synthetic leather company, exposed to DMAC, ethylenediamine, and diphenylmethane diisocyanate in a confined space for 4–6 hours per day for 3 days, prior to hospital admission for hallucinations and delusions as well as subsequent pulmonary edema. Seizures, liver injury, and rhabdomyolysis were noted on the fourth hospital day. The patient was treated by hemoperfusion, and a decrease of DMAC in urine, from 3265 mg/g to 4 mg/g creatinine (mg/g cr) over 4 days, was observed. Serial urinary dimethylacetamide concentrations and electroencephalograms correlated with the clinical condition. However, a causal relation between DMAC exposure and the signs and symptoms observed remains uncertain, as other substances were present at the workplace and other differential diagnosis were not searched for.

Marino et al. (1994) reported the case of a worker accidentally exposed to both DMAC and ethylenediamine for 90 min in a confined space by inhalation and dermal route. The observed clinical effects included delirium, hallucinations, skin burns, cellulitis, bilateral conjunctivitis, hepatitis, secondary coagulopathy, rhabdomyolysis and oesophagitis.

When used as a drug solvent, ingestion of repeated doses of 400 mg/kg for 3 or 4 days caused neuropsychic disorders in most subjects: depression, lethargy, mental confusion and disorientation. At the end of treatment, some subjects experienced hallucinations and perceptual disturbances. These symptoms disappeared within a few days after discontinuation of the product. When doses of 200 or 300 mg/kg were used, these adverse effects did not occur (Gosselin et al. 1984).

According to Oechterin et al. (2005), no indication of DMAC toxicity was observed after two infusions of a DMAC-based intravenous formulation of Busulfan in children. Two patients developed neurotoxic symptoms, but these were attributed to Busulfan.

3.2.1.2 In animals

According to the registered dossier available on ECHA's website⁴⁰, DMAC toxicity is low, after acute oral exposure in rats (LD50 ranged between 4800 – 5830 mg/kg bw), mice (LD50: 4610 - 6020 mg/kg bw), and rabbits (LD50: 2820 mg/kg bw). Dogs seem to be more sensitive than

⁴⁰ <https://www.echa.europa.eu/web/guest/registration-dossier/-/registered-dossier/15266/1> (consulted on July 2020)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 353

other species. Data suggest that the target organs of acute oral toxicity are the liver (dogs and rats), stomach (mice, rabbits, rats) and kidney (rats).

Results from acute toxicity studies of DMAC are reported in table VI.4.

Table VI.4: Acute toxicity of DMAC in animals

Route	Species	Observation	References
Oral	Rats Mice Rabbits	Rats: LD50: 4800-5830 mg/kg bw Mice: LD50: 4610-6020 mg/kg bw Rabbits: LD50: 2820 mg/kg bw	ECHA website (registered dossier) Consulted on July 2020
	Rats Rabbits Dogs	Rats: LD50: 3000-6000 mg/kg bw Rabbits: LD50: > 5000 mg/kg bw Dogs: LD100: 1880 mg/kg bw	DuPont, 1988 (cited in OECD-SIDS, 2001)
	Rabbits	LD50: 2100 mg/kg bw	ECHA website (registered dossier) Consulted on July 2020
Dermal	Rats Rabbits	Rats: LD50: 7500 mg/kg bw Rabbits: LD50: 5000 mg/kg bw	Stula and Krauss, 1977 (cited in Kennedy, 1986; ACGIH 2001)
	Rabbits Guinea pigs	Rabbits: LD50: 2100-3600 mg/kg bw Guinea pigs: LD50: <940 mg/kg bw	DuPont, 1988 (cited in OECD-SIDS, 2001)
	Rats	LD50: 8.81 mg/l for a 1-hour exposure, estimated to be 2.2 mg/l for a 4-hour exposure (for aerosol).	DuPont (1979)/Watts (1978) (cited in Kennedy, 1986; DFG, 1998; OECD-SIDS, 2001). ECHA website (registered dossier) Consulted on July 2020
Inhalation	Rats	No mortality at 12 mg/l for 8 hours	Smyth et al., 1962 (cited in OECD-SIDS, 2001)
	Mice	LD50: 1.47 mg/l for a 3.5-hour exposure	DuPont, 1988 (cited in OECD-SIDS, 2001)

3.2.2 Skin and eye irritation and respiratory tract irritation

In REACH registration data, a study (1970) on two rabbits is documented concluding that the substance is irritating in rabbit eyes. This results in a classification as Eye Irrit 2, H319.

According to Smyth et al. (1962), DMAC received a score of 3 (out of 10) in its irritation rating scale, when applied undiluted to the rabbit eye. DMAC induced mild conjunctival inflammation in rabbit's eye either washed or unwashed, which was reversible after 3 to 4 days. No clear evidence of corneal injury was observed and all corneas appeared microscopically normal after 7 days. This indicates that DMAC is a mild ocular irritant (as cited in ACGIH, 2018).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 354

Mice treated dermally with 2.5 g/kg showed slight skin irritation while rabbits given 0.5 g/kg were unaffected. Guinea pigs treated dermally with up to 1 g/kg DMAC showed severe skin irritation along with lethality (Kennedy, 1986 quoted by ACGIH 2018).

In the study by Horn (1961) exposing two dogs and 20 rats by inhalation at concentrations of 40, 64.4, 103 and 195 ppm 6 hours/day, 5 days/week during 6 months, evidence of respiratory tract irritation was reported. In the same study, the authors dermally exposed dogs to 0.1, 0.316, 1 and 4 ml/kg/d (daily applications to the clipped trunks) during 5 days/week for six weeks at the two higher levels and six months at the two lower levels. Dogs at both high levels showed weight loss and mild to moderate skin irritation.

In an inhalation study conducted in rats and mice (male and female), the authors did not report any lesions in nose or respiratory tract at the highest concentration (350 ppm) (Malley et al., 1995).

3.2.3 Skin sensitisation

DMAC was not a skin sensitiser when repeated sublethal doses were used in an attempt to elicit a delayed hypersensitivity response in guinea pigs (Kennedy, 1986). Moreover, in the REACH registration data, DMAC is not considered to be a sensitiser.

According to REACH registration data, a human patch test with 3.7% DMAC applied to the arms of 13 men and to the arms or legs of 6 women for 6 days, followed by the application of new patches for 2 days after a 2 weeks rest period, did not result in sensitisation (DuPont 1995, TSCA OTS0558317)⁴¹

3.2.4 Sub-chronic and chronic toxicity

3.2.4.1 Hepatic effects

In humans

Several case reports have documented the effects of DMAC on liver. Johnson (1961, as cited in ACGIH 2018) reported observations of jaundice in workers repeatedly exposed to 20 to 25 ppm of DMAC, with appreciable skin penetration contributing to this effect. In 1971, Corsi described 14 cases of abnormal liver function with hepatomegaly among 41 workers exposed to DMAC for 2 to 10 years; exposure conditions and concentrations were not reported (ACGIH 2018). Baume and Suruda (1997) also reported two cases of hepatitis in women following occupational dermal exposure to DMAC among 25 employees on an acrylic-fiber line in a manufacturing plant.

Worker exposure to DMAC in an acrylic-fiber manufacturing plant was measured over one year by full-shift personal air monitoring (12 hours) and by biological monitoring of DMAC, tNMAC and acetamide (Spies et al., 1995a, b). Hepatotoxicity was assessed in 127 workers exposed to DMAC and 217 workers with no previous or current exposure to DMAC, by serum chemistry with total bilirubin, aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and γ -glutamyl transferase (γ -GT). No significant DMAC exposure-related trend in serum chemistry was detected. There was also no change in the samples from those subjects with the highest exposure biomarker level (60 mg tNMAC/g cr) (Spies et al., 1995b).

⁴¹ <https://echa.europa.eu/registration-dossier/-/registered-dossier/15266/7/1/1/5>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 355

In a study by Lee et al. (2006), 440 workers exposed to DMAC in two Korean elastane-fiber factories were monitored for hepatic injury. Concentrations of DMAC in the workplace atmosphere were not measured. Twenty-eight (28) cases of hepatocellular damage (characterised by an ALT activity twice above the upper limit of the normal range or a ratio of ALT activity to serum alkaline phosphatase activity equal to 5 or greater) were observed. The exposure estimate for DMAC was based on urinary levels of tNMAC. It was noted that the incidence of hepatic injury in the high exposure group was 7 to 10 times higher than in the low exposure group for workers exposed for less than 7 months. Low and high exposure groups were distinguished by the geometric mean value of urinary tNMAC concentrations i.e. either ≤ 20 mg/g cr or > 20 mg/g cr in model 1 and either ≤ 30 mg/g cr or > 30 mg/g cr in model 2. Those levels of urinary tNMAC were both positively associated with the risk of hepatic injury with odd ratios of 3.70 (95 % CI, 1.33 - 10.26) in model 1 and 4.67 (95 %CI, 1.66 - 13.15), in model 2. No hepatic injury was found in workers exposed for more than 7 months in both low and high exposure group. According to Lee et al., this could reflect a type of healthy workers effect or tolerance to DMAC-induced liver damage.

Another study conducted by Jung et al. (2007) in two elastane factories in Korea found 38 cases of DMAC-induced hepatocellular liver injury, including three recurrences, among 1045 employees exposed to DMAC. The latency between the beginning of exposure to DMAC and the appearance of liver injury was less than 2 months and never more than 6 months. The recurrent cases had shorter latency periods to signs of liver injury after re-exposure than at their initial exposure. Twenty-one of the 38 cases appeared in the same work department. The median urinary concentration of tNMAC in this department was 25.1 mg/g cr, which was higher than the median urinary tNMAC concentration in the other department, which was 11.8 mg/g cr. The tNMAC concentration in the urine of the 21 workers with hepatocellular injury was not reported (only the average values from the department), so a LOAEL for the N-methylacetamide concentration cannot be derived from these data.

Kim & Kim (2010) reported toxic hepatitis cases in Korean workers exposed to DMAC or DMF. According to Korean surveillance data, thirty-four cases of toxic hepatitis occurred in two synthetic fiber-producing companies which used DMF and DMAC from January 1st, 2001 to April 30th, 2002. Most cases occurred within 2 or 3 months of starting work, and the shortest period was 4 days. Most workers recovered with treatment after early detection, but deaths in spite of proper treatment were also observed. Kim & Kim cited the study of Jang et al. (2006), which reported on 72 cases of suspected toxic hepatitis among 997 workers in synthetic fiber production plants using DMAC from February 1st, 2000 to June 30th, 2004, with most cases occurring between 2 and 17 weeks of starting employment. Jang et al. also reported that most workers quickly recovered after exposure was discontinued, and at 48-week follow up all cases had resolved.

In 2016, Gong et al. reported one case of acute hepatitis in a worker exposed to DMAC in a Chinese polyimide film factory. This episode was followed by a short-term recurrence after recovery as soon as coming back to work.

Weiss et al. (1962a, as cited in ACGIH 2018) also observed hepatotoxicity induced by DMAC. They treated patients with varying malignancies with an intravenous injection of 10% solution of DMAC from 100 to 610 mg/kg bw/d for 2 to 5 consecutive days. Four additional patients were treated with one or two additional cycles. Hepatotoxicity occurred in all patients receiving 400 mg/kg bw/d for at least 3 days.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 356

Despite the similarities between DMAC and DMF metabolisms, occurrence of Antabuse effects due to DMAC exposure has not been reported in occupational studies.

In animals

Liver effects induced by DMAC exposure have been extensively documented in animals.

In 1961, Horn investigated the chronic toxicity of DMAC by dermal application to dogs at doses of 0.1 to 4.0 ml/kg bw (94-3,760 mg/kg bw) and by exposing both rats and dogs to atmosphere containing DMAC at concentrations of 40.0 to 195 ppm. Liver damage was observed at all dose levels greater than 0.1 ml/kg bw (94 mg/kg bw) dermally and 40 ppm by inhalation (Horn, 1961).

Kelly et al. (1984) exposed groups of 10 male and female rats by inhalation to 100, 288 or 622 ppm, 6 hours per day for two weeks. At 622 ppm, livers were enlarged and necrotic, while at 288 ppm rats showed moderate liver hypertrophy but recovered within two weeks (as cited in Kennedy, 1986).

Kennedy and Sherman (1986) reported the liver as target organ of DMAC toxicity. Nine repeated oral doses of 450 mg/kg bw of DMAC over two weeks led to liver injury among other effects, all being readily reversible. Dermal doses of 2,000 mg/kg bw of DMAC applied daily in rabbits were lethal within five doses. Rabbits showed evidence of acute hepatic necrosis, presumably the cause of death. However, repeated inhalation of 2,000-2,500 ppm of DMAC did not produce mortality in rats when the same concentrations of DMF were lethal in this species.

In the inhalation study of Malley et al. (1995), the authors exposed female and male rats (N=87/sex/group) and mice (N=78/sex/group) at 0, 25, 100 and 350 ppm DMAC for 6h/day, 5 days/week for 18 months (mice) or 2 years (rats). They observed morphological changes in the liver. In rats exposed to 100 and 350 ppm, the authors reported increased absolute and /or relative liver weights, hepatic focal cystic degeneration, hepatic peliosis, biliary hyperplasia (350 ppm only), and lipofuscin/hemosiderin accumulation in Kupffer cells. In mice exposed to 100 and 350 ppm, they showed increases in absolute and relative liver weights (350 ppm females only), accumulation of lipofuscin/hemosiderin in Kupffer cells, and centrilobular single cell necrosis. No effects were observed at the lowest exposure level of 25 ppm and the authors concluded that the NOAEL for male and female rats and mice was 25 ppm.

Kinney et al. (1993) exposed rats by inhalation to 10 to 300 ppm of DMAC for 3, 6 or 12 hours for a total of 10 exposures. Hepatocellular hypertrophy together with margination of hepatocellular cytoplasmic contents and lipid-like cytoplasmic vacuolation were seen in hepatocytes of rats exposed for 12 hours/day to 300 ppm. These liver changes did not resolve completely after a 14-day post-exposure period. In two inhalation studies conducted by Valentine et al. (1997), liver damage, among other effects was also observed in mice exposed to 490 ppm of DMAC, with the occurrence of centrilobular hepatocellular necrosis and hypertrophy.

The IARC (2020) reports a well-conducted good laboratory practice (GLP) study on mice exposed to DMAC by whole-body inhalation at a concentration of 0, 12, 60, or 300 ppm (0, 43, 214, 1068 mg/m³) for 6 hours per day, 5 days a week, for 104 weeks. In this study, a significant increase in the incidence of eosinophilic foci in the liver was observed in males and females at 300 ppm (JRBC, 2013a and b, as cited in IARC, 2020). Another GLP study was conducted in groups of 50 male and 50 female rats exposed to doses of 0, 18, 90, 450 ppm (0, 65, 320, 1600 mg/m³) of DMAC by whole-body inhalation for 6 hours per day, 5 days a week, for 104 weeks. The results showed a significant increase in the incidence of eosinophilic foci in the liver in males at 450 ppm, of hepatic clear cell foci in females at 450 ppm, of hepatic Kupffer cell

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 357

pigment accumulation in males at 450 ppm and in females at 90 and 450 ppm. Moreover, the authors observed a significant increase in the incidence of focal fatty degeneration in the liver in males at 90 and 450 ppm (JRBC, 2013c and d, as cited in IARC, 2020).

3.2.4.2 Neurotoxicity

In studies by Weiss et al. (1962b), effects of DMAC on the central nervous system were observed. Patients receiving an intravenous injection of 400 mg/ kg bw/d for 3 days or more developed abnormal mental state, with delusions, hallucinations, mental confusion and drowsiness (as reported in ACGIH 2018).

3.2.4.3 Genotoxicity

As stated in OECD-SIDS (2001), DMAC is clearly not mutagenic in a battery of tests". In 2020, the IARC working group reviewed available data to assess the genotoxicity of DMAC. Negative results were obtained in multiple test systems. Data are summarised in Annex 1 (taken from IARC, 2020).

McGregor (1980) conducted an unscheduled DNA synthesis assay in human diploid fibroblasts (*in vitro*), tests for dominant lethal mutation in male rats and sperm morphology in male mice after exposure by inhalation, cytogenetic evaluations in male and female rat bone marrow after exposure by inhalation, and the sex-linked recessive lethal test in *Drosophila melanogaster* after atmospheric exposure. All these assays gave negative results (as cited in IARC, 2020).

Terada et al. (1978) claimed that DNA damage occurred based on changes in DNA sucrose sedimentation rates after exposing mouse erythroleukemia cells to DMAC.

Acetamide genotoxicity has also been investigated in several assays in *Drosophila melanogaster*, giving conflicting results (Mitchell et al., 1981; Valencia et al., 1985; Batiste-Alentorn et al., 1991, 1995; Muñoz and Barnett, 2003).

IARC (2020) concluded that there is *weak* evidence that DMAC and its metabolite acetamide are genotoxic.

3.2.4.4 Carcinogenicity

In 2020, IARC reported an analysis of available data regarding the carcinogenicity of DMAC.

In humans

An epidemiological retrospective study undertaken by Mastrangelo et al. (1993) studied the mortality of 671 workers employed for at least 12 months in an acrylic-fiber manufacturing plant in Venice, Italy. During the process of the manufacture of acrylic fiber, workers were co-exposed to acrylonitrile. Workers were grouped according to their work area and job task, reflecting their exposure to DMAC and acrylonitrile. However, workers with past exposure to vinyl chloride or benzidine, known as carcinogenic substances, were excluded. All the cohort subjects were followed-up for deaths, and death certificates were used to establish the cause of death. Only 32 deaths from all causes including accidents, were observed when 31.2 were expected, on the basis of death rates of the general population in the Veneto region.

Statistically significant increased risks were only observed for tumors of the intestine and colon and for death from "ill-defined symptoms". The number of deaths from cancers of the intestine and colon was significantly increased in the subgroup with a short duration of exposure for less than 4 years, and in the subgroup with less than 9 years since the first exposure. IARC (2020) noted that the association between DMAC exposure and occurrence of cancers in the facility

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 358

workforce studied by Mastrangelo et al. (1993) is “*unclear, given the study’s crude exposure assessment methodology*”. Mastrangelo et al. (1993) also discussed the possibility that the observed significant increase in death from tumors of the intestine and colon may depend on the influence of local confounding factors; the mean mortality rate from these tumors in the cohort’s area of residence was 30 % higher than the mean regional value that was used for the calculation of expected deaths. IARC (2020) also noted that the study population was relatively young and the number of deaths from cancer was small.

Perbellini et al. (2003) investigated the exposure in the workforce in the same factory, about a decade after the completion of the epidemiological study by Mastrangelo et al. (1993). At this time, DMAC levels in air were low (less than 1.5 ppm). Median concentration of NMAC in urine was 20.5 mg/g cr with around 20 % of measurements greater than 30 mg/g cr. IARC (2020) noted that these findings suggest high dermal absorption of DMAC, and that it is unclear whether data from this study are representative of historical conditions in the factory.

In animals

Malley et al. (1995) evaluated the potential chronic toxicity and oncogenicity of DMAC in groups of 87 male and female rats and of 78 male and female mice, by exposing them to 0, 25, 100 or 350 ppm of DMAC for 6 hours per day, 5 days a week for 18 months (mice) or 2 years (rats). Clinical pathology was evaluated at 3, 6, 12, 18 (for mice) and 24 (for rats) months. No increase in hepatic cell proliferation was seen in rats or mice at any exposure concentration and there was no significant increase in the incidence of any tumors in male or female mice or rats. The authors concluded that DMAC was not oncogenic under these experimental conditions in either the rat or mouse. IARC (2020) reported a limitation of the study, as there were inconsistencies in the numbers of rats reported throughout the article.

IARC (2020) analysed a GLP-compliant study by the Japan bioassay research center (JBRC 2013a, b). Mice were exposed to DMAC by whole-body inhalation at concentrations of 0, 12, 60, or 300 ppm for 6 hours per day, 5 days a week, for 104 weeks (n=50/sex/dose). In males, a significant positive trend in the incidence of hepatocellular adenoma was found and a statistically significant increase was observed at 300 ppm. IARC (2020) considered that this increased incidence of hepatocellular adenoma was DMAC-related. A significant positive trend was also seen in females, and at 300 ppm a significant increase in the incidence of hepatocellular adenoma, hepatocellular carcinoma and of hepatocellular adenoma or carcinoma combined was observed.

Another GLP-compliant study was conducted by the Japan bioassay research center in groups of 50 male and female rats exposed to 0, 18, 90, 450 ppm of DMAC by whole-body inhalation for 6 hours per day, 5 days a week, for 104 weeks (JRBC, 2013c and d, as cited in IARC, 2020). In male rats, a significant increase in the incidence of hepatocellular adenoma, and of hepatocellular adenoma and carcinoma combined, were observed; the incidence of hepatocellular carcinoma at 450 ppm exceeded the upper bound of the range for historical controls, at this concentration, the Maximum Tolerated Dose (MTD) was also reached and high hepatotoxicity in general was observed. In females, there was no significant increase in tumor incidence in any of the treated groups compared to controls.

In a study by McGaughey & Jensen (1980) four groups of 10 female hamsters were treated by painting the right cheek pouches with dimethylbenz[a]anthracene (DMBA) in dimethylsulfoxide, 3 times a week for 4 weeks. This was followed by application of either-retinyl acetate (0.05 M) or croton oil (0.5 % in DMSO), then DMSO (control) or DMAC (0.1 M, purity not reported), DMAC

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 359

did not increase the incidence of total oral mucosa tumours, particularly advanced tumors promoted by retinyl acetate or croton oil after initiation by 7,12-dimethylbenz(a)anthracene. IARC (2020) noted some limitations of this study such as the short duration two-stage design, the small number of animals per group, the use of only one sex and a single dose, and the lack of precise information about the exact amount of chemicals applied.

Conclusion

According to the data available and analysed, IARC (2020) concluded that there is *inadequate* evidence in humans for the carcinogenicity of DMAC, while there is *sufficient* evidence of its carcinogenicity in experimental animals. DMAC was classified in Group 2B as *possibly carcinogenic* to humans.

However, neoplastic lesions in available animal studies were located only in the liver and no increase in the risk of developing hepatic tumors has been shown in humans. Moreover, there is only *weak* evidence that DMAC is genotoxic. Therefore, it cannot be ruled out that the carcinogenicity observed in animals results from the hepatotoxicity of DMAC with a dose threshold effect.

3.2.4.5 Reproductive and developmental effects

In humans

No human data was found on reproductive or developmental toxicity.

In animals

Fertility

Groups of 10 male and 20 female rats were exposed to 0, 30, 100 or 300 ppm of DMAC vapour in a one-generation reproduction study by whole-body inhalation. Rats were exposed 6 hours a day, 5 days a week for 7 to 8 weeks through breeding, gestation and lactation. Females were not exposed between gestation day 21 and post-partum day 4. Fertility was not affected at up to the highest concentration tested. The NOAEC for male and female fertility was 300 ppm. The NOAEC for parental toxicity was 100 ppm since reduced body weight and increased relative liver weight were seen in the parental rats at 300 ppm (Ferenz and Kennedy, 1986).

In another study, groups of male rats were exposed to 0, 40, 116 and 386 ppm of DMAC in an inhalation chamber for 6 hours a day, 5 days a week, for 69 days total (43 prior the initiation of mating). No signs of impaired fertility were observed, thus the NOAEC for male fertility was 386 ppm. The NOAEC for parental toxicity was 116 ppm due to increased relative weight of liver at the highest concentration. (Wang et al. 1989).

In a sperm abnormality test, male mice were exposed to 0, 20 or 700 ppm for 7 hours a day, 5 days a week, for 6 weeks. They were not mated and sperm was analysed 5 weeks after the end of exposure. No differences in frequency of sperm abnormality between exposed groups and controls were observed (Fairhurst et al., 1992 as cited in OECD-SIDS, 2001).

Valentine et al. (1997) exposed mice to DMAC in two 10-day inhalation toxicity studies. In the first study, pubescent mice (35 days old) were exposed to DMAC at 30, 100, 310, 490, or 700 ppm for 6 h/day, 5 days/wk for 10 days. Exposure to 490 ppm or greater caused a decrease in relative testes weights and an increase in relative liver weight. Testicular damage, consisting of degeneration of seminiferous tubules and oligospermia, occurred in a concentration-dependent manner from 310 to 700 ppm. In the mice showing less testicular injury, some evidence of

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 360

reversibility was seen after a 14-day recovery period. Since the testicular toxicity of DMAC was thought to be attributable to the use of pubescent mice, a second study was conducted with young adult mice (62 days old) and rats (47 days old) at concentrations of 0, 52, 150, 300, and 480 ppm DMAC. Similar but morphologically less severe testicular lesions than in the pubescent mice were noted but only at 480 ppm; sperm counts and testes weights in all groups were similar to controls. No effects on testicular weights were found in rats at any exposure level. The NOAEC in this study was 100 ppm DMAC for pubescent mice and 300 ppm for young adult mice. Pubescent mice appeared to be more sensitive to the testicular effects of DMAC than young adult rats or mice (Valentine et al., 1997).

Khera et al. (2020) addressed the effect of DMAC on spermatogenesis in rats after intraperitoneal dosing with 862 mg/kg of DMAC, once a week for 8 weeks. They observed oligozoospermia in treated animals, decreased epididymal sperm counts, altered sperm morphology, and decreased sperm motility. According to the authors, DMAC treatment resulted in loss of fertility in male rats; this was not shown, but spermatogenesis was clearly impaired.

Developmental toxicity

In the study by Okuda et al. (2006), pregnant rats were exposed by whole-body inhalation to vapour of DMAC at 0, 100, 300, 450, or 600 ppm for 6 hours a day on gestation day (GD) 6-19. Maternal signs of toxicity (decreased body weight) were seen at 300 ppm and higher. Fetal body weights and the number of live male foetuses were significantly decreased and intra-uterine deaths were increased. The number of foetuses with skeletal and visceral malformations were significantly increased at 450 ppm and above. The NOAEC for maternal and embryofetal toxicity was 100 ppm and the NOAEC for teratogenicity was 300 ppm.

Prenatal toxicity studies were performed by Haskell Lab (1997). In the pilot developmental toxicity study, groups of 8 mated Sprague-Dawley rats were dosed with DMAC at 0, 62.5, 125, 250 or 500 mg/kg bw/day by gavage on gestation days 7 - 21. In dams, decreased body weights at 250 and 500 mg/kg bw were seen, with increased kidney weights (125, 250 and 500 mg/kg bw), and increased liver weights at all doses. At 500 mg/kg bw marked embryoletality was observed. At 250 mg/kg reduced fetal weight and malformations were found. At 125 mg/kg bw 3 fetuses with cleft palate were also observed (total number of fetuses in this group not reported). In the following main prenatal developmental toxicity study, groups of 24 - 25 pregnant Sprague Dawley rats received DMAC by gavage at 0, 20, 65, 150 or 400 mg/kg bw/d on GD 7-21. Mean maternal growth was reduced during the dosing period for animals dosed at 150 and 400 mg/kg. No effect on maternal body weight occurred at lower dose levels. In dams of the 400 mg/kg group absolute and relative kidney weight and relative liver weights were increased, but no histopathological evidence of organ damage and no changes in clinical chemistry were found. At 400 mg/kg embryoletality occurred. In addition, at this dose level fetal weights were reduced, and the incidence of malformed fetuses was increased. At 150 mg/kg minimal developmental toxicity occurred. At this level there was a slight reduction in maternal bodyweight gain and in fetal body weight

The NOAEL for both maternal toxicity and developmental toxicity in this study was 65 mg/kg bw/d (as reported in ECHA, 2014).

Solomon et al. (1991) exposed pregnant rats to DMAC vapours at 0, 32, 100 or 282 ppm for 6 hours per day on GD6-15, by whole body inhalation. No embryofoetal mortality or teratogenicity were observed. At 282 ppm, reduced body weights in foetuses and reduced maternal body

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 361

weight gain during the treatment period were observed with a dose-response trend. The NOAEC for maternal and fetal toxicity was 100 ppm.

Klimisch and Hellwig (2000) conducted a study in pregnant rabbits (15 females per group) exposed to DMAC vapours at 0, 57, 199.5 or 570 ppm (0, 0.2, 0.7, 2 mg/L), for 6 hours a day on GD7-19. The NOAEC of 57 ppm (0.2 mg/L) was obtained for foetotoxic effects (e.g. increased skeletal variations). The NOAECs for teratogenicity (due to increased visceral and skeletal malformations) and for maternal toxicity were 200 ppm and 570 ppm respectively (DFG, 2019).

In the study by Johannsen et al. (1987) groups of 22-25 pregnant rats were given DMAC by gavage at 0, 65, 160 or 400 mg/kg bw/d on GD6-19. A statistically significant reduction of mean maternal body weight gain was observed at 400 mg/kg/d, and at 160 mg/kg/d group there was a slight reduction in body weight gain within the adjusted weight range of 0 - 20 days. At 400 mg/kg bw/d, there was a small but significant increase in the number of resorptions and an increase in total number of malformations.

The latter were mostly cardiovascular malformations, with some skeletal variations such as retardation of ossification. It is unlikely that malformations were secondary to maternal toxicity because of their high incidence and the specificity of cardiovascular defects. The dose-response curve for teratogenicity was very steep since no malformations were observed at the next lower dose of 160 mg/kg bw/d. However, at this dose, increased skeletal variations (associated with decreased body weight) were observed to a slight degree. Thus, the NOAEL for maternal toxicity was 65 mg/kg bw/d and the NOAEL for embryofetal toxicity and teratogenicity was 160 mg/kg bw/d (OECD-SIDS, 2001; (ECHA, 2014).

A study from DuPont (1997) confirmed these findings in groups of 24-25 pregnant rats administered DMAC by gavage at 0, 20, 65, 150 or 400 mg/kg bw/d on GD7-21. Marked maternal toxicity was seen at 400 mg/kg/d with an increase in absolute and relative kidney weight and relative liver weight. Mean maternal body weight gain was reduced during the dosing period at 150 and 400 mg/kg bw/d. At 400 mg/kg bw/d, total number of malformations and skeletal variations was increased. Minimal developmental toxicity was observed at 150 mg/kg bw/d. Therefore, the NOAEL for maternal and developmental toxicity was 65 mg/kg bw/d.

Merkle and Zeller (1980) administered DMAC by gavage in rabbits at 0, 94, 282 or 470 mg/kg bw/d from GD6-18. At 282 and 470 mg/kg bw/d, there was an increase in resorptions, a decrease in the number of live foetuses and an increased number of cleft palates (not statistically different). At 94 mg/kg bw/d and 282 mg/kg bw/d, dams had reduced food intake and bodyweight gain. Thus, the NOAEL for developmental toxicity was 94 mg/kg bw/d.

In an unpublished study cited by DFG (2019), pregnant rats gavaged with 323 mg/kg bw/d of DMAC from GD6-15 had reduced body weights and their fetuses had slightly increased incidences of external and visceral malformations. At this dose level and above, body weight gains in the dams were reduced. The NOAEL for maternal and developmental toxicity was 106 mg/kg bw/d (ECHA 2014).

In two other unpublished studies reported by DFG (2019), mice were given DMAC by gavage from GD6-15. A decrease in foetal body weights and in absolute placenta weights were found at the lowest dose tested of 240 mg/kg bw/d and above in one study. In the other study, pregnant mice were given 1, 1200, and 3000 mg/kg bw/d at GD 6-15 and additional doses of 600 mg/kg bw/d at GD9-12 (with a lower dose of 400 mg/kg bw/d at GD9). The highest sensitivity to

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 362

teratogenic effects was seen on GD9 with effects on body weights at 600 mg/kg bw/d (ECHA, 2014).

Regarding dermal application of DMAC, the studies by Stula (1979) and Stula and Krauss (1977) were not considered appropriate because they are scarcely documented and inadequately reported, and the number of animals tested was low (OECD-SIDS, 2001; DFG, 2019). All developmental studies are summarised in the CLH report (ECHA, 2014), where they were used by the dossier submitter to calculate an overall ED₁₀⁴². This value was of 217 mg/kg bw/d (derived by PROAST) and corresponded to the medium potency group (i.e. 4 mg/kg bw/d < ED10 value < 400 mg/kg bw/d). This value was supported by RAC.

Overall, according to the conclusions of the CLH report (ECHA, 2014), no conclusive information is available on the mechanism of action of DMAC for the induction of developmental effects, but there are no data available indicating that DMAC animal data would not be relevant for humans.

⁴² ED10 (effective dose with a 10 % effect level above the background) or reproductive toxicity dose descriptor: value is the lowest dose which induces reproductive toxic effects with an incidence or magnitude of 10% effect level above background data

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 363

4 Existing toxicity reference values for DMAC for occupationally exposed workers

4.1 Scientific committee on occupational exposure level (SCOEL)

In 1994, the SCOEL retained the respiratory tract irritation as the critical effect to derive an 8h-TWA (Time Weighted Average). The key study by Horn et al. (1961) on rats and dogs reported a LOAEL of 40 ppm (145 mg/m³) for slight irritation of the respiratory tract. The committee applied an uncertainty factor of 5 to extrapolate from LOAEL to NOAEL. Taking into account the preferred value approach, the resulting 8h-TWA was about **10 ppm (36 mg/m³)**.

To limit peak exposure, which could result in irritation, the SCOEL also proposed a 15 min-STEEL of 20 ppm (72 mg/m³).

Due to the contribution of the dermal uptake to systemic toxicity, the committee proposed a “skin notation”.

However, to date, no biological limit value is recommended.

Unfortunately, this assessment has not been updated and as it does not take into account later publications on DMAC effects after 1994, this recommendation is not considered reliable and relevant for this work.

4.2 Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG)⁴³

4.2.1 MAK (maximale Arbeitsplatz Konzentration)⁴⁴ value

As summarised in DFG (2019), the MAK commission selected the Malley et al. (1995) study on lifelong inhalation exposure in rats and mice to derive a MAK value. The liver was the target organ in both species (and liver damage was also reported in workers employed in elastane fibre production after exposure to N,N-dimethylacetamide). The NOAEC in both species was 25 ppm, based on histological changes in the liver of male rats such as focal cystic degeneration and peliosis, and in mice, haemosiderin/lipofuscin accumulation and apoptosis. The MAK commission applied a factor of 2 for extrapolation from animal to human and a factor of 2 to take into account the higher respiratory volume of humans at the workplace compared with animals at rest.

Using the preferred number approach, the MAK value was lowered to **5 ppm** (DFG, 2019).

It is important to note that the MAK commission applied an assessment factor (AF) for POD extrapolation to humans which differs from the usual factors used by other recognised organisations/agencies (ECHA for example recommended at least 2.5 for interspecies kinetic/dynamic differences). Moreover, the German commission did not apply any factor for intraspecies adjustment (e.g. 5 for workers).

4.2.2 BAT value (Biologischer Arbeitsstoff Toleranzwert)⁴⁵

As summarised in DFG (2019), all studies yielded tNMAC concentrations in the range of 30 to 62 mg/l or mg/g cr at air concentrations of 10 ppm DMAC (which was the previous level of the

⁴³ German Research Foundation

⁴⁴ Maximum Workplace concentration

⁴⁵ Concentration for which there is no impact on human health (for non-carcinogenic substances)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 364

MAK value). The results of experimental studies (Maxfield et al., 1975; Knecht et al., 1997) and the field studies by Borm et al. (1987) and Kennedy et al. (1989) are in mutually comparable orders of magnitude, ranging from 21.4 to 40 mg/g cr. A value of 31.3 mg/g cr was indicated, by the MAK commission, as an average concentration for an exposure level of 10 ppm. Based on this, the MAK commission recommended a BAT value of 30 mg/g cr for tNMAC.

In 2018, following the update of the MAK value (5 ppm), the MAK commission estimated that a level of 30 mg tNMAC/g cr is to be expected at the MAK value of 5 ppm, because the level of 10 ppm corresponds to about 30 mg N-methylacetamide/g cr after an 8-hour exposure of volunteers without increased physical activity (Nomiyama et al., 2000) (DFG, 2019). Indeed, the committee argued by the following explanation: “A concentration of 10 ppm in the air corresponds to about 30 mg N-methylacetamide/g creatinine after an 8-hour exposure of volunteers without increased physical activity (Nomiyama et al., 2000). Assuming the uptake due to increased respiratory activity to be twice as high, it may be concluded from this that a level of 30 mg N-methylacetamide/g creatinine is to be expected at the MAK value of 5 ppm, the BAT value is thus preserved”.

4.3 American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH)

4.3.1 Threshold limit value - Time Weighted Average (TLV-TWA)

ACGIH (2018) maintained its previous recommendation (from 1963), supported by studies published afterwards. Indeed, the study by Malley et al. (1995) described above was considered relevant to derive a TLV-TWA based on hepatotoxicity with a NOAEL of 25 ppm. Moreover, the studies by Klimish and Hellwig (2000) and Okuda et al. (2006) reported respectively a NOAEL of 0.2 mg/L (57 ppm) for developmental effects in rabbits and a NOAEL of 100 ppm for fetal (and maternal) toxicity in rats. Therefore, the ACGIH experts recommended a TLV-TWA of **10 ppm (36 mg/m³)** to minimise the potential for hepatotoxicity and for reproductive or developmental effects. This value is also intended to minimise the potential for central nervous system effects observed in human’s studies (Marino et al., 1994 and Weiss et al., 1962a,b). Data were not sufficient to recommend a TLV-STEL.

Due to the dermal absorption of DMAC vapors contributing to the total uptake, the committee attributed a “skin notation”.

4.3.2 Biological Exposure Index

ACGIH (2018) based the recommended BEI on the relationship between exposures to airborne DMAC and tNMAC in urine. According to ACGIH, three volunteer studies (Maxfield et al., 1975; Knecht, 1997; Nomiyama et al., 2000) and two field studies (Borm et al., 1987; Spies et al., 1995) reported consistent results. A level of 10 ppm of DMAC exposure corresponds to a concentration of tNMAC in urine of 20 - 62 mg/g cr. ACGIH recommended a BEI of 30 mg/g cr. However, the experts underlined that the relationship is saturable, thus, results significantly higher than the BEI should be considered with attention.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 365

4.4 Summary of the existing values for DMAC

4.4.1 Summary of the existing occupational exposure level (OEL) values for DMAC

Table VI.5: Overview of existing OELs for DMAC derived for the occupational field

Agency	Date of publication	Endpoint	Key study Description	POD	Assessment factors (AF)	Reference values
SCOEL Europe	1994	Respiratory irritation	Horn et al., 1961 (Rats and dogs)	LOAEL = 40 ppm	AFL = 5	8h-TWA = 8 rounded to 10 ppm
DFG Germany	2019	Liver toxicity	Malley et al., 1995 (Rats and mice)	NOAEC = 25 ppm	AFA = 2 and Allometric = 2 (respiratory volume)	MAK value = 5 ppm
ACGIH USA	2018	Liver toxicity	Malley et al., 1995 (Rats and mice)	NOAEL = 25 ppm	-	TLV-TWA = 10 ppm

AF_L: Assessment factor for extrapolation of a NOAEL from a LOAEL

AF_A: Assessment Factor accounting for interspecies differences

4.4.2 Summary of the existing internal toxicity reference values for DMAC

Table VI.6: Overview of existing biological values for DMAC derived for the occupational field

Agency	Date of publication	Biomarker	Approach	Endpoint – key study	Internal toxicity reference values and sampling time
DFG Germany	2000 Confirmed in 2018	tNMAC in urine	Correlation between airborne DMAC and tNMAC in urine For a MAK value of 5 ppm	Volunteer studies Maxfield et al. (1975); Knecht et al. (1997) Field studies Borm et al. (1987); Kennedy et al. (1989)	BAT: 30 mg.g-1 cr End of shift after several shifts
ACGIH USA	2011	tNMAC in urine	Correlation between airborne DMAC and tNMAC in urine For a TLV-TWA of 10 ppm	Volunteer studies Maxfield et al. (1975); Knecht et al. (1997) Field studies Borm et al. (1987); Kennedy et al. (1989)	BEI: 30 mg.g-1 cr End of shift after several shifts

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 366

4.5 Conclusion

First concerning the European 8h-TWA, additional relevant studies have been published after the initial assessment conducted by SCOEL in 1994. Thus, it appears that the corresponding initially derived 8h-TWA needs to be updated and therefore, cannot be used for the derivation of HBM-GV_{worker}.

Recently, ACGIH (2018) and DFG (2019) selected the same experimental study by Malley et al. (1995) reporting liver effects on rodents for deriving atmospheric values (MAK value of 5 ppm and TLV-TWA of 10 ppm respectively for DFG and ACGIH).

Secondly, for the biological values, SCOEL (1994) did not propose a BLV for DMAC. ACGIH (2018) and the MAK commission (DFG, 2019) have recommended a BEI of 30 mg/g cr for tNMAC in urine. The two committees based their values on the same approach, i.e. the relationship between airborne DMAC concentration and urinary tNMAC concentration. ACGIH and DFG also used the same studies (volunteer and field studies).

Although TLV-TWA and MAK values are different values, the two committees derived the same biological value. The German commission justified this position by:

- The fact that a concentration of 10 ppm in the air corresponds to about 30 mg tNMAC/g cr after an 8-hour exposure of volunteers without increased physical activity (Nomiyama et al., 2000).
- Assuming the uptake due to increased respiratory activity to be twice as high

Therefore, the MAK commission concluded that a level of 30 mg NMAC/g cr is to be expected at the MAK value of 5 ppm.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 367

5 HBM parameters

5.1 Choice of biomarkers

As observed by Spies et al. (1995a), DMAC is present in the urine after DMAC exposure in 93 workers (wearing gloves but no respiratory protection). The authors reported that the majority of data were below the limit of detection and the levels did not appear to vary according to the time sampling.

In the same study, the authors measured acetamide levels in urine and reported correlation with atmospheric DMAC concentration. According to the authors, this correlation is significant but weaker compared to that between urinary total NMAC and DMAC in air. This last metabolite is not used as biomarker of DMAC exposure in routine⁴⁶.

In 2003, Perbelleni et al. identified for the first time AMMA as a new metabolite of DMAC exposure. Princivalle et al. (2010) showed that AMMA could be a relevant urinary biomarker with urinary values similar to those for tNMAC. Moreover, because of its longer half-life, this metabolite could reflect cumulative exposure over the previous few days better than tNMAC. However, there is a lack of data regarding the association of this biomarker with health effects and/or external exposure.

Urinary tNMAC is a specific biomarker of DMAC exposure at the workplace (mainly by inhalation and dermal route), not present in urine of people not exposed to DMAC. Several studies reported correlations between tNMAC concentrations and airborne DMAC (Annex 2).

The time of sampling is important because urinary levels are affected by exposure (*via* inhalation and dermal route) over the preceding day (ACGIH, 2011). Urinary tNMAC is the biomarker recommended by ACGIH and DFG for biomonitoring of DMAC exposure. However, the interpretation of the results must consider the analytical method. To date, almost all authors have used the GC-methodology developed by Barnes and Henry (1976) including a gas chromatography separation under moderate temperature conditions (200°C) while Kawai et al. (1997) observed that a temperature of 250°C in the injection port is required to decompose completely HMMAC into tNMAC.

Table VI.7: Advantages and shortcomings of relevant BME

Analyte	Biological matrix	Advantages	Shortcomings
DMAC	Urine	Specific Not invasive Not found in unexposed workers	Lack of data
DMAC	Blood	Specific Not found in unexposed workers	Short half life Invasive Lack of data
AMMA	Urine	Not invasive Long half-life (30h)	Lack of data Possibly influenced by alcohol consumption

⁴⁶ Biotox website: https://www.inrs.fr/publications/bdd/biotox/dosage.html?refINRS=Dosage_220 (in French) consulted in December 2020

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 368

Analyte	Biological matrix	Advantages	Shortcomings
Acetamide	Urine	Not invasive	Not specific Lack of data Possibly influenced by alcohol consumption
tNMAC	Urine	Specific Not found in unexposed workers Good correlation with airborne DMAC level (<10 ppm) Half-life (16 hours) Not invasive	Possibly influenced by alcohol consumption

Although AMMA in urine may be a relevant biomarker of DMAC, sufficient data to allow the derivation of a biological value are available only for tNMAC. In the absence of a study reporting results for NMAC levels without HMMAC associated, and despite the analytical uncertainty described by Yamamoto et al. (2018), it seems appropriate to recommend the biomonitoring of total NMAC (tNMAC) in urine.

5.2 Analytical methods

Within the HBM4EU project, the published deliverable D9.5 “Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 2nd prioritisation round of substances” gives an insight into the analytical protocols and methods for HBM measurement of tNMAC within HBM4EU. Most studies detailed in this report are based on an historical analytical method based on gas chromatography (GC) described by Barnes and Henry in 1974 for measuring tNMAC in urine. Noteworthy, several authors (Perbellini et al., 2003; Kawai et al., 1997; quoted by Yamamoto et al., 2018) further demonstrated that this approach could be associated to some technical drawbacks (result variability according to the applied GC injection port temperature). The limit of detection of tNMAC was 1.5 mg/L (Perbellini et al. 2003).

More recently, Yamamoto et al. (2018) developed an alternative method to quantify DMAC urinary metabolites (DMAC, NMAC, HMMAC, AMMA), based on liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS), permitting to quantify low concentrations of NMAC and AMMA with precision. The limits of detection for DMAC, HMMAC, NMAC, and AMMA in urine were 0.04, 0.02, 0.05, and 0.02 mg/l, respectively. According to the authors, the BEI recommended by the ACGIH cannot be applied to the NMAC measured in this study because the value was determined by a different method in which HMMAC is decomposed to NMAC.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 369

6 Derivation of HBM-GVs for workers

6.1 Derivation method

According to the methodology developed in the framework of the HBM4EU project, there are three possible options for deriving HBM-GV (Apel et al., 2020).

1. The 1st option to explore is whether HBM-GVs can be derived on the basis of relevant human data, providing evidence of a relationship between concentrations of a substance/its metabolites in human biological media and the occurrence of adverse effects.
2. If derivation is not possible with the 1st option, the 2nd possible option is to derive HBM-GVs on the basis of external limit values proposed by EU or relevant non-EU bodies.
3. If derivation is not possible with the two previous options, the 3rd possible option to consider is to derive HBM-GVs on the basis of critical effects observed in animal toxicological studies.

There is no data linking biomarker levels and health effects of DMAC exposure in human beings. Several studies report a correlation between atmospheric DMAC and BME concentrations.

Thus, option 2 could be preferred, despite the fact that dermal exposure often represents an important additional route of exposure (alone or together with inhalation exposure), so that global exposure is generally badly reflected by airborne DMAC.

Unfortunately, neither the SCOEL recommendations nor the MAK or ACGIH proposals can be used:

The 8h-TWA recommended at European level by the SCOEL (1994) cannot be used to derive a HBM-GV_{Worker} because data are not relevant anymore, regarding the studies published later.

- Despite the robustness of the POD selected by the MAK commission, a NOAEL of 25 ppm based on liver effects in rodents (Malley et al., 1995), the MAK value cannot be used for the derivation of HBM-GV_{Worker}. Indeed, uncertainty factors applied by the German commission are not consistent neither with the ECHA methodology (ECHA, 2019) or the HBM4EU methodology (Apel et al., 2020).
- The extensive database analysed by ACGIH for the derivation of the TLV-TWA is relevant but there is not enough explanation on the extrapolation of the POD (reported from the animal study of Malley et al. 1995) and the final value. Indeed, there is only a factor of 2.5 between the POD and the TLV-TWA. This does not seem protective enough according to the methodology developed in HBM4EU for the derivation of a HBM-GV_{Worker} based on animal results (Apel et al., 2020).

Therefore, the third option is finally considered as the most appropriate to calculate the HBM-GV_{Worker} for DMAC exposure.

The first step is the calculation of a toxicity reference-like value or “TRV-like value” for workers (corresponding to an OEL).

6.2 Calculation of the “TRV-like value”

Based on data described in the toxicological profile of this report but also on the assessments conducted by the MAK commission (2019) and ACGIH (2018), hepatotoxic effects are considered as the most sensitive effects reported in humans and animals following DMAC

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 370

exposure. These effects are therefore selected as critical effects for the derivation of the HBM-GV_{Worker}.

Due to the lack of studies in humans regarding effects on liver, the experimental study by Malley et al. (1995) was selected as the key study; it was also the key study selected for the recommendations by ACGIH 2018 and the MAK commission (DFG, 2019). The authors reported a NOAEC of 25 ppm.

Therefore, based on this POD of 25 ppm for hepatotoxic effects reported in the Malley et al. study, a “TRV-like value” can be derived applying the following AFs according to our methodology (Apel et al., 2020):

- an AF_A for interspecies variability (toxicodynamic component) of 2.5 for the extrapolation to humans (rodents in Malley et al. (1995) being exposed by inhalation, no allometric adjustment is required).
- an AF_H of 5 to take into account interindividual variabilities (value by default for a population of workers)

$$\text{"TRV – like value"} = \frac{25}{12.5} = \mathbf{2 \text{ ppm}}$$

Therefore, the “TRV-like value” of 2 ppm is derived by applying the overall AF of 12.5 to the POD of 25 ppm.

This “TRV-like value” which is intended to protect workers from hepatotoxic effects is appropriate for deriving a HBM-GV_{worker} for DMAC exposure, when workers exposure occurs by inhalation only.

6.3 Calculation of HMB-GVworker

Studies reporting relationships between internal and external concentrations are described in Annex 2. Results based on these studies show tNMAC concentrations in the range of 30 to 62 mg/l or mg/g cr for DMAC concentrations of 10 ppm in the air (DFG, 2019). This large range of values is probably mostly explained by variations in physical effort and consequently in respiratory flow and above all by variable skin exposure and DMAC absorption through this route.

Three relevant studies reporting equations based on correlations between DMAC exposure and tNMAC in urine are detailed in the table below (table VI.8). Thus, based on these equations, tNMAC concentrations could be calculated for an exposure corresponding to the “TRV-like” of 2 ppm (around 7 mg/m³).

In 1989, Kennedy and Pruett studied a group of five workers during four consecutive days exposed to low levels of DMAC (mean between 0.81-1.96 ppm). The authors showed that changes in DMAC exposures could be quantitatively reflected by urinary tNMAC. Indeed, they reported a relationship of 10 ppm (i.e. 10 mg/L) urinary tNMAC for each 1 ppm DMAC inhaled.

In the study by Spies et al. (1995a) conducted on 93 workers (12h workday), the authors reported a correlation between urinary tNMAC and atmospheric DMAC levels ($r^2=0.53$ and $p<0.001$ and $r^2 = 0.54$ when data on workers wearing gloves are only included). To minimise exposure misclassification due to variability in the regression relationship, the authors proposed a limit based on the 80th percentile biomonitoring result about 36 mg/g cr (for tNMAC in urine) corresponding to air levels over 6.7 ppm 12h TWA (or 10 ppm for 8h TWA according to ACGIH).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 371

Qian et al (2012) showed a correlation between tNMAC and DMAC in air on a large population of 201 workers ($r^2= 0.487$ and $p<0.001$). In this study (for which only the abstract is available in English), the authors reported an equation and proposed a biological value of 20 mg/g cr (end of shift at end of week) corresponding to the Chinese reference 8h-OEL of 20 mg/m³ (i.e. 5.5 ppm).

These studies are not easily comparable in terms of methodological aspects and exposure scenarios. Indeed, workers can be exposed mainly by inhalation (wearing gloves) or both by inhalation and dermal route. Moreover, working periods vary, i.e. 8h in Kennedy and Pruett in 1989 and 12h in Spies et al. 1995a, and not available in Qian et al. (2012). Within these studies, Kennedy and Pruett (1989), reported tNMAC concentrations without creatinine adjustment. ACGIH (2011) applied a simple linear extrapolation to an 8h exposure for results based on 12h exposure (Spies et al., 1995a). According to Spies et al. (1995a) an extrapolation from a value corresponding to 12h-exposure to a value for 8h-exposure by a simple linear extrapolation is problematic because the rate of tNMAC varies with route of exposure but also with the time from the start of exposure.

However, in the table below (Table VI.8) this assumption is proposed in italics to compare these values.

Table VI.8: Correlation between DMAC concentration in airborne and tNMAC (designated only by NMAC in the equations) in urine

Reference	Description	Equation linking exposure to tNMAC in urine (sampling time)	Calculation of [tNMAC] in urine for exposure to the TRV-like (2 ppm; 7 mg/m ³)
Kennedy and Pruett 1989	Field study N= 5 4 consecutive weeks 8 hours/d DMAC air (PS) <i>Mean (week): 0.81-1.96 ppm</i>	$C_{NMAC} (mg/L) = 10.8 [IC_{95}: 9.4-12.4] C_{DMAC(ppm)}^*$ Post-shift tNMAC <i>Mean (week): 8-21 mg/l</i> Gas chromatography	21.6 mg/l
Spies et al. 1995a	Field study N=93 12 hours/d Each month for 1 year DMAC air (PS): Mean: 2.01 ppm Range: 0.2-20 ppm	Equation $LnC_{NMAC} (mg/g cr) = 0.894 \times LnC_{DMAC(ppm)} + 2.47$ $R^2 = 0.54$ Post-shift (second workday after 3 days break) tNMAC: 25.2 mg/g cr (Post-shift) Gas chromatography	20 mg/g cr (for 12 hours exposure) <i>13 mg/g cr (for 8h-exposure)</i>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 372

Reference	Description	Equation linking exposure to tNMAC in urine (sampling time)	Calculation of [tNMAC] in urine for exposure to the TRV-like (2 ppm; 7 mg/m ³)
Qian et al. 2012 (only abstract available in English)	Field study N=201 Working period: NA DMAC air (PS): GM = 19.4 (0.4-300.12) mg/m ³ (i.e. 5.3 ppm (0.11-83))	Equation $\text{Log}(C_{\text{NMAC}} \text{ mg/g cr}) = 0.685 + 0.455 \text{ log}(C_{\text{DMAC}} \text{ mg/m}^3)$ $R^2 = 0.497$ and $p < 0.001$ Post- shift/End of workweek tNMAC GM: 23.7 (1.30-189.42) mg/g cr 95e perc (<20 mg/m ³): 23.9 mg/g cr Gas chromatography	12 mg/g cr

* According to the authors this relationship should not be used for extrapolations at air concentrations > 2 ppm
PS: personal air sampler; GM: geometric mean; 95e perc: 95e percentile; NA: Not Available

The study by Kennedy and Pruetz gives interesting results (21 mg/l of tNMAC in urine for a DMAC exposure of 2 ppm). This value is expressed in mg/l thus it is difficult to compare these results with those from Spies et al. and Qian et al.

Based on the values calculated using equations from Spies et al. (1995a) and Qian et al. (2012) (respectively 13 mg/g cr for 8h-exposure, and 12 mg/g cr), a mean value of 12.5 mg/g cr rounded to 12 mg/g cr can be proposed as a HBM-GV_{worker} for tNMAC in urine.

Therefore, based on these results and on the “TRV-like value” of 2 ppm, it seems cautious and conservative to recommend a HBM-_{Worker} of **12 mg/g cr for total NMAC**.

The sampling of urine for the tNMAC measurements should be performed at the end of the work shift (after at least two days of DMAC exposure).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 373

7 Level of confidence attributed to the HBM-GVs

As mentioned in the HBM4EU concept paper to derive HBM-GVs, a level of confidence (low, medium or high) should be attributed to each calculated HBM-GV. The level of confidence should reflect the uncertainties identified during the derivation of the value and could constitute a good incentive to later revise values with estimated 'lower' level of confidence.

It should be specified that the levels of confidence proposed in this document are not determined according to an established recognised methodology, but rather rely on expert judgment regarding the reliability of the data and the calculation method used to derive the HBM-GV values.

The levels of confidence attributed to the HBM-GVs_{worker} are set to “**medium-low**” for **tNMAC**. Please refer to note n 2 of the factsheet presented in section 9 for an explanation of the level of confidence.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 374

8 Discussion

Unlike DMF, the available dataset for DMAC is not robust enough to allow a derivation of an HBM-GV_{Worker} based on relationships between biomarkers levels and health effects.

Despite the existence of an 8h-TWA recommended by SCOEL at European level, and the MAK value recently derived by the German MAK commission, it was not possible to derive a HBM-GV_{Worker} on the basis of these existing reference values. However, the proposed “TRV-like value” in this document is based on the experimental study by Malley et al. (1995) which is also the key study selected by the MAK commission and ACGIH, in 2018.

Since dermal intake can be important depending on the worker's activities results must be interpreted with regards to the actual exposure scenario (to identify an excess exposure via the dermal route for example).

Therefore, the derivation of an HBM-GV_{Worker} presents many uncertainties, thus, the level of confidence applied to this value is “medium-low”.

The choice of total NMAC in urine as the only biomarker selected for deriving an HBM-GV_{Worker} is based on data collected with the method developed by Barnes and Henry (1974) (DFG, 2019). Therefore, biomonitoring measurements should be performed according to this method or by a validated method with respect to a complete HMMAC/NMAC conversion (ACGIH, 2011) to be comparable to the value of 12 mg/g cr of urinary tNMAC. The recent analytical method developed by Yamamoto et al. in 2018 could lead to a development of an HBM-_{Worker} for NMAC with more precision, but further method development needs to be undertaken

Because the estimated half-life of NMAC of 9 - 16 hours implies potential accumulation over the workweek, sampling time is critical, and it is recommended to collect sample urine at the end of the shift after at least two days of exposure.

Alcohol consumption can result in reduced excretion of NMAC, leading to underestimation of DMAC uptake, and should therefore be avoided for 2 days prior to the sampling. Workers must be informed in advance and asked if they have consumed alcohol in the two days prior to the collection.

Although liver effects are the most sensitive, DMAC is classified as Reprotoxic Cat 1B (H360D), thus this effect must be considered. Moreover, DMAC is listed in Directive 92/85/EEC, which aims to encourage improvements in the safety and health at work of pregnant workers and workers who have recently given birth or are breastfeeding. According to this directive, employers must take special measures to assess and to avoid any risk of exposure for breastfeeding and pregnant workers to dangerous chemicals.

DMAC has been classified as possibly carcinogen (2B) by IARC working group (IARC, 2020), because sufficient evidence in animals, despite inadequate evidence in humans. However, as neoplastic lesions in available animal studies were located only in the liver and no increase in the risk of developing hepatic tumors has been shown in humans while evidence of genotoxicity of DMAC is weak, it cannot be ruled out the carcinogenicity observed in animals results from dose threshold hepatotoxicity of DMAC. Thus, carcinogenicity was not considered as an adequate endpoint for deriving a HBM-GV in this document.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 375

9 Factsheet reporting the HBM-GV_{Worker} derivation

Target population Workers			
Parameter	Note	Value/descriptor	Comments
HBM-GV_{Worker} and Status			
HBM-GV _{Worker}	1	tNMAC: 12 mg/g cr	Analytical method to be used for HBM: GC (temperature: injection port about 250°C)
Level of confidence	2	Medium-low	
HBM-GV status	3	Agreed on within HBM4EU	
HBM-GV year of issue	4	2020	
CLP-INDEX-Nr.	5		
EC-Nr.	6	204-826-4	
CAS-Nr.	7	127-19-5	
Harmonised CLP classification	8	Repro 1B (H360D) Acute Tox 4* (H312) Acute Tox 4* (H332)	
Molar mass [g/mol]	9	87.12	
Biomarker(s)			
Identification	10	Total N-methylacetamide in urine	
Molar mass of biomarker(s) [g/mol]	11	61	
Half-life of selected biomarker(s)	12	9-16 h	
Derivation method, starting point and assessment factors			
Type of derivation method selected	13	Based on an animal POD	
Key study	14	Malley et al., 1995	
Species	14	Rats and mice (Sprague Dawley)	
Route/type of study	14	Inhalation	
Exposure duration	14	6h/d for 5 days/week for 18 months (mice) or 2 years (rats)	
Critical endpoint	14	Liver effects	
POD value	14	25 ppm	
Assessment factors	15	2.5 and 5	Inter-species and intra-species variability

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 376

Target population			
Workers			
TRV-like value	16	2 ppm (7 mg/m ³)	
Calculation of HBM-GV_{worker}			
Correlation between BME concentrations and exposure	17	Based on three studies (Kennedy and Pruett 1989, Spies et al., 1995a, Qian et al., 2012)	
Rounded value of HBM-GV_{worker}	18	12 mg/g cr	
Additional Comments			

***Manufacturers or importers must apply at least this minimum classification, but must classify in a more severe hazard category in the event that further information is available which shows that the hazard(s) meet the criteria for classification in the more severe category”

1. HBM-GV_{Worker}: numerical value for total N-methylacetamide in urine
2. Level of confidence in the HBM-GV_{Worker}: reflects the reliability of the proposed HBM-GV. The level of confidence takes into account the various uncertainties underlying the derivation of the HBM-GV (e.g. reliability of the key study used to derive the TRV-like value, uncertainties related to the calculation of the TRV-like value, to toxicokinetic data on the substance of interest, to the extrapolations and calculation of the final HBM-GV). Attribution of a global level of confidence for the proposed tNMAC HBM-GV_{Worker} is suggested, considering:
 - the nature and quality of the toxicological data: the database on DMAC is based on human or animal studies and on few studies carried out at workplace. However, recent data are missing. Moreover, unlike DMF, there are no field studies reporting a relationship between health effects and metabolites levels. Some studies described a correlation between DMAC exposure and the concentration of total NMAC in urine, at workplace with a significant number of subjects. However, studies are conducted following different methodologies →medium confidence
 - the critical endpoint, liver effects, is based on a key study used by the MAK commission (DFG, 2019) and ACGIH (2018), and is relevant for humans. Evidence for these effects is available from epidemiological studies and case studies. → medium confidence
 - the selected key study for identification of the POD: the study by Malley et al. (1995) reported a NOAEL of 25 ppm. The authors exposed female and male rats (696) and mice (624) for 18 months (mice) or 2 years (rats). No effects on liver were observed at the lowest exposure level of 25 ppm and the authors concluded that the NOAEL for male and female rats and mice was 25 ppm. This study is the key study selected by the MAK commission and ACGIH in 2019 and 2018 respectively to derive 8h-OEL. However, no BMDL approach was used to calculate the POD which would reduce the uncertainty in the NOAEL/LAOEL pair and no POD from human data was available →medium confidence
 - the extrapolations to the TRV-like value: according to intra-individual variability (AFH), inter-individual adjustment (AFA) and data quality with default values → medium confidence
 - the calculation of the HBM-GV: Field studies reporting correlations between DMAC exposure and tNMAC are not easily comparable, even if the results are consistent. The

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 377

study by Qian et al. (2012) is not available (abstract only). Moreover, the HBM-GV_{Worker} for tNMAC (NMAC and HMMAC) is closely linked to the analytical method (Gas chromatography), HBM-GV_{Worker} recommended in this report can not be interpreted using the recent assay method developed by Yamamoto et al. (2018) to analyse separately NMAC (without HMMAC) → low confidence

The global level of confidence for tNMAC HBM-GV in the occupational field is set to “medium-low”

3. HBM-GV_{Worker} status: Agreed on within HBM4EU.
4. HBM-GV_{Worker} year of issue: year of setting the HBM-GV_{Worker} in the HBM4EU workframe
5. CLP Index Number: according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures, implementing the globally harmonised system of chemical classification or GHS
http://guidance.echa.europa.eu/docs/guidance_document/clp_introductory_en.pdf
6. EC Number: under European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS), ELINCS (European List of Notified Chemical Substances) in support of Directive 92/32/EEC, the 7th amendment to Directive 67/548/EEC, NLP (No-Longer Polymers), see: ESIS: European chemical Substances Information System:
https://web.archive.org/web/20131106181548if_/http://esis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/
7. CAS Number: collection of disclosed chemical compound information by Chemical Abstracts Service. Almost all molecule databases can be searched by CAS Registry Number.
8. Harmonised CLP classification: CLP classification including CMR and other health-relevant effects. In the case that classification is not harmonised, this should be stated.
9. Molar mass: mass of DMAC per amount of this substance expressed in g/mol
10. Biomarker(s) identification: total N-methylacetamide in urine. Consequently, this metabolite is selected for the HBM-GV derivation.
11. Molar mass of the biomarker(s): mass of the selected biomarkers (expressed in g/mol)
12. Half-life of biomarker: estimated elimination half-lives for tNMAC
13. Derivation method: based on the POD from an animal study which is the third option of the underlying concept
14. POD: Malley et al. (1995) is regarded as the pivotal study for deriving the HBM-GV_{Worker}. The critical effects considered assessment-relevant are the effects on liver.
15. Assessment factors: extrapolation to a concentration of DMAC below which – according to the current knowledge on the substance – there is negligible risk for adverse human health effects anticipated needs application of assessment factors (2.5 interspecies factor, 5 for intraspecies variability)
16. TRV-like value: application of a total assessment factor of 12.5 leads to a TRV-like value of 2 ppm (7 mg/m³)
17. The resulting HBM-GV_{Worker} for the total NMAC is based on this TRV-like value and correlations between airborne DMAC and tNMAC are well-studied (from volunteer and field studies) and consistent (although almost all studies derive the biological values from an atmospheric value of 10 ppm):
18. HBM-GV_{Worker}: 12 mg/g cr

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 378

10 References

American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH) (2011). Biological Exposure Index documentation for N,N-Dimethylacetamide. 7th Edition Documentation. Cincinnati, United States.

American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH). (2018) Threshold Limit Value Documentation for N,N-Dimethylacetamide. Cincinnati, United States.

Apel P, Rousselle C, Lange R., Sissoko F, Kolossa-Gehring M, Ougier E. (2020) Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU) - Strategy to derive Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for health risk assessment. International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health 230 (2020) 113622.

Barnes, JR, Ranta KE (1972). The metabolism of dimethylformamide and dimethylacetamide. Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology 23 (2): 271-76.

Barne JR and Henry NW. (1974). The determination of N-methylformamide and N-methylacetamide in urine. American Industrial Hygien Association 35: 84-87

Batiste-Alentorn M, Xamena N, Creus A, Marcos R (1995). Genotoxic evaluation of ten carcinogens in the Drosophila melanogaster wing spot test. Experientia, 51(1):73–6.

Batiste-Alentorn M, Xamena N, Creus A, Marcos R, Aaron CS (1991). Genotoxicity studies with the unstable zeste-white (UZ) system of Drosophila melanogaster: results with ten carcinogenic compounds. Environmental and Molecular Mutagenesis, 18(2):120–5.

Baum SL, Suruda AJ, (1997) Toxic Hepatitis from Dimethylacetamide. International Journal of Occupational and Environmental Health. 3(1):1–4.

Borm PJA, de Jong L, Vliegen A. (1987) Environmental and biological monitoring of workers occupationally exposed to dimethylacetamide. Journal of Occupational Medicine, 29(11):898–903.

Brindley C, Gescher A, Ross D. (1983) Studies on the Metabolism of Dimethylformamide in Mice. Chem.-Biol. Interactions, 45: 387 - 392.

Cendana M, Lee S, Upadhyay PJ, Byrne JA, Shaw PJ, Earl J, Nath C. (2017) An HPLC-UV method for determining plasma dimethylacetamide concentrations in patients receiving intravenous busulfan. Biomedical Chromatography, 31(7):e3906.

Corsi GC (1971). On occupational pathology caused by dimethylacetamide (with special reference to hepatic function). Med Lav, 62(1):28–42. [Italian]

DFG (2019). Hartwig, A. and MAK Commission *N,N*-Dimethylacetamide [MAK Value Documentation, 2018]. In The MAK-Collection for Occupational Health and Safety (eds). doi:[10.1002/3527600418.mb12719e6519](https://doi.org/10.1002/3527600418.mb12719e6519)

Watts J.C. (1978) Du Pont Company Data, Haskell Laboratory, Unpublished Data

DuPont-Haskell Laboratory-Internal DMAC Review (1988). Unpublished Summary of Data

Du Pont Haskell Labs (1997). DMAC: Developmental toxicity study in Sprague-Dawley rats. Unpublished data.

ECHA (2019). Guidance on information requirements and chemical safety assessment Appendix to Chapter R.8: Guidance for preparing a scientific report for health-based exposure limits at the workplace. European Chemicals Agency.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 379

ECHA (2011). SVHC support document – N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAC). Helsinki, Finland : European Chemicals Agency. Available at <https://www.echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/42751bc8-cad5-4035-82ea-a91c0efe5768> (accessed on september 2020)

ECHA (2012). Draft background document for N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAC). European Chemicals Agency Database. Helsinki, Finland: European Chemicals Agency.

ECHA (2014). Committee for Risk Assessment, RAC, Annex 1, Background document to the opinion proposing harmonised classification and labelling at community level of N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAC). Helsinki, Finland: European Chemicals Agency.

Ferenz RL, Kennedy Jr. GL. (1986) Reproduction Study of Dimethylacetamide following Inhalation in the Rat, *Toxicological Sciences*, 7(1):132–137.

Gong W, Liu X, Zhu B. (2016) Dimethylacetamide-induced occupational toxic hepatitis with a short term recurrence: a rare case report. *Journal of Thoracic Disease*, 8(6):E408–11.

Gosselin, RE, Smith RP, Hodge HC. (1984) *Clinical Toxicology of Commercial Products*. 5th ed. Baltimore: Williams and Wilkins, 1984, p. II-200.

Hempel G, Oechtering D, Lanvers-Kaminsky C, Klingebiel T, Vormoor J, Gruhn B, Boos J. (2007). Cytotoxicity of dimethylacetamide and pharmacokinetics in children receiving intravenous busulfan. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 25(13):1772–8.

Horn HJ. (1961) Toxicology of dimethylacetamide. *Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology*, 3(1):12–24.

Hundley S, Lieder P, Valentine R, McCooley K, Kennedyjr G. (1994) Dimethylacetamide pharmacokinetics following inhalation exposures to rats and mice. *Toxicology Letters*, 73(3):213–25.

IARC - International Agency for Research on Cancer (2020), Volume 123: Some nitrobenzenes and other industrial chemicals. IARC monographs on the evaluation of carcinogenic risks to humans. World Health Organization, Lyon.

Jang YS, Yoon SY, Jo SY, Choi TS, Yoo JY, Woo KH, Ha BG, Jung SJ, Chun BY, Kim JS. (2006). Incidence of dimethylacetamide-induced toxic liver injury among workers in a synthetic fiber manufacturing company. *Korean J Occup Environ Med* 2006; 18: 246-54.

Johannsen FR, Levinskas GJ, Schardein JL. (1987) Teratogenic response of dimethylacetamide in rats. *Fundam. Appl. Toxicol.* 9, 550-556.

JBRC (2013a). Summary of inhalation carcinogenicity study of N,N-dimethylacetamide in B6D2F1/Crlj mice[*text*]. Japan Bioassay Research Center. [Japanese].

JBRC (2013b). Summary of inhalation carcinogenicity study of N,N-dimethylacetamide in B6D2F1/Crlj mice[*tables*]. Japan Bioassay Research Center. [Japanese].

JBRC (2013c). Summary of inhalation carcinogenicity study of N,N-dimethylacetamide in F344/DuCrI/Crlj rat[*text*]. Japan Bioassay Research Center. [Japanese].

JBRC (2013d). Summary of inhalation carcinogenicity study of N,N-dimethylacetamide in F344/DuCrI/Crlj rat [tables]. Japan Bioassay Research Center. [Japanese].

Jung S-J, Lee C-Y, Kim S-A, Park K-S, Ha B-G, Kim J, Yu J-Y, Choi T. (2007) Dimethylacetamide-induced hepatic injuries among spandex fibre workers. *Clinical Toxicology*, 45(5):435–9.

Kawai T, Mizunuma K, Okada Y, Odachi T, Horiguchi S, Iguchi H, Ikeda M. (1997) Separate determination by gas-chromatography of dimethylformamide, dimethylacetamide, monomethylformamide and monomethylacetamide in urine for biological monitoring. *Journal of Occupational Health*, 39(2):113–8.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 380

Kelly DP, KernsWD, Burgess BA, Kennedy Jr. GL. (1984) Subchronic inhalation of dimethylacetamide in rats, *Toxicologist*, 4:65.

Kennedy GL, Pruett JW (1989). Biologic monitoring for dimethylacetamide: measurement for 4 consecutive days in a workplace. *J Occup Med*, 31:47-50.

Kennedy GL and Sherman H. (1986) Acute and Subchronic Toxicity of Dimethylformamide and Dimethylacetamide Following Various Routes of Administration. *Drug and Chemical Toxicology*, 9(2):147–70.

Kennedy GL. (1986) Biological Effects of Acetamide, Formamide, and Their Monomethyl and Dimethyl Derivatives. *CRC Critical Reviews in Toxicology*, 17(2):129–82.

Khera N, Ghayor C, Lindholm AK, Pavlova E, Atanassova N, Weber FE (2020). N,N-Dimethylacetamide, an FDA approved excipient, acts post-meiotically to impair spermatogenesis and cause infertility in rats. *Chemosphere*, 256:127001.

Kim HR, Kim TW. (2010) Occupational Hepatic Disorders in Korea. *Journal of Korean Medical Science*, 25(Suppl):S36.

Kinney LA, Burgess BA, Stula EF, Kennedy GL Jr (1993). Inhalation studies in rats exposed to dimethylacetamide (DMAc) from 3 to 12 hours per day. *Drug and Chemical Toxicology*, 16(2):175–94

Klimisch HJ, Hellwig J. (2000) Developmental toxicity of dimethylacetamide in rabbits following inhalation exposure. *Human Exp Toxicol*, 19:676-683.

Knecht U. (1997) Studies on dermal vapor phase absorption of N,N-dimethylacetamide under standardized conditions. In: A Harwerth (Ed), *Verband Deutscher Betriebs und Berufsärzte (VDBW), Documentation Autumn Conference*, 153-155. Gantner Verlag Stuttgart.

Lauwerys R, Hoet P (1993) *Industrial chemical exposure: Guidelines for Biological Monitoring*. Lewis Publishers, Boca Raton, Ann Arbor, London, Tokyo; 2nd ed

Lee C-Y, Jung S-J, Kim S-A, Park K-S, Ha B-G. (2006) Incidence of dimethylacetamide induced hepatic injury among new employees in a cohort of elastane fibre workers. *Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 63(10):688–93.

Malley LA, Slone TW, Makovec GT, Elliott GS, Kennedy GL. (1995) Chronic Toxicity/Oncogenicity of Dimethylacetamide in Rats and Mice Following Inhalation Exposure. *Fundamental and Applied Toxicology*, 28(1):80–93.

Marino G, Anastopoulos H, Woolf AD (1994). Toxicity associated with severe inhalational and dermal exposure to dimethylacetamide and 1,2-ethanediamine. *Journal of Occupational Medicine*, 36(6):637–41.

Mastrangelo G, Serena R, Marzia V. (1993) Mortality from tumours in workers in an acrylic fibre factory. *Occupational Medicine*, 43(3):155–8.

Maxfield, M. E., Barnes, J. R., Azar, A., & Trochimowicz, H. T. (1975). Urinary excretion of metabolite following experimental human exposures to DMF or to DMAC. *Journal of occupational medicine*. Official publication of the Industrial Medical Association, 17(8), 506–511.

McGaughey C, Jensen JL. (1980) Effects of the Differentiating Agents (Inducers) Dimethylacetamide, Di- and Tetramethylurea on Epidermal Tumor Promotion by Retinyl (Vitamin A) Acetate and Croton Oil in Hamster Cheek Pouch. *Oncology*, 37(2):65–70.

McGregor DF. (1980) Tier II mutagenic screening of 13 NIOSH priority compounds, individual compound report, N,N-dimethyl-acetamide, Report No. 27. Cincinnati (OH), USA: National Institute of Occupational Safety and Health.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 381

Merkle J, and Zeller H. (1980) Investigations of acetamides and formamide for embryotoxic and teratogenic effects in rabbits. *Arzneim. Forsch.* 30, 1557- 1562.

Mitchell ID, Gilbert PJ, Brice AJ, White DJ (1981). Somatic eye mutation in *Drosophila melanogaster* as a shortterm test for mutagens and carcinogens. *Carcinogenesis*, 2(8):783–6.

Muñoz ER, Barnett BM (2003). Chromosome malsegregation induced by the rodent carcinogens acetamide, pyridine and diethanolamine in *Drosophila melanogaster* females. *Mutat Res*, 539(1-2):137–44.

Nomiyama T, Omae K, Ishizuka C, Yamauchi T, Kawasumi Y, Yamada K, et al. Dermal absorption of N,N-dimethylacetamide in human volunteers. *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health*. 2000 Feb 15;73(2):121–6.

OECD-SIDS (2001). N,N-Dimethylacetamide SIDS Initial Assessment Report for 13th SIAM (Bern, Switzerland, 6–9 November 2001). Available from: <https://hvpchemicals.oecd.org/ui/handler.axd?id=16564422-daff-4489-8c27-735d3ab0b260>, accessed September 2020.

Oechtering D, Boos J, Hempel G (2006). Monitoring of N,N-dimethylacetamide in children during i.v. busulfan therapy by liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry. *J Chromatogr B Analyt Technol Biomed Life Sci*, 838(2):129–34

Okuda H, Takeuchi T, Senoh H, Arito H, Nagano K, Yamamoto S, et al. (2006). Developmental toxicity induced by inhalation exposure of pregnant rats to N,N-dimethylacetamide. *Journal of Occupational Health*, 48(3):154–60.

Palmen NG, Evelo CT, Borm PJ, Henderson PT. (1993) Toxicokinetics of dimethylacetamide (DMAC) in rat isolated perfused liver. *Human and Experimental Toxicology*, 12(2):127-33.

Perbellini L, Princivalle A, Caivano M, Montagnani R. (2003) Biological monitoring of occupational exposure to N,N-dimethylacetamide with identification of a new metabolite. *Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 60(10):746–51.

Princivalle A, Pasini F, Perbellini L. (2010) S-(acetamidomethyl)mercapturic acid (AMMA): A new biomarker for occupational exposure to N,N-dimethylacetamide. *Journal of Chromatography B: Analytical Technologies in the Biomedical and Life Sciences*, 878(27):2515–9.

Qian YL, Xu CM, Lu YY, Tang HF, Ruan Z, Wang H, Zhu HB, Liu DH, Zhang X. (2012) Biological limit value for occupational exposure to N, N-dimethylacetamide. *Zhonghua Lao Dong Wei Sheng Zhi Ye Bing Za Zhi*, 30(9):709-11. [Chinese]

Sherman H and Barnes JA. (1986) Biological effects of acetamide, formamide, and their monomethyl and dimethyl derivatives. Kennedy GL. *CRC Crit Rev Toxicol* 17:129182

Shrivastava SP. (1974) Metabolic fate of N,N-dimethyl-acetamide-carbonyl-¹⁴C in rats, Haskell Laboratory Report N° 686.

Menicagli S, Longo V, Mazzaccaro A, Gervasi Pier G. (1994). Microsomal metabolism of N,N-dimethylacetamide and N,N-dimethylacetamide and their effects on drug-metabolizing enzymes of rat liver. *Biochemical Pharmacology*, 48(4), 717-726

Smyth HF, Carpenter CP, Well CS, Pozzani UC, Striegel JA. (1962) Range-Finding Toxicity Data: List VI. *American Industrial Hygiene Association Journal*, 23(2):95–107.

Solomon HM, Ferenz RL, Kennedy Jr. GL, Staples RE. (1991) Developmental Toxicity of Dimethylacetamide by Inhalation in the Rat, *Toxicological*, 16(3):414–422

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 382

Spies GJ, Rhyne RH Jr, Evans RA, Wetzel KE, Ragland DT, Turney HG, Leet TL, Oglesby, JL. (1995a) Monitoring acrylic fiber workers for liver toxicity and exposure to dimethylacetamide: Assessing exposure to dimethylacetamide by air and biological monitoring. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 37(9):1093–101.

Spies GJ, Rhyne RH Jr, Evans RA, Wetzel KE, Ragland DT, Turney HG, Leet TL, Oglesby, JL. (1995b) Monitoring acrylic fiber workers for liver toxicity and exposure to dimethylacetamide: Serum clinical chemistry results of dimethylacetamide-exposed workers. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 37(9):1102–7.

Stula and Krauss, 1977 (cited in Kennedy 1986, ACGIH 2001)

Su TC, Lin PH, Chiu MJ, Chu TS, Chang MJW, Wang JD, et al. (2000). Dimethylacetamide, ethylenediamine, and diphenylmethane diisocyanate poisoning manifest as acute psychosis and pulmonary edema: treatment with hemoperfusion. *Journal of Toxicology: Clinical Toxicology*, 38(4):429–33.

Terada M, Nudel U, Fibach E, Rifkind RA, Marks PA (1978). Changes in DNA associated with induction of erythroid differentiation by dimethyl sulfoxide in murine erythroleukemia cells. *Cancer Research*, 38(3):835–40.

Tolando R, Zanovello A, Ferrara R, Iley JN, Manno M. (2001) Inactivation of rat liver cytochrome P450 (P450) by N,N-dimethylformamide and N,N-dimethylacetamide. *Toxicology Letters*, 124(1–3):101–11.

Trame MN, Bartelink IH, Boos J, Boelens JJ, Hempel G (2013). Population pharmacokinetics of dimethylacetamide in children during standard and once daily IV busulfan administration. *Cancer Chemotherapy and Pharmacology*, 72(5):1149–55.

Valencia R, Mason JM, Woodruff RC, Zimmering S (1985). Chemical mutagenesis testing in *Drosophila*. III. Results of 48 coded compounds tested for the National Toxicology Program. *Environmental Mutagenesis*, 7(3):325–48.

Valentine R, Hurtt ME, Frame SR, Kennedy Jr. GL. (1997) Inhalation toxicology of dimethylacetamide (DMAC) in mice and rats: age-related effects on lethality and testicular injury. *Inhalation Toxicology*, 9(2):141–56.

Wang GM, Kier LD, Pounds GW (1989) Male fertility study on N,N-dimethylacetamide administered by the inhalation route to Sprague-Dawley rats. *J Toxicol Environ Health*, 27:297-305.

Weiss AJ, Jackson LG, Carabasi RA, Mancall EL, White JC (1962a). A phase I study of dimethylacetamide. *Cancer Chemotherapy Report*, 16:477–85.

Weiss AJ, Mancall EL, Koltjes JA, White JC, Jackson LG. (1962b) Dimethylacetamide: A Hitherto Unrecognized Hallucinogenic Agent. *Science*, 3511(136): 151-152.

Yamamoto S, Matsumoto A, Yui Y, Miyazaki S, Kumagai S, Hori H, Ichiba M. (2018) Concentration determination of urinary metabolites of N,N-dimethylacetamide by high-performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry. *Journal of Occupational Health*, 60(2):140–7.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 383

11 Annexes

11.1 Annex 1: Genetic and related effects of DMAC and its metabolite acetamide in human cell *in vitro* and in experimental systems (IARC, 2020)

Test system (species, strain, sex)	Endpoint	Results		Agent, concentration (LEC or HIC)	Comments	Reference
		Without metabolic activation	With metabolic activation			
Human embryonic intestinal cells	Unscheduled DNA synthesis	-	(-)	DMAC, 9366 µg/ml	The incorporation of radiolabel was insufficient to permit analysis of results in the presence of S9	McGregor (1980)
Rat, CD (M, F)	Chromosomal aberrations	-	NA	N,N Dimethylacetamide, inhalation, 700 ppm, 7 h/d for 5 d		McGregor (1980)
Rat, CD (M)	Dominant lethal test	-	NA	N,N Dimethylacetamide, inhalation, 700 ppm, 7 h/d for 5 d		McGregor (1980)
Rat, CD (M, F)	DNA damage	-	NA	N,N Dimethylacetamide, inhalation, 700 ppm, 7 h/d for 5 d		McGregor (1980)
Mouse erythroleukaemia cell, strain 745A	DNA damage	+	NT	N,N Dimethylacetamide, 30 mM		Terada et al. (1978)
Drosophila melanogaster	Sex-linked recessive lethal mutations	-	NA	N,N Dimethylacetamide, 200 ppm, 95 min in atmosphere		McGregor (1980)
Drosophila melanogaster (sc z w ⁺ sn)	Somatic mutation and recombination test (SMART)	-	NA	Acetamide, 4500 ppm after feeding		Mitchell et al. (1981)
Drosophila melanogaster	Sex-linked recessive lethal mutations	-	NA	Acetamide, 50000 ppm, after feeding or injection		Valencia et al. (1985)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 384

Test system (species, strain, sex)	Endpoint	Results		Agent, concentration (LEC or HIC)	Comments	Reference
		Without metabolic activation	With metabolic activation			
Drosophila melanogaster, unstable Zeste- White (UZ)	SMART	+	NA	Acetamide, 10 mM	Doses tested: 0, 10, 20, and 30 mM; positive result at 10 mM	Batiste Alentorn et al. (1991)
Drosophila melanogaster, trans heterozygous (mwh +/-flr3)	SMART	+	NA	Acetamide, 50 mM	Doses tested: 0, 20, 30, and 50 mM; positive result at 50 mM	Batiste Alentorn et al. (1995)

d, day; F, female; HIC, highest ineffective concentration; LEC, lowest effective concentration; M, male; min, minute; NA, not applicable; NT, not tested; ppm, parts per million; +, positive; -, negative; (-), negative in a study of limited quality

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 385

11.2 Annex 2: Exposure at workplace and relation between airborne DMAC and total NMAC in urine

References	Subjects	Results (total NMAC in urine (NMAC))	Comments
Field studies			
Borm et al. 1987	Field study N= 8 Average exposure: 14 ppm (0.7-51.9) 8 hours - 5 days	NMAC: Mean 0.54 +/- 0.20 µmol/(hxkg bw) Corresponding to 57 mg/l (i.e. 57 mg/g cr according to ACGIH* 2011 and 48 according to DFG, 2000) <i>After 2-3 days (Post-shift)</i> ACGIH extrapolated to 8h-exposure to 10 ppm: 34 mg/L or 34 mg/g cr after 2 or 3days exposure	No correlation found between end of shift NMAC in urine and DMAC in air According to ACGIH, this can be explained by influence of dermal absorption
Kennedy and Pruett 1989	Field study N= 5 4 consecutive weeks Mean (week): 0.81-1.96 ppm	Mean (week) 13 mg/l (range 1-42 mg/L) <i>Post-shift</i> Equation reported by authors NMAC (mg/l)= 10.8 (9.2-12.4) x DMAC (ppm)	According to the authors this relationship should not be used for extrapolations at air concentrations >2 ppm In this study, workers had to minimise the dermal exposure
Spies et al. 1995a	Field study N=93 Mean: 2.01 ppm (range 0.2-20 ppm) 12 hours schedules (2 days on, 2 off, 3 on, 3 off, 2 on, 2 off...)-	Geometric Mean (Geometric standart deviation) = 16.1 mg/g cr (2.5) Equation LnCNMAC (mg/g cr)= 0.894 x lnCDMAC(ppm) + 2.47 R ² = 0.54	Relationship based on workers wearing gloves but no respiratory protection According to the authors, an air level of 6.7 ppm (12h- TWA) corresponded to a NMAC level of 62 mg/g cr (ES)
Perbellini et al. 2000	N=223 No ambient monitoring but previous measurements: Median < 1.5 ppm	Survey 1: N= 223 Mean: 20.5 mg/g cr. (Post-shift) Median: 7.7 mg/g cr (1.5-173.6)	
		Survey 2: N=35 Mean: 14.2 mg/g cr Median: 4.9 mg/g cr (1.5-30.6 mg/g cr)	Subjects above 30 mg/g cr (in survey 1) and with instruction to avoid dermal exposure
Qian et al. 2012 (only abstract available in english)	Field study N=201 GM = 19.4 (0.4-300.12) mg/m ³ (i.e. 5.3 ppm (0.11-83))	GM: 23.7 (1.30-189.42) mg/g cr 95e perc <20 mg/m ³ : 23.9 mg/g cr Equation Log(NMAC mg/g Cr) = 0.685 + 0.455 log (DMAC mg/m(3)) Post- shift/End of workweek	The authors recommended a BLV of 20 mg/g cr (end of workweek) corresponding to the China OEL of 20 mg/g cr (i.e. 5.5 ppm)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 386

References	Subjects	Results (total NMAC in urine (NMAC))	Comments
Experimental studies			
Maxfield et al. 1975	N= 2 Volunteers Exposed 2x3 hours at 10 ppm	25 µg/min Corresponding to: ACGIH 2011: 30 mg/l or 30 mg/g cr (and 40 mg/l for 8h exposure) DFG 2000: 25 mg/l or 30 mg/g cr	With and without protective mask between 5 to 15 hours after the end of exposure
Knecht 1997	Volunteer study N= 10 volunteers Exposed 2x4 hours at 10 ppm	Mean = 21.4 +/- 13.2 mg/g cr Two hours post exposure 95 ^e perc. = 31.9 mg/g cr	Exposure <i>via</i> inhalation and dermal route
Nomiyama et al. 2000	Volunteer study N= 12 volunteers Exposed 4 hours to 6.1 ppm	11.2 mg /g cr. (6.9-20.1 mg/g cr) The authors extrapolated the NMAC concentration for an exposure of 10 ppm (8h): 33.7 mg/g cr after 5 days	Inhalation only

* ACGIH estimated an average body weight of 70 kg, assumed a urinary flow rate of 0.83 ml/min and a mean urinary creatinine concentration of 1 mg/l

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 387

Part VII

Substance dossier on perfluorohexane sulfonic acid (PFHxS) - CAS no.: 355-46-4

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 388

Table of contents (Part VII)

Authors and acknowledgement	389
Glossary	390
1 Introduction	392
2 General information and physico-chemical properties of PFHxS	393
3 Production volumes and use of PFHxS	394
4 Exposure and Human Biomonitoring	395
5 Toxicological profile of PFHxS	401
5.1 Toxicokinetics	401
5.1.1 Human data	401
5.1.2 Animal data	401
5.2 Toxicity	403
5.2.1 Acute toxicity	403
5.2.2 Irritation and sensitisation	403
5.2.3 Repeated dose toxicity	403
5.2.4 Genotoxicity	405
5.2.5 Carcinogenicity	406
5.2.6 Toxicity to reproduction and development	406
5.2.7 Mechanistic studies and in vitro data	406
6 Existing evaluations and derivations of tolerable doses (toxicity reference values)	408
7 Selected biomarkers and analytical method	410
8 Summary and Discussion	411
9 References	412

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 389

Authors and acknowledgement

Authors

Jens Uwe Voss on behalf of UBA, Petra Apel (UBA)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 390

Glossary

AF	Assessment factor(s)
ALT	Alanine transaminase
AM	Arithmetic Mean
AP	Alkaline Phosphatase
AST	Aspartate transaminase
ATSDR	Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry
bw	Body weight
CAR	Constitutive Activated Receptor, Constitutive Androstan Receptor
DNEL	Derived no effect level
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
F	Female
GD	Gestation day
GM	Geometric Mean
GV	Guidance value (Richtwert)
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
IUPAC	International Union of Pure and Applied Chemicals
LD	Lactation day
LD50	Lethal dose, 50 %
LO(A)EL	Lowest observed (adverse) effect level
LoD	Limit of detection
LoQ	Limit of quantification
M	Male
NHANES	National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey
NO(A)EL	No observed (adverse) effect level
NTP	National Toxicology Program
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PFBS	Perfluorbutane sulfonic acid
PFC	Perfluoro compounds
PFHxS	Perfluorohexane sulfonic acid
PFNA	Perfluorononanoic acid
PFOA	Perfluorooctanoic acid
PFOS	Perfluorooctane sulfonic acid

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 391

PND	Postnatal day
POD	Point of departure
PPAR	Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
SD	Standard Deviation
TRV	Toxicity Reference Value
ESB	Environmental specimen bank
US EPA	United States Environmental Protection Agency

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 392

1 Introduction

Perfluorohexane sulfonic acid (PFHxS, structure see figure VII.1) and its derivatives belong to the group of perfluorinated substances used in numerous products (NEA, 2018). For the findings compiled in this report, several recent reviews and evaluations were used (ATSDR, 2021; Bull et al., 2014; EFSA, 2020; FSANZ, 2017; Hassauer et al., 2016; NTP, 2016; UBA, 2017).

Studies critical for the evaluation were checked as original publication. Furthermore, an Annex XV report prepared by the Swedish Chemicals Agency is also available (ECHA, 2017). Under REACH, PFHxS, like some of its salts, has so far only been pre-registered.

However, PFHxS and its salts have been classified as substances with particularly high persistence and bioaccumulation in accordance with Annex XII under REACH. Due to the weak data situation and the mostly co-occurrence of PFHxS and other perfluorinated substances in the environment and in humans, no HBM-GV is proposed for PFHxS alone in the following, but only the available data are presented.

Figure VII.1: Structural formula of perfluorohexane sulfonic acid (PFHxS)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 393

2 General information and physico-chemical properties of PFHxS

Table VII.1 lists the substance characteristics and physicochemical properties of PFHxS. It is a solid substance at room temperature with low to moderate water solubility and low vapour pressure.

Table VII.1: Physico-chemical properties of perfluorohexane sulfonic acid

Substance	perfluorohexane sulfonic acid*
IUPAC Name	1,1,2,2,3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6,6-tridecafluorohexane-1-sulfonic acid
CAS-No.	355-46-4
Sum formula	C ₆ HF ₁₃ O ₃ S
Molar mass	400.1 g/mol
Vapour pressure ⁺	58.9 Pa (calculated)
Melting point	272-274 °C
Boiling point ⁺	no data
Density	no data
Log k _{ow} ⁺	not measurable 5.17 (non-ionised, estimated) 7.55 (non-ionised, COSMOtherm, estimated) -2.75 (at pH 1-9, ToxSuite, estimated) -2.38 (non-ionised, COSMOtherm, estimated)
pK _s	-3.45 (estimated, COSMOtherm) -5.8 ± 1.3 (Danish QSAR database)
Solubility in water ⁺	2300 mg/l (COSMOtherm, estimated)
Physical state at 20 °C, 1013 hPA ⁺	solid
Colour ⁺	no data

*: Data from ECHA (2017)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 394

3 Production volumes and use of PFHxS

The starting material for PFHxS and its salts and derivatives is perfluorohexane sulfonylfluoride (PFHxSF). Rough estimates based on sales figures and prices indicate a future expected annual consumption of PFHxSF of about 10-40 t in Europe, 10 - 60 t in the USA and Canada and 60-300t in Asia.

However, the current global production capacity is estimated to be in the order of 1000 - 1500 kg/a, but probably only a small proportion of potential producers have been identified. The main final consumption is in the textile sector, followed by surfactants and foams and packaging materials, and the semiconductor production sector (NEA, 2018).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 395

4 Exposure and Human Biomonitoring

According to a study on PFHxS sources commissioned by the Norwegian Environmental Protection Agency, there are significant data gaps in the global production, use and release of PFHxS, its salts and structurally related compounds (79 substances in total) (NEA, 2018). According to the information currently available, PFHxS or its derivatives may be present in both industrial and consumer products such as extinguishing foam, coated paper in contact with food, water-repellent agents or cleaning agents.

Drinking water has been repeatedly shown to be a possible source of oral exposure for the general population, being contaminated in various ways with perfluorinated substances. The studies carried out to determine exposure generally show that there is exposure to several perfluorocarboxylic and perfluorosulfonic acids at the same time, and due to the early widespread use, C₈ perfluorocarbons still predominate in most cases.

PFHxS can also be detected in food. In a study conducted in Spain of forty food groups (meat, fish, eggs, milk, dairy products, vegetables, fruit, cereals, baked goods, oils), the highest levels were found in fish and seafood (mean value: 45 pg PFHxS/g fresh weight), followed by vegetables (mean value 4.5 pg/g fresh weight) and meat (3.2 pg/g fresh weight); in the other food groups the levels were generally below the detection limit (Domingo et al., 2012). The highest total intake of PFHxS was estimated to be 0.17 ng/(kg bw x d) for 6 - 9-year-old children (these estimates included non-measurable exposures of food with PFHxS at half the detection limit, which was not mentioned. Intake without these values was 0.08 ng/(kg bw x d)). Recently, the EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain (EFSA CONTAM Panel) conducted a detailed evaluation of perfluoroalkyl substances in food. Based on 4745 analytical data, the mean PFHxS exposure ranged for the LB from 0.04 to 0.36 ng/(kg bw x d) and for the UB⁴⁷ from 2.5 to 29.0 ng/(kg bw x d) across surveys and age groups. At high (95th percentile) exposure, the LB ranged from 0.09 to 0.86 ng/(kg bw x d) and the UB from 4.6 to 57.6 ng/(kg bw x d) (EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain et al., 2020).

The internal exposure to perfluorine compounds is usually determined by measuring the concentration in blood serum or plasma. PFHxS, similar to PFOS, could be detected in the majority of the samples examined (Table VII.2). For example, PFHxS could be detected in almost all samples in the German Environmental Specimen Bank measured in 1982-2010 (Schröter-Kermani et al., 2013). The range of the median values determined over the years in this study, 0.85-1.87 ng/ml, covers the range that was also determined in other studies conducted in Germany in groups of persons not exposed to any particular source of exposure. More recent measurements carried out in this investigation programme up to 2019 showed that PFHxS could be detected in all samples investigated, but that the PFHxS load had decreased compared to the previous investigation period. Median values and 90th percentiles for this more recent period tended to show a decreasing burden (e.g. P50, 2009: 0.8 ng/ml, 2019: 0.5 ng/ml). Broken down by gender, a higher burden was found in men than in women, although this difference tended to become smaller over the years (Göckener et al., 2020).

Elevated serum PFHxS levels were found in a number of studies in people who were exposed to PFC contaminated drinking water, e.g. in Arnsberg (Hölzer et al., 2008), where the levels were still elevated two years after the drinking water contamination had been switched off (Brede et al., 2010). Similar to higher internal PFHxS exposures also occurred in an area of northern Italy

⁴⁷ UB: upper bound, i. e. levels based on using LOQ/LOD in case of non-detected levels;

LB: lower bound, i.e. levels using zero for nondetects (EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain et al., 2020).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 396

where the drinking water supply had been contaminated by PFCs (Ingelido et al., 2018). Extremely high values occurred in an area in southern Sweden: Here the groundwater used for drinking water production was contaminated by perfluorosulfonic acids from an airport in the middle of the water supply area. The median contamination by PFHxS reached values that were already higher than the 95th percentiles of other investigations, with peak values above 1500 µg/l (Li et al., 2018).

According to research conducted in an area in Sweden (Uppsala district), PFHxS in the blood of first-time mothers (n=413) shows a positive trend with an increase of 8.3 %/a over the period 1996-2010 (Glynn et al., 2012). This finding is consistent with the steady increase of PFHxS concentrations in the serum of blood donors in North Rhine-Westphalia over the period 1977-2004 (Wilhelm et al., 2009). The analysis of samples of the German environmental specimen bank (ESB) also showed an increase in PFHxS concentrations between 1982 and 2005, after which the concentration in blood plasma dropped significantly (Göckener et al., 2020).

Table VII.2: Concentration and detection frequency of PFHxS in blood serum or plasma

Study location, group, group size and study period	Number of samples	Detection limit	Frequency of detection (%)	Concentration (ng/ml)	Study
ESB, general population, 10 M + 10 F/a, 20 – 29 a, 2009 – 2019 (every 2 nd year)	20/a	0.25 ng/ml	100	P50: 0.5-0.8 ^a P90: 1.1-1.6 Max. 4.6	(Göckener et al., 2020)
ESB, general population, 10 M + 10 F/a, 20-29 a, 1982-2010	258	0.5 ng/ml	98.4	P50: 0.85-1.87 [§] Max. 8.0	(Schröter-Kermani et al., 2013)
Greater Berlin, 21 mothers of non-breastfed children, 1997-1999	21	0.25 ng/ml	100	AM ± SD: 1.8 ± 0.9	(Abraham et al., 2020)
Arnsberg, PFC-contaminated drinking water, 101 M (47.1 a ⁺), 164 F* (36.2 +), 90 children (school beginners, 5.8 a ⁺)*, 2006	101, 164, 90	0.1 ng/ml	M: 100 F: 98,8 Children: 100	M, AM: 2.7, P95: 4.4, Max. 8.7 F, AM: 1.2, P95: 2.2, Max. 5.7 Children, AM: 1.4, P95: 2.1, Max. 13.4	(Hölzer et al., 2008)
Brilon, without PFC-contaminated drinking water, 103 M (47.9 a ⁺), 2006	103	0.1 ng/ml	100	AM: 2.4, P95: 4.3, Max. 5.4	(Hölzer et al., 2008)
Siegen, without PFC-contaminated drinking water, 153 F* (35.4 a ⁺), 80 children (school beginners, 5.7 a ⁺)*, 2006	153, 80	0.1 ng/ml	F: 98,7 Children: 98,8	F, AM: 0.7, P95: 1.5, Max. 2.1 Children, AM: 1.0, P95: 2.2, Max. 9.1	(Hölzer et al., 2008)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 397

Study location, group, group size and study period	Number of samples	Detection limit	Frequency of detection (%)	Concentration (ng/ml)	Study
Arnsberg: 23 M, 22 F, 20 children (follow-up), 2008	23, 22, 20	0.1 ng/ml	100, 100, 100	M, P50: 2.3, P95: 3.3, Max. 3.7 F, P50: 0.8, P95: 1.6, Max. 1.9 Children, P50: 0.7, P95: 7.0 Max. 11.8	(Brede et al., 2010)
Brilon: 24 M, Siegen: 24 F, 25 children, 2008	24, 24, 25	0.1 ng/ml	100, 54, 2, 84	M, P50: 1.4, P95: 4.1, Max. 4.1 F, P50: 0.5, P95: 1.3, Max. 1.8 Children, P50: 0.5, P95: 1.9 Max. 4.2	(Brede et al., 2010)
Arnsberg, blood donor, 1997-2004, 20-31 a	30	0.1 ng/ml		P50: 1.7, range 0.5-4.6	(Wilhelm et al., 2009)
Emmerting, blood donor, 2009 and 2015	2009: 60 2015: 26	0.2 ng/ml	2009: 88.3 2015: 76.9	2009: P50 0.4, P95 1.3, Max. 2.3 2015: P50 0.4, P95 0.9, Max. 1.1	(Fromme et al., 2016; 2017)
Passau, blood donor, 2009 and 2015	2009: 60 2015: 50	0.2 ng/ml	2009: 100 2015: 88	2009: P50 0.7, P95 1.4, Max. 5.7 2015: P50 0.3, P95 0.8, Max. 1.0	(Fromme et al., 2016; 2017)
Munich, blood donor, 2014 and 2016	2014: 42 2016: 158	0.2 ng/ml	2014: 57.1 2016: 98.1	2014: P50 0.2, P95 0.5, Max. 0.6 2016: P50 0.5, P95 1.5, Max 11.6	(Fromme et al., 2016; 2017)
Veneto, Northern Italy, PFC contaminated drinking water, 127 M, 130 F, 20-51 a	257	Not specified	91.1	Median: 2.98 P95: 21.20 Max.: 43.4	(Ingelido et al., 2018)
Veneto, Northern Italy, without PFC-contaminated drinking water, 127 M, 123 F, 20-51 a	250	Not specified	18	Median: 2.49 P95: 6.04 Max.: 9.14	(Ingelido et al., 2018)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 398

Study location, group, group size and study period	Number of samples	Detection limit	Frequency of detection (%)	Concentration (ng/ml)	Study
Uppsala District, Sweden, 413 primiparous F, 1996-2010	413	Not specified	Not specified	Max.: 8.0	(Borg et al., 2013; Glynn et al., 2012)
Ronneby, Sweden, PFC-contaminated drinking water, 3418 persons, 2014-2016	3418	0.5 ng/ml	Not specified	Median 152, Max. 1790	(Li et al., 2018)
Ronneby, subgroup, Sweden, PFC-contaminated drinking water, 50 M + 60 F, 4-83 a	106	0.5 ng/ml	100	Median 277, Max 1660	(Li et al., 2018)
Karlshamm, Sweden, without PFC-contaminated drinking water, 3418 persons, 2014-2016	242	0.5 ng/ml	Not specified	Median 0.84, P90: 2.58, Max. 60.1	(Li et al., 2018)

*: Mothers and all available mother-child pairs; +: middle age; #: P: percentile, a: range of median values in the period 2009-2019; \$: range of median values in the period 1982-2010

Some data on the occurrence of PFHxS in serum of adolescents and children, pregnant women, as well as in umbilical cord blood and breast milk are summarised in table VII.3. According to this table, PFHxS could be detected in practically all serum samples tested. In pregnant women, there is evidence of a reduction in PFHxS exposure in the months after delivery, whereas in infants there is evidence of an increase in PFHxS exposure in the first months of life, which is likely to result from absorption with breast milk.

In a study conducted on one-year-old children in the Berlin area, the influence of breastfeeding duration on the concentration of PFHxS, PFOA, PFOS and other perfluoroalkyl compounds in blood plasma was investigated (Abraham et al., 2020). A high correlation was found between exposure to PFOA, PFOS and PFNA (r in the range of 0.59 to 0.63) and the duration of exclusive breastfeeding, but a significantly lower correlation was observed for PFHxS ($r=0.32$).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 399

Table VII.3: Concentration and detection frequency of PFHxS in serum of children, adolescents and pregnant women as well as in umbilical cord blood and breast milk

Matrix	Study group and size, study period	Frequency of detection (%)	Concentration (ng/ml)	Reference
Plasma	Germany, 1109 children, 3-17 a (GerEs V), 2014-2017	74	P50 0.38 P95 1.26 Max. 34.1 AM 0.542	(Duffek et al., 2020)
Plasma	Greater Berlin area, children < 1 a (10 M, 11 F), 1997-1999, "formula-fed" (not breastfed) (41 M, 39 F), „breastfed“	99	AM ± SD: 1.7 ± 1.1; Range: <0.25-3.8 AM ± SD: 2.1 ± 1.3, Range: 0.3-7.1	(Abraham et al., 2020)
Serum	US NHANES, 12-19 a, n=640, 1999-2000	100	GM 2.7 P95: 12.9	Calafat et al., 2007
Serum	US NHANES, 12-19 a, n=640, 2003-2004	98,3	GM 2.4 P95: 13.1	Calafat et al., 2007
Serum	US NHANES, 12-19 a, n=640, 2005-2006	N.a.	GM 2.09 P95 13.1	CDC, 2013
Serum	US NHANES, 12-19 a, n=640, 2007-2008	N.a.	GM 2.09 P95 14.1	CDC, 2013
Serum	US NHANES, 12-19 a, n=640, 2009-2010	N.a.	GM 2.03 P95 12.3	CDC, 2013
Serum	USA, children, 2-12 a, n=598, 1994-1995	85	GM 4.5 P95 65	(Olsen et al., 2004)
Serum (cord blood)	Munich, n=33, 2007 and 2009	73	Median 0.2 P95 1.5	(Fromme et al., 2010)
Serum	Munich, n=40, age 6 months	98	Median 0,6 P95 1.6	(Fromme et al., 2010)
Serum	Munich, n=40, age 19 months	100	Median 0.6 P95 1.2	(Fromme et al., 2010)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 400

Matrix	Study group and size, study period	Frequency of detection (%)	Concentration (ng/ml)	Reference
Serum	Munich, n=38, pregnant woman giving birth, 21-43 a	97	Median 0.5 P95 3.0	(Fromme et al., 2010)
Serum	Munich, n=47, 6 months after delivery, 21-43 a	96	Median 0.3 P95 0.9	(Fromme et al., 2010)
Breast Milk	Breast milk, Massachusetts, n=45, n. r.	51	Minimum < 0.012 Maximum 63.8	Tao et al., 2008
Breast Milk	Breast milk, China, n=19, n. r.	100	Minimum 0.004 Maximum 0.1	So et al., 2006

#: Percent above LOD, value of LOD mostly not mentioned; n.r.: not reported

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 401

5 Toxicological profile of PFHxS

5.1 Toxicokinetics

5.1.1 Human data

There are no quantitative data on absorption available for humans.

As a result of contamination of drinking water by perfluorine compounds, high levels of PFHxS (as well as PFOA and PFOS) were found in the exposed population (see table VII.2) (Li et al., 2018). After the abrupt end of exposure via this pathway, a subgroup of 106 people was further monitored over a period of just over two years. From the time course of the decrease in serum PFHxS exposure, a half-life of elimination from serum of 5.3 a was calculated on average (95 % confidence interval 4.6-6.0 a). The half-life of elimination for PFHxS was thus significantly longer than for PFOA (2.7 a) and PFOS (3.4 a). In men (age 15 - 50 a), the half-life of elimination for PFHxS was longer (on average 7.4 a) than for women of the same age (4.7 a), but the difference was not statistically significant.

In an earlier study of a group of 83 people from the general population of two cities in China, an elimination half-life of 29 a (median, geometric mean 25 a, arithmetic mean 35 a) was calculated for the group of men and older women (n=64) from data on concentrations in serum and urine (paired samples) using kinetic assumptions. For younger women (n=19), the clearance due to menstruation was also taken into account and thus a half-life of 7.1 a was calculated (median and geometric mean, arithmetic mean 7.7 a). The calculated half-lives for PFOS were 18 and 5.8 a (geometric mean, median 18 and 6.0 a), respectively (Zhang et al., 2013).

A kinetic study was conducted on 26 people (24 M, 2 F, age 55-75 a) with previous occupational exposure to PFC (Olsen et al., 2007). At the beginning of the study, occupational exposure was between 0.4 and 11.5 a back. Serum concentrations of PFHxS, measured several times (as well as PFOA and PFOS) over a period of about 5 a, initially amounted to 290 ng/ml (mean value, range 16-1295 ng/ml). The elimination was described by first order kinetics and resulted in a half-life of 8.5 a for PFHxS (arithmetic mean, 95 % confidence interval 6.4-10.6 a). The geometric mean was 7.3 a (5.8-9.2 a). Also, in this study, the half-life of elimination was longer for PFHxS than for PFOS (arithmetic mean 5.4 a) and PFOA (3.8 a).

Testing of paired serum, plasma and whole blood samples for PFHxS showed approximately equal values for serum and plasma and approximately half the values in whole blood, regardless of the concentration level of PFHxS. These findings suggest that PFHxS is primarily present extracellularly (Bull et al., 2014). In plasma, PFHxS is almost completely (99.4 - 100 %) bound to proteins in the examined range of 1 - 500 mg/l (FSANZ, 2017).

5.1.2 Animal data

In animal experiments with perfluorocarboxylic and -sulfonic acids, a very high oral absorption and a bioavailability of almost 100 % was consistently found. Inhalation also results in rapid and extensive absorption, while dermal absorption is considered negligible (Borg, 2013; DEPA, 2015; Olsen et al., 2009). PFHxS crosses the placental barrier and passes into breast milk (ECHA, 2017).

Absorption, distribution and elimination of perfluoric acids were studied in Sprague-Dawley rats after oral administration of 30 µg PFHxS /kg bw. The mixture used contained one PFHxS isomer with linear chain and two with unspecified chain branching. Resorption rates of 70 and 75 %

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 402

were determined for the branched-chain isomers. The highest concentrations were found in liver, lung and heart. The elimination half-lives from plasma are reported to be 6.9 and 3.6 d for branched chain representatives and 15.9 d for linear chain PFHxS. More detailed information on this study, which was only reported in summary, is not available (Benskin et al., 2009; ECHA, 2017).

For pigs, an elimination half-life of 713 d is reported after oral absorption of a mixture of perfluoric acids with feed; also, in this species this value was higher for PFHxS than for PFOS (634 d) (ECHA, 2017).

In a comparative study, toxicokinetic parameters after single or multiple administration of potassium PFHxS were investigated in rats, mice and cynomolgus monkeys (Sundström et al., 2012). After a single oral administration of 1 or 10 mg/kg bw only 6-7 % were excreted by male rats (4/group) with urine within 96 h, whereas 30 % were excreted at 100 mg/kg bw; in females there were no dose-dependent differences with 35, 28 and 41 %. The daily excretion with the faeces was < 0.5 %. Furthermore, the kinetics in male and female rats (n=3 each) were investigated after oral and intravenous absorption. The half-life of elimination from serum after intravenous administration was 6.83 d (males, only one animal) and 1.83 d (females), in two males this value could not be determined because the model did not allow for proper data adjustment. After oral administration this value could only be determined in two females (0.83 d). Furthermore, the authors themselves describe the values as probably not very reliable because of the short exposure time. Elimination was investigated over a period of 10 weeks after the animals (8 M + 8 F each) had received a single intravenous dose of 10 mg/kg bw. In males, elimination from the serum was described by biphasic kinetics with half-lives of 0.96 d and 29.1 d. In females, elimination was faster and PFHxS concentrations were below the detection limit from day 16 onwards (estimated half-life 1.64 d).

In mice (4 M + 4 F/group each), after oral administration of 1 or 20 mg/kg bw once and observation over 162 d, half-lives of elimination from serum were determined to be 30.5 and 28 d in males and 24.8 and 26.8 d in females, respectively (Sundström et al., 2012).

In this study, cynomolgus monkeys (3 M + 3 F/group each) were given 10 mg/kg bw intravenously once and were examined over a period of 171 d with regard to elimination. The half-life of elimination from serum was 141 d in males and 87 d in females.

In all three animal species investigated, the calculated distribution volume in the steady state was between 200 and 300 ml/kg bw, indicating a predominantly extracellular distribution of PFHxS (Sundström et al., 2012).

The clear difference in the elimination half-life of PFHxS from serum in male and female rats after single oral or intravenous administration was confirmed in a further study. Mean half-lives were reported to be 0.9-1.7 d for male rats and 20.7-26.9 d for female rats (Kim et al., 2016).

The concentrations of PFHxS in serum and liver determined in a study in rats (Butenhoff et al., 2009) after oral administration of the potassium salt of PFHxS are reported in Chapter 5.2.3.2, as are the findings of the corresponding study in mice (Chang et al., 2018).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 403

5.2 Toxicity

5.2.1 Acute toxicity

There are no published data available on acute toxic effects.

5.2.2 Irritation and sensitisation

There are no case reports or investigations available. In general, perfluorosulfonic acids are strong acids, so that an irritating to corrosive effect can be assumed. In general, perfluorosulfonic acids are not regarded as sensitising.

5.2.3 Repeated dose toxicity

5.2.3.1 Data on humans

There are numerous studies on possible correlations between the level of internal exposure to perfluorocarboxylic and -sulfonic acids and the impairment of metabolic processes or of organ development as well as functional disorders. Most of these studies have focused on PFOA and PFOS. In particular, indications of changes in lipid metabolism and impairments of the immune response, possibly also of fertility, were observed that could be linked to the level of PFOA and/or PFOS exposure. An overview of the most important studies is provided by Bull et al. (2014), ATSDR (2021), FSANZ (2017), EFSA (2020) and Hölzer et al. (2015) and, specifically on the question of effects on the immune system, by NTP (2016). In some of the reported individual studies, PFHxS was also detected in serum in addition to PFOA and PFOS and included in the evaluation.

Since PFHxS is always present in co-exposure with the other two (and sometimes other) acids and the concentration of those was usually higher than that of PFHxS, it was hardly possible to discriminate a possible role of PFHxS in the relationships investigated. In the cross-sectional study by Abraham et al. (2020) on one-year-old breastfed or at best briefly or not at all breastfed one-year-old children in Germany, no significant correlation was found between the level of exposure to PFHxS (or PFOS, but for PFOA) in the children's blood plasma and the level of antibody levels after vaccination. There are, however, individual data available indicating that the associations reported were most pronounced with PFHxS. For example, the Canadian Health Measures Survey showed significant associations between plasma concentrations of PFHxS and total cholesterol, LDL, total cholesterol-HDL ratio and non-HDL cholesterol in adults, while no significant evidence was found for such associations with PFOA and PFOS in this cross-sectional study (Fisher et al., 2013).

5.2.3.2 Animal studies

A combined repeated dose toxicity/screening study for developmental and reproductive toxicity (comparable to OECD Guideline 422) was conducted in Sprague-Dawley rats with oral administration of PFHxS (Butenhoff et al., 2009). For this purpose, the animals were administered (15 M + 15 F/dose each) 0, 0.3, 1, 3 or 10 mg potassium PFHxS/(kg bw x d) (with 0.5 % carboxymethylcellulose in water) by gavage; the females were exposed from 14 d prior to mating up to PND 21, the males were exposed for at least 42 d, thereof at least 14 d prior to the start of mating. In addition, the concentration of PFHxS in serum was determined in 3 M per dose on day 42, and in 3 F per dose on day 21. Neither reproductive nor developmental toxicity nor other treatment-related effects on the dams and their offspring were observed up to the highest dose. In the F0 males, the absolute liver weight was significantly and dose-dependently

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 404

increased at 3 and 10 mg/(kg bw x d) (+20 and +56 % respectively), a slight, non-significant increase (approx. 10 %) already occurred at 1 mg/(kg bw x d). The increase in liver weight from 3 mg/(kg bw x d) was associated with hepatocellular hypertrophy, but without an increase in the activity of liver enzymes (AP, ALT, AST) in serum. There was also a slightly increased incidence of hyperplasia and hypertrophy of the thyroid gland at the above doses; T3 and T4 and TSH in serum were not measured. At all doses, total serum cholesterol was significantly lower than in the control, but there was no clear dose dependence. Serum triglyceride levels decreased by 10 - 70 % depending on the dose, but the effect was significant only at the highest dose. The biological relevance of a minimally increased prothrombin time (maximum +6 %) observed at all doses must be considered questionable. The haemoglobin content was only minimally reduced (less than 5 %) in all treatment groups; the same applies to the haematocrit (maximum reduction -7.5 %) and the number of erythrocytes per unit volume (maximum reduction -8 %).

The concentration of PFHxS in the serum of male animals increased with increasing oral dose, but not to the same extent as the administered dose. The serum concentrations measured at 0, 0.3, 1, 3 and 10 mg potassium PFHxS/(kg bw x d) on day 42 were 0.32±0.09, 44.22±12.66, 89.12±0.80, 128.67±10.3 and 201.50±20.02 µgPFHxS/ml (mean±SD in each case). The concentration of PFHxS in the liver was higher than in serum at all doses except the lowest (0.35 ± 0.23, 43.80 ± 8.07, 149.50 ± 26.06, 388.67 ± 128.42 and 593.50 ± 81.41 µg/g) (Butenhoff et al., 2009).

A corresponding study comparable to OECD Guideline 422 as in rats was also conducted in mice (Chang et al., 2018). In this study, CD-1 mice (each 30 M + 30 F/group) received 0, 0.3, 1.0 or 3.0 mg/(kg bw x d) of potassium PFHxS over the periods of time mentioned in the study above (Butenhoff et al., 2009). In addition, unlike in the study with rats, the F1 animals were treated with potassium PFHxS directly after weaning for 14 d.

Table VII.4: Concentration (µg/ml) of PFHxS in serum of mice after oral administration of potassium PFHxS (data from Chang et al., 2018)

Generation and sex	Time point	0,3 mg/(kg bw x d)*	1,0 mg/(kg bw x d)	3,0 mg/(kg bw x d)
F0, M	Exposure day 14	24.7	77.9	172.9
	Exposure day 28	35.8	123.0	188.2
	Exposure day 42	50.1	110.1	187.7
F0, F	Exposure day 14	27.2	89.0	179.5
	GD 18	16.8	51.5	111.3
	LD 22	21.7	65.8	136.6
F1, M+F	GD 18 (pooled)	20.8	62.3	137.7
	PND 4 (pooled)	22.1	59.4	120.9
F1, M	PND 21	12.9	33.4	58.8
F1, F	PND 21	12.1	31.9	69.0
F1, M	PND 36	19.6	64.6	180.4
F1, F	PND 36	18.9	52.0	175.4

*: concentration in the control in all groups each < LOD (0.001 µg/ml). The mean values of 5-10 samples (F0) and 4-27 samples (F1) are given.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 405

The PFHxS content in serum and liver was determined in F0 and F1 animals at the end of the study. In addition, in a further study arm, each of 5 M + 12 F/group received the mentioned doses for 14 d, in a second study arm 7 M + 7 F/dose each of the named doses from 14 d before mating for a total of 28 d (M) or up to GD 18 (F). The concentration of PFHxS in serum and liver was determined at the end of these phases. Pooled samples of fetal blood and liver were also taken at GD 18 (see table VII.4). In both generations, the concentration of PFHxS in serum (and liver) increased in relation to dose and time. Only at the highest dose was the concentration of PFHxS in the liver approximately as high or higher than in serum in F0 males and F1 animals (only before weaning).

With regard to reproductive toxicity effects, the authors found a slightly reduced mean number of offsprings/litters born, which was considered as a questionable effect; the effect was significant from the mean dose onwards (control: 12.3 ± 1.86 , with increasing dose 11.8 ± 2.28 , 10.6 ± 2.39 , 10.8 ± 1.72). However, there was no clear dose-response relationship, and the ratio of the number of kittens born to the number of implants did not show any significant change. No further effects to reproduction or development were observed up to the highest dose. In F0 males and females, the absolute and relative liver weight was increased dose-dependently from the mean dose onwards, reaching +26 and 70 % in males and 13 and 29 % in females, respectively. As in rats, the increased liver weight was associated with centrilobular hypertrophy. In addition, at the highest dose, males showed slight microvesicular fat deposits and single cell necrosis and some females showed vacuoles in the liver cells. In the absence of an increase in serum transaminases, the authors considered the changes described to be compatible with an adaptive response. The only clinical-chemical changes observed in males at the highest dose were a nearly 30 % reduction in cholesterol, a 60 % reduction in total bilirubin and an increase in alkaline phosphatase (AP) to 2.3 times the control value (Chang et al., 2018).

Similar effects on the liver as in the F0 generation were observed in F-1 male and females: increased absolute and relative organ weight and centrilobular hypertrophy, but no necrosis. In the F1 animals, as in the F0 animals, increased gene expression of PPAR α and CAR and factors of the fatty acid metabolism were also observed. No histological changes in the thyroid gland or altered TSH levels were found in either F0 or F1 generation animals (Chang et al., 2018).

In mice (male C57Bl6, 6-8/dose), exposure to the potassium salt of PFHxS (6 mg/kg bw x d) in feed for 4 - 6 weeks resulted in reduced plasma levels of triglycerides (-59 %), non-HDL cholesterol (non-high-density lipoprotein, -68 %), HDL cholesterol (-62 %) and total cholesterol (-67 %). Lipase activity (+74) and clearance of radiolabelled triolein were increased (Bijland et al., 2011).

There are no studies available with prolonged subchronic or chronic exposure.

5.2.4 Genotoxicity

In an in vitro study on the human liver cell line HepG2, PFHxS (2×10^{-7} to 2×10^{-4} M) led to a concentration-dependent increase in the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS). In the comet assay (tested to 2×10^{-5} M) PFHxS led to increased DNA damage (Wielsoe et al., 2015).

No further information on genotoxic effects of PFHxS is available.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 406

5.2.5 Carcinogenicity

There are no data available on carcinogenic effects of PFHxS in humans or experimental animals.

5.2.6 Toxicity to reproduction and development

The results of the toxicity studies after repeated administration/screening study for developmental and reproductive toxicity in rats and mice are presented in chapter 5.2.3.2.

Fertility studies

No other studies than those described in Chapter 5.2.3.2 are available.

Developmental toxicity studies

In a study in pregnant Wistar rats, the animals (20 per group) were administered 0, 0.05, 5 or 25 mg/(kg bw x d) potassium PFHxS (Ramhøj et al., 2018) from GD 4 to PND 22 (or the day of birth, if earlier). Treatment with PFHxS had no effect on maternal weight development, post-implantation or perinatal losses, litter size or sex ratio. The birth weight of the male offspring was slightly reduced at the highest dose (about 3.5 %). No changes in anogenital distance occurred in either male or female offspring. The liver weight of the mother animals showed substance-related changes. In the female off-spring the liver weight was significantly increased from 5 mg/(kg bw x d) at PND 17 and from 25 mg/(kg bw x d) at PND 22, in males the effect was less pronounced. From 5 mg/(kg bw x d) onwards, the thyroxine level in the serum was also significantly reduced in dams and offspring; in the dams this was already detectable from GD 15 onwards. TSH was not measured in this study.

In a study in NMRI mice (14-18 M+F/dose), young animals received a single oral dose of potassium-PFHxS (0, 0.61, 6.1, 9.2 mg/(kg bw x d)) at PND10 (Lee and Viberg, 2013). Behavioural changes at the ages of 2 and 4 months were investigated. At the highest concentration a reduced spontaneous motor activity in the first 20 min and an increased activity in the last 20 min of the test were described. The behaviour of the animals treated with the highest dose of PFHxS was not altered by nicotine, unlike the animals of the lower doses and the control group. The authors of the study discuss that the changes described are associated with changes in the concentration of neuroproteins that are important for the development of certain brain areas (Lee and Viberg, 2013).

5.2.7 Mechanistic studies and in vitro data

In COS cells transfected with mouse or human PPAR α plasmids, mouse PPAR α was activated at 76 μ M and human PPAR α at 81 μ M in a comparable manner. Binary mixtures of PFHxS and PFOS had an additive effect at low concentrations (Wolf et al., 2012; 2008).

In vitro studies on isolated rat and human hepatocytes showed that PFHxS is taken up by liver cells in a sodium-dependent transport process. Further studies on modified cell lines expressing transport proteins for taurocholate or bile acids indicate that NTCP (Na⁺/taurocholate cotransporting polypeptides) of humans and rats can transport PFHxS (as well as PFBS and PFOS). The km values for all three perfluoric acids were lower for human NTCP than for NTCP from rats (hao et al., 2015). Further *in vitro* studies have shown that PFHxS (as well as PFBS and PFOS) can be bound and transported by several human and rat OATPs (organic anion transporting polypeptides) (Zhao et al., 2017).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 407

Effects of PFHxS on the liver and mechanisms of steatosis induction were studied in wild-type SV-129 mice (WT) and in a strain without PPAR α receptor (PPAR α -null) (Das et al., 2017). The animals were administered orally with potassium-PFHxS (10 mg/(kg bw x d)) for 7 d. In both mouse strains, i.e. independently of PPAR α activation, PFHxS led to an increase in liver weight and cell count and a decrease in DNA concentration in liver tissue. With the PPAR α agonist WY-14643, these effects were observed only in WT mice. Further investigations showed that PFHxS leads to steatosis in WT and PPAR α -zero mice. However, the triglyceride level in the liver was only increased in WT by PFHxS. The β -oxidation of palmitoyl carnitine in vitro was not inhibited. Further findings indicate that the expression of genes involved in lipid degradation, but also in fatty acid and triglyceride synthesis, is induced by perfluoric acids in WT mice and, to a lesser extent, in PPAR α zero-mouse. The authors suspect that perfluoric acids such as PFHxS disturb the balance between fatty acid synthesis and accumulation on the one hand and their degradation on the other hand in favour of lipid accumulation (Das et al., 2017). These findings show that PFHxS has effects on the lipid metabolism of the liver that occur independently of PPAR α .

In the estrogen receptor assay with estrogen-sensitive transformed breast cancer cells, the effect of PFHxS (similar to PFOS) was 10^{-6} times weaker than that of 17 β -estradiol. In the androgen receptor assay, PFHxS acted as a concentration-dependent agonist (Kjeldsen and Bonfeld-Jørgensen, 2013). In microsomes from rats and human tests, 250 μ M PFHxS in vitro, in contrast to PFOS, did not inhibit the activity of 3 β -hydroxy steroid dehydrogenase or 17 β -hydroxy steroid dehydrogenase (Zhao et al., 2010).

In a developmental toxicity study of PFHxS, only weak evidence was found for possible interactions between PFHxS and simultaneous exposure to a mixture of 12 substances (total dose 32.11 mg/(kg bw x d)) considered endocrine disrupters (Ramhöj et al., 2018).⁴⁸

⁴⁸ A mixture of the following substances was used (percentage by weight): dibutyl phthalate (3.1), di-2-ethylhexyl phthalate (6.2), vinclozolin (2.8), prochloraz (4.4), procymidone (4.7), linuron (0.2), epoxyconazole (3, 1), 4 methylbenzylidene camphor (18.7), octylmethoxycinnamate (37.4), p,-p'-DDE (0.3), bisphenol A (0.47), butyl paraben (18.9).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 408

6 Existing evaluations and derivations of tolerable doses (toxicity reference values)

For PFHxS there is no harmonised classification according to CLP Regulation 1272/2008/EC (ECHA C&L Inventory, 2018). The substance has so far only been pre-registered under REACH, so there is no proposal for classification from a registration dossier.

Existing guide values for PFHxS to protect the general population are summarised in table VII.5.

In a recommendation of the German Environment Agency after consultation of the Drinking Water Commission (UBA, 2016), a "human equivalent dose" of 2 ng/(kg bw x d) is calculated for PFHxS on the basis of the NOAEL of 1 mg/(kg bw x d) from the 42-d study in rats (Butenhoff et al., 2009). A toxicokinetic factor of 1331 was applied for interspecies extrapolation, corresponding to the different half-lives of elimination in humans (2662 d) and rats (about 2 d). For time extrapolation, a factor of 15 is applied because of the study duration of only 42 d. The high uncertainty, caused by the high extrapolation factor and the uncertainties in the kinetics, is pointed out. With reference to the longer half-life of 30 d from the biphasic elimination kinetics in male rats, a tolerable dose of 30 ng/(kg bw x d) is alternatively derived with otherwise identical factors, which is ultimately used to recommend a drinking water guide value for PFHxS.

In an assessment of the health and environmental risks of PFCs carried out on behalf of the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, Borg and Håkansson (2012) proposed the derivation of a DNEL for internal exposure of 98 ng PFHxS/ml serum. The assessment is based on the findings of the study by Butenhoff et al (2009) in rats, where the lowest dose of 0.3 mg/(kg bw x d) was interpreted as a LOAEL given the minimally prolonged prothrombin time in male rats. The serum PFHxS concentration measured at this dose was 44 µg/ml serum. With the factors listed in table VII.5, this led to a DNEL of 98 ng/ml serum (the kinetic factor for interspecies extrapolation was set at 1, since an internal load was already used as a starting point).

The Minnesota Department of Health (MDH) has submitted a basic document on the health effects of PFHxS, but has not derived a "Health Risk Limit for Groundwater" due to a lack of suitable data (MDH, 2009). FSANZ (Food Standards Australia New Zealand (FSANZ)) also did not see a sufficient data basis for deriving a HBGV (health-based guidance value) (FSANZ, 2017).

In an assessment and derivation of guide values for Basel-county, Switzerland, the quantitative transfer of animal experimental data on PFHxS to humans was considered extremely uncertain and a "read-across" to data on PFOS was preferred (Hassauer et al., 2016).

In its current assessment of the health risks of perfluoroalkyl substances in blood, based on epidemiological and animal experimental data, the CONTAM Panel of EFSA considers the effects on the immune system to be the most critical for the risk assessment of these substances. The evaluation was carried out for the sum of the four compounds PFOA, PFOS, PFNA and PFHxS, which were judged by the CONTAM Panel to be equipotent. An epidemiological study carried out in Germany (Abraham et al., 2020) showed a negative correlation between the sum of the concentration of the four perfluoric acids mentioned and the level of the antibody titre after diphtheria vaccination in children in the first year of life. A BMDL₁₀ of 17.5 ng/ml was determined for this correlation.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 409

Using PBPK modelling, it was estimated that this maternally corresponds to a long-term tolerable oral intake of 0.63 ng/(kg bw x d). As accumulation over time is important, a tolerable weekly intake (TWI) of 4.4 ng/(kg bw x d) was established (EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain et al., 2020).

Table VII.5: Guide values for PFHxS to protect the general population in case of chronic continuous exposure (for explanations see text)

Endpoint, species	Extrapolation factor					Guide value	Reference
	POD	Other	Time	Inter-species	Intra-species		
Liver weight, rat	NOAEL: 1 mg/(kg bw x d)		15	1331 x 2.5	10	(2 ng/kg bw x d)	(UBA, 2016)
Liver weight, rat (M)	NOAEL: 1 mg/(kg bw x d)		15	90 x 2.5	10	(30 ng/kg x d)	(UBA, 2016)*
Haematology rat	LOAEL: 0.3 mg/(kg bw x d) (44 µg/ml serum)	3 (LOAEL to NOAEL)	6	2.5	10	98 ng/ml serum	(Borg and Håkansson, 2012)

*: evaluation of the Drinking Water Commission considering the half-life of the elimination kinetics in male rats

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 410

7 Selected biomarkers and analytical method

Published methods for the determination of PFHxS in serum are available and have been used in numerous studies. For example, Hölzer et al. (2008) describe a method for the detection of C4 - C8 perfluorocarboxylic and -sulfonic acids using HPLC and tandem mass spectrometry with a detection limit (LoD) of 0.1 µg/l for PFHxS for the monitoring studies conducted in North Rhine-Westphalia.

In principle, as with other perfluorocarboxylic and sulfonic acids, the concentration of PFHxS in serum can be used as a measure of the internal body burden. There are several studies available, in which the concentration of PFHxS in serum was determined. Collectives with an increased exposure to PFC-contaminated drinking water as well as groups of the general population without known specific sources of exposure were examined (tables VII.2 and VII.3).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 411

8 Summary and Discussion

There are no studies with subchronic or chronic exposure to PFHxS, nor - with the exception of toxicokinetic studies - studies in primates. In one study each on rats and mice, which were conducted in accordance with OECD Guideline 422, male animals were treated for a maximum of 42 d and females from 14 d before mating up to PND 21 (Butenhoff et al., 2009; Chang et al., 2018).

These studies primarily showed changes in the liver with organ weight increase and hepatocellular hypertrophy without an increase in the activity of liver enzymes in serum. However, in male mice, the highest dose tested (3 mg/(kg bw x d)) led to slight microvesicular fat deposition and single cell necrosis and in some females vacuoles were formed in the liver cells. In both, rats and mice, changes in clinical-chemical parameters of fat metabolism were also recorded, sometimes without clear dose dependence or without statistical confirmation. In rats, slight changes in haematological parameters were also noted.

The adversity of individual changes seems questionable, but altogether the observations provide evidence for a NOAEL of 1 mg/(kg bw x d) in rats and of 0.3 mg/(kg bw x d) in mice. In the recommendation of the German Environment Agency after consultation of the Drinking Water Commission (UBA, 2016), the NOAEL of 1 mg/(kg bw x d) from the study in rats (Butenhoff et al., 2009) is used to derive a tolerable dose for humans, with reference to the very limited data available and the uncertainty of the evaluation. Since then, however, further studies on the toxicity of PFHxS have been published, in particular a study carried out in accordance with OECD Guideline 422, i.e. the above-mentioned study in mice (Chang et al., 2018).

The studies of Butenhoff et al. (2009) and Chang et al. (2018) provide no evidence of reproductive or developmental toxicity effects in rats and mice; also, a further study on rats did not indicate development toxicity of PFHxS (Ramhöj et al., 2018).

PFHxS was included as a component of the mixture of perfluoric acids in some epidemiological studies evaluated by the NTP (2016), but no statement was made on PFHxS in the overall evaluation. There are no animal studies available on immunotoxicity with PFHxS as a single substance.

In the overall assessment, one could consider the dose of 0.3 mg/(kg bw x d) from the study by Chang et al (2018) in mice as basis for deriving a provisional HBM-GV, being aware of the discussed limitations. In male mice, the aforementioned applied dose corresponded to a concentration of 50 µg PFHxS/ml serum determined in the same study. The duration of exposure was 42 d, slightly above the usual duration of subacute studies (28 d), but considerably below the duration of 90 d required for standard subchronic studies. For this reason, a time extrapolation factor of 6 would have to be applied. Furthermore, an interspecies extrapolation factor for toxicodynamics of 2.5, an intraspecies extrapolation factor of 10 and a factor for insufficient data basis (no studies with subchronic to chronic exposure, insufficient data on immunotoxicity) of 3 would have to be applied, which in summary would lead to a value of 0.111 µg PFHxS/ml.

However, in view of the uncertain data situation and the mostly co-occurrence of PFHxS and other perfluorinated substances in the environment and in humans, the derivation of a single value for PFHxS is not considered adequate at this stage.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 412

9 References

Abraham K, Mielke H, Fromme H, et al. (2020) Internal exposure to perfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) and biological markers in 101 healthy 1-year-old children: associations between levels of perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and vaccine response. *Arch Toxicol* 94:2131-2147

Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ATSDR). 2021. Toxicological profile for Perfluoroalkyls. Atlanta, GA: U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Public Health Service. DOI: 10.15620/cdc:59198

Benskin JP, De Silva AO, Martin LJ, et al. (2009) Disposition of perfluorinated acid isomers in sprague-dawley rats; Part 1: Single dose. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 28:542-554. Cited in ECHA Dissemination (2017)

Bijland S, Rensen PC, Pieterman EJ, et al. (2011) Perfluoroalkyl sulfonates cause alkyl chain length-dependent hepatic steatosis and hypolipidemia mainly by impairing lipoprotein production in APOE*3-Leiden CETP mice. *Toxicol Sci* 123:290-303

Borg D (2013) Tissue distribution studies and risk assessment of perfluoroalkylated and polyfluoroalkylated substances (PFASS). In: Karolinska Institute, Stockholm, Sweden. https://openarchive.ki.se/xmlui/bitstream/handle/10616/41507/Thesis_Daniel_Borg.pdf

Borg D, Håkansson H (2012) Environmental and Health Risk Assessment of Perfluoroalkylated and Polyfluoroalkylated Substances (PFASs) in Sweden. Agency TSEP. Online: www.naturvardsverket.se/Documents/publikationer6400/978-91-620-6513-3.pdf

Borg D, Lund B-O, Lindquist N-G, Håkansson H (2013) Cumulative health risk assessment of 17 perfluoroalkylated and polyfluoroalkylated substances (PFASs) in the Swedish population. *Environment International* 59:112-123

Brede E, Wilhelm M, Göen T, et al. (2010) Two-year follow-up biomonitoring pilot study of residents' and controls' PFC plasma levels after PFOA reduction in public water system in Arnsberg, Germany. *Int J Hyg Environ Health* 213:217-223

Bull S, Burnett K, Vassaux K, Ashdown L, Brown T, Rushton L (2014) Extensive literature search and provision of summaries of studies related to the oral toxicity of perfluoroalkylated substances (PFASs), their precursors and potential replacements in experimental animals and humans. Area 1: Data on toxicokinetics (absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion) in in vitro studies, experimental animals and humans. Area 2: Data on toxicity in experimental animals. Area 3: Data on observations in humans. EFSA Supporting Publications 11:572E-n/a

Butenhoff JL, Chang S-C, Ehresman DJ, York RG (2009) Evaluation of potential reproductive and developmental toxicity of potassium perfluorohexanesulfonate in Sprague Dawley rats. *Reproductive Toxicology* 27:331-341

Calafat AM, Kuklennyik Z, Reidy JA, Caudill SP, Tully JS, Needham LL (2007) Serum concentrations of 11 polyfluoroalkyl compounds in the U.S. population: data from the national health and nutrition examination survey (NHANES). *Environ Sci Technol* 41:2237-2242. Cited in ATSDR (2021)

CDC (2013) Fourth national report on human exposure to environmental chemicals. Updated tables, September 2013. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Cited in ATSDR (2021).

Chang S, Butenhoff JL, Parker GA, et al. (2018) Reproductive and developmental toxicity of potassium perfluorohexanesulfonate in CD-1 mice. *Reproductive Toxicology* 78:150-168

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 413

Das KP, Wood CR, Lin MT, et al. (2017) Perfluoroalkyl acids-induced liver steatosis: Effects on genes controlling lipid homeostasis. *Toxicology* 378:37-52

DEPA (2015) Short-chain Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS). A literature review of information on human health effects and environmental fate and effect aspects of short-chain PFAS. Environmental project No. 1707.(DEPA) TDEPA. Copenhagen, Denmark. Online:

Domingo JL, Jogsten IE, Eriksson U, et al. (2012) Human dietary exposure to perfluoroalkyl substances in Catalonia, Spain. Temporal trend. *Food Chemistry* 135:1575-1582

Duffek A, Conrad A, Kolossa-Gehring M, et al. (2020) Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances in blood plasma – Results of the German Environmental Survey for children and adolescents 2014–2017 (GerES V). *International journal of hygiene and environmental health* 228:113549

ECHA (2017) Annex XV report: Proposal for identification of a substance of very high concern on the basis of the criteria set out in REACH Article 57. Substance Name(s): Perfluorohexane-1-sulphonic acid and its salts. Submitted by the Swedish Chemical Agency. Online:

<https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/40a82ea7-dcd2-5e6f-9bff-6504c7a226c5>

ECHA C&L Inventory (2018) Classification and Labelling Inventory: Harmonised Classification - Annex VI of Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008 (CLP Regulation). In: European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), Annankatu 18, P.O. Box 400, FI-00121 Helsinki, Finland. <http://clp-inventory.echa.europa.eu/>

EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain, Schrenk D, Bignami M, et al. (2020) Risk to human health related to the presence of perfluoroalkyl substances in food. *The EFSA Journal* 18:e06223
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6223>

Fisher M, Arbuckle TE, Wade M, Haines DA (2013) Do perfluoroalkyl substances affect metabolic function and plasma lipids?—Analysis of the 2007–2009, Canadian Health Measures Survey (CHMS) Cycle 1. *Environmental Research* 121:95-103

Fromme H, Mosch C, Morovitz M, et al. (2010) Pre- and postnatal exposure to perfluorinated compounds (PFCs). *Environ Sci Technol* 44:7123-7129

Fromme H, Roscher E, Völkel W (2016) Sachstandsbericht ADONA und perfluorierte Substanzen. Bayerisches Landesamt für Gesundheit und Lebensmittelsicherheit (LGL) Sachgebiet Chemikaliensicherheit und Toxikologie M. Online:

https://www.lgl.bayern.de/downloads/gesundheit/arbeitsplatz_umwelt/doc/adona_sachstandsbericht.pdf

Fromme H, Wockner M, Roscher E, Völkel W (2017) ADONA and perfluoroalkylated substances in plasma samples of German blood donors living in South Germany. *Int J Hyg Environ Health* 220:455-460

FSANZ (2017) Hazard assessment report – Perfluorooctane Sulfonate (PFOS), Perfluorooctanoic Acid (PFOA), Perfluorohexane Sulfonate (PFHxS). Food Standards Australia New Zealand (FSANZ). Online: [http://www.health.gov.au/internet/main/publishing.nsf/content/2200FE086D480353CA2580C900817CDC/\\$File/6.sd1-Hazard-assessment-report.pdf](http://www.health.gov.au/internet/main/publishing.nsf/content/2200FE086D480353CA2580C900817CDC/$File/6.sd1-Hazard-assessment-report.pdf)

Glynn A, Berger U, Bignert A, et al. (2012) Perfluorinated Alkyl Acids in Blood Serum from Primiparous Women in Sweden: Serial Sampling during Pregnancy and Nursing, And Temporal Trends 1996–2010. *Environmental Science & Technology* 46:9071-9079

Göckener B, Weber T, Rüdell H, Bücking M, Kolossa-Gehring M (2020) Human Biomonitoring of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances in German blood plasma samples from 1982 to 2019. *Environment International* 145:106123

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 414

Hassauer M, Berkefeld H, Kalberlah F (2016) Herleitung von Konzentrationsleitwerten gemäss ALTLV für 10 perfluorierte Carbonsäuren und Carbonsulfonsäuren. Forschungs- und Beratungsinstitut Gefahrstoffe (FoBiG), Freiburg. Im Auftrag des Amtes für Umweltschutz und Energie, Kanton Basel-Landschaft, Liestal, Schweiz. Online:

HBM-Kommission (2007a) Ableitung von Human-Biomonitoring-(HBM-)Werten auf Basis tolerabler Aufnahmemengen - Teil I: Einführung. Bundesgesundheitsblatt - Gesundheitsforschung - Gesundheitsschutz 50:249-250

HBM-Kommission (2007b) Ableitung von Human-Biomonitoring-(HBM-)Werten auf Basis tolerabler Aufnahmemengen - Teil II: Grundlagen und Ableitungsweg. Stellungnahme der Kommission Human-Biomonitoring des Umweltbundesamts. Bundesgesundheitsblatt - Gesundheitsforschung - Gesundheitsschutz 50:251-254

HBM-Kommission (2014) Grundsatzpapier zur Ableitung von HBM-Werten. Bundesgesundheitsblatt 57:138-147

Hölzer J, Joswig M, Lilienthal H, Schümann M, Wilhelm M (2015) Human-Biomonitoring von perfluorierten Chemikalien (PFCs), Entwicklung toxikologischer Beurteilungswerte für Perfluorooctansäure (PFOA) und Perfluorooctansulfonsäure (PFOS) in Humanblut. Abteilung für Hygiene, Sozial- und Umweltmedizin der Ruhr-Universität Bochum. Umweltbundesamt B. Online:

Hölzer J, Midasch O, Rauchfuss K, et al. (2008) Biomonitoring of perfluorinated compounds in children and adults exposed to perfluorooctanoate-contaminated drinking water. Environ Health Perspect 116:651-657

Ingelido AM, Abballe A, Gemma S, et al. (2018) Biomonitoring of perfluorinated compounds in adults exposed to contaminated drinking water in the Veneto Region, Italy. Environ Int 110:149-159

Kim S-J, Heo S-H, Lee D-S, Hwang IG, Lee Y-B, Cho H-Y (2016) Gender differences in pharmacokinetics and tissue distribution of 3 perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances in rats. Food and Chemical Toxicology 97:243-255

Kjeldsen LS, Bonefeld-Jørgensen EC (2013) Perfluorinated compounds affect the function of sex hormone receptors. Environmental Science and Pollution Research 20:8031-8044. Cited in UBA (2016)

Lee I, Viberg H (2013) A single neonatal exposure to perfluorohexane sulfonate (PFHxS) affects the levels of important neuroproteins in the developing mouse brain. NeuroToxicology 37:190-196

Li Y, Fletcher T, Mucs D, et al. (2018) Half-lives of PFOS, PFHxS and PFOA after end of exposure to contaminated drinking water. Occupational and Environmental Medicine 75:46

MDH (2009) Health Risk Limits for Groundwater: Perfluorohexane sulfonate. Minnesota Department of Health (MDH). Online: <http://www.health.state.mn.us/divs/eh/risk/guidance/gw/pfhxs.pdf>

NEA (2018) Investigation of sources to PFHxS in the environment. Final Report. Bipro and ETH Zurich. Norwegian Environment Agency (NEA), Oslo. Online:

NTP (2016) NTP Monograph: Immunotoxicity Associated with Exposure to Perfluorooctanoic Acid or Perfluorooctane Sulfonate. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services PHS, National Institutes of Health. Online: https://ntp.niehs.nih.gov/ntp/ohat/pfoa_pfos/pfoa_pfosmonograph_508.pdf

Olsen GW, Burris JM, Ehresman DJ, et al. (2007) Half-life of serum elimination of perfluorooctanesulfonate, perfluorohexanesulfonate, and perfluorooctanoate in retired fluorochemical production workers. Environ Health Perspect 115:1298-1305

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 415

Olsen GW, Chang SC, Noker PE, et al. (2009) A comparison of the pharmacokinetics of perfluorobutanesulfonate (PFBS) in rats, monkeys, and humans. *Toxicology* 256:65-74

Olsen GW, Church TR, Hansen KJ, et al. (2004) Quantitative Evaluation of Perfluorooctanesulfonate (PFOS) and Other Fluorochemicals in the Serum of Children. *Journal of Children's Health* 2:53-76

Ramhöj L, Hass U, Boberg J, et al. (2018) Perfluorohexane Sulfonate (PFHxS) and a Mixture of Endocrine Disruptors Reduce Thyroxine Levels and Cause Antiandrogenic Effects in Rats. *Toxicol Sci* 163:579-591

Schröter-Kermani C, Müller J, Jüling H, Conrad A, Schulte C (2013) Retrospective monitoring of perfluorocarboxylates and perfluorosulfonates in human plasma archived by the German Environmental Specimen Bank. *Int J Hyg Environ Health* 216:633-640

So MK, Yamashita N, Taniyasu S, et al. (2006) Health risks in infants associated with exposure to perfluorinated compounds in human breast milk from Zhoushan, China. *Environ Sci Technol* 40:2924-2929

Sundström M, Chang SC, Noker PE, et al. (2012) Comparative pharmacokinetics of perfluorohexanesulfonate (PFHxS) in rats, mice, and monkeys. *Reprod Toxicol* 33:441-451

Tao L, Kannan K, Wong CM, Arcaro KF, Butenhoff JL (2008) Perfluorinated compounds in human milk from Massachusetts, U.S.A. *Environ Sci Technol* 42:3096-3101. Cited in ATSDR (2021)

UBA (2016) Fortschreibung der vorläufigen Bewertung von per- und polyfluorierten Chemikalien (PFC) im Trinkwasser: Begründungen der vorgeschlagenen Werte im Einzelnen. Umweltbundesamt. Online: https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/374/dokumente/bewertung_der_konzentration_en_von_pfc_im_trinkwasser_-_wertebegruendungen.pdf

UBA (2017) Fortschreibung der vorläufigen Bewertung von per- und polyfluorierten Chemikalien (PFC) im Trinkwasser. *Bundesgesundhbl – Gesundheitsforsch – Gesundheitsschutz* 60:350-352

Wielsoe M, Long M, Ghisari M, Bonfeld-Jorgensen EC (2015) Perfluoroalkylated substances (PFAS) affect oxidative stress biomarkers in vitro. *Chemosphere* 129:239-245

Wilhelm M, Hölzer J, Dobler L, et al. (2009) Preliminary observations on perfluorinated compounds in plasma samples (1977-2004) of young German adults from an area with perfluorooctanoate-contaminated drinking water. *Int J Hyg Environ Health* 212:142-145

Wolf CJ, Schmid JE, Lau C, Abbott BD (2012) Activation of mouse and human peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor-alpha (PPARalpha) by perfluoroalkyl acids (PFAAs): further investigation of C4-C12 compounds. *Reprod Toxicol* 33:546-551. Cited in UBA (2016)

Wolf CJ, Takacs ML, Schmid JE, Lau C, Abbott BD (2008) Activation of mouse and human peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha by perfluoroalkyl acids of different functional groups and chain lengths. *Toxicol Sci* 106:162-171. Cited in UBA (2016)

Zhang Y, Beesoon S, Zhu L, Martin JW (2013) Biomonitoring of perfluoroalkyl acids in human urine and estimates of biological half-life. *Environ Sci Technol* 47:10619-10627

Zhao B, Hu GX, Chu Y, et al. (2010) Inhibition of human and rat 3beta-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase and 17beta-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase 3 activities by perfluoroalkylated substances. *Chem Biol Interact* 188:38-43. Cited in UBA (2016)

Zhao W, Zitzow JD, Ehresman DJ, et al. (2015) Na⁺/Taurocholate Cotransporting Polypeptide and Apical Sodium-Dependent Bile Acid Transporter Are Involved in the Disposition of Perfluoroalkyl Sulfonates in Humans and Rats. *Toxicological Sciences* 146:363-373

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 416

Zhao W, Zitzow JD, Weaver Y, et al. (2017) Organic Anion Transporting Polypeptides Contribute to the Disposition of Perfluoroalkyl Acids in Humans and Rats. *Toxicological Sciences* 156:84-95

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 417

Part VIII

Derivation of an HBM Guidance Value (HBM-GV) for Deoxynivalenol (DON): HBM-GVGenPop for the general population

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 418

Table of contents (Part VIII)

Authors and acknowledgements	420
Glossary.....	421
1 Introduction	422
2 General information on DON	424
2.1 Identification of the substance	424
2.2 Physico-chemical properties	425
2.3 Existing EU classification and regulation	425
2.3.1 Harmonised classification and labelling.....	425
2.3.2 EU regulations of DON.....	425
2.4 Sources of human exposure to DON.....	427
3 Toxicological profile of DON	429
3.1 Toxicokinetics	429
3.1.1 Absorption.....	429
3.1.2 Distribution.....	429
3.1.3 Metabolism	429
3.1.4 Excretion.....	430
3.2 Health effects of DON	431
4 Existing toxicity reference values for DON.....	433
5 HBM parameters	435
5.1 Choice of biomarkers	435
5.2 Analytical methods	435
6 Derivation of the HBM-GV for DON	436
6.1 Approach for deriving the HBM-GV	436
6.2 Parameters used for the derivation of the HBM-GV.....	436
6.3 Toxicokinetic aspects related to the derivation of the HBM-GV	437
6.4 Type of urine sample used for the HBM-GV	438
6.5 Derivation of the HBM-GV for the general population.....	439
7 Level of confidence attributed to the HBM-GV.....	440
8 Factsheet	442
9 Annex.....	446
9.1 Annex 1: Literature review related to the reduction of the body weight gain/reduced feed intake as chronic effect of DON in toxicological studies.....	446

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 419

9.2 Annex 2: Determination of the half-lives of DON, DON-glucuronides and total DON	448
10 References.....	449

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 420

Authors and acknowledgements

Lead authors

Annick van den Brand (RIVM), Eva Ougier (Anses), Marcel Mengelers (RIVM), Matthieu Meslin (Anses)

Contributors

Rudolf Hoogenveen (RIVM)

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the following experts for reviewing this report:

Robert Garnier (Expert of the Anses' Biomarker Working group - Paris University Hospitals), Sophie Ndaw (Expert of the Anses' Biomarker Working group - INRS), Marjolijn Woutersen (RIVM), Marco Zeilmaker (RIVM), Benedikt Warth (University of Vienna), Hanns Moshhammer (Medical University of Vienna), Christina Hartmann (EAA), Marthe De Boevre (Ghent University), Sarah De Saeger (Ghent University), Christine Vinkx (Belgian Federal Public Service - Health, Food Chain Safety & Environment), Ricardo Assunção (INSA), Lucija Perharic (NIJZ), Adela López de Cerain Salsamendi (UNAV), Guillermina Font (Universitat de Valencia), Trine Husøy (NIPH)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 421

Glossary

3-Ac-DON	3-acetyl-deoxynivalenol
15-Ac-DON	15-acetyl-deoxynivalenol
ARfD	Acute Reference Dose
BMD	Benchmark dose
BMDL05	Lower confidence limit for a benchmark response of 5% extra risk
BW	Body weight
DOM-1	Deepoxy-deoxynivalenol
DON	Deoxynivalenol
DON-3-GlcA	DON-3-glucuronide
DON-15-GlcA	DON-15-glucuronide
EC	European Commission
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EU	European Union
F _{ue}	Urinary excretion factor
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM-GV	Human Biomonitoring Guidance Value
HBM-GV _{GenPop}	HBM-GV for the general population
HBM4EU	Human Biomonitoring for Europe
IARC	International Agency for Research on Cancer
LB	Lower bound
LoC	Level of Confidence
MAPKs	Mitogen-activated protein kinases
ML	Maximum level
POD	Point of departure
RDF	Reverse dosimetry factor
TDI	Tolerable Daily Intake
TK	Toxicokinetic
T _{max}	Time to reach maximum excreted amount (or concentration)
TRV	Toxicity reference value
UB	Upper bound

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 422

1 Introduction

Within the framework of task 5.2 of the European Joint Programme HBM4EU, Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) are derived for HBM4EU priority substances. The methodology applied to derive these values is described in a concept paper elaborated within the HBM4EU task 5.2 (Apel et al. 2020).

For the time being, HBM-GVs are derived in HBM4EU under inclusion of experts from the 30 partner countries. Future use and implementation will be discussed among partners and the EU Commission but are without prejudice to existing or ongoing risk assessment work in order to inform EU policy-making.

Within the HBM4EU project a scoping document regarding the prioritised mycotoxins has been published and updated⁴⁹. On page seven the following policy question has been raised: “Is it possible to set an HBM guidance value for deoxynivalenol”? There are two main reasons for this request:

1. In 2017, EFSA has established a health-based guidance value for the sum of deoxynivalenol (DON) and its acetylated and modified forms, a so-called group tolerable daily intake (TDI) (EFSA 2017). These acetylated and modified forms of DON are 3-acetyl-DON (3-Ac-DON), 15-acetyl-DON (15-Ac-DON) and DON-3-glucoside. These compounds are not yet taken into account in routine food analysis but they are converted by humans into DON by hydrolysis of the acetyl-group or deglycosylation of the glucoside-group. The added value of the biomonitoring of DON is that it takes these modified forms into account, when the glucuronide metabolites in urine are deconjugated to DON.
2. In HBM4EU an inventory will be made of the epidemiological studies related to the biomonitoring of DON. This is an inventory of already published results and ongoing aligned studies being carried out within the HBM4EU project. In these studies, different urine samples are taken (spot urine, first morning urine and 24 urine) and an HBM-GV for DON in urine could be used in this context to assess a possible risk of the exposure to DON and its acetylated and modified forms.

In addition to this request, it has already been anticipated that the interpretation of the internal exposure to DON, and thereby the derivation of an HBM-GV for DON in urine, represents a challenge due to the daily but variable dietary exposure to DON in relation to the relatively short elimination half-life of DON in humans.

⁴⁹ <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/the-substances/mycotoxins/>

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 423

Disclaimer

In the current report, a general population HBM-GV (HBM-GV_{GenPop}) is derived for deoxynivalenol (DON). Please note that this value is derived based on 24-hour urine collection and total DON concentration. The use of this value for samples other than 24-hour urine samples is not recommended. Yet, the authors note that 24-hour urine collection is associated with practical difficulties. Therefore, the use of a urinary value in relation to first morning urine is discussed.

The toxicological profile of DON presented below relies on a recent literature review performed by EFSA and Workpackage (WP) 13 of HBM4EU. Therefore, this report is less detailed than other Task 5.2 deliverables.

Due to the lack of toxicokinetic data for possible dermal and inhalation routes of exposure, no HBM-GV for occupationally exposed adults could be proposed.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 424

2 General information on DON

2.1 Identification of the substance

Deoxynivalenol (DON) is a naturally-occurring mycotoxin mainly produced by *Fusarium graminearum* and *F. culmorum*. It is also known as vomitoxin due to its strong emetic effects after acute exposure. Chemically, DON is a member of the trichothecenes type B.

Some chemical identification data are reported in Table VIII.1.

Table VIII.1: DON Chemical identification

Name	Deoxynivalenol (DON)
Synonyms	Vomitoxin, Dehydronivalenol, 4-Deoxynivalenol ¹ Trichothec-9-en-8-one, 12, 13-epoxy-3,7,15-trihydroxy-, (3a,7a) ²
IUPAC Names	12,13-epoxy-3 α ,7 α ,15-trihydroxytrichothec-9-en-8on ³ (1 <i>R</i> ,2 <i>R</i> ,3 <i>S</i> ,7 <i>R</i> ,9 <i>R</i> ,10 <i>R</i> ,12 <i>S</i>)-3,10-dihydroxy-2-(hydroxymethyl)-1,5-dimethylspiro[8-oxatricyclo[7.2.1.0 ^{2,7}]dodec-5-ene-12,2'-oxirane]-4-one ¹
CAS Number	51481-10-8 ¹
EC/List no.	610-668-0 ¹
InChI Key	LINOMUASTDIRTM-QGRHZQQGSA-N ¹
SMILES	<chem>CC1=CC2C(C(C1=O)O)(C3(CC(C(C34CO4)O2)O)C)CO1</chem>
Molecular Formula	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₆
Structural formula¹	

1. EFSA (2017)

2. <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Deoxynivalenol>

3. Sobrova et al. (2010)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 425

2.2 Physico-chemical properties

Some physico-chemical properties of DON are shown in table VIII.2. The trichothecenes are thermostable compounds, both during storage/milling and the processing/cooking of food, and are not degraded by high temperatures (Marin et al. 2013). DON is therefore resisting to thermal cooking such as baking, frying and extrusion cooking. But being water-soluble, the DON concentration is reduced during cooking using a larger quantity of boiling water if the cooking liquid is discarded, as for pasta preparation for example (Kushiro 2008)

Table VIII.2: Physico-chemical properties of DON

Physical state	Colourless fine needles ¹
Molar mass	296.32 g/mol
Vapour pressure	4.26×10 ⁻¹⁴ Torr (25°C) ¹ 6.8×10 ⁻¹¹ mm Hg (25°C) ²
Melting point	151–153°C ¹
Boiling point	543.9 ± 50.0°C ¹
Partition coefficient n-octanol/water	log Kow = -0.71 ² ; log D = -0.97 ³
Solubility	In polar organic solvents (e.g. aqueous methanol, ethanol, chloroform, acetonitrile, and ethyl acetate) and water ²

1. Sobrova et al. (2010)

2. <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Deoxynivalenol>

3. Maresca (2013)

2.3 Existing EU classification and regulation

2.3.1 Harmonised classification and labelling

No harmonised CLP classification is available for DON or its modified forms.

Classification and labelling according to CLP criteria were notified by companies to the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) for:

- DON-3-glucoside (CAS N 131180-21-7), as acute Tox. 2 - H300 (fatal if swallowed);
- 3-Ac-DON (CAS N 50722-38-8), as acute Tox. 2 - H300 (fatal if swallowed), acute Tox. 3 - H311 (toxic in contact with skin), acute Tox. 3 - H331 (toxic if inhaled).

2.3.2 EU regulations of DON

The EU Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 established the maximum levels (MLs) for DON in specific food products, as indicated in table VIII.3 (EC 2006a). Foodstuffs shall not be placed on the market where they contain DON exceeding the ML set. The ML should be read together with article 2 of the regulation for compound foodstuffs, and with Regulation (EC) N 401/2006 laying down the methods of sampling and analysis for the official control of the levels of mycotoxins in foodstuffs (EC 2006c).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 426

Table VIII.3: Maximum levels for DON in foodstuffs for human consumption in EU Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006

Category number	Foodstuffs ^{1,2}	Maximum levels (µg/kg)
1	Unprocessed cereals ^{3,4} other than durum wheat, oats and maize	1 250
2	Unprocessed durum wheat and oats ^{3,4}	1 750
3	Unprocessed maize ¹ , with the exception of unprocessed maize intended to be processed by wet milling ⁵	1 750 ⁶
4	Cereals intended for direct human consumption, cereal flour, bran and germ as end product marketed for direct human consumption, with the exception of foodstuffs listed in 7, 8 and 9	750
5	Pasta (dry) ⁷	750
6	Bread (including small bakery wares), pastries, biscuits, cereal snacks and breakfast cereals	500
7	Processed cereal-based foods and baby foods for infants and young children ^{8,9}	200
8	Milling fractions of maize with particle size > 500 micron falling within CN code 1103 13 or 1103 20 40 and other maize milling products with particle size > 500 micron not used for direct human consumption falling within CN code 1904 10 10	750 ⁶
9	Milling fractions of maize with particle size ≤ 500 micron falling within CN code 1102 20 and other maize milling products with particle size ≤ 500 micron not used for direct human consumption falling within CN code 1904 10 10	1 250 ⁶

1. As regards fruits, vegetables and cereals, reference is made to the foodstuffs listed in the relevant category as defined in Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 February 2005 on maximum residue levels of pesticides in or on food and feed of plant and animal origin and amending Council Directive 91/414/EEC as last amended by Regulation (EC) No 178/2006. This means, inter alia, that buckwheat (*Fagopyrum* sp.) is included in 'cereals' and buckwheat products are included in 'cereal products'.
2. Rice is not included in 'cereals' and rice products are not included in 'cereal products'.
3. The ML applies to unprocessed cereals placed on the market for first-stage processing. 'First-stage processing' means any physical or thermal treatment, other than drying, of or on the grain. Cleaning, including scouring, sorting and drying procedures are not considered to be 'first-stage processing' in so far as the whole grain remains intact after cleaning and sorting. Scouring is cleaning cereals by brushing and/or scrubbing it vigorously. In case scouring is applied in the presence of ergot sclerotia, the cereals need to undergo a first cleaning step before scouring. The scouring, performed in combination with a dust aspirator, is followed by a colour sorting before milling. Integrated production and processing systems means systems whereby all incoming lots of cereals are cleaned, sorted and processed in the same establishment. In such integrated production and processing systems, the ML applies to the unprocessed cereals after cleaning and sorting but before first-stage processing. Food business operators shall ensure compliance through their HACCP

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 427

procedure whereby an effective monitoring procedure is established and implemented at this critical control point.

4. The ML applies to cereals harvested and taken over, as from the 2005/06 marketing year, in accordance with Commission Regulation (EC) No 824/2000 of 19 April 2000 establishing procedures for the taking-over of cereals by intervention agencies and laying down methods of analysis for determining the quality of cereals (OJ L 100, 20.4.2000, p. 31), as last amended by Regulation (EC) No 1068/2005 (OJ L 174, 7.7.2005, p. 65).
5. The exemption applies only for maize for which it is evident e.g. through labelling, destination, that it is intended for use in a wet milling process only (starch production).
6. ML shall apply from 1 October 2007.
7. Pasta (dry) means pasta with a water content of approximately 12 %.
8. Foodstuffs listed in this category as defined in Regulation (EU) No 609/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 June 2013 on food intended for infants and young children, food for special medical purposes, and total diet replacement for weight control and repealing Council Directive 92/52/EEC, Commission Directives 96/8/EC, 1999/21/EC, 2006/125/EC and 2006/141/EC, Directive 2009/39/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and Commission Regulations (EC) No 41/2009 and (EC) No 953/2009 (OJ L 181, 29.6.2013, p.35).
9. The ML refers to the dry matter. The dry matter is determined in accordance with Regulation (EC) No 401/2006.

Cereals and cereal by-products constitute a major part of the daily diet of animals and are important ingredients in animal compound feed (Pinotti et al. 2016). Mycotoxin contamination of feed has become a major concern in animal feed science because it can cause acute or chronic mycotoxicosis in animals (Kim et al. 2013). Maximum levels and guidance values for DON in animal feed (feed materials, cereals and cereal products, maize by-products, etc.) have been set in Commission Recommendation 2006/576/EC (EC 2006b).

DON is not addressed at the present time in any other EU directives or regulations.

2.4 Sources of human exposure to DON

DON is the most prevalent *Fusarium* toxin in European grains and its occurrence is frequently reported in cereals (especially oats, barley, wheat, rye, and maize and less frequently in rice, sorghum, and triticale) and cereal-based products such as bread, pasta, or beer (Agriopoulou et al. 2020; Marin et al. 2013). DON can co-occur in grains and in cereal-based food and feed together with its acetyl derivatives, e.g. 3-Ac-DON and 15-Ac-DON that are also produced by *Fusarium* spp. These acetyl derivatives are occurring at much lower levels than DON itself, but they also exert toxicity (EFSA 2017). Biologically modified mycotoxins are also detected in plants infected by mycotoxin-producing fungi, due to their ability to alter the chemical structure of the mycotoxins. DON-3-glucoside (considered as “masked” mycotoxin) is the main plant metabolite of DON (EFSA 2017).

The *Fusarium* spp. fungi grow on the cereals in the field, preferably at temperate climates and favoured by high humidity at the time of flowering (EFSA 2017; Marin et al. 2013). Contamination of plants with DON and its acetyl forms and its modified forms can occur naturally during plant growth. Nonetheless cereal grains intended for food and feed may also become contaminated during transport and (improper) storage. Their presence is also known to be largely dependent

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 428

on environmental factors such as temperature and humidity, and thus is dependent on the climate conditions (Arce-López et al. 2020; Van der Fels-Klerx et al. 2013).

Human exposure to DON is commonly linked to cereal-based diets (Battilani et al. 2020), and the most common route of exposure is thus oral ingestion (Agriopoulou et al. 2020). According to EFSA (2017), the transfer of DON from feed to food of animal origin was identified for dairy cows, pigs and poultry. However, a substantial contribution of the residues of DON in products of animal origin to human exposure was considered to be unlikely. No information on the transfer of 3-Ac-DON, 15-Ac-DON and DON-3-glucoside was identified (EFSA 2017).

Depending on dietary habits it is likely that consumers are exposed to DON on a daily basis and that exposure may occur several times a day. According to the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), the mean acute human exposure to the sum of DON, 3-Ac-DON, 15-Ac-DON and DON-3-glucoside across 39 different dietary surveys in EU countries and all age groups ranged from 0.2 to 2.9 µg/kg body weight (bw) per day (minimum lower bound (LB) - maximum upper bound (UB)). The 95th percentile acute exposure ranged from 0.7 to 6.7 µg/kg bw per day. Infants showed the highest acute dietary exposure. The mean chronic human exposure to the sum of DON, 3-Ac-DON, 15-Ac-DON and DON-3-glucoside across 33 different dietary surveys and all age groups ranged from 0.2 to 2.0 µg/kg bw per day (minimum LB - maximum UB), and the 95th percentile chronic exposure ranged from 0.5 to 3.7 µg/kg bw per day (minimum LB - maximum UB). Again, infants showed the highest mean chronic dietary exposure (EFSA 2017). The CONTAM Panel noted that the overall human dietary exposure to the sum of DON, 3-Ac-DON, 15-Ac-DON and DON-3-glucoside was mainly driven by DON.

There is also a risk of exposure by inhalation of spores of pathogenic species of filamentous fungi and mycotoxins as such, especially during tasks involving close contact with organic dust or mold such as storing, loading, handling, or processing of contaminated materials (grain, waste, and feed). In addition, occupational exposure to DON may occur through handling of animals in animal production settings due to activities related to DON-contaminated litter and feed such as feeding, floor sweeping and removal/change of litter (Viegas et al. 2018a). In two German studies, for example, blood plasma concentrations of mycotoxins were measured in workers involved in grain handling or storage exposed to dust (DON concentrations in air and dust of 2 ng/m³ and 416 ng/g, respectively) (Mayer et al. 2007a; Mayer et al. 2007b), as also in the studies of : Turner et al. (2010a) (pilot study of 76 French farmers in which total DON was analysed in 75 urine samples with levels ranging from 0.5 to 28.8 µg/L); Viegas et al. (2019) (biological sampling of DON-glucuronide in urine for 25 individuals working in the Portuguese Swine Production); Viegas et al. (2018a) (biological sampling of DON-glucuronide in urine for 21 workers of fresh bread dough company) ; or also in a recent French small pilot study aiming to assess mycotoxin contamination in workers during cleaning of a grain elevator (DON concentrations in airborne dust samples between 28.3 and 108 ng/m³) (Ndaw et al. 2021). Dermal absorption may also take place through the deposition of mycotoxins-containing dust particles on the skin, contact with work surfaces contaminated with dust particles (Boonen et al. 2012; Viegas et al. 2018b).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 429

3 Toxicological profile of DON

3.1 Toxicokinetics

3.1.1 Absorption

DON is rapidly absorbed after oral exposure in humans and most animals (Broekaert et al. 2017; EFSA 2017; Fæste et al. 2018; Mengelers et al. 2019). A difference can be observed between the absorption of DON and DON-3-glucoside in humans and pigs (Vidal et al. 2018; Mengelers et al. 2019; Broekaert et al. 2017). Broekaert et al. (2017) administered DON orally to pigs *via* a cross-over design, and took plasma samples as well as samples from the vena porta. They observed a maximum DON plasma concentration within one hour and the relative bioavailability was 81 %, whereas the relative bioavailability of DON-3-glucoside, completely hydrolysed to DON, was 16 %. DON was also administered orally to pigs in a study by Fæste et al. (2018). Plasma samples were taken during 24h after administration; maximum concentrations were observed after 3.5h and the absolute bioavailability was 53 %. Vidal et al. (2018) administered DON orally to 20 human volunteers and followed the excretion of DON in all individual urine discharges collected during 24h after administration. At the end of the experiment about 64 %, based on the molar amounts of DON and two DON-glucuronides, namely DON-3-glucuronide (DON-3-GlcA) and DON-15-glucuronide (DON-15-GlcA), was recovered in urine. The highest excreted amount of DON and its glucuronides was observed after one hour.

After oral administration of DON-3-glucoside to pigs only DON was detected in plasma, indicating a complete presystemic hydrolysis of the absorbed fraction of DON-3-glucoside (Broekaert et al. 2017). However, the absorbed fraction of the glucoside (recovered as DON) was 16 %, approximately 5 times lower than after oral administration of DON. Oral administration of DON-3-glucoside in humans also led to an almost complete hydrolysis of DON-3-glucoside and the amount excreted in urine as DON and the DON-glucuronides was 58 % (Vidal et al., 2018; Mengelers et al., 2019).

3.1.2 Distribution

DON is rapidly distributed in laboratory and farm animals and can be detected in many organs (Fæste et al. 2018; EFSA 2017). The distribution volume based on a 1-compartment model in pigs was 0.7 L/kg (Faeste et al. 2018). Broekaert et al. (2017) applied a 2-compartment model for the kinetics of DON and the central and peripheral distribution volumes were respectively 0.6 and 0.8 L/kg. Fæste et al. (2018) predicted DON kinetics in humans by *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation and allometric scaling of *in vivo* animal data. Based on allometric scaling, the predicted distribution volume in humans was 1.2 l/kg. The aforementioned distribution volumes, in particular those in pigs, suggest that DON is distributed in the whole body fluid and that it is not likely that DON in pigs or humans is stored somewhere in a peripheral compartment or is bound to specific biological material. This corresponds partly with the solubility and polarity of DON, having a partition coefficient of -0.97 at pH 7 (Maresca, 2013).

3.1.3 Metabolism

Metabolism of DON is characterised by phase I and II metabolism. Predominantly in animals, DON is de-epoxidised to the less toxic phase I metabolite DOM-1 (deepoxy-deoxynivalenol). Gut microfloral transformation of DON or modified DON into DOM-1 is less evident in humans than in rats. Subsequent phase II metabolism of DOM-1 is conjugation with sulphate and glucuronic acid (EFSA 2017; Warth et al. 2016).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 430

In several studies, it has been shown that in humans the main metabolic pathway is glucuronidation (EFSA 2017; Sarkanj et al. 2013; Turner et al. 2010b; Warth et al. 2012). One study has been reported where urine samples were obtained from one human volunteer following a diet, naturally contaminated with DON and some of its modified forms, over a period of four days (Warth et al. 2013). These data suggest that approximately 70 % of ingested DON is excreted *via* urine, of which about 80% was in conjugated forms, mainly as DON-15-GlcA that was about threefold more efficiently formed than DON-3-GlcA. In the human intervention study of Vidal et al (2018), it was shown that the ratio of the cumulative amounts (in nmol) of DON-15-GlcA/DON and DON-15-GlcA/DON-3-GlcA after 24h was respectively 2.6 and 4.5. In addition, based on the large comprehensive intervention study, DON-15-GlcA was the most prominent urinary biomarker followed by free DON and DON-3-GlcA. Moreover, correlations among the presence of DON-15-GlcA and DON-3-GlcA were observed (within 24 hours ($r = 0.61$)) (Vidal et al., 2018). Sarkanj et al. (2013) also showed that DON-15-GlcA was the main excreted metabolite, followed by DON-3-GlcA and DON. The excreted concentration of DON-15-GlcA was about eight times higher than that of DON and five times higher than that of DON-3-GlcA (Sarkanj et al. 2013).

3.1.4 Excretion

In humans, the urinary excretion is the predominant route of excretion for DON. Only a low percentage of ingested DON is found in the faeces of mono-gastric animals (humans, pigs, rodents) (Vidal et al. 2018).

A study in three European countries (Italy, Norway, and the United Kingdom) provided data on levels of total DON (free DON plus (unidentified) glucuronides) and DON-1 in human urine samples from different population groups (Brera et al. 2015). Morning urine samples were collected over two consecutive days from 635 volunteers and associated food consumption was recorded on the same days. On average, DON glucuronides accounted for 66 - 82 % of the total DON in urine. The remaining portion was free DON. It was concluded that de-epoxidation did not represent a main metabolic path in the excretion route of ingested DON. EFSA concluded that the exposure estimates, derived from the biomarker data from these three European countries, were of the same order of magnitude as the exposure estimates for the sum of DON, 3-Ac-DON, 15-Ac-DON, and DON-3-glucoside derived from the occurrence data reported to EFSA and the dietary surveys from these countries (EFSA 2017). In addition, morning urine samples were collected in a Belgian population and DON-15-GlcA was the most frequently detected metabolite (in 100 % of the samples, as compared to 82 % for DON-3-GlcA and 50 % for DON) (Heyndrickx et al. 2015).

In the human intervention study of Vidal et al. (2018) an average of approximately 73% of total urinary DON was excreted in its glucuronidated form within 24 hours. In the latter study it was also shown that DON and its glucuronides were rapidly excreted renally. Based on an extensive modelling approach, Mengelers et al. (2019) verified that after oral administration of DON, the time to reach the maximum excreted amount (T_{max}) of DON, DON-3-GlcA, and DON-15-GlcA in urine, based on the estimated parameters, varied between 0.5 and 1 h (Mengelers et al., 2019). From the same study, it was also concluded that 95 % of the cumulative excreted amount of DON was already excreted after 12 hours.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 431

3.2 Health effects of DON

DON was classified by the IARC in Group 3 (not classifiable as to its carcinogenicity to humans) as no experimental or epidemiological evidence for mutagenic and/or carcinogenic properties were available (IARC 1993).

The EFSA CONTAM Panel recently performed a comprehensive literature review on the toxicity of DON (and its modified forms) to support the hazard identification and characterisation in animals and humans in order to identify an acute and a chronic critical effect of DON for human risk assessment.

Regarding the acute effect of DON, the CONTAM Panel noted that after a single DON exposure feed refusal appeared very quickly (within 2 h after exposure) in mice. Decreased feed intake was identified as relevant endpoint for acute effects of DON in mice. It has to be noted that mice (and rats) are incapable of vomiting and hence are not useful for specifically studying emetic effects of DON. Vomiting was identified as the critical acute effect in pigs. As for humans, acute outbreaks due to ingestion of DON contaminated food has occurred repeatedly in China and India, with symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, diarrhoea, abdominal pain, headaches, dizziness, fever, and in severe cases, bloody stool. Since studies from experimental and farm animals could not provide a basis for an acute reference dose (ARfD), EFSA decided to use the human data on vomiting and gastrointestinal effects, collected in a number of epidemiological studies on the outbreaks of acute mycotoxicosis in Asia, for the human hazard characterisation. See also Chapter 4 with respect to the derivation of a group ARfD.

EFSA's conclusions regarding the chronic effects of DON are the following:

- no new data on DON carcinogenicity was identified since the 2-year study in mice from Iverson et al. (1995), which did not indicate any carcinogenic properties of DON;
- *in vitro* data are indicating genotoxic properties of DON, the available *in vivo* data were however inconclusive. The available evidence suggests that oxidative stress may be involved in the mechanism of genotoxicity, rather than a direct interaction of DON (DNA-adduct formation) with cellular DNA;
- DON has an impact on the immune response. Subchronic studies performed in mice and in farm animals indicate that the ingestion of this toxin induces an increase in the plasmatic level of IgA. The DON-induced elevated IgA level was not associated with IgA nephropathy in humans and rodents. In studies with high doses, DON induced inflammation in mice. An increase in TNF- α and IL-1- β was observed at doses as low as 2.5 μg DON/kg bw per day administered in C57BL/6 mice, but with absence of an observed adverse effect;
- DON exhibits both developmental and reproductive toxicity in experimental animals including reduced fertility, embryotoxicity, skeletal abnormalities, effects on body weight and relative epididymal weight and postnatal mortality. Based on studies with rats treated orally with DON, the CONTAM Panel concluded that the NOAEL was 1.0 mg/kg bw per day for reproductive endpoints, 1.0 mg/kg bw per day for fetal toxicity and 0.5 mg/kg bw per day for maternal toxicity. The CONTAM Panel concluded that the increase in postnatal mortality in pups from mice treated orally with DON, with a NOAEL of 0.38 mg/kg bw per day, was the most critical effect for developmental or reproductive toxicity of DON;

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 432

- the limited data reporting neurotoxicological effects of DON did not allow any identification of a dose–response relationship (nor any link with the mode of action of DON);
- available data showed only minor (subacute) haemato- or myelotoxicity of DON;
- The CONTAM panel identified reduced body weight gain in experimental animals as the critical chronic effect for human risk assessment. A clear dose–response relationship between the exposure to DON and mean body weight was observed both for female and male mice. See also Chapter 4 with respect to the derivation of a group TDI.

According to EFSA (2017), the mode of action of DON is exerted through its binding to the ribosomes leading to: i) inhibition of protein synthesis and subsequently also RNA and DNA synthesis and ii) induction of ribotoxic stress and activation of different mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs), which is explaining several effects of DON, such as apoptosis or survival of cells, inflammatory effect and oxidative stress. Pro-inflammatory cytokines and secretion of satiety hormones, are two known mediators of DON-induced anorexia/emesis.

The mechanism of action of 3-Ac-DON and 15-Ac-DON also suggests an activation of MAPK and an induction of inflammatory cytokine and satiety hormones. In three different models (differentiated intestinal epithelial cell line, intestinal explant and the intestine of exposed animals), 15-Ac-DON activated the MAPKs, ERK1/2, p38, and JNK, at lower dose than DON and 3-Ac-DON, indicating a higher intrinsic toxicity of 15-Ac-DON in comparison to DON. 15-Ac-DON induces greater histological intestinal lesions and had a higher impact on barrier intestinal function. On the opposite, DON-3-glucoside cannot bind to the ribosome, and thus neither activates MAPKs nor induces inflammation (EFSA 2017).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 433

4 Existing toxicity reference values for DON

The most recently identified toxicological or toxicity reference values (TRVs) for effects of DON are the group ARfD of 8 µg/kg bw per eating occasion and the group TDI of 1 µg/kg bw per day set for the sum of DON, 3-Ac-DON, 15-Ac-DON and DON-3-glucoside by the EFSA CONTAM Panel in 2017 (EFSA 2017).

Based on the available toxicokinetic and toxicity information, the CONTAM Panel noted that the 3-Ac-DON and 15-Ac-DON were largely deacetylated to DON prior to systemic distribution, and that the mode of action and the toxicity data indicated a similar toxicity as that of DON, indicating that they might induce the same acute and chronic effects as DON (although 15-Ac-DON showed a higher intrinsic toxicity than DON). The available data suggested also that DON-3-glucoside could be cleaved to DON by bacteria in the gastrointestinal tract and distributed, metabolised and excreted similarly to DON. However, a firm conclusion on the hazard of DON-3-glucoside toxicity in comparison to that of DON data and the two acetylated forms could not be formulated, given the limited available data and the lack of *in vivo* data on chronic toxicity. Therefore, the CONTAM Panel applied a conservative approach assuming that: i) 3-Ac-DON, 15-Ac-DON and DON-3-glucoside are all metabolised to DON and absorbed at the same extent as DON, ii) the acetylated forms of DON induce the same acute and chronic adverse health effects as DON and iii) similar acute and chronic adverse health effects of DON-3-glucoside as DON cannot be excluded. Therefore, the CONTAM Panel decided to characterise the hazard for the group of DON, 3-Ac-DON, 15-Ac-DON and DON-3-glucoside together, both for chronic and for acute adverse health effects in humans.

Acute DON toxicosis has been associated with symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, diarrhoea, abdominal pain, headaches, dizziness, fever, and in severe cases, bloody stool in humans. From a large number of outbreaks of mycotoxicoses, the CONTAM Panel identified the study of (Luo et al. 1987) (cited in EFSA's 2017 Scientific Opinion), in which primarily gastrointestinal disorders including vomiting in humans were recorded and could be associated with the measured DON concentrations in samples of contaminated grains (external exposure) consumed by the affected subjects. In this study, none of the 73 persons in the town of Qingzu (one of the three towns studied) became ill after being exposed to DON concentrations ranging between 1 and 8 mg/kg wheat. The CONTAM Panel considered this study as the most suitable to derive a NOAEL for vomiting in humans exposed to DON and identified the highest concentration of 8 mg/kg wheat from this population as a NOAEL. This value was calculated further to a NOAEL of 26 µg DON/kg bw for a single eating occasion. A default uncertainty factor of 3.16 for toxicokinetic differences in the human population was applied, resulting in a group ARfD of 8 µg/kg bw per eating occasion.

In the absence of data on chronic effects in humans, the CONTAM Panel identified reduced body weight gain in experimental animals as the most relevant and suitable critical chronic effect for human risk assessment (EFSA 2017). The selected key study (Iverson et al. 1995) is a long-term study (over 2 years) on mice, from which a clear dose–response relationship between the exposure to DON and mean body weight was observed in both female and male mice. In this study, male and female B6C3F1 mice in groups of 50 (2 mice per cage, males and females separated) were given diets containing DON mixed with 4 % corn oil at a concentration of 0, 1, 5 and 10 mg/kg diet, equal to 0, 0.115, 0.661 and 1.520 mg/kg bw per day in females and 0, 0.098, 0.506 and 1.126 mg/kg bw per day in males for 2 years.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 434

Although this study had been designed to assess DON for possible carcinogenicity (and being negative for this endpoint), the data reported on general toxicity of the animals, in particular on feed intake and body weight, were suitable for a dose–response analysis using the benchmark dose (BMD) approach to assess the critical effect of reduced body weight gain and reduced intake. The CONTAM Panel combined the data from both sexes to calculate a lower 95% confidence limit for a benchmark response of 5 % extra risk (BMDL05) of 0.11 mg/kg bw per day for reduced body weight gain, and established a group-TDI for the sum of DON, 3-Ac-DON, 15-Ac-DON and DON-3-glucoside using the default uncertainty factor of 100 for inter- and intraspecies variability. Since the BMDL values calculated for developmental and reproductive toxicity were all larger than the BMDL05 of 0.11 mg DON/kg bw per day, the CONTAM Panel concluded that the group TDI was also protective for developmental and reproductive toxicity (EFSA 2017).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 435

5 HBM parameters

5.1 Choice of biomarkers

Several studies in humans have shown that the major metabolic pathway in humans is glucuronidation (see 3.1.3). DON itself, DON-3-GlcA and the predominant DON-15-GlcA are the main biomarkers of DON in human urine. However, commercial sources for the reference standards of DON-glucuronides are non-existent and no (certified) reference materials are available for these glucuronides. Nevertheless, the glucuronidated DON metabolites in urine samples can be deglucuronidated by enzymatic treatment to DON (HBM4EU 2020a; Vidal et al. 2020). Furthermore, as will be described in section 6.2, the rate of renal excretion of DON is proportional to those of the glucuronides. Therefore, as an (practical) alternative to the quantitative measurement of DON-glucuronides in urine, urinary total DON can be used as a biomarker of exposure for DON after deglucuronidation (HBM4EU 2020a). However, Vidal et al. (2020) stated that not all DON glucuronides were quantitatively transformed to free DON during enzymatic treatment, causing an underestimation of total DON. The glucuronidation however also depends on the enzymatic activity of the β -glucuronidase that was used and related laboratory protocols that were applied (HBM4EU 2020b). Alternatively, the standards for the glucuronidated DON metabolites can be synthesised synthetically, or by a biological approach (Fruhmann et al. 2012; Wu et al. 2007), although deglucuronidation to assess total DON in urine is generally considered more feasible and practical.

5.2 Analytical methods

Due to the lack of commercial reference standards and the low levels of biomarkers present in biological matrices, the analyses of DON-glucuronides remain a challenge. Publications often report methods that imply the use of procedures using an enzymatic treatment for deglucuronidation, along with a procedure without enzymatic treatment. By subtracting the free DON contribution from the total DON, the contribution of DON-glucuronides is obtained (Battilani et al. 2020; Turner et al. 2010b).

Within WP9, an interlaboratory study has started in 2020 that is based on the determination of total DON after enzymatic deconjugation. For the deconjugation, β -glucuronidase from *Escherichia coli* was considered the best choice to be used for deconjugation at 37°C for at least 15 h at pH 6.8-7.4 (HBM4EU 2020b).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 436

6 Derivation of the HBM-GV for DON

6.1 Approach for deriving the HBM-GV

As detailed in Apel et al. (2020), three options for deriving an HBM-GV are available: the first option consists in deriving the HBM-GV based on a relationship observed in humans between a selected critical effect (i.e. the most sensitive health effect) and the selected biomarker(s). The second possible approach consists in estimating the biomarker(s) concentration that corresponds to a selected external TRV proposed by European or international bodies. The third option consists to derive the HBM-GV based on a critical effect and a critical dose reported in animal toxicological studies.

A literature review aiming to identify health effects of DON for the development of an Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) was performed at the end of 2019 within HBM4EU WP13. Scientific articles were retrieved using Embase, Scopus and Pubmed, for the period 2016 - October 2019. The review of the articles did not allow to identify any new human studies on DON (with the exception of a cross-sectional study by De Santis et al. (2019) (linking DON to clinical manifestations in children with autism) or any new toxicological studies that would support the selection of another critical chronic effect than the reduction of body weight gain to perform a human risk assessment (nor the selection of an alternative critical dose (see Annex 1) for this specific adverse effect).

Since no human data are available to derive an HBM-GV_{Genpop} for DON, it was decided to consider the group-TDI set by EFSA in 2017 as starting point for the derivation of an HBM-GV_{Genpop} (i.e. the second option described in Apel et al. 2020).

6.2 Parameters used for the derivation of the HBM-GV

According to Apel and coworkers, three parameters are used for the derivation of the HBM-GV in option two: the TRV, the urinary excretion factor (F_{ue}) and the daily urinary flow rate (Apel et al. 2020). In case the selected biomarker of exposure is a metabolite, the molecular weights of the parent compound and the metabolite are used. However, in case of DON, two other kinetic parameters need to be taken into consideration (elimination half-life and dosing interval) and these will be discussed in section 6.3.

In various epidemiological studies (EFSA 2017), it was concluded that the main metabolite in human urine is DON-15-GlcA. This statement was validated in a comprehensive human intervention study of Vidal et al. (2018), where modelling and kinetic parameters were investigated by Mengelers et al. (2019). However, this biomarker is not commercially available and this shortcoming limits the practical use of this metabolite as a biomarker of exposure for DON. As indicated by Mengelers et al. (2019) the determination of total DON after deglucuronidation of a urine sample can serve as a good alternative for determination of the DON-exposure. In WP9 of the HBM4EU project, it has been decided to perform an interlaboratory study in 2020 on the determination of total DON after deglucuronidation of the urine sample (HBM4EUa, b). This means that derivation of the HBM-GV can be based on the urinary fraction of total DON. Mengelers et al. (2019) have calculated the urinary fraction of total DON in two ways. First, a total recovery of 64 % in humans was calculated based on the molar amounts of DON and its metabolites recovered in urine during 24 hours. A second approach was to determine the so-called 'reverse dosimetry factor' (RDF). The RDF is the ratio of the intake of DON to the calculated cumulative excreted amount and is the inverse of F_{ue}. Because the distribution of the ratios is skewed, a logistic transformation was applied to calculate the

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 437

confidence bounds. The F_{ue} for total DON is 0.69 with a confidence interval of [0.14-0.97]. The small discrepancy with the fraction recovered (0.64) is related to the logistic transformation of the RDFs for calculating the mean value of the RDF.

Apel and coworkers (2020) already mentioned that the daily urinary flow rate they used for children and adults (respectively, 30 and 20 ml/kg bw/day) should be updated because the daily fluid intake and urine production in men and women have increased over the past decade. Therefore, the raw data of the study of Vidal et al. (2018) were used. In this study, the daily urinary flow rates of women were slightly higher than those of men, but the difference between the sexes was not significant and the observed urinary flow rate of both sexes was 29.4 ± 8.5 ml/kg bw/day.

6.3 Toxicokinetic aspects related to the derivation of the HBM-GV

As mentioned in section 3.1.4, the urinary excretion of a single dose of DON in humans is almost complete within 12h (95 % of the cumulative excretion). This renal excretion can be expressed by means of an elimination rate or an elimination half-life. However, an elimination half-life of DON in humans has not been described yet. Fæste et al. (2018) predicted DON kinetics in humans by *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation and allometric scaling of *in vivo* animal data. By using the predicted plasma clearance (based upon *in vitro* data) and distribution volume (based upon allometric scaling), Fæste et al. (2018) estimated an elimination half-life of DON in humans of 2.9 to 3.6h. The data of Vidal et al. (2018) & Mengelers et al. (2019) can also be used to derive an elimination half-life in urine from the cumulative excretion function. This urinary half-life is defined as the time duration until half of the DON-intake (fraction DON absorbed) is transported into the excretion compartment (i.e. urine). The latter amount consists of unchanged or total DON excreted during 24 hours. In mathematical-statistical terms, the half-life is the time value at which the cumulative excretion probability has a value of 0.5 (50 % of the total amount of unchanged or total DON excreted). Since no closed formula describing the cumulative excretion function exists, the half-life was calculated numerically (for details see Annex 2, chapter 9). Using the data of Mengelers et al. (2019) the calculated elimination half-lives of DON, its main metabolite DON-15-GlcA, and total DON are respectively, 2.55h, 2.95h and 2.95h. The half-life of total DON is driven by the larger contribution of the half-life of DON-15-GlcA, since this is the major validated biomarker of DON in urine.

The exposure of the general population to DON occurs through the consumption of contaminated food. The main contributors to the dietary exposure to (modified) DON are grains and grain-based products. This covers a large range of food products and in practice this means that an average consumer (depending on the type of diet) can be exposed at breakfast, lunch and evening meal. However, even in case of three exposure moments per day the elimination half-lives of all biomarkers are shorter than the dosing interval. In practice, this means that a steady-state will not be reached even after continuous (daily) exposure. Therefore, the prerequisite of the compound being in a steady-state, made by Apel and coworkers (2020) for calculating an HBM-GV, is not met. Yet, the time it takes to reach 95 % of the cumulative amount excreted (P₉₅) is 12 hours (Mengelers et al. 2019). Therefore, if the last exposure of the day occurs during the evening meal, inclusion of the next morning urine in a 24h urine sample will ensure that almost all of a daily DON exposure will be captured in a 24h urine sample. The down side is that excreted amounts of DON (or total DON) in different spot urine samples (samples taken at random during the day) will vary too much to be of practical use (see also section 0).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 438

6.4 Type of urine sample used for the HBM-GV

Due to the fact that a single dose of DON in humans is almost completely excreted within 12h of the last exposure to DON, it has been decided to relate the HBM-GV for DON in urine to a 24h urine sample (see section 0). As substantiated in section 6.3, a large variation is anticipated in the excreted amount of DON in a spot urine sample. This variation will only increase whenever the daily variation in the volume of a spot urine sample is added to the variation in the excreted amount and DON would be expressed as a concentration (regardless of a correction for diuresis).

To the present day, not many epidemiological studies have used 24h urine samples (De Ruyck et al. 2020). However, some studies have used morning urine samples and the practical use of this timed sample has been explored. The major practical problem with DON is its short half-life in combination with the possibility of exposure at different time points during the day preceding the morning urine sample. The only scenario that can be used in case of a morning urine sample, is a constrained scenario with a few conditions. First, the morning urine sample needs to be collected before the first DON exposure of that day, i.e. before breakfast, a so-called first morning urine sample. Secondly, the last DON exposure during the preceding day needs to occur at the evening meal. Thirdly, no urine must be voided during the period between the last evening meal and breakfast (approximately 12h). Taking these three conditions into account, then almost all of the DON intake during that evening meal will be excreted in the morning urine. Therefore, if the last DON intake would have been at the level of the TDI, i.e. 1 µg/kg bw per day, and taking the F_{ue} of 0.69 for total DON into account, the excreted amount in the morning urine would have been 0.69 µg/kg bw. The 24h urinary flow rate observed by Mengelers et al. (2019) was 29.4 ± 8.5 ml/kg bw. Consequently, assuming a constant flow rate during a 12h period, this would lead to an average urinary volume of 14.7 ml/kg bw and an average concentration of total DON of 46.9 µg/l (= 1000*0.69/14.7). Obviously, the averages of the F_{ue} and the urinary volume have been used and knowing the confidence intervals, the extremes (the P95 of the F_{ue} and the P05 of the urinary volume) could also have been taken into account. Yet, it is highly unlikely that no urine is voided between the evening meal and the first morning void (third condition). Therefore, we think it is safe to assume that a concentration above 47 µg/l (rounded value) in a first morning urine sample indicates that the TDI has been exceeded in the previous day. However, importantly, one cannot conclude that a total DON concentration in a first morning urine sample below 47 µg/l would indicate that the TDI was not exceeded the previous day. In other words, it is a constraint. The practical use of the value of 47 µg/l for a first morning urine sample is being investigated at the moment by analysing the raw data supplied by Martins et al. (2019). In this study, concentrations of DON and the two DON-glucuronides in first morning urine and in 24h urine are compared on a population level. On the one hand, it remains questionable as to how indicative a morning urine sample would be considering that many people would likely have at least one urine discharge between the last DON intake of the day and the following morning urine sample. On the other hand, EFSA stated in (the summary of) its opinion that the exposure estimates, derived from first morning urine samples collected in three European countries, were of the same order of magnitude as the exposure estimates derived from the occurrence data reported to EFSA and the dietary surveys from those countries (intra-class correlation coefficients however not available) (Brera et al. 2015).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 439

6.5 Derivation of the HBM-GV for the general population

The HBM-GV_{GenPop} for DON is derived by calculating the concentration of the selected biomarker of exposure (i.e. urinary total DON) in a 24h urine sample:

$$\text{HBM-GV}_{\text{GenPop}} = \frac{\text{group TDI} \cdot \text{Fue}}{24\text{h urinary flow rate adjusted to the bodyweight}} = \frac{1 \mu\text{g/kg bw/d} \cdot 0.69}{29.4 \text{ ml/kg bw/d}} = 0.023 \mu\text{g/ml}$$

with:

a group-TDI for DON of 1 µg/kg bw/day

a urinary excretion factor (Fue) of 0.69, as calculated by Mengelers et al. (2019)

an average 24h urinary flow rate of 29.4 ml/kg bw/day, as observed by Mengelers et al. (2019)

Using the confidence interval around the Fue, we calculated a confidence interval around the HBM-GV for total DON: [0.005 - 0.033 µg/ml]. As explained in section 6.3, the short elimination half-life of total DON (< 3h) implies that the HBM-GV of DON (23 µg/l) cannot be used for a spot urine sample because the variation in the total DON concentration in such a sample will be much larger than the confidence interval calculated for a 24h urine sample. The practical consequences of the use of this HBM-GV have been addressed in section 0.

It is likely that the main biomarker of exposure, DON-15-GlcA, will become commercially available as a reference standard in the near future. Because the confidence intervals related to the Fue of DON and DON-15-GlcA are comparable, it is possible to derive an HBM-GV for this biomarker of exposure. Therefore, this value has also been calculated and presented in the factsheet (cf. section 0).

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 440

7 Level of confidence attributed to the HBM-GV

The Level of Confidence (LoC) of an HBM-GV is attributed to aspects like: nature and quality of epidemiological/toxicological data (including toxicokinetic data); the critical effect and the mode of action; the selection of the key study; the selection of the POD and the extrapolations across and within species (Apel et al. 2020).

Considering the nature and quality of epidemiological/toxicological data

DON has been assigned the trivial name ‘vomitoxin’ because of its ability to induce acute vomiting in animals after high dosing. DON has also been involved in a number of incidents of human intoxication events and its acute effects in humans are similar to those in animals. An ARfD of 8 µg/kg bw based on human data on vomiting and gastrointestinal effects was set by EFSA (EFSA 2017). Human data on chronic exposure to DON are however lacking. Regarding the toxicokinetic data in humans, up to date there is only one quantitative study on DON urinary excretion after oral exposure under conditions in one human sub-population group (Vidal et al. 2018; Mengelers et al., 2019). This study nevertheless included 20 adult volunteers, with an equal proportion of women and men. ⇒ a **medium** LoC is attributed to this aspect.

Considering the critical effect and the mode of action

The derivation of this HBM-GV is based on a defined external TRV, i.e. a group-TDI, established by EFSA in 2017 (EFSA 2017). The critical effect used for the derivation of a BMDL was reduced body weight gain in mice, the most common effect of long-term dietary exposure in animals besides anorexia. Feed refusal and reduced feed intake have been associated with hormonal and immunotoxic effects of DON since changes of satiety hormones and changes of proinflammatory cytokines have been observed to be related to DON-induced anorexia. However, the database was too weak for EFSA to identify any critical endpoints based on immunotoxic or hormonal effects in experimental animals for chronic exposure to DON. EFSA also relates that DON is genotoxic *in vitro* but that the *in vivo* data available on the DON genotoxicity were inconclusive. ⇒ a **medium** LoC is attributed to this aspect.

Considering the key study

The key study selected by EFSA for deriving the group-TDI is the 2-year feeding study in mice by Iverson et al. (1995). This study was designed to examine DON for possible carcinogenicity, but the data on general toxicity of the animals were also reported. The design was very similar to the OECD Guidelines 452 - Chronic Toxicity Studies (2009). It is considered as a good quality experimental study. ⇒ a **high** LoC is attributed to this aspect.

Considering the POD

The POD is a BMDL05 of 0.11 mg/kg bw per day for reduced body weight gain based on the body weight data of Iverson et al. (1995) for female and male mice combined, as calculated by EFSA. The BMD approach for continuous data was applied using the default BMR of 5% in the absence of statistical or toxicological considerations supporting a deviation. ⇒ a **high** LoC is attributed to this aspect.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 441

Considering the extrapolations across and within species

In the absence of specific data, default uncertainty factors of 10 were applied to take into account the inter- and intraspecies differences. ⇒ a **low** LoC is attributed to this aspect.

Overall, with respect to the single aspects mentioned by Apel et al. (2020), the LoC of the proposed HBM-GV_{GenPop} for DON is **medium**.

Hays et al. (2008) has mentioned one other important aspect with respect to the assessment of the LoC in derived HBM-GVs, namely the relevance of the biomarker to the critical dose metric (Hays et al. 2008). As mentioned in sections 3.1 and 5.1, glucuronidation is the major pathway in humans and the use of total DON is most likely a reliable exposure biomarker for DON in humans. EFSA noted that DON urinary biomarkers have been frequently investigated in several European populations and that these biomarkers correlate well with dietary DON exposure.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 442

8 Factsheet

DEOXYNIVALENOL		Target population: General population	
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
HBM-GV	1	23 µg DON/l urine (CI: 5-33 µg/l) 20 µg DON-15-GlcA/l urine (CI: 7-39 µg/l)	Based on a 24-urine sample
HBM-GV year of issue	2	2021	
General Information			
CLP-INDEX-Nr.	3	-	
EC-Nr.	4	610-668-0	
CAS-Nr.	5	51481-10-8	
Harmonised CLP classification	6	-	Only notified C&L for: - DON-3-glucoside (acute Tox. 2, H300: fatal if swallowed) - 3-Ac-DON (acute Tox. 2, H300: fatal if swallowed; acute Tox. 3, H311: toxic in contact with skin; acute Tox. 3, H331: toxic if inhaled)
Molar mass	7	296.31 g/mol	
Biomarker(s)			
Identification	8	Biomarker(s) of exposure	
Molar mass of biomarker(s)	9	DON: 296.31 g/mol DON-15-GlcA: 472.4 g/mol	
Half-life of selected biomarker(s) *	10	DON: 2.55 h (CI : 2.2 – 2.8 h) DON-15-GlcA: 2.95 h DON-total: 2.95 h	Vidal et al. (2018) Mengelers et al. (2019)
Factor for metabolic conversion (F _{ue}) **	11	DON: 0.14 (0.03-0.42); RDF: 7.20 (CI 2.37-29.1) DON-15-GlcA: 0.37 (0.13-0.71); RDF: 2.67 (CI 1.4-7.96) Total DON: 0.69 (0.14-0.97); RDF: 1.45 (CI 1.03-7.10)	Mengelers et al. (2019) RDF: Reversed Dosimetry Factor
Derivation method, starting point and assessment factors (uncertainty factors)			
Type of derivation method selected ***	12	Option 2 as described in Apel et al. 2020: HBM-GV derivation based on a defined external toxicity reference value.	Estimation by means of TK extrapolation.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 443

DEOXYNIVALENOL		Target population: General population	
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
		<i>Note: total urinary volume per 24 h used differs from German HBM Commission</i>	
Key study, Author(s), Year	13	Iverson et al., 1995 . Chronic feeding study of deoxynivalenol in b6c3f1 male and female mice	
Species	14	Animal: mice	
Exposure route of study	15	Oral	
Study length	16	Chronic	
Exposure dose and conditions	17	0, 0.115, 0.661 and 1.520 mg/kg bw per day in females and 0, 0.098, 0.506 and 1.126 mg/kg bw per day in males for 2 years	Dose calculated by the CONTAM Panel by using the values reported in the study (EFSA 2017).
Critical endpoint	18	Reduced body weight gain	
Point of departure (POD) value	19	BMDL05: 0.11 mg DON/kg bw/d	
Extrapolations of the starting point	20	External TRV (group-TDI for DON, 3-Ac-DON, 15-Ac-DON and DON-3-glucoside of 1 µg/kg bw/day) to HBM-GV (linked to urinary total DON by means of TK modelling).	
TK/PBTK model for animal-human data extrapolation or intra-species extrapolation	21	TK model by Mengelers et al. (2019)	
Assessment Factors	22	100 (from animal POD to external TRV taking into account inter- and intraspecies variability into account)	
Rounded value of HBM-GV	23	Total DON: 0.69 ug DON/kg bw/total 24h ≈ 23 µg DON/l urine (CI: 5-33 µg/l) # DON-15-GlcA: 0.60 ug DON-15-GlcA/kg bw/total 24h ≈ 20 µg DON-15-GlcA/l urine (CI: 7-39 µg/l) #	# Based on a 24-urine sample
Additional Comments	24	Derivation of HBM-GV is not based on a steady-state situation due to an elimination half-life that is shorter than the dosing interval	

Explanation of notes

- HBM guidance value (HBM-GV):** numerical value of the HBM-GV in µg/l
- HBM-GV year of issue:** year when the HBM guidance value has been issued within HBM4EU.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 444

3. **CLP Number:** according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures. Implementing the globally harmonized system of chemical classification or GHS.
4. **EC Number** (unique seven-digit identifier assigned to substances for [regulatory](#) purposes within the [European Union](#) by the European Commission): no number for DON.
5. **CAS Number:** collection of disclosed chemical compound information by Chemical Abstracts Service. Almost all molecule databases can be searched by CAS Registry Number.
6. **Harmonised CLP classification:** CLP classification including CMR and other health relevant effects. In the case that classification is not harmonized, this should be stated. For self-classifications by industry the ECHA- CLP inventory can be searched at: <http://echa.europa.eu/web/quest/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database>
7. **Molar mass:** symbol M , is a physical property characteristic of a given substance (chemical element or chemical compound), namely it's mass per amount of substance [g/mol].
8. **Identification of the selected biomarker(s):** type of biomarker(s) (exposure or effect biomarker(s)).
9. **Molar mass of biomarker(s)**
10. **Half-life of selected biomarker(s):** excretion half-life of the biomarker(s) in the selected biological matrix, in hours or years (indication of the underlying TK study providing the data)

* The half-life value of DON was calculated based on the compartmental model and the calculated model parameter values (described in Mengelers et al., 2019). Within the context of this compartmental model, the half-life is defined as the time duration until half of the DON-intake (fraction DON absorbed) is transported into the excretion compartment (i.e. urine). The latter amount consists of unchanged DON excreted during 24 hours. In mathematical-statistical terms, the half-life is the time value at which the cumulative excretion function has value 0.5 (50 % of the total amount of unchanged DON excreted). Since the cumulative excretion function has no closed formula, it was calculated numerically.

The half-lives of the two major metabolites of DON, DON-3-GlcA and DON-15-GlcA, have also been defined as the time value at which the cumulative excretion function of each metabolite has value 0.5 (50 % of the total amount of DON-glucuronide excreted). Since the cumulative excretion functions of these metabolites have also no closed formula, their half-lives have also been calculated numerically.

In case of total DON, the cumulative excretion function was defined as the sum of the three (DON, DON-3-GlcA and DON-15-GlcA) cumulative excretion functions.
11. **Factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}):** in case of urinary biomarker(s), fraction of the biomarker(s) excreted compared to the total dose of the parent compound absorbed (indication of the underlying TK study providing the data)

** F_{ue} is the inverse of the Reversed Dosimetry Factor (RDF) as described in Mengelers et al. (2019). The RDF is a factor that was derived based on the total excretion of DON, DON-3-GlcA, DON-15-GlcA and total DON in urine after a single dose of 1 μ g DON/kg bw. This factor can be used to estimate the DON intake based on the urinary excretion of DON or its metabolites.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 445

12. **Derivation method selected:** either option 1 (internal dose-effect relationship from human study/studies) or option 2 (existing TRV) or option 3 (animal POD), as described in Apel et al. (2020).
*** The equation of option 2 has been used because it is applicable to this specific situation where 95 % of total DON is excreted within 12 hours and not because steady-state has been reached.
13. **Key study, Authors, Year:** name, authors and year of publication of selected key study/studies (for option 2: key study underlying the selected TRV derivation)
14. **Species:** animal/human
15. **Exposure route of study:** route of exposure (oral, dermal or inhalation study)
16. **Study length:** duration of the human or animal study
17. **Exposure dose and conditions:** dose, exposure pattern (frequency and duration of administration, constant feeding pattern, etc.)
18. **Critical endpoint:** selected critical adverse effect observed in the key study and used for derivation of the HBM-GV ("either the adverse effect that first appears in the dose response curve, or as a known precursor to the first adverse effect")
19. **Point of departure (POD):** Lowest concentration or dose at which the critical effect occurred or did not occur. POD will be mainly NOAEC*L, or LOAEC*L, BMD*L
20. **Extrapolations of the starting point:** calculation to transpose the selected starting point (POD or TRV) into corresponding human internal biomarker(s) concentration level
21. **21) TK/ PBTK model:** description of peer-reviewed TK/PBTK model in case it is used for the HBM-GV derivation
22. **Assessment Factors:** numerical adjustment values used to extrapolate the selected POD to the target population. They are physiological scaling factors that account for differences between species and variability within populations. They also account for differences in study protocols, exposure conditions and other uncertainties
23. **Rounded value of the calculated HBM-GV:** numerical value of the HBM-GV and eventually recommendation for the moment of sampling (especially for the occupational field)
24. **Additional comments:**
The half-lives of all biomarkers are shorter than 3 hours. In practice this means that the half-lives ($T_{1/2}$) are shorter than the dosing interval (τ) and consequently steady-state is not reached ($AUC_{\tau} \neq AUC_{\infty}$). Nevertheless, the equation of option 2 can be used because it is applicable to this specific situation where 95 % of total DON is excreted within 12 hours and total DON will be excreted almost completely between the last dosing (= evening meal) and the last urine void (= morning urine).
The production of urine per 24h has been taken from the study of Vidal et al. (2018). The mean urinary flow rate for adults (\pm s.d.) is 29.44 ± 8.51 ml/kg bw/day.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 446

9 Annex

9.1 Annex 1: Literature review related to the reduction of the body weight gain/reduced feed intake as chronic effect of DON in toxicological studies

A literature review from 2017 until February 2021 was performed on Pubmed with the following search string:

(trichothecenes[Title/Abstract] OR DON[Title/Abstract] OR deoxynivalenol[Title/Abstract] OR vomitoxin[Title/Abstract]) AND (toxic*[Title/Abstract] OR health effect[Title/Abstract] OR intoxic*[Title/Abstract]).

The results specifically linked to the critical chronic effect of DON (i.e. reduction of the body weight gain) in mice, that is underlying the derivation of the TDI set by EFSA (2017) are presented in Table 1. These results do not support any change in the key study (Iverson et al. 1995) and thus nor the POD (BMDL05 of 0.11 mg/kg bw per day) considered for the TDI derivation.

Table VIII.4: Reduction in body weight / body weight gain

Animal model	Route of exposure	Dose and duration of exposure	Effect	Reference
Chicken	Oral / contaminated diet	DON-contaminated feed at 0, 2, 5, and 10 mg/kg for 16 weeks	Male chickens of 2 and 5 mg/kg groups were significantly different ($p = 0.004$). In addition, BWG of male chickens in the 2 mg/kg group tended to be lower than that in the 10 mg/kg group ($p = 0.090$). For female chickens, no significant differences of control and DON-groups were found throughout the experiment.	Chen et al. (2017)
Rat	Oral / gavage	F0: DON-contaminated feed at 0, 0.03, 0.1, 0.3, 1, or 3 mg DON/kg bw/d from GD 6 to PND 27 F1: DON-contaminated feed during lactation + same dose as their respective dam from PND 12 to PND 27	No treatment-related changes in maternal BW or feed consumption at any of the doses administered (up to 3 mg/kg/d) during gestation or lactation. - LOAEL at 3 mg/kg bw/day: *F0 females had smaller live litter sizes than controls (not statistically significant) *F1 pups had lower BW (4–13%) compared to controls (starting on PND 15 and until PND 28, BW was significantly lower in the 3 mg/kg/day dose group compared to controls; 10% lower in males and 13% lower in females). - NOAEL at 1 mg/kg bw/day	Huang et al. (2021)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 447

Animal model	Route of exposure	Dose and duration of exposure	Effect	Reference
Pig	Oral / contaminated diet	Feed contaminated with a mixture of DON (2.6 mg/kg), 3A–DON (0.1 mg/kg) and 15A– DON (0.3 mg/kg) from d0 to d14. DON-contaminated feed at 1 mg/kg from d15 to d37	No significant differences between control groups (CON and CON + BIN) and DON-challenged groups (DON and DON + BIN) regarding growth performances	Jin et al. (2017)
Piglets		DON-contaminated feed at 1 mg/kg and 3 mg/kg for 28 days	DON at 1.0 and/or 3.0 mg/kg reduced ($P < 0.05$) the BW gain (16.0–60.8%) and feed intake (18.1–38.7 %) during the whole experiment, while the feed/gain ratio increased ($P < 0.05$) by 12.8–33.8 % during d1–28. Compared to 1.0 mg/kg DON, the BW gain and feed intake were further reduced ($P < 0.05$) in 3.0 mg/kg DON during d15–28.	Liu et al. (2020)
Broiler (male)	Oral / contaminated diet	DON-contaminated diet with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 5 mg DON/kg of feed ; - 15 mg DON/kg of feed from d0 to d42 	DON presence at 5 mg/kg did not affect the productive parameters compared with the control group ($p > 0.05$). A tendency of decrease in a linear way ($p = 0.08$) was observed in broilers fed 15 mg/kg feed on body weight gain (BWG) which was 6 % lower than broilers fed the control diet. DON at 5 mg/kg to 15 mg/kg significant increase of absolute and relative weight of thymus and the relative weight of gizzard and decrease in absolute and relative weight of the colon.	Riahi et al. (2020)
Mice aged 7 weeks (male C57BL/6)	Oral / water	10 µg DON/kg bw/d during 9 months	No mortality or any gross behavioral change, no weight loss, but DON-exposed mice gained slightly less weight than control mice (p value not indicated)	Vignal et al. (2018)
Piglet	Oral / contaminated diet	DON-contaminated diet with 1.3 and 2.2 mg/kg for 60 days	No information on BW/BWG Significant morphological changes in Intestinal Porcine Epithelial Cells, in mRNA Expression of Inflammatory Cytokines in Intestinal Tissues, etc.	Wang et al. (2019)

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 448

9.2 Annex 2: Determination of the half-lives of DON, DON-glucuronides and total DON

The model of the deoxynivalenol (DON) kinetics is defined by the following differential equations, together with the initial conditions.

$$P_{GItract}'(t) = -KaD * P_{GItract}(t)$$

$$P_{liver}'(t) = KaD * P_{GItract}(t) - KeD * P_{liver}(t) - KmD_{3GlcA}P_{liver}(t) - KmD_{15GlcA}P_{liver}(t)$$

$$P_{kidney_3GlcA}'(t) = KmD_{3GlcA}P_{liver}(t) - KeD_{3GlcA}P_{kidney_3GlcA}(t)$$

$$P_{kidney_15GlcA}'(t) = KmD_{15GlcA}P_{liver}(t) - KeD_{15GlcA}P_{kidney_15GlcA}(t)$$

$$P_{excr}'(t) = KeD * P_{liver}(t)$$

$$P_{excr_3GlcA}'(t) = KeD_{3GlcA}P_{kidney_3GlcA}(t)$$

$$P_{excr_15GlcA}'(t) = KeD_{15GlcA}P_{kidney_15GlcA}(t)$$

with: $t =$ time

$P =$ probability distribution function defined for each compartment

Initial condition: $P_{GItract}(0) = 1$, $P(0) = 0$ for other organs.

The half-life for excretion of DON is defined as: T such that $P_{excr}(T) = \frac{1}{2}P_{excr}(\infty)$. The half-life for excretion of DON-3-GlcA is defined as: T such that $P_{excr_3GlcA}(T) = \frac{1}{2} P_{excr_3GlcA}(\infty)$, likewise for DON-15-GlcA. The half-life for excretion of all substances combined is defined as: T such that:

$$P_{excr}(T) + P_{excr_3GlcA}(T) + P_{excr_15GlcA}(T) = \frac{1}{2} (P_{excr}(\infty) + P_{excr_3GlcA}(\infty) + P_{excr_15GlcA}(\infty)) = \frac{1}{2}.$$

The resulting half-lives for respectively DON, DON-15-GlcA and total DON are: 2.55 h, 2.95 h and 2.95 h.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 449

10 References

- Agriopoulou S, Stamatelopoulou E, Varzakas T. 2020. Advances in occurrence, importance, and mycotoxin control strategies: Prevention and detoxification in foods. *Foods (Basel, Switzerland)* 9.
- Apel P, Rousselle C, Lange R, Sissoko F, Kolossa-Gehring M, Ougier E. 2020. Human biomonitoring initiative (HBM4EU) - strategy to derive human biomonitoring guidance values (hbm-gvs) for health risk assessment. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health* 230:113622.
- Arce-López B, Lizarraga E, Vettorazzi A, González-Peñas E. 2020. Human biomonitoring of mycotoxins in blood, plasma and serum in recent years: A review. *Toxins* 12.
- Battilani P, Palumbo R, Giorni P, Dall'Asta C, Dellaflora L, Gkrillas A, Toscano P, Crisci A, Brera C, De Santis B, Rosanna Cammarano R, Della Seta M, Campbell K, Elliot C, Venancio A, Lima N, Gonçalves A, Terciolo C, Oswald IP. 2020. Mycotoxin mixtures in food and feed: Holistic, innovative, flexible risk assessment modelling approach. *EFSA Supporting Publications* 17:1757E.
- Boonen J, Malysheva SV, Taevernier L, Diana Di Mavungu J, De Saeger S, De Spiegeleer B. 2012. Human skin penetration of selected model mycotoxins. *Toxicology* 301:21-32.
- Brera C, de Santis B, Debegnach F, Miano B, Moretti G, Lanzone A, Del Sordo G, Buonsenso D, Chiaretti A, Hardie L, White K, Lise Brantsæter A, Knutsen H, Sundstøl Eriksen G, Sandvik M, Wells L, Allenf S, Sathyapalanf T. 2015. Experimental study of deoxynivalenol biomarkers in urine. *EFSA Supporting Publications* 12:818E.
- Broekaert N, Devreese M, van Bergen T, Schauvliege S, De Boevre M, De Saeger S, Vanhaecke L, Berthiller F, Michlmayr H, Malachová A, Adam G, Vermeulen A, Croubels S. 2017. In vivo contribution of deoxynivalenol-3-β-d-glucoside to deoxynivalenol exposure in broiler chickens and pigs: Oral bioavailability, hydrolysis and toxicokinetics. *Arch Toxicol* 91:699-712.
- Chen SS, Li Y-H, Lin M-F. 2017. Chronic exposure to the fusarium mycotoxin deoxynivalenol: Impact on performance, immune organ, and intestinal integrity of slow-growing chickens. *Toxins* 9:334.
- De Ruyck K, Huybrechts I, Yang S, Arcella D, Claeys L, Abbeddou S, De Keyzer W, De Vries J, Ocke M, Ruprich J, De Boevre M, De Saeger S. 2020. Mycotoxin exposure assessments in a multi-center european validation study by 24-hour dietary recall and biological fluid sampling. *Environment International* 137:105539.
- De Santis B, Debegnach F, Miano B, Moretti G, Sonogo E, Chiaretti A, Buonsenso D, Brera C. 2019. Determination of deoxynivalenol biomarkers in italian urine samples. *Toxins* 11:441.
- EC. 2006a. European commission regulation (ec) 1881/2006, setting maximum levels for certain contaminants in foodstuffs. *Fed Reg L364*.
- EC. 2006b. European commission recommendation 2006/576/ec on the presence of deoxynivalenol, zearalenone, ochratoxin a, t-2 and ht-2 and fumonisins in products intended for animal feeding.
- EC. 2006c. European commission regulation (ec) no 401/2006 of 23 february 2006 laying down the methods of sampling and analysis for the official control of the levels of mycotoxins in foodstuffs.
- EFSA. 2017. Risks to human and animal health related to the presence of deoxynivalenol and its acetylated and modified forms in food and feed. *EFSA Journal* 15:e04718.
- Fæste CK, Ivanova L, Sayyari A, Hansen U, Sivertsen T, Uhlig S. 2018. Prediction of deoxynivalenol toxicokinetics in humans by in vitro-to-in vivo extrapolation and allometric scaling of in vivo animal data. *Arch Toxicol* 92:2195-2216.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 450

- Fruhmann P, Warth B, Hametner C, Berthiller F, Horkel E, Adam G, Sulyok M, Krska R, J. F. 2012. Synthesis of deoxynivalenol 3-beta-d-o-glucuronide for its use as biomarker for dietary deoxynivalenol exposure. *World Mycotoxin Journal* 5 127-132.
- Hays SM, Aylward LL, LaKind JS, Bartels MJ, Barton HA, Boogaard PJ, Brunk C, DiZio S, Dourson M, Goldstein DA, Lipscomb J, Kilpatrick ME, Krewski D, Krishnan K, Nordberg M, Okino M, Tan Y-M, Viau C, Yager JW. 2008. Guidelines for the derivation of biomonitoring equivalents: Report from the biomonitoring equivalents expert workshop. *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology* 51:S4-S15.
- HBM4EU. 2020a. Deliverable 9.5 - Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 2nd prioritisation round of substances. <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>
- HBM4EU. 2020b. ICI report mycotoxin (DON) in urine round 3. ONLINE LIBRARY: HBM4EU - science and policy for a healthy future
- Heyndrickx E, Sioen I, Huybrechts B, Callebaut A, De Henauw S, De Saeger S. 2015. Human biomonitoring of multiple mycotoxins in the belgian population: Results of the biomyco study. *Environ Int* 84:82-89.
- Huang MC, Furr JR, Robinson VG, Betz L, Shockley K, Cunny H, Witt K, Waidyanatha S, Germolec D. 2021. Oral deoxynivalenol toxicity in harlan sprague dawley (hsd:Sprague dawley® sd®) rat dams and their offspring. *Food and chemical toxicology : an international journal published for the British Industrial Biological Research Association* 148:111963.
- IARC. 1993. Monographs on the evaluation of carcinogenic risks to humans, some naturally occurring substances, food items and constituents, heterocyclic aromatic amines and mycotoxins. Lyon:International Agency for Research on Cancer.
- Iverson F, Armstrong C, Nera E, Truelove J, Fernie S, Scott P, Stapley R, Hayward S, Gunner S. 1995. Chronic feeding study of deoxynivalenol in b6c3f1 male and female mice. *Teratogenesis, carcinogenesis, and mutagenesis* 15:283-306.
- Jin L, Wang W, Degroote J, Van Noten N, Yan H, Majdeddin M, Van Poucke M, Peelman L, Goderis A, Van De Mierop K, Mombaerts R, De Smet S, Michiels J. 2017. Mycotoxin binder improves growth rate in piglets associated with reduction of toll-like receptor-4 and increase of tight junction protein gene expression in gut mucosa. *Journal of Animal Science and Biotechnology* 8:80.
- Kim D-H, Lee I-H, Do W-H, Nam W-S, Li H, Jang H-S, Lee C. 2013. Incidence and levels of deoxynivalenol, fumonisins and zearalenone contaminants in animal feeds used in korea in 2012. *Toxins* 6:20-32.
- Kushiro M. 2008. Effects of milling and cooking processes on the deoxynivalenol content in wheat. *Int J Mol Sci* 9:2127-2145.
- Liu M, Zhang L, Chu XH, Ma R, Wang YW, Liu Q, Zhang NY, Karrow NA, Sun LH. 2020. Effects of deoxynivalenol on the porcine growth performance and intestinal microbiota and potential remediation by a modified hscas binder. *Food and chemical toxicology : an international journal published for the British Industrial Biological Research Association* 141:111373.
- Luo X, Li Y, Wen S, Hu X. 1987. Food poisoning caused by scabby wheat and the detection of fusarium mycotoxins. *Journal of Hygiene Research* 16:33-37.
- Maresca M. 2013. From the gut to the brain: Journey and pathophysiological effects of the food-associated trichothecene mycotoxin deoxynivalenol. *Toxins* 5:784-820.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 451

Marin S, Ramos AJ, Cano-Sancho G, Sanchis V. 2013. Mycotoxins: Occurrence, toxicology, and exposure assessment. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 60:218-237.

Mayer S, Curtui V, Usleber E, Gareis M. 2007a. Airborne mycotoxins in dust from grain elevators. *Mycotoxin research* 23:94-100.

Mayer S, Degen G, Blaszkewicz M, Curtui V, Usleber E. 2007b. Exposure to airborne mycotoxins at grain/corn storage facilities and mycotoxin concentrations in the blood of grain storage workers. *Gefahrstoffe Reinhaltung der Luft* 67:119-125.

Mengelers M, Zeilmaker M, Vidal A, De Boevre M, De Saeger S, Hoogenveen R. 2019. Biomonitoring of deoxynivalenol and deoxynivalenol-3-glucoside in human volunteers: Renal excretion profiles. *Toxins* 11:466.

Ndaw S, Jargot D, Antoine G, Denis F, Melin S, Robert A. 2021. Investigating multi-mycotoxin exposure in occupational settings: A biomonitoring and airborne measurement approach. *Toxins* 13.

Pinotti L, Ottoboni M, Giromini C, Dell'Orto V, Cheli F. 2016. Mycotoxin contamination in the eu feed supply chain: A focus on cereal byproducts. *Toxins* 8:45-45.

Riahi I, Marquis V, Ramos AJ, Brufau J, Esteve-Garcia E, Pérez-Vendrell AM. 2020. Effects of deoxynivalenol-contaminated diets on productive, morphological, and physiological indicators in broiler chickens. *Animals* 10.

Sarkanj B, Warth B, Uhlig S, Abia WA, Sulyok M, Klapac T, Krska R, Banjari I. 2013. Urinary analysis reveals high deoxynivalenol exposure in pregnant women from croatia. *Food and chemical toxicology : an international journal published for the British Industrial Biological Research Association* 62:231-237.

Sobrova P, Adam V, Vasatkova A, Beklova M, Zeman L, Kizek R. 2010. Deoxynivalenol and its toxicity. *Interdiscip Toxicol* 3:94-99.

Turner P, Hopton R, Lecluse Y, White K, Fisher J, Lebailly P. 2010a. Determinants of urinary deoxynivalenol and de-epoxy deoxynivalenol in male farmers from normandy, france. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* 58:5206-5212.

Turner P, White K, Burley V, Hopton R, Rajendram A, Fisher J, Cade J, Wild C. 2010b. A comparison of deoxynivalenol intake and urinary deoxynivalenol in uk adults. *Biomarkers : biochemical indicators of exposure, response, and susceptibility to chemicals* 15:553-562.

Van der Fels-Klerx HJ, van Asselt ED, Madsen MS, Olesen JE. 2013. Impact of climate change effects on contamination of cereal grains with deoxynivalenol. *PLOS ONE* 8:e73602.

Vidal A, Claeys L, Mengelers M, Vanhoorne V, Vervaet C, Huybrechts B, De Saeger S, De Boevre M. 2018. Humans significantly metabolize and excrete the mycotoxin deoxynivalenol and its modified form deoxynivalenol-3-glucoside within 24 hours. *Scientific reports* 8:5255.

Vidal A, Bouzaghane N, De Saeger S, De Boevre M. 2020. Human mycotoxin biomonitoring: Conclusive remarks on direct or indirect assessment of urinary deoxynivalenol. *Toxins* 12:139.

Viegas S, Assunção R, Nunes C, Osteresch B, Twarużek M, Kosicki R, Grajewski J, Martins C, Alvito P, Almeida A, Viegas C. 2018a. Exposure assessment to mycotoxins in a portuguese fresh bread dough company by using a multi-biomarker approach. *Toxins* 10.

Viegas S, Viegas C, Oppliger A. 2018b. Occupational exposure to mycotoxins: Current knowledge and prospects. *Annals of work exposures and health* 62:923-941.

D5.9 - 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 2.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Claire Beausoleil, Farida Lamkarkach, Matthieu Meslin, Jens Uwe Voss, Marcel Mengelers	Page: 452

Viegas S, Assunção R, Martins C, Nunes C, Osteresch B, Twarużek M, Kosicki R, Grajewski J, Ribeiro E, Viegas C. 2019. Occupational exposure to mycotoxins in swine production: Environmental and biological monitoring approaches. *Toxins* 11:78.

Vignal C, Djouina M, Pichavant M, Caboche S, Waxin C, Beury D, Hot D, Gower-Rousseau C, Body-Malapel M. 2018. Chronic ingestion of deoxynivalenol at human dietary levels impairs intestinal homeostasis and gut microbiota in mice. *Archives of Toxicology* 92.

Wang X-C, Zhang Y-F, Cao L, Zhu L, Huang Y-Y, Chen X-F, Chu X-Y, Zhu D-F, Ur Rahman S, Feng S-B, Li Y, Wu J-J. 2019. Deoxynivalenol induces intestinal damage and inflammatory response through the nuclear factor-kb signaling pathway in piglets. *Toxins* 11:663.

Warth B, Sulyok M, Fruhmann P, Berthiller F, Schuhmacher R, Hametner C, Adam G, Fröhlich J, Krska R. 2012. Assessment of human deoxynivalenol exposure using an lc-ms/ms based biomarker method. *Toxicology letters* 211:85-90.

Warth B, Sulyok M, Berthiller F, Schuhmacher R, Krska R. 2013. New insights into the human metabolism of the fusarium mycotoxins deoxynivalenol and zearalenone. *Toxicology letters* 220:88-94.

Warth B, Del Favero G, Wiesenberger G, Puntischer H, Woelflingseder L, Fruhmann P, Sarkanj B, Krska R, Schuhmacher R, Adam G, Marko D. 2016. Identification of a novel human deoxynivalenol metabolite enhancing proliferation of intestinal and urinary bladder cells. *Scientific reports* 6:33854.

Wu X, Murphy P, Cunnick J, Hendrich S. 2007. Synthesis and characterization of deoxynivalenol glucuronide: Its comparative immunotoxicity with deoxynivalenol. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 45:1846-1855.L